

Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 30000

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Abstract

This paper brings natural numbers from 20001 to 30000 written in **ascending** and **descending** orders of 1 to 9. Most of the numbers are obtained by using basic operations, except few. It is revised version of author's previous work [39, 40], where for the missing numbers **factorial** and **square-root** were used. In this work, only **factorial** are used for missing numbers. The representations from 0 to 20000 are in author's two works [16] and [41]. For more details and comments see author's site link [17]. This work combines and revise author's previous works [39, 40].

Contents

1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers	1
1.1 Increasing and Decreasing	1
1.2 Comments and Discussions	2
2 Crazy Representations From 20001 to 30000	3
2.1 Factorial-Type Representations	3
2.1.1 Increasing Order of 1 to 9	3
2.1.2 Descending Order of 1 to 9	16
2.2 Complete List	20

1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section natural numbers are represented in three different types.

1.1 Increasing and Decreasing

In 2013-2014, author [16] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See below some examples:

$$100 := 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$101 := 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1$$

$$102 := 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1$$

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$$\begin{aligned}103 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\104 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\105 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\106 &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\107 &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\108 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 &= 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1.\end{aligned}$$

Below are few more examples,

$$\begin{aligned}786 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 56 + 78 \times 9 &= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\999 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 &= 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321 \\2535 &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 &= 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\2607 &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 &= 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\10483 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 - 7 - 8 + 9 &= (9 \times 87 \times 6 + 543) \times 2 + 1 \\10549 &:= 1^2 \times 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 &= 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\10550 &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 &= 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\10553 &:= 1 \times 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 &= 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5 \times 43 + 21) \\10554 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 &= -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\11807 &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 &= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1.\end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's complete work [16, 17].

1.2 Comments and Discussions

This work has been considered as "**Improbable Research**". For details see the link:

- (i) <http://www.improbable.com/2013/02/12/lots-of-numbers-plain-and-almost-simple/> - [1];
- (ii) <http://www.improbable.com/2013/06/08/lots-more-numbers-deemed-crazy-sequential/> - [2].

We observe that the number 10958 is the only number among 0 to 11111 that is not possible to write in terms of 1 to 9 in the increasing case. We need to use extra operations, such as **square-root** and/or **factorial**, etc. See below:

$$10958 := 1 + 2 + 3!! + (-4 + 5! + 6 - 7) \times 89.$$

Recently, **Numberphile** produced two videos on **YouTube** using **concatenation** as an extra operation to bring representation of number 10958 in increasing order. See below both the links [3, 4]:

- (i) **The 10,958 Problem - Numberphile;**
- (ii) **A 10,958 Solution - Numberphile.**

For more comments and studies on the number 10958 by different researchers refer to author's site [17].

Extensions of above work to higher numbers refer to Ames [6, 7], and A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Velden [8, 9, 10, 11]. For different bases see A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Velden [12, 13]. Also extension to small bases refer Wylie [15].

The representations from 11112 to 20000 refer author's works [41]. This work combines author's previous two works [39, 40]. It also includes **extensive corrections** made by A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Velden [9].

More studies on representations of numbers in different situations refer author's work [16]-[41]. For different representations of 2019 see **YouTube** video by Matt Parker [5] based on author's work [42]

2 Crazy Representations From 20001 to 30000

Below are representations of natural numbers from 20001 to 30000 in ascending orders of 1 to 9. Most of the results are with operations, except few, i.e. total 393. In these, we have used the idea of **factorial**. These results are divided in two subsections. One on the numbers with factorial and another with complete list.

Remark 2.1. *Most of the results are with **excess of brackets**. After simplifications, these **extra brackets** can easily be removed. Moreover, the expressions of type " $\times - a$ " etc. requires more attention for simplifications.*

2.1 Factorial-Type Representations

This subsection give the result in increasing and decreasing order of 1 to 9 or 9 to 1, the numbers that require the use of extra operations such as **factorial**.

Remark 2.2. *In our representations, the fractional part and negative powers are not considered. If we allow the representations with fractional parts and/or negative powers (see [9] and A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Velden [9]), then some of these numbers can be obtained just by **basic operations**.*

2.1.1 Increasing Order of 1 to 9

There are very few numbers not written in terms of **basic operations**. These can be represented by use of **factorial**. Among 10000 numbers from 20001 to 30000 there are only 397 are written by use of **factorial**. These are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 20082 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3! + (-4 + 5! + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 20092 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! \times 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 20103 &:= 12 + (34 - 5) \times 6! - 789 \\
 20104 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\
 20320 &:= 1 \times 2^{3!} + (4 + 5! + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 20630 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5^6 + 7! - 8 \times 9 \\
 20642 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5^6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 20687 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5^6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 20794 &:= (1 + 2)!! + 3 + 4 \times 5! \times 6 \times 7 - 89 \\
 20860 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 20863 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5! + 6!) + 78 \times 9 \\
 20866 &:= 1 \times (2 \times 3!)^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
 20900 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 20902 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4! + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 21107 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)^5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21137 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (-5! + 6! \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 21211 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 21212 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! + (-4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 21220 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (-4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 21229 &:= (1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 21260 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!! - (4 + 5 \times 6)) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\
 21261 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5! + 6! \times (-7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 21278 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 21406 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 21586 &:= (1 + 2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5 \times 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 21589 &:= (1 + 23 \times 4! \times 5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 21677 &:= (1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (-5 + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 21739 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!! / 4) \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 21741 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 21742 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21778 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 \times 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 21908 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 21956 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 21974 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 22026 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 22046 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3!)^4 + (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 22052 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5! - 6) + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 22061 &:= (1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4567 + 8! + 9 \\ 22109 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 22124 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 22208 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 22256 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 22280 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 + 8) - 9 \\ 22281 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (-3!! + 4!) \times (-5 + 6 + 7 + 8) + 9 \\ 22291 &:= -(1 + 2)^{3!} + 4 \times (-5 + 6! + 7!) \times (-8 + 9) \\ 22322 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (-4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 22324 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 22358 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4! + 5!/6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 22363 &:= (1 - 2 - 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 22381 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 \times 6 + (-7 + 8)^9 \\ 22442 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 22493 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (-5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 22556 &:= (1 - 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 22646 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (-5! + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 22648 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4^5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 22664 &:= -1 + 2 + (-3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 22738 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (-4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)/8) + 9 \\ 22937 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (-4! + 5 \times 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 22970 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 23018 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 23080 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!!) \times 4 \times (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 \times 9 \\ 23082 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 23150 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (5 - 6!) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 23173 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 23218 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6!) - 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 23260 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 23261 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 23282 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 \times 5! - (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 23289 &:= -1 + 2 \times (-3 + 4)!/5! + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23303 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} \times 4 - 5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 23308 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 23729 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 23731 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 23732 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 23734 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 23747 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 23819 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 23882 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 23956 &:= 1 + 2 - 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8) + 9 \\ 23962 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4! - 5 + (6! + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 23974 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 23990 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 23996 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5!)) \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 24035 &:= -1 - 2 + (-3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6 + 7! \times (8 + 9) \\ 24286 &:= -1 \times 2 + (-3! + 4^5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 24331 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5)) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 24349 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5) + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 24371 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 - 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 24763 &:= -123 \times 4 + 5 \times (-6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 24806 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!)! - 4! - 5^6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 24810 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)! \times (4 + 5!)/6) \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\ 24811 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4! \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 24826 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5) + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 24827 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (-4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 24844 &:= (1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4) + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 \times 9) \\ 24869 &:= -1^{234} + 5 \times (6 + 7! - 8 \times 9) \\ 24926 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5 \times 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 24942 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 24946 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 24950 &:= (1 - 2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5! + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 24963 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3) \times (-4 \times (5 + 6) + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 24971 &:= -1 \times 2 + (-3 - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 24980 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 25028 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\ 25034 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 25045 &:= -1 + (-2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25060 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25061 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

- 25141 := (1 - 2 + 3!!) × (4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9
25142 := (1 × 2 + 3) × (-4 - 5 - 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9
25158 := -1 × 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 × (-6 + 7!) - 8 - 9
25171 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! × 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9
25178 := 1 × 2 + 3!! × (4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9
25180 := (1 × 2 + (3 + 4)!) × 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9
25195 := -1 + 2 + 3! × (4! - 5) × (6 + 7) × (8 + 9)
25196 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) × (-4 + 5 × 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9
25204 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) × (4 + 5 × 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9
25222 := -1 × 2 + 3!! × (4! + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9
25238 := -1 × 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 × (6 + 7!) + 8 + 9
25240 := (1 × 2 + (3 + 4)!) × 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
25241 := -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 × (6 + 7!) + 8 + 9
25250 := ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4) × 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9
25259 := -1 + (2 + (3 + 4) × 5!) × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
25261 := -1 + (-2 - 3 × 4! + 5! × (6 + 7)) × (8 + 9)
25283 := (-1 × 2 + 3 + 4) × (5!/6 + 7!) - 8 - 9
25288 := (1 + 2 × (3 + 4) + 5 × 6!) × 7 - 8 - 9
25292 := (1 × 2 + 3) × (4 + 5 + 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9
25306 := -1 × (2 + 3 + 4) + 5 × (6 + 7! + 8 + 9)
25333 := -1 + (-2 + (3 + 4)!) × 5 + 6 × (7 + 8 + 9)
25384 := -1 + (2 + 3) × ((4 + 5) × 6 + 7! - 8 - 9)
25403 := (1 × 2 + 3) × (4 × (5 + 6) + 7!) - 8 - 9
25409 := -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4) × (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
25412 := -1 + 2³⁺⁴ + 5 × (6! × 7 + 8 + 9)
25436 := (1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!) × 5 + (6 + 7) × (8 + 9)
25445 := (1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) × (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
25456 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) × (4 + 5 × (6! + 7)) - 8 - 9
25458 := -1 × 2 + 3⁴⁺⁵ + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9
25459 := -1 + (2 + 3) × (4! + 5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9)
25467 := -1 - 2 + 3! × ((4 - 5! + 6!) × 7 + 8 + 9)
25580 := (1 × 2 + 3) × (4! + (5 + 6!) × 7 + 8 + 9)
25589 := 1 × 2 × ((3!⁴ - 5) × 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9
25664 := 1 × 2 × (3!! - 4 - 5 + (6! - 7) × (8 + 9))
25670 := (1 - 2 + 3 + (-4 + 5!) × (6 + 7)) × (8 + 9)
25688 := -1 + 2 + (3 + (-4 + 5!) × (6 + 7)) × (8 + 9)
25742 := 1 × 2 × ((3!! - 4) × (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9)
25744 := -1 + (-2 + 3 + 4) × (5! + 6 + 7! - 8 - 9)
25747 := -1 + (2 × 3!)⁴ - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9
25763 := -1 + 2 × (3! - 4!) × (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9
25780 := (1 × 2 + 3) × ((4! - 5 + 6!) × 7 - 8 - 9)
25781 := -1 + (2 × 3!)⁴ - 5 - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9
25798 := -1 × 2 - 3!! + 4! × 5 × (6 + 7) × (8 + 9)
25816 := -1 × 2 - 3! × ((4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7! + 8 + 9)
25832 := 1 × 2 × (3 × (-4 - 5 - 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9)
25834 := -1 - (2 + 3) × (4 - 5! + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)
25835 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4!) + 5 × (6! × 7 - 8 - 9)
25853 := 1 × 2 × 3! × (4! × 5! - 6! - 7) + 8 + 9
25859 := -1 + (-2 + 3! × (4! + 5!)) × (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
25861 := (-1 + 2 + 3)! × 4! + 5 × (6! × 7 + 8 + 9)
25879 := -1 + (2 - 3!)⁴ × 5 × (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)
25891 := (1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!) × 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9
25904 := (-1 × 2 + 3!)⁴ × 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9
25906 := (1 × 2 + (3 + 4)!) × 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9
25931 := (-1 + 2 + 3) × ((4 + 5) × 6! + 7) - 8 - 9
25949 := (-1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!) × 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9
25996 := (1 + (2 + 3!!) × (4 + 5)) × (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9)
26003 := -1 × 2 + 3!! + (4 - 5 + 6) × (7! + 8 + 9)
26014 := -1 × 2 + 3! × (4 - 5 - 6! + 7! + 8 + 9)
26108 := 1 × 2 - 3! + (-4! + 5! × (6 + 7)) × (8 + 9)
26110 := (1 × 2 + 3!! + 4!) × (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)
26114 := 1 × 2 - (3! × 4 - 5! × (6 + 7)) × (8 + 9)
26115 := ((-1 + 2) × 3 - (4! - 5! × (6 + 7)) × (8 + 9))
26123 := -1 - 2 × (3! - 4!) × (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9
26126 := -1 - 2³⁺⁴⁺⁵ + 6 × 7! - 8 - 9
26170 := (1 - (2 + 3)! + 4! × (5! - 6)) × (-7 + 8 + 9)
26188 := -1 + (-2 + 3!) × (4 + 5) × (6! + 7) + 8 + 9
26269 := -1 + (2 + (3 + 4) × 5) × (6! + 7 - 8 - 9)
26270 := (1 + (-2 + 3!) × (4 + 5)) × (6! + 7 - 8 - 9)
26274 := (1 + (2 + 3)!/4) × (5! + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9
26284 := 1 × 2 × (-3 + 4⁵ + (6! - 7) × (8 + 9))
26288 := -1 + (2 + (3! × 4! - 5) × (6 + 7 + 8)) × 9
26290 := (1 - 2 + 3) × (4⁵ + (6! - 7) × (8 + 9))
26293 := -1 × 2 × 3!⁴ + 5 × (6! + 7! + 8 + 9)
26347 := -1 - 2 - (3! + 4 - 5! × (6 + 7)) × (8 + 9)
26354 := -1 × 2 + 3!! + (-4 + 5!) × (6 + 7) × (8 + 9)
26357 := (-1 + 2) + 3!! + (-4 + 5!) × (6 + 7) × (8 + 9)
26358 := (-1 + (2 + 3!) × 4!) × (5! - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)

$$\begin{aligned} 26365 &:= (-1 - 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9)) \\ 26366 &:= -1 + (-2 - 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26374 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26382 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4 \times 5! + 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 26383 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26391 &:= -1 - 2^{3+4} + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26408 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 26409 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!!/4 + 5 \times 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 26429 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (-4! + (5! - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26437 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26504 &:= -(-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26506 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26510 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26526 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26527 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26645 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times (4! - 5) - 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 26734 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 26756 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 26764 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times 5 + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26771 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times (-5 + 6 \times 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 26813 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\ 26852 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26885 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6! \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26906 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5!) + (6! + 7!/8) \times 9 \\ 26908 &:= (1 - 2 - 3! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7) + 8! - 9 \\ 26914 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 26936 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3! + (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26941 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (5! + (6! + 7 + 8) \times 9) \\ 26942 &:= -1 + (2^{3+4+5} - 6! - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 26943 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 \times 5! - 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 26944 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26950 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6!/(7 + 8) - 9) \\ 26957 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3^4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 26958 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 26977 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26987 &:= -1 + 2 \times (-3 \times 4! + (5! - 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26989 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - 5 \times 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 27004 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27022 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 - (5! - 6!) \times (7 + 8)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27094 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + (6! + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 27265 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27266 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27272 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4^5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 27275 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 - 5 + 6) \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27277 &:= (1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27282 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27283 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!!) \times (4 \times 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27292 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times (4! - 5) - 6 \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 27310 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27443 &:= -(1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 27445 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 - 5 + 6) \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 27452 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27454 &:= -1 - (2 + (3 - 4!)) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 27518 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 27536 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^4 + 5) + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27554 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 \times (-6 + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 27686 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 27706 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3^4 \times (5! - 6) + 7) - (8 + 9) \\ 27751 &:= (1 \times 2)^{3!+4+5} + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 27754 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!!/4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27814 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27842 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 27851 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\ 27859 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4!) \times 5!/6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27860 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (-3!! + 4!)) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 27868 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) + 4! \times (5! - 6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 27870 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!) \times (-4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27884 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 27902 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4^5) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27905 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4^5) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27923 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5! + (6 - 7 - 8) \times 9) \\ 27950 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! \times 5! - 6! + 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 27977 &:= (1 - (2 + 3) \times 4) \times 5! + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 27979 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27986 &:= 1 \times (2 \times 3!)^4 + (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27994 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! - 6! - 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 27995 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3) \times (-4! - 5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 28001 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$28021 := -1 + 2 - 3!! + (4! \times 5! - 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$28030 := 1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4^5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9)$$

$$28031 := -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$28039 := -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$28048 := (1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$28078 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$28172 := -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$28174 := (1 + 2) \times (-3!! + 4!) + 5 + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$28276 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$28318 := ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$28337 := (1 - 2 - 3) \times 4 \times 5! + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$28354 := -1 - 2 \times 3!! / 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$28388 := 1 \times 2 + (-3! + 4!) \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$28393 := 1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$28425 := (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8) + 9$$

$$28426 := -1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4! + (5 \times (6! + 7! - 8 - 9))$$

$$28447 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (-5! + 6! - 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$28451 := (1 - 2 \times 3!) \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$28453 := -1 + (-2 + 3!! - 4!) \times ((5 + 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9)$$

$$28501 := -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$28546 := -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) \times (-5 + 6!) - 7!) + 8 + 9$$

$$28616 := 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5! / 6 - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$28734 := -1 - 2 - 3 + (4! \times 5! - 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$28877 := (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$28894 := 1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$28910 := ((1 \times 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$28940 := (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4)) \times 5 \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$28948 := ((1 + 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$28958 := -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$28960 := (1 \times 2 + 3!) \times (-4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$28966 := -1 \times 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$28967 := -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$28984 := 1 \times 2 \times ((3!! + 4) \times 5! / 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$29003 := -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9))$$

$$29011 := -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$29012 := -1 + 2^{3+4} + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$29020 := -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$29031 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 \times (5 + 6!)) \times (-7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$29032 := (1 - 2 + 3! \times (-4! - 5 + 6!)) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$29038 := (1 - 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5 \times 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$29042 := -1 + 2 - 3!^4 - 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$29044 := -1 - 2 - 3!^4 + 5! + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$29083 := -(-1 + 2 + 3!)! / 4 + 5! + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$29084 := -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times 5 \times (6! + 7)) + 8 + 9$$

$$29092 := -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4! + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$29096 := -1 + (-2 + (3 + 4)! / 5!) \times (6! + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$29098 := ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4!) + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$29099 := -1 - (2 + 3 + 4 \times 5!) \times 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$29101 := -1 + 2 + (3!! \times 4 + 5 \times 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$29108 := -1 - 2 - 3 - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$29117 := (-1 + 2) \times 3 - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$29174 := 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$29198 := -1 \times (2 + 3)! - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$29201 := (-1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4! / 5 + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$29203 := -1 + 2 + 3 - 4^5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$29211 := (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$29212 := -1 - 2 - (3 + 4)! / 5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9$$

$$29218 := (1 + 2) \times (3! - (4 + 5 - 6)!!) + 7 \times 8! / 9$$

$$29219 := (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times (5! - 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$29221 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (-4 - 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$29226 := (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5!) + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$29228 := (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$29246 := -1 - 2 - (3 + 4)! / 5 + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$29252 := 1 \times 2 \times (3^{4+5} - 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$29254 := -1 - 2 + ((3 + 4)! / 5 + (6! - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$29263 := -1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$29264 := 1 \times 2 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$29265 := 1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$29266 := 1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (-4 + 5!) \times 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$29270 := (-1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5! + 6!)) \times 7 + (8 + 9)$$

$$29290 := -1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} - 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9$$

$$29298 := (1 - 2) \times (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$29307 := -1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$29330 := 1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9)$$

$$29343 := -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 \times (5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9))$$

$$29362 := -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$29372 := (1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4! - 5 + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29378 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29390 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5 + 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 29399 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)^4 - 5! + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29426 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29428 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29434 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29470 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4!) - 5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29488 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29498 &:= 1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4)! - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 29499 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29500 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (-4! + 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\ 29504 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\ 29506 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!) - 4 - 5! \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 29533 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4^5 + 6! - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29537 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3!! \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\ 29539 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 29554 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!) + 4 - 5! \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 29570 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4!) + 5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29586 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (-5! - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29587 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (-4! \times 5 - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29588 &:= (1 - 2^{3+4}) \times 5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29596 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29598 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4+5} \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29599 &:= 1 \times 2^{3+4+5} \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29608 &:= (1 - (2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29612 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29620 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5 - 6)! \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29621 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5 - 6)! \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29650 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 29651 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 29660 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!!) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\ 29677 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 29678 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4! + 5! + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 29689 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8) - 9 \\ 29693 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29698 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4^5 - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29702 &:= -1 \times 2^{3+4} \times 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29708 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4! + 5!) + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29753 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29756 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 29758 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29765 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 29773 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4^5 + 6! + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29774 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29776 &:= (1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5 + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 29866 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (-3!! + 4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29867 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29909 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5!) + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 29924 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!!/4 - 5! + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29963 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (-5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 29967 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (-4! + 5) + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29968 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) + (6 \times 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29972 &:= -(1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29973 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29974 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (-3 - 4 + (5! + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29995 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 20082 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3! + (-4 + 5! + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 20092 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! \times 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 20103 &:= 12 + (34 - 5) \times 6! - 789 \\ 20104 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!!) \times (4 + (5!/(6 + 7 + 8 + 9)))! \\ 20320 &:= 1 \times 2^{3!} + (4 + 5! + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 20630 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5^6 + 7! - 8 \times 9 \\ 20642 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5^6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 20687 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5^6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 20794 &:= (1 + 2)!! + 3 + 4 \times 5! \times 6 \times 7 - 89 \\ 20860 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 20863 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5! + 6!) + 78 \times 9 \\ 20866 &:= 1 \times (2 \times 3!)^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 20900 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 20902 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4! + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 21107 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)^5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 21137 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (-5! + 6! \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 21211 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 21212 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! + (-4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 21220 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (-4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 21229 &:= (1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 21260 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!! - (4 + 5 \times 6)) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 21261 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5! + 6! \times (-7 + 8 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

- 21278** := $1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9))$
21406 := $-1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9$
21586 := $(1 + 2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5 \times 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9$
21589 := $(1 + 23 \times 4! \times 5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9$
21677 := $(1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (-5 + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9$
21739 := $(1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$
21741 := $-1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
21742 := $-1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))$
21778 := $-1 + (-2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 \times 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9)$
21908 := $(-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times (5 + 6) + 7! - 8 - 9$
21956 := $(1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9$
21974 := $(1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$
22026 := $(1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$
22046 := $1 + (2 \times 3!)^4 + (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)$
22052 := $(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5! - 6) + 7! + 8 + 9)$
22061 := $(1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4567 + 8! + 9$
22109 := $-1 + (-2 + 3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
22124 := $(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9)$
22208 := $(1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9)$
22256 := $(-1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$
22280 := $(1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 + 8) - 9$
22281 := $-1 \times 2 \times (-3!! + 4!) \times (-5 + 6 + 7 + 8) + 9$
22291 := $-(1 + 2)^{3!} + 4 \times (-5 + 6! + 7!) \times (-8 + 9)$
22322 := $1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (-4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
22324 := $(-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$
22358 := $-1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4! + 5!/6 + 7! + 8 + 9$
22363 := $(1 - 2 - 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7!) + 8 + 9$
22381 := $(1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 \times 6 + (-7 + 8)^9$
22442 := $1 \times 2 + (3 + 4!) + (5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$
22493 := $(-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (-5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9)$
22556 := $(1 - 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$
22646 := $(1 + 2) \times 3! + 4 \times (-5! + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9)$
22648 := $(1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4^5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$
22664 := $-1 + 2 + (-3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9$
22738 := $(-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (-4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)/8) + 9$
22937 := $(1 \times 2 + 3) \times (-4! + 5 \times 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9$
22970 := $-1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9)$
23018 := $1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9$
23080 := $(-1 + 2 - 3!!) \times 4 \times (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 \times 9$
23082 := $(1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$
23150 := $(1 \times 2 + 3!)! + 4! \times (5 - 6!) + 7 - 8 - 9$
23173 := $(-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7!) + 8 + 9$
23218 := $(-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6!) - 7! - 8 - 9$
23260 := $-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$
23261 := $(1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$
23282 := $(-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 \times 5! - (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9))$
23289 := $-1 + 2 \times (-3 + 4)!/5! + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)$
23303 := $-1 + (2^{3!} \times 4 - 5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$
23308 := $-1 - 2 + 3!^4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9$
23729 := $(-1 + 2 \times (3 - 4!)) \times 5 \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))$
23731 := $-1 + 2 \times (3!! - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$
23732 := $1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$
23734 := $(-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$
23747 := $(1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9)$
23819 := $1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)$
23882 := $(1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9$
23956 := $1 + 2 - 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8) + 9$
23962 := $(1 + 2 + 3!!) \times 4! - 5 + (6! + 7 + 8) \times 9$
23974 := $((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7) - 8 - 9$
23990 := $(-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9)$
23996 := $(-1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5!)) \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9)$
24035 := $-1 - 2 + (-3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6 + 7! \times (8 + 9)$
24286 := $-1 \times 2 + (-3! + 4^5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$
24331 := $(1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5)) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9))$
24349 := $-1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5) + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9))$
24371 := $(1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 - 6! - 7 \times (8 + 9)$
24763 := $-123 \times 4 + 5 \times (-6 + 7! + 8 + 9)$
24806 := $(1 \times 2 + 3!)! - 4! - 5^6 + (7 + 8) \times 9$
24810 := $(-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5!)/6 \times (7 - 8 - 9)$
24811 := $-1 \times 2 + (3! + 4! \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8) \times 9$
24826 := $1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5) + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9))$
24827 := $(-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (-4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$
24844 := $(1 - 2) \times (3!! - 4) + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 \times 9)$
24869 := $-1^{234} + 5 \times (6 + 7! - 8 \times 9)$
24926 := $-1 - 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5 \times 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9$
24942 := $-1 - (2 - 3!) \times 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9$
24946 := $-1 - (2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9$
24950 := $(1 - 2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5! + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9))$

$$\begin{aligned} 24963 &:= 1 \times (2+3) \times (-4 \times (5+6) + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 24971 &:= -1 \times 2 + (-3 - 4 + 5!) \times (6+7) \times (8+9) \\ 24980 &:= -1 + 2 + (3+4)! \times 5 - (6+7) \times (8+9) \\ 25028 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! \times (6+7) + 8+9) \\ 25034 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3+4) \times (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 25045 &:= -1 + (-2 + (3+4)!) \times 5 - 6 \times (7+8+9) \\ 25060 &:= ((-1+2) \times 3!! - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\ 25061 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4) \times (5+6+7+8+9) \\ 25141 &:= (1 - 2 + 3!!) \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25142 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (-4 - 5 - 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 25158 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 \times (-6 + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 25171 &:= -1 + 2 + (3+4)! \times 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25178 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25180 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3+4)!) \times 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25195 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! - 5) \times (6+7) \times (8+9) \\ 25196 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (-4 + 5 \times 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25204 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25222 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4! + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25238 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times (6+7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 25240 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3+4)!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25241 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times (6+7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 25250 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25259 &:= -1 + (2 + (3+4) \times 5!) \times (6+7+8+9) \\ 25261 &:= -1 + (-2 - 3 \times 4! + 5!) \times (6+7) \times (8+9) \\ 25283 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5!/6 + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 25288 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3+4) + 5 \times 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25292 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 25306 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) + 5 \times (6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 25333 &:= -1 + (-2 + (3+4)!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7+8+9) \\ 25384 &:= -1 + (2+3) \times ((4+5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 25403 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5+6) + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 25409 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25412 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25436 &:= (1 + 2 + (3+4)!) \times 5 + (6+7) \times (8+9) \\ 25445 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25456 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 \times (6! + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\ 25458 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 25459 &:= -1 + (2+3) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 25467 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times ((4 - 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25580 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4! + (5+6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25589 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3!^4 - 5) \times 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 25664 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 + (6! - 7) \times (8+9)) \\ 25670 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 + (-4 + 5!) \times (6+7)) \times (8+9) \\ 25688 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + (-4 + 5!) \times (6+7)) \times (8+9) \\ 25742 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3!! - 4) \times (5+6+7) - 8 - 9) \\ 25744 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! + 6 + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 25747 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!)^4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 25763 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25780 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times ((4! - 5 + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 25781 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!)^4 - 5 - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 25798 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4! \times 5 \times (6+7) \times (8+9) \\ 25816 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4+5-6)!! - 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 25832 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (-4 - 5 - 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9) \\ 25834 &:= -1 - (2+3) \times (4 - 5! + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 25835 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4!) + 5 \times (6! \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 25853 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! \times 5! - 6! - 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 25859 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3! \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6+7+8+9) \\ 25861 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! \times 4! + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25879 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!^4) \times 5 \times (6+7-8-9) \\ 25891 &:= (1 - 2 + (3+4)!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25904 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25906 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3+4)!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25931 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4+5) \times 6! + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 25949 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3+4)!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25996 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4+5)) \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26003 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 - 5 + 6) \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 26014 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 - 5 - 6! + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 26108 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! + (-4! + 5! \times (6+7)) \times (8+9) \\ 26110 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26114 &:= 1 \times 2 - (3! \times 4 - 5! \times (6+7)) \times (8+9) \\ 26115 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 - (4! - 5! \times (6+7))) \times (8+9) \\ 26123 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 26126 &:= -1 - 2^{3+4+5} + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 26170 &:= (1 - (2+3)! + 4! \times (5! - 6)) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26188 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!) \times (4+5) \times (6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 26269 &:= -1 + (2 + (3+4) \times 5) \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 26270 &:= (1 + (-2 + 3!) \times (4+5)) \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 26274 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)!/4) \times (5! + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26284 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (-3 + 4^5 + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26288 &:= -1 + (2 + (3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8)) \times 9 \\ 26290 &:= (1 - 2 + 3) \times (4^5 + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26293 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 26347 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26354 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (-4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26357 &:= (-1 + 2) + 3!! + (-4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26358 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5! - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26365 &:= (-1 - 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9)) \\ 26366 &:= -1 + (-2 - 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26374 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26382 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4 \times 5! + 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 26383 &:= -1 - (2 + 3! - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26391 &:= -1 - 2^{3+4} + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26408 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 26409 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!!/4 + 5 \times 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 26429 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (-4! + (5! - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26437 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26504 &:= -(-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26506 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26510 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26526 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26527 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26645 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!!) \times (4! - 5) - 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 26734 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 26756 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 26764 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times 5 + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26771 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times (-5 + 6 \times 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 26813 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\ 26852 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26885 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6! \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26906 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (4 + 5!) + (6! + 7!/8) \times 9 \\ 26908 &:= (1 - 2 - 3! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7) + 8! - 9 \\ 26914 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 26936 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3! + (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26941 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (5! + (6! + 7 + 8) \times 9) \\ 26942 &:= -1 + (2^{3+4+5} - 6! - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 26943 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 \times 5! - 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 26944 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26950 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6!/(7 + 8) - 9) \\ 26957 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3^4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 26958 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 26977 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26987 &:= -1 + 2 \times (-3 \times 4! + (5! - 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26989 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - 5 \times 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 27004 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27022 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 - (5! - 6!)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9 \\ 27094 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + (6! + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 27265 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27266 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27272 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4^5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 27275 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 - 5 + 6) \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27277 &:= (1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4! - 5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27282 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27283 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!!) \times (4 \times 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27292 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times (4! - 5) - 6 \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 27310 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27443 &:= -(1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4! + 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 27445 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 - 5 + 6) \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 27452 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + (4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27454 &:= -1 - (2 + (3 - 4!)) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 27518 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 27536 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^4 + 5) + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27554 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 \times (-6 + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 27686 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 27706 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3^4 \times (5! - 6) + 7) - (8 + 9) \\ 27751 &:= (1 \times 2)^{3!+4+5} + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 27754 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!!/4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27814 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27842 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 27851 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\ 27859 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4!) \times 5!/6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27860 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (-3!! + 4!)) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 27868 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) + 4! \times (5! - 6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 27870 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!) \times (-4 + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27884 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5!/6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 27902 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4^5) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27905 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4^5) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27923 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5! + (6 - 7 - 8) \times 9) \\ 27950 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! \times 5! - 6! + 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 27977 &:= (1 - (2 + 3) \times 4) \times 5! + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 27979 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27986 &:= 1 \times (2 \times 3!)^4 + (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27994 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! - 6! - 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 27995 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3) \times (-4! - 5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 28001 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28021 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + (4! \times 5! - 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28030 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4^5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\ 28031 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\ 28039 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 28048 &:= (1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 28078 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28172 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28174 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3!! + 4!) + 5 + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 28276 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 28318 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 28337 &:= (1 - 2 - 3) \times 4 \times 5! + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 28354 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3!!/4 + 5 \times (6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 28388 &:= 1 \times 2 + (-3! + 4!) \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\ 28393 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 28425 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8) + 9 \\ 28426 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4! + (5 \times (6! + 7! - 8 - 9)) \\ 28447 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (-5! + 6! - 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 28451 &:= (1 - 2 \times 3!) \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 28453 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!! - 4!) \times ((5 + 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9) \\ 28501 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 28546 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) \times (-5 + 6!) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 28616 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5!/6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 28734 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4! \times 5! - 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28877 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 28894 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 28910 &:= ((1 \times 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28940 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4)) \times 5 \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28948 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 28958 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 28960 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!) \times (-4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28966 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28967 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 28984 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3!! + 4) \times 5!/6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 29003 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 29011 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29012 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29020 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29031 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 \times (5 + 6!)) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29032 &:= (1 - 2 + 3! \times (-4! - 5 + 6!)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 29038 &:= (1 - 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5 \times 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29042 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!^4 - 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29044 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!^4 + 5! + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29083 &:= -(-1 + 2 + 3)!/4 + 5! + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29084 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times 5 \times (6! + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\ 29092 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4! + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29096 &:= -1 + (-2 + (3 + 4)!/5!) \times (6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 29098 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4!) + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 29099 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 + 4 \times 5!) \times 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) \\ 29101 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! \times 4 + 5 \times 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29108 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29117 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29174 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29198 &:= -1 \times (2 + 3)! - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29201 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4!/5 + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 29203 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4^5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29211 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29212 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4)!/5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29218 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3! - (4 + 5 - 6)!!) + 7 \times 8!/9 \\ 29219 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times (5! - 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 29221 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (-4 - 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 29226 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5!) + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29228 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 29246 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4)!/5 + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 29252 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3^{4+5} - 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 29254 &:= -1 - 2 + ((3 + 4)!/5 + (6! - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29263 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29264 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29265 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29266 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (-4 + 5!)) \times 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29270 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5! + 6!)) \times 7 + (8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29290 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} - 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\
 29298 &:= (1 - 2) \times (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29307 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29330 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29343 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 \times (5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 29362 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
 29372 &:= (1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4! - 5 + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29378 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 29390 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5 + 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 29399 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)^4 - 5! + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 29426 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29428 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29434 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29470 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4!) - 5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\
 29488 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 29498 &:= 1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4)! - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 29499 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29500 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (-4! + 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
 29504 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\
 29506 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! - 4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 29533 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4^5 + 6! - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29537 &:= (1 - 2) \times 3!! \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
 29539 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 29554 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 29570 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4!) + 5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\
 29586 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (-5! - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29587 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (-4! \times 5 - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29588 &:= (1 - 2^{3+4}) \times 5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 29596 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29598 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4+5} \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 29599 &:= 1 \times 2^{3+4+5} \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 29608 &:= (1 - (2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29612 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29620 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5 - 6)! \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29621 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5 - 6)! \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29650 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
 29651 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
 29660 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!!) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\
 29677 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 29678 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4! + 5! + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 29689 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! / 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8) - 9 \\
 29693 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29698 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4^5 - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29702 &:= -1 \times 2^{3+4} \times 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29708 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4! + 5!) + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29753 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 29756 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times 5! / 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 29758 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 29765 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 29773 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4^5 + 6! + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29774 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29776 &:= (1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5 + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 29866 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (-3!! + 4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 29867 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29909 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5!) + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 29924 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! / 4 - 5! + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 29963 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (-5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 29967 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (-4! + 5) + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29968 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) + (6 \times 7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29972 &:= -(1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29973 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! + 6)) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
 29974 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (-3 - 4 + (5! + 6)) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) \\
 29995 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.3. In our representations, the **fractional part** and **negative powers** are not considered. If we allow the representations with fractional parts and/or negative powers (see A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Velden [9]), then some of the above numbers can be replaced by **basic operations**. See below:

• **Numbers Due to B. Ames [7]**

The following numbers only with basic operations sent by B. Ames [7], are already included in the **Complete List**

$$\begin{aligned}20768 &:= 12 \times (-34 + 5^6 - 7 - 8)/9 \\20846 &:= ((12 + 3)^4 - 5 + 6) \times 7/(8 + 9) \\20858 &:= (-12 + 3 \times (4 \times 5^6 + 78))/9 \\20864 &:= 12 + 3 \times (4 \times 5^6 + 7 \times 8)/9 \\20984 &:= 123 \times 4^5/6 - 7 + 8 - 9 \\21227 &:= (1 - 23)^4/(5 + 6) - 78 + 9 \\23106 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + (4 + 5)^6)/(78 - 9) \\23264 &:= 1 + ((-2 + 3 + 4)^5 \times 67 - 8)/9 \\24315 &:= (1 + 2 \times (34 + 5^6 \times 7 + 8))/9 \\24738 &:= (-1 + 23^4)/(5 + 6) - 78 \times 9 \\24805 &:= (-1 + (23 + 4) \times (5^6 - 7))/(8 + 9) \\25310 &:= ((12 + 3)^4 - 5)/(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9) \\25340 &:= 12 \times (3^{4+5} - 678)/9 \\25430 &:= (-1 + 23^4)/(5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\25684 &:= -12^3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times 89 \\25796 &:= 12 \times (3^{4+5} - 6 \times 7 \times 8)/9 \\25890 &:= (1 - 23 \times 4 + 5^6) \times (7 + 8)/9 \\25978 &:= -12 + 345 \times 678/9 \\26005 &:= (12 - 34 + 5^6) \times (7 + 8)/9 \\26006 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 - 5 \times 6 \times 7 + 8)/9 \\26021 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 - 5 - 6 - 7 \times 8)/9 \\26059 &:= 1 + 23 + (-4 + 5^6) \times (7 + 8)/9 \\26098 &:= (-1 - 2 + (34 + 5^6) \times (7 + 8))/9 \\26149 &:= 1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4)^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8)/9 \\26272 &:= 12 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 + 7 + 8)/9 \\26356 &:= 12 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 + 78)/9 \\26492 &:= -12^3 - 4 + 56 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\26573 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 - 6) \times 78/9 \\26770 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 \times 5^6)/7 - 8 - 9 \\26806 &:= (1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6)) \times 78/9 \\26924 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 \times 6 \times 7/8 + 9) \\26926 &:= 1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 \times 6 \times 7/8 + 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}27021 &:= (1 + 2)^3 \times (4^5 + 6) - 789 \\27317 &:= (-1 + (-2 + (3 + 4)^5) \times (6 + 7))/8 + 9 \\27320 &:= (12 + 3) \times (4^{(-5+6) \times 7} + 8)/9 \\27752 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (-3 - 4 + 5^6 - 7)) \times 8/9 \\27815 &:= -(1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4^5 + 6^7/8 + 9 \\27832 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (34 + 5^6) - 7) \times 8/9 \\27983 &:= (-1 \times 23^4 + (5 + 6))/(7 - 8 - 9) \\28003 &:= (12 + ((3 + 4)^5 - 6) \times (7 + 8))/9 \\28004 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 + 4)^5 - 6) \times (7 + 8)/9 \\28022 &:= (1 + 2 + ((3 + 4)^5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))/9 \\28076 &:= 12 \times (-3 + 45 \times 6 \times 78)/9 \\28427 &:= -(12 - 3)^4 + 5 + 6^7/8 - 9 \\28957 &:= 1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)^5 \times 6/7 + 8 \times 9) \\29210 &:= (1 - 23)^4/(-5 + 6 + 7) - 8 \times 9 \\29236 &:= (1 + 2 - (3 + 4)^5 + 6^7 - 8)/9 \\29272 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 + 5 - 6 - 7)/8 - 9 \\29288 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 - 5 + 6)^7)/8 - 9 \\29299 &:= (1 - 23)^4/(-5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\29300 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 + 5 + 67)/8 + 9 \\29306 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 - 5 + 6)^7)/8 + 9 \\29354 &:= (1 - 23)^4/(-5 + 6 + 7) + 8 \times 9 \\29365 &:= -1 + (23^4 - 5^6 + 78)/9 \\29396 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (((3 \times 4 - 5)^6 + 7)/8 - 9) \\29398 &:= 1 \times ((2 \times (3 + 4)^5 - 6) \times 7/8 - 9) \\29473 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4^5 + 6^7)/(8 \times 9) \\29524 &:= (1 - (2 + 3 + 4)^5)/(6 - 7 + 8 - 9) \\29525 &:= (1 + (2 + 3 + 4)^5)/(-6 + 7 - 8 + 9) \\29772 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (-4 + 56 \times (7 + 8) - 9) \\29926 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3456) \times 78/9 \\29984 &:= 12 \times (3^{4+5} - 6)/7 \times 8/9\end{aligned}$$

• **Numbers Due to A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Velden [9]**

*The following numbers only with basic operations sent by A.E. Bras [9], are not included in the **Complete List***

$$\begin{aligned}20103 &:= ((1+2)^{3+4} + 5/6 \times 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\20320 &:= (1^2 + 3)^4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7/8 + 9) \\20687 &:= -1 + (-2/3 + 4 \times (5 + 67)) \times 8 \times 9 \\20846 &:= ((12 + 3)^4 - 5 + 6) \times 7/(8 + 9) \\20902 &:= (1/2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 67 \times 89) \\21211 &:= 1 + (2/3 + 4) \times (567 \times 8 + 9) \\21261 &:= (1/2 + 34) \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times 8 + 9 \\21586 &:= -1/2 + (3/4 + 5 \times 6) \times 78 \times 9 \\22026 &:= (-1/2 + 3 + 4) \times 5 \times 678 - 9 \\22109 &:= 1/2 \times (34 + 56 \times 789) \\22358 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 \times 5/6 \times 789 \\22363 &:= ((1/2 + (3 + 4)^5)/6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 \\22442 &:= (12^3 + 4 - 5)/6 \times 78 - 9 \\22493 &:= ((1/2 + 3^4) \times 5 - 6) \times 7 \times 8 + 9 \\23018 &:= 1 - 23 + 4^5/6 \times (7 + 8) \times 9 \\23080 &:= 12 \times (34 \times (5/6 + 7 \times 8) - 9) \\23218 &:= (-1 - 2 + 345) \times (67 + 8/9) \\23260 &:= 12 \times (-3 + 4 \times 56 \times 78/9) \\23282 &:= 1 - 2 + (34 - 5/6) \times 78 \times 9 \\23289 &:= -1 + (2/3 + 45) \times (6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9) \\23303 &:= -1 + 2/3 \times (-45 + 6^7/8 + 9) \\23308 &:= 1 + 2/3 \times (-45 + 6^7/8) + 9 \\23819 &:= (-1/2 + 3^4) \times (-5 + 6 \times 7) \times 8 - 9 \\24035 &:= (1/2 + 3/4^{-5} - 67) \times 8 - 9 \\24286 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (-3 \times 4 + 5^6) \times 7 - 8)/9 \\24349 &:= -1 + 2/(3 + 4 \times 5) \times (6^7 + 89) \\24371 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3/4 \times (5^6 + 7 \times 89) \\24763 &:= (-1/2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\24869 &:= (1/2 + 3) \times (4^5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 \times 9 \\24942 &:= ((1/2 + 3) \times (4^5 - 6) \times 7 - 8) + 9 \\24946 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times (4/5^{-6}/(7 + 8) - 9) \\25045 &:= ((1/2 + 3) \times 4^5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\25158 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (-4 + 5/6 + 78 \times 9) \\25241 &:= -1 + (2 + 34) \times (-5/6 + 78 \times 9) \\25456 &:= (1 + 23) \times (4^5 + 6 \times (7 - 8/9)) \\25589 &:= (-1/2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6 \times 7)) \times 8 + 9 \\25589 &:= (-1/2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6 \times 7)) \times 8 + 9 \\25861 &:= (12^3 - 4 \times 5/6) \times (7 + 8) - 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}25879 &:= -1/2 + 3^{4+5}/6 \times (7 + 8/9) \\25891 &:= (1/2 \times 3 \times 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\25904 &:= (-1/(2 \times 3) + 45 \times 6) \times (7 + 89) \\25931 &:= -1 + (2^{-3} + 45 \times 6) \times (7 + 89) \\26269 &:= (1 + 2^{3+4+5}) \times (6 + 7/(8 + 9)) \\26270 &:= -1 + (2^{-3} - 4 + 56) \times 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\26274 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3^{4+5}/6 + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\26284 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 \times (6 - 7/8) + 9) \\26288 &:= (1 \times 2^{-3} - 4) \times (5 - 6789) \\26290 &:= -(1 + (-23 + 4)^5 + 6^7 \times 8)/9 \\26293 &:= 1 \times (-2 + 3^{4+5}/6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\26527 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((-3 + 4^5)/6 \times 78 - 9) \\26771 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3 + 4^5)/6) \times 78 - 9 \\27265 &:= -1 + 2 + 3456 \times (7 + 8/9) \\27266 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3456 \times (7 + 8/9) \\27445 &:= (-1 + 2^3)/4 \times (5^6 + 7) + 89 \\27554 &:= ((-1 + 2^3)^4 - 5)/6 \times (78 - 9) \\27994 &:= 1/(-2 + 3 \times 4) \times (5 + 6^7 + 8 - 9) \\28030 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4^5 \times ((-6 + 7)/8 + 9) \\28031 &:= -1 + (-2/3 \times 4 + 56 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\28048 &:= -1 - 2 + (3/4)^{-5} \times 6^7/(8 \times 9) \\28078 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3456 \times (-7/8 + 9) \\28172 &:= 1 \times 2 + (-3/4 + 56 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\28276 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3/4 + 56 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\28354 &:= 1/2 \times (-3^4 + 56789) \\28501 &:= 1/2 \times (-3 + (4^5 - 6) \times 7) \times 8 + 9 \\28734 &:= (-1/2 + 34) \times (5 + 6) \times 78 - 9 \\28877 &:= (12^3 - 4) \times ((-5 + 67)/8 + 9) \\29011 &:= (12^3 + 4) \times ((-5 + 67)/8 + 9) \\29020 &:= -1/2 + (3^{4+5}/6 - 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\29031 &:= (1/2 + 345) \times (6 + 78) + 9 \\29083 &:= (1/2 \times (3 + 4^5) + 6) \times 7 \times 8 - 9 \\29101 &:= (1/2 \times (3 + 4^5) + 6) \times 7 \times 8 + 9 \\29174 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (-3 + 4^5/6) \times (78 + 9) \\29264 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 - 5 - 67)/8 - 9 \\29265 &:= (1 - 23)^4/56 \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\29290 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 - 56/7)/8 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29307 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + (4 - 5 + 6)^7) / 8 + 9 \\ 29330 &:= (1 + 234567) / 8 + 9 \\ 29390 &:= 1/2 + (3^{4+5} / 6 - 7 - 8) \times 9 \\ 29399 &:= 1 + (2 / (3 + 4)^{-5} - 6) \times 7 / 8 - 9 \\ 29533 &:= -1/2 + (3^{4+5} / 6 - 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 29537 &:= 1 + (2 + 3^{-4} + 5) \times 6 \times 78 \times 9 \\ 29596 &:= (1234 - 5/6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29608 &:= -1 + 2 \times (-3 + 4^5) / (6 / (78 + 9)) \\ 29660 &:= 1/2 + (3^{4+5} / 6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 29689 &:= -1 + 2 \times (-3 + 4^5 / (6 / (78 + 9))) \\ 29702 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 + 4^5 / 6 \times (78 + 9)) \\ 29924 &:= -1 + (-2/3 + 45) \times (67 + 8) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

2.1.2 Descending Order of 1 to 9

There are very few numbers not written in terms of **basic operations**. These can be represented by use of **factorial**. Among 10000 numbers from 20001 to 30000 there are only 191 are written by use of **factorial**. These are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 20218 &:= (9 + 8! - 7 - 6 + 5!) / (-4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 20228 &:= (9 + 8 + 7!) \times (-6! / 5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 20230 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 20797 &:= (9 + 8 + 7) / 6 + (5 + 4!) \times (-3 + (2 + 1)!) \\ 21082 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 21094 &:= (9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4!) - 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\ 21212 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 21379 &:= -(9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! / 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 21434 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7! - 6) \times 5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\ 21458 &:= -9 + 8! - 7! + 6 + 5 - 4!^{3!-2-1} \\ 21469 &:= (9 \times 8 + (-7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4!)) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 21499 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7! \times 6 + 5!) / 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 21765 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 21782 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5! / 4 + 3! / (2 + 1) \\ 21821 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5! / 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 21822 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6! + 5!) \times (-4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 22255 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\ 22300 &:= ((9 - 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 22306 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 22412 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7! + 6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 22570 &:= (9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 22758 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7!) / 6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 22991 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((-7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\ 23020 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! - 6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 23117 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 23728 &:= (-9 + 8! / 7 + 6 - 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 23756 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23794 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\ 23888 &:= -9 + 8! - 7 + (6 - 5!) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 23890 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!) - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 23918 &:= (9 \times (-8 \times 7 + 6!) + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 24062 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!) \\ 24131 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5^4 - 3!^{2+1}) \\ 24133 &:= (9 + 8 + 7! / 6) \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 24142 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! \times 6 / 5) \times 4 + 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\ 24155 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!)) \times 5 - (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\ 24203 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + (5 + 4!)^3 + 2 + 1 \\ 24204 &:= (-9 + (8! - 7!) / (6! / 5!)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 24260 &:= (9 + 8 + 7! \times 6 / 5) \times 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 24404 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 24748 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\ 24754 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! \times 5 - 4^3) + 2 + 1 \\ 24781 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4^{3!} \times (2 + 1)! \\ 24878 &:= (-9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4)) \times 3! / (2 + 1) \\ 24902 &:= (9 + (8 - 7 + 6)!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\ 24917 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7! / 6) + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 24925 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!!)) \\ 24941 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6) \times 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 24946 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!!)) \\ 25012 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4) - 3!! - (2 + 1)!! \\ 25069 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! + 6) \times 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 25132 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7! - 6! \times 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 25180 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 25196 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6! \times 5 - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25204 &:= (9-8) \times 7 \times 6! \times 5 + 4! / (3+2+1) \\ 25261 &:= -9 + (8+7!+6) \times (-5+4+3+2+1) \\ 25294 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! \times 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 25302 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7!+6) \times (-5+4+3+2+1) \\ 25310 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6+5 \times (4+(3+2+1)!)) \\ 25322 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times 6 + 5! - (4+3)! + 2 + 1 \\ 25348 &:= (9 \times (-8-7+6!) - 5) \times 4 - 3! - (2+1)! \\ 25355 &:= (9+8) \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times ((4+3)! + (2+1)!) \\ 25363 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! + (6 \times 5 + (4+3)!) \times (2+1)! \\ 25364 &:= (9+8) \times ((7+6) \times (5!+4) - 3! / (2+1)!) \\ 25366 &:= (9 \times (-8-7+6!) - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 25402 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (-6+5 \times (4+3+(2+1)!)) \\ 25436 &:= (9+8) \times (7+6) + 5 \times ((4+3)! + 2 + 1) \\ 25549 &:= (9 + (8!/7!+6!) \times 5) \times (4+3) + (2+1)! \\ 25556 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6!) \times 5 - 4 + (3+2+1)! \\ 25573 &:= (9+8+7!/6) \times (5+4!) + (3+2+1)! \\ 25574 &:= (9-8 \times 7+6!) \times (5 \times (4+3) + 2 + 1) \\ 25576 &:= -9 + 8! + 7 + (6+5! - (4+3)!) \times (2+1) \\ 25612 &:= (9 \times (-8!/7!+6!) - 5) \times 4! / (3+2+1) \\ 25636 &:= (9+8) \times (7+6) \times (5! - 4! / (3+2+1)) \\ 25682 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 \times (-6+5!) + 4) \times 32 + 1 \\ 25719 &:= -9 + (-8+7! - 6 \times 5! - 4!) \times (3+2+1) \\ 25720 &:= (9 \times (8+7+6!) - 5) \times 4 - (3+2+1)! \\ 25763 &:= (-9+8!+7-6-5) - 4!^3 - (2+1)!! \\ 25765 &:= -9 + 8! - (7+6!) \times (5 \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 25779 &:= 9 \times (-8-7+6 \times 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 25796 &:= (9+8) \times (7+6) \times 5! - 4 - (3+2+1)! \\ 25798 &:= -(9+8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 \times (4+3)! - 2 - 1 \\ 25934 &:= (9 \times (8-7) \times 6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 25979 &:= (9-8+7!+6) \times 5 + 4! + (3+2+1)! \\ 26084 &:= (9+8) \times (7+6) \times (5!+4-3!) + (2+1)! \\ 26420 &:= -9 \times 8 - (7+6 \times 5) \times (4 - (3+2+1)!) \\ 26562 &:= (-9-8+7! - 6! + 5! + 4) \times (3+2+1) \\ 26564 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7+6 \times 5) \times (-4 + (3+2+1)!) \\ 26584 &:= (9 \times (-8+7+6!) - 5) \times 4 + (3+2+1)! \\ 26602 &:= -9 + 8 + (7+6 \times 5) \times (-4+3+(2+1)!) \\ 26606 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + (6+5) \times (4 \times 3!! - 2 - 1) \\ 26662 &:= (9+8) \times ((7+6) \times 5! + 4! / 3) + (2+1)! \\ 26664 &:= (9+8) \times (7+6) \times 5! + 4! \times (3+2+1) \\ 26716 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7+6 \times 5) \times (4 + (3+2+1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26723 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + (4!+3!) \times (2+1)!! \\ 26728 &:= (9+8+7! - 6!) \times 5 + (4+3)! + 2 + 1 \\ 26734 &:= -9 - 8 + (-7 + (6+5) \times 4) \times (3 + (2+1)!) \\ 26764 &:= -9 + 8! + (-7+6!) \times (5-4 \times (3+2+1)) \\ 26771 &:= -9 - 8 + (7+6 \times 5) \times (4 + (3+2+1)!) \\ 26772 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7!) / 6 + 5 \times (4+3)! + (2+1)!! \\ 26798 &:= (9+8) \times (7+6) \times (5!+4-3!) + (2+1)!! \\ 26799 &:= -9 + (8+7!) \times 6 + 5 \times (4! - (3+2+1)!) \\ 26818 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7! / 6 - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 26822 &:= 9 \times (-8-7+6!) + 5 \times 4^{3!} - 2 - 1 \\ 26834 &:= -9 + 8! - (7+6 \times 5 + (4!/3)!) / (2+1) \\ 26836 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! \times 5 + 4 + 3!! / (2+1)) \\ 26840 &:= (9+8-7) \times (6+5) \times (4+3!! / (2+1)) \\ 26841 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! \times 6 / (5+4) - 3) - (2+1)! \\ 26941 &:= -9 + (8+7!+6) \times 5 + (4+3)! / (2+1) \\ 26947 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + (5!/4)^3 + (2+1)! \\ 26948 &:= (9 \times (8!/7!+6!) + 5) \times 4 + (3+2+1)! \\ 26966 &:= -9 + (8-7-6) \times 5 + (4!+3!)^{2+1} \\ 27122 &:= -(9+8) \times 7 + 6! \times (-5+4!) \times 3! / (2+1) \\ 27481 &:= (9+8 \times 7+6!) \times 5 \times (4+3) + (2+1)! \\ 27598 &:= (9-8+7 \times 6) \times 5^4 + 3 + (2+1)!! \\ 27628 &:= (9+8) \times (7+6) \times (5!/4!)^3 + 2 + 1 \\ 27662 &:= -9 + 8! - 7 + 6 - (5!+4^{3!}) \times (2+1) \\ 27668 &:= (-9+8 \times 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4) - (3+2+1)! \\ 27688 &:= (-9+8-7) \times (6! + 5 - 4^{3!}) + (2+1)!! \\ 27715 &:= (9+8 \times 7) \times (6+5) + (4!+3!)^{2+1} \\ 27731 &:= (-9+8 \times (-7+6!)) \times 5 - 4! - (3+2+1)! \\ 27770 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6+5! - 4^{3!}) - 2 - 1 \\ 27778 &:= (-9-8!/7!) \times (6 + (5! - (4+3)!)) / (2+1) \\ 27779 &:= (-9-8 \times (7-6!)) \times 5 + 4! - (3+2+1)! \\ 27788 &:= (-9+8 \times (7+6!+5!)) \times 4 + (3+2+1)! \\ 27806 &:= (9+8) \times (7! - 6) / ((5+4)/3) - (2+1)!! \\ 27851 &:= -(9+8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5) \times 4! / 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 27868 &:= (9-8 \times 7) \times (-6!+5!+4+3) - 2 - 1 \\ 27869 &:= (9+8 \times (-7+6!)) \times 5 + 4! - (3+2+1)! \\ 27878 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5!+4!^3) / (2+1) \\ 28012 &:= (-9+8 \times 7) \times (6! - 5! - 4! / (3+2+1)) \\ 28102 &:= (9+8!/7-6) \times 5 + 4 + 3 - (2+1)!! \\ 28276 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! - 6^5 / 4!) \times 3! - 2 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28291 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!)) \times 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 28292 &:= -9 + 8! + 7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 \times 3)^{2+1}) \\
 28298 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! - 6^5/4!) \times 3! + 2 + 1 \\
 28318 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! \times 4 - 3!/(2 + 1) \\
 28324 &:= (9 + 8 + 7)/6 + 5! \times (-4 + 3!/(2 + 1)) \\
 28325 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 28335 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! - 6^5/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28337 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
 28346 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!) + (6^5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 28379 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (-5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!) \\
 28408 &:= -9 + (-8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
 28410 &:= (9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6!) + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 28411 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4^3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
 28426 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6^5 + 4!) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 28427 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
 28429 &:= (9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!)) \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 28436 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 28451 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (-7 + 6!)) \times 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28508 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
 28532 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 28604 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!) \times 6 + 5 - (4 + 3)!/(2 + 1) \\
 28722 &:= (-9 + 8!/(7 \times 6) \times 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28724 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28768 &:= (9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! \times 5 - 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 28786 &:= ((9 + 8 - 7) \times 6! - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 28787 &:= (9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)) \times 5 - 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 28823 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28834 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! \times 5) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
 28841 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 28843 &:= (9 + 8!/(7!/6!)) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 28851 &:= (9 + 8!/7) \times (6 - 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 28852 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28867 &:= (9 + 8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 28869 &:= (9 + 8!/(7!/6!)) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28870 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 28878 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times 6 - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 28902 &:= (9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28940 &:= (9 + 8 - 7) \times ((6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 28941 &:= -9 + (8!/(7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28946 &:= (9 - 8 - 7 \times 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3! - (2 + 1)!!) \\
 28948 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 - (5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)! \\
 28957 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
 28958 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 \times (5!/4 - 3!)) + 2 + 1 \\
 28964 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 28965 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28966 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! + 6) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
 28978 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!) \times 6 + 5 \times (4! - 3!)/(2 + 1) \\
 28982 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4^3! + 2 + 1 \\
 28984 &:= (9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! \times 5 + 4! - (3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
 28996 &:= (9 - 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5^4 \times 3!/(2 + 1) \\
 28997 &:= (9 + 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 29010 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 29074 &:= -9 + 8! + 7 + 6 - 5^4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
 29364 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)! \\
 29426 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 + 65) \times 4! + 3) - 2 + 1 \\
 29462 &:= -9 + (-8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 29530 &:= (9 - 8 + 7!) \times 6!/5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 29536 &:= (9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! \times 5 - 4 + 3!) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 29550 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 29723 &:= (9 + 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 29860 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3! \times (2 + 1)!!) \\
 29885 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 \times (6! - 5) - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.4. In our representations, the *fractional part* and *negative powers* are not considered. If we allow the representations with fractional parts and/or negative powers (see A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Velden [9]), then some of the above numbers can be replaced by *basic operations*.

• **Numbers Due to A.E. Bras and V.H.J. van der Velden [9]**

The following numbers only with basic operations sent by A.E. Bras [9], are not included in the **Complete List**

$$\begin{aligned} 20218 &:= (9 \times (87 + 6^5) - 4) / (3 + 2^{-1}) \\ 20228 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 - (3/2)^{-1}) \\ 20230 &:= (-98 \times 7 + 6) \times (5/4 - 32 + 1) \\ 20797 &:= (987 \times 6 + 5 \times 4) \times (3 + 2^{-1}) \\ 21082 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times (4^3 - 2^{-1}) \\ 21379 &:= (9/8 + 7 \times 6 + 5^4) \times 32 - 1 \\ 21434 &:= -(9 + (8 - 7 \times 6 - 5 + 4)^3) / 2 + 1 \\ 21458 &:= (987 + 6 + 5) \times 43/2 + 1 \\ 21469 &:= (-987 + (6 + 5)^4 \times 3) / 2 + 1 \\ 21765 &:= (9 + 8 - 7 \times 6^5) / (-4 + 3/2) - 1 \\ 21782 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + 5)^4 \times 3/2 - 1 \\ 21821 &:= (9 / (8 + 7^6 + 54^3 / 2))^{-1} \\ 21822 &:= -9 + (-87 + (6 + 5)^4) \times 3/2 \times 1 \\ 22300 &:= 98 + (7 + 6 - 54 \times 3)^2 + 1 \\ 23117 &:= 9 + 8 \times (-76 \times (5 - 43) + 2^{-1}) \\ 23728 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times ((6 \times 5/4)^3 + 2 \times 1) \\ 23756 &:= (9 + (8 + 76 \times 5^4) - 3) / 2 - 1 \\ 24131 &:= 9 - 8 + 76 \times 5 \times (4^3 - 2^{-1}) \\ 24142 &:= 9 \times (87 + (6^5 + 4) / 3 + 2) + 1 \\ 24155 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (7 + (654 + 3) / 2) - 1 \\ 24203 &:= -98 + 76 \times (-5/4 + 321) \\ 24204 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (7/6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 \times 21)) \\ 24260 &:= -98 + 76 \times (5/4^{-3} + 2^{-1}) \\ 24404 &:= -9 + 8 \times (((-7 + 65) / 4)^3 + 2 + 1) \\ 24754 &:= (9 + 8 + (7 + 6)^5) / (4 \times 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 24781 &:= 9 - 8 \times ((-7 - 65) \times 43 - 2^{-1}) \\ 24902 &:= (9 - 8 \times (7 + 6^5)) / (-4 + 3) / 2 + 1 \\ 24925 &:= ((9 \times 8 + 7) \times (6 + 5^4) + 3) / 2 - 1 \\ 24941 &:= -98 \times (7 - 65 \times 4 - 3/2)^1 \\ 25012 &:= (9 + (-8 + 7 + 6)^5 \times 4 - 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\ 25180 &:= (-9/8 + 7 \times 6) \times (5^4 - 3^2) + 1 \\ 25196 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7 + 6)^5) / 4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\ 25204 &:= (-9 + (8 - 7 + 6)^5 + 4) \times 3/2 + 1 \\ 25261 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6 + (-5 + 43)^2) - 1 \\ 25302 &:= -9 + ((8 + 7 - 6 \times 5)^4 - 3) / 2 \times 1 \\ 25310 &:= (((-9 + 8 + 76) / 5)^4 - 3) / 2 - 1 \\ 25322 &:= 987 + (6 - 54 \times 3)^2 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25363 &:= (-98 + 7) \times (6^5 / (4 - 32) - 1) \\ 25402 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (6 \times (54 + 3^{-2}) + 1) \\ 25573 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 / (5 + 4)) \times 321 \\ 25574 &:= (9 - 8/7) \times (6 + (54 + 3)^2) - 1 \\ 25576 &:= (9 \times 87 + 65/4) \times 32 \times 1 \\ 25636 &:= 9 + (8 / (7 \times ((6 + 5)^4 + 3) \times 2))^{-1} \\ 25934 &:= 98/7 + 6^5 \times (4 - (3/2)^{-1}) \\ 25979 &:= 9 + (8 + 7 + 6^5) \times (4 - (3/2)^{-1}) \\ 26084 &:= 9 + 8 + (76 + 5^{4+3}) / (2 + 1) \\ 26564 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7/6) \times (5 \times 4^3 + 2) - 1 \\ 26602 &:= -987 \times (-6 \times 5 + 4^3 / 21) \\ 26606 &:= 98 \times (7 - 6) \times 543/2 - 1 \\ 26662 &:= (-9 + 8/7 \times ((6^5 + 4) \times 3 - 2) - 1) \\ 26664 &:= 9 \times (8 \times (-7 + 6^5) + 4^3) / 21 \\ 26728 &:= -9 + 87/6 \times (-5 + 43^2) - 1 \\ 26772 &:= -9 - 8 + 7654 \times (3 + 2^{-1}) \\ 26799 &:= -9 + 8/7 \times (6^5 + 43) \times (2 + 1) \\ 26841 &:= 9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6)^5 - 4 \times 321 \\ 26947 &:= (9 + 876 \times (-5/4 + 32)) + 1 \\ 27662 &:= 98/7 + 6^5 \times 4 \times (-3^{-2} + 1) \\ 27668 &:= (9/8 \times 765 + 4) \times 32 \times 1 \\ 27688 &:= -9 + (-8 + 76 \times (5 + 4)^3) / 2 - 1 \\ 27715 &:= -9 + 87 \times 6 \times (54 + 3^{-2} - 1) \\ 27778 &:= (9 + 8) \times 76 / (5 \times 4 + 3/2)^{-1} \\ 27779 &:= 9 - 8 + 76 \times ((5 + 4)^3 / 2 + 1) \\ 27851 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((76 + 5) \times 43 - 2^{-1}) \\ 27869 &:= 9 + 8 \times ((76 + 5) \times 43 - 2^{-1}) \\ 27878 &:= 9 - 87 \times (6 / (5 + 4) - 321) \\ 28012 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7)^6 \times 5 + 4 + 3) / 21 \\ 28102 &:= 9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6)^5 - 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ 28291 &:= (987 \times (6 \times 5 - 4/3) - 2) - 1 \\ 28292 &:= -987 \times (-6 \times 5 + 4/3) - 2/1 \\ 28324 &:= -9 + 87 \times (6 \times (54 + 3^{-2}) + 1) \\ 28325 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 - (((-6 - 5) \times 4)^3)) / (2 + 1) \\ 28379 &:= (9 - 8 \times 7 + ((6 + 5) \times 4)^3) / (2 + 1) \\ 28410 &:= 9 \times ((-8 + 7 + 6)^5 - 4) + 321 \\ 28427 &:= (-9 + (-8 + (7 + 6 - 5)^4) / 3) \times 21 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28451 &:= (9 + 87 \times 654 - 3)/2 - 1 & 29426 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7^6 - 5)/4 + 3^2 - 1 \\
 28722 &:= 9 \times ((-8 + 7 + 6)^5 + 4^3) + 21 & 29462 &:= (98 + 7^6 + 5)/4 + 3 + 21 \\
 28851 &:= (9 + 87 \times 6) \times (54 + 3^{-2+1}) & 29530 &:= 9 + ((8 + 7 - 6)^5 - 4 - 3)/2 \times 1 \\
 28946 &:= (98 \times 76 - 5) \times (4 - 3^{-2}) + 1 & 29536 &:= 9 + ((8 + 7 - 6)^5 + 4 + 3)/2 - 1 \\
 28966 &:= (9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4) \times (3 + 2^{-1}) & 29723 &:= (98 \times 7 \times 65 - 4)/3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 28982 &:= 9 \times (87 \times (6/(5 \times 4))^{-3} - 2 \times 1) & 29860 &:= (9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5^4 - 3) + 2^{-1}) \\
 28997 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6/(5 \times 4))^{-3} - 2 - 1 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Complete List

The numbers below are the representations in terms of 1 to 9 using basic operations. The numbers given in above subsection using **factorial** are written again to complete the list. There are total 10000 numbers from 20001 to 30000.

$$\begin{aligned}
 20001 &:= -((123 + ((-4 \times (567 - 8)) \times 9))) & 20001 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 20002 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9))) & 20002 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 - 1 \\
 20003 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9)) & 20003 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 \times 1 \\
 20004 &:= (-12 + (((((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7) - 8) \times 9)) & 20004 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 + 1 \\
 20005 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 20005 &:= ((((((((-9 + 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -5)^4 + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 20006 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (3 \times (-4 - (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 20006 &:= ((-9 \times ((87 + 654) \times -3)) - (2 - (1))) \\
 20007 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^{4+5})) + (((6 \times 7) \times -8) + 9))) & 20007 &:= 9 \times (87 + 654) \times 3 \times (2 - 1) \\
 20008 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)^4 \times (5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 & 20008 &:= ((-9 \times ((87 + 654) \times -3)) + (2 - (1))) \\
 20009 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3)^4 \times (5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 & 20009 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times ((5 \times 4)^3))/2)) \times -1) \\
 20010 &:= 1 + (2 + 3)^4 \times (5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 & 20010 &:= ((-9 \times ((87 + 654) \times -3)) + (2 + (1))) \\
 20011 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 20011 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20012 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 20012 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6))/5)^4 - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 20013 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((345 - 67) \times 8) \times 9)) & 20013 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^3) - 2 - 1 \\
 20014 &:= -((-1 \times (-2 - ((345 - 67) \times (8 \times -9)))) & 20014 &:= 9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 - 1 \\
 20015 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 20015 &:= 9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 \times 1 \\
 20016 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (((3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 20016 &:= 9 + (8 - 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 + 1 \\
 20017 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times ((5 + 6) - 7))) \times -8) + 9) & 20017 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^3) + 2 - 1 \\
 20018 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7) - 8) \times 9)) & 20018 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^3) + 2 \times 1 \\
 20019 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((345 - 67) \times (8 \times 9))) & 20019 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^3) + 2 + 1 \\
 20020 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 20020 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 + 5) \times (4 \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
 20021 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - ((6 \times 78) - 9)) & 20021 &:= (((((98/7) + 6) - ((5^4) \times -32)) - (-1)) \\
 20022 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 20022 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times ((5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)) + 1))) \\
 20023 &:= -1 - 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 \times 67 \times 8 \times 9 & 20023 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
 20024 &:= -1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 \times 67 \times 8 \times 9 & 20024 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + (7 \times 6))/5)^4 + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 20025 &:= 1 - 2^{3 \times 4} + 5 \times 67 \times 8 \times 9 & 20025 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times 7) - ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 20026 &:= ((1 + ((-2^3) + 45)) \times -((67 \times -8) - 9)) & 20026 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times 54) - (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 20027 &:= (1 - ((23 - 4) \times ((5 - 67) \times (8 + 9)))) & 20027 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 + (54 \times 3))) + 2)) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20028 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) - (6 - (-78) \times 9)) \\ 20029 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 20030 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 20031 &:= (-((1 - (2 - 34))) \times (((5 + 6) \times -7) \times 8) + 9) \\ 20032 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times - (56 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 20033 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7)) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 20034 &:= (1 \times (-2 \times ((3 \times (-4 + (5 \times (67 + 8)))) \times -9))) \\ 20035 &:= (1 + (-2 \times ((3 \times (-4 + (5 \times (67 + 8)))) \times -9))) \\ 20036 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 - 45) \times ((6 \times 78) + 9))) \\ 20037 &:= (-(((1 - ((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times 6)) \times 78)) - 9) \\ 20038 &:= ((1 - 234) \times -((5 + (-6 + ((78 + 9)))))) \\ 20039 &:= (-1 \times (((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\ 20040 &:= (-12 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8) + 9)) \\ 20041 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)^4) \times (5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 20042 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (((34 \times 5) \times (67 - 8)) - 9)) \\ 20043 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 + 7)))) - 8) \times 9) \\ 20044 &:= (1 - ((23 + (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 20045 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) \\ 20046 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 + (5 \times -((678 - 9)))))) \\ 20047 &:= (1 + (2 \times -((3 \times (4 + (5 \times -((678 - 9))))))) \\ 20048 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)))) - 9) \\ 20049 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)))) \\ 20050 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)))) \\ 20051 &:= -1 + (-2^3 + 4 \times (567 - 8)) \times 9 \\ 20052 &:= 1 \times (-2^3 + 4 \times (567 - 8)) \times 9 \\ 20053 &:= 1 + (-2^3 + 4 \times (567 - 8)) \times 9 \\ 20054 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)))) \\ 20055 &:= (-(((1 - ((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times 6)) \times 78)) + 9) \\ 20056 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 20057 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) \\ 20058 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times - (3 + (((4^5) + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 20059 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))))) \\ 20060 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))))) \\ 20061 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times 9) \\ 20062 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((34 + (5^6))/7) - 8) \times 9) \\ 20063 &:= ((((-12 - (3^4) \times 5) \times 6) - 7) \times -8) - 9 \\ 20064 &:= (((1 \times 23) - 4) \times ((-5 - 6) \times (-7 - 89))) \\ 20065 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) \\ 20066 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 20067 &:= (-12 \times ((3 + 4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20028 &:= (((9 \times (87 + 654)) \times 3) + 21)) \\ 20029 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 20030 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20031 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times (((4^3)/2) + 1)) \\ 20032 &:= (((-98 \times 7) + (6 + 54)) \times ((32 \times -1))) \\ 20033 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6^5)/(4 + 3) \times 2 - 1 \\ 20034 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6^5)/(4 + 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\ 20035 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6^5)/(4 + 3) \times 2 + 1 \\ 20036 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 20037 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1)) \\ 20038 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) - 2)))) - 1) \\ 20039 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) - 2 \times 1)))) \\ 20040 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5 - ((4 \times 3)^2))) - 1)) \\ 20041 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) + ((5^4) \times (32 \times 1))) \\ 20042 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 \times (6 + ((5^4) + 3))))/2)) - 1) \\ 20043 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 - 3) - 2 - 1 \\ 20044 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 - 3) - 2 \times 1 \\ 20045 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 - 3) - 2 + 1 \\ 20046 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5^4/3 \times 2) - 1 \\ 20047 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 - 3) + 2 - 1 \\ 20048 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 - 3) + 2 \times 1 \\ 20049 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 - 3) + 2 + 1 \\ 20050 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 20051 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (-76 + ((-5 \times 432)))) + (-1)) \\ 20052 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 20053 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (-76 + ((-5 \times 432)))) - (-1)) \\ 20054 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 20055 &:= ((987 + (6 + (5 - 43))) \times 21) \\ 20056 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - 654) \times (32 + (-1)))) \\ 20057 &:= (98 - 76 + 5^4) \times (32 - 1) \\ 20058 &:= (((9 + (8 \times 7)) - ((6 - ((5^4) \times 32)) + 1))) \\ 20059 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))/2) - 1) \\ 20060 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))/2) \times 1) \\ 20061 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) - 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 20062 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 - (7 - 6))) + ((5^4) \times 32)) - 1) \\ 20063 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((76 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) - 2)) + 1))) \\ 20064 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5^4/3 \times 2) - 1 \\ 20065 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5^4/3 \times 2) \times 1 \\ 20066 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5^4/3 \times 2) + 1 \\ 20067 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20068 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (34 \times (5 \times (67 - 8)))) + 9)) \\
 20069 &:= (((-1 \times (2 \times (34 \times 5)))) \times (67 - 8) + 9) \\
 20070 &:= (((1 + (-2 + 3)) + 4) \times (5 \times (678 - 9))) \\
 20071 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20072 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20073 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3)^{4+5} + 6 \times (7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 20074 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20075 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20076 &:= (-12 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (78 - 9))))) \\
 20077 &:= ((((-1 + 23) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 20078 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 20079 &:= ((1 + (234 + 56)) \times (-(-78) - 9)) \\
 20080 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - (4 \times (567 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 20081 &:= (((12 \times 34) \times (56 - 7)) + 89) \\
 20082 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3! + (-4 + 5! + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 20083 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -(4 \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 20084 &:= (-1 + (((234 + 5) \times (6 + 78)) + 9)) \\
 20085 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20086 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8 + 9)) \\
 20087 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 20088 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4 + (5 + (6 + 78)))) \times 9) \\
 20089 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 \times (7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 20090 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 \times (7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 20091 &:= 1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 \times (7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 20092 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! \times 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 20093 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 \times (678 - 9))))) \\
 20094 &:= (12 + 3) \times 4^5 + 6 \times 789 \\
 20095 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) - ((-3^{4+5}) - (6 \times (78 - 9)))) \\
 20096 &:= ((12^3) + (4 \times (56 \times (-7 + (89))))) \\
 20097 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (-((4 \times 567) + 8)) \times -9) \\
 20098 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (78 - 9)))) \\
 20099 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (78 - 9)))) \\
 20100 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times -(5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9))))) \\
 20101 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -(4 \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 20102 &:= ((1 - 23) + (4 \times ((567 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 20103 &:= 12 + (34 - 5) \times 6! - 789 \\
 20104 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!) \times (4 + (5! / (6 + 7 + 8 + 9))) \\
 20105 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 20106 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 20107 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 89)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20068 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 20069 &:= (98 - (((-7 + (6 \times 54)) \times -((3 \times 21)))) \\
 20070 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 20071 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 20072 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4) \times (32 \times 1)) \\
 20073 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
 20074 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 - 6)) + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1)) \\
 20075 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 76)) + ((5^4) \times (32 \times 1))) \\
 20076 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 76)) + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1)) \\
 20077 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) \times 4) \times (3^{2+1}))) \\
 20078 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (54 \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 20079 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 20080 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 - 1 \\
 20081 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 \times 1 \\
 20082 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 + 1 \\
 20083 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) / -6) + ((5^4) \times 32)) - 1) \\
 20084 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + (7 + 6)) + ((5^4) \times 32)) - 1) \\
 20085 &:= ((98 + (-7 - 6)) - (((5^4) \times 32) \times -1)) \\
 20086 &:= ((98 + (-7 - 6)) + (((5^4) \times 32) + 1)) \\
 20087 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times -(((5 + 4) - 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 20088 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) - 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 20089 &:= -(9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 20090 &:= -(9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1 \\
 20091 &:= -(9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20092 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (65 \times ((43 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 20093 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times (5^4)) / 3)))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 20094 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) - (((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) - 1))) \\
 20095 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 20096 &:= ((-9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 20097 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (((5 + 4) - 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 20098 &:= 9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 - 1 \\
 20099 &:= 9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 \times 1 \\
 20100 &:= 9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 + 1 \\
 20101 &:= ((-98 + 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 \times 1))) \\
 20102 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6 \times (5^4)) / 3)) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 20103 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6 \times (5^4)) / 3)) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
 20104 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + ((6 \times (5^4)) / 3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 20105 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((76 \times (5 - (4^3))) / 2))) - 1) \\
 20106 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (((7 + 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 20107 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((76 \times (5 - (4^3))) / 2))) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20108 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 89)))) \\ 20109 &:= (12 + ((3^{4+5}) - (6 \times (-78) + 9))) \\ 20110 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times ((34 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 20111 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 20112 &:= (-12 \times -(3 + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8) + 9))) \\ 20113 &:= 12^{-3-4+5+6} - 7 \times 89 \\ 20114 &:= (-1 - (((((2 + 34) - (5^6))/7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 20115 &:= ((-1 - (((23 \times 4) + 56))) \times ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\ 20116 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) - (4 \times ((567 - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20117 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -(4 \times (5 \times 67))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 20118 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (34 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 20119 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) - (3 - (-4 \times -(((567 - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20120 &:= ((1 - 2) + (-3 + (-4 \times -((567 - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20121 &:= ((-12 + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20122 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) + (4 \times ((567 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 20123 &:= (((1 \times 2) - 3) + ((4 \times -((567 - 8))) \times -9)) \\ 20124 &:= (((-((1 \times 2))^3) + 4) \times -((567 - 8) \times 9)) \\ 20125 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 \times 5))) \times -(6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20126 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + (4 \times ((567 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 20127 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20128 &:= ((-((1 \times 23)) - (4 + 5)) \times (-6 + (7 \times -(89)))) \\ 20129 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (34 \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 20130 &:= ((1 + 2) - (-3 - (-4 \times -((567 - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20131 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times -3))) - ((-4 \times -((567 - 8))) \times -9)) \\ 20132 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) - (-4 \times ((567 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 20133 &:= (-(((1 \times (2 + 34)) \times (567 - 8))) + 9) \\ 20134 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20135 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20136 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\ 20137 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times (34 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 20138 &:= (1 - ((2 \times (34 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 20139 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 20140 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 20141 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7) + 8)) \times 9) \\ 20142 &:= (((1 - 23) + ((4 \times 567) - 8)) \times 9) \\ 20143 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times -8) - 9) \\ 20144 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((45 + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20145 &:= (((1234 - 56) + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 20146 &:= ((-1 + 23) - ((4 \times (567 - 8)) \times -9)) \\ 20147 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + (4 \times ((567 - 8) \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20108 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -(6 + (5 \times 43))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 20109 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) \times 21)) \\ 20110 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 20111 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 20112 &:= -(((((-9 - 8) - 7) \times ((-65 - ((-43 \times 21)))))) \\ 20113 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - (76 \times 5))) + 4) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 20114 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times ((4 + 3) - 2))) - 1) \\ 20115 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (5 \times (4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\ 20116 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3)/(2 \times 1)) \\ 20117 &:= (((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3)/2) + 1) \\ 20118 &:= -(((((-98 - ((-7 \times (6 \times 54)) \times 3)) \times ((-2 - 1)))) \\ 20119 &:= (((9 + 8) - 76) \times ((-5 \times 4) + (-321))) \\ 20120 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 - 5^4) \times (3 \times 2 - 1) \\ 20121 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 20122 &:= (9 + ((8 \times ((7 + ((6 \times (5^4))/3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 20123 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times 4) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\ 20124 &:= ((-98 + (7 - 65)) \times ((-43 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 20125 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + 5) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 20126 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + (((6^5)/4) \times ((3^2) + 1))) \\ 20127 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 20128 &:= (((9 + 8) \times ((-7 - 6) - ((54 + 3) \times 21))) \\ 20129 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))/ - 2) + 1) \\ 20130 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 20131 &:= (-((9 \times (-8 - 76))) + (((5^4) \times (32 - 1)))) \\ 20132 &:= (-((98/7) \times (6 - ((5 - 43)^2 \times 1))) \\ 20133 &:= (-9 \times (-8 - (((76 \times 5) + (43^2)) \times (1)))) \\ 20134 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 20135 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20136 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 20137 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 + 1))) \\ 20138 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2) - 1) \\ 20139 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 20140 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20141 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 - 1))) \\ 20142 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 20143 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) - (2 - 1))) \\ 20144 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((65 \times 4) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 20145 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times ((6 - 5) - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 20146 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((65 \times 4) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 20147 &:= (((98 \times (-7 \times 6)) \times -5) - (432 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20148 &:= ((-((1-23)) - (45 \times -6)) \times (78 - 9)) \\ 20149 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9)) \\ 20150 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9 \\ 20151 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((3 \times 4) \times -5) \times ((6 \times 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 20152 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\ 20153 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 20154 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6 \times (7 + 8 \times 9) \\ 20155 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6 \times (7 + 8 \times 9) \\ 20156 &:= -1^2 + 3^{4+5} + 6 \times (7 + 8 \times 9) \\ 20157 &:= 1^2 \times 3^{4+5} + 6 \times (7 + 8 \times 9) \\ 20158 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20159 &:= (((1 + 23) \times ((4 \times 5) \times (6 \times 7))) - (-8 + 9)) \\ 20160 &:= ((1 + (2 \times -3)) \times (-4 \times ((56 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 20161 &:= (((1 + 23) \times ((4 \times 5) \times (6 \times 7))) + (-8 + 9)) \\ 20162 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7) + 8) \times 9) \\ 20163 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 20164 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 20165 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (34 + 5)) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 20166 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9) \\ 20167 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9)) \\ 20168 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3 \times 4) \times -5) \times ((6 \times 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 20169 &:= (((1 \times 2345) - ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times -(-9)) \\ 20170 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9) \\ 20171 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9)) \\ 20172 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 20173 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 20174 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 20175 &:= -((1 - 2) \times ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times -((7 - 89)))) \\ 20176 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 \times (7 - 89))) \\ 20177 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 20178 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20179 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20180 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20181 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^{4+5}) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20182 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^{4+5} - 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\ 20183 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3^{4+5} - 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\ 20184 &:= 1 + 2 + 3^{4+5} - 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\ 20185 &:= (1 + (-((2 - ((34 + 5) \times 6))) \times (78 + 9))) \\ 20186 &:= (-1 + ((((((2 + 3) \times 4) + (5^6))/7) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 20187 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 + 7))) + 8)) \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20148 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 20149 &:= (((((98 \times (7 \times 6)) \times 5) - 432) + (1)) \\ 20150 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 20151 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 20152 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 - 1)) \\ 20153 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 20154 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 20155 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times 6) + 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 20156 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times 5) + 4^3)/(2 \times 1))) \\ 20157 &:= (((9 - 87) \times 6) + ((5^4) \times -((-32 - (1)))) \\ 20158 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 20159 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 20160 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 20161 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 20162 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 20163 &:= (98 + 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3)^2 - 1 \\ 20164 &:= (98 + 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3)^2 \times 1 \\ 20165 &:= (98 + 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3)^2 + 1 \\ 20166 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) + 2))) - 1) \\ 20167 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 20168 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) + 2)) + 1)) \\ 20169 &:= ((9 \times (((8 + 76) - 5) + 4)) \times (3^{2+1})) \\ 20170 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times ((6 \times 54) - (3 + 2)))))) + 1) \\ 20171 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + 2)) \times -1) \\ 20172 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + 21)) \\ 20173 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 - (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 20174 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20175 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 20176 &:= (((-9 - (87 \times 6)) \times (5 - 43)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 20177 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1) \\ 20178 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 20179 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + (6 + 5)) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\ 20180 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4)) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 20181 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) - 6) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\ 20182 &:= -9 + (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5^4 \times 32 + 1 \\ 20183 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 20184 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))))) \times -3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 20185 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^2)) + 1) \\ 20186 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))/2))) - 1) \\ 20187 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20188 &:= -1 + 2 + (3^{-4+5+6} + 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\
 20189 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3^{-4+5+6} + 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\
 20190 &:= 1 + 2 + (3^{-4+5+6} + 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\
 20191 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\
 20192 &:= 1 - 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\
 20193 &:= (((-1 + ((-2 - 3) \times (4 - 56))) \times 78) - 9) \\
 20194 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\
 20195 &:= -1 + (2^3 + 4 \times (567 - 8)) \times 9 \\
 20196 &:= 1 \times (2^3 + 4 \times (567 - 8)) \times 9 \\
 20197 &:= 1 + (2^3 + 4 \times (567 - 8)) \times 9 \\
 20198 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 \times (-7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 20199 &:= 1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 \times (-7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 20200 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times ((5 - 6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20201 &:= (((-1 - 234) \times -((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 20202 &:= ((-12 + (3^{4+5})) + ((67 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 20203 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 20204 &:= 1 - 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6 \times (78 + 9) \\
 20205 &:= ((12 + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) - (7 \times (-(-8) \times -9))) \\
 20206 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6 \times (78 + 9) \\
 20207 &:= -((((1 + 2) - (3^{4+5})) - ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 20208 &:= (-12 \times -(((3^{4+5+6}) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 20209 &:= (((-1^2) - (-3^{4+5})) - ((67 \times -8) + 9)) \\
 20210 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^{4+5}) + ((67 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 20211 &:= (((-1 + ((-2 - 3) \times (4 - 56))) \times 78) + 9) \\
 20212 &:= (-1 \times ((-2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (67 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 20213 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((67 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 20214 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (3 \times (((4 + 56) \times 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 20215 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times (45 - 6))) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 20216 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^{4+5}) + ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 20217 &:= (-1 \times -((23 + (45 \times 6)) \times (78 - 9))) \\
 20218 &:= (1 + ((23 + (45 \times 6)) \times (78 - 9))) \\
 20219 &:= (((-1 - 234) \times -((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\
 20220 &:= -((12 - (3 \times (-45) + 6789))) \\
 20221 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 + (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) \\
 20222 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (((34 + (5^6))/7) + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20223 &:= (-((-1 - 2)) \times -((3 + 45) + 6789)) \\
 20224 &:= (((-((1 - 2) + 3)^4) \times (-5 + (67 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20225 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times 5))) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 20226 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (45 \times 6))) \times (7 + 8)) - 9) \\
 20227 &:= ((-1 \times 23) + (45 \times (((6 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20188 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3))/2))) + 1) \\
 20189 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 20190 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 20191 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4)) + (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 20192 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
 20193 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 \times 7)) + 6) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
 20194 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4)) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 20195 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (654 \times ((32 - 1)))) \\
 20196 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 20197 &:= -(-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 20198 &:= -(-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1 \\
 20199 &:= -(-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20200 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 - 5)) \times 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 20201 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2))) - 1) \\
 20202 &:= ((-98 + 7) \times -(6 + (((5 + 4) - 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 20203 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20204 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5) \times (43^2 \times 1))) \\
 20205 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 20206 &:= ((-98 / -7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 \times 1))) \\
 20207 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 - 1)))) \\
 20208 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^2) + 1)) \\
 20209 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + 7) + (654 \times ((32 - 1)))) \\
 20210 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times (5 \times 43)) / (2 + 1))) \\
 20211 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (((76 - 5) \times 4) - 3))) - 21) \\
 20212 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 + 5)) \times -(43 - 2)) - 1) \\
 20213 &:= (((-((-98 \times 7)) + 6) + 5) \times ((-4 + 32) + (1))) \\
 20214 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) + 4) \times -(3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 20215 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 + (5 \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 20216 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - ((5^4) + 3))) / 2) + 1) \\
 20217 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4)) - (3 \times 21)) \\
 20218 &:= (9 + 8! - 7 - 6 + 5!) / (-4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 20219 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (43^2))) - 1) \\
 20220 &:= (((-9 + 87) + ((6^5) / 4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 20221 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6 + 5) \times (43^2)) + 1)) \\
 20222 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 65) - 4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 20223 &:= -(((((-98 + ((7 \times (6 + (-5 + 4)))) \times 321)) \\
 20224 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3+2-1})) \\
 20225 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 - 54) / -3)^2)) + 1) \\
 20226 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 \times (43 + 2))) - 1))) \\
 20227 &:= (-(-9) + (-(((8 \times 7) + (-654 \times (32 - 1))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20228 &:= ((-((1 \times (2 - (345)))) \times (67 - 8)) - 9) \\
 20229 &:= ((-1 - (-2 - ((3^{4+5}) + (67 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 20230 &:= ((-((1 - 234) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) - (-8 \times 9))) \\
 20231 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9) \\
 20232 &:= 12^3/4 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) - 8 \times 9 \\
 20233 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 + 45) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 20234 &:= (-1 + ((-2 - 3) \times (((4 - 56) \times 78) + 9))) \\
 20235 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 20236 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 345) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20237 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - 345) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20238 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 20239 &:= ((-((123 - 4) \times 5) \times ((-6 \times 7) + 8)) + 9) \\
 20240 &:= (-(((12 - 34) \times 5) \times (6 - (7 - 89))) \\
 20241 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9) \\
 20242 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 20243 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 20244 &:= (12 + (3 \times (-45) + 6789)) \\
 20245 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 + 45 \times (6 \times 7 + 8) \times 9 \\
 20246 &:= ((-12/3) - (45 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 20247 &:= (123 - ((-4 \times (567 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20248 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) - (45 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 20249 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))))) \\
 20250 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))))) \\
 20251 &:= (((12 \times -3) \times (4 - 567)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 20252 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 20253 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((67 - 8) - 9)))) \\
 20254 &:= (1 \times 23 - 45 \times 6) \times (7 - 89) \\
 20255 &:= 1 + (23 - 45 \times 6) \times (7 - 89) \\
 20256 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 20257 &:= -1 + 2^3 + 45 \times (6 \times 7 + 8) \times 9 \\
 20258 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 20259 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 20260 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 20261 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 20262 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 20263 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 20264 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 20265 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) - (((-6 \times 7) \times 8) + 9))) \\
 20266 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20228 &:= (9 + 8 + 7!) \times (-6!/5! + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 20229 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 20230 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 + 5!) \times (4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 20231 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 20232 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 20233 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) \times 4)/3) \times 2 + 1) \\
 20234 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3)))/2) + 1) \\
 20235 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3)))/(2 \times 1))) \\
 20236 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3)))/2) - 1) \\
 20237 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\
 20238 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 20239 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 20240 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2) - 1) \\
 20241 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + 6)) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
 20242 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (43 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 20243 &:= (((-98/7) \times ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 20244 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 - 1))) \\
 20245 &:= (((-98/7) \times ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 20246 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (((7 - 6) \times 5^4)) \times 32)) - 1) \\
 20247 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 20248 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 20249 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 20250 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (7 + 6)) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 20251 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 20252 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 20253 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 20254 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 20255 &:= ((-98 \times (7 \times (6 \times -5))) - ((4 + 321))) \\
 20256 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 20257 &:= (-(((9 + 87) \times ((6 - (5 \times 43)) - 2))) - (-1)) \\
 20258 &:= ((98 + (((7 \times 6) \times (5 \times 4)) \times (3 + 21)))) \\
 20259 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20260 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2) + 1) \\
 20261 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 20262 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 20263 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2)) + 1) \\
 20264 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20265 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times -(4 \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 20266 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (-7 + (654 \times (32 - 1))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20267 &:= ((12 \times -3) \times (4 - 567)) + (8 - 9) \\
 20268 &:= (((1 - 2) - 3) \times (-4 - ((567 - 8)))) \times 9 \\
 20269 &:= (1 + ((-2 - 34) \times (-5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times -9)))) \\
 20270 &:= (-1 - (((234 + 5) + (-6)) \times -((78 + 9)))) \\
 20271 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 \times (4 \times (((5 \times 6) \times 7) \times 8) + 9))) \\
 20272 &:= ((-1 + 23) - (45 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 20273 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 20274 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 20275 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) \times 5))) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 20276 &:= (-1 - ((23 + 4) \times (5 - ((6 + 78) \times 9)))) \\
 20277 &:= (-(((1 \times (23 - (4 \times 567))) - 8)) \times 9) \\
 20278 &:= (1 - ((23 + 4) \times (5 - ((6 + 78) \times 9)))) \\
 20279 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 - ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 20280 &:= -(((1 - (-2 - 3)) \times -((4 \times (-56) - 789)))) \\
 20281 &:= ((-1 + (-((2 + 3)^4) - 567)) \times (-8 - 9)) \\
 20282 &:= (1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 20283 &:= (((-12 - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9) \\
 20284 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 89)))) \\
 20285 &:= ((12 \times -3) \times (4 - 567)) + (8 + 9) \\
 20286 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20287 &:= 12^3/4 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 20288 &:= (-1 + (((((2 \times 3)^4) + 56) \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
 20289 &:= 12 + (3 - 45 \times (6 - 7 \times 8)) \times 9 \\
 20290 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) - 6)))) \times -((7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 20291 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20292 &:= -(((1 - 234) - (-((5 - 6) - 7)) \times 89)) \\
 20293 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - ((4 \times 56) + 7)) \times 89)) \\
 20294 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((45 \times (6 \times (7 + 8))) + 9))) \\
 20295 &:= -((-123) \times ((4 + (5 + 67)) + 89)) \\
 20296 &:= ((-1 + (2 - 345)) \times -((-6 - 7) + (8 \times -9))) \\
 20297 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 20298 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + ((4 \times 5) - (6789)))) \\
 20299 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 20300 &:= (-((12 - (3^{4+5}))) + 6) + (7 \times 89)) \\
 20301 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (6 - (7 \times 89))) \\
 20302 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (((3^{4+5}) - 6) + (7 \times 89))) \\
 20303 &:= 12^3/4 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 8 - 9 \\
 20304 &:= -(((1 - ((12 - 3)) - ((45 - 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 20305 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 4)) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\
 20306 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - 6789)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20267 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 20268 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 20269 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -((3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 20270 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 20271 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times -((4 \times 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 20272 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 - 6)) + 5) \times -((4 \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
 20273 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + 2)) - 1) \\
 20274 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 - ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 20275 &:= (((9 - 87) \times (-65 \times 4)) + (-3 - (2 \times (1)))) \\
 20276 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (-65 \times -4)) + (-3 - (2 - (1)))) \\
 20277 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (-65 \times -4)) + (-3 \times (2 - (1)))) \\
 20278 &:= ((((-9 + (87 \times (6 + (5 \times 4)))) \times (3^2)) + 1) \\
 20279 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times 65) \times -4) + (-3/(2 + (1)))) \\
 20280 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times 65) \times 4) \times (-3/(2 + (1)))) \\
 20281 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times 65) \times -4) - (-3/(2 + (1)))) \\
 20282 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 76)) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
 20283 &:= ((-98 \times -(((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4) \times 3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 20284 &:= ((987 - 65) \times (43 - 21)) \\
 20285 &:= (((9 - 87) \times (-65 \times 4)) - (-3 - (2 \times (1)))) \\
 20286 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) - 4) \times -((3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 20287 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - (7 - 6))) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1) \\
 20288 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (76 + 5)) \times -(((4 - 321)))) \\
 20289 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times (-65 \times -4)) - (-3 \times (2 + (1)))) \\
 20290 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
 20291 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + 5 \times 4^{3+2+1} \\
 20292 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\
 20293 &:= ((-98 + 7) \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 20294 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - ((7 \times 65) + 4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 20295 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 20296 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20297 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 20298 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 20299 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times 65)) \times -43) + (2 + 1)) \\
 20300 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 + (4 + 3))^2) + 1)) \\
 20301 &:= (-9 + ((87 + ((6^5)/4)) \times ((3^2) + 1))) \\
 20302 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((65 \times 4) - 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 20303 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 - 5) + (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
 20304 &:= (-9 \times (8 \times ((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 20305 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5^4) \times (32 - 1) \\
 20306 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((65 \times 4) - 3)) + (2 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20307 &:= (((1 \times -2) \times -3) \times (-4 - (5 \times -(678)))) - 9) \\ 20308 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - 3)^4) - (((5 \times (6 - 7))) - 8)^9) \\ 20309 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (-3 \times ((4 \times 5) - (6789)))) \\ 20310 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (-3 \times (4 + ((5 \times 678) - 9)))) \\ 20311 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - ((4 \times 567) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 20312 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) - (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\ 20313 &:= (((-1 + (2^3))^4) - ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 20314 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (-6 - ((7 \times 89)))) \\ 20315 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 - (4 \times 567)) + 8) \times -9)) \\ 20316 &:= (-1 + (-23 + (((4 \times 567) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 20317 &:= (-1 \times (23 - (((4 \times 567) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 20318 &:= ((1 - 23) + (((4 \times 567) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 20319 &:= (((1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - ((67 + 89))) \\ 20320 &:= 1 \times 2^{3!} + (4 + 5! + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 20321 &:= 12^3 / 4 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 20322 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - 3) + ((4 \times 567) - 8))) \times 9) \\ 20323 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^{4+5+6}) \times 7)) - 89) \\ 20324 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (((4 - 56) \times 78) - 9))) \\ 20325 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^{4+5+6}) \times 7) - 8) + 9) \\ 20326 &:= (1 - ((2 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 \times 678)))) - 9)) \\ 20327 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 20328 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -4 + ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 20329 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - 78) \times 9)) \\ 20330 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + (4 \times 567)) - 8) \times 9) \\ 20331 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -((3 + (4 + (5 - 6789)))))) \\ 20332 &:= -1 \times 2^3 + (4 \times 567 - 8) \times 9 \\ 20333 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 - 78) \times 9)) \\ 20334 &:= (((1 \times -2) \times -(-3)) + (((4 \times 567) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 20335 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 20336 &:= ((-1 - (2 - 34)) \times -((-567) - 89)) \\ 20337 &:= (((1^2) \times -3) + (((4 \times -(567)) + 8) \times -9)) \\ 20338 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 20339 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (3 - (((4 \times 567) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 20340 &:= ((1 - (2345 - (6 + 78))) \times -9) \\ 20341 &:= ((1^2) - (3 \times (4 + (5 - 6789)))) \\ 20342 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) - 6789)))) \\ 20343 &:= (((12 \times ((34 \times 5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 20344 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (-3 + (-((4 \times 567) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20345 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times (45 - 6))) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 20346 &:= ((-12 + (3^{4+5})) + ((67 + 8) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20307 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times 54)))) - (32 + (1))) \\ 20308 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6 - (5^4)) \times (32 + 1))) \\ 20309 &:= (-((-9 + (-8 - (76 \times -((54 - 321)))))) \\ 20310 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 20311 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times (6 \times 54)) - 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 20312 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 + (5 \times 4))) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 20313 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\ 20314 &:= (-98 + (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4))^{3-2+1})) \\ 20315 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6 + 5) \times 4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\ 20316 &:= (-((9 + 87)) + (((6 \times (54 \times 3)) \times 21))) \\ 20317 &:= ((-98 + (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times 32)) - 1) \\ 20318 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6 + 5) \times ((43^2) - 1))) \\ 20319 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 20320 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times 6) - 5) \times -((4^3) / (2 \times 1))) \\ 20321 &:= (((((-98 - 7) \times 6) - 5) \times -((4^3) / 2)) + 1) \\ 20322 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - (765 - 4)) \times 3) + ((2 - 1)))) \\ 20323 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3^{2+1})))) \\ 20324 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 \times 5))) - (4^{3+2-1})) \\ 20325 &:= (((-9 \times 87) - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 20326 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5) \times ((43^2) + 1))) \\ 20327 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 20328 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) - 4) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 20329 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) - 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 20330 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 + (5 \times 4))) - 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 20331 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 20332 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 + (5 \times 4))) - 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 20333 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) / 4) \times 3) / 2) - 1)) \\ 20334 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 20335 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times 6) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 20336 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times 6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20337 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times 6) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\ 20338 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 20339 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20340 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 20341 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2)))) + 1) \\ 20342 &:= ((-98 / 7) \times (6 - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 20343 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times 54)))) + (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 20344 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20345 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 20346 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20347 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + (((4 \times 567) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 20348 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (-345) \times (-67 + 8)) - 9) \\
 20349 &:= (((1 + 2) - ((34 - 5) \times -6)) \times -7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 20350 &:= ((-(1 + 2) - 34) \times (-5 - ((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 20351 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 20352 &:= (((1^2) \times 3)^{4+5}) + ((678 - 9)) \\
 20353 &:= (1 + (-((2 - 3) + 4)) \times (5 - 6789)) \\
 20354 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 20355 &:= ((12 + 3) \times (-((4 \times -((5 \times 67))) - 8) + 9)) \\
 20356 &:= ((1 \times -2) + (((34 + 5) \times 6) \times (78 + 9))) \\
 20357 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((67 + 8) \times -9)) \\
 20358 &:= (-12 - (3 \times (4 - (5 + 6789)))) \\
 20359 &:= ((-(1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((67 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 20360 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 20361 &:= (((12 \times ((34 \times 5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\
 20362 &:= (-1 - (-23 - (((4 \times 567) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 20363 &:= ((-1 \times -23) + (((4 \times 567) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 20364 &:= ((1 + 23) - (((4 \times 567) - 8) \times -9)) \\
 20365 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 \times 7 - 8 \times 9 \\
 20366 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 \times 7 - 8 \times 9 \\
 20367 &:= ((12 / ((3 - 4) + 5)) \times 6789) \\
 20368 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (-3 \times ((4 - 5) - 6789)) \\
 20369 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3 + (4 \times 567)) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 20370 &:= (((1^2) \times -3) \times (4 + (-5 - 6789))) \\
 20371 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((-3^{4+5}) - (678))) - (-9)) \\
 20372 &:= (((-(-1) \times 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (678))) + 9) \\
 20373 &:= -(((1 + 2) \times (-((3 + 4) + ((5 - 6789)))) \\
 20374 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 \times 678)))) + 9)) \\
 20375 &:= (((1 + (-2^3)) \times (((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 20376 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4)) \times (567 + (8 - 9))) \\
 20377 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times -(67 \times 8)) + 9) \\
 20378 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - (6 + (7 + 89))) \\
 20379 &:= (12 + (((3 + (4 \times 567)) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 20380 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
 20381 &:= (-((((((1 \times 2) - 34) - 5) \times -6) + 7)) \times -(89)) \\
 20382 &:= (12 - (3 \times (4 - (5 + 6789)))) \\
 20383 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4 + 5) \times 67)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 20384 &:= 1 - 2 + (3^{-4+5+6} + 78) \times 9 \\
 20385 &:= (-12 + ((3^{4+5}) - ((-6 \times 7) \times (-(-8) + 9)))) \\
 20386 &:= -1 + 2 + (3^{-4+5+6} + 78) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20347 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) \times 3)/2) + 1)) \\
 20348 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 + (5 \times 4))) - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\
 20349 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 20350 &:= (((9 + 8) \times (765 + 432)) - (-1)) \\
 20351 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((-7 \times 6) - 5) \times (-432 + (-1)))) \\
 20352 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 20353 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 20354 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) - 3 - 2 + 1 \\
 20355 &:= ((9 + 876) \times ((54 - 32) + (1))) \\
 20356 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20357 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 20358 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) + 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 20359 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) + 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 20360 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) + 3 - 2 + 1 \\
 20361 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 20362 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 - 1 \\
 20363 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 20364 &:= 9 \times 87 \times (6 \times 5 - 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 20365 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
 20366 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20367 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20368 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20369 &:= ((-98 - (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20370 &:= ((-98 - (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20371 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20372 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20373 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times 54)))) + (32 + (1))) \\
 20374 &:= ((-98 - (7 + 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20375 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 20376 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))/3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 20377 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4)/3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 20378 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 20379 &:= ((((-98/7) - 6) \times (5 - (4^{3+2}))) - 1) \\
 20380 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 20381 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20382 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times (5 - (((4 + 3)^2) - 1))) \\
 20383 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7^{6-5})^4) - 3)/(2 \times 1)) \\
 20384 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 76)) - (5 \times 4)) \times (32 \times -1))) \\
 20385 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 20386 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (((6 + 5) \times 4) + 3)^2)) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20387 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3^{-4+5+6} + 78) \times 9 \\ 20388 &:= 1 + 2 + (3^{-4+5+6} + 78) \times 9 \\ 20389 &:= (-1 + (((2^3)^4) \times 5) + (((6-7) - 89))) \\ 20390 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - ((6+7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 20391 &:= ((((-1-2) - (3^4) \times 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 20392 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - (6 + (78 + 9))) \\ 20393 &:= (((1 + (-2^3) \times ((4-56) \times 7) \times 8) + 9) \\ 20394 &:= ((-1-2) + ((3^{4+5} + (6 \times (7 \times (8+9)))))) \\ 20395 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^{4+5} + (6 \times (7 \times (8+9)))))) \\ 20396 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4} \times 5) - (67 + (8 + 9))) \\ 20397 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3)^{4+5} + (6 \times (7 \times (8+9)))) \\ 20398 &:= ((-1+2) + ((3^{4+5} + (6 \times (7 \times (8+9)))))) \\ 20399 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^{4+5} + (6 \times (7 \times (8+9)))))) \\ 20400 &:= ((1 + (234 + 5)) \times (6 + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20401 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times (((45 + 67) \times -8) + 9)) \\ 20402 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6-7) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 20403 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times -3) \times (((4 \times 567) + 8) - 9)) \\ 20404 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 - (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20405 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))))) \\ 20406 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 - 7 - 8 \times 9 \\ 20407 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4^{5-6+7}))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 20408 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times -(4^{5-6+7})) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 20409 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4} \times 5) - ((6-7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 20410 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5) - 6))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 20411 &:= (((-1 \times ((2 + 34) \times 567))) + 8) - 9) \\ 20412 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3^4) \times ((5 - (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 20413 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6-7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 20414 &:= (-(((1-2) - 345)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (-8 - 9))) \\ 20415 &:= (-12 + (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + 6789))) \\ 20416 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 20417 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4} \times 5) - ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20418 &:= (((-1 - 2) - 3) \times (-4 - ((5 \times 678) + 9))) \\ 20419 &:= 1 + ((2 - 3 + 4)^5 + 6) \times (-7 + 89) \\ 20420 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - 3) \times (4^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 20421 &:= ((-1 + (2345 - (67 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 20422 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20423 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4} + ((5^6) + (78 \times 9))) \\ 20424 &:= (12 - (3 \times (-((4 + 5) \times ((6 + 78) \times 9)))) \\ 20425 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) - ((3 \times (-((4 \times 5) - (6789)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20387 &:= ((-98 \times (((7-6) - (5^4))/3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 20388 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) \times 3)/2) - 1)) \\ 20389 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\ 20390 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 20391 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 20392 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 76)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20393 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times (5 \times 4)) + 3) \times -2) - 1) \\ 20394 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\ 20395 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2 \times 1} \\ 20396 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\ 20397 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times 6)) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\ 20398 &:= -9 + 8 - 76 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\ 20399 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20400 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -5 \times ((4 + (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 20401 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20402 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 20403 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2) + 1)))) \\ 20404 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20405 &:= (((9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 \times 54) \times (3 \times 21)))) \\ 20406 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\ 20407 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2 \times 1} \\ 20408 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\ 20409 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2 \times 1} \\ 20410 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\ 20411 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 20412 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((76 + 5) \times ((4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\ 20413 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((76 + 5) \times ((4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\ 20414 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20415 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 20416 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 20417 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 - 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20418 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -5 \times (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 20419 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 - ((6 \times 54) \times (-3 \times 21)))))) \\ 20420 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 - ((6 \times 54) \times (-3 \times 21)))))) \\ 20421 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20422 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\ 20423 &:= (((-98 + (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 20424 &:= (((9 \times (8 \times -7)) - (-654 \times 32)) \times (1)) \\ 20425 &:= -9 \times 8 \times 7 + 654 \times 32 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20426 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\
 20427 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 20428 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 34) \times 567) + 8) + 9) \\
 20429 &:= ((-((-1 \times ((2 + 34) \times 567))) + 8) + 9) \\
 20430 &:= (((1 \times 2345) - (67 + 8)) \times 9) \\
 20431 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times -(4^{5-6+7}) - 8) - 9) \\
 20432 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) \times (4 - (-5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 20433 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 20434 &:= ((1 \times -2) \times (-((34 + 567)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 20435 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4^{5+(6-7)^8} - 9) \\
 20436 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
 20437 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 20438 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 20439 &:= (((-1 \times (((2^3)^4) \times -5) - 6) - (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
 20440 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3^{4+5}))) + ((6 + 78) \times 9)) \\
 20441 &:= ((1 \times 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (-((6 + 78) \times -9))) \\
 20442 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
 20443 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
 20444 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
 20445 &:= (((1^2) + ((34 + 5) \times 6)) \times (78 + 9)) \\
 20446 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9) \\
 20447 &:= ((1 + (-2^3)) \times (((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 20448 &:= (((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 20449 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20450 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - (6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20451 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) + (4^5))/6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 20452 &:= (1 - (((23 \times (4 - 56)) - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 20453 &:= (-1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 + 67 - 89 \\
 20454 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((-3 + (4 \times 567)) + 8) \times -9)) \\
 20455 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - (6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20456 &:= (-1 + ((23 - (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 20457 &:= ((-((1 + 2)^3) + (((4 \times 567) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 20458 &:= ((-1 \times (((-2^3)^4) \times -5)) + ((67 - 89))) \\
 20459 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((3 - ((4 \times 567) + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20460 &:= (((12 \times 34) \times 5) + 6) \times (-7 - (-8 - 9)) \\
 20461 &:= ((1 \times -23) + (((4 \times 567) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 20462 &:= (1 - (-(-23) - (((4 \times 567) + 8) \times 9))) \\
 20463 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times -(4^{5-6+7})) - (8 + 9)) \\
 20464 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - (6 - (7 - (8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20426 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20427 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 20428 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 \times 43)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 20429 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 20430 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 20431 &:= ((-9 + (-8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 - 432)))) \times (1)) \\
 20432 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20433 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20434 &:= (((-9 + (8^{7+6-5-4})) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 20435 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20436 &:= (((-9 + (8^{7+6-5-4})) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 20437 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 20438 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 \times (4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 20439 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3+2+1} \\
 20440 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) - (4 - 3))^2 \times 1)) \\
 20441 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) - (4 - 3))^2) + 1)) \\
 20442 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20443 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
 20444 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20445 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\
 20446 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 20447 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 20448 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 20449 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\
 20450 &:= ((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20451 &:= ((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)) \\
 20452 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 20453 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -(((5 \times 4) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
 20454 &:= (((-((987 - 6) - 5) + (4 \times 3)) \times -21) \\
 20455 &:= ((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20456 &:= (((((-98 - 7) + (6^5)) \times 4)/3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20457 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) - 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 20458 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 \times 65 \times (43 + 2 \times 1) \\
 20459 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (-54 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\
 20460 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4^{3+2}) - 1)) \\
 20461 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 + 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 20462 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) - 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20463 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 - 6) \times 5) \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20464 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20465 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) - ((6 \times (7 + 8))/9)) & 20465 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20466 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9) & 20466 &:= ((9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 \times 54)))) - (-3 - (-21))) \\
 20467 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 20467 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20468 &:= (((1 \times 2) + ((34 - 5) \times -6)) \times (-7 \times -((-8 - 9))) & 20468 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3+2+1} \\
 20469 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 20469 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 20470 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4 + 5) + 67))) \times 89) & 20470 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (65 \times ((4 - 321)))) \\
 20471 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) & 20471 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7)^6) \times (5 \times (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 20472 &:= (1 \times (((2^3)^4) \times 5) + ((6 - 78)/9)) & 20472 &:= (-9 + 8)^7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 20473 &:= ((1 + (((2^3)^4) \times 5)) + ((6 - 78)/9)) & 20473 &:= (-9 + 8)^7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1 \\
 20474 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) - (6/((7 + 8) - 9))) & 20474 &:= (-9 + 8)^7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20475 &:= (((1 \times 2) - (3 - ((4 \times 567) + 8))) \times 9) & 20475 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 20476 &:= (1 \times -(((2^3) - (((4 \times 567) + 8) \times 9))) & 20476 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times (-65 \times (-43 + (-((2 \times 1))))))) \\
 20477 &:= (1 - ((2^3) - (((4 \times 567) + 8) \times 9))) & 20477 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 20478 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6/((7 + 8) - 9))) & 20478 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1 \\
 20479 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times 4^5 \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9) & 20479 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20480 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3) \times 4^5 \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9) & 20480 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20481 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) & 20481 &:= 987 + 6 \times (54 + 3)^2 \times 1 \\
 20482 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - (6 - (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 20482 &:= 987 + 6 \times (54 + 3)^2 + 1 \\
 20483 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) & 20483 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) - 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} \times 1) \\
 20484 &:= (((-((1 \times 2)) + 3) \times ((4 \times 567) + 8)) \times 9) & 20484 &:= (-9 + 8)^7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 20485 &:= ((-1 - (((2^3) + (4^5))/6) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9) & 20485 &:= (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 20486 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 \times (7 - 8)^9 & 20486 &:= (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2 \times 1} \\
 20487 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9)) & 20487 &:= (9 - 8)^7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20488 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3))) - (-((4 \times 567) + 8)) \times 9) & 20488 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) - 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\
 20489 &:= (((1 \times 2) + 3) - (-((4 \times 567) + 8)) \times 9) & 20489 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7)^6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20490 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 - ((4 \times 567) + 8) \times -9)) & 20490 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\
 20491 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 20491 &:= (((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
 20492 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 - 9 & 20492 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 20493 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) - (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 20493 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1 \\
 20494 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 20494 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20495 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 20495 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} \times 1) \\
 20496 &:= 1 + 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6 \times (7 + 8) \times 9 & 20496 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20497 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 20497 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 - 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20498 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 20498 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -(7 + 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20499 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) & 20499 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
 20500 &:= (((1 \times -2) - ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times (-7 + 89)) & 20500 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\
 20501 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 20501 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5 + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 20502 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))) & 20502 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 + 5))) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 20503 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 20503 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 + (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20504 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\ 20505 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + (6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 20506 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times 789))) \\ 20507 &:= (-((1 \times -23)) + (((4 \times 567) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 20508 &:= ((((-12 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(6 + (7 + 8))) - 9) \\ 20509 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 + (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\ 20510 &:= ((-12/3) + ((-4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 789)) \\ 20511 &:= -((((1 \times ((2 + 3) \times 456)) + 7) - 8) \times -9)) \\ 20512 &:= ((1^2) + (((3 + (4 \times 567)) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 20513 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((3 + (4 \times 567)) + 8) \times 9))) \\ 20514 &:= (((-(1 + 2)) + (3 - 4)) - (5 \times -6)) \times 789 \\ 20515 &:= 1^{23} - (4 - 5 \times 6) \times 789 \\ 20516 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\ 20517 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 20518 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9))) \\ 20519 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) \\ 20520 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) \times (((45 \times -6) - (7 + 8)) \times -9)) \\ 20521 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\ 20522 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 20523 &:= (12 - (3 + (((4 \times 5) + 6) \times -(789)))) \\ 20524 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + (6 + 7 - 8) \times 9 \\ 20525 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (((6 + 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 20526 &:= ((1 + (-2 + 34)) \times (5 - (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 20527 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9))))) \\ 20528 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 \times -((7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 20529 &:= (((1 \times ((2 + 3) \times 456)) - 7) + 8) \times -(-9)) \\ 20530 &:= (1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 + (6 + 7 - 8) \times 9 \\ 20531 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))) \\ 20532 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 - 9 \\ 20533 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 - 9 \\ 20534 &:= 1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 - 9 \\ 20535 &:= 1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 \times (-7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 20536 &:= ((1 \times -23) - (((4 \times -(56)) - 7) \times 89)) \\ 20537 &:= (-1 + ((2 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 67))) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20538 &:= -((((1 - 23) - ((4 \times 567) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20539 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 20540 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - 3) \times (4^5)) - 6) \times (7 - (8 + 9)) \\ 20541 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((67 + 8) - 9)) \\ 20542 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - ((-6 \times 7) \times 89)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20504 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 20505 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20506 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\ 20507 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(65 \times 4)) - (32 + 1)) \\ 20508 &:= ((9 + 87) + ((6 \times (54 \times 3)) \times 21)) \\ 20509 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\ 20510 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20511 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\ 20512 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) - 2 \times 1 \\ 20513 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) - 2 + 1 \\ 20514 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times (4^3 - 2) + 1 \\ 20515 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) + 2 - 1 \\ 20516 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) + 2 \times 1 \\ 20517 &:= (-9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\ 20518 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 20519 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - 2))) - 1) \\ 20520 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 6) + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 20521 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\ 20522 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1 \\ 20523 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\ 20524 &:= (((-9 - (8^{7+6-5-4})) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 20525 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20526 &:= (((-9 - (8^{7+6-5-4})) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 20527 &:= (9 - 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\ 20528 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20529 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\ 20530 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20531 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times (4^3 - 2 \times 1) \\ 20532 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 20533 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20534 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20535 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 20536 &:= 98 - 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1 \\ 20537 &:= 98 - 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\ 20538 &:= 9 + 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5 \times 43) \times 2 + 1 \\ 20539 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20540 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20541 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))^2 + 1))) \\ 20542 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 - (7 - 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20543 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20544 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 + 4)^5)) + ((6 \times 7) \times 89)) \\
 20545 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 67 + 8 - 9 \\
 20546 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 20547 &:= (((-1 \times -23) + ((4 \times 567) - 8)) \times 9) \\
 20548 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20549 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (-3 \times (-4 + (((5 + 6) \times 7) \times 89)))) \\
 20550 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) + 6)))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 20551 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4^{5-6+7})) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 20552 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) - 45) \times -((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 20553 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 \times 3) - 45) \times -((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 20554 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 + 78) - 9))) \\
 20555 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9))) \\
 20556 &:= (-((1 \times (2 + 34))) \times (5 + (6 \times (-7 - 89)))) \\
 20557 &:= (1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 \times (-6 + 7) + 8 \times 9 \\
 20558 &:= (1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 \\
 20559 &:= ((-1 \times ((2 \times 3) - (45 - 6))) \times (7 \times 89)) \\
 20560 &:= (1 - ((-(2 \times 3) + (45 - 6)) \times -((7 \times 89)))) \\
 20561 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((34 + (5 - 6)) \times (7 \times -89))) \\
 20562 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4) - ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
 20563 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (67 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20564 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4^{5-6+7}) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20565 &:= (((1 - 2345) + (67 - 8)) \times -9) \\
 20566 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - ((6 - (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20567 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 - (7 - 89)))) \\
 20568 &:= (-((123 \times 4) + (((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 20569 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (67 + (8 + 9))) \\
 20570 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times (3^4) + (5 + 6)) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 20571 &:= (((1 - 2) \times -3) \times (4 + (((5 + 6) \times 7) \times 89))) \\
 20572 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 + (78 + 9)))) \\
 20573 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((45 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 20574 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
 20575 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 20576 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times -4 \times (5 + ((6 - 78) \times 9))) \\
 20577 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) - 9)) \\
 20578 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) \\
 20579 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
 20580 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 20581 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 + (7 + 89)))) \\
 20582 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20543 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - (7 - 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20544 &:= (-(((9 + 87) \times 6) / (5 + 4))) \times -321 \\
 20545 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20546 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - (7 - 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 20547 &:= (((9 \times (8 + 76)) + 5) \times (-4 - (-32 + (1)))) \\
 20548 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - (7 - 6))) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20549 &:= (((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4) - (3^{2+1})) \\
 20550 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) + ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 20551 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - (7 - 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20552 &:= ((98 + ((-7 \times -6) \times ((54 \times (3^2)) + 1))) \\
 20553 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 - 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20554 &:= (-98 + 7 + (6^5 \times 4) / 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
 20555 &:= (9 - 8) \times (76 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2}) - 1 \\
 20556 &:= (9 - 8) \times (76 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2}) \times 1 \\
 20557 &:= (9 - 8) \times (76 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2}) + 1 \\
 20558 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 - 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20559 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) / -6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 20560 &:= ((9 - 8) - ((7 + ((6 \times 54) \times 3)) \times (-21))) \\
 20561 &:= ((9 + ((-8 \times 7) \times (65 - (432 \times 1)))) \\
 20562 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 - 6)))) + (((5^4) \times (32 + 1)))) \\
 20563 &:= ((-(-9) \times 8) + ((-7 - 654) \times -(((32 - 1)))) \\
 20564 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) / -6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20565 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20566 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5^4)) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 20567 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 \times 5))) - (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 20568 &:= ((987 + ((65 - 4) \times 321))) \\
 20569 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) / -6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20570 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\
 20571 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 \times 5))) - ((4 \times 3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 20572 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 \times 5))) - ((4 + (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 20573 &:= ((((((9 \times 8) + 7) \times 65) \times 4) + 32) - (-1)) \\
 20574 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 20575 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20576 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20577 &:= (((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + 5))) / 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 20578 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) \times 4) / 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20579 &:= (((98 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (-4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
 20580 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\
 20581 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 - 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 20582 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 \times 5))) - (4 - (3 + (2 + 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20583 &:= (((1 + 2345) - (67 - 8)) \times 9) \\ 20584 &:= -(((1 - (2^3 \times 4)) \times (-5 + (678 - 9)))) \\ 20585 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20586 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20587 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times (3^4)) - (5 + 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 20588 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) - (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20589 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 20590 &:= ((1 - ((2 - 345) \times 6)) \times -((7 + (-8 - 9)))) \\ 20591 &:= (-1 - (-((234) \times (-5 - (-6 - (78 + 9))))) \\ 20592 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (45 - 6)) \times ((-7 - 8) - 9)) \\ 20593 &:= (1 - (234 \times (5 + (-6 - (78 + 9))))) \\ 20594 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9 \\ 20595 &:= 1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9 \\ 20596 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times 45)) \times ((6 + 7) - (89))) \\ 20597 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) - (67 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 20598 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20599 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 20600 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 20601 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 20602 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (((5 \times 67) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 20603 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4 + 5) \times 67)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20604 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (-3 - ((4 + 5) \times 67))) \times -((8 + 9)))) \\ 20605 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 + 9))))) \\ 20606 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 + 9))))) \\ 20607 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times ((5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9))) \\ 20608 &:= (-((12 + (34))) \times (-56) \times ((7 - 8) + 9)) \\ 20609 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 20610 &:= -(((12 + 3) - 45) \times (678 + 9)) \\ 20611 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 \times 7) + 89)) \\ 20612 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\ 20613 &:= -((123 + (4 \times (((5 + 67) \times -8) \times 9))) \\ 20614 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) - (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 20615 &:= (((((1 + 234) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\ 20616 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 20617 &:= -(((1 \times 23) \times ((45 + 67) \times -8)) - 9) \\ 20618 &:= -1^2 + 3^{4+5} + (6 + 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\ 20619 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 20620 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20621 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20583 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))))) - (2 + 1))) \\ 20584 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 20585 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times ((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 20586 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - (5 - 4)) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 20587 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - (((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) - 1))) \\ 20588 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -7) - 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 20589 &:= ((98 + ((7 + 654) \times (32 - 1)))) \\ 20590 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -(((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 20591 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 20592 &:= (-9 \times (-8 + (76 \times -((54 - 3)) - (-21)))) \\ 20593 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -7) - 6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20594 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20595 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times 6)) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\ 20596 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 \times 5))) + (4 \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 20597 &:= (-(((9 - 8) + 7)) + (-65 \times ((4 - 32)))) \\ 20598 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -7) - 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20599 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20600 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\ 20601 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 20602 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times 2 + 1)) \\ 20603 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2))) - 1) \\ 20604 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\ 20605 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) \times (-65 \times ((4 - 32)))) \\ 20606 &:= (((9 - 8)^7) + (-65 \times ((4 - 32)))) \\ 20607 &:= (((98 \times 7) \times -6) \times -5) - ((4 - 32) - (-1)) \\ 20608 &:= ((((-9 - 87) - 65) \times (4^3)) \times (-2 \times (1))) \\ 20609 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} \times 1) \\ 20610 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) - 6) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\ 20611 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 20612 &:= (-((9 \times (8 - 76))) + ((5^4) \times (32 \times (1)))) \\ 20613 &:= (((9 - 8) + 7) + (-65 \times ((4 - 32)))) \\ 20614 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\ 20615 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - (6^{5-4+3})) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\ 20616 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\ 20617 &:= (9 + ((8 \times 7) \times -(((65 - 432) - 1)))) \\ 20618 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times 2 + 1)) \\ 20619 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + 6))) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\ 20620 &:= ((((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + 6) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 20621 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20622 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 20623 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
 20624 &:= (1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 + 67 + 8 \times 9 \\
 20625 &:= (1 - 2 + 34) \times 5^{-6-7+8+9} \\
 20626 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 20627 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + 78) \times 9) \\
 20628 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) \\
 20629 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20630 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5^6 + 7! - 8 \times 9 \\
 20631 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) + 9)) \\
 20632 &:= (-1 \times (23 - (45 \times ((6 \times 78) - 9)))) \\
 20633 &:= (((((1 + 234) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 20634 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) - (6 + ((7 + 89)))) \\
 20635 &:= -12 + (3 \times 4)^{5+6-7} - 89 \\
 20636 &:= (((1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((67 + 89)) \\
 20637 &:= (((1 + (((-2^3)^4) \times 5)) + 67) + (89)) \\
 20638 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times 5)) - (6 - 7)) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 20639 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 20640 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - 5) \times (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 20641 &:= ((((-12 \times 34) - 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 20642 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5^6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 20643 &:= 12^{3-4+5} - 6 - 78 - 9 \\
 20644 &:= ((12^3) + (4 \times (-5 + (6 \times 789)))) \\
 20645 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times ((4 \times (-((5 + 6)) \times 78)) - 9))) \\
 20646 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
 20647 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))^{5+6-7}) - 89) \\
 20648 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7})) - 89) \\
 20649 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + ((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7})) - 89) \\
 20650 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6)))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 20651 &:= ((-12/3) + (45 \times ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
 20652 &:= ((-12 + ((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7})) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 20653 &:= (-((1 - 2)) + (-3 + (45 \times ((6 \times 78) - 9)))) \\
 20654 &:= -1 + (2 - 3 + 4)^5 \times (6 + 7 + 8 \times 9) \\
 20655 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 20656 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 \times 3))^4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 20657 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
 20658 &:= (((1 - 2) \times -3) + (45 \times ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\
 20659 &:= ((1^2) + (3 - (-45) \times ((6 \times 78) + (-9)))) \\
 20660 &:= (-((1 - ((-(2 + 3)) + (45 \times 6)) \times 78)) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20622 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + 6) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\
 20623 &:= ((((-98 \times -7) \times (-6 \times -5)) + (4^3)) + (-21)) \\
 20624 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20625 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times -(((4^3)/2) + 1)) \\
 20626 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\
 20627 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 - ((5^4) \times ((32 + 1)))))) \\
 20628 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + ((7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 20629 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + 76) - ((5^4) \times (-32 + (-1)))) \\
 20630 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 20631 &:= ((-98 - 7) + (((6^5) \times 4)/3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20632 &:= ((-98 - 7) + (((6^5) \times 4)/3) \times 2 + 1) \\
 20633 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - (6^{5-4+3})) \times 2))) \times -1) \\
 20634 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 \times 4) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
 20635 &:= 9 + (8 - 7)^6 + 5^4 \times (32 + 1) \\
 20636 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 20637 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) + 6) + ((5^4) \times ((32 + 1)))) \\
 20638 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) - (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
 20639 &:= (((98 \times (7 \times 6)) \times 5) - 4) - (-3 \times 21) \\
 20640 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times 5) \times -((4^3)/(2 \times 1))) \\
 20641 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times 5) \times -((4^3)/2) + 1) \\
 20642 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4^3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 20643 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4^3 - 2 + 1 \\
 20644 &:= (((-98 + 7) + (((6^5) \times 4)/3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 20645 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4^3 + 2 - 1 \\
 20646 &:= 98 \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4^3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 20647 &:= 98 - 76 + 5^4 \times (32 + 1) \\
 20648 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (43 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 20649 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 20650 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 - (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 20651 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 20652 &:= (((-98 - ((7 - (6^5)) \times 4))/3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20653 &:= ((((-98 - ((7 - (6^5)) \times 4))/3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 20654 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 20655 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times (5 + 4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 20656 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2)))) + 1) \\
 20657 &:= (((9 - 87) + (((6 - 54) \times -3)^2) - 1)) \\
 20658 &:= (((-98 \times 7) + (6 + 54)) \times (-32 - (1))) \\
 20659 &:= (((-9 - ((87 - ((6^5) \times 4))/3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 20660 &:= ((-9 - ((87 - ((6^5) \times 4))/3)) \times (2 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20661 &:= (((-1-2) + ((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7})) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 20662 &:= ((1 \times -2) + (((3-45) \times 6) \times -((-7+89)))) \\ 20663 &:= -1 + (2^3 + 4)^{5+6-7} - 8 \times 9 \\ 20664 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20665 &:= 12^{3-4+5} - 6 - 7 \times 8 - 9 \\ 20666 &:= (1 \times -((-2 + (((3-45) \times 6) \times (-7+89)))) \\ 20667 &:= ((12^{34-5 \times 6}) - (78-9)) \\ 20668 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 20669 &:= (-(((12^{3-4+5}) - 67)) \times (8-9)) \\ 20670 &:= ((12 - (-3)) - (-45) \times ((6 \times 78) - 9)) \\ 20671 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((34-5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8+9))) \\ 20672 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5)) \times -(-6 - (7 - (8+9)))) \\ 20673 &:= (((12^{3-4+5}) + 6) + (-78) + 9) \\ 20674 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20675 &:= (-1 \times -(-2 - ((3 - (4 \times (567 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 20676 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 20677 &:= 12^{3-4+5} + 6 + 7 - 8 \times 9 \\ 20678 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) - (45 \times 6)) \times 78) - 9) \\ 20679 &:= (1 \times (((-((2+3)) + (45 \times 6)) \times 78) + 9)) \\ 20680 &:= ((-1 - 234) \times -((-5 - (-6 - ((78 + 9)))))) \\ 20681 &:= (-1 + ((2 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 20682 &:= (((12 \times 3) \times 45) + 678) \times 9 \\ 20683 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4 \times ((5 + 67) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 20684 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times -4 - ((567 + 8) \times 9)) \\ 20685 &:= ((-12 - 3) + (4 \times ((567 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 20686 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) - (67 - (8 + 9))) \\ 20687 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + 5^6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 20688 &:= (-12 \times ((3 \times 4) - (((5^6) + (7 - 8))/9)) \\ 20689 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) - (-((6 \times 7)) + (89))) \\ 20690 &:= (-1 + ((23 + ((4 \times 567) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20691 &:= ((((-1-2) \times (3 \times 4)) \times (-567-8)) - 9) \\ 20692 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) - (4 \times ((567 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20693 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) - (4 \times ((567 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20694 &:= (-12 + ((34-5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20695 &:= (-1 \times ((2+3) - (4 \times ((567 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20696 &:= -12/3 + (4 \times (567 + 8) \times 9) \\ 20697 &:= ((-1-2) + (345 \times (-6 \times ((7-8) - 9)))) \\ 20698 &:= ((1 \times -2) - ((345 \times -6) \times (-7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 20699 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (3 + ((4 \times (567 + 8)) \times -9))) \\ 20700 &:= (((1+2) - (3+4)) \times ((567+8) \times -9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20661 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3) - 2 - 1 \\ 20662 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3) - 2 \times 1 \\ 20663 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3) - 2 + 1 \\ 20664 &:= ((((-9-8) + (76+5)) \times (4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\ 20665 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3) + 2 - 1 \\ 20666 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3) + 2 \times 1 \\ 20667 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3) + 2 + 1 \\ 20668 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 20669 &:= (-((9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6)))) + (((5 \times 4321)))) \\ 20670 &:= ((-9 + 87) \times ((-65 \times -4) + ((3 + 2) \times (1)))) \\ 20671 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6^5)/(4-3) \times (2+1)))) \\ 20672 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((76 \times (5 + 43))/(2+1))) \\ 20673 &:= (9 + ((-8 \times 7) \times (6 + ((-54 - 321)))) \\ 20674 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 + 6))) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20675 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 20676 &:= ((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -5 - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})) \\ 20677 &:= (((9 + 8) \times 76) - ((5^4)) \times (32 + (-1))) \\ 20678 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) - (6^5)) \times 4)/3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 20679 &:= (((-9 - (((8 + 7) - (6^5)) \times 4)/3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 20680 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 + 5) - 4) \times 3^2) - 1) \\ 20681 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) + 2) - 1) \\ 20682 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) - (5^4)) \times -3^{2+1}) \\ 20683 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) + 2) + 1) \\ 20684 &:= ((9 \times 8) + (7 + (-65 \times (4 + (-321)))) \\ 20685 &:= ((-98 - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\ 20686 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - (6^5)) \times 4)/3 \times 2) + 1) \\ 20687 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 - 654) \times 32) \times -1)) \\ 20688 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 20689 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2))) - 1) \\ 20690 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) - (6^5)) \times 4)/3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 20691 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 20692 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + 65) \times 4) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 20693 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + ((7 - (6^5)) \times 4)/3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 20694 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + ((7 - (6^5)) \times 4)/3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 20695 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (((7 - ((6^5) + 4))/3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 20696 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 20697 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -5 \times (4 \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 20698 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 20699 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -5 \times (4 \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 20700 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3) \times 2 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20701 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (-3 + (4 \times -((567 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20702 &:= (-((1 \times -2) - ((345 \times -6) \times (-7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 20703 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((34 - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20704 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((34 - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20705 &:= ((-1 \times -((2 + 3))) + (-4 \times ((-567) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 20706 &:= (((123 + 45) + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 20707 &:= ((-12 + ((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7})) - (8 + 9)) \\ 20708 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((34 - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 20709 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 \times 4)) \times (-567 - 8)) + 9) \\ 20710 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + 67) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 20711 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times -(5 - (6 + (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\ 20712 &:= (-12 \times ((3 - 4) - (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 20713 &:= (-1 \times (23 - (4 \times ((5 + 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20714 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) + (67 - 89)) \\ 20715 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -((4 \times ((5 \times 67) + 8)) + 9)) \\ 20716 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7}) - 8) - 9) \\ 20717 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7}) - 8)) - 9) \\ 20718 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) + 4)^{5+6-7})) - (8 + 9)) \\ 20719 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))^{5+6-7}) - (8 + 9)) \\ 20720 &:= (((12^{3-4+5}) + (-6 + (7 - 8))) - 9) \\ 20721 &:= (1 + ((-2 + (345 \times -6)) \times -((-7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 20722 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4 + 56) - 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 20723 &:= (-(-1) \times ((23 \times ((4 + 56) - 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 20724 &:= (-(-1) + ((23 \times ((4 + 56) - 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 20725 &:= ((-12 + ((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7})) - (8 - 9)) \\ 20726 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (34)) \times ((5 + 67) \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 20727 &:= (-(-1) \times (((2 + (34)) \times ((5 + 67) \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 20728 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) - (4 \times ((5 + 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20729 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times -(5 - (6 + (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\ 20730 &:= (((1 + 2) + (345 \times 6)) \times -(((7 - 8) - 9))) \\ 20731 &:= 12^{3-4+5} - 6 - (7 - 8)^9 \\ 20732 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7}) + (8 - 9))) \\ 20733 &:= 12^{3-4+5} + 6 + (7 - 8) \times 9 \\ 20734 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3 \times 4)^{5-6/(7+8-9)})) \\ 20735 &:= ((1 - ((-((2^3) - 4)^{5+6-7})) \times (8 - 9)) \\ 20736 &:= ((12 \times 3) \times (((45 - 6) \times (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\ 20737 &:= ((12 + (((3 - 45) \times 6) + 7)) \times -(89)) \\ 20738 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 + 5)^{-6-7+8+9} \\ 20739 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (34)) - 5) \times (678 - 9) \\ 20740 &:= (1 \times (-((-2 + (((34 - 5) \times -6) \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20701 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20702 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + 6)) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\ 20703 &:= (98 - (-((7 + 6)) \times (-(-5) \times -((4 - 321)))) \\ 20704 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/(2 + 1))) \\ 20705 &:= (-((-9 + 8)) - (-((7 - 654) \times (-((32 \times 1)))) \\ 20706 &:= (((-98 + ((-7 \times (6 \times 54)) \times 3)) \times (-2 - 1)) \\ 20707 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2)))) + 1) \\ 20708 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) \times 4))/3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 20709 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4)/3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 20710 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 20711 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - ((6^5) + (4 - 3)))/(2 + 1))) \\ 20712 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6^5)/(4 + (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\ 20713 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) \times 4)/3) \times 2 + 1)) \\ 20714 &:= (((9 + (((8 - ((7 - 6))) + 5)^4)) - (32 - 1)) \\ 20715 &:= (((9 \times -8) \times (76 + (5 \times 4))) \times -3) - 21) \\ 20716 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 - ((6^5) + 4))/3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 20717 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4)) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 20718 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 20719 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) - (5 - 4))^{3+2-1})) \\ 20720 &:= (-9 - (876 - ((5 \times 4321)))) \\ 20721 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 20722 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 - ((6^5) + 4))/3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 20723 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 20724 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 20725 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4)) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 20726 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4)) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 20727 &:= (987 \times (-6 - ((-5 - (43 - 21)))) \\ 20728 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 20729 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5)^4 + 3 - 2 + 1 \\ 20730 &:= (-9 + ((-8 - (7 + 654)) \times -(((32 - 1)))) \\ 20731 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5)^4 + 3 + 2 - 1 \\ 20732 &:= ((-98 + 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times ((32 + 1)))) \\ 20733 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5)^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 20734 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\ 20735 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) / - (7 - (6 - 5)))^4) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 20736 &:= ((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))^{(5+4+3)/(2+1)}) \\ 20737 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) / - (7 - (6 - 5)))^4) + (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 20738 &:= (9 - (876 - ((5 \times 4321)))) \\ 20739 &:= (((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6)))^{5-4+3}) + (2 + 1)) \\ 20740 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6) - 5)) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20741 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9 \\
 20742 &:= (-12 - ((34 + ((-5 \times 6) \times 78)) \times 9)) \\
 20743 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times (5 - (6 + (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
 20744 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + (34))) \times ((5 + 67) \times 8))) + 9 \\
 20745 &:= 1^2 \times (3 \times 4)^{-5-6+7+8} + 9 \\
 20746 &:= 1^2 + (3 \times 4)^{-5-6+7+8} + 9 \\
 20747 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4)^{-5-6+7+8} + 9 \\
 20748 &:= ((-12 - ((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7})) \times (8 - 9)) \\
 20749 &:= (1 + ((2 + (-3 \times 45)) \times (-67) - 89))) \\
 20750 &:= (((12^{3-4+5}) - (-6 - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
 20751 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7}) + (8 + 9))) \\
 20752 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + 4)^{5+6-7}) + (8 + 9)) \\
 20753 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4))^{5+6-7}) + (8 + 9)) \\
 20754 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7}) + (8 + 9))) \\
 20755 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7}) + (8 + 9))) \\
 20756 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 20757 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times 4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 20758 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 20759 &:= (-((1 \times -23)) - (4 \times (((5 + 67) \times -8) \times 9))) \\
 20760 &:= ((1 + 23) + (4 \times (((5 + 67) \times 8) \times 9))) \\
 20761 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 \times (-7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 20762 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 \times (-7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 20763 &:= 1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 - 6 \times (-7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 20764 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + (4 \times ((5 + 67) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 20765 &:= (-1 \times -2 + ((3 + (4 \times ((5 + 67) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 20766 &:= (12 - ((34 - (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\
 20767 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3 \times 4 \times 5) \times 6) \times 7 \times 8 - 9 \\
 20768 &:= 12 \times (-34 + 5^6 - 7 - 8) / 9 \\
 20769 &:= (1 + 2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7 - 8) - 9) \\
 20770 &:= ((-(-1) + (2 - 34)) \times (5 - ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 20771 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) \times 4) - (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9) \\
 20772 &:= (-((1 + 2)) \times -(((3 \times 45) + 6789))) \\
 20773 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 20774 &:= ((12^3) - ((-4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89)) \\
 20775 &:= (((-1 + (23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\
 20776 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times 67) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20777 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 20778 &:= ((-123 \times -4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)))) - 9 \\
 20779 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20741 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) / - (7 - (6 - 5)))^4) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 20742 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) / - (7 - (6 - 5)))^4) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 20743 &:= 9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5)^4 - 3 + 2 - 1 \\
 20744 &:= 9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5)^4 - 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 20745 &:= 9 + (8 - 7 + 6 + 5)^4 - 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 20746 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4) + (3 - 2))) \times -1) \\
 20747 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) \times 4) / 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 20748 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - (7 - (6 + 5)))^4) + 3)) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
 20749 &:= (((98 - 7) \times -((6 \times (5 - 43)))) - ((-2 + 1))) \\
 20750 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7 - 6 - 5)^4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 20751 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7 - 6 - 5)^4 + 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 20752 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7 - 6 - 5)^4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 20753 &:= (((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 20754 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7 - 6 - 5)^4 + 3^2 \times 1 \\
 20755 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 20756 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 20757 &:= (((9 \times -8) \times (76 + (5 \times 4))) \times -3) + 21) \\
 20758 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) + (6^5) \times 4) / 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20759 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + (6^5)) - 4) / 3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 20760 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6^5) / (4 + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 20761 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4^3 + 2 + 1) \\
 20762 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20763 &:= (((9 \times 87) + 6) + ((5 \times -4)) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
 20764 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) \times 4) / 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 20765 &:= (((-9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) \times 4) / 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 20766 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) + (6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 20767 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + (6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20768 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) / (2 + 1))) \\
 20769 &:= 9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6^5 - 4) / 3 + 2 \times 1) \\
 20770 &:= (((-9 + (((8 + 7) + (6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20771 &:= (((-9 + (((8 + 7) + (6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 20772 &:= (((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 \times 5))) + (4^3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 20773 &:= (((9 \times 8) + 76) - ((5^4) \times (-32 + (-1)))) \\
 20774 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 + 5) - 4) \times 3)^2 + 1) \\
 20775 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) \times 4) / 3)) \times 2) \times -1) \\
 20776 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 20777 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times ((6 \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1)) \\
 20778 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + ((7 + (6^5)) \times 4) / 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 20779 &:= (9 + (((8 \times -7) - 6) \times -5) \times -(-4) + (3 \times 21)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20780 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) + (4 \times ((5+67) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 20781 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) - ((6 + (7-8)) \times -9)) \\
 20782 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8))) - 9) \\
 20783 &:= (((12^{3-4+5}) - ((6 \times 7))) + (89)) \\
 20784 &:= (-12 \times -((3+4) + (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
 20785 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
 20786 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 20787 &:= (-123 \times ((4 \times 5) - ((6 + (7+8)) \times 9))) \\
 20788 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) + ((6 \times 78)/9)) \\
 20789 &:= (((12^{3-4+5}) + 6) - ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
 20790 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (((4 \times 5) \times 6) - (7+8)) \times 9) \\
 20791 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 20792 &:= (-1 \times -(23 \times (4 \times (5 + ((6+7) \times (8+9)))))) \\
 20793 &:= (((-1 + (23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\
 20794 &:= (1+2)!! + 3 + 4 \times 5! \times 6 \times 7 - 89 \\
 20795 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) + ((6 \times 7) + (8+9))) \\
 20796 &:= -12 + (3 \times 4)^{5+6-7} + 8 \times 9 \\
 20797 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 789))) \\
 20798 &:= (-1 + ((2345 - ((6 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20799 &:= (((-1 \times 2345) + ((6 \times 7) - 8)) \times -9) \\
 20800 &:= ((-1 + (23 + 4)) \times (5 + (6 + 789))) \\
 20801 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (789)))) \\
 20802 &:= (((12^{3-4+5}) + 67) + 8) - 9) \\
 20803 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) - (67 \times (8-9))) \\
 20804 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) + (67 - (8-9))) \\
 20805 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7}) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 20806 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (34 \times (-((-5-6)) - ((7 \times 89)))))) \\
 20807 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + (6+7))) + 8) \times 9) \\
 20808 &:= ((-12 - (34 + (-5 \times 67))) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 20809 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7}) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 20810 &:= (-12 - (-((3^4+5)) + (67 \times (-8-9)))) \\
 20811 &:= (12 + (3 \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 789))) \\
 20812 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 20813 &:= -12 + (3 \times 4)^{5+6-7} + 89 \\
 20814 &:= (-12 - (-(((3 - (4 \times -(56))) + 7)) \times 89)) \\
 20815 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times (6 - (7 - (8+9)))) \\
 20816 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 \times 3))^4) + 5) \times (6 - (7 - (8+9)))) \\
 20817 &:= (((1 \times 234) \times ((5+6) + 78)) - 9) \\
 20818 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times 78)) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20780 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((65 \times 4) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 20781 &:= (-9 \times -(8 - ((7+6) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times (2+1)))))) \\
 20782 &:= (((-9 - (((8+7) + (6^5)) \times 4))/3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 20783 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6^5)/(4-3) \times (2+1)))))) \\
 20784 &:= ((9 \times (-((8+765) - 4)) \times -3) + 21) \\
 20785 &:= ((((-9 - (8+7)) - (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 20786 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20787 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\
 20788 &:= ((((-9+87) + ((6^5) \times 4))/3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20789 &:= ((-9 \times -((8+7) \times ((6+5) \times ((4+3) \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 20790 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 20791 &:= ((-9 \times -((8+7) \times ((6+5) \times ((4+3) \times 2)))) + 1) \\
 20792 &:= 9 + 8 \times ((7-6+5)^4 + 3) \times 2 - 1 \\
 20793 &:= 9 + 8 \times ((7-6+5)^4 + 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\
 20794 &:= 9 + 8 \times ((7-6+5)^4 + 3) \times 2 + 1 \\
 20795 &:= (((-9 - (((8+7) + (6^5)) \times 4)/3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 20796 &:= ((-9 + (8 + (7+6))) \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 20797 &:= (9+8+7)/6 + (5+4!) \times (-3 + (2+1)!!) \\
 20798 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times ((4+3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 20799 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times ((-7-65) \times 4)) + (3 \times 21)) \\
 20800 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times ((4+3)^2)))) + 1) \\
 20801 &:= (((-((98 \times 7)) - (-6-5)) + 4) \times (-((32-1)))) \\
 20802 &:= ((((-9-8) \times ((7+6) - (5^4))) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20803 &:= ((98 - ((7-654) \times 32)) - (-1)) \\
 20804 &:= (9 + (((87 + ((6^5) \times 4))/3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 20805 &:= (((((-98-7) - ((6^5) \times 4))/3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 20806 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 20807 &:= ((9-87) + ((6 \times ((5 - (4^3))^2)) + (-1))) \\
 20808 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times -(7 + (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + (3^{2+1})))))) \\
 20809 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7+6) + (5 \times (4+3)))^2))) + 1) \\
 20810 &:= (((-9 - (8-7)) \times -(((65 \times (4^3))/2) + 1)) \\
 20811 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
 20812 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20813 &:= -9 + 87 + ((-6+54) \times 3)^2 - 1 \\
 20814 &:= ((((-9-8) \times ((7+6) - (5^4))) + 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20815 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6+5^4) \times (32+1) \\
 20816 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (-32 + (-1)))) \\
 20817 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (((7+6) + (5 \times (4+3)))^2) + 1))) \\
 20818 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + ((6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20819 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times 78) + 9)) \\
 20820 &:= (((12^{3-4+5}) + 67) + 8) + 9 \\
 20821 &:= (1 + (((-2 - 345) \times -6) \times (-7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20822 &:= (((1^2) \times (-3^{4+5})) + (67 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 20823 &:= (((1^2) - (-3^{4+5})) + (67 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 20824 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 20825 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 20826 &:= ((((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + 8) \times -9) \\
 20827 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times 4)^{5+6-7}) + 89)) \\
 20828 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - (5 + 6)) \times (7 - 89)) \\
 20829 &:= (1 + ((-2 + ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times -((-7 + 89)))) \\
 20830 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3 \times 4) \times (((5^6) + (7 - 8))/9))) \\
 20831 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + 4) \times (((5^6) + (7 - 8))/9))) \\
 20832 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 20833 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times 4) \times (((5^6) + (7 - 8))/9))) \\
 20834 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 20835 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)))) \times 9) \\
 20836 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times 78) - 9)) \\
 20837 &:= 12 + (3 \times 4)^{5+6-7} + 89 \\
 20838 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + 7) \times 89))) \\
 20839 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4^{5-6+7}) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20840 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times -((4^{5-6+7}) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 20841 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(3 + (4 \times (((5^6) + (7 - 8))/9)))) \\
 20842 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (3^{4+5})) - ((6 + 7) \times -(89))) \\
 20843 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
 20844 &:= (((1 + (-2)) - 3) \times -(((4 + 567) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 20845 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3 \times 4)) - (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\
 20846 &:= ((12 + 3)^4 - 5 + 6) \times 7 / (8 + 9) \\
 20847 &:= -1 + 2^3 \times (-4 + 5 \times 6 \times (78 + 9)) \\
 20848 &:= 1 \times 2^3 \times (-4 + 5 \times 6 \times (78 + 9)) \\
 20849 &:= 1 + 2^3 \times (-4 + 5 \times 6 \times (78 + 9)) \\
 20850 &:= (((12^{3-4+5}) + ((6 \times 7))) + (-8 \times -9)) \\
 20851 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 20852 &:= (12 + ((3^{4+5}) + ((6 + 7) \times 89))) \\
 20853 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)))) \times -9) \\
 20854 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 20855 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20856 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 20857 &:= ((((-123 \times 4) - 5) \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 20858 &:= (-12 + 3 \times (4 \times 5^6 + 78)) / 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20819 &:= ((((-98 - ((7 + (6^5)) \times 4)) / 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 20820 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4^3)^2 - 1 \\
 20821 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 20822 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4^3)^2 + 1 \\
 20823 &:= (((98 + 7) \times 6) + (5 - 4)) \times ((32 + 1)) \\
 20824 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 20825 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 20826 &:= (((-9 - 87)) \times ((6 \times -((5 + 4))) + 321)) \\
 20827 &:= ((98 - 7) + (((6 - 54) \times 3)^2) \times (1)) \\
 20828 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times ((43 - 2) \times 1)) \\
 20829 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6^{5-4+3})))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 20830 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6^{5-4+3})))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 20831 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + (6^{5-4+3})) \times 2) - 1))) \\
 20832 &:= (((-9 + (876 + 5)) - 4) \times ((3 + 21))) \\
 20833 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times 32) + 1) \\
 20834 &:= 98 + (76 + 5) \times 4^{3+2-1} \\
 20835 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 20836 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\
 20837 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 20838 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (-5 + 4^3)^2 - 1 \\
 20839 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (-5 + 4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 20840 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (-5 + 4^3)^2 + 1 \\
 20841 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 20842 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - 6) + ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2 \times 1))) \\
 20843 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4)) \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 20844 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4)) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 20845 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4)) \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 20846 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + 6)) + ((5^4) \times (32 + 1))) \\
 20847 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
 20848 &:= ((((-9) \times -8) - ((7 + (-654 \times 32)) + 1)) \\
 20849 &:= ((9 - ((87 + (654 \times -32)) + 1)) \\
 20850 &:= ((-9 + ((876 - 5) \times 4)) \times ((3 + 2) + (1))) \\
 20851 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3) - 2 \times 1 \\
 20852 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 20853 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 20854 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3))) + (2 - 1)) \\
 20855 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3) + 2 \times 1 \\
 20856 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 20857 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1) \\
 20858 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - 6) \times -(5 \times 43)) + (2 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20859 &:= (123 - (4 \times ((5 + 67) \times -8) \times 9)) \\ 20860 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (4! + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 20861 &:= 12^{3-4+5} + 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 20862 &:= (((12 - 34) - ((-5 \times 6) \times 78)) \times 9) \\ 20863 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times 4 \times (5! + 6!) + 78 \times 9 \\ 20864 &:= 12 + 3 \times (4 \times 5^6 + 7 \times 8) / 9 \\ 20865 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20866 &:= 1 \times (2 \times 3!)^4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 20867 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) - 5)) \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 20868 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 20869 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20870 &:= (-1 + ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) \times 9) \\ 20871 &:= (-1 \times -((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) \times 9) \\ 20872 &:= -(((1 + (2 - 34)) \times (-5 + 678)) - 9) \\ 20873 &:= (((((123 \times 4) + 5) \times 6) \times 7) + (-(-8) - 9)) \\ 20874 &:= (((((123 \times 4) + 5) \times 6) \times -7) \times (-(-8) - 9)) \\ 20875 &:= (((((123 \times 4) + 5) \times 6) \times 7) - (-(-8) - 9)) \\ 20876 &:= (((1234 - 5) + 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 20877 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + ((4 \times 56) - 7) \times 8))) + 9 \\ 20878 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 20879 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 20880 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + (3 - 45))) \times (6 \times (78 + 9))) \\ 20881 &:= (1 + ((-2 - (3 - 45)) \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 20882 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 20883 &:= (-12 + (((-34) + (-5)) \times (67 \times -8)) - 9) \\ 20884 &:= (-1 \times -(23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9)))) \\ 20885 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (78 + 9))))))) \\ 20886 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (78 + 9))))))) \\ 20887 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (67 + 8))) + 9) \\ 20888 &:= (-1 - (((23 - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\ 20889 &:= (((1 \times 23) - 4) - ((5 \times 6) \times 78)) \times -9 \\ 20890 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 34)) \times -567) - 89) \\ 20891 &:= ((((((123 \times 4) + 5) \times 6) \times 7) + 8) + 9) \\ 20892 &:= (-1 + ((-2 - ((34 + 5) \times (67 \times -8))) - 9)) \\ 20893 &:= (1 \times ((-2 - ((34 + 5) \times (67 \times -8))) - 9)) \\ 20894 &:= ((1 + ((-2 - ((34 + 5) \times (67 \times -8)))) - 9) \\ 20895 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 - ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) \\ 20896 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 \times (5 - ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) \\ 20897 &:= (-(-1) \times (((-2 - ((34 + 5) \times -(67))) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 20898 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (3^4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times (-7 - 8))) - 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20859 &:= (9 \times (8 + 765) - 4) \times 3 \times (2 - 1) \\ 20860 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 \times 3)^2 \times 1))) \\ 20861 &:= (((-98 - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 \times 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 20862 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\ 20863 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2) + 1)))) \\ 20864 &:= (98 \times 7 - 6 \times 5 - 4) \times 32 \times 1 \\ 20865 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 + (5 \times ((4^3) - (2 - 1)))))) \\ 20866 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + (6^{5-4+3})))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 20867 &:= -((((9 - (8 - 76)) \times ((-54 \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))) \\ 20868 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -((5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\ 20869 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\ 20870 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20871 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 20872 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 20873 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)))) \times -1) \\ 20874 &:= (-98 \times -(((7 + (6 + 5)) \times (4 \times 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 20875 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20876 &:= ((-9 + (((87 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) + 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 20877 &:= (-9 + (((87 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 20878 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 20879 &:= ((((-((98 + 76)) \times (-5 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 20880 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times 6) \times -(5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 20881 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times (4^3)))) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 20882 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 765)) - 4) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 20883 &:= ((-9 - (((87 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 20884 &:= ((((-98 \times (76 - 5)) - 4) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 20885 &:= ((((-98 \times (76 - 5)) - 4) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 20886 &:= ((((-98 \times (76 - 5)) - 4) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 20887 &:= (-9 + (((-8 + 7) + 654) \times (32 \times (1)))) \\ 20888 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 + 1))) \\ 20889 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 20890 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\ 20891 &:= ((((-9 + 87) + (((6^5) \times 4) / 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 20892 &:= (((-9 + 87) + (((6^5) \times 4) / 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 20893 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 20894 &:= (-9 - (((876 - 5) \times ((-4 \times 3) \times 2)) - (-1))) \\ 20895 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 20896 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times -(54 \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 20897 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times -(54 \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 20898 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) / 5) \times -(((4^3) \times 2) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20899 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (6 \times (78 - 9))) \\ 20900 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times 5 + 6! \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 20901 &:= (-123 - ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\ 20902 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + (4! + 5) \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 20903 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 - (78 \times 9))))))) \\ 20904 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (-3 \times 45))) \times (-67) - 89) \\ 20905 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 34)) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 20906 &:= (((-1 - 234) \times (-((5 + 6) - 78)) + (-9)) \\ 20907 &:= (((-1 + (2345)) - ((6 + 7) + 8)) \times 9) \\ 20908 &:= (1 + (23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 789))) \\ 20909 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 20910 &:= (1 \times (-(((2 + 3) \times (45 + 6))) \times (7 - 89))) \\ 20911 &:= -1 + 2^3 \times (4 + 5 \times 6 \times (78 + 9)) \\ 20912 &:= 1 \times 2^3 \times (4 + 5 \times 6 \times (78 + 9)) \\ 20913 &:= 1 + 2^3 \times (4 + 5 \times 6 \times (78 + 9)) \\ 20914 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 - 45) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 20915 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) - 5)) \times 6)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 20916 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((34 + 5) \times (67 \times -8)) - 9)) \\ 20917 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 - 45) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 20918 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 20919 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9) \\ 20920 &:= (1 - (((2 - (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 20921 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((34 + 5) \times 67)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 20922 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 20923 &:= ((-12 + (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 20924 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (45 + 6))) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 20925 &:= -((-1 \times (-(((2 + 34) - 5)) \times ((67 + 8) \times -9)))) \\ 20926 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 20927 &:= (1 \times (2 \times 3)^4 - 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 20928 &:= (((-12 + (3^4)) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 20929 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 20930 &:= ((-1 - (-23 - 4)) \times (-5 + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 20931 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) - (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))) \\ 20932 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 20933 &:= ((1 - (2^{3+4})) + ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) \times 9)) \\ 20934 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\ 20935 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))))) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9)) \\ 20936 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 20937 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9) \\ 20938 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20899 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - 65))) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 20900 &:= ((-9 + ((87 + (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 20901 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 20902 &:= (-9 + (((87 + (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 20903 &:= (((-9 - ((87 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) + 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 20904 &:= (((-9 - 8) - 7) - (654 \times -((32 \times (1)))))) \\ 20905 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times -((4 \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\ 20906 &:= ((((-9 \times ((87 + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 20907 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 - 1)))))) \\ 20908 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\ 20909 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 20910 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -(5 + (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 20911 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 20912 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - (7 - 6))^5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1) \\ 20913 &:= (((98 \times -7) - (6 - (5 \times 4321)))) \\ 20914 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1))) \\ 20915 &:= -98 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4 \times 3)^2 + 1 \\ 20916 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) - (-((6 \times 54) \times 3)) \times 21) \\ 20917 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 20918 &:= (((-9 - 8) + 7) - ((-654 \times -32) \times (-1))) \\ 20919 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 20920 &:= ((-9 - (-8 + 7)) + (654 \times (32 \times (1)))) \\ 20921 &:= (((9 - 8) - 7) + ((654 \times 32) - (1))) \\ 20922 &:= (((9 - 8) \times (-7 - (654 \times -32))) + ((1))) \\ 20923 &:= (((-98 + 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\ 20924 &:= ((9 \times ((-8 - 7) + ((65 \times (4 + 32)))))) - (1) \\ 20925 &:= ((9 \times (87 + 6)) \times (5 - (-4 \times (((3 \times 2) - 1)))))) \\ 20926 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -((6 + 5) + ((4 \times 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 20927 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - (((5^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\ 20928 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 20929 &:= ((-((-9 + 8))^7) + (654 \times -(-((32 \times (1)))))) \\ 20930 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 20931 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times 6))) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\ 20932 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4^3)^2 - 1 \\ 20933 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4^3)^2 \times 1 \\ 20934 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4^3)^2 + 1 \\ 20935 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 20936 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3^2))) - 1)) \\ 20937 &:= ((-9 \times (-8 + 7)) - (-654 \times (32 \times (1)))) \\ 20938 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (654 \times 32)) \times -1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20939 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 \times 78 - 9 \\
 20940 &:= (12 \times (((3^4) + ((5^6))) - (-7 + 8))/9) \\
 20941 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 20942 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 34)) \times ((-567) - 8) + 9) \\
 20943 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9) \\
 20944 &:= (((1^2) + 3) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 20945 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 20946 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
 20947 &:= ((12 + (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 20948 &:= -(((12^3) - (4 \times (5678 - 9)))) \\
 20949 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 20950 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 20951 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
 20952 &:= ((12 \times (((3 \times 45) + 67) - 8)) \times 9) \\
 20953 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 20954 &:= (-((-1 - 2) - (((34 \times (5 + 6)) \times -7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 20955 &:= (((1 \times 2) - (-34 \times (((5 + 6) \times 7) \times 8))) + 9) \\
 20956 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 \times 78) + 9))) \\
 20957 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times -5)) \times ((6 \times 78)/9))) \\
 20958 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 34) + (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 20959 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 67 \times 89) \\
 20960 &:= (((1 \times (2 - 34)) \times 5) \times -(((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\
 20961 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times 9) \\
 20962 &:= (((1 - (-2 - 34)) \times 567) - (8 + 9)) \\
 20963 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 67 \times 89) \\
 20964 &:= (12 \times (((-(3 - 45)) \times -6) \times -7) + (-8 + (-9))) \\
 20965 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 67)) - 89) \\
 20966 &:= (-1 + 23) \times (4^5 - 6 - 7 \times 8 - 9) \\
 20967 &:= (-1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 - 89) \\
 20968 &:= (((1 \times -23) \times 4) + ((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 20969 &:= (1 - ((23 \times 4) + (((5 \times 6) \times 78) \times -9))) \\
 20970 &:= ((((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) - 8) \times -9) \\
 20971 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 \times (7 - 89))) \\
 20972 &:= ((-1 + ((-2 + (3 - (45 \times 6))) \times -(78))) - 9) \\
 20973 &:= (-(-1) \times (((-2 + (3 - (45 \times 6))) \times -(78)) - 9)) \\
 20974 &:= ((1 + (((2 - 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times 78)) - 9) \\
 20975 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20976 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
 20977 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20939 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) - (32 + 1)) \\
 20940 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) - (32 \times 1)) \\
 20941 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((54 \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
 20942 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (32 + 1))) \\
 20943 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 20944 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))))) \\
 20945 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\
 20946 &:= (98 \times 7 \times 6 - 5^4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 20947 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 20948 &:= (((-98 \times (((7 \times 6) \times -5) - 4)) - 3) - 21) \\
 20949 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\
 20950 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4^3)^2 - 1 \\
 20951 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 20952 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 - 4^3)^2 + 1 \\
 20953 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))^2 \times 1)) \\
 20954 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 20955 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 20956 &:= (-98 + (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (32 + 1))) \\
 20957 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + 6)) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
 20958 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 20959 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2} + 1)))) \\
 20960 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\
 20961 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 20962 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times (3^2)) + 1) \\
 20963 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 20964 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
 20965 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 20966 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 20967 &:= (-9 \times 87 + 6^5 - 4) \times 3 \times (2 - 1) \\
 20968 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 20969 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - ((3^2) - 1)))) \\
 20970 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times (((4^3) \times 2) + 1)))) \\
 20971 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\
 20972 &:= (-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + ((4 + 3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 20973 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times ((6 - (5 - 4)^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 20974 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 20975 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 20976 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times -65)) \times ((-43 - 2) - (1))) \\
 20977 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20978 &:= (1234 \times ((-5 - 67) + (89))) \\
 20979 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)/5) \times -((6 - (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 20980 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
 20981 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
 20982 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 67)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 20983 &:= (1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 - 6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\
 20984 &:= 123 \times 4^5 / 6 - 7 + 8 - 9 \\
 20985 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20986 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -((45 \times 67) - (8 + 9))) \\
 20987 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 34) \times (5 \times (6 + 7))) - 8) \times 9) \\
 20988 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))))) + 8) \times -9) \\
 20989 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20990 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 20991 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 34))) - ((5 \times 6) \times (-78) \times 9)) \\
 20992 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times ((5 \times (6 + 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
 20993 &:= (1 - ((2 - 34) \times (567 + 89))) \\
 20994 &:= (-1 + ((23 - 4) \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 20995 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4)) \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 20996 &:= (((1 - (-2 - 34)) \times 567) + (8 + 9)) \\
 20997 &:= ((-1 - (((2 + 34) \times (5 \times (6 + 7))) - 8)) \times -9) \\
 20998 &:= -1 + 2 + (-3 - 4 + 78 \times 5 \times 6) \times 9 \\
 20999 &:= (-1 \times -23 \times (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 21000 &:= ((123 + 45) \times -((-6 - (7 \times (8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21001 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\
 21002 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + ((67 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21003 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3^4) - (5 - (6 \times 7))) \times 89))) \\
 21004 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (((4 + 5) \times 6) - 7))) \times -89) \\
 21005 &:= (-1 + ((23 + 4) \times -((5 + 6) - (-789)))) \\
 21006 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3)^4) - ((5 + 6) + (7 \times 8))) \times 9) \\
 21007 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((67 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21008 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times -5)) \times ((6 \times 78)/9)) \\
 21009 &:= (((12 \times (3 \times 4) + 5) \times -((-6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 21010 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 21011 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 21012 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 21013 &:= (1 - (((23 - (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9)) \\
 21014 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) - (45 \times 6)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 21015 &:= (-(((12 \times 3) + (45 \times -((6 \times 78)))) - 9) \\
 21016 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)^5 + 6 \times 78 \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20978 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1 \\
 20979 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 20980 &:= (((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) + (3^2)) - 1) \\
 20981 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 20982 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 20983 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) - 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20984 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 \times (-5 - 432)) - (1))) \\
 20985 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\
 20986 &:= ((-9 - (((87 + (6^5)) \times 4)/3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 20987 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)) \times (3^2)))) - 1) \\
 20988 &:= (-9 + (-((8 \times 76)) - (-((5 \times 432)))) \\
 20989 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4^3)^2 - 1 \\
 20990 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 20991 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4^3)^2 + 1 \\
 20992 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times -(4^{3+2-1})) \\
 20993 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3)/2)) + 1) \\
 20994 &:= ((987 + 6) + ((5^4) \times 32)) - (-1) \\
 20995 &:= (((98 - 7) - 6) \times (-5 + (4 \times ((3 \times 21)))) \\
 20996 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times 54) - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\
 20997 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)) \times (3^2)) + 1))) \\
 20998 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 20999 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) + (3^{2+1})) \\
 21000 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21001 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 - (6 - (5 + 4)))^3) \times 21)) \\
 21002 &:= (9876 + 5^4) \times (3 - 2 + 1) \\
 21003 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
 21004 &:= ((98 \times (((7 \times 6) \times 5) + 4)) + ((32 \times 1))) \\
 21005 &:= (-(((9 - 87) - (654 \times 32))) - (1)) \\
 21006 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 76)) + (5 \times 432))) \\
 21007 &:= (-(((9 - 87) - (654 \times 32))) + (1)) \\
 21008 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 21009 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -5 + ((4 \times 3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 21010 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -5 + ((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 21011 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 21012 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21013 &:= (((98 \times (-7 \times 6)) \times -5) + (432 + 1)) \\
 21014 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((65 \times 4) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21015 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) + (4 - 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 21016 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) + (4 - 3))^2 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21017 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3+4)^5 + 6 \times 78 \times 9 \\
 21018 &:= -1^2 + (3+4)^5 + 6 \times 78 \times 9 \\
 21019 &:= (-1+2) \times ((3+4)^5 + 6 \times 78 \times 9) \\
 21020 &:= -1 + 2 + (3+4)^5 + 6 \times 78 \times 9 \\
 21021 &:= (((1 \times 2) - ((-3-4)^5)) + ((6 \times 78) \times 9)) \\
 21022 &:= (((-1+2) - 3) - ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\
 21023 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3^4) + (5 \times (6+7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21024 &:= (((1 - ((2 + (3+45)) \times 6)) + 7) \times (-(-8) \times -9)) \\
 21025 &:= (1 - (((2+3) + (4 \times -(56))) \times (7+89))) \\
 21026 &:= ((-1+2) \times -(34 - (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 21027 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\
 21028 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21029 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))))) \times -(8+9)) \\
 21030 &:= (((-1 \times 23) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7+8))) + 9) \\
 21031 &:= ((12 - ((-3-4)^5)) - ((6 \times -(78)) \times 9)) \\
 21032 &:= ((-1+23) \times ((4 \times 5) + ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21033 &:= (-(((12 \times 3) + (45 \times -((6 \times 78)))) + 9) \\
 21034 &:= ((-1+2) + (((3+4) \times (5 \times 67)) - 8) \times 9) \\
 21035 &:= (((-1 \times (2-3)) + 4) \times (-5 - (-6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 21036 &:= (-(((12+3) + (45 \times -((6 \times 78)))) - 9) \\
 21037 &:= -((((-1) - 23) \times ((4^5) - 67)) + (8+9)) \\
 21038 &:= (12 - (34 + (((-5 \times 6) \times 78) \times 9)) \\
 21039 &:= -((((1+2) \times (3+4)) - ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) \times 9)) \\
 21040 &:= ((-((1+23)) + 4) - ((-5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9)) \\
 21041 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((4-56) \times (7+8)))) \times 9) \\
 21042 &:= (((-1-2) \times (34 \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) + 8) \times -9) \\
 21043 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 \times 45) \times (-6-7))) - (8 - (-9))) \\
 21044 &:= (((-1 + (2+3)) \times -4) + (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 21045 &:= ((-1-23) + (((45 \times 6) \times 78) + 9) \\
 21046 &:= (((((-1 + (2+3))^4) \times 5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8+9)) \\
 21047 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 + (34 \times (5+6))) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 21048 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 21049 &:= ((1 - ((2^3) + 4)) + ((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 21050 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (56 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))))) \\
 21051 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7+8)))) \times 9) \\
 21052 &:= (-((12^3)) + ((4 \times (5 \times 67)) \times (8+9)) \\
 21053 &:= (((1-2) \times 3) - 4) + (((5 \times 6) \times 78) \times 9) \\
 21054 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times 6 \times 78 \times 9 \\
 21055 &:= (((-1 + ((2+3)^4)) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9) \\
 21056 &:= (((1+2) - (3+4)) + ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21017 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) + (4 - 3))^2) + 1)) \\
 21018 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)) + (5^4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\
 21019 &:= ((((-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6))^5))/4) \times -(3+2)) - 1) \\
 21020 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6))^5))/4) \times -((3+2) \times 1)) \\
 21021 &:= ((98 - 7) \times ((-6 \times (5 - 43)) + (2 + (1)))) \\
 21022 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times -((4+3)^2)) + 1) \\
 21023 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times 76) + (54 \times 32))) - (1)) \\
 21024 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times ((7+6) - (5 \times ((4^3) - (2+1)))) \\
 21025 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times 76) + (54 \times 32))) + (1)) \\
 21026 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4+3))))^2) + 1) \\
 21027 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times ((6 - (5 - 4))^3))) \times -(2+1)) \\
 21028 &:= (((-(-9) + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times 54)) + (-32 \times (1))) \\
 21029 &:= ((-((9+87)) + ((65 \times (4+321)))) \\
 21030 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 + ((6 - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2))) + 1) \\
 21031 &:= (((-98+7) \times -6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 21032 &:= (((98+7) + (654 \times 32)) - (1)) \\
 21033 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (7 \times 6)) + ((5+4)^3)) \times (2+1))) \\
 21034 &:= ((98+7) + ((654 \times 32) + (1))) \\
 21035 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 4)) + (3 \times 21)) \\
 21036 &:= (((9 - (-8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times 54)) - (3+21)) \\
 21037 &:= ((9 \times ((87 \times 6) - 5)) - (-4^{3 \times 2+1})) \\
 21038 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 21039 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + 6)) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\
 21040 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5)/4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 21041 &:= ((-9 \times (((8+7) \times (6 - (54 \times 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 21042 &:= (((-9-8) - ((7 + (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))^2)) \times -1) \\
 21043 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + 6)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 21044 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - ((4^3) + 2))) - 1) \\
 21045 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6) \times (-5 + 4^3 + 2 \times 1) \\
 21046 &:= ((-9-8) \times ((7 \times 6) - (5 \times (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
 21047 &:= (((9-87) + (65 \times (4+321)))) \\
 21048 &:= ((((-98+7) - 6) \times -((5 \times 43) + 2)) - 1) \\
 21049 &:= (((98 \times 7) - 6) - (5-4)) \times (32 - ((1))) \\
 21050 &:= (((-9 \times (87+6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 21051 &:= (-9 \times -(((8+7) \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + (3 \times 2)))) - 1)) \\
 21052 &:= ((-9 \times ((8-7) - ((65 \times 4) \times (3^2)))) + 1) \\
 21053 &:= (((-9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 21054 &:= (((-987 - (6 \times -5)) \times -((43-21)))) \\
 21055 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
 21056 &:= (((-9-87) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1})))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21057 &:= ((1^{23}) - (4 + (((5 \times 6) \times 78) \times -9))) & 21057 &:= (-((9 \times -87)) - (-654 \times ((32 - 1)))) \\ 21058 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 - 56) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 21058 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (54 \times 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 21059 &:= (-1 - (((-234) \times 5) \times (-6 + ((7 + 8) + 9)))) & 21059 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times 6) + (5 \times (4321))) \\ 21060 &:= ((1^{2 \times 3 + 4}) \times ((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) & 21060 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 21061 &:= ((1^{2 \times 3 + 4}) + ((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) & 21061 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2)) + 1) \\ 21062 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((34 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) & 21062 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))/2)) - 1) \\ 21063 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times ((3^4) + 5)) + 6)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))) & 21063 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) + (((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) + 1))) \\ 21064 &:= -(((1 + 2) - (3 + 4)) - ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) \times 9)) & 21064 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\ 21065 &:= ((1^{23}) - (-4 + (((5 \times 6) \times 78) \times -9))) & 21065 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times 54)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 21066 &:= (((12 + 3) - ((45 \times -(6 \times 78)))) - 9) & 21066 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times 54)) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 21067 &:= (-1 - (23 \times ((4 \times 5) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 21067 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times 54)) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 21068 &:= (-1 \times (23 \times ((4 \times 5) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 21068 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + ((65 \times 4) \times (3^2)))) - 1) \\ 21069 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3 + 4)) + ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) & 21069 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + (3 \times 2)))) + 1)) \\ 21070 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3 + 4)) + ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) & 21070 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 21071 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) + 4)) + (((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) & 21071 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 21072 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) + 4) + ((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) & 21072 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\ 21073 &:= (-(((1 - 2) - 3)) - (((45 \times 6) \times -(78)) - 9)) & 21073 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) \times 4))/3) \times -2) + 1) \\ 21074 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)))))) & 21074 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 76)) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2} - 1))) \\ 21075 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 \times 4) + (((-5 \times 6) \times 78) \times -9))) & 21075 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 76) \times (5 - (4^{3 + 2 - 1})))) \\ 21076 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 21076 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) - 5) \times -((43 + 2) - 1)) \\ 21077 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) & 21077 &:= (((-9 \times -(87 \times 6)) - 5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\ 21078 &:= (-1 \times -((2 - (3 \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) & 21078 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\ 21079 &:= (((1 \times 23) - 4) - (((5 \times 6) \times 78) \times -9)) & 21079 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((-7 - 654) \times 32) + 1)) \\ 21080 &:= (((1 + (23 - 4)) \times (-5 + 67)) \times (8 + 9)) & 21080 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 \times 5^4 / 3 - 2 - 1) \\ 21081 &:= 12^{3-4+5} + 6 \times 7 \times 8 + 9 & 21081 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times -((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 21082 &:= ((-12 + 34) - (((-5 \times 6) \times 78) \times 9)) & 21082 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 21083 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 \times 4)) + (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 21083 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 - 32)) - 1) \\ 21084 &:= (((12 + 3) - ((45 \times -(6 \times 78)))) + 9) & 21084 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) \times (5 - (4^{3 + 2 - 1}))) \\ 21085 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)))))) & 21085 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 - 32)) + 1) \\ 21086 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)))))) & 21086 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) - 1) \\ 21087 &:= ((12 \times 3) - ((45 \times -(6 \times 78))) + 9) & 21087 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 4)))) + 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 21088 &:= (((1 + 23) + 4) - (((5 \times 6) \times 78) \times -9)) & 21088 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times -((5 \times 43) - 2)) + 1) \\ 21089 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - ((-4 + ((-5 \times -6) \times -(78))) \times 9)) & 21089 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\ 21090 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 21090 &:= (((-9 + ((876 + 5) \times 4)) \times -3) \times -((2 \times (1)))) \\ 21091 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 21091 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 76)) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 21092 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) \times 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) & 21092 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - 76)) + (5 \times (4^{3 + 2 + 1}))) \\ 21093 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((-34) \times 5) - 67) \times 89) & 21093 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 + 5) + (4^{3 + 2 - 1}))) \\ 21094 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 21094 &:= (9 - 8 + 7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4!) - 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\ 21095 &:= -(((1 - (2 + 34)) - (-5 \times (-6 \times (-78) \times -9)))) & 21095 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6^5)) \times 4)/3) \times -2) - 1) \\ 21096 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((-34) \times 5) - 67) \times 89) & 21096 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 \times 5^4 / 3 - 2) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21097 &:= (((-1 - (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times 6) + 7) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 21098 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((34 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) \\
 21099 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 21100 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\
 21101 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9))) \\
 21102 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times 3) + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9))) \\
 21103 &:= -1 + 2^3 + (4 + 5 \times 6 \times 78) \times 9 \\
 21104 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))) \\
 21105 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 + 5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 21106 &:= ((12 + 34) - (((-5 \times 6) \times 78) \times 9)) \\
 21107 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4)^5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 21108 &:= (-12 \times (((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 21109 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 89 \\
 21110 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
 21111 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
 21112 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (34 \times (((5 + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 21113 &:= (-1 + (-2 \times (3 \times -((45 + 6) \times (78 - 9)))))) \\
 21114 &:= (-((1 \times -2)) \times (-3 \times -((45 + 6) \times (78 - 9)))) \\
 21115 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (34 \times (((5 + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 21116 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (-34 \times (((5 + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 21117 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7 - 8) \times 9 \\
 21118 &:= ((-1 + 23) + ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\
 21119 &:= (-1 \times (-23 + ((-4 + (-5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9))) \\
 21120 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) + (4 \times -(56)))) \times (7 + 89)) \\
 21121 &:= (-12 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 21122 &:= (((-1 + (-2 \times 3)) \times -(45 \times 67)) - ((-8 - 9))) \\
 21123 &:= (((1 + 2345) \times (-6 - (-7 - 8))) + 9) \\
 21124 &:= ((1^2) + (((3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\
 21125 &:= (-((1 + ((2 \times 3) \times 4)) \times (-56) - (789))) \\
 21126 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6))) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9) \\
 21127 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 34)) + ((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 21128 &:= ((-1 \times -((2 \times 34)) + ((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 21129 &:= (-12 + (-3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (789)))))) \\
 21130 &:= ((1 - (-((-2 + 3) - (45 \times -6))) \times 78) - 9) \\
 21131 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 21132 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) - 8) \times -9) \\
 21133 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 21134 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 21135 &:= (-1 \times -2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 21136 &:= (-12 + (34 \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times 89)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21097 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 \times 5^4 / 3 - 2 \times 1) \\
 21098 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 \times 5^4 / 3 - 2) + 1 \\
 21099 &:= (((-98 + ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21100 &:= (((-98 + ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21101 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) + (-65 \times ((4 + 321)))))) \\
 21102 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21103 &:= (((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times 2) + 1) \\
 21104 &:= ((-9 \times -(((87 + 6) \times 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 21105 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 21106 &:= ((-9 \times -(((87 + 6) \times 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 21107 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 + (5 \times 4321))) \\
 21108 &:= (((-9 \times 87) + ((6^5) + 43)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 21109 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
 21110 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4^3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 21111 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21112 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4^3) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 21113 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + (4^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 21114 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times (5^4)) - 3) / (2 + 1)))) \\
 21115 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + (4^3))) + (2 - 1)) \\
 21116 &:= ((-9 + (-8 \times (-7 - 654))) \times (3 - (-2 - ((-1)))))) \\
 21117 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - 7) + (-65 \times -((4 + 321)))))) \\
 21118 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3))) - 21) \\
 21119 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 21120 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 + 5)) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 21121 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 21122 &:= ((-9 \times -87) + ((6 + 5) \times (43^2 \times 1))) \\
 21123 &:= (((((9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times 54) - ((-3 \times 21))) \\
 21124 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(65 \times ((4 + 3) - 2))) - 1) \\
 21125 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2) + 1)) \\
 21126 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 32)) + 1))) \\
 21127 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21128 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) / 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21129 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4^3) \times 2))) \times -1) \\
 21130 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21131 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 21132 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 \times 5^4 / 3) + 2 - 1 \\
 21133 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 \times 5^4 / 3) + 2 \times 1 \\
 21134 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 \times 5^4 / 3) + 2 + 1 \\
 21135 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(4 + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21136 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (-((7 + 654) \times 32)) + ((1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$21137 := 1 \times 2 \times 3!! + 4 \times (-5! + 6! \times 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$21138 := (-((1 + 2)) - ((3 \times (4 + 5)) \times (6 - 789)))$$

$$21139 := ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times 9)))$$

$$21140 := (-1 + ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) + 9)))$$

$$21141 := (((12 - 34) - 5) \times (6 - (789)))$$

$$21142 := -(((-1 + 23) \times (-4 + ((5 + 6) \times (-78) - 9))))$$

$$21143 := ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times 9)))$$

$$21144 := (1 \times (-((2 \times 3)) \times (-(-4) - ((56 - 7) \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$21145 := ((-1 - 2) + (34 \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times 89))))$$

$$21146 := ((-12 \times 3) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89)))$$

$$21147 := (-1 + (2 \times (34 \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))))$$

$$21148 := (-1 \times -2 \times (34 \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))))$$

$$21149 := (1 \times (((2^3)^4) \times 5) - (-678 + 9))$$

$$21150 := ((1 + 234) \times ((5 + 6) + (7 - (-8 \times 9))))$$

$$21151 := (-((1 - (23 \times 4))) - (((5 \times 6) \times 78) \times -9))$$

$$21152 := ((1 \times (23 \times 4)) - (((5 \times 6) \times 78) \times -9))$$

$$21153 := (1 - (-((23 \times 4)) + (((5 \times 6) \times 78) \times -9)))$$

$$21154 := (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((67 + 8) \times 9)))$$

$$21155 := (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9)$$

$$21156 := (-12 + (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$21157 := (1 - (2 \times (((3 \times 45) - 6) \times (7 - 89))))$$

$$21158 := ((-1 - 23) + ((4 + (-5 \times -6)) \times (7 \times 89)))$$

$$21159 := ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)$$

$$21160 := ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))$$

$$21161 := (1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 - 5 + 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9)$$

$$21162 := (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9))$$

$$21163 := ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))$$

$$21164 := (((1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times -5)) \times ((6 \times 78) / 9))$$

$$21165 := ((-1 + (((2 \times ((3^4) + 5)) + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$21166 := ((-1 + (((2^3)^4) \times 5)) + (678 + 9))$$

$$21167 := (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$21168 := (((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))$$

$$21169 := ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$21170 := (-1 \times -2 + (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$21171 := ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)))$$

$$21172 := (((1 - ((2^3) \times 45)) \times -((67 - 8))) - 9)$$

$$21173 := (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8)))) + 9)$$

$$21174 := ((-1 - 2) + (((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 67)) + 8) \times 9)$$

$$21175 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89)))$$

$$21176 := (-1 \times ((2 \times 3) - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89))))$$

$$21137 := (((9 - 87) \times 6) + (5 \times (4321)))$$

$$21138 := ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 \times 1))$$

$$21139 := (((98/7) + (-65 \times (-4 - 321)))$$

$$21140 := (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 - 1)))$$

$$21141 := (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 + 1)))$$

$$21142 := (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1)))$$

$$21143 := (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (((54 - 3)^2) + 1))))$$

$$21144 := (((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 65) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1)$$

$$21145 := ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 65) - 4) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1))$$

$$21146 := (((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 65) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)$$

$$21147 := (((-9 - 8) \times -((((7 - 6) \times 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1)$$

$$21148 := ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times (5^4)) + 3) / (2 + 1))))$$

$$21149 := (((-9 - 8) \times -((((7 - 6) \times 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1)$$

$$21150 := ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times (5 \times ((4 \times 3) + (2 + 1))))$$

$$21151 := (9 - 8) \times (7 + 654) \times 32 - 1$$

$$21152 := (9 - 8) \times (7 + 654) \times 32 \times 1$$

$$21153 := (9 - 8) \times (7 + 654) \times 32 + 1$$

$$21154 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(4 + 3)) + 21)$$

$$21155 := ((-9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3)) + 2)) \times -1)$$

$$21156 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times -((54 \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))$$

$$21157 := ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times -(2 - 1))$$

$$21158 := ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times (54 + (3^2)))) - 1)$$

$$21159 := (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + (2 + 1))))$$

$$21160 := ((((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times 4) \times -((3^2) + 1))$$

$$21161 := (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 - 4)) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1))$$

$$21162 := ((-9 - ((876 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 \times 1))$$

$$21163 := (((-9 - ((876 + 5) \times (4 \times 3))) \times -2) + 1)$$

$$21164 := (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - 6) + (((5^4) - 3) \times 2))) - 1)$$

$$21165 := ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 \times 3)))))) - (2 + 1))$$

$$21166 := 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (-5 + 4 \times 3) - 2 \times 1$$

$$21167 := (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (6 - 5)))) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)$$

$$21168 := (-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (((6 + 5) - 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))$$

$$21169 := (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (6 - 5)))) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)$$

$$21170 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))$$

$$21171 := ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 + 1))$$

$$21172 := -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 - 2 - 1$$

$$21173 := -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$21174 := -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 - 2 + 1$$

$$21175 := (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4^3 \times (2 - 1))))$$

$$21176 := -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 + 2 - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21177 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 8)))))) \times -9) \\
 21178 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 67)) + 8) \times 9) \\
 21179 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 67)) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 21180 &:= (-((1 \times 2) + ((34 \times (5 - 6)) \times -7) \times 89)) \\
 21181 &:= (1 + (-2 + ((34 \times (5 - 6)) \times (-7 \times 89))) \\
 21182 &:= (((1 \times (234 - 56)) \times 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 21183 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (45 + 6))) \times (78 - 9)) \\
 21184 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - (34 \times ((5 - 6) \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
 21185 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9) \\
 21186 &:= (((1 - (2345 \times (6 - 7))) + 8) \times 9) \\
 21187 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4} + (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 21188 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4} + (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 21189 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 21190 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 + 6) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 21191 &:= (-12 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21192 &:= (((1 \times -2) \times 3) \times (-4 - (((56 - 7) \times 8) \times 9)) \\
 21193 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4} \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 21194 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4} \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 21195 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4} + (5 \times 6))) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 21196 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21197 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + 3) - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21198 &:= ((((-12 - 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 21199 &:= (((((1 \times 2) \times 3)^4) - (56 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 21200 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21201 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9) \\
 21202 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21203 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21204 &:= (((1 - 234) + 5) \times (-6 - (78 + 9)) \\
 21205 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9) \\
 21206 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 78))) - 9) \\
 21207 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 21208 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 21209 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89)) \\
 21210 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21211 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 - (4! - 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 21212 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! + (-4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 21213 &:= ((((-12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times 9) \\
 21214 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5 - 6) - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 21215 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 34) - 5) \times 6) \times - (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 21216 &:= (12 \times (-34) \times ((5 \times 6) + (7 - 89)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21177 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 21178 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 21179 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 + 65)) - 4) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\
 21180 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + 65)) - 4) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 21181 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21182 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times (5^4))/3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21183 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 21184 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times (4^3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 21185 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 \times 3)))) - 2)) - 1) \\
 21186 &:= (((((-9 - 8) - 7) - 6) \times 5) + 4) \times -321) \\
 21187 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21188 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21189 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 21190 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 - 2 - 1 \\
 21191 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 21192 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 - 2 + 1 \\
 21193 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 \times (2 - 1) \\
 21194 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 - 5) \times 4^3 + 2 - 1 \\
 21195 &:= -(((9 \times -87) + (6 \times ((54 \times -((3 \times 21)))))) \\
 21196 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - (5 \times (4^3)))/2)) + 1) \\
 21197 &:= ((-98 + (((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 21198 &:= (-98 + (((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 21199 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 21200 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -(4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21201 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -(4 + 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21202 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -(4 + 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 21203 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((4 + 3) \times (2 - 1))) \\
 21204 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21205 &:= (9 + (-8 - (((-76 \times (5 + 4)) \times (32 - 1)))) \\
 21206 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -(4 + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21207 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3/(2 + 1)))) \\
 21208 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 - 2))) - 1)) \\
 21209 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4))) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21210 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4))) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21211 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4))) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 21212 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 21213 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 21214 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 21215 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (76 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21216 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21217 &:= ((-1+2) - (34 \times ((5-6) - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 21218 &:= ((-12 \times -3) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89))) \\
 21219 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times 4)) \times (5 + ((6-78) \times 9))) \\
 21220 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 + (-4! + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 21221 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3+45) \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) \times 9) \\
 21222 &:= ((-12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times ((7-8) \times 9))) \\
 21223 &:= (1 + (((2+3) \times 456) + 78) \times 9) \\
 21224 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 78)) + 9)) \\
 21225 &:= (((-1-2) \times -(((3^4) \times (5+6)) - 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 21226 &:= (((-1-2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7)) - 89) \\
 21227 &:= (1 - 23)^4 / (5 + 6) - 78 + 9 \\
 21228 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) - (6 \times (7 - 89))) \\
 21229 &:= (1 + 2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 21230 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 21231 &:= ((-(((1 \times 23) - 4)) - ((5 \times 6) \times 78)) \times -9) \\
 21232 &:= (1 + ((-(-23) + (-4 - (-5 \times (6 \times 78)))) \times 9)) \\
 21233 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 \times 3))^4) - (5 + (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 21234 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 21235 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
 21236 &:= (((((1 \times 2)^3)^4) \times 5) + ((6 + 78) \times 9)) \\
 21237 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 + 45) \times 6) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 21238 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 21239 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - (45)) \times (67 - 8)) \times 9) \\
 21240 &:= (((1 - 234) + (5 - 67)) \times -((8 \times 9))) \\
 21241 &:= -((-1 + (((2 + 3) - (45)) \times (67 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 21242 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3 + 45) \times 6) + 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 21243 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 21244 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) - 456) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21245 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 34)) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 21246 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 21247 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (34 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 21248 &:= (((12/3)^4) \times ((-5 + ((6 - 7))) + 89)) \\
 21249 &:= ((((-1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times 6) + (7 + 8)) \times -9) \\
 21250 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 21251 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 21252 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (34 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 21253 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((34 + 5) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 21254 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - 45) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 21255 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3 \times 4)) \times (-5 \times (((6 \times 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 21256 &:= 1 \times 2^3 \times ((-4 + 5 \times 67) \times 8 + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21217 &:= ((-98 + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4^3))^2)) - 1) \\
 21218 &:= (-98 + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4^3))^2 \times 1)) \\
 21219 &:= (-98 + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4^3))^2 + 1)) \\
 21220 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (76 \times 5))) \times (4 + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21221 &:= -(((((-9 + 87)) - ((65 \times (4 + 321)))))) \\
 21222 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
 21223 &:= (98 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times (4 + 321)))))) \\
 21224 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 21225 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 21226 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (32 + 1))) \\
 21227 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + 32)) \times -1) \\
 21228 &:= ((-98 - 76) \times (5 - (((4^3) \times 2) - 1))) \\
 21229 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 21)) \\
 21230 &:= ((98 + 7) + (65 \times (4 - (-321)))) \\
 21231 &:= ((-((-9 \times 87)) - (6 \times (5 - 43))) \times 21) \\
 21232 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 21233 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (6 \times ((5 + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 21234 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2))) + 1) \\
 21235 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21236 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 21237 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21238 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 21239 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 21240 &:= (((9 - (-87 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4) - (-32 + 1))) \\
 21241 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^{4+3-2-1}))) \\
 21242 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3/(2 + 1)))) \\
 21243 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21244 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 21245 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21246 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 21247 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21248 &:= (-(((((-9 - 8) + (7 - 654))) \times ((32 \times 1))) \\
 21249 &:= ((9 \times 8) - (((-7 - 6) \times ((543 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 21250 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 21251 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21252 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 21253 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3 \times 2))) \times -1) \\
 21254 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5^4 - 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 21255 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 21256 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times -(2 - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21257 &:= -((1 \times -2)) - ((-34) - 5) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 21258 &:= 12^{3-4+5} + 6 \times (78 + 9) \\
 21259 &:= (1 + ((2 + (((3 + 45) \times 6) + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 21260 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!! - (4 + 5 \times 6)) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\
 21261 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 - 5! + 6! \times (-7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 21262 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5)) - (6 - 789)) \\
 21263 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) + ((67 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21264 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\
 21265 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times (4 - ((5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) \\
 21266 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 34)) \times (-567) - 8) - 9) \\
 21267 &:= (-((1 + 2) \times (3 - ((4 + 56) \times 7)))) \times (8 + 9) \\
 21268 &:= ((-((-1 - ((2^3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 - (789))) \\
 21269 &:= -(-1 + 2^3)^4 + 5 \times 6 \times 789 \\
 21270 &:= (-1 - ((-2 + ((-34) \times 5) - 67)) \times 89) \\
 21271 &:= (((1 \times 2) - (((-34) \times 5) - 67)) \times 89) \\
 21272 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 + (5 \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 21273 &:= ((-12 \times (((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9) \\
 21274 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)))) \\
 21275 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) \\
 21276 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
 21277 &:= (((-12 + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21278 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 - 5 \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9)) \\
 21279 &:= (-123) \times ((4 \times -((56 - (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
 21280 &:= 1 \times 2^3 \times (-4 + (-5 + 6 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9) \\
 21281 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) + ((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 21282 &:= -(((-(-1) + 2) - (((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times 78) - 9))) \\
 21283 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((345 - 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 21284 &:= -(((-(-1234) - (5 + (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 21285 &:= (((1 - 2) + 34) \times (5 \times (-6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 21286 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - 89) \\
 21287 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 78) + 9))) \\
 21288 &:= ((1 + 23) \times -((((45 + 67) \times -8) + 9))) \\
 21289 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 21290 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 21291 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) - 5))) \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 21292 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 21293 &:= ((-1 + 234) + (-((5 \times 6)) \times (-78) \times 9)) \\
 21294 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 - ((4 \times -5) \times (67 - 8))) \times -9)) \\
 21295 &:= ((1 + 234) + (((-5 \times 6)) \times -78) \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21257 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 21258 &:= (-98 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4) \times 3 \times (2 - 1) \\
 21259 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4))) \times -(3/(2 + 1))) \\
 21260 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4))) - (3 - 2)) \times -1) \\
 21261 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21262 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21263 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
 21264 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4))) - (3 + 2)) \times -1) \\
 21265 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4))) - (3 \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 21266 &:= (-((-98 \times 7)) \times (-6 - ((5 - (43 - 2)) - (1)))) \\
 21267 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3))/(2 + 1)))) \\
 21268 &:= 98 \times 7 \times (6 \times 5 + 4 - 3) + 2 \times 1 \\
 21269 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 21270 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2) \times 1) \\
 21271 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 21272 &:= (-9 - (((8 - ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 21273 &:= -((((98 \times (-7 - 6)) - ((5^4) \times 32)) + 1)) \\
 21274 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\
 21275 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3/(2 + 1)))))) \\
 21276 &:= (9 \times 87 + 6 - 5 + 4) \times 3^{2+1} \\
 21277 &:= (((-9 + (((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) - 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21278 &:= (9 + (-(((8 \times 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21279 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 21280 &:= (9 \times 8 \times (7 \times 6 - 5) - 4) \times (3^2 - 1) \\
 21281 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\
 21282 &:= (((-98 \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 21283 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 21284 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 21285 &:= (9 \times (8 + 7) - 6) \times 5 \times (4^3/2 + 1) \\
 21286 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) - 4)^3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21287 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) - 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21288 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) - 4)^3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 21289 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 21290 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2 \times 1} \\
 21291 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) \times 6 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} + 1 \\
 21292 &:= (((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - (5^4)) \times -(3 + 2) - 1) \\
 21293 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21294 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 - 6))) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 21295 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3) \times (2 \times 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21296 &:= (-1 + (((-2 - 34) + 5) \times (-678) - 9)) \\
 21297 &:= (-1 \times -(((-2 - 34) + 5) \times (-678) - 9))) \\
 21298 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (-3 - (((-4^5) + 6) \times -7))) - 89) \\
 21299 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 \times (4^5 - 6)) \times 7 - 8 \times 9 \\
 21300 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7) + 8)) + 9) \\
 21301 &:= ((1 + (234 - 56)) \times (-7 \times -((8 + 9)))) \\
 21302 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times 78)) + 9) \\
 21303 &:= (((((1 + 2) + 34) \times (5 + 67)) \times 8) - 9) \\
 21304 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 21305 &:= ((1 \times 2) + ((3^{4+5-6}) \times 789)) \\
 21306 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
 21307 &:= -(((1 \times 23) + (45 \times (-6 \times -((-7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 21308 &:= ((1 - 23) - ((45 \times -6) \times (7 + ((8 \times 9)))) \\
 21309 &:= (-123 + (456 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 21310 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -7) - 89) \\
 21311 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (34 + 5)) \times -6) \times (7 + 89))) \\
 21312 &:= ((-1 \times (((2^3) - 45) \times 6)) \times (7 + 89)) \\
 21313 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 21314 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 21315 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 21316 &:= (((1 - (2 + 3))^4) + (((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 21317 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 21318 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) \times 5) + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 21319 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times (5 + 6))) + 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
 21320 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 21321 &:= (((((1 + 2) + 34) \times (5 + 67)) \times 8) + 9) \\
 21322 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) - (45 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 21323 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times (-4^5)) + ((67 \times 89))) \\
 21324 &:= (12 \times (-3 - (-((4^5)) - ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
 21325 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 21326 &:= (-((12/3)) + ((45 \times 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21327 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21328 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 21329 &:= (-1 - ((-2 - (3 + 4)) \times ((5 \times 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21330 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 21331 &:= (((((1 + 2) \times 34) \times 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (89)) \\
 21332 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\
 21333 &:= ((-12 + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 8)) - 9) \\
 21334 &:= ((12/3) + ((45 \times 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21296 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times -(7 + (6 + (5 + 4))))^3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21297 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times -(7 + (6 + (5 + 4))))^3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 21298 &:= (((-9 + 8) - ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 21299 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 21300 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4^3))^2) + 1)) \\
 21301 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 21302 &:= ((-(-98) - (76 \times ((-(-5) + 4) \times (-32 + 1)))) \\
 21303 &:= (-9 + ((8 + ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 21304 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 21305 &:= 9 + (8 + 7 + 6 + 5 - 4)^3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 21306 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 21307 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 21308 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 21309 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 21310 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (43 - 2)))) - 1) \\
 21311 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 \times 3)))) - 2))) - 1) \\
 21312 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 21313 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 21314 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) - 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 21315 &:= (((98 + (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4 + 3)) \times 21) \\
 21316 &:= 9 \times (87 + 6) + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\
 21317 &:= (((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -6) - (5 - (4 + 3)))^2) + 1) \\
 21318 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6 \times (5^4))/3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 21319 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 21320 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 + ((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 21321 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 21322 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (-76 \times 5))) \times (-4 - 3)) - 21) \\
 21323 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6) + (5 \times 4321)) \\
 21324 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times 3)) + 21) \\
 21325 &:= ((-9 - ((876/((5 + 4) - 3))^2)) \times -1) \\
 21326 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 32)) - 1) \\
 21327 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3))/(2 + 1)))) \\
 21328 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 - 6))) - (5^4)) \times -(32 - 1)) \\
 21329 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 21330 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (5 \times 4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 21331 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 21332 &:= (((9 + 8) + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4^3))^2)) - 1) \\
 21333 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4^3))^2)) \times -1) \\
 21334 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((-7 + 654) \times (32 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21335 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 21336 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 21337 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times (5 + 6))) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\ 21338 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7 - 8)) \times 9) \\ 21339 &:= (-(-1) + (((23 \times (4 \times 5)) - 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 21340 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 21341 &:= (((((12^3)/4) - 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 21342 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 8))) - 9) \\ 21343 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 - ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 21344 &:= ((12 + 34) \times ((56 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 21345 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + (7 + 8))) + 9) \\ 21346 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 21347 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 21348 &:= ((((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9) \\ 21349 &:= (((-12 - (-3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - 8) - 9) \\ 21350 &:= (((((12^3)/4) - 5) \times (67 - (8 + 9))) \\ 21351 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 21352 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 21353 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + (45 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 21354 &:= ((-1 \times -2) \times (((3^4) + (56)) \times 78) - 9) \\ 21355 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3^4) + 56) \times 78) - 9)) \\ 21356 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\ 21357 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 \times 8))) \times -9) \\ 21358 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 21359 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 21360 &:= (-12 \times (((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times 7) + 89)) \\ 21361 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 21362 &:= 1^2 + 3 \times (4^5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 21363 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 21364 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 21365 &:= -(((12 + (-3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - 8) + 9) \\ 21366 &:= (((((1 - 2) + (345 - 6)) \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\ 21367 &:= ((-1 \times -23) \times ((-4 \times (5 \times (-6 \times 7))) + 89)) \\ 21368 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 21369 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times 5)) - (6 \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 21370 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 \times (4^5 - 6)) \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\ 21371 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 21372 &:= ((1 \times (-2 + (-3 \times 45))) \times -(67 - 89)) \\ 21373 &:= ((12 - (-3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21335 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 21336 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (((5^4) + 3) \times 2))) + 1) \\ 21337 &:= (987 + ((6 + 5) \times ((43^2) + 1))) \\ 21338 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((65 \times (4 + 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\ 21339 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + ((4^3) \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 21340 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 21341 &:= ((9 - (((8 \times -7) + 6) \times (5 - 432))) \times (-1)) \\ 21342 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\ 21343 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 21344 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\ 21345 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 21346 &:= -9 + 876 + 5 \times 4^{3 \times 2} - 1 \\ 21347 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times (54 + 3)) - 2)))) - 1) \\ 21348 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 21349 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times -((4 \times 3^2) + 1)) \\ 21350 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 21351 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 - 6) \times (5^4 + 3) \times 2 - 1 \\ 21352 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 - 6) \times (5^4 + 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\ 21353 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 - 6) \times (5^4 + 3) \times 2 + 1 \\ 21354 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 32)) + 1)) \\ 21355 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (765 \times 4)) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\ 21356 &:= (((-9 \times (876 - ((54 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 21357 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 21358 &:= (((-9 \times (876 - ((54 + 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 21359 &:= -(((9 \times 8) + (-765 + 4)) \times (32 + (-1))) \\ 21360 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 21361 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times -(2 - 1)) \\ 21362 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 32) + 1) \\ 21363 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3))) - 2) \times -1) \\ 21364 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (-76 \times 5))) \times (-4 - 3)) + 21) \\ 21365 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 21366 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5))^4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 21367 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 \times 5^4/3) - 2 \times 1 \\ 21368 &:= (-(-9) - ((-8 - ((-7 + 654) \times (32 + 1)))) \\ 21369 &:= (-9 - ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5 - ((4^{3+2}) - 1)))) \\ 21370 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) + (((5^4) - 3) \times 2))) + 1) \\ 21371 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 \times (5^4))/3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 21372 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 \times (5^4))/3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 21373 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21374 &:= (((-1-2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) + (8+9) \\
 21375 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) + 5))) \times (6 + (7 \times (8+9)))) \\
 21376 &:= ((-1+2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8-9))) \\
 21377 &:= (((-1 + (((2+3)^4) + 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9) \\
 21378 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times -(((4^5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8-9)))) \\
 21379 &:= ((-1+2) - (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8-9)))) \\
 21380 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) - (8+9))) \\
 21381 &:= ((-1-2) + ((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times (7 + (8+9)))) \\
 21382 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times (7 + (8+9)))) \\
 21383 &:= -((((12 + (-3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - 8) - 9)) \\
 21384 &:= ((12^3) + (((45 - 6) \times -7) \times (-8 \times 9))) \\
 21385 &:= (-1 \times (((-2 + 3) - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 21386 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)^4 - 5 \times 6 - 7) \times (8+9) \\
 21387 &:= (1 + ((2 \times ((3 \times -4) - 5)) \times (-6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 21388 &:= ((((-1+2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -7) + (8+9)) \\
 21389 &:= (-1 - (((2+3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + (7+8))) + 9) \\
 21390 &:= (((-1 - 234) + 5) \times (-6 - ((78+9)))) \\
 21391 &:= (((-1+2) + (((3 \times (4^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 21392 &:= ((-1-2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8+9))) \\
 21393 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8+9))) \\
 21394 &:= (((-1+2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + 8)) - 9) \\
 21395 &:= ((12 + (3 - 4)) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9) \\
 21396 &:= (12 \times (3 - ((4^5) - ((6+78) \times 9))) \\
 21397 &:= (((12 - 3)^4) + ((5^6))) - 789 \\
 21398 &:= ((((-1-2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -7) + (8-9)) \\
 21399 &:= ((((-1-2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times (7 \times (8-9))) \\
 21400 &:= ((((-1-2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -7) - (8-9)) \\
 21401 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3 - (4^5))) - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 21402 &:= ((1 + (234 + (5+6))) \times (78+9)) \\
 21403 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 \times 3))^4) + (5 - (6 \times 7))) \times (8+9)) \\
 21404 &:= (((-1-2) \times -(3 + (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + (8+9)) \\
 21405 &:= (1+2) \times (-3 + (4^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 \times 9) \\
 21406 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + 5) \times (6! - 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 21407 &:= ((12 - (-3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) + (8+9)) \\
 21408 &:= (-1 \times ((-23 - (4+5)) \times (678 - 9))) \\
 21409 &:= (((-((1 \times 2)) + 3) - (45 \times -6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 21410 &:= (-1 + (((2345 + (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 21411 &:= ((((-1 + (2+3)) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + (7+8))) - 9) \\
 21412 &:= (-1 + (-23 \times ((-4^5) + ((6+78) + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21374 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (65 + 4))) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 21375 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5 + 4))) \times (3^2)) - 1)) \\
 21376 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (65 + 4))) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 21377 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 21378 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) - ((5^4) + 3)) \times -21) \\
 21379 &:= -(9+8) \times (7+6) + 5!/4 \times (3+2+1)! \\
 21380 &:= (9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5^4)) \times (3 + 2 - 1) \\
 21381 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21382 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21383 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (65 - (4 - 321)))))) \\
 21384 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6))) \times ((54 \times (32 + 1)))) \\
 21385 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - (5 \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21386 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)/(2 + 1)))) \\
 21387 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21388 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4^3))^2 \times 1)) \\
 21389 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (-5 + 4^3)^2 - 1 \\
 21390 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (-5 + 4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 21391 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (-5 + 4^3)^2 + 1 \\
 21392 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 21393 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 21394 &:= (((-98 - (((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 21395 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
 21396 &:= ((9 + 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times 5 - 4) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 21397 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 21398 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 654)) \times 32)) - 1) \\
 21399 &:= (((-98 \times 7) + ((6^5) + 43)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 21400 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + 654)) \times 32) + 1)) \\
 21401 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (65 - (4 - 321)))))) \\
 21402 &:= (((98 + 76) \times ((5 - (4 \times 32)) \times -1)) \\
 21403 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) + ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 21404 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6 \times (5^4))/3) + 2))) + 1) \\
 21405 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)))) + 21) \\
 21406 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (76 + ((54 - 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 21407 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times -32) - 1) \\
 21408 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4^{3+2})))) \times -1) \\
 21409 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 21410 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 21411 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4 + (3^{2+1})))) \\
 21412 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21413 &:= ((1 \times -23) \times -(((4^5) - 6) - (78 + 9))) \\
 21414 &:= -((-1 - (-23 \times ((-4^5) + ((6 + 78) + 9)))) \\
 21415 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21416 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 21417 &:= (-12 + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\
 21418 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 21419 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 21420 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times (5 + ((6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 21421 &:= ((1^2) + ((3 - 45) \times (-6 + (-7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21422 &:= (-1 \times -(-2 - ((3 - 45) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 21423 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((34 \times ((5 \times 6) \times -7)) - (-8 + 9))) \\
 21424 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21425 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (67 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
 21426 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\
 21427 &:= -(((1 \times 2) - (-3 - (-456) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 21428 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (((4^5) - 67) + (8 + 9))) \\
 21429 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 21430 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\
 21431 &:= ((-1^{23}) - (456 \times (-((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 21432 &:= ((-1^{23}) \times (456 \times (-((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 21433 &:= ((1^{23}) + (456 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 21434 &:= (-(((1^2) - 3)) + (456 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 21435 &:= (-((1 - 2) \times (3 - (-456) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 21436 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + (-456) \times (-((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 21437 &:= (-1 \times (((23 \times 4) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times (-8 - 9))) \\
 21438 &:= ((-12 - (-3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7))) - (-8 \times 9)) \\
 21439 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 34) \times (5 - ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 21440 &:= (-(-1) \times ((2 - 34) \times (5 - ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 21441 &:= (-(-1) + ((2 - 34) \times (5 - ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 21442 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (-3 - ((4 \times -5) \times (67 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
 21443 &:= (((1 - (2 + 345)) \times (-6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 21444 &:= ((12^{3-4+5}) + (6 - (-78) \times 9)) \\
 21445 &:= (((12 + (-3 \times -(((4^5) - 6))) \times 7) + (-8 - 9)) \\
 21446 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + ((-4 - (-5 \times -6)) \times -7)) \times 89)) \\
 21447 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21448 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9)) \\
 21449 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times (5 + 6))) - 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
 21450 &:= (-((12 + 3)) - ((45 \times (-((6 \times 78) - 9)))) \\
 21451 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21413 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + 5) \times (4 - (3^{2+1}))) \\
 21414 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times (5 - (((4 + 3)^2) - 1))) \\
 21415 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
 21416 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 21417 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + 6))) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\
 21418 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 76) \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21419 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 21420 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times (6 \times (((5 + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21421 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)))) + 1) \\
 21422 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + (((6^5) \times 4) / 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21423 &:= 98 \times 7 + ((-6 + 54) \times 3)^2 + 1 \\
 21424 &:= ((-9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times 21))) \\
 21425 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (76 + ((54 - 3)^2)))) \times -1) \\
 21426 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (76 + ((54 - 3)^2))) + 1)) \\
 21427 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (765 \times 4)) \times -(3 \times 2) + 1) \\
 21428 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 21429 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\
 21430 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
 21431 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times ((5 - 43) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 21432 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^2))) - 1)) \\
 21433 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times 7) - (654 \times -32)) + (1) \\
 21434 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7! - 6) \times 5 - 4^{3+2+1} \\
 21435 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times 6)) + ((5^4) \times (32 + 1))) \\
 21436 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 21437 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + ((5^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
 21438 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
 21439 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 21440 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -2) \times 1) \\
 21441 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 21442 &:= ((-98 - (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
 21443 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
 21444 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 21445 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\
 21446 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\
 21447 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 + 6) - (((5^4) - 3) / 2))) + 1)) \\
 21448 &:= (((-98 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 21449 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times ((54 + 3) - 2))) - 1) \\
 21450 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times -(5 + (((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 21451 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times (5 - (4 \times (3^2)))) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21452 &:= ((((-1+2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - 6) \times 7) - (8+9)) \\
 21453 &:= ((((-1+2) - 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7+8))) - 9) \\
 21454 &:= (((-1-2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times 7)) - (89)) \\
 21455 &:= (((-1+2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - 6)) \times (7 \times (8-9))) \\
 21456 &:= (((1-234) - (5 \times (6+7))) \times (-8 \times 9)) \\
 21457 &:= ((12 - (((-3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times 7)) + (-8-9)) \\
 21458 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) \times ((4 \times (5 \times (67 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 21459 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - 6)) \times -7) - (8+9)) \\
 21460 &:= (((-1-2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) - (8-9)) \\
 21461 &:= (((1 - (2+345)) \times (-6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\
 21462 &:= -(((1+2) - ((3 \times (4+5)) \times (6+789)))) \\
 21463 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) \times (4 + (-((-5 \times 67) \times 8))) - 9) \\
 21464 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times ((3 - (4 \times ((-5 \times 67) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 21465 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + (3+4))) \times (-5 \times ((6 \times 78) + 9))) \\
 21466 &:= (1 - ((2 - (34-5)) \times (6+789))) \\
 21467 &:= ((((-1+2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times -7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 21468 &:= (12 \times (-3 - ((-4 \times 56) \times (7 + (-8+9)))) \\
 21469 &:= ((((-1+2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - 6) \times -(7 \times (8-9))) \\
 21470 &:= ((((-1+2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - 6) \times 7) - (8-9)) \\
 21471 &:= ((((-1+2) - 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7+8))) + 9) \\
 21472 &:= ((-1+23) \times ((4^5) + (-6 \times (7 - (8-9)))) \\
 21473 &:= ((-1 + (((2-3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7+8)))) - 9) \\
 21474 &:= ((((-1+2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + (7+8))) - 9) \\
 21475 &:= (((-1+2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 21476 &:= (((12 \times -(34)) - 5) \times ((6 \times -(78))/9)) \\
 21477 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - 6) \times 7) + (8+9)) \\
 21478 &:= 1 + (2 + 3 \times 4^5 - 6) \times 7 - 8 + 9 \\
 21479 &:= (((12 + (-3 \times -(((4^5) - 6)))) \times 7) - (-8-9)) \\
 21480 &:= ((12+3) - ((45 \times -((6 \times 78)) - 9))) \\
 21481 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3+4) \times (5+6 \times 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\
 21482 &:= ((1 \times -23) \times -(((4^5) - (-6 - (-7-89)))) \\
 21483 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) - (5 - (6 - (7+8)))) \times 9) \\
 21484 &:= (((1+2) \times -3^4) - (-((5^6)) + (78 \times 9))) \\
 21485 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((3+4) \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 21486 &:= -(((1 + ((234+5) \times -6)) \times (7+8)) + 9) \\
 21487 &:= -1 \times 2^3 + 4^5 \times (6+7+8) - 9 \\
 21488 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + ((4^5) \times (6 + (7+8)))) - 9) \\
 21489 &:= (((-1 - (2+3)) + ((4^5) \times (6 + (7+8)))) - 9) \\
 21490 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + ((-4^5) \times ((6+7) + 8))) + 9)) \\
 21491 &:= ((1-23) - (((-((4^5))) \times ((-6-7) - 8)) - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21452 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times (5 - (4 \times (3 \times (2+1)))) \\
 21453 &:= (((-98 \times ((7 \times (6+5)) - 4) + 3) \times -(2+1)) \\
 21454 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (((6 + ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\
 21455 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6+5))) \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 21456 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4+3)) - (2+1))) \\
 21457 &:= (-((9 \times 8)) + (-76 - (-5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21458 &:= -9 + 8! - 7! + 6 + 5 - 4!^{3!-2-1} \\
 21459 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
 21460 &:= ((987 - (6 - (5 \times ((-4^3)^2)))) + (-1)) \\
 21461 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 + (3+2)))) - 1) \\
 21462 &:= (-98 \times -(((7 + (6+5)) \times (4 \times 3)) + (2+1))) \\
 21463 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2)))) \times -1) \\
 21464 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4+3)) - 2)) - 1) \\
 21465 &:= (-9 \times -((8+7) \times ((6 \times ((5+4) \times 3)) - (2+1)))) \\
 21466 &:= 987 - 6 + 5 \times (4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\
 21467 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (765 \times 4)) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
 21468 &:= ((987 + 6) + (5 \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 21469 &:= (9 \times 8 + (-7 + 6!) \times (5 + 4!)) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 21470 &:= (((-9-8) \times -(7 + (((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 21471 &:= ((-9-8) \times -((7 + (6 \times (5 + (4^3)))) \times (2+1))) \\
 21472 &:= (((-9-8) \times -(7 + (((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2))) + 1) \\
 21473 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) - 2)))) - 1) \\
 21474 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (7 \times ((6-5) - ((4+3)^{2+1})))) \\
 21475 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
 21476 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times (54+3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21477 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times (54+3)))) + (2+1)) \\
 21478 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((65 \times (4+3)) + 2)) - 1) \\
 21479 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
 21480 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4+3))) - (2+1)) \\
 21481 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 - 6) \times 5 \times 43) \times 2 - 1 \\
 21482 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 - 6) \times 5 \times 43) \times 2 \times 1 \\
 21483 &:= (-9 + (8 \times 7 - 6) \times 5 \times 43) \times 2 + 1 \\
 21484 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4+3))) + (2-1)) \\
 21485 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4+3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21486 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4+3))) + (2+1)) \\
 21487 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 21488 &:= ((-9-8) \times -(7 + (((6 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1))) \\
 21489 &:= ((-98-7) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
 21490 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 21491 &:= ((9 \times -8) + (((7 \times -6) - (-5 \times 4321))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21492 &:= ((-1-2) \times -(((3+(4^5))-6) \times 7) + (8+9)) \\
 21493 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - 6)) \times -7) + (8+9) \\
 21494 &:= ((-1 + (((2-3) \times -4)^5) \times (6+(7+8)))) - 9 \\
 21495 &:= ((((-1 - (2 - (3+4)))^5) \times (6+(7+8))) - 9) \\
 21496 &:= (((1 \times -2)^3) + (4 \times (56 \times (7+89)))) \\
 21497 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times ((4^5) \times (6 - (7-8)))))) - 9 \\
 21498 &:= -(((1 + (2+3)) \times (((456-7) \times -8) + 9))) \\
 21499 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) + (((4^5) \times (6+(7+8))) - 9))) \\
 21500 &:= (((((-1-2) \times (3 - (4^5))) + 6) \times 7) + (8+9)) \\
 21501 &:= (((-1 \times -(2 \times 3)) + ((4^5) \times (6+(7+8)))) - 9) \\
 21502 &:= (-1 + ((2-3) - (-((4 \times 56) \times (7+89)))) \\
 21503 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) + (((4^5) \times (6+(7+8))) - 9)) \\
 21504 &:= ((1^{23}) \times ((4 \times -(56)) \times -((7+89)))) \\
 21505 &:= ((1^{23}) + ((4 \times -(56)) \times -((7+89)))) \\
 21506 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) - (-((4 \times 56) \times (7+89)))) \\
 21507 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + (((4^5) \times (6+(7+8))) + 9)) \\
 21508 &:= (((((-1-2) \times (3+(4^5))) + 6) \times -7) - (8+9)) \\
 21509 &:= (((((1+2) \times 34) \times 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + (89)) \\
 21510 &:= (((-1+2) \times -3) + (((4^5) \times (6+(7+8))) + 9)) \\
 21511 &:= (((-1+2) - 3) + (((4^5) \times (6+(7+8))) + 9)) \\
 21512 &:= -(((1 \times -2)^3) - (4 \times (56 \times (7+89)))) \\
 21513 &:= (((-1-2) \times -3) - (-(-4 \times -(56)) \times (-7 - (89)))) \\
 21514 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times 7) + (8+9))) \\
 21515 &:= -(((12^3) \times (-4-5)) - ((67 \times 89))) \\
 21516 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 \times 4^5 \times (6 - 7 + 8) + 9 \\
 21517 &:= ((-1 + (2+3)) + (((4^5) \times (6+(7+8))) + 9)) \\
 21518 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (3 - (-4 \times ((5 \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
 21519 &:= 12^{3-4+5} - 6 + 789 \\
 21520 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + (((4^5) \times (6+(7+8))) + 9))) \\
 21521 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) + (((4^5) \times (6+(7+8))) + 9)) \\
 21522 &:= ((((-1+2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times -7) - (8+9)) \\
 21523 &:= (-1 \times -(((2+345) \times (6+(7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 21524 &:= (((((-1-2) \times (3+(4^5))) + 6) \times -7) + (8-9)) \\
 21525 &:= ((-1-2) + ((3+(4 \times 5)) \times ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21526 &:= (((-1-2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times 7)) - (8+9)) \\
 21527 &:= (-1 - ((23 \times (-45) + 6)) \times -(((7-8) - 9))) \\
 21528 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4+5)))) \times ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 21529 &:= (((1 + ((23 \times (-4-5)) \times (6+7))) \times -8) - (-9)) \\
 21530 &:= (((-1+2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times 7)) - (8+9)) \\
 21531 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times 7)) - (8+9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21492 &:= (-((9 + (8 \times (7+6)))) + ((5 \times 4321))) \\
 21493 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{(6-5)^4}) - (3+2)))) + 1) \\
 21494 &:= (((-98-7) + (6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\
 21495 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 - (4-3))^{2+1}))) \\
 21496 &:= ((-98-7) + ((6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\
 21497 &:= ((((-9-87) \times 6) - 5) \times -((4 \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
 21498 &:= ((-9-87) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
 21499 &:= (9+8) \times (7! \times 6+5)! / 4! - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 21500 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4+3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 21501 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7+6) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3))) - (2+1))) \\
 21502 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4+3) + 2)) + 1) \\
 21503 &:= (9+8-7+6+5) \times 4^{3+2} - 1 \\
 21504 &:= (9+8-7+6+5) \times 4^{3+2} \times 1 \\
 21505 &:= (9+8-7+6+5) \times 4^{3+2} + 1 \\
 21506 &:= (-9 + (((8+7) \times -6) + (5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21507 &:= (-98 - (((-7+6) \times 5) \times (4321))) \\
 21508 &:= (((-98+7) - 6) + (5 \times (4321))) \\
 21509 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 - 6) \times 5 \times 43 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 21510 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7^{6+5-4-3}) - (2+1)))) \\
 21511 &:= ((((-9 \times (-8 \times 7)) - 65) \times ((-4-3)^2 \times 1))) \\
 21512 &:= -(((9+8) + 76) - ((5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21513 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{(6-5)^4}) - 3))) + (2+1)) \\
 21514 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times 4)) \times -(32-1)) \\
 21515 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 + (5 \times ((4^3) + (2-1)))) \\
 21516 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{6+5-4-3}))) - 21) \\
 21517 &:= -(((9 - (8 \times -7)) - (654 \times (32 + (1)))) \\
 21518 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{6+5-4-3}) - 2))) - 1) \\
 21519 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7+6)) \times ((5 + (4^3)) \times (2+1)))) \\
 21520 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{6+5-4-3}) - 2))) + 1) \\
 21521 &:= ((9 - (87+6)) - (5 \times (-4321))) \\
 21522 &:= ((-9-8) \times ((7+6) + (5 - (4 \times -((-321)))))) \\
 21523 &:= (9 - ((8 - ((7+6) \times 54)) \times (32-1))) \\
 21524 &:= (((-98-7) \times -(((65+4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1) \\
 21525 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7+6) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) - (2+1)) \\
 21526 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7+6) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21527 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 \times ((6+5) \times 4)) - (3^2))) - 1) \\
 21528 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6+5) \times 4)) - (3 \times (2+1)))))) \\
 21529 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 \times ((6+5) \times 4)) - (3^2))) + 1) \\
 21530 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7+6) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21531 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5)^4}))) - (3 + (2+1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21532 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) + 9))) \\
 21533 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) - (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
 21534 &:= (1 + 2) + 3 \times (4^5 \times (6 - 7 + 8) + 9) \\
 21535 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 + 4)^{5+6-7}) - 8) \times 9) \\
 21536 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9) \\
 21537 &:= (((((1 \times 2) \times 3) - (45 \times -6)) \times 78) + 9) \\
 21538 &:= ((-1 \times (234 - ((5 - 6) - 7))) \times -(89)) \\
 21539 &:= (((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 21540 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 - 4^5 \times (-6 + 7 - 8) + 9) \\
 21541 &:= ((12 - (((-3 \times (4^5)) + (-6)) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21542 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times (3 + (4^5))) + 6) \times -7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 21543 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6) \times 7 \times (-8 + 9) \\
 21544 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3) \times ((-456) + 7) \times -8))) - 9) \\
 21545 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 21546 &:= ((-123) + (4 + 5)) \times (-((6 + ((7 + 8)))) \times 9) \\
 21547 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 - 9) \\
 21548 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 21549 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + (4^5 + 6) \times 7) - 8 \times 9) \\
 21550 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21551 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 21552 &:= ((123 \times 4) + ((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 21553 &:= (-((1 + 2)) - ((-34) \times (5 - (-6 - (7 \times 89)))))) \\
 21554 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3 + 4)^{5+6-7}) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 21555 &:= (((((-1 + 2) - 3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + (7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 21556 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 \times 4^5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 21557 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (34 \times ((5 + 6) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 21558 &:= (((12 - (-3 \times (4^5))) - (-6)) \times 7) - ((8 \times 9)) \\
 21559 &:= ((1 + 2) - (-34) \times (5 - (-6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 21560 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 \times 9) \\
 21561 &:= -((((1 \times -2) \times (3 \times -((456 - 7)))) \times -8) - 9) \\
 21562 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) - 89) \\
 21563 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times 3)^4) + (5^6)) + (7 \times -(89))) \\
 21564 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((-3 - ((-4^5) - 6)) \times 7) + 8) - 9) \\
 21565 &:= ((1 \times (2 - ((3 \times (-4^5)) - 6) \times 7)) - ((-8 - 9))) \\
 21566 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 21567 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((-3 + (4^5)) + 6) \times (7 \times -((8 - 9)))))) \\
 21568 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
 21569 &:= (-1 - (-2 \times ((3 \times ((456 - 7) \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 21570 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21532 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 21533 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 21534 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{6+5-4-3}))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21535 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{6+5-4-3}))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21536 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\
 21537 &:= 9 \times (-8 + 7^{(6-5) \times (4+3-2-1)}) \\
 21538 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3/(2 + 1))) \\
 21539 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times ((6 + 5) - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 21540 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{6+5-4-3}))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21541 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 21542 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 21543 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 21544 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 21545 &:= (((((-9 - 8) + 7) \times 6) - (-5 \times 4321))) \\
 21546 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 21547 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 21548 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3^2))) - 1)) \\
 21549 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + 4) \times -(32 + 1)) \\
 21550 &:= (((-9 + 876) - 5) \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 21551 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times ((4 \times (3^2)) - 1))) \\
 21552 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times 3))) - 21) \\
 21553 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4 \times 3)^2 \times 1 \\
 21554 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{6+5-4-3}) + 2))) - 1) \\
 21555 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5))^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21556 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{6+5-4-3}) + 2))) + 1) \\
 21557 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) + (5 \times 4321)) \\
 21558 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (-7 - 654)) \times (-32 - 1)))) \\
 21559 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 + (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 21560 &:= (-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 + (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 21561 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21562 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times -6)) - (-5 \times (4321))) \\
 21563 &:= (9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - (5 \times 4 \times 3)^2) - 1 \\
 21564 &:= (9 - 8 - 7) \times (6 - (5 \times 4 \times 3)^2) \times 1 \\
 21565 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5))^4) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 21566 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) + 3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21567 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 21568 &:= (-98 - ((7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
 21569 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (32 \times 1)) \\
 21570 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21571 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) & 21571 &:= -((9 + ((-8 + (7 + 6)) \times -(((5 + 4321)))))) \\
 21572 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((3 + (456)) \times ((7 \times -8) + 9))) & 21572 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) + (((5^4) + 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 21573 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9)) & 21573 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + 4)))) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
 21574 &:= (-((-12 - 34)) \times (-5 + (-6 \times (-7 - (-8 \times -9)))) & 21574 &:= ((-9 + (-((-8 + 7)) - (654 \times -((32 + 1)))))) \\
 21575 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 - (((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))) & 21575 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\
 21576 &:= (12 \times (-3 + (((45 \times 6) \times 7) - 89))) & 21576 &:= (((9 - 8) + (-7)) + (654 \times ((32 + 1)))) \\
 21577 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) & 21577 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1)) \\
 21578 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9)) & 21578 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) - (32 - 1)) \\
 21579 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) & 21579 &:= (9 + (-(((8 + 7) \times (6 - (((5 - 43)^2 \times 1)))))) \\
 21580 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) & 21580 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\
 21581 &:= ((-1 - (-2^3)) \times (-4 - (((-5 \times 67) - 8) \times 9)) & 21581 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{(6-5)^4}) + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 21582 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (((3 + 4)^5)/(6 - (7 - 8)))) \times 9) & 21582 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6)^5)/(4 + 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 21583 &:= (-12 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) & 21583 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7^{(6-5)^4}) + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 21584 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) + (8 + 9)) & 21584 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21585 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 21585 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21586 &:= (1 + 2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5 \times 6!) - 7 + 8 + 9 & 21586 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\
 21587 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) & 21587 &:= (-((9 + 8)) + (-7 + (6 + (5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21588 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) & 21588 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6)^5)/(4 + 3))) - 21) \\
 21589 &:= (1 + 23 \times 4! \times 5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 & 21589 &:= ((-((9 + 87))/6) - (5 \times (-4321))) \\
 21590 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3 + 4)^5)/(6 - (7 - 8)))) \times 9)) & 21590 &:= (9 - (-((-8 + 7)) + ((654 \times -((32 + 1)))))) \\
 21591 &:= (((((1 - (2^3))^4) + ((5 - 6) + 7)) - 8) \times 9) & 21591 &:= (-(((9 - 8) + (7 + 6)) - (5 \times 4321))) \\
 21592 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) & 21592 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 \times (6 - 5))^4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1) \\
 21593 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times 4)) \times -(((5^6) + 7)/8) + 9)) & 21593 &:= -9 - 8 + ((7 \times (-6 - 5 + 4) \times 3))^2 + 1 \\
 21594 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) & 21594 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
 21595 &:= 1^2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (-6 + 7 \times 89) & 21595 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 21596 &:= (-1 - (-23 \times (((4^5) - 6) - ((7 - (8 \times -9)))))) & 21596 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 21597 &:= -12 + (3 + 4)^{-5-6+7+8} \times 9 & 21597 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6) \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 21598 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) & 21598 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 21599 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) & 21599 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5 + (4^{3+2})))) - 1) \\
 21600 &:= (((1 \times 23) + 4) \times -(((5 - 6) - (789)))) & 21600 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 - 5) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 21601 &:= ((-12 + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) & 21601 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) - ((-5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21602 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 45) \times (-6 + 7 \times 8) \times 9 & 21602 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 21603 &:= (1 - (-2 - (-((3 + 45)) \times ((-6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) & 21603 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 21604 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) & 21604 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 21605 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times -3) \times ((456 - 7) \times 8) + 9)) & 21605 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 \times 3)^2 + 1) \\
 21606 &:= (-1 - (2 - (((3 + 4)^5)/(6 - 7) + 8)) \times 9)) & 21606 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6)^5)/(4 + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21607 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) \times ((456 - 7) \times 8) + 9)) & 21607 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6)^5)/(4 + 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21608 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 345) \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) & 21608 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 21609 &:= (-((-1 - (2 \times 3))) \times ((45 \times 67) + (8 \times 9))) & 21609 &:= (-9 \times -((8 - (7 - 6))^{(5+4+3)/(2+1)}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21610 &:= (1 - ((2 - 345) \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9))) \\
 21611 &:= (1 \times ((-23 \times ((-4^5) + (6 + 78))) + (-9))) \\
 21612 &:= (1 - (-((-23 \times ((-4^5) + (6 + 78)))) - (-9))) \\
 21613 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times ((4^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8) + 9 \\
 21614 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 \times ((4^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8) + 9 \\
 21615 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 21616 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
 21617 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9)) \\
 21618 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 21619 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 21620 &:= (1 \times (-23 \times (-((4^5)) + (((67 + 8) + 9)))) \\
 21621 &:= (1 + (-23 \times (-((4^5)) + (((67 + 8) + 9)))) \\
 21622 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21623 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\
 21624 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (34 \times -(((5 \times 67) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 21625 &:= (12 - ((3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times -7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
 21626 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\
 21627 &:= -((((-1 - 234) + ((5 - 6) - 7)) \times -(-89))) \\
 21628 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 - 9))) \\
 21629 &:= (1 \times ((-23 \times ((-4^5) + (6 + 78))) - (-9))) \\
 21630 &:= (1 + ((-23 \times ((-4^5) + (6 + 78))) - (-9))) \\
 21631 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\
 21632 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 21633 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 + 9 \\
 21634 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21635 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times ((4^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8 + 9) \\
 21636 &:= (((12 \times -3) \times ((-4 - 5) \times 67)) - ((8 \times 9))) \\
 21637 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times 7 \times (-8 + 9)) \\
 21638 &:= -((((-1 - 2) - (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times 7)) - (89))) \\
 21639 &:= (((1 + 2) \times ((-3 - ((-4^5) - 6)) \times 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 21640 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 21641 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 \times 3))^4) - ((5 \times 6) - 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 21642 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 21643 &:= ((1 \times -23) \times (4 + ((5 \times ((6 + 7) + 8)) \times -9))) \\
 21644 &:= -1 - 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 21645 &:= ((-1 + (-2 - (34))) \times (-((5 + 67) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21646 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8))) - 9) \\
 21647 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\
 21648 &:= (-12 \times (3 + (((-4^5) + 6) - 789)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21610 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) + (3/(2 + 1))) \\
 21611 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6))^5)/(4 + 3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21612 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6))^5)/(4 + 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21613 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 21614 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 21615 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5^4) \times (32 + 1) \\
 21616 &:= (-9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 21617 &:= (-9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 21618 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4321)))) \\
 21619 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4321)))) \\
 21620 &:= ((-98 / -7) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 21621 &:= ((9 + 8) + (-7 + (6 + (5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21622 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\
 21623 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3))^2 \times 1))) \\
 21624 &:= (-9 + ((8 + ((7^{(6-5)^4} \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 21625 &:= ((-98 / -7) + (6 + (5 \times 4321))) \\
 21626 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6))^5)/(4 + 3)) + 2)) - 1) \\
 21627 &:= ((98 - 76) - ((5 \times -(4321)))) \\
 21628 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6))^5)/(4 + 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\
 21629 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 65) - 4) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21630 &:= ((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -((5 \times ((4 \times 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 21631 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 21632 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 - 5)) \times -43) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21633 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21634 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\
 21635 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7^{(6-5)^4})) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 21636 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6))^5)/(4 + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 21637 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7^{(6-5)^4})) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 21638 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21639 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21640 &:= ((((-98 + 7) \times 6) + 5) \times 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 21641 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\
 21642 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 21643 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5) \times (4 - (3^{2+1}))) \\
 21644 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times 54) + (3^2))) - 1) \\
 21645 &:= (((9 \times 8) - 7) \times (654 - 321))) \\
 21646 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\
 21647 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 21648 &:= (((98 \times 7) + (6 \times -5)) \times ((4 \times 3) - (-21)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21649 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\ 21650 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 21651 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 21652 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 21653 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((34 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 21654 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 21655 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((34 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 21656 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 21657 &:= (12 - ((3 \times (((-((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\ 21658 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 21659 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4 + 56))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 21660 &:= (-12 + ((34 + (-5 \times 67)) \times -(8 \times 9))) \\ 21661 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 21662 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\ 21663 &:= (1 \times 2^3 + 4^5) \times (6 + 7 + 8) - 9 \\ 21664 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + 8)) + 9) \\ 21665 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((-((4 - (56 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 21666 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + 456) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 21667 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + 456) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 21668 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) + 456) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 21669 &:= (-12 + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 21670 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (4 + ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 21671 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 21672 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 21673 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((34 - (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 21674 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((34 - (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 21675 &:= ((-(-1) + 2) - ((34 - (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 21676 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -(78))) - 9) \\ 21677 &:= (1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (-5 + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 21678 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 21679 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 21680 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9) \\ 21681 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (((4 \times 5) - 6) + 789)) \\ 21682 &:= (((12 - 3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 21683 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 21684 &:= (((12 \times -3) \times 4) + 5) \times (-67 - 89) \\ 21685 &:= (((1 - (2 \times 3))^4) + ((5 \times 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 21686 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 + (5 \times 67)) \times 8))) - 9) \\ 21687 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21649 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\ 21650 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - (32 - 1)) \\ 21651 &:= (((((9 \times 8) \times 7) \times (6 - 5)) \times 43) - 21) \\ 21652 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 21653 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5))^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 21654 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7^{6+5-4-3}))) - (2 + 1))) \\ 21655 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 21656 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 21657 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 21658 &:= 98 \times (-7 \times 6 \times 5 + 432 - 1) \\ 21659 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 21660 &:= (-(((9 + (8 - 7)) \times (6 + (5 \times 432)))) \times -((1))) \\ 21661 &:= ((9 + (8 - 7)) \times (6 + (5 \times 432))) + ((1)) \\ 21662 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7^{6+5-4-3}))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 21663 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 - ((7 - 6)^5))^4) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 21664 &:= (-9 + (-((8 - 76)) + (5 \times (4321)))) \\ 21665 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 21666 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 21667 &:= ((-9 - (-8 \times 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) + 432) - 1)) \\ 21668 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - (7 - 6))) + (5 \times 4321)) \\ 21669 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 21670 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 21671 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 21672 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) \times 4) - (3 / (2 + 1)))) \\ 21673 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2)))) + 1) \\ 21674 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 21675 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 21676 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 21677 &:= ((9 \times 8) + (((-((7 - 6)) \times (-5 \times 4321)))) \\ 21678 &:= ((9 \times 8) + ((7 - 6) - ((-5 \times 4321)))) \\ 21679 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{6+5-4-3}))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 21680 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) - (3 / (2 + 1))) \\ 21681 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (7^{(6-5) \times (4+3-2-1)}))) \\ 21682 &:= (((9 + (-8 + 76)) - (5 \times -(4321))) \\ 21683 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{6+5-4-3}))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 21684 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{6+5-4-3}))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 21685 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 21686 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 21687 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7^{(6-5) \times 4}))) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21688 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 \times 9 \\
 21689 &:= 1 + (-2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6)) \times 7 + 8 \times 9 \\
 21690 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\
 21691 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (34 \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)))) \\
 21692 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 21693 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + (4^5 + 6) \times 7) + 8 \times 9 \\
 21694 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -(78))) + 9) \\
 21695 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 21696 &:= ((1 - ((2 - 3) - (4 \times 56))) \times (7 + 89)) \\
 21697 &:= (((-12 - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21698 &:= ((-1 - (-(-2) \times -(3^4) \times (56 + 78)))) - 9) \\
 21699 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) + ((5 + (6 + 7)) - 8)) \times 9) \\
 21700 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 21701 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 21702 &:= (((12 - (-3 \times (4^5))) - (-6)) \times 7) + ((8 \times 9)) \\
 21703 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 21704 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 \times 9 \\
 21705 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times (((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 21706 &:= (1 + (((23 + (4 + 5)) \times 678) + 9)) \\
 21707 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 - 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 21708 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3^4) \times ((5 - 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 21709 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - (5 + (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 21710 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\
 21711 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(3 + (((4^5) + 6) \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 21712 &:= 1 \times 2^3 \times (-4^5 + 6 \times 7 \times 89) \\
 21713 &:= (((-12 - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) + (8 - 9)) \\
 21714 &:= -(((1 \times (2 \times 3)) + 456) \times ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
 21715 &:= (1 - (((-2 \times 3) - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 21716 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 21717 &:= (-((1 + ((2 + 34) \times (-5 - (6 - (78)))))) \times -9) \\
 21718 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 21719 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((-34) + ((5 \times 6) \times -7)) \times 89) \\
 21720 &:= (12 \times ((3 - ((-4^5) + 6)) + 789)) \\
 21721 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + 89)) \\
 21722 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + 89)) \\
 21723 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 21724 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21725 &:= (((-12 \times (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times 67) + ((8 + 9))) \\
 21726 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((34 + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21688 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 21689 &:= (((98/7) \times 6) + (5 \times (4321))) \\
 21690 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 21691 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 21692 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 21693 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 + 6)) - 5) \times (4^3)) \times -21) \\
 21694 &:= ((((-9 + 876) \times 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 21695 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 21696 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 21697 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 21698 &:= (((9 + 8) + 76) + ((5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21699 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + ((7^{6+5-4-3}) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 21700 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7^{6+5-4-3}) + 2))) + 1) \\
 21701 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\
 21702 &:= (-((-98 + 7)) - (-6 - (-5 \times -((4321)))) \\
 21703 &:= (-(-98) - (((-7 + 6) \times 5) \times (4321))) \\
 21704 &:= ((98 - (-7 + 6)) - ((5 \times 4321))) \\
 21705 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7^{6-5} \times 4) + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21706 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7^{6-5} \times 4) + 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21707 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -2) - 1) \\
 21708 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + ((7^{6+5-4-3}) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 21709 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -2) + 1) \\
 21710 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7^{6-5} \times 4) + 3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21711 &:= ((9 \times 87) + ((654 \times 32) \times (1))) \\
 21712 &:= ((9 \times 87) + ((654 \times 32) + (1))) \\
 21713 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
 21714 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\
 21715 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 76) - 5) \times 4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 21716 &:= ((-(-98) - (-7 - 6)) + ((5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21717 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + ((7^{6-5} \times 4) + ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 21718 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) + ((5 \times 4321))) \\
 21719 &:= ((9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) - (-5 \times (4321)))) \\
 21720 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + ((6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\
 21721 &:= ((((-98/7) - 6) \times -543 \times 2) + 1) \\
 21722 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 + (3^2))) - 1) \\
 21723 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 21724 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 21725 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7^{6-5} \times 4) + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 21726 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) + (2 + 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21727 &:= (((-12 \times (3 + (4 \times 56))) + 7) \times -8) - 9 \\
 21728 &:= (12 + ((-34) - ((5 \times 6) \times 7)) \times -(89)) \\
 21729 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 - 89))) \\
 21730 &:= (-((-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times 45)) + 6) \times (-7 + 89)) \\
 21731 &:= (((-12 - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 21732 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 + 8)) \times 9) \\
 21733 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 + 8)) \times 9) \\
 21734 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + (5 - 6)) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 21735 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
 21736 &:= -1 + 2 + (3^4 \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8) \times 9 \\
 21737 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3^4 \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8) \times 9 \\
 21738 &:= 1 + 2 + (3^4 \times 5 \times 6 - 7 - 8) \times 9 \\
 21739 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5! - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 21740 &:= (1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6)) \times 7 + 89 \\
 21741 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 21742 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4! + 5! \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 21743 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3 - 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7) \times (-8 \times 9) \\
 21744 &:= 1 \times (2 \times 3 - 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7) \times (-8 \times 9) \\
 21745 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3 - 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7) \times (-8 \times 9) \\
 21746 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3^4))) - 5) \times ((6 \times -7) - 89)) \\
 21747 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4))/5) \times (6 + 78)) - 9 \\
 21748 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) - 789)) \\
 21749 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times (78 + 9))) \\
 21750 &:= ((12 + (-3^{-4+5+6})) \times (7 - ((8 + 9)))) \\
 21751 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 + 8)))) - 9 \\
 21752 &:= (-1 - ((2345 - (6 - 78)) \times -9)) \\
 21753 &:= (((1 \times 2345) - 6) + (78)) \times 9 \\
 21754 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5)) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9) \\
 21755 &:= (-1 \times -((234 - 5) \times (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 21756 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 21757 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 \times 456) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21758 &:= (-1 \times -2 \times (((3 \times 456) - 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21759 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4^{5+6-7}) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 21760 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 \times (-5 - 6 + 7 + 89) \\
 21761 &:= (((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 21762 &:= ((((-12 + 3) + 4) \times 5) - 6) \times (-78 \times 9) \\
 21763 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((34 + 5) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 21764 &:= (-1 \times -2 + ((34 + 5) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 21765 &:= ((-((1 + (23 \times 45))) \times -((6 + 7) + 8)) + 9) \\
 21766 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (((3 \times 456) - 7) \times 8))) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21727 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 21728 &:= (-98 - (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))) \\
 21729 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\
 21730 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\
 21731 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 654)) \times ((32 - 1))) \\
 21732 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 21733 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 21734 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\
 21735 &:= ((987 \times (65 - 43)) + 21)) \\
 21736 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 21737 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\
 21738 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
 21739 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times -(4^3)) - 21) \\
 21740 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times (((6 - (5 - 4))^3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 21741 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\
 21742 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times (4^3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21743 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (5 \times (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
 21744 &:= (-((9 \times 8)) \times ((76 + ((54/3) \times -21)))) \\
 21745 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((-7 - 6) \times (54 \times (-32 + ((1)))))) \\
 21746 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (6 + (5 \times 4321))) \\
 21747 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4) - 321) \\
 21748 &:= (9 - (((8 - 76) \times (5 \times (4^3))) + 21))) \\
 21749 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 \times (-6 + 5^4)) \times (3 + 2) - 1 \\
 21750 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 \times (-6 + 5^4)) \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 21751 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 \times (-6 + 5^4)) \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\
 21752 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times ((4^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 21753 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 21754 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))) \\
 21755 &:= 98 \times (-7 \times 6 \times 5 + 432) - 1 \\
 21756 &:= 98 \times (-7 \times 6 \times 5 + 432 \times 1) \\
 21757 &:= 98 \times (-7 \times 6 \times 5 + 432) + 1 \\
 21758 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 21759 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times -(4^3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 21760 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) \times 5)) \times -(4^{3+2-1})) \\
 21761 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\
 21762 &:= 98 + 7 \times (-6 + 5^4) \times (3 + 2) - 1 \\
 21763 &:= 98 + 7 \times (-6 + 5^4) \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 21764 &:= 98 + 7 \times (-6 + 5^4) \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\
 21765 &:= -9 + ((8 - 7 + 6!) \times 5 + 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 21766 &:= (-9 - (((-8 \times 7) - 6) - 5) \times (4 + 321)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21767 &:= -(((12+34) \times (-5 - (6 \times 78)))) + 9 \\ 21768 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9)) \\ 21769 &:= (((-1 + (2+3))^4) \times - (5 - (6 \times (7+8)))) + 9 \\ 21770 &:= -(((1 - (2+34)) \times (5 - ((6 - (7 \times 89)))))) \\ 21771 &:= (((12+34) - 5) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9)) \\ 21772 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 78) \times 9)) \\ 21773 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 \times 89)) \\ 21774 &:= (-1 - (((((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\ 21775 &:= -(((1 \times 2) + 3) \times (4 - ((56 \times 78) - 9))) \\ 21776 &:= (1 - ((2+3) \times (4 - ((56 \times 78) - 9)))) \\ 21777 &:= ((-1 - ((2+3) \times (4^{5+6-7}))) \times -(8+9)) \\ 21778 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!! + 4) \times 5 \times 6 + 7 \times (8+9) \\ 21779 &:= (-1 - ((-2345) - (67+8) \times 9)) \\ 21780 &:= -(((((-1 \times 2345)) - (67)) - 8) \times 9) \\ 21781 &:= -((-1 + ((-2345) - (67+8) \times 9))) \\ 21782 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7)) + 89) \\ 21783 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 21784 &:= -((-((1 + (23+4))) \times (-5 - (6 - (789)))))) \\ 21785 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - 8)) - 9) \\ 21786 &:= (((-12 - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 21787 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\ 21788 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\ 21789 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4+5) \times (6 \times (7+8)))) \times 9)) \\ 21790 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) \\ 21791 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 21792 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (-4 \times 56)) \times (7 + (89))) \\ 21793 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times ((5 - 6) - (-78) \times -9)) \\ 21794 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((-3 + (4 \times -(56))) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 21795 &:= -(((12 - (3+4)) \times ((-56) \times 78) + 9)) \\ 21796 &:= (((-1 + ((2+3)^{4-5+6})) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 21797 &:= (((((-1 + ((2+3)^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\ 21798 &:= ((((-1 + ((2+3)^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 21799 &:= (((((-1 + ((2+3)^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 21800 &:= (-12 + ((3+4) \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9))) \\ 21801 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((34 \times 5))) \times (-6 + ((7+8) \times 9))) \\ 21802 &:= ((-1 + (((2+3)^{4-5+6}) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 21803 &:= -(((1 - 2) - (((3 - 45) \times 6) + 7) \times -(89))) \\ 21804 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) + (5+6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 21805 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21767 &:= 9 + (-8 + 76) \times (5 \times 4^3) - 2 \times 1 \\ 21768 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3+2)) + 1)))) \\ 21769 &:= 9 + ((-8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5) \times 4^3 \times 2 \times 1 \\ 21770 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times (6 - (((5+4)^3) \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 21771 &:= (-9 - ((8+7) \times (6 - (((5+4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\ 21772 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times (6 - (((5+4)^3) \times 2))) - 1)) \\ 21773 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -76) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\ 21774 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times ((65 - 4) \times 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 21775 &:= ((-(-9) + ((-87 + 6) + 5)) \times -(((4 + 321)))) \\ 21776 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}))) - 1) \\ 21777 &:= (9 + 5 \times (-8 + 7 \times 6) \times 4^3) \times 2 - 1 \\ 21778 &:= (9 + 5 \times (-8 + 7 \times 6) \times 4^3) \times 2 \times 1 \\ 21779 &:= (9 + 5 \times (-8 + 7 \times 6) \times 4^3) \times 2 + 1 \\ 21780 &:= ((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 21781 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 21782 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5! / 4 \times 3! / (2 + 1) \\ 21783 &:= (((-98/7) \times -(((6^5) + 4) / (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 21784 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 21785 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\ 21786 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\ 21787 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ 21788 &:= (((-9 - (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times 4)) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\ 21789 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 21790 &:= (((-9 - (((8 \times 76) - 5) \times 4)) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\ 21791 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (65 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 21792 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times (((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 21793 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6^5 / (4 \times 3)) \times 2 - 1 \\ 21794 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6^5 / (4 \times 3)) \times 2 \times 1 \\ 21795 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6^5 / (4 \times 3)) \times 2 + 1 \\ 21796 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) - 1))) \\ 21797 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 \times 3)) + 2)) - 1) \\ 21798 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) + 2))) - 1)) \\ 21799 &:= -((((987 \times (6 + 5)) + 43) \times -2) + 1)) \\ 21800 &:= ((-9 + (876 + 5)) \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 21801 &:= ((-(-98) + (76 - 5)) \times ((-(4 \times -32)) + 1)) \\ 21802 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}))) - 1) \\ 21803 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2} \times 1))) \\ 21804 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 + (3 + 2))) + 1))) \\ 21805 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21806 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 7)) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 21807 &:= -(((-123) - ((-4) \times (567 + 8))) \times -(-9)) \\
 21808 &:= -(((-12 \times 34) - 56) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21809 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5)) - 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9) \\
 21810 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3 + 4) \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9))) \\
 21811 &:= ((-1234) - (56 - 7)) \times (-8 - 9) \\
 21812 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)) \\
 21813 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9))) \\
 21814 &:= -1 \times 2 + (345 - 6 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\
 21815 &:= ((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9) \\
 21816 &:= (((1 - 2) \times 345) + ((6 \times 7))) \times (-8 \times 9) \\
 21817 &:= -1 + 2 + (345 - 6 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\
 21818 &:= 1 \times 2 + (345 - 6 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\
 21819 &:= 1 + 2 + (345 - 6 \times 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\
 21820 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 + (78 \times 9))) \\
 21821 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)^4 \times 5 + 6) \times 7 - 89 \\
 21822 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times (67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 21823 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - 6) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 21824 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -6 - (7 - 89)) \\
 21825 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 3) - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9) \\
 21826 &:= (-1 + (23 \times -(((4^5) + ((6 + 78) - 9)))) \\
 21827 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times ((-4^5) + ((6 + 78) - 9))) \\
 21828 &:= -((-1 - (23 \times -(((4^5) + ((6 + 78) - 9)))) \\
 21829 &:= (((-((1 \times 2)) - 3) \times (4 - (56 \times 78))) - (-9)) \\
 21830 &:= ((1 + ((-2 - 3) \times (4 - (56 \times 78)))) + 9) \\
 21831 &:= -1 + ((-2 + 3 + 4)^5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\
 21832 &:= -1 + ((-2 + 3 + 4)^5 - 6) \times 7 \times (-8 + 9) \\
 21833 &:= 1 + ((-2 + 3 + 4)^5 - 6) \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\
 21834 &:= 1 + ((-2 + 3 + 4)^5 - 6) \times 7 \times (-8 + 9) \\
 21835 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + 6) \times -7) - 89) \\
 21836 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (67 + 8))) + 9) \\
 21837 &:= -(((1 - 2) - ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times -((78 + 9))) \\
 21838 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5^{6+7-8}))) - 9) \\
 21839 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - 6) \times -7) + (8 - 9)) \\
 21840 &:= (((12^3) + 456) \times (-7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 21841 &:= (12^3/4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7 + 8) - 9 \\
 21842 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 - 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 21843 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5)) - 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9) \\
 21844 &:= ((-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21806 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 21807 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 65 - 4) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 21808 &:= ((-9 \times -8 + (7 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) + 2))) + 1) \\
 21809 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))) \\
 21810 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - (((5 + 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 21811 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) - 2)) + 1) \\
 21812 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 - 1 \\
 21813 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 21814 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 21815 &:= ((-9 \times -8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 21816 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 21817 &:= ((-9 \times -8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 21818 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21819 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 21820 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 21821 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5!/4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 21822 &:= (-9 + (8 + 7) \times 6! + 5!) \times (-4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 21823 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)))) \\
 21824 &:= (((9 - ((87 - 6) \times 54)) \times (-3 - 2)) - (1)) \\
 21825 &:= 9 \times ((-8 + 7 \times 6 \times 5) \times 4 \times 3 + 2 - 1) \\
 21826 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
 21827 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4) \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 21828 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 21829 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6 \times 5 + 4) \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 21830 &:= (9 - (8 - 7 + 6) \times 5^4) \times (-3 \times 2 + 1) \\
 21831 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1))))))) \\
 21832 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\
 21833 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
 21834 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 21835 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 \times 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\
 21836 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times ((4^3) + 2))) - 1) \\
 21837 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 21838 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
 21839 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)))) \\
 21840 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 21841 &:= (-9 + 8^{(7-6) \times 5} + 4)/3 \times 2 - 1; \\
 21842 &:= (((-9 + ((8^{(7-6) \times 5} + 4))/3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21843 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 21844 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21845 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7)))))) \times -(8 + 9)) & 21845 &:= (((-98 + 7) + 6) \times ((-5 + (-((4 \times 3) \times 21)))) \\ 21846 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6}))) \times (7 + 8)) - 9) & 21846 &:= -(((-987 - 6) \times ((54 - (32 \times 1)))) \\ 21847 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3) \times (-4 + 5^{-67+8 \times 9}) & 21847 &:= (((((-98 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\ 21848 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 56)) \times -7) \times -8) - 9)) & 21848 &:= (((((-98 / -7) - 6)^5) + 4) / 3) \times (2 \times 1) \\ 21849 &:= (-1 + ((((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9))) & 21849 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -7) \times (-(-65) + ((4 + 321)))) \\ 21850 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3^{-4+5+6}) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) & 21850 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\ 21851 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^{4-5+6})) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) & 21851 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) - 1))) \\ 21852 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times 9)) & 21852 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 21853 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((67 + 8) \times 9)) & 21853 &:= -(((-98 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 - (43 - 2)))))) + (1)) \\ 21854 &:= -12 + (3 + 4) \times 5^{6+7-8} - 9 & 21854 &:= (-98 \times ((7 - (6 \times (5 - (43 - 2)))) \times -((1))) \\ 21855 &:= ((1 + 234) \times (-((-5 - 6) - (7 - (89)))) & 21855 &:= (((9 - (876 \times 5)) \times (4 + (3 - 2))) \times (-1)) \\ 21856 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5^{6+7-8}))) + 9) & 21856 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + (6^{(5+4)/3}))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 21857 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)^{4-5+6} \times 7 - 8 - 9 & 21857 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}))) - 1) \\ 21858 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3)^{4-5+6} \times 7 - 8 - 9 & 21858 &:= (-(((98 \times 76) + (54 \times -3))) \times -(((2 + 1))) \\ 21859 &:= 1 + (2 + 3)^{4-5+6} \times 7 - 8 - 9 & 21859 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) + 1)) \\ 21860 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) \times (7 + 8)))) - 9) & 21860 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3) / 2) - 1)) \\ 21861 &:= (-((1 \times 2345)) - (6 + 78)) \times -9 & 21861 &:= ((987 - (6 - ((5 \times 4) \times 3))) \times 21) \\ 21862 &:= ((((-12^3) + 45) \times (-6 - 7)) + (-8 + (-9))) & 21862 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6^{5-4+3}) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 21863 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8}))) - 9) & 21863 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times 6) + (((5^4) - 3) \times 2))) + 1) \\ 21864 &:= (((1 + 2) + 3) \times (4 - (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 21864 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 76)) + 5) \times -4) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 21865 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^{4-5+6})) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) & 21865 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 21866 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4)) \times (5^{6+7-8})) - 9) & 21866 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\ 21867 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 21867 &:= (-(((9 \times 8) \times -76) \times (5 - (4 - 3)))) + (-21)) \\ 21868 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 21868 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) - 1)) \\ 21869 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 - 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 21869 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -((5 + 4)^3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 21870 &:= (((-((1 + 2345)) - 6) - (78)) \times -9) & 21870 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times -(((5 + 4) / 3)^{2+1})) \\ 21871 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) \times (56 + ((7 + (8 \times 9)))))) & 21871 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -((5 + 4)^3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 21872 &:= 1 \times 2 + (-3^4 \times 5) \times 6 \times (7 - 8) \times 9 & 21872 &:= (((98 - 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4) \times ((3^2) + (-1)) \\ 21873 &:= -1 + (2 + 3)^{4-5+6} \times 7 + 8 - 9 & 21873 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -((5 + 4)^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 21874 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3)^{4-5+6} \times 7 + 8 - 9 & 21874 &:= (((-((9 - (876 \times 5))) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) - ((1))) \\ 21875 &:= 1 + (2 + 3)^{4-5+6} \times 7 + 8 - 9 & 21875 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2} \times 1)) \\ 21876 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3)^{4-5+6} \times 7 - 8 + 9 & 21876 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2})) + 1) \\ 21877 &:= 1 + (2 + 3)^{4-5+6} \times 7 - 8 + 9 & 21877 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4)^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 21878 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) \times (7 + 8))) + 9)) & 21878 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 - ((6 + 5)^4)) / (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 21879 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5 - 6) - 7))) \times (8 + 9)) & 21879 &:= (-9 \times (8 + ((7 - ((6 + 5)^4)) / (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 21880 &:= (((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -7) - (8 \times 9)) & 21880 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\ 21881 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5^{6+7-8} + 9 & 21881 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 21882 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8})) + 9)) & 21882 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) + 1)) \\ 21883 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^{4-5+6})) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) & 21883 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4)^3) + (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21884 &:= (((-1+2) \times (3+4)) \times (5^{6+7-8})) + 9 \\
 21885 &:= (((1-2)^3) - 4) \times ((56 \times -(78)) - 9) \\
 21886 &:= ((-1-2) - ((3+4) \times ((-56) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 21887 &:= (((1+2345)/6) \times -7) \times -8 - 9 \\
 21888 &:= ((-((1-(2+3))) \times ((-4-(5+67)) \times -8)) \times 9) \\
 21889 &:= ((-1+2) \times ((3+4) \times ((56 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 21890 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3^{-4+5+6}) \times (-7+8+9) \\
 21891 &:= -1 + (2+3)^{4-5+6} \times 7+8+9 \\
 21892 &:= 1 \times (2+3)^{4-5+6} \times 7+8+9 \\
 21893 &:= 1 + (2+3)^{4-5+6} \times 7+8+9 \\
 21894 &:= ((-1+2+3)^4 + 5+6) \times (-7+89) \\
 21895 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - (-((6-7) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 21896 &:= (((-12^3) + 45) \times (-6-7)) - (-8 + (-9)) \\
 21897 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times 4) + ((5 \times 6) \times 78))) \times -(-9)) \\
 21898 &:= (((-1 + (((2+3)^4) \times 5)) - 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9) \\
 21899 &:= ((-((1-23)) \times (4^5)) + (-6 - (7 \times 89))) \\
 21900 &:= (12 \times -(((34 \times -(56)) + 7) + ((8 \times 9)))) \\
 21901 &:= (((-1 - ((2+3)^4)) \times -(5 \times (6 - (7-8)))) - 9) \\
 21902 &:= (-1 \times -((23 \times (4 \times 5)) + 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 21903 &:= ((-12 \times -((34 \times 56) - 78)) - 9) \\
 21904 &:= (-1 + (((((2+3)^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 21905 &:= ((-((1 \times 2) - 3) \times -((4 + ((56 \times 78) + 9)))) \\
 21906 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) - (7+8)) \times -9) \\
 21907 &:= (((-1 - (((2+3)^4) \times 5) + 6) \times -7) - (8+9)) \\
 21908 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} \times 4!) \times (5+6) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 21909 &:= (-((1 - (23+45))) \times (((-6 \times 7) \times -8) - 9)) \\
 21910 &:= ((-1 - ((2+3)^4)) \times -(5 + (6 + (7 + (8+9)))) \\
 21911 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5+6) \times (7 + (8+9)))) \\
 21912 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)^4 + 7 \times (5-6)) \times (8+9) \\
 21913 &:= 1 \times ((2 \times 3)^4 + 7 \times (5-6)) \times (8+9) \\
 21914 &:= 1 + ((2 \times 3)^4 + 7 \times (5-6)) \times (8+9) \\
 21915 &:= (((123 \times 4) - 5) \times ((6 + (7-8)) \times 9)) \\
 21916 &:= (((((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8-9)) \\
 21917 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))^5) + 6) \times -(7 \times (8-9))) \\
 21918 &:= (((((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))^5) + 6) \times 7) - (8-9)) \\
 21919 &:= ((1 \times 23) \times ((4^5) + ((-6 - ((7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 21920 &:= (1 - (23 \times (4 - ((5+6) \times (78+9)))) \\
 21921 &:= ((-1-2) - ((3-45) \times (6 \times (78+9)))) \\
 21922 &:= ((1 \times -2) - (((3-45) \times 6) \times (78+9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21884 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7-6)) \times ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) \times -1) \\
 21885 &:= ((-9 - ((8-7) \times 6)) \times -(((5+4)^3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 21886 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times (5 - (4-3)))))) - (2 \times 1) \\
 21887 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 76 \times (-5+4+3) \times 2 - 1 \\
 21888 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7+6)) \times 5)) \times -((4^3) \times (2+1))) \\
 21889 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8+7) \times (6 \times ((5+4) \times 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\
 21890 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times (5 - (4-3)))))) + (2 \times 1) \\
 21891 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times (5 - (4-3)))))) + (2+1) \\
 21892 &:= (((-9-8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5-4))^{3+2}))) \times -1) \\
 21893 &:= ((-9-8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5^4) \times (3+2)) - 1))) \\
 21894 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (5^4)) \times -(3 + (2+1))) \\
 21895 &:= (((9+8) \times -((-7 + (654-3)))) \times -2) - (1) \\
 21896 &:= (((9 \times 87) - 6) + 5) \times ((4 + (3+21))) \\
 21897 &:= (-9 \times -(((8+7) \times (6 \times ((5+4) \times 3))) + (2+1))) \\
 21898 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3+2)) - 1)))) \\
 21899 &:= (((-9-8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) - 1) \\
 21900 &:= ((-9-8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\
 21901 &:= (((-((9 \times 8) \times 76)) + 5) \times -4) + (32 - (-1)) \\
 21902 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 76)) - 5) \times -4) - (3 + (2+1)) \\
 21903 &:= (((((-9-8) \times -7) - (6 - (5 \times (4+3))))^2) - 1) \\
 21904 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) + 1)) \\
 21905 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\
 21906 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) - 1)) \\
 21907 &:= (9 \times 8 + 76)^{-5+4+3} + 2 + 1 \\
 21908 &:= ((9 \times 87) - (-((65 \times (4+321)))) \\
 21909 &:= ((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5^4) \times (3+2)) - 1))) \\
 21910 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - (6^{5-4+3}))) - (2+1)) \\
 21911 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times (5 - ((4+3)^2))) - 1) \\
 21912 &:= (((-(-9) - (-8+7)) + 654) \times (32 + ((1)))) \\
 21913 &:= (((9+8) \times (7-6)) \times (5 + (-4 \times -321))) \\
 21914 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7 - (6^{5+4-3-2}))) + 1) \\
 21915 &:= (((-9+8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) - 1) \\
 21916 &:= ((-9+8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\
 21917 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times -(6 + (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
 21918 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times -(6 + ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) + 1) \\
 21919 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + (6+5)) - 4)^3) - (2+1))) \\
 21920 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7-6)) \times (5^4))) \times -((3+2) \times 1)) \\
 21921 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (7-6)) \times (5^4))) \times -(3+2)) + 1) \\
 21922 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((7 + (6+5)) - 4)^3))) - 21)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21923 &:= -(((-1 + 2) + ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))))) \\
 21924 &:= ((12 \times -((34 - 5))) \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times -9)) \\
 21925 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\
 21926 &:= (-12 + ((3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8} + 9))) \\
 21927 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (-((4 \times (-5 - 678))) + 9))) \\
 21928 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (34 \times (5 \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 21929 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 - (6 - 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 21930 &:= (((1 - 2) \times -((34 \times 5))) \times (-6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 21931 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -((5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 21932 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - (34 \times (5 \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 21933 &:= -(1 + 2)^{3+4} + 5 \times 67 \times 8 \times 9 \\
 21934 &:= ((-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4)^5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 21935 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8} + 9) \\
 21936 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8} + 9) \\
 21937 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8} + 9) \\
 21938 &:= (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8} + 9) \\
 21939 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8} + 9) \\
 21940 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8} + 9) \\
 21941 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8} + 9) \\
 21942 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 21943 &:= ((1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4)^{5 \times (6-7)+8} - 9 \\
 21944 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 21945 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 21946 &:= -(((12^3) - (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 789)))))) \\
 21947 &:= (-1 + ((-2 - (34 - 5)) \times (-6 + (78 \times -9)))) \\
 21948 &:= (-12 - ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 21949 &:= (-123) + (-4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 89)) \\
 21950 &:= (12 + ((3 + 4) \times (5^{6+7-8} + 9))) \\
 21951 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 21952 &:= (-12 - (34 \times (56 - (78 \times 9)))) \\
 21953 &:= ((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 21954 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) \times -((456) - 7) \times -(-8)) - 9)) \\
 21955 &:= ((12 + ((3 + 4) \times (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 21956 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times 5! + 6 + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 21957 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 21958 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (-78 \times -9)) \\
 21959 &:= 1 \times (2 + (3 + 4) \times 56 \times 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 21960 &:= (((1 \times 2) + 3) \times (((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)) \\
 21961 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 21962 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21923 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)))) \\
 21924 &:= (((9 + (876 \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2)) - ((1)) \\
 21925 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) - 3))))/2) + 1) \\
 21926 &:= (((9 + (876 \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2)) + ((1)) \\
 21927 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 21928 &:= ((9 + (((876 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) - ((1)) \\
 21929 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 21930 &:= (9 + (((876 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) + ((1))) \\
 21931 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) + 2)) + 1) \\
 21932 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21933 &:= (9 + (87 \times -(((65 + 4) - 321)))) \\
 21934 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 + (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))))) \times -1) \\
 21935 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\
 21936 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1))) \\
 21937 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 21938 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 21939 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 21940 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21941 &:= 9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 - 3) - 2) - 1 \\
 21942 &:= 9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 - 3) - 2 \times 1) \\
 21943 &:= 9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 - 3) - 2) + 1 \\
 21944 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 21945 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 21946 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 - 6 + 5)^4 - 3 - 2) - 1 \\
 21947 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 - 6 + 5)^4 - 3 - 2 \times 1) \\
 21948 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 - 6 + 5)^4 - 3 - 2) + 1 \\
 21949 &:= ((((-9 - (8/(7 - (6 + 5)))) \times -4)^3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21950 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 21951 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\
 21952 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/ - (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))^{2+1}) \\
 21953 &:= ((((-9 - (8/(7 - (6 + 5)))) \times -4)^3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 21954 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 21955 &:= ((((-9 - (8/(7 - (6 + 5)))) \times -4)^3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 21956 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times - (4 + (3^2))) - 1) \\
 21957 &:= ((-9 \times - (8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 21958 &:= 9 + (8 \times (7 - 6) + 5 \times 4)^3 - 2 - 1 \\
 21959 &:= 9 + (8 \times (7 - 6) + 5 \times 4)^3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 21960 &:= 9 + (8 \times (7 - 6) + 5 \times 4)^3 - 2 + 1 \\
 21961 &:= ((-9 \times - (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 21962 &:= ((-9 \times - (8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - 3))) + (2 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21963 &:= ((1+2) - ((-(34 \times (5+67))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 21964 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3+4) \times (56 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9) \\
 21965 &:= ((-1+2) - (34 \times (56 - (78 \times 9)))) \\
 21966 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 + ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9))) \\
 21967 &:= ((1+2) - (-34) \times (-56) + (78 \times 9)) \\
 21968 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6) + (7-8) \times 9)) \\
 21969 &:= ((((-1 - ((2+3)^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -7) + (8+9)) \\
 21970 &:= ((1 - (23+4)) \times -((56+789))) \\
 21971 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 21972 &:= (-12 \times (3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\
 21973 &:= (12 + (((3+4) \times (56 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 21974 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4 + 5!)) \times (6+7) + 8+9 \\
 21975 &:= ((-12-3) \times (((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 21976 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3+4) \times (56 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 21977 &:= -1 + (2 + 3^4 \times 5) \times (6 \times (-7+8) \times 9) \\
 21978 &:= (((-1-2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7+8))) \times 9) \\
 21979 &:= 1 + (2 + 3^4 \times 5) \times 6 \times (-7+8) \times 9 \\
 21980 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3+4)^5)) / (6+7)) \times (8+9))) \\
 21981 &:= (1 \times (((2 + ((3+4)^5)) / (6+7)) \times (8+9))) \\
 21982 &:= (1 + (((2 + ((3+4)^5)) / (6+7)) \times (8+9))) \\
 21983 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 \times (3+4)) + 5) \times ((6+7) \times 89))) \\
 21984 &:= (((-1-2) - (-(-34) - 5)) \times -(678 - 9)) \\
 21985 &:= (1 \times (((2 + (34+5)) \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 21986 &:= (1 + (((2 + (34+5)) \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 21987 &:= (-((12^3)) - (45 \times (-((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 21988 &:= (-((1 \times 23)) \times (-((4^5)) - (-67) + (8-9))) \\
 21989 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 21990 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (((3 \times 456) + 7) \times 8))) - 9) \\
 21991 &:= (((-1+23) \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\
 21992 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (((3 \times 456) + 7) \times 8))) - 9) \\
 21993 &:= (-12 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7+8) \times 9)) \\
 21994 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 21995 &:= ((1 \times ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times (6 - ((7 \times -8) + 9))) \\
 21996 &:= (-12 \times (-((3 \times (((4+5) + 67) \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 21997 &:= (((-1+23) \times (4^5)) - ((67-8) \times 9)) \\
 21998 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3^4 - (-5+6)^7) \times (8+9)) \\
 21999 &:= (((123 + ((45 \times 6))) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 22000 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times -(5 + ((67 \times 8) + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$22001 := (((-1+23) \times (4^5)) - ((67 \times 8) - 9))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21963 &:= (9-8) \times 76 \times (5+4 \times 3)^2 - 1 \\
 21964 &:= (9-8) \times 76 \times (5+4 \times 3)^2 \times 1 \\
 21965 &:= (9+8) \times 76 \times (5+4 \times 3) + 2 - 1 \\
 21966 &:= (9+8) \times 76 \times (5+4 \times 3) + 2 \times 1 \\
 21967 &:= (9+8) \times 76 \times (5+4 \times 3) + 2 + 1 \\
 21968 &:= (-9 - (((87 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 21969 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + (6 \times (5+4))) \times (3+2))) + 1)) \\
 21970 &:= ((-9 - (8-7)) \times -(((6-5) + (4 \times 3))^{2+1})) \\
 21971 &:= (((-9-8) - (((7 \times ((6-5) \times 4))^3) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 21972 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7+6) \times 5))) \times 43) - (2-1)) \\
 21973 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times ((6 - (5-4))^{3+2}))) \times -1) \\
 21974 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7+6) \times 5))) \times 43) + (2-1)) \\
 21975 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7+6) \times 5))) \times 43) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 21976 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4)^{3-2+1})) \\
 21977 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (((7 + (6+5)) - 4)^3) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 21978 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7+6))) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 21979 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 21980 &:= 9 + 8 + 76 \times (5 + 4 \times 3)^2 - 1 \\
 21981 &:= 9 + 8 + 76 \times (5 + 4 \times 3)^2 \times 1 \\
 21982 &:= (9+8) \times ((7-6+5)^4 - 3) + 2 - 1 \\
 21983 &:= (9+8) \times ((7-6+5)^4 - 3) + 2 \times 1 \\
 21984 &:= (((-9-8) \times -(((7 - (6-5))^4) - 3)) + (2+1)) \\
 21985 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - (6-5)) \times -((4^3)/2)) + 1) \\
 21986 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - ((7 - ((6+5)^4)/3)/2)) - 1) \\
 21987 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6+5) \times 4)) - 3)) + (2+1))) \\
 21988 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) - 1) \\
 21989 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\
 21990 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) + 1)) \\
 21991 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7-654)) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 21992 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7-654)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 21993 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) + (5^4) \times 32)) \times -1) \\
 21994 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times (3+2)) + 1))) \\
 21995 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 21996 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2+1)))) - 1) \\
 21997 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 21998 &:= ((-9-8) \times ((-7 - ((6 \times (5 \times 43)) - (2+1)))) \\
 21999 &:= ((((-9-8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3+2)) - 1) \\
 22000 &:= ((((-9-8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times ((3+2) \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$22001 := ((((-9-8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3+2)) + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22002 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 22003 &:= (-12 - ((-3 - 4) \times (-5 \times (-6 - (7 \times 89)))))) \\ 22004 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) - (5 - 6)) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 22005 &:= (-(((-12 \times 3) \times (((4 + 5) \times 67) + 8))) + 9) \\ 22006 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 22007 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 22008 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + 89)) \\ 22009 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times -(4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))))) + 9) \\ 22010 &:= -1 + 23 \times (-4^5 + 67) \times (8 - 9) \\ 22011 &:= ((-12 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 22012 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times ((56 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 22013 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + 4) \times ((56 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\ 22014 &:= ((1 - 2) + (-((3 + 4) \times (-5 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))))) \\ 22015 &:= (((-12 \times 3) + (-4 + 5)) \times (-6 - (7 \times 89))) \\ 22016 &:= (((-12^3) - (4^5)) \times -((-6 + 78)/9)) \\ 22017 &:= ((((-1 - 23) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + (7 + 8))) + 9) \\ 22018 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22019 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 \times 456) + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 22020 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -(4 \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\ 22021 &:= (-1 + ((23 - (4^5)) \times (67 - 89))) \\ 22022 &:= (-1 - (((2 + ((345 + 6) \times -7)) + 8) \times -(-9))) \\ 22023 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + ((345 + 6) \times -7)) + 8) \times -(-9))) \\ 22024 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((345 + 6) \times -7)) + 8) \times -(-9))) \\ 22025 &:= (12^3 + 4^{5 \times (-6+7)}) \times 8 + 9 \\ 22026 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 22027 &:= (12 - ((-3 - 4) \times (-5 \times (-6 - (7 \times 89)))))) \\ 22028 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - 67)) + (8 + 9)) \\ 22029 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + 45) \times ((6 \times 78) - 9))) \\ 22030 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22031 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 34) \times (-((-5 - 6) - ((7 \times 89)))))) \\ 22032 &:= (-12 \times (((34 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times -9) \\ 22033 &:= (-1 \times -(((23 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\ 22034 &:= ((-12 - 34) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22035 &:= (1 - (-23 \times ((4^5) + (-((67 + 8) + 9)))) \\ 22036 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 - 89))) \\ 22037 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 \times 89)) \\ 22038 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((345 + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9) \\ 22039 &:= (((-12 - ((3 + 4) \times (56 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9) \\ 22040 &:= (-1 - ((2345 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22002 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1))) \\ 22003 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3)) - 21) \\ 22004 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -((6 + (5 \times (4^3)))/2)) - 1) \\ 22005 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 22006 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 22007 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 22008 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 22009 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) - 2)) - 1) \\ 22010 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 - 6) \times 5 \times (-4^3 + 2 \times 1) \\ 22011 &:= (((9 + 8) \times 76) - ((5^4)) \times (32 - (-1))) \\ 22012 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 22013 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 22014 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 22015 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 - 6 + 5)^4 - 3 + 2 \times 1) \\ 22016 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 - 6 + 5)^4 - 3 + 2) + 1 \\ 22017 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - (7 - 6))) - (5^4)) \times -32) + 1) \\ 22018 &:= 9 - 8 \times (-7 + (6 - 5 \times 4)^3) + 2 - 1 \\ 22019 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) + 654) \times (32 - 1))) \\ 22020 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\ 22021 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 22022 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - ((7 - ((6 + 5)^4))/(3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 22023 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 - 6 + 5)^4 - 3 \times (2 + 1) \\ 22024 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\ 22025 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 22026 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22027 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 22028 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 22029 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 22030 &:= (-(((9 - (87 \times 65)) - (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})))) \\ 22031 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 22032 &:= (-9 \times -8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 22033 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) + (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 22034 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 22035 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\ 22036 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 22037 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 22038 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22039 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 + 6 - 5)^4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ 22040 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22041 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times 8)))) \times -9) & 22041 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 22042 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((345 + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9) & 22042 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 22043 &:= ((-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) - 5) \times 6)) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) & 22043 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 22044 &:= (-12 \times -(3 + ((4^5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 22044 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22045 &:= (((-1 - 2)^3) - (4 \times ((-5 + 67) \times -(89)))) & 22045 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) + 21)) \\ 22046 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3!)^4 + (5 + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) & 22046 &:= (((9 + 8) \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) - ((2 + 1))) \\ 22047 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times 56)) \times 7)) \times 8) - 9) & 22047 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 22048 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 22048 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 22049 &:= (-((1 \times 23)) + (4 \times ((-5 + 67) \times 89))) & 22049 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + (3 / (2 + 1)))) \\ 22050 &:= ((1 - 23) + (4 \times ((-5) - 67) \times -(89))) & 22050 &:= ((987 + ((6 + 54) + 3)) \times 21) \\ 22051 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3)^4 + 5^6 - (7 + 8) \times 9 & 22051 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) - 6)) \times -((5 \times (4 + 3))^2)) + 1) \\ 22052 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5! - 6) + 7! + 8 + 9) & 22052 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 22053 &:= (-123 + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 22053 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22054 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 22054 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7 \times (6 + 5^4)) \times (3 + 2 \times 1) \\ 22055 &:= (((((-1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) & 22055 &:= 9 + (-8 + 7 \times (6 + 5^4)) \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\ 22056 &:= (-12 + (((3^{4+5}) - 67) / 8) \times 9) & 22056 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\ 22057 &:= (((1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - ((-6 - 7) - 8))) - 9) & 22057 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times 43)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 22058 &:= (-1^{23} + 45 \times 6) \times (-7 + 89) & 22058 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4) - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 22059 &:= (((((-1 \times 2) + ((345 + 6))) \times 7) + 8) \times -(-9)) & 22059 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5))^4)) + (3^{2+1})) \\ 22060 &:= (1 - (((2 - (345 + 6)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9) & 22060 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4) - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 22061 &:= (1 \times 2 - 3!) \times 4567 + 8! + 9 & 22061 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 22062 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) + (4^5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9) & 22062 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 76 + 5) \times 4 - 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\ 22063 &:= (-12 + (3 - ((4 \times (5 - 67)) \times 89))) & 22063 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 76 + 5) \times 4 - 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ 22064 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) + (4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 89)))) & 22064 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 76 + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 + 1 \\ 22065 &:= (1 - ((2^3) + ((4 \times (5 - 67)) \times 89))) & 22065 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 76 + 5) \times 4 + 3 \times (-2 + 1) \\ 22066 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^{4+5}) - 67) / 8) \times 9) & 22066 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 76 + 5) \times 4 - 3 + 2 - 1 \\ 22067 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3) - (-4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 89)))) & 22067 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 22068 &:= (((123 \times (4 \times 5)) - ((6 - 7) \times -8)) \times 9) & 22068 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 76 + 5) \times 4 + 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 22069 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^{4+5}) - 67) / 8) \times 9) & 22069 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 22070 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^{4+5}) - 67) / 8) \times 9) & 22070 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 76 + 5) \times 4 + 3 - 2 + 1 \\ 22071 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9) & 22071 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4)) + (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 22072 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) & 22072 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 22073 &:= (((((-1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) & 22073 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times -(6 - ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\ 22074 &:= ((-1 + (23 + 4)) \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) & 22074 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6^5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 22075 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 8)))) + 9) & 22075 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 76 + 5) \times 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ 22076 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times (678 - 9))) & 22076 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4) + (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 22077 &:= (((1 + 2) - (34 \times (5 + 67))) - 8) \times -9) & 22077 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 22078 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) & 22078 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\ 22079 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) & 22079 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 22080 &:= ((1 \times (2^3)) - ((4 \times (5 - 67)) \times 89)) & 22080 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6^5) - (4^{3+2+1}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22081 &:= ((1 + (2^3)) - ((4 \times (5 - 67)) \times 89)) \\
 22082 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - 67)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 22083 &:= ((-1234) - (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times -((8 + 9))) \\
 22084 &:= (((-1 + (2^3))^4) + (((5 \times (6 - 7)) + 8)^9)) \\
 22085 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (((3^{4+5}) - 67)/8) \times 9)) \\
 22086 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (((3^{4+5}) - 67)/8)) \times -9) \\
 22087 &:= ((12 + 3) - (4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 89))) \\
 22088 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (4 - ((-56) - (7 \times 8)) \times -9))) \\
 22089 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - ((6 + 7) \times 8))) + 9) \\
 22090 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 + 89))) \\
 22091 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 - 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 789)) \\
 22092 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times 67) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 22093 &:= (1 - ((23 - (45 + 6)) \times 789)) \\
 22094 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times ((45 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 22095 &:= -((-1 \times 23) - (4 \times ((-5 + 67) \times 89))) \\
 22096 &:= ((1 + 23) - (4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 89))) \\
 22097 &:= -((1 + ((-2 + ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times (78 + 9))) \\
 22098 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (3 + (((4 \times 5) - 6) \times -(-789)))) \\
 22099 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 22100 &:= ((1 - (2 + (345 - 6))) \times ((7 \times -8) - 9)) \\
 22101 &:= ((1 + ((2 - 34) \times 5)) \times (-67) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 22102 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9))) \\
 22103 &:= (((-1 - 2) + 34) \times (5 - (-6 + ((-78) \times 9)))) \\
 22104 &:= ((12 - 3) \times (-4 - ((5 \times (6 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\
 22105 &:= 1 + (2 - 3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\
 22106 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((34 \times (5 + 67)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
 22107 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22108 &:= ((-12 \times -3) - (4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 89))) \\
 22109 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!! + 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 22110 &:= ((-1 + (2 - 34)) \times (5 - ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 22111 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 34) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 22112 &:= (((-1 \times (2^3))) \times 4) \times ((5 + 6) - (78 \times 9)) \\
 22113 &:= (((1 \times 23) + 4) \times ((-5 \times -6) + (789))) \\
 22114 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 \times (78 - 9))) \\
 22115 &:= (((12^3) - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 89 \\
 22116 &:= (-(-12) + (((-34) \times (5 + 67)) - 8) \times -9) \\
 22117 &:= (((1 + 2) \times -3)^4) + (((5^6) - 78) + 9)) \\
 22118 &:= ((1 - 23) - (45 \times (6 \times (7 - 89)))) \\
 22119 &:= (((-1 + ((23 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) + 7)) \times 8) - 9) \\
 22120 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times (5 - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22081 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4^3 - 2) + 1) \\
 22082 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 22083 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5 \times 4 \times (3 + 2) - 1) \\
 22084 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\
 22085 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 22086 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22087 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) + 2)) + 1) \\
 22088 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times ((65 \times 4) - (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 22089 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((65 \times -4) + (3 \times 2)))) \times -((1))) \\
 22090 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 22091 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\
 22092 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 22093 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4) + 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 22094 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\
 22095 &:= ((9 \times (8 + (7 \times (65 + 4)))) \times (((3 \times 2) - 1))) \\
 22096 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) \times (3^2)) + 1) \\
 22097 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4) + 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22098 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times -(((4^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 22099 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 76) \times ((-((5 + 4)) \times 32) - (-1))) \\
 22100 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22101 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22102 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((65 + 4) \times 321))) \\
 22103 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3 - 2)))) - 1) \\
 22104 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + (2 + 1)))))))) \\
 22105 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3 - 2)))) + 1) \\
 22106 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22107 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22108 &:= (9 - ((87 \times ((65 \times -4) + (3 \times 2))) - ((1)))) \\
 22109 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
 22110 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 22111 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6 + 5 - 4)^3 + 21) \\
 22112 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -((6^5)/((4^3)/2))) - 1) \\
 22113 &:= (9 \times (((-87 - 6) + 54) \times ((-3 \times 21)))) \\
 22114 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -((6^5)/((4^3)/2))) + 1) \\
 22115 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times 7) + 6) - ((-5 \times 4321)) \\
 22116 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 22117 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 22118 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 22119 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2))) - 1) \\
 22120 &:= -((((98 - (7 \times 65)) \times (43 + (-2 - 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22121 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 22122 &:= ((1234 - 5) \times ((-6 + (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\
 22123 &:= ((-1234 \times -(5 + (6 + 7))) - 89) \\
 22124 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\
 22125 &:= (((-12 - 345) \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 22126 &:= -(((12 + 34) \times ((-56) \times 7) - (89))) \\
 22127 &:= (-1 \times -(((23 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) + 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 22128 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -(((4^5) + ((-6 - 7) - 89)))) \\
 22129 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 34) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
 22130 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3^{4+5})) - (6 + 7))/8) \times 9) \\
 22131 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6))) \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 22132 &:= -(((1 \times 2)) - ((3 - 45) \times ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 22133 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 - 45) \times -(((67 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 22134 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 + 4) \times (5 - 67))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 22135 &:= (-((-1 \times -2)) - (3 - (-45) \times (6 \times (7 - 89)))) \\
 22136 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((3 - 45) \times ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 22137 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 45) \times ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 22138 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (3 - (-45) \times (6 \times (7 - 89)))) \\
 22139 &:= -1^{23} + 45 \times 6 \times (-7 + 89) \\
 22140 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6))) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 22141 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((34 \times 5) - 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 22142 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + (-((45 \times 6) \times (7 - 89))) \\
 22143 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 - (45 \times (6 \times (7 - 89)))) \\
 22144 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) + 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 22145 &:= (-1 \times -(((23 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) + 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 22146 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 22147 &:= (-1 - (-((2^3)) + ((45 \times 6) \times (7 - 89))) \\
 22148 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (((45 + 6) + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 22149 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6))) \times (7 + 8))) \times -9) \\
 22150 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)^4 + (-5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 22151 &:= 1 \times ((2 \times 3)^4 + (-5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 22152 &:= 1 + ((2 \times 3)^4 + (-5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 22153 &:= (-1 \times (23 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 22154 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (((4^5) + ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 22155 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^{4+5}) + (6 + 7))/8) \times 9) \\
 22156 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^{4+5}) + (6 + 7))/8) \times 9) \\
 22157 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((34 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 22158 &:= (((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^{4+5}) + (6 + 7))/8) \times 9) \\
 22159 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^{4+5}) + (6 + 7))/8) \times 9) \\
 22160 &:= -((-1 - (-2 + (-((3 - (4 \times (56 + 7)))) \times 89))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22121 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) - (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 22122 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22123 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) - (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\
 22124 &:= (((-9 - 876) \times -(5 + (4 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 22125 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 22126 &:= (((-9 - 876) \times -(5 + (4 \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 22127 &:= (-98 + (7 \times ((6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) + 1))) \\
 22128 &:= ((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -(5 - (43^2 \times 1))) \\
 22129 &:= (((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -(5 - (43^2))) + 1) \\
 22130 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 22131 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 22132 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 22133 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 22134 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22135 &:= -98/7 + (65 + 4) \times 321 \\
 22136 &:= ((9 - (87 \times -6)) + (-5 \times -((4321)))) \\
 22137 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 + 5) \times 43) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 22138 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 + 5) \times 43) - 2)) + 1) \\
 22139 &:= ((((-9 + 8)) + 7) + ((-65 - 4) \times -321))) \\
 22140 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times 4)) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
 22141 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) + 2))) + 1) \\
 22142 &:= (((-98 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 22143 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 22144 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 \times (4 + 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 22145 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2))) - 1) \\
 22146 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22147 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 22148 &:= (((-9 + 8)^7) - ((65 + 4) \times -321)) \\
 22149 &:= (((-9 + 8)^7) \times ((65 + 4) \times -321)) \\
 22150 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (6^{5+4-3-2}))) - 1) \\
 22151 &:= -(((((-98 + 7) \times 6) - (5 \times (4321)))) \\
 22152 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22153 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (6^{5-4+3}))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22154 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times (-6 - (-5 \times -((43 - 2)))))) - (1)) \\
 22155 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22156 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times (-6 - (-5 \times -((43 - 2)))))) + (1)) \\
 22157 &:= -(((((-9 + 8) - 7) - ((-65 - 4) \times -321))) \\
 22158 &:= -((9 \times ((8 \times -76) + (-5 - (((43^2) \times 1)))))) \\
 22159 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3^{2+1})))) \\
 22160 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) + 4) \times -((3 + 2) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22161 &:= ((-12-3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22162 &:= ((-1+23) - ((-45) \times -((-6 \times (-7 + (89)))))) \\ 22163 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 - (4 \times (56+7))) \times 89))) \\ 22164 &:= (-12 - (((3 \times 4) - 56) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22165 &:= -(((-1 \times ((2+345) - 6) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 22166 &:= (1 - ((2 + (345 - 6)) \times ((7 \times -8) - 9))) \\ 22167 &:= -(((-12 \times ((34 \times 56) + (-7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 22168 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 - (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 22169 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) - (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22170 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22171 &:= (-1 \times ((2+3) - (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22172 &:= ((-12/3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22173 &:= ((-1+2) \times -(3 - (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22174 &:= (((-1+2) - 3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22175 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (34 - 56)) \times -7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22176 &:= (-(-1) \times (((2 \times (34 - 56)) \times -7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22177 &:= (-(-1) + (((2 \times (34 - 56)) \times -7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22178 &:= (((1 - 2) + 3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22179 &:= (-12+3)^4 + (-5^6 + 7) \times (8 - 9) \\ 22180 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) + ((5^6) - ((7+8) - 9))) \\ 22181 &:= (-1 \times -((2+3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22182 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times 3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22183 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22184 &:= (-1 - ((-2 - 3) \times ((45+6) \times (78+9)))) \\ 22185 &:= (((((-123 \times -4) \times 5) - (6+7)) + 8) \times -9) \\ 22186 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 22187 &:= ((((-12 - 3)^4) + ((5^6))) - ((7 - 8)^9)) \\ 22188 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 - ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\ 22189 &:= (1 - ((2 + (34 \times 5)) \times (6 - ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\ 22190 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 34)) \times ((5+6) + (7 \times 89))) \\ 22191 &:= (-12 + ((3 + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 22192 &:= ((1+2) \times 3)^4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 - 9 \\ 22193 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6+7)) + (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22194 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6+7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22195 &:= -(((-1234) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 22196 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 22197 &:= ((-12 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times 78)))))) + 9) \\ 22198 &:= ((-1 + 23) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22199 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22200 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - ((-6 \times (7 + 8)) - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22161 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7+6) \times ((5 \times 43) - 2)))) \times -1) \\ 22162 &:= ((-98/7) \times -(((6+5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 22163 &:= -(((9 \times -((8 \times 7) - 6)) + (-5 \times (4321)))) \\ 22164 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\ 22165 &:= -((((-9 - 87) + (6 - (5^4))) \times ((32 + (-1)))))) \\ 22166 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 - 3^2 - 1 \\ 22167 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 \times 3^2 \times 1 \\ 22168 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 22169 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 22170 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22171 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 22172 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 22173 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 22174 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 22175 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 22176 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 22177 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 22178 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 22179 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 22180 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 22181 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 22182 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22183 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ 22184 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 22185 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 22186 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3^2 + 1 \\ 22187 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 76) + (5^4))) + 3) \times -2) - 1) \\ 22188 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 22189 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 76) + (5^4))) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\ 22190 &:= -(((-9 + ((8 - (-76)) - 5)) \times (4 - 321))) \\ 22191 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - ((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 22192 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - 4) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 22193 &:= (-9 + (((8 - ((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 22194 &:= (-9 \times -((8 - (7 \times 6)) + ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 22195 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) - ((4 \times 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 22196 &:= ((-((9 - (8 \times 7))) + (((65 + 4) \times 321)))) \\ 22197 &:= (-98 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 22198 &:= (-98 + (((7 \times 65) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\ 22199 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 76) + (5^4))) - 3) \times -2) - 1) \\ 22200 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22201 &:= (12 \times 3 \times 4 + 5)^{-6+7-8+9} \\ 22202 &:= (((1234 + 5) + 67) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 22203 &:= (((1 \times -(-2)) - (((345 + 6) \times -7) - 8)) \times 9) \\ 22204 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\ 22205 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\ 22206 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times 8) \times 9 \\ 22207 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (456 + 7)))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 22208 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4 \times (5 + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 22209 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) - 9)) \\ 22210 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 22211 &:= ((1234 \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\ 22212 &:= (((-1 \times (2^{3+4})) - (5 \times (6 \times 78))) \times -9) \\ 22213 &:= ((-1234 \times -(5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\ 22214 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((456 + 7) \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 22215 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times 7)) \times 8) - 9) \\ 22216 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((456 + 7) \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 22217 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (((4 \times 5) - 6) \times (78 - 9)))) \\ 22218 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 22219 &:= (((-12 \times (3^4)) - (5 \times 67)) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 22220 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 22221 &:= ((12345 / (6 + (7 - 8))) \times 9) \\ 22222 &:= (-1 \times (((2 - 3) - ((45 \times 6))) \times (-7 + (89)))) \\ 22223 &:= (((1 - (-2 \times (3 \times (456 + 7)))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 22224 &:= (-12 \times -(34 + (((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 22225 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\ 22226 &:= (-1 - ((234 + 5) \times (-6 - ((78 + 9)))) \\ 22227 &:= (-1 \times ((234 + 5) \times (-6 - ((78 + 9)))) \\ 22228 &:= (1 + ((234 + 5) \times (6 + (78 + 9)))) \\ 22229 &:= (-((-1234) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) + (8 + 9) \\ 22230 &:= ((-1 \times 234) \times ((-((5 - 6) - 7) - 89)) \\ 22231 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times 7)) \times -8) - 9) \\ 22232 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 \times ((456 + 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 22233 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -3^4) + ((5^6) + ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 22234 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 \times ((456 + 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 22235 &:= (-1 + ((23 + 45) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 22236 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 \times (4 + (5 \times 6))) + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 22237 &:= (1 + ((23 + 45) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 22238 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times 67) - 8) \times 9) \\ 22239 &:= (((12 - 345) \times -(67)) - ((8 \times 9))) \\ 22240 &:= ((1 \times ((2 - 34) \times 5)) \times -(67 - (8 \times 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22201 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) - 2 \times 1 \\ 22202 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) - 2 + 1 \\ 22203 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 22204 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) + 2 - 1 \\ 22205 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) + 2 \times 1 \\ 22206 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\ 22207 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + (32 - 1)) \\ 22208 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\ 22209 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) + (32 + 1)) \\ 22210 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - ((7 - (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times 3))^2)) \times -1) \\ 22211 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4^3)) / 2)) - 1) \\ 22212 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 22213 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times (4^3)) / 2)) + 1) \\ 22214 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 765) \times (4 - (32 + 1))) \\ 22215 &:= ((9 \times (876 - 54)) \times 3) - (-21)) \\ 22216 &:= ((9 + (-((8 - ((7 + 6) \times 54))) \times 32)) - (1)) \\ 22217 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\ 22218 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22219 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) + 1) \\ 22220 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 22221 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times (3^{2+1})) \\ 22222 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 22223 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 22224 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\ 22225 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 22226 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\ 22227 &:= ((-((9 - 87)) - (-((65 + 4) \times 321))) \\ 22228 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 22229 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\ 22230 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 22231 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\ 22232 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 22233 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22234 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times 43)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22235 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) \times -1) \\ 22236 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 + (4^3)) - (2 - 1))) \\ 22237 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 43)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 22238 &:= ((-9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 43) - 2)) \times -1) \\ 22239 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 22240 &:= ((-9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 43)) \times -(2 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22241 &:= (((1 - (-2 \times (3 \times (456 + 7)))) \times 8) + 9) \\
 22242 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 22243 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 22244 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 22245 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8))) + 9) \\
 22246 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 22247 &:= (-1 + (-2 + (((3^{4-5+6}) + 7) \times 89))) \\
 22248 &:= (12 \times (-3 \times ((4 - 5) + (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 22249 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) \\
 22250 &:= ((123 + (((4 \times 5) \times 6) + 7)) \times 89) \\
 22251 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22252 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^{4-5+6}) + 7) \times 89)) \\
 22253 &:= ((-1 - (((2 + 34) - 5) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 22254 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((34 \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) + 9))) \\
 22255 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(456 \times 7)) - 89) \\
 22256 &:= (-1 - 2 \times 3! \times (4 - 5!)) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 22257 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times 8 + 9) \\
 22258 &:= (-12 + (34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
 22259 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\
 22260 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 22261 &:= (1 + ((-2 \times 3) \times ((4^5) + (-6 \times 789))) \\
 22262 &:= (12 + (((3^{4-5+6}) + 7) \times 89)) \\
 22263 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9)) \\
 22264 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (4 - ((56 - (-7 \times 8)) \times -9))) \\
 22265 &:= (12 - 3)^4 + (5^6 + 7 + 8 \times 9) \\
 22266 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 + 8)) \times 9) \\
 22267 &:= (-((1 + 2)) + (34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
 22268 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) + ((5^6) - (7 - 89))) \\
 22269 &:= (-((-1 + 2)) + ((34 \times 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\
 22270 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
 22271 &:= -((-((-1 + 2)) - ((34 \times 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
 22272 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (34 \times -((5 \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
 22273 &:= -((-((1 + 2)) - (34 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
 22274 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 + 8)) \times 9) \\
 22275 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times -((5 + 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 22276 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 22277 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22278 &:= ((12 - ((3 + 4) \times -5)) \times (-(-6) \times (7 - (-8 \times 9)))) \\
 22279 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 22280 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!! - 4) \times (5 \times 6 - 7 + 8) - 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22241 &:= (9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 43) + (2 - 1))) \\
 22242 &:= ((-9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times 43) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 22243 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 22244 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 22245 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 22246 &:= (-98 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 \times 4)) \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 22247 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + (3 - 2)))) - 1) \\
 22248 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\
 22249 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + (3 - 2)))) + 1) \\
 22250 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 22251 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))) + 21) \\
 22252 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 76) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\
 22253 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 76) \times ((-((5 + 4)) \times 32) + (-1))) \\
 22254 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 76) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1) \\
 22255 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times (4! + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 22256 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\
 22257 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 22258 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\
 22259 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 22260 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 22261 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -(5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 22262 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 22263 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1) \\
 22264 &:= (-9 + ((87 \times (((6 - 54) / -3)^2)) + 1)) \\
 22265 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 22266 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) + ((3^2) + 1))) \\
 22267 &:= ((-9 \times -((((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 22268 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + ((65 + 4) \times 321)) \\
 22269 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6^5) / (4 \times 3))) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 22270 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6^5) / (4 \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 22271 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 22272 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 22273 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 22274 &:= (9 + (8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5) \times 43 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 22275 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22276 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) + (65 \times 4))) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\
 22277 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 65) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\
 22278 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 22279 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 65) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
 22280 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + (6 \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22281 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (-3!! + 4!) \times (-5 + 6 + 7 + 8) + 9 \\
 22282 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 + 89))) \\
 22283 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 - 45) \times (67 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 22284 &:= -(((1234) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) - (-8 \times -9)) \\
 22285 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3 - 45) \times (67 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 22286 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4 \times 56) + 789)) \\
 22287 &:= -(123) + (45 \times (-6 + ((7 \times 8) \times 9))) \\
 22288 &:= 1 \times 2^3 \times (-4 + 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) \times 9) \\
 22289 &:= ((1 + 2)^3 + 4) \times (5 + 6 \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
 22290 &:= (-12 - ((3 - 45) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 22291 &:= -(1 + 2)^{3!} + 4 \times (-5 + 6! + 7!) \times (-8 + 9) \\
 22292 &:= (-12 + (34 \times (567 + 89))) \\
 22293 &:= (((-1 - (((2^3) \times 45) - 6)) \times 7) + 8) \times -9 \\
 22294 &:= (((-12 + 345) \times 67) - (8 + 9)) \\
 22295 &:= (((-1 + (2^3))^{4+5-6}) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 22296 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 22297 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9 \\
 22298 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3 + 45) \times 6)) \times 78) + 9)) \\
 22299 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 + ((5 - 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22300 &:= (1 \times (-2 - ((-3 + 45) \times ((67 - 8) \times -9))) \\
 22301 &:= ((-1234 \times -(5 + (6 + 7))) + 89) \\
 22302 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times ((-3 + 45) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 22303 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((-3 + 45) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 22304 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times -((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 - 89))) \\
 22305 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 - 45) \times (-67) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 22306 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (34 \times (567 + 89)))) \\
 22307 &:= ((1 + 2) + (34 \times (567 + 89))) \\
 22308 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - ((6 \times (7 + 8))/9))) \\
 22309 &:= (((1 - 23) \times ((-4^5) + 6)) - (78 + 9)) \\
 22310 &:= -((((12 + 345) \times -(67)) - (8 - 9))) \\
 22311 &:= (((12 + 345) \times -(67)) \times (8 - 9)) \\
 22312 &:= (((12 + 345) \times 67) - (8 - 9)) \\
 22313 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 22314 &:= (((1 - 23) \times -(((4^5) - 6))) - (-7 + 89)) \\
 22315 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 22316 &:= (12 + (34 \times (567 + 89))) \\
 22317 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) + 5))) \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 22318 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 22319 &:= -((1 + ((-2 + (3 + 4)) \times (((5 - 67) \times 8) \times 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22281 &:= ((((-98 \times 76) + (5 \times 4)) \times -3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22282 &:= ((((-98 \times 76) + (5 \times 4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 22283 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 22284 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22285 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\
 22286 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + (6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1))) \\
 22287 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6^5)/(4 \times 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 22288 &:= (((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 22289 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 22290 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 22291 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
 22292 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22293 &:= (-9 \times -((8 - 7) - ((6 - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 22294 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 22295 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\
 22296 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 22297 &:= (-((98 \times -7)) + (6 + ((5 \times 4321)))) \\
 22298 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22299 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -65) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\
 22300 &:= ((9 - 8 + 7) \times 6! - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 22301 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 22302 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 22303 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 22304 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times -((4^3)/(2 \times 1))) \\
 22305 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times -((4^3)/2)) + 1) \\
 22306 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 + 6)! - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 22307 &:= ((((-9 - 87) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 22308 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 22309 &:= ((((-9 - 87) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1) \\
 22310 &:= (((-98 + 7) - 6) \times -(5 \times (43 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22311 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + (7 + 6)) - ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 22312 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times 65) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
 22313 &:= ((((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) + 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 22314 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
 22315 &:= ((((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 22316 &:= ((-98 - ((7 \times 6) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
 22317 &:= ((((-98 + 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 22318 &:= ((((-98 + 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 22319 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22320 &:= (((1^{23}) + 4) \times ((-5 + 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 22321 &:= (1 - ((-2 + (3 + 4)) \times (((5 - 67) \times 8) \times 9))) \\
 22322 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (-4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 22323 &:= ((-12 + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 22324 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4 + 5! \times 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 22325 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 22326 &:= (-12 + ((34 \times ((5 \times (-6 - 7)) - 8)) \times -9)) \\
 22327 &:= ((((-1 - (2^3)) \times 456) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 22328 &:= (((-12 + 345) \times 67) - (-8 - 9)) \\
 22329 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(6 \times (7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 22330 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (4^5)) \times -(67 - 89)) \\
 22331 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 22332 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 22333 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 22334 &:= (((-1 - 234) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\
 22335 &:= ((((((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 22336 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 22337 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 + (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 22338 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 \times 3))^4) + (5 + (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 22339 &:= (((-1 + (234 + 5)) + (6 + 7)) \times 89) \\
 22340 &:= 1 \times 2 + 34 \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8) \times 9 \\
 22341 &:= (-12 + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8) + 9) \\
 22342 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - (4 \times (5 - 67))) \times 89)) \\
 22343 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 22344 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 \times (5 - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22345 &:= ((12 + 34) - 5) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9) \\
 22346 &:= (1 + ((2 + (34 + 5)) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 22347 &:= (12 + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times -((7 \times -8)) - 9) \\
 22348 &:= (((12^3) - (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 22349 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 6)) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 22350 &:= (-(-12) + ((34 \times ((5 \times (-6 - 7)) - 8)) \times -9)) \\
 22351 &:= (12 + ((-3 + (4 \times (5 - 67))) \times -(89))) \\
 22352 &:= (-((1 - 23)) \times ((4^5) + (((-6 + 7)^8) - 9))) \\
 22353 &:= ((((((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
 22354 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8) + 9) \\
 22355 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 22356 &:= (((-((1 + 2)) - 3)^4) + (-5 \times (-6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\
 22357 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 22358 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! \times 4! + 5!/6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 22359 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22320 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times ((7 + 6) - ((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22321 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times (4 \times (3 + 2))) + 1))) \\
 22322 &:= (-98 - (76 \times (5 \times (4 - (3 \times 21)))) \\
 22323 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 + (4 \times 3)))) \times -21) \\
 22324 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 + 5) \times 43) + 2)) - 1) \\
 22325 &:= ((((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) - 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 22326 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 22327 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 22328 &:= ((-987 - (((6^5) - 4) \times -3)) + (-((2 - 1))) \\
 22329 &:= (((98 \times 76) - 5) \times (4 + ((-3 - (2 \times -1)))) \\
 22330 &:= (((-98/7) \times (6 + 5)) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 22331 &:= (-987 + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22332 &:= (((((-98 \times 76) + 5) - 4) + 3) \times (-2 - 1)) \\
 22333 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22334 &:= (((9 \times (87 - 6)) - (-5 \times 4321)) \\
 22335 &:= ((-9 + ((87 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 22336 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - 76) \times 5)) \times -(4^3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 22337 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) - ((4^3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 22338 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
 22339 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) - ((4^3) \times 2))) + 1) \\
 22340 &:= ((-987 + ((6^5) \times (4 - (3 - 2)))) - 1) \\
 22341 &:= -(((98 \times (7 + (6 + (5 \times 43)))) - (-((2 + 1)))) \\
 22342 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 22343 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 22344 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + 5) \times -(4 \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22345 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\
 22346 &:= ((-98 + ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 22347 &:= (-9 \times -8 - (((7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
 22348 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 76) + ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 - 1)) \\
 22349 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 76) + ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22350 &:= (-9 + (87 \times ((6 - 5) + (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
 22351 &:= (-9 - (((-87 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3)) - 2) - (-1)) \\
 22352 &:= (((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 22353 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 \times (((6 + 54)/3)^2 - 1) \\
 22354 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 43))) + (2 + 1))) \\
 22355 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times 4)) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\
 22356 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 22357 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7) \times (-6 + (5 \times 4 - 3)^2 \times 1) \\
 22358 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (65 \times 43)) - (2 \times (1))) \\
 22359 &:= (((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (65 \times 43)) - (2 - (1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$22360 := ((1 - (23 \times ((4 + 5) + 6))) \times (7 + (8 \times -9)))$$

$$22361 := (((1 - (2^3)) \times 456) \times -7) + (8 + 9)$$

$$22362 := (((12^3) + (4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (89)$$

$$22363 := (1 - 2 - 3!!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7!) + 8 + 9$$

$$22364 := (-1 - (((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times 678) + 9))$$

$$22365 := (((1 - 2) - 34) \times (-567 - (8 \times 9)))$$

$$22366 := (1 - (((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times 678) + 9))$$

$$22367 := ((((-12 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) - 9$$

$$22368 := ((-1 \times (-234) - (5 - 6)) \times (7 + 89))$$

$$22369 := (((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) \times -8) + 9$$

$$22370 := (1 + (((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) \times 8) + 9))$$

$$22371 := ((-(-12 - 3)) \times ((4^5) - (-6 \times 78))) - 9$$

$$22372 := ((12 + (34 \times 5)) + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))$$

$$22373 := ((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) + ((5 \times 6) \times 789))$$

$$22374 := (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (-4 + 5 \times (-6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9))$$

$$22375 := ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)$$

$$22376 := ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)$$

$$22377 := (((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) \times -8) + 9$$

$$22378 := ((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times ((5 \times 67) + (8 - 9)))$$

$$22379 := ((1 - ((2 - 34) \times 5)) \times (67 + (8 \times 9)))$$

$$22380 := (-12 + ((3 + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))$$

$$22381 := (1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times 5 \times 6 + (-7 + 8)^9$$

$$22382 := (-1 + ((23 + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))$$

$$22383 := (((-1 + 2) - ((3 + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9)$$

$$22384 := (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9))))$$

$$22385 := ((((-12 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times -8) + 9$$

$$22386 := ((1 + (-2^3)) \times ((45 - 6) \times (7 - 89)))$$

$$22387 := (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))$$

$$22388 := (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 - (8 - 9)))$$

$$22389 := ((-(-12 - 3)) \times ((4^5) - (-6 \times 78))) + 9$$

$$22390 := (-(((1 - 2) - 3)) \times (4567 - 89))$$

$$22391 := (-1 - (-((2 + 34) \times ((5 - 6) + (7 \times 89))))$$

$$22392 := ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 + 5)) \times (6 + 7)))) \times (8 \times 9))$$

$$22393 := ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))$$

$$22394 := ((-1 - (-23 \times (4^5))) + ((-6 - 7) \times 89))$$

$$22395 := ((-12 - 3) - (45 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$22396 := (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (4^5)) \times -(67 - 89))$$

$$22397 := (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) + 89))$$

$$22398 := (((-1 + 2) - (3 + 4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 89))))$$

$$22360 := ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 - 5) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$22361 := (((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (65 \times 43)) + (2 - (1)))$$

$$22362 := (((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (65 \times 43)) + (2 \times (1)))$$

$$22363 := (((9 - (8 - 7)) \times (65 \times 43)) + (2 + (1)))$$

$$22364 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1)$$

$$22365 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))$$

$$22366 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1))$$

$$22367 := (((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$22368 := (((-9 - 87) \times -(((6 + (5 \times 4)) \times (3^2)) - 1))$$

$$22369 := ((((-9) - (-87 \times ((65 \times 4) - 3))) + 2) + (-1))$$

$$22370 := (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1))$$

$$22371 := (((-9 \times -8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))) - (2 + 1))$$

$$22372 := (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) + (4^3)) \times (2 \times 1)))$$

$$22373 := (((-9 \times -8) \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + 3)) - 2) - 1$$

$$22374 := (-9 \times -8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))))$$

$$22375 := (((-9 \times -8) \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + 3)) - 2) + 1$$

$$22376 := (-((9 - (8 - 7))) \times ((-65 \times 43) - ((-2 \times -1))))$$

$$22377 := (((-9 \times -8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3)))) + (2 + 1))$$

$$22378 := (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1)$$

$$22379 := (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - 2)) - 1)$$

$$22380 := -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1$$

$$22381 := -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1$$

$$22382 := -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1$$

$$22383 := (-9 \times ((8 - ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) - 3)) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$22384 := (((-9 \times -87) + ((6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1))$$

$$22385 := (((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1))$$

$$22386 := (((-9 + (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times ((543 + 2) + 1))$$

$$22387 := (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))$$

$$22388 := (-98 - ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)))$$

$$22389 := (((-9 \times -8) \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + 3)) - (2 + 1))$$

$$22390 := (9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 \times 43)) + 21))$$

$$22391 := (((-9 \times -8) \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + 3)) - (2 - 1))$$

$$22392 := (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + (4 + 3))^{2+1})))$$

$$22393 := (((-9 \times -8) \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + 3)) + (2 - 1))$$

$$22394 := (((9 \times 87) + 6) + (5 \times (4321)))$$

$$22395 := (((-9 \times (-8 - ((7 \times 6)) \times (5 + (-4^3)))) + 21)$$

$$22396 := (((-98 - 7) + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1))$$

$$22397 := 9 + (-8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3) \times 2 \times 1$$

$$22398 := (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22399 &:= (((-12 \times (34 + 5)) \times -6) - 7) \times -8 - 9 \\ 22400 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times -56) \times ((-7 + 8) - (-9)) \\ 22401 &:= -(((-1 + 2) + (34 \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + 89)) \\ 22402 &:= -((-1 \times (23 \times ((4^5) - 67) + (8 + 9)))) \\ 22403 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 22404 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 6)) + (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 22405 &:= -((1 \times 23) - (-4 \times ((56 + 7) \times 89))) \\ 22406 &:= ((-12/3) - (-45) \times (-6 - (-7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22407 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\ 22408 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4)^5))/6) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 22409 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times (4 \times 5)) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\ 22410 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 \times 5)) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9) \\ 22411 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 - (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 22412 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (67 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 22413 &:= ((-12 - 3) - ((-4 \times (56 + 7)) \times 89)) \\ 22414 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 22415 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 22416 &:= (-12 + ((-3 - 45) - 6) \times (7 \times 89)) \\ 22417 &:= ((-1 + (2^3)) - (45 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22418 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) + (-5^6)) - ((7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 22419 &:= (-12 + (3 + (-4 \times (56 + 7)) \times 89)) \\ 22420 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 6)) + (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 22421 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - 5) + (6 \times (7 \times 89))))) \\ 22422 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5 \times 6) - 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 22423 &:= ((((-1 \times -2 \times 3)^4) + ((5 \times 6) - 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 22424 &:= (-1 - (23 \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22425 &:= -(((-1 - 2) \times 3) - (-4 \times ((56 + 7) \times 89))) \\ 22426 &:= -(((1 - 2) + 3) + ((-4 \times (56 + 7)) \times 89)) \\ 22427 &:= (-1 - (((234 + 5) + (6 + 7)) \times -89)) \\ 22428 &:= (-1 \times (((234 + 5) + (6 + 7)) \times -89)) \\ 22429 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - 3) - ((4 \times (56 + 7)) \times 89)) \\ 22430 &:= (((1 - 2) + 3) - (-4 \times (56 + 7) \times 89)) \\ 22431 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times 3) - (-4 \times ((56 + 7) \times 89)) \\ 22432 &:= -((1 - 2) + (3 - (-4 \times ((56 + 7) \times 89)))) \\ 22433 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times 8 - 9)) \\ 22434 &:= (1 \times ((-2 \times 3) \times ((4 - 5) + (6 \times (7 \times -89)))) \\ 22435 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 22436 &:= (-1234) + ((-5 \times 6) \times -789) \\ 22437 &:= (1 + ((2^3) + ((4 \times (56 + 7)) \times 89))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22399 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 22400 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 22401 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 22402 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 \times 1 \\ 22403 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22404 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 22405 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 22406 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 22407 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 22408 &:= (((-98 + 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 22409 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 22410 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 22411 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 22412 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7! + 6! + 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 22413 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 22414 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 22415 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1))) \\ 22416 &:= (((-98/7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22417 &:= ((((-98/7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 22418 &:= ((-98 + 76) \times (5 - (4^{3+2} \times 1))) \\ 22419 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 22420 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 22421 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\ 22422 &:= (9 + (-87 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times ((-3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 22423 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 22424 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 22425 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -(5 \times (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1))))) \\ 22426 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 22427 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 22428 &:= ((9 + 87) + (6 \times (54 \times 3))) \times 21 \\ 22429 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 22430 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 76) \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2) + 1)) \\ 22431 &:= (-98 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 22432 &:= (-9 - (((8 + ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 22433 &:= (-9 - ((8 + ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 22434 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 22435 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\ 22436 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 22437 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 + 4)))) \times (3^{2+1})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22438 &:= ((-1+2) - ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\ 22439 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\ 22440 &:= (-((12 \times 34)) \times ((-5 - 67) + (8 + 9))) \\ 22441 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) + ((5^6) - (7 + 89))) \\ 22442 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! + (5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 22443 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7)) + 8)) - 9 \\ 22444 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (67 + (8 + 9))) \\ 22445 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8))) \times 9)) \\ 22446 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -(((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\ 22447 &:= (((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9 \\ 22448 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) \\ 22449 &:= ((12 \times (34 \times (56 + (7 - 8)))) + 9) \\ 22450 &:= (-12 + ((3 - (4^5)) \times (67 - 89))) \\ 22451 &:= ((1 \times 23) - (-4 \times ((56 + 7) \times 89))) \\ 22452 &:= ((1 + 23) + (4 \times ((56 + 7) \times 89))) \\ 22453 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 78) - 9)) \\ 22454 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 + 45) \times 6 \times 78 - 9 \\ 22455 &:= (((((-1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) + 6) - 7) - (-8 \times -9)) \\ 22456 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 45) \times 6 \times 78 - 9 \\ 22457 &:= (-1 + 23) \times 4^5 - (6 + 7 \times 8 + 9) \\ 22458 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 + 4)) \times (5 + ((6 \times 7) \times 89))) \\ 22459 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((-3 + (4^5)) \times (67 - 89))) \\ 22460 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (67 - (8 - 9))) \\ 22461 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((34 + 5) \times (-6 \times (7 + 89)))) \\ 22462 &:= ((1^2) \times -((-3 + (4^5))) \times (67 - 89))) \\ 22463 &:= ((1^2) + (-((-3 + (4^5))) \times (67 - 89))) \\ 22464 &:= ((-1 \times 234) \times (((5 - 6) \times 7) - 89)) \\ 22465 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 22466 &:= (-((-1 \times 2) - (((34 + 5) \times -6) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 22467 &:= ((-12 + (((3^{4+5}) - 6) / 7) \times 8)) - 9 \\ 22468 &:= (((12/3) + (45 \times 6)) \times (-7 + (89))) \\ 22469 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 22470 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22471 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (((3^{4+5}) - 6) / 7)) \times -8) - 9) \\ 22472 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3 + 45) \times (6 \times 78)) + 9)) \\ 22473 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3 + (4 + 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)))) \times -9) \\ 22474 &:= (-1 + (-((2 + 3) \times (-4567) + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22475 &:= ((1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (-(((4 - 567) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 22476 &:= (-(-12) - ((-34) - 5) \times -((-6 \times (7 + 89)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22438 &:= (-9 + ((87 \times ((65 + (4^3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 22439 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 22440 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22441 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22442 &:= ((9 \times (87 + 6)) - (5 \times (-4321))) \\ 22443 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 22444 &:= (((98 + 7) - 6) + (5^4)) \times ((32 - 1)) \\ 22445 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 22446 &:= ((9 \times ((-87 + 6) - 5)) \times (((4 - 32) - 1))) \\ 22447 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + (4 + 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 22448 &:= ((-987 + (6 + 5)) \times (4 - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 22449 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - 76) \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2))) \times -1) \\ 22450 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 22451 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\ 22452 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22453 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\ 22454 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((65 + (4^3)) \times 2))) - 1) \\ 22455 &:= 9 \times ((-8 + 7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 + 1) \\ 22456 &:= (((-9 + 8) - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 22457 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22458 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22459 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times ((4 \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\ 22460 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1) \\ 22461 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 22462 &:= ((-((9 - 87)) \times (6 \times (5 + 43))) - (2 \times (1))) \\ 22463 &:= ((-(((9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times 54)) \times -32) - (1) \\ 22464 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 22465 &:= ((-(((9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times 54)) \times -32) + (1) \\ 22466 &:= ((-((9 - 87)) \times (6 \times (5 + 43))) + (2 \times (1))) \\ 22467 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22468 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 22469 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 22470 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 22471 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\ 22472 &:= (9 - 8 + 7) \times (65 - 4 \times 3)^2 \times 1 \\ 22473 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times (5^4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 22474 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4^{3+2-1})))) \\ 22475 &:= (((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1) \\ 22476 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22477 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - 5)) \times (-6 - 7)) \times (8 - 9) \\
 22478 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 22479 &:= ((((((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^{4+5}) - 6) / 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 22480 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) - (6 \times ((7 - 8) + 9))) \\
 22481 &:= ((((((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 22482 &:= (((((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6) - (7 \times 8)) \times -9) \\
 22483 &:= (((1 - 23) \times ((-4^5) + 6)) + (78 + 9)) \\
 22484 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 - (7 - (8 - 9)))))) \\
 22485 &:= (12 + (((3 + 45) \times (6 \times 78)) + 9)) \\
 22486 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 22487 &:= (((((1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) + 6) + (7 \times -8)) + 9) \\
 22488 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times ((4 - 5) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22489 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (-((4^5) + 6)) + 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 22490 &:= ((-1 - (23 \times (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 22491 &:= (((1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4) \times (56 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 22492 &:= (1 + ((23 + 4) \times ((56 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 22493 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (-5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\
 22494 &:= (((12^3) - (4 - 5)) \times (-(-6) + 7)) - (-8 - 9) \\
 22495 &:= (-1 + (-((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + (78 \times 9)))))) \\
 22496 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times -4 \times ((5 - 6) - (78 \times 9))) \\
 22497 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times ((4^5) + (-6 \times 7))) - 89)) \\
 22498 &:= (1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + (-6 \times 7))) - 89)) \\
 22499 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times (((5 + 6) - (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
 22500 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\
 22501 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (((3 - 45) \times (67 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 22502 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3 - 45) \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 22503 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) - (((6 \times 7) - 8) + (-9))) \\
 22504 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3 - 45) \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 22505 &:= (-((1 \times 23)) - ((-(-4)^5) \times (67 - 89))) \\
 22506 &:= (-1 + (2 - 3 + 4)^5) \times (6 + 78 + 9) \\
 22507 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 - 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 22508 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times -((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 22509 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 + 8)))) \times -9) \\
 22510 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 22511 &:= (-((1 \times ((2 + 3) \times ((4 - 567) \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 22512 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times ((4 - 567) \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 22513 &:= ((-1 - (23 \times (-((4^5) - (6 \times -7)))) + (8 \times -9)) \\
 22514 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
 22515 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 6)) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22477 &:= (((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1) \\
 22478 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((54 \times 32) + 1))) \\
 22479 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22480 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 22481 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 \times 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
 22482 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 22483 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\
 22484 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22485 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22486 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times (((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1))) \\
 22487 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\
 22488 &:= ((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\
 22489 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\
 22490 &:= (9 + (876 + ((5 \times 4321)))) \\
 22491 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6) \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 22492 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 22493 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 22494 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times (5^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 22495 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 22496 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times (4^3 + 2) - 1 \\
 22497 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times (4^3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 22498 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times (4^3 + 2) + 1 \\
 22499 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times (5^4)) - (3 / (2 + 1))) \\
 22500 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 / (2 + 1) \\
 22501 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3 / (2 + 1))) \\
 22502 &:= (((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22503 &:= (((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22504 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 22505 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 22506 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 22507 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 22508 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)}))) \\
 22509 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 22510 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times (5^4)) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 22511 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 22512 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 22513 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1) \\
 22514 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times (4^3 + 2) - 1 \\
 22515 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times (4^3 + 2) \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22516 &:= (((12^3) + 4) \times ((-5 - (6 - (7 + 8))) + 9)) \\
 22517 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
 22518 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
 22519 &:= (((1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - 567))) \times 8) - 9) \\
 22520 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3 - (45)) \times (67 \times -8)) + 9)) \\
 22521 &:= (-1 + 23) \times 4^5 - 6 - (-7 + 8)^9 \\
 22522 &:= (-1 + 23) \times 4^5 + 6 \times (7 - 8)^9 \\
 22523 &:= ((1 \times -2) - (3 - ((4^5) \times (67 - 89)))) \\
 22524 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 22525 &:= (((-12 \times ((3^4) + (5 \times 6))) + 7) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 22526 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 22527 &:= -(((1 \times -2) + (3 - ((4^5) \times (67 - 89)))) \\
 22528 &:= (((-1^{23}) \times 4^5) \times (67 - 89)) \\
 22529 &:= (-((1 \times ((2 + 3) \times ((4 - 567) \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 22530 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times ((4 - 567) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 22531 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 6)) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 22532 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) - (6 + (7 - 8))) + 9) \\
 22533 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 22534 &:= (-1 + 23) \times 4^5 + 6 \times (-7 + 8)^9 \\
 22535 &:= (-1 + 23) \times 4^5 + 6 + (-7 + 8)^9 \\
 22536 &:= (-((12 \times 3) \times (4 - ((-5 - 67) + 8) \times 9))) \\
 22537 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 - ((3 - 45) \times 67)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 22538 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 \times (7 + 8))/9)) \\
 22539 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - ((45 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8))) - 9) \\
 22540 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - 5)) \times (6 + 7) + (89)) \\
 22541 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 - 9) \\
 22542 &:= -((((1 - 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
 22543 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 22544 &:= -((((1 - 23) \times (4^5)) - 6) - ((-7 + 8) + 9)) \\
 22545 &:= (((((-1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7 + 8)) \times -9) \\
 22546 &:= 1 + ((2 + 3^4) \times 5 \times 6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\
 22547 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) - (-((5^6) - (7 - 8))) - 9) \\
 22548 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 + 4)^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 8))/9) \\
 22549 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
 22550 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6/(7 + 8) - 9))) \\
 22551 &:= (-(-((1 \times 23))) - ((-4)^5) \times (67 - 89)) \\
 22552 &:= ((1 + 23) - ((4^5) \times (67 - 89))) \\
 22553 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 22554 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) + (5 \times (6 + (7 + 8)))) \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22516 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 + 5) \times (4^3 + 2) + 1 \\
 22517 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 22518 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 22519 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\
 22520 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22521 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22522 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1) \\
 22523 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 22524 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 22525 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 22526 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 22527 &:= -((9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54))) + (32 + (1)))) \\
 22528 &:= (((-9 + (8 - 7)) \times ((-65) \times -43) - 21)) \\
 22529 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})) \\
 22530 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22531 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 22532 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2) - 1) \\
 22533 &:= (((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times -(5 + (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22534 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2) + 1) \\
 22535 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 22536 &:= -((-((-9 - (876 + 54))) \times (-3 - 21))) \\
 22537 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 22538 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times (54 - 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22539 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 22540 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + 5) \times -(4 \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
 22541 &:= ((9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (5 \times 4321)) \\
 22542 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 22543 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 22544 &:= (-9 \times 87) + 6^5 \times (4 - 3 + 2) - 1 \\
 22545 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 22546 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 22547 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 22548 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 22549 &:= ((9 \times 8) - (((-7 - 6) \times ((54 \times 32) + 1)))) \\
 22550 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1)) \\
 22551 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times 43) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 22552 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times 65)) \times 4) - (32 \times 1)) \\
 22553 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3^2))) - 1) \\
 22554 &:= (((98 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times 4)) \times (3 \times 21))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$22555 := -(((123 - (4 \times -(56))) \times ((7 \times -8) - 9)))$$

$$22556 := (1 - 2 \times 3!! \times 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$22557 := ((-12 \times (3 - ((45 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8))) + 9)$$

$$22558 := (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 + (8 + 9))))$$

$$22559 := (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))$$

$$22560 := (12 \times ((-34) \times -(56)) - ((7 + (8 + 9))))$$

$$22561 := (1 + ((234 - (5 - 6)) \times (7 + 89)))$$

$$22562 := (-1 + (23 \times ((4 + (5 \times (6 + (7 + 8)))) \times 9)))$$

$$22563 := ((-12 + ((345 - 6))) \times (78 - 9))$$

$$22564 := (-12 - (34 \times (5 - (678 - 9))))$$

$$22565 := (-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times (((4 - 567) \times 8) - 9)))$$

$$22566 := (1 - ((2 + 3) \times (((4 - 567) \times 8) - 9)))$$

$$22567 := (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) + (8 + 9))$$

$$22568 := ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (((5^6) + (7 - 8))/9))$$

$$22569 := (((-12 - 3) \times -(4 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) + 9)$$

$$22570 := (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9))))$$

$$22571 := (-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times ((5 + 6) - 7)) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$22572 := (-((1 - 23) \times (((4^5) - 6) + 7) + (-8 + 9)))$$

$$22573 := (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (-78 - 9))$$

$$22574 := (-1 \times -(2 - (3 \times ((4 - (56 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))))$$

$$22575 := (((1 - 2) - 34) \times (5 \times -((6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))))$$

$$22576 := (((1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) + (6 \times ((7 - 8) + 9)))$$

$$22577 := ((-1 + 2) - (34 \times (5 - (678 - 9))))$$

$$22578 := (-((1 \times -2)) + (-34 \times ((5 - 678) + 9)))$$

$$22579 := ((1 + 2) - (34 \times (5 - (678 - 9))))$$

$$22580 := ((-123) + (4 \times 5678)) - 9$$

$$22581 := ((-(((12^3) + 4)) - 5) \times (-6 + (7 \times (8 - 9))))$$

$$22582 := (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (6 \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))$$

$$22583 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))$$

$$22584 := ((-1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))$$

$$22585 := (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9))))))$$

$$22586 := ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9))))$$

$$22587 := (-12 + ((3^4) \times (((5 \times 6) - (7 - 8)) \times 9)))$$

$$22588 := (12 + (-34) \times ((5 - 678) + 9))$$

$$22589 := (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8)) \times 9))$$

$$22590 := (((-(((123 \times 4) \times 5)) + 6) + ((7 \times -8)) \times -9)$$

$$22591 := (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9))$$

$$22592 := ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 + (4^5)) \times (67 - 89)))$$

$$22593 := (-1 + 2 \times (3 \times 4 \times 56 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$22594 := ((1 - 23) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times -((-7 + 8)) - 9))$$

$$22555 := (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3^2))) + 1)$$

$$22556 := ((-98 + ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times 2))) \times -1)$$

$$22557 := (((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) - 2)) - 1))$$

$$22558 := ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)))$$

$$22559 := (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times 5) \times -((4^3)/2)) - 1)$$

$$22560 := (((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))$$

$$22561 := (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times 5) \times -((4^3)/2)) + 1)$$

$$22562 := (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + (4^3))) - (2 - 1))$$

$$22563 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5)) \times (4 - (3^{2+1})))$$

$$22564 := (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + (4^3))) + (2 - 1))$$

$$22565 := (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))$$

$$22566 := (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + (4^3))) + (2 + 1))$$

$$22567 := ((-9 - ((8 + ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times 2)) \times -1)$$

$$22568 := (((-9 + (87 \times 65)) - 4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1))$$

$$22569 := (987 + (654 \times (32 + 1)))$$

$$22570 := (9 - 8 + 7! + 6! - 5!) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$22571 := (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1)$$

$$22572 := ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times 4) \times (3^{2+1}))$$

$$22573 := (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1)$$

$$22574 := (((-98 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1)$$

$$22575 := (-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4^{3+2-1}))))$$

$$22576 := ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) - (2 + 1)))$$

$$22577 := ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)$$

$$22578 := (-(((9 - (87 \times 65)) \times 4) + (3 + 2))) + (-1)$$

$$22579 := (((9 - (87 \times 65)) \times 4) + (3 + 2)) \times (-1)$$

$$22580 := (-(((9 - (87 \times 65)) \times 4) + (3 + 2))) - (-1)$$

$$22581 := (-9 + (((8 + 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))$$

$$22582 := ((-(((9 - (87 \times 65)) \times 4)) - (3 - 2)) + (-1))$$

$$22583 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)$$

$$22584 := (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 + (2 + 1))))$$

$$22585 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) + 1)$$

$$22586 := ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)))$$

$$22587 := (((9 \times -87) \times 6) \times -5) - (43 \times 21))$$

$$22588 := (((-9 + (87 \times 65)) \times 4) + ((3 + 2) - 1))$$

$$22589 := ((((-9 \times ((8 + 7) + (6 \times (5^4))))/3) \times -2) - 1)$$

$$22590 := ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 + 1)))$$

$$22591 := ((-9 \times (((-87 \times 6) + (5 \times 4)) \times (3 + 2))) - (-1))$$

$$22592 := (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) - 2)) - 1)$$

$$22593 := (((9 + (87 \times 65)) \times 4) + ((3 \times -21)))$$

$$22594 := (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2-1})))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22595 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 22596 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (-3 \times -(45)))) \times ((67 + 8) + 9)) \\ 22597 &:= (1 + (2 - (-((-3 - (4^5)))) \times (67 - 89))) \\ 22598 &:= ((-123) + (4 \times 5678)) + 9 \\ 22599 &:= (((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8))) + 9) \\ 22600 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 \times 6) - (7 - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 22601 &:= (-((1 - 234)) \times (-5 + ((6 + 7) + 89))) \\ 22602 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9))) \\ 22603 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 22604 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 7) - 89)) \\ 22605 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 22606 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 22607 &:= (1 + (((23 + (4 \times 56)) + 7) \times 89)) \\ 22608 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -(6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 22609 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 22610 &:= (((1 - 234) - 5) \times (((6 + 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\ 22611 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times 89)))) \\ 22612 &:= ((-(((1 - 23) \times (4^5))) + (67 + 8)) + 9) \\ 22613 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 22614 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - ((567 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 22615 &:= (((((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9 \\ 22616 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (((-4^5) + 6) + ((7 - 8) - 9))) \\ 22617 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9) \\ 22618 &:= 12 + (-3^4 + 5 \times 67) \times 89 \\ 22619 &:= (((12^3) \times 4) + (((5^6) - 7) + (89))) \\ 22620 &:= (-1 \times -((2 - (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22621 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 + (78 + 9))) \\ 22622 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 22623 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 22624 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - 6))) - 789) \\ 22625 &:= -(((1 - 23) \times (-23 \times ((-4^5) + 6))) + 789) \\ 22626 &:= ((-(-1) + (-23 \times ((-4^5) + 6))) - (789)) \\ 22627 &:= ((12 \times (3 + ((45 \times 6) \times 7))) - 89) \\ 22628 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3 + 45) \times 6)) \times 78) + 9)) \\ 22629 &:= -(((((-1 \times 234) - 56) \times -(-78)) - 9)) \\ 22630 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 + 89))) \\ 22631 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\ 22632 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 22633 &:= (((((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9 \\ 22634 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times ((567 \times 8) - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22595 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 22596 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) \times -7) / 6) \times ((54 \times (-3 - 2)) + 1))) \\ 22597 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\ 22598 &:= ((987 + 6) + (5 \times (4321))) \\ 22599 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 + 4)))) - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 22600 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 \times 4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\ 22601 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\ 22602 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 - 1))) \\ 22603 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 22604 &:= (-9 + (((87 \times 65) \times 4) - (3 \times 2)) - (1)) \\ 22605 &:= (((98 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times ((4 \times 3) + 21)) \\ 22606 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times (-65 \times -4))) - (3 + 2)) \times (1)) \\ 22607 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times (-65 \times -4))) - (3 + 2)) + (1)) \\ 22608 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) + (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 22609 &:= (((-9 - (-((87 \times 65)) \times 4)) - 3) - (-((2 - 1)))) \\ 22610 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 22611 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22612 &:= ((-98 - ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 22613 &:= (-9 - (-(((87 \times 65) \times 4)) - (((3 - 2) + 1)))) \\ 22614 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 22615 &:= (-9 + (((87 \times (-65 \times -4)) + (3 + 2)) - (1))) \\ 22616 &:= (-9 + (((87 \times (-65 \times -4)) + (3 + 2)) \times (1))) \\ 22617 &:= (-9 + (((87 \times (-65 \times -4)) + (3 + 2)) + (1))) \\ 22618 &:= (-9 - ((87 \times (65 \times -4)) - ((3 \times 2) + ((1)))))) \\ 22619 &:= (-9 - (((87 \times -65) \times 4) - ((3^2) + (-1)))) \\ 22620 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 22621 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 22622 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((54 + 3)^2) - 1)))) \\ 22623 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + 4) \times -3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 22624 &:= (((9 \times (8 - (-76 + 5))) - 4) \times ((32 \times 1))) \\ 22625 &:= ((9 + (-87 \times (65 \times -4))) - (((3 + 2) - (1)))) \\ 22626 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 22627 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 65) \times 4)) + (-((3 - 2)) - ((1)))) \\ 22628 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 22629 &:= (((9 + ((87 \times 65) \times 4)) + ((3 - 2))) - ((1))) \\ 22630 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22631 &:= (((9 + ((87 \times 65) \times 4)) + ((3 - 2))) + ((1))) \\ 22632 &:= -98 \times 7 + (6^5 - 4) \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\ 22633 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22634 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22635 &:= (((-1-2) - ((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8)) \times -9) & 22635 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 65) \times 4)) + (((3+2) + 1))) \\ 22636 &:= (((-1+23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 + (8+9))) & 22636 &:= ((9 + ((87 \times 65) \times 4)) + (((3 \times 2) + (1)))) \\ 22637 &:= -1 + (2+3+4^5) \times (-67+89) & 22637 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 + ((5+4) \times 3)))) - (2-1)) \\ 22638 &:= ((-1+23) \times ((4^5) - (67 - (8 \times 9)))) & 22638 &:= 98 \times 7 \times (6+5+43-21) \\ 22639 &:= 1 + (2+3+4^5) \times (-67+89) & 22639 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (((6^5) - (4-3)) \times (2+1))) \\ 22640 &:= -(((12 \times 3) + (-4 \times (5678-9)))) & 22640 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 + ((5+4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 22641 &:= (((-1+23) \times (4^5)) - (6 - (7 \times (8+9)))) & 22641 &:= (98 + (((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) \times -2) + (1))) \\ 22642 &:= (((-1+23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 22642 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + ((6^5) \times ((4-3) \times (2+1)))) \\ 22643 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) - 5)) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) & 22643 &:= ((((-9 - (8+7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 22644 &:= ((-1-2) \times (3 \times (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8+9)))) & 22644 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + (2+1))) \\ 22645 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - (45 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8-9)) & 22645 &:= ((((-9 - (8+7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 22646 &:= (1+2) \times 3! + 4 \times (-5! + 6! + 7! + 8+9) & 22646 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times (((6 \times (5+4)) + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\ 22647 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^{4-5+6}) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) & 22647 &:= ((9 - (-((87 \times 65) \times 4)) + ((-3+21))) \\ 22648 &:= (1+2 \times 3!) \times (4^5 + 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 & 22648 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times (6+5))) - 4) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 22649 &:= (((-1-2)^3) + (4 \times (5678-9))) & 22649 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7-6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2-1))) \\ 22650 &:= (((-1+23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7 - (8+9))) & 22650 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 65)) \times 4) - (3+2)) + (-1) \\ 22651 &:= (-1 \times (((2+3) \times (4 - (567 \times 8))) + 9)) & 22651 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 65)) \times 4) - ((3+2) \times 1)) \\ 22652 &:= (((-1+23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 - (8-9))) & 22652 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6 \times (5+4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 22653 &:= (((-1-2) + (3 \times ((4 + (5+6)) \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9) & 22653 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + (5+4)) \times 3))) - (2+1))) \\ 22654 &:= (-((-1+23)) - (-4 \times (-(-5678) - 9))) & 22654 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times (3 \times (2-1)))) \\ 22655 &:= (-1 \times -(23 \times (4 + ((5 + ((6+7) \times 8)) \times 9)))) & 22655 &:= ((((-9 - 876)/5) \times -((4 \times 32))) - (1)) \\ 22656 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) \times (4 - (5 \times ((6+78) \times 9)))) & 22656 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7+6)) + 5)) \times -((4^3) \times (2+1))) \\ 22657 &:= (1 - (-((23 + (4+5))) \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))) & 22657 &:= ((((-9 - 876)/5) \times -((4 \times 32))) + (1)) \\ 22658 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)) & 22658 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 22659 &:= ((-1-2) \times ((3+4) - (56 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) & 22659 &:= (((9-8) \times 7) \times ((6 \times 543) - 21)) \\ 22660 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 - (6 \times 7))) \times (8+9)) & 22660 &:= (((-9-8) \times -(((7 + ((6-5) \times 4))^3) + 2)) - 1) \\ 22661 &:= (-((12+3)) - (4 \times (-5678+9))) & 22661 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + (5+4)) \times 3))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 22662 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - (3 \times ((4 + (5+6)) \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) & 22662 &:= ((-9 + (8+7)) \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 22663 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) + 5))) \times -((6 \times 7) + 89)) & 22663 &:= (((9 \times 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times 43) + (-2 \times -((1))) \\ 22664 &:= -1 + 2 + (-3+4!) \times (5! + 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 & 22664 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times (5+4)) + 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 22665 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^{4-5+6}) - 7) \times 8)) + 9) & 22665 &:= (((-9 \times 87) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3+2) \times 1)) \\ 22666 &:= ((-1 + 23456) - (789)) & 22666 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -3) + 2) + 1) \\ 22667 &:= ((1 \times 23456) - 789) & 22667 &:= (((-98 + 7654) \times 3) - (2-1)) \\ 22668 &:= ((1 + 23456) - 789) & 22668 &:= ((-9 - (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times 43) - 2)) \times -1) \\ 22669 &:= (((-1+23) \times (4^5)) + (6 + ((7+8) \times 9))) & 22669 &:= (((-98 + 7654) \times 3) + (2-1)) \\ 22670 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + ((4 \times (5678-9)))) & 22670 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times (5+4)) + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 22671 &:= ((1 \times (((23+4) \times -(56)) \times (-7-8))) - 9) & 22671 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5+4)))) + 3) \times -(2+1)) \\ 22672 &:= (-((12/3)) + (4 \times (5678-9))) & 22672 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (((6 \times (5+4)) + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\ 22673 &:= -((((1-23) \times (((4^5) + 6) - (7-8))) + 9)) & 22673 &:= (((((-9-8) \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^4))) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\ 22674 &:= ((-1 + (2-3)) + (4 \times (5678-9))) & 22674 &:= ((-9 + (8+7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3+2))) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22675 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) + 89) \\ 22676 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - 3) - 4)) \times (5678 - 9)) \\ 22677 &:= ((1^{23}) - (4 \times -((5678 - 9)))) \\ 22678 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 22679 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))))) \\ 22680 &:= ((12/3) + (4 \times (5678 - 9))) \\ 22681 &:= (-((-1 + 23)) + ((-4 \times -(5678)) - 9)) \\ 22682 &:= (((1 + 2) + 3) + (4 \times (5678 - 9))) \\ 22683 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - 4) - (56 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 22684 &:= (((1 - 23) \times -((4^5))) + (67 + 89)) \\ 22685 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 22686 &:= (((1 - ((23 + 4) \times -(56))) \times -((-7 - 8))) - 9) \\ 22687 &:= (((12/3) \times (-4 + (5678))) + (-9)) \\ 22688 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (45 \times -((6 + 78)))) + 9) \\ 22689 &:= ((1 \times (((23 + 4) \times -(56)) \times (-7 - 8))) + 9) \\ 22690 &:= (-1 - (((-2 \times (34 \times 5)) \times 67) + (89))) \\ 22691 &:= (-1 \times (((-2 \times (34 \times 5)) \times 67) + (89))) \\ 22692 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times ((5 \times -6) - (-78) \times -9)) \\ 22693 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4 + (56 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 22694 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 + (56 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))))) \\ 22695 &:= ((12 + (-3 \times (456 - 7))) \times -((8 + 9))) \\ 22696 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times 67) - (8 + 9)) \\ 22697 &:= (-1 \times (-2 + (-((3 + (4 \times (56 + 7))) \times 89))) \\ 22698 &:= ((-1 + 23) - (-4 \times -((-5678) - 9))) \\ 22699 &:= -((-1 - (-23 + ((-4 \times -(5678)) + 9))) \\ 22700 &:= ((1 + 23) + (4 \times (5678 - 9))) \\ 22701 &:= ((((-1 + ((2 \times 34))) \times 5) - 6) \times (78 - 9)) \\ 22702 &:= (((((1 - 2)^3) - (-4 \times 5678)) - 9) \\ 22703 &:= (-((1 + 2)) + (3 + ((4 \times 5678) - 9))) \\ 22704 &:= -12^3 + (4^5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 22705 &:= ((1 \times -((2 + 3))) \times ((4 - (567 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 22706 &:= ((-12 - 3) + (((4 \times 5678) + 9))) \\ 22707 &:= (((12 - 3) - (45 \times 6)) \times -((78 + 9))) \\ 22708 &:= (-((1 - (2 \times 3))) + (((4 \times 5678) - 9))) \\ 22709 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + ((4 \times 5678) - 9))) \\ 22710 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + ((4 \times 5678) - 9))) \\ 22711 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - 6))) - (78 \times 9)) \\ 22712 &:= (-12 - (-3 - ((4 \times 5678) + 9))) \\ 22713 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8))) + 9) \\ 22714 &:= (1 - (-((-2^3)) + (-((4 \times 5678) - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22675 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + 21)) \\ 22676 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 543) - 21))) \\ 22677 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times (7 \times ((6 - 54) + 3))) - 2) - (1)) \\ 22678 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times (7 \times ((6 - 54) + 3))) - 2) \times (1)) \\ 22679 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times (7 \times ((6 - 54) + 3))) - 2) + (1)) \\ 22680 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\ 22681 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 22682 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 22683 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22684 &:= -(((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - (((54 + 3)^2 \times 1))))) \\ 22685 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^4))) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\ 22686 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 22687 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -((4^3)/2)) - 1) \\ 22688 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -((4^3)/(2 \times 1))) \\ 22689 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) \times ((6 - 54) + 3)) - 2) + (1)) \\ 22690 &:= ((-9 \times ((87 \times (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + 2)) + 1) \\ 22691 &:= ((((-9 - 87) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 22692 &:= ((((-9 - 87) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) \times 1) \\ 22693 &:= ((((-9 - 87) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 22694 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 22695 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 22696 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 22697 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\ 22698 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) \times ((6 - 54) + 3)) - 2) \times (1)) \\ 22699 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\ 22700 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 22701 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -(((5 \times (4^3))/2) + 1)) \\ 22702 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -(((5^4) - 3)/2)) - 1) \\ 22703 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5 \times (4^3 - 2) + 1) \\ 22704 &:= (-((98 \times ((7 - 65) \times 4))) - (((32 \times 1)))) \\ 22705 &:= (((98 \times -((7 - 65))) \times 4) + (-32 - (-1))) \\ 22706 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 - (3 + 2))))) - 1) \\ 22707 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 22708 &:= ((98 + (-7 \times (6 \times 543))) \times (-2 + (1))) \\ 22709 &:= ((((-98 - 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 22710 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\ 22711 &:= ((((-98 - 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 22712 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (65 \times 4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\ 22713 &:= ((9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 543) - ((2 + 1)))) \\ 22714 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (6 + ((54 + 3)^2))) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22715 &:= (((1 \times -2) \times 3) - (-((4 \times 5678) - 9)) \\
 22716 &:= ((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + 5)) \times -(6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
 22717 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 + (7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 22718 &:= (((1 - 2) \times 3) + (4 \times 5678)) + 9 \\
 22719 &:= (12 + ((34 - 5) \times (-6 + 789))) \\
 22720 &:= (((1 - 2)^3) - (-4 \times 5678)) + 9 \\
 22721 &:= (((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times 5678) + 9) \\
 22722 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + ((4 \times 5678) + 9)) \\
 22723 &:= -(((1 + (2 - 34)) \times -(56 - 789))) \\
 22724 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) \\
 22725 &:= ((-1 + 23) + ((-4 \times -(5678) - 9)) \\
 22726 &:= (((1 \times 2) + 3) - (-((4 \times 5678) - 9)) \\
 22727 &:= -((((1 \times -2) \times 3) - (4 \times 5678)) - 9) \\
 22728 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 56))) - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 22729 &:= (((1 \times ((-2 \times (3 \times 4)) \times -(56))) - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 22730 &:= ((1 - (-2^3)) - (-((4 \times 5678) - 9)) \\
 22731 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times 67))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 22732 &:= -(((12/3) \times (4 - (5678 + 9)))) \\
 22733 &:= (((-12 \times (-3 + ((45 \times -6) \times 7))) + 8) + 9) \\
 22734 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - ((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 22735 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\
 22736 &:= ((12 + 3) + ((4 \times 5678) + 9)) \\
 22737 &:= (((12/3) \times (4 + 5678)) + 9) \\
 22738 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)!) \times (-4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)/8) + 9 \\
 22739 &:= (-((-12 \times 3)) - (-((4 \times 5678) + 9))) \\
 22740 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 22741 &:= ((1 + (-2^3)) + (4 \times (5678 + 9))) \\
 22742 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times -(((4^5) - 6))) - (7 - 89)) \\
 22743 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7) \times 8)) \times 9) \\
 22744 &:= ((-12 \times 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 22745 &:= (((((-1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
 22746 &:= -((((1 \times 2) + 3) \times -(4567)) - 89) \\
 22747 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (78 + 9)) \\
 22748 &:= ((-(-1) + 2) - (3 + (-4 \times (5678 + 9)))) \\
 22749 &:= (-1 - (-((-2 - 3)) \times (-((4567 - 8) - (-9)))) \\
 22750 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 22751 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 + 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 22752 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) \times 4) \times -(((5 - (6 + 78)) \times 9)) \\
 22753 &:= (-1 - (-23456) - (-78) \times 9)) \\
 22754 &:= ((1 \times 23456) + (-78) \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22715 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 22716 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22717 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22718 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((54 + 3)^2 \times 1)))) \\
 22719 &:= (((9 + (87 \times 65)) \times 4) - ((3 \times -21))) \\
 22720 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -5) \times ((43 + 21))) \\
 22721 &:= (-((-9 - 8)) - (-((7 \times 6)) \times (543 - (2 \times (1)))) \\
 22722 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 22723 &:= ((9 - 8) - (-((7 \times 6)) \times (543 - (2 \times (1)))) \\
 22724 &:= ((-9 \times ((87 \times (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - 2)) - 1) \\
 22725 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 22726 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
 22727 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 22728 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4) + 3)^2) - 1) \\
 22729 &:= (((98 \times (7 - 65)) \times -4) - ((3 \times 2) + (1))) \\
 22730 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 22731 &:= ((-((-9 \times 8)) \times ((76 \times 5) - (4^3))) - 21) \\
 22732 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 - 65) \times 4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 22733 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 22734 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 22735 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 22736 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 543)) + 2)) \times (1)) \\
 22737 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 543)) + 2)) + (1)) \\
 22738 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 22739 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\
 22740 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 - 65) \times 4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 22741 &:= (((98 \times (7 - 65)) \times -4) + ((3 \times 2) - (1))) \\
 22742 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
 22743 &:= (((98 \times (7 - 65)) \times -4) + ((3 \times 2) + (1))) \\
 22744 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2) + 1) \\
 22745 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 + 5)^{4-3+2}))) - 1) \\
 22746 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 + 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)}))) \\
 22747 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 + 5)^{4-3+2}))) + 1) \\
 22748 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1) \\
 22749 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22750 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - 7) - 6) \times 5) \times (-4 - 321)) \\
 22751 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 22752 &:= ((9 \times 8) \times -(((7 - 6)^5)) + (-4 + 321)) \\
 22753 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 - 1)) \\
 22754 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - (-((6 - 54)))) \times (-32 + (1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22755 &:= (1 - (-23456) - (-78 \times 9)) \\
 22756 &:= ((-1 - (23 \times (-4^5))) - (6 + 789)) \\
 22757 &:= ((-12 \times -3) + ((4 \times 5678) + 9)) \\
 22758 &:= (-12 + (((3 + 4)^5) + (67 \times 89))) \\
 22759 &:= (((-1 + (23 \times 4)) \times -(5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 22760 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 \times 7) - 8)))) - 9) \\
 22761 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 22762 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) \times -(4567)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 22763 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + 3) \times -(4567)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 22764 &:= (((1 - 2) - 3) \times -((4 + (5678 + 9)))) \\
 22765 &:= ((-12 - 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 22766 &:= ((12 \times (34 \times 56)) + (7 - 89)) \\
 22767 &:= (-1 - (2 - (345 \times ((67 + 8) - 9)))) \\
 22768 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (345 \times ((67 + 8) - 9)))) \\
 22769 &:= (-1 \times ((23 \times (-4^5)) - (6 - 789))) \\
 22770 &:= (((1 - 2) - (3 \times -4)) \times (5 \times 6)) \times (78 - 9) \\
 22771 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 22772 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 22773 &:= -(((1 - 2) - ((345 \times ((67 + 8) - 9)))) \\
 22774 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (4 \times (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 22775 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (((45 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 22776 &:= (-12 \times -((3 + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 22777 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 22778 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9)) \\
 22779 &:= -(((1 \times (2 + 3))) - ((4^{5+6-7}) \times -(89))) \\
 22780 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times -(5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 22781 &:= ((-(-1 \times ((2 \times 34) \times (5 \times 67)))) - 8) + 9) \\
 22782 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) + ((4^{5+6-7}) \times 89)) \\
 22783 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 34)) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 22784 &:= ((-((1 \times 2)) + 34) \times ((56/7) \times 89)) \\
 22785 &:= (((-((1 - 23)) - (45 \times -6)) \times 78) + 9) \\
 22786 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4 + (56 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 22787 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((34 \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 22788 &:= (-12 \times -(3 \times (4 - ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 22789 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4 + (56 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\
 22790 &:= -(((1 - ((2 + 3) \times 456))) \times ((-7 + 8) + 9)) \\
 22791 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + ((4^{5+6-7}) \times 89))) \\
 22792 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9))) \\
 22793 &:= (-1 \times (23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) + 9))) \\
 22794 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) - (45 \times 6)) \times -(78 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22755 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22756 &:= (((-98 - (7 + 6)) \times -(5 \times (43 - 2))) + 1) \\
 22757 &:= ((-98 \times -76) + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 21)) \\
 22758 &:= ((-9 \times 8 + 7!)/6 + 5!) \times 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 22759 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times -(5 - 43)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22760 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2))) \times -1) \\
 22761 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 + 4)))) + 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 22762 &:= (((-9 - (-8 \times 76)) \times (((5 \times 4) - 3) + 21))) \\
 22763 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4 \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 22764 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7/6 \times (54 \times (3 + 2) + 1) \\
 22765 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 - 32)) + 1) \\
 22766 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (6 - (((54 + 3)^2) - 1)))) \\
 22767 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 + ((54 + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 22768 &:= (-((98 \times ((7 - 65) \times 4))) + (((32 \times 1)))) \\
 22769 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\
 22770 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 + (4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 22771 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\
 22772 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times (6 - ((54 + 3)^2)))) + 1) \\
 22773 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (6 - ((54 + 3)^2 \times 1)))) \\
 22774 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times (6 - ((54 + 3)^2))) - 1)) \\
 22775 &:= ((-9 + (((87 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\
 22776 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -(((5^4) - 3)/2) + 1) \\
 22777 &:= (-9 + (((87 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 22778 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54)))) + (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 22779 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 22780 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 22781 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 22782 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 22783 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times ((4 \times (3^2)) + 1))) \\
 22784 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times -(4^{3+2-1})) \\
 22785 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 22786 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 543))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 22787 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 543)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 22788 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times 4) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 22789 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (5 \times (43 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 22790 &:= (((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times -5) \times (43 \times 2)) \times (1) \\
 22791 &:= (((9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times -5) \times (43 \times 2)) + (1) \\
 22792 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) + (4 + 3))^2 \times 1)) \\
 22793 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) + (4 + 3))^2) + 1) \\
 22794 &:= ((-9 - (((87 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) \times -1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22795 &:= ((1 + 234) \times -(((5 - 6) - 7) - 89)) \\ 22796 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times (34 \times 5)) \times 67)) + 8) + 9) \\ 22797 &:= (-((-1 \times ((2 \times 34) \times (5 \times 67)))) - (-8 - 9)) \\ 22798 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (34 \times (5 \times 67))) + (8 + 9))) \\ 22799 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times ((4^5) - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22800 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times 456) \times ((-7 + 8) + 9))) \\ 22801 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) \times 456) \times ((-7 + 8) + 9))) \\ 22802 &:= ((-1 + 23) + (4 \times (5 \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 22803 &:= ((1 \times 23) + (-((4 \times 5) \times (67 \times (-8 - 9)))) \\ 22804 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((34 \times (5 \times 67)) + 8)) + 9)) \\ 22805 &:= ((12 \times (3 + ((45 \times 6) \times 7))) + 89) \\ 22806 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + (3 \times (4 + (56 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 22807 &:= ((-1 \times -23) + ((4^{5+6-7} \times 89)) \\ 22808 &:= ((1 + 23) + ((4^{5+6-7} \times 89)) \\ 22809 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -3^4) + ((5^6) + (7 \times 89))) \\ 22810 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times 456)) \times ((-7 + 8) + 9)) \\ 22811 &:= (1 + 2)^3 + 4^{5+6-7} \times 89 \\ 22812 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 22813 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\ 22814 &:= (-1 + ((23 + 4) \times (56 + 789))) \\ 22815 &:= ((12 + (345 - 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 22816 &:= (((12 \times 3) - 4) \times (5 + (6 - (-78) \times 9))) \\ 22817 &:= (-(((1 - ((2 + 3) \times 4567)) + 8) - 9) \\ 22818 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times 4567) - (8 + 9))) \\ 22819 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times 4567)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 22820 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -((4 \times (5 + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 22821 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 22822 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 22823 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22824 &:= -(((12 \times ((34 \times 5) + (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times -9) \\ 22825 &:= 1 - (2 \times 3)^4 + 5 \times 67 \times 8 \times 9 \\ 22826 &:= (-((-123) - (4 \times 5678))) - 9) \\ 22827 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times 7) - 8)) - 9) \\ 22828 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 67))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 22829 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 67))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 22830 &:= (1 - (-((-2 + 34) + 5) \times -((6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 22831 &:= ((((-1 \times -((2 + 3))) \times (-4 - (567))) \times -8) - 9) \\ 22832 &:= (-1 - (((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times (67 - 8)) \times -9)) \\ 22833 &:= (-1 - (-(((2 + 3) \times 4567)) - ((8 - 9)))) \\ 22834 &:= ((1 + 23456) - (7 \times 89)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22795 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 \times (5 + 4)) \times (3^2)) - 1)) \\ 22796 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54))) + 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 22797 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 22798 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54))) + 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 22799 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4) + 3^2)) - 1) \\ 22800 &:= (((((9 - 87) - (6 \times 5)) + (-43))^2) - (1)) \\ 22801 &:= (((((9 - 87) - (6 \times 5)) + (-43))^2) \times (1)) \\ 22802 &:= (((((9 - 87) - (6 \times 5)) + (-43))^2) + (1)) \\ 22803 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 22804 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 654)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 22805 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 76) - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 22806 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 22807 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 76) - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 22808 &:= ((-((9 - 8)) - ((-7 \times (6 \times 543)) - ((2 + 1)))) \\ 22809 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 22810 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) + (4 + 3))^2)) \times -1) \\ 22811 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 22812 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 22813 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 22814 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 54) - 3^2 - 1 \\ 22815 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 54) - 3^2 \times 1 \\ 22816 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 54) - 3^2 + 1 \\ 22817 &:= (((-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 22818 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3^2))) - 1)) \\ 22819 &:= (((-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\ 22820 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((-6 \times 543) - ((2 \times 1)))) \\ 22821 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 22822 &:= (((9 + 8) - (((-7 \times 6) \times 543) + 2)) - ((-1))) \\ 22823 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2))) - 1) \\ 22824 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times ((7 - 6)^5)) \times (-4 + 321)) \\ 22825 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2))) + 1) \\ 22826 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((-7 \times 6) \times 543)) - (-2 - 1)) \\ 22827 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (7 - (6 \times 54))) - 3) \times (-2 - (-1)) \\ 22828 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 22829 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 76)) \times -((5 \times (4 + 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 22830 &:= ((-9 \times ((-8 \times (-7 + (6 \times 54))) - 3)) - 21) \\ 22831 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (-((7 \times 6)) \times -((543 + 2)) + (1))) \\ 22832 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54))) - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 22833 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 54) + 3^2 \times 1 \\ 22834 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22835 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times (4567 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 22836 &:= (((1 - 2) + 34) \times (5 + (678 + 9))) \\
 22837 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 22838 &:= (((12 \times (34 \times 56)) + 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 22839 &:= (-1 - ((-2 - 3) \times ((4567 - 8) + 9))) \\
 22840 &:= (((1 \times 2) + 3) \times ((4567 - 8) + 9)) \\
 22841 &:= (((-((-12 \times -(34))) \times 56) + 7) \times (8 - 9)) \\
 22842 &:= (((((12 \times 3) + (45)) \times -(-6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 22843 &:= (((-1 - (-23 \times (4^5))) - 6) - (78 \times -(-9))) \\
 22844 &:= (-((-123) - (4 \times 5678))) + 9) \\
 22845 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times 7) - 8)) + 9) \\
 22846 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times -67) + (8 - 9)) \\
 22847 &:= (-1 + ((2^{(3-4) \times -5}) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 22848 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4) - 5)^6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 22849 &:= (((-1 + ((2^3) \times ((45 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\
 22850 &:= (-1 \times -(-2 - (34 \times ((5 \times 6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\
 22851 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + ((56 + 7) \times 8)))) \times 9) \\
 22852 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (34 \times 5)) \times 67) + ((8 \times 9)) \\
 22853 &:= ((-12 \times -((34 \times 56) - 7)) + 89) \\
 22854 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (34 \times 56))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
 22855 &:= ((-1 - (-23 \times (4^5)) - 6) + (78 \times -9)) \\
 22856 &:= (((-1 \times (-23 \times (4^5))) + 6) + (78 \times -9)) \\
 22857 &:= (((-(-1) - ((-23 \times (4^5)))) + 6) + (78 \times -9)) \\
 22858 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 - ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 22859 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + ((56 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 22860 &:= ((12 \times ((34 \times 56) + 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 22861 &:= -(((12 - (-34) \times (5 - 678))) + 9)) \\
 22862 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -(((4^5) - (6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
 22863 &:= (((-12 + (3 \times ((4^5) - 67))) \times 8) - 9) \\
 22864 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (56 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 22865 &:= (((((1 \times 2) \times 3)^4) + (56 - 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 22866 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times (4567 + 8)) - 9)) \\
 22867 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4567 + 8))) - 9) \\
 22868 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (34 \times (5 \times 67))) + 89)) \\
 22869 &:= (-1 \times (((-2 \times (34 \times 5)) \times 67) - (89))) \\
 22870 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 89)) \\
 22871 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 89)) \\
 22872 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -(((4^5) - ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22873 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (-34) \times (5 - 678)) - 9) \\
 22874 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 89))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22835 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 22836 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 22837 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 22838 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22839 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22840 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -(6 + (5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 22841 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4) \times 3^2 - 1 \\
 22842 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4) \times 3^2 \times 1 \\
 22843 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times 6 \times (5 + 4) \times 3^2 + 1 \\
 22844 &:= ((-((-9 - 8)) + (7 \times ((6 \times 543) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 22845 &:= (((-98 + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3)) + (-2 - ((1)))) \\
 22846 &:= (((-98 + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 22847 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times (6 \times ((5 - 4) \times 32)))) - 1) \\
 22848 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((76 - (5 + (4 + 3))) \times 21)) \\
 22849 &:= (((-98 + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3)) - (-2 + ((1)))) \\
 22850 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((54 + 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
 22851 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 22852 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54))) - 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\
 22853 &:= (((-9 - (((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 22854 &:= (((9 - 87) \times ((65 \times -4) - (32 + 1)))) \\
 22855 &:= (-98 + (7 \times -((-6 \times 543) + (-21)))) \\
 22856 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + ((54 + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 22857 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + ((54 + 3)^2 \times 1)))) \\
 22858 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times (6 + ((54 + 3)^2))) + 1)) \\
 22859 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) - 3))/2)) - 1) \\
 22860 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 22861 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) - 3))/2)) + 1) \\
 22862 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 22863 &:= -(((98 - ((7654 \times 3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
 22864 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + (((54 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
 22865 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((-6 \times (543 + (2 - 1)))))) \\
 22866 &:= (-9 - ((87 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 22867 &:= (-98 + ((7654 \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 22868 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54))) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 22869 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 22870 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 54))) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 22871 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times ((43 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 22872 &:= ((-9 \times ((-8 \times (-7 + (6 \times 54))) - 3)) + 21) \\
 22873 &:= ((-98 - ((7654 + 3) \times (-2 - 1))) \\
 22874 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22875 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 22876 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) - ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 22877 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times (4^5)) - ((67 + 8) \times 9)) \\ 22878 &:= ((-(-1) - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times -(56))) \times (7 - 89)) \\ 22879 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 + 4) \times 5) - 6) \times 789) \\ 22880 &:= (((12 \times 34) - 56) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 22881 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times (5 \times 67))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 22882 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + (56 - 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 22883 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3 + 4) \times 5) - 6) \times 789)) \\ 22884 &:= (((-1 \times -(2 + 3)) \times (4567 + 8)) + 9) \\ 22885 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times -(4567 - 8)) - 9)) \\ 22886 &:= -(1234 + ((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22887 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8))) \times -9) \\ 22888 &:= (((((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}))/6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 22889 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\ 22890 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (-3 + (((456 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 22891 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - 45) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 22892 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 - 45) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 22893 &:= (-(-12) - (((-3 + 4) - (5 \times 6)) \times 789)) \\ 22894 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((-34) \times (-5 + 678)) - 9)) \\ 22895 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) \times (-((4 + 56) + 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22896 &:= (-1 \times (((2 \times 3) \times (-((4 + 56) + 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22897 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) \times (-((4 + 56) + 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22898 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 \times ((456 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 22899 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((((3^4) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 22900 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5) - 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22901 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (3 \times ((456 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 22902 &:= (-1 \times (-((-2 - 345)) \times (-67) - (8 - 9))) \\ 22903 &:= (-(-123) - ((4 \times 5) \times (67 \times (-8 - 9)))) \\ 22904 &:= (-12 + (34 \times ((5 + 678) - 9))) \\ 22905 &:= (((-1) - ((-23 \times (4^5)))) - ((6 - 78) \times -9)) \\ 22906 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 + 4)^5) + (678 \times 9))) \\ 22907 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22908 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22909 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - 6))) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22910 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 22911 &:= (1 - (((-234) - 56) \times (-7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22912 &:= (((1 + 2) + ((3 + 4)^5)) - (678 \times -9)) \\ 22913 &:= ((((-12 \times 34) - (-5 + 6)) \times (-7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 22914 &:= (((-1 \times 23) + 4) \times ((-56) - (78) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22875 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) \times -((54 \times 3) - 21))) \\ 22876 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 543)) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 22877 &:= ((9 - 8) + (76 \times -((5 \times 4) + 321))) \\ 22878 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 + (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 22879 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) \times -((4^3)/2)) - 1) \\ 22880 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) \times -((4^3)/(2 \times 1))) \\ 22881 &:= ((-((-9 \times 8)) + ((7 \times (6 \times 543)) + 2)) + (1)) \\ 22882 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2) + 1) \\ 22883 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (-6 \times 543))) + (-21)) \\ 22884 &:= 9 \times 876 + 5^4 \times (3 + 21) \\ 22885 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 654)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 22886 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 654)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 22887 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 22888 &:= ((-9 - ((87 \times ((65 \times 4) + 3)) - 2)) \times -1) \\ 22889 &:= ((-((9 - 8)) - ((7 \times 6) \times ((-543 - 2) \times 1))) \\ 22890 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 22891 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2))) + 1) \\ 22892 &:= ((-9 - ((87 \times ((65 \times 4) + 3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\ 22893 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (-((-7654) \times 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 22894 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 22895 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 22896 &:= ((9 \times 8) - (-((-7 - 65) \times (4 - 321)))) \\ 22897 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 22898 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 22899 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22900 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (543 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 22901 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (6 \times 543))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 22902 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 22903 &:= ((98 + (7 \times (6 \times 543))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 22904 &:= ((98 - (-7 \times (6 \times 543))) \times -((-2 + (1)))) \\ 22905 &:= ((98 - (-7 \times (6 \times 543))) - (-2 + (1))) \\ 22906 &:= ((98 - (-7 \times (6 \times 543))) - (-2 \times (1))) \\ 22907 &:= ((98 - (-(-7) \times -((6 \times 543)))) - (-2 - (1))) \\ 22908 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 22909 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 22910 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 22911 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 22912 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 22913 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 22914 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22915 &:= (-((-1+2) + (34 \times (5 + (678 - 9)))) \\
 22916 &:= ((-1+2) \times (34 \times (5 + (678 - 9)))) \\
 22917 &:= ((-1+2) + (34 \times ((5 + 678) - 9))) \\
 22918 &:= (((-1+23) \times (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22919 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (((45+6) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 22920 &:= (-((1 - (2 \times 3))) \times (4567 + (8 + 9))) \\
 22921 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
 22922 &:= (-1 + ((23 + 4) \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) \\
 22923 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8))) \times -9) \\
 22924 &:= (-(((1 \times 2) + 3) \times -(4567))) + 89) \\
 22925 &:= ((1 + ((-2 - 3) \times -(4567))) + (89)) \\
 22926 &:= ((-1 - 23) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22927 &:= (-1 \times (23 - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22928 &:= (12 + (34 \times ((5 + 678) - 9))) \\
 22929 &:= (((-12 + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 22930 &:= ((12 \times (34 \times 56)) - (7 - 89)) \\
 22931 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 22932 &:= (((1 - 234) \times (-5 - 6)) - (7 + 8)) \times 9) \\
 22933 &:= ((-1 \times (-2 + (-3 \times (456 - 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 22934 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 22935 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - 67))) \times 8) - 9) \\
 22936 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times -67) + 89) \\
 22937 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (-4! + 5 \times 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 22938 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 67) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 22939 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 67) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 22940 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times (4 + (56 \times (7 - 89)))) \\
 22941 &:= (-(-1) - ((-2 - 3) \times -((4 + ((56 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\
 22942 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22943 &:= (((((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}))/6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 22944 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4 \times 5) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22945 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 22946 &:= ((-12/3) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22947 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -(3 - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22948 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22949 &:= (-1 - (((-2 - 3) \times 45) \times -((-6 - 7)) + (89))) \\
 22950 &:= (((((-1 - 2) - (3^{4+5}))/6) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 22951 &:= (-1 + (23456 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22952 &:= (1 \times (23456 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22953 &:= (1 + (23456 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 22954 &:= 12/3 + 45 \times (6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22915 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 3) + 2)) + 1) \\
 22916 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22917 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22918 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times (43 - 2)) - 1) \\
 22919 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times ((43 - 2) \times 1)) \\
 22920 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 22921 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -((5^4 + 3)/2)) - 1) \\
 22922 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\
 22923 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 + 4)))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 22924 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\
 22925 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (-6 \times 543))) - (-21)) \\
 22926 &:= (((98 - 7) - ((6^5) - 43)) \times -((2 + 1))) \\
 22927 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 22928 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7654) \times 3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 22929 &:= ((-98 \times -(((7 + 6) \times 54)/3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22930 &:= ((-98 \times -(((7 + 6) \times 54)/3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 22931 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + 6)) \times -((5 + 4) + (3^2))) - 1) \\
 22932 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22933 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 22934 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\
 22935 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 22936 &:= -((((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (65 - 4)) \times ((3^2) - 1))) \\
 22937 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22938 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22939 &:= ((((-98 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 22940 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 76) \times 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 22941 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6^5 - 4^3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 22942 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7654 \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22943 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7654 \times 3)) + ((2 \times 1)))) \\
 22944 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 22945 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) \times (4^3))/2) + 1)) \\
 22946 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7654 \times 3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 22947 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (54 - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 22948 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (54 - 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 22949 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -(5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 22950 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 22951 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -(5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 22952 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (54 - 3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 22953 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (54 - 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 22954 &:= ((-987 - (6 + 5)) \times (4 - (3^{2+1})))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22955 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 + 45 \times (6 + 7 \times 8 \times 9) \\ 22956 &:= (-12 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))) \\ 22957 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22958 &:= (1 \times (-2 \times (((-34) \times 5) \times 67) - 89)) \\ 22959 &:= (1 + (-2 \times (((-34) \times 5) \times 67) - 89)) \\ 22960 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})/6) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 22961 &:= (((((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})/6) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 22962 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 89) \\ 22963 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 345) \times 67) + (8 + 9))) \\ 22964 &:= (-1 \times (((2 - 345) \times 67) + (8 + 9))) \\ 22965 &:= (-12 + ((3 \times ((4^5) - 67) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 22966 &:= (1 + 2 + 3^{4+5})/6 \times 7 + 8 - 9 \\ 22967 &:= (-1 - ((-234) + (5 \times -6)) \times (78 + 9)) \\ 22968 &:= (-1 \times ((-234) + (5 \times -6)) \times (78 + 9)) \\ 22969 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 \times (5 + 6) \times (78 + 9) \\ 22970 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 + 4 \times (5! \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 22971 &:= ((12 + (3 \times ((4^5) - 67) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 22972 &:= ((-1 + 23) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 22973 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 22974 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) - 67) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 22975 &:= (((12 - 3)^4) + ((5^6))) + 789 \\ 22976 &:= ((1 \times (23 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times (7 + 89))) \\ 22977 &:= ((-123) + 456) \times (78 - 9) \\ 22978 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 22979 &:= (-1 - ((-2 - 3) \times (4 - ((56 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\ 22980 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -(4 \times ((56 - 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 22981 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (345)) \times 67) + (8 - 9))) \\ 22982 &:= (-1 \times (((2 - 345) \times 67) + (8 - 9))) \\ 22983 &:= ((-(-1) - (((-2 + 345) \times -(67)) + 8)) + 9) \\ 22984 &:= (((((-1 - 2) - (3^{4+5})/6) \times -7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 22985 &:= (((1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (67))) - (-8 - 9)) \\ 22986 &:= ((-((1 + 2) - 345)) \times 67) + (8 \times 9) \\ 22987 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 \times 78) - 9)) \\ 22988 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5) + 6) - (78 \times 9)) \\ 22989 &:= (((1 + 234) + 56) \times (7 - (-8 \times 9))) \\ 22990 &:= (-1 - (((23 \times (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times -8))) + 9)) \\ 22991 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 22992 &:= (-12 \times -(3 + (((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 22993 &:= (((((-1 - 23) \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\ 22994 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22955 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((654 \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 22956 &:= -((9 + (((8 + 7654) \times -3) + 21))) \\ 22957 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1) \\ 22958 &:= (-(((9 - (8 + ((7654 \times 3) - 2))) + 1))) \\ 22959 &:= (-9 - ((87 \times 6) \times -((5 \times 4) + ((3 + 21)))))) \\ 22960 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1) \\ 22961 &:= -((-9 + ((8 - (7654 \times 3)) + ((2 \times 1)))) \\ 22962 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7654 \times 3))) + (-((2 - 1)))) \\ 22963 &:= -9 + 8 + 7654 \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\ 22964 &:= ((9 - (8 - (7654 \times 3))) - (-((2 - 1)))) \\ 22965 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((-7654) \times -3) - ((-2 - 1))) \\ 22966 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((-7654) \times -3) - ((-2 - 1))) \\ 22967 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -((6 - 5) + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 22968 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 22969 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 - 1)) \\ 22970 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 22971 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 22972 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6 + 5) \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\ 22973 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 22974 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7654) \times -3) + 21)) \\ 22975 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 22976 &:= (((-9 \times 87) + 65) \times -((4^3)/(2 \times 1))) \\ 22977 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 22978 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7654) \times 3) + (2 - 1))) \\ 22979 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - ((5 + 43)^2))) - 1) \\ 22980 &:= (((9 + (8 + (7654 \times 3))) + 2) - 1) \\ 22981 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 - 6) \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\ 22982 &:= (((9 + (8 + (7654 \times 3))) + 2) - (-1)) \\ 22983 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 22984 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 22985 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 - 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 22986 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 22987 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 - 6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 22988 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times (654 \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\ 22989 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5 + 43)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 22990 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - (((5 + 43)^2) + 1))) \\ 22991 &:= -9 + 8 \times ((-7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\ 22992 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7654)) \times 3) - 21) \\ 22993 &:= 9 + (-8 + 76) \times (-5 + (4 + 3)^{2+1}) \\ 22994 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times (43 + 2)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22995 &:= (((1-2)-34) \times (((5 \times (-6-7)) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 22996 &:= ((-1+2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 67) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 22997 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 67) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 22998 &:= (-1 \times (((2-345) \times 67) - (8+9))) \\ 22999 &:= ((((-1+2) - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) \times -8) - 9) \\ 23000 &:= (-1 \times -(23 \times (4 \times (5 \times (67 - (8+9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23001 &:= (-123) \times ((-4 - ((5-6) \times -7)) \times (8+9)) \\ 23002 &:= (((-1+23) \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23003 &:= (-1 + ((2+34) \times ((56 + (7+8)) \times 9))) \\ 23004 &:= ((12 \times ((34 \times 56) + 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 23005 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\ 23006 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - ((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 23007 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8+9))))))) \\ 23008 &:= (((-1) + ((23 \times (4^5)) - (67 \times 8)) - 9) \\ 23009 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times -((4 \times 5))) \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 23010 &:= (((-1-2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8+9)))) \\ 23011 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times 45) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 23012 &:= (((-1+23) + (4^5)) \times -(67-89)) \\ 23013 &:= ((1+2) \times (((3 + (4^5)) - (67)) \times 8) - 9) \\ 23014 &:= ((-12 + (-345) \times -(67))) - 89) \\ 23015 &:= ((((-1+2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) \times 8) - 9) \\ 23016 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 + (8+9))) \\ 23017 &:= (((1 - (2 + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times -7)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 23018 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! + 5) \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 23019 &:= ((((-1-2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (67-8))) + 9) \\ 23020 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - ((67-8) \times 9)) \\ 23021 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - ((67-8) \times 9)) \\ 23022 &:= ((-1-2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8) + 9) \\ 23023 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8) + 9) \\ 23024 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - ((67 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 23025 &:= ((1-2) - (-((345 \times 67)) + 89)) \\ 23026 &:= ((1-2) \times (-((345 \times 67)) + 89)) \\ 23027 &:= (-1 + (2 - (-((345 \times 67)) + 89))) \\ 23028 &:= (1 \times (2 - (-((345 \times 67)) + 89))) \\ 23029 &:= (1 + (2 - (-((345 \times 67)) + 89))) \\ 23030 &:= ((1 + 234) \times (5 - (-6 - (78 + 9)))) \\ 23031 &:= ((-12 + (345 \times 67)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 23032 &:= (-((12/3) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times 789))) \\ 23033 &:= -((1 + ((23 + (4^5)) \times (67 - 89))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22995 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times ((7-6) - (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2+1))) \\ 22996 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7+6) \times 5))) \times (43+2)) + 1) \\ 22997 &:= ((-9 - (((8+7654) \times 3) + 2)) \times -1) \\ 22998 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\ 22999 &:= ((((-98-7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1) \\ 23000 &:= ((((-98-7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2-1) \\ 23001 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2+1))) \\ 23002 &:= ((((-98-7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2-1) \\ 23003 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\ 23004 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\ 23005 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5^4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ 23006 &:= (-98 + ((76 \times -(5 - (4+3)))^2 \times 1)) \\ 23007 &:= (((-9 \times (-8 \times ((76+5) \times 4))) - 321)) \\ 23008 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4^3)/(2 \times 1))) \\ 23009 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3))) - (2-1)) \\ 23010 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6+5) + ((4+3)^{2+1}))) \\ 23011 &:= (((9 + (8 + (7654))) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23012 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times (5 - (4^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23013 &:= (-(((-9 \times 8) + (7654 \times -3))) + (-21)) \\ 23014 &:= ((((-98-7) + (6^5)) \times (4 - (3-2))) + 1) \\ 23015 &:= (((9 + (8 + (7654))) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23016 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2+1))) \\ 23017 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2+1))) \\ 23018 &:= ((-9-8) \times -(((7 \times 65) - 4) \times 3) + (2-1)) \\ 23019 &:= ((-987+6) - (((5 \times 4^3) \times (-2 + (-1)))) \\ 23020 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7! - 6 - 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 23021 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7-6) \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 23022 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7-6) \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 23023 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7-6) \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1) \\ 23024 &:= ((((-98-7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2-1)) \\ 23025 &:= (((-98-7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times (3 \times (2-1))) \\ 23026 &:= ((((-98-7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2-1)) \\ 23027 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) - 3)) - (2+1)) \\ 23028 &:= ((((-98-7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2+1)) \\ 23029 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 - (6 \times (5+4))) \times (3+2))) - 1) \\ 23030 &:= (-98 \times -(7 + (6 \times ((5 \times (4+3)) + (2+1)))) \\ 23031 &:= (((-9 - ((87 - (6^5)) - 4)) \times 3) - 21) \\ 23032 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23033 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) - 3)) + (2+1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23034 &:= (1 \times -(((23 + (4^5)) \times (67 - 89)))) \\ 23035 &:= (1 - ((23 + (4^5)) \times (67 - 89))) \\ 23036 &:= (((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4) \times -(5 - (6 \times 7))) - 89) \\ 23037 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times 7) + 8)) + 9) \\ 23038 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23039 &:= (-(((1 - (2 - (3 - 45))) \times (67 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 23040 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times -(5 \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\ 23041 &:= (((1 + (23 \times (4 \times 5))) \times ((6 \times 7) + 8)) - 9) \\ 23042 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23043 &:= (-12 - (((34 - 5) \times -((6 + 789)))))) \\ 23044 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23045 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 89))))))) \\ 23046 &:= (-(-1) - (-2 - ((-345) \times -(67)) + (-8 \times 9))) \\ 23047 &:= (((((1 - 2) + 345) \times 67) + 8) - 9) \\ 23048 &:= (((1^2) - 345) \times (67 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 23049 &:= ((((((1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4^5))/6) \times -(7 + 8)) + 9) \\ 23050 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 89)) \\ 23051 &:= ((((-1 + 2)^3) - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times -89) \\ 23052 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 23053 &:= (1 \times (-2 + ((34 - 5) \times (6 + (789)))))) \\ 23054 &:= (1 \times (((23 \times (4^5)) + 6) - ((7 \times 8) \times 9))) \\ 23055 &:= (1 + (((23 \times (4^5)) + 6) - ((7 \times 8) \times 9))) \\ 23056 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (3 \times ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 78)) \times 9)))) \\ 23057 &:= (-(((1 - (2 - (3 - 45))) \times (67 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 23058 &:= (1 - (-2 - ((34 - 5) \times (6 + (789)))))) \\ 23059 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 8)))))) - 9) \\ 23060 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\ 23061 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times -678) + 9) \\ 23062 &:= (1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times 678)) - 9)) \\ 23063 &:= (12 + (-(((3 - 45) \times 6) - 7)) \times 89) \\ 23064 &:= ((1 + 23) \times (((4^5) + 6) - 78) + 9) \\ 23065 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - 345) \times -(67)) + (8 + 9)) \\ 23066 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + 6))) - (7 \times 89)) \\ 23067 &:= (12 - ((34 - 5) \times -((6 + 789)))) \\ 23068 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 23069 &:= ((((((1 \times 2) + 3) \times 45) \times -6) - 7) \times (-8 - 9)) \\ 23070 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times 678) - 9))) \\ 23071 &:= ((1 - ((-2 + 345) \times -(67))) + (89)) \\ 23072 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 89)))))) \\ 23073 &:= (123 + (45 \times (6 + ((7 \times 8) \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23034 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\ 23035 &:= ((9 \times 8) - (((-7654) \times 3) - 2) + (1)) \\ 23036 &:= ((9 \times 8) - (((-7654) \times 3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 23037 &:= ((9 \times 8) - (((-7654) \times 3) - 2) - (1)) \\ 23038 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 - 6) \times 5))) \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23039 &:= ((-9 \times -((8^{7-(6-5)} \times 4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 23040 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6) \times 5 \times 4^3 \times (2 - 1) \\ 23041 &:= ((-9 \times -((8^{7-(6-5)} \times 4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 23042 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 - 6) \times 5))) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23043 &:= (9 + (-(((87 - (6^5)) + 4) \times 3)) - 21) \\ 23044 &:= (((((-98 + 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23045 &:= ((-98 + 7) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23046 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 23047 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 23048 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) - ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 23049 &:= ((-9 \times (-8 - (7 \times (65 - 432)))) \times (-1)) \\ 23050 &:= (((-98 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) - 4) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 23051 &:= (98 + (7 \times -(((6 \times 543) + (-21)))))) \\ 23052 &:= ((((-98 + 7) + (6^5)) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23053 &:= ((((-9 - 87) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23054 &:= ((((-98 + 7) + (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 23055 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23056 &:= ((((-98 + 7) + (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 23057 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23058 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7))) \times (6 \times ((5 - 432) \times -((1)))))) \\ 23059 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) - (6^{5-4+3})) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 23060 &:= ((-98 - (7654 \times 3)) \times -(2 - 1)) \\ 23061 &:= ((98 + ((7654 \times 3) + 2)) - (1)) \\ 23062 &:= ((98 + ((7654 \times 3) + 2)) \times (1)) \\ 23063 &:= ((98 + ((7654 \times 3) + 2)) + (1)) \\ 23064 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23065 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^2)) + 1) \\ 23066 &:= ((((-98 + 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23067 &:= ((9 - (((87 - (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + 21)) \\ 23068 &:= ((((-98 + 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23069 &:= ((((-98 + 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23070 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23071 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23072 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\ 23073 &:= (((-9 - ((87 - (6^5)) - 4)) \times 3) + 21) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23074 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times (67 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 23075 &:= ((-1 \times (-23 \times (4^5))) - ((6 \times 78) + 9)) \\
 23076 &:= -(((-1 - ((-23 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times 78))) + 9) \\
 23077 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 8)))) + 9)) \\
 23078 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 23079 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times -((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 23080 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3!!) \times 4 \times (5 - 6 - 7) + 8 \times 9 \\
 23081 &:= (((((1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times -7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 23082 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!/4) \times (5! + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 23083 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (34 \times (56 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 23084 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 23085 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 23086 &:= ((((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times 5) + 6) \times -((7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 23087 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -((5 - (6 \times 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
 23088 &:= (-1 \times (-2 - (34 \times (-(-56)) + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 23089 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -((5 - (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 23090 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 23091 &:= (1 + 2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7 - 8) + 9) \\
 23092 &:= (-1 \times (23 \times (4 - ((56 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 23093 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5)) - ((6 \times 78) - 9)) \\
 23094 &:= ((-1 - ((-23 - 4) \times -((5 - (-6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times -9) \\
 23095 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((345 \times 67) - (8 + 9))) \\
 23096 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((345 \times 67) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 23097 &:= (((-1) - 2) - (((-345) \times -((67))) - (-8 - 9))) \\
 23098 &:= (((-12 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 23099 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (345 \times 67)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 23100 &:= (((1 \times 2) - (-345 \times 67)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 23101 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 23102 &:= -(((12 - ((345 \times 67) + 8)) + 9)) \\
 23103 &:= (((((1 + 2) + 3^4) + (56 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 23104 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (3^4 - 5))^{-6+7-8+9} \\
 23105 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -((5 - (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\
 23106 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + (4 + 5)^6) / (78 - 9) \\
 23107 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\
 23108 &:= (-12 + (-34) \times -((5 + (((67 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 23109 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\
 23110 &:= (12 + ((345 \times 67) - (8 + 9))) \\
 23111 &:= (-1 + (-2 - ((345 \times -67)) - (8 - 9))) \\
 23112 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (345 \times -67)) \times -((8 - 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23074 &:= ((-98 \times -76) + ((5^{4 \times 3/2}) + 1)) \\
 23075 &:= (((-((-9 - ((8 \times 7)))) \times (((6 \times 54) + 32) - 1))) \\
 23076 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 + 1) \\
 23077 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4) \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 23078 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 - 1) \\
 23079 &:= -9 + (-87 + 6^5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 23080 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1) \\
 23081 &:= (-9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4) \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 23082 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) - (4^3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 23083 &:= ((((-9 + 87) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 23084 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 23085 &:= ((9 \times ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times (43 + 2))) \times (-1)) \\
 23086 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) \times (65 + (43 \times (2 + ((1)))))) \\
 23087 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((76 \times -(5 - (4 + 3)))^2 \times 1)) \\
 23088 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5)) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\
 23089 &:= (9 - (8 \times ((76 \times (5 - 43)) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 23090 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\
 23091 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23092 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\
 23093 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 - 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) - 2)) - 1) \\
 23094 &:= (9 \times (((8 \times -7) + (6 \times (5 + 432))) \times (1))) \\
 23095 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3))))^2 \times 1)) \\
 23096 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3))))^2) + 1)) \\
 23097 &:= -9 + 8 \times 76 \times (-5 + 43) + 2 \times 1 \\
 23098 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) - (4^3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 23099 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 23100 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5) + 4) \times 3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 23101 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5) + 4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 23102 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6^5) + 4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\
 23103 &:= (9 \times ((8 \times -7) + ((6 \times (5 + 432)) + (1)))) \\
 23104 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times 3))^2 \times 1) \\
 23105 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times 3))^2) + 1) \\
 23106 &:= ((((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (6^5)) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 23107 &:= ((((-9 + 87) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 23108 &:= (9 - 87 + 6^5 + 4) \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 23109 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 - 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 23110 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 - 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 23111 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 - 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 23112 &:= (((9 - (8 \times 7)) + 65) \times ((4 \times 321)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23113 &:= (((-1-2) + (345 \times 67)) - (8-9)) \\ 23114 &:= (((-12 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) + (8-9)) \\ 23115 &:= ((-1+2) - ((345 \times -(67)) - (8-9))) \\ 23116 &:= (-1 \times (-2 + ((345 \times -(67)) - (8-9)))) \\ 23117 &:= (-1 \times (23 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))) \\ 23118 &:= (-((-1-2)) + ((345 \times -(67)) \times (8-9))) \\ 23119 &:= (-((-1-2)) + (-((345 \times -(67)) - (8-9)))) \\ 23120 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) \times (-((34 \times (5 \times (67 - (8-9)))))) \\ 23121 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times (45 + 67)) - 8)) \times 9) \\ 23122 &:= ((1+2)^3 + 4^5) \times (-67 + 89) \\ 23123 &:= (-1 - (((2+3)^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - (8-9))) \\ 23124 &:= (123 \times ((45 \times 6) + (7 - 89))) \\ 23125 &:= (-12 - (-(-3) - ((4 \times -5) \times ((6+7) \times -(89)))))) \\ 23126 &:= ((12 + ((345 \times 67) + 8)) - 9) \\ 23127 &:= ((12 + ((345 \times 67))) \times (-8+9)) \\ 23128 &:= (((12 + (345 \times 67)) - 8) + 9) \\ 23129 &:= ((-1-2) + ((345 \times 67) + (8+9))) \\ 23130 &:= -(((1 \times 2) + ((-345) \times 67) - (8+9))) \\ 23131 &:= (((-1-2) \times 3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))) \\ 23132 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) - (4 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))) \\ 23133 &:= ((-(((1-2) - (345 \times 67))) + 8) + 9) \\ 23134 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((-345) \times 67) - (8+9)) \\ 23135 &:= ((-(-1) + 2) - (((345 \times -(67)) - 8) - 9)) \\ 23136 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times (6+7))) \times (8+9)) \\ 23137 &:= ((-1-2) + ((3 + (-((45 \times 6)) + 7)) \times -(89))) \\ 23138 &:= (-1 + ((2-3) - (-4 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))) \\ 23139 &:= (-1 + ((2-3) \times (-4 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))) \\ 23140 &:= ((1 + ((2-3) + 4)) \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89))) \\ 23141 &:= (-1 - (((2+3)^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - (8+9)) \\ 23142 &:= ((1 - ((2-3))) + ((4 \times 5) \times ((6+7) \times 89))) \\ 23143 &:= ((-1+2) \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))) \\ 23144 &:= ((12 + ((345 \times 67) + 8)) + 9) \\ 23145 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) + ((4 \times 5) \times ((-6-7) \times -(89)))))) \\ 23146 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times 3) + (4 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times 89)))) \\ 23147 &:= (-1 - ((2+34) \times (5 + ((6-78) \times 9)))) \\ 23148 &:= (-12 \times ((-34) \times ((5 \times (6+7)) - 8) + 9)) \\ 23149 &:= (1 - ((2+34) \times (5 + ((6-78) \times 9)))) \\ 23150 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!) + 4! \times (5 - 6!) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 23151 &:= ((-1-2) - (3 \times (4 - ((5+6) \times (78 \times 9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23113 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 - (4 + 3))))))^2) \times -1) \\ 23114 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23115 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23116 &:= (-(-9) - (((-8 \times 76) \times (-5 + 43)) - ((2 + 1)))) \\ 23117 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! + 6! + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 23118 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23119 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times ((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 23120 &:= (((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23121 &:= (((9 - (-((876 \times 5))/4)) - 3) \times 21) \\ 23122 &:= (((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23123 &:= (((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23124 &:= ((-9 \times (((87 \times 6) \times -5) + 43)) + 21) \\ 23125 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times -((4 \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\ 23126 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23127 &:= (-9 + (((((8 - 7) \times 6)^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23128 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23129 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23130 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23131 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 - (6^{5-4+3})) \times 2))) + 1) \\ 23132 &:= ((-9 - (-87 \times ((65 \times 4) + (3 \times 2)))) + (-1)) \\ 23133 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23134 &:= ((-9 - (-87 \times ((65 \times 4) + (3 \times 2)))) - (-1)) \\ 23135 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6^5) - (4^3))/2)) - 1) \\ 23136 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23137 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))^2) - 1)) \\ 23138 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23139 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3)))/(2 + 1))) \\ 23140 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + (6^5)) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23141 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 23142 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4) \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 23143 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4) \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\ 23144 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4) \times 3 - 2 + 1 \\ 23145 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23146 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4) \times 3 + 2 - 1 \\ 23147 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4) \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\ 23148 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 23149 &:= 9 \times (-8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4)/3 + 2 - 1 \\ 23150 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\ 23151 &:= (9 - 8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4 \times 3) \times (2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23152 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (3 \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (78 \times 9)))))) \\ 23153 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 23154 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (-3 \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 23155 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (3 \times (4 - ((5 + 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 23156 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times 6) - (7 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 23157 &:= (((-1 - 23)) \times (4^5)) - (-6 - (7 \times 89)) \\ 23158 &:= ((1 + ((23 + 4) \times ((5 + 6) \times 78))) - 9) \\ 23159 &:= (-((1 - ((2 + 345) \times 67))) - 89) \\ 23160 &:= -(((1 - ((2 + 345) \times 67)) + 89)) \\ 23161 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 345) \times 67)) - 89) \\ 23162 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 23163 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\ 23164 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 23165 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 - 4)) \times ((5 + 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 23166 &:= ((-1 \times 234) \times ((-((5 \times 6) - 78) + 9)) \\ 23167 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (67 - 8)) - 9))) \\ 23168 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (67 - 8)) - 9))) \\ 23169 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) \\ 23170 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) \\ 23171 &:= (((1 \times 23) - ((4 \times 5) \times -(67))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 23172 &:= (-12 \times -(3 + (4 \times (5 + ((6 \times 78) + 9)))) \\ 23173 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6! + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 23174 &:= (-1 - ((234 \times (5 - ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 23175 &:= ((12 + 3) \times 4^5 / 6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 23176 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (78 \times 9)))))) \\ 23177 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (345)) \times 67) - (8 \times 9) \\ 23178 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\ 23179 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 23180 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times -(((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 23181 &:= (((1^2) + (345)) \times 67) + 8 - 9) \\ 23182 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 345)) \times -(67 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 23183 &:= (((1 - 2) - 345) \times -(67)) + (-8 + 9) \\ 23184 &:= (((1^2) - 3) - 4) \times 56 \times (-78 + 9) \\ 23185 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + 6))) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 23186 &:= ((1 \times -2) - (-34) \times ((-5 + 678) + 9)) \\ 23187 &:= ((-12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 23188 &:= (((12 - 34) \times (5 - 67)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 23189 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((345 \times 67) + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23190 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23152 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 23153 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))^2))) - 1) \\ 23154 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23155 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))^2))) + 1) \\ 23156 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 + (6^5)) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23157 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23158 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 + ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23159 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3))) - (2 \times 1)))) \\ 23160 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23161 &:= (((9 + ((8 \times -7) - 6)) \times ((5 + 432) \times -1))) \\ 23162 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23163 &:= ((9 + (-8 \times -((76 + (-5 \times 43)))) \times (-21)) \\ 23164 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times (-43 + 2) - 1 \\ 23165 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23166 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23167 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3))) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 23168 &:= (((-9 \times (87 - 6)) + 5) \times -((4^3) / (2 \times 1))) \\ 23169 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23170 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) - (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 23171 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 23172 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23173 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23174 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + (4^3)))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23175 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 23176 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4^3) + 2 - 1 \\ 23177 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4^3) + 2 \times 1 \\ 23178 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4^3) + 2 + 1 \\ 23179 &:= (((9 \times 8) + 7654) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23180 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\ 23181 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 23182 &:= 9 + (-8 \times 7 + 6^5 + 4) \times 3 + 2 - 1 \\ 23183 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23184 &:= (((-9 - 87) - 6) \times (-(-5) + (-((4 - 321)))) \\ 23185 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)))) + 1) \\ 23186 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (6^5)) \times -(4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 23187 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (6^5)) \times -((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23188 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23189 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - ((7 - (6 - 5))^4))) + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 23190 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23191 &:= ((1+2) - (34 \times (5 - (678+9)))) & 23191 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - ((7 - (6 - 5))^4))) + 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 23192 &:= (-12 + ((345 \times 67) + 89)) & 23192 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) \times (4 - (3 - 2)))) - 1) \\ 23193 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8))) - 9)) & 23193 &:= 9 + (8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 \times 4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\ 23194 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4567 + (8 \times 9)))) & 23194 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4^3) + 2 - 1 \\ 23195 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) \times (4567 + (8 \times 9)))) & 23195 &:= (-9 - 8) \times 7 + (6^5 - 4) \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\ 23196 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9)) & 23196 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4^3) + 2 + 1 \\ 23197 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4) \times -(5 - (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)) & 23197 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 23198 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) + 9)) & 23198 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23199 &:= (12 + ((345 \times 67) + (8 \times 9))) & 23199 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23200 &:= (12 - (34 \times ((5 - 678) - 9))) & 23200 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23201 &:= (-12 + ((34 \times (5 + 678)) - 9)) & 23201 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23202 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) + ((345 \times 67) + (89))) & 23202 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 - 6)) \times (5 + (-4 \times -321))) \\ 23203 &:= (((1 - 2) + (345 \times 67)) + 89) & 23203 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23204 &:= (-(((1 - 2) \times (345 \times 67))) + 89) & 23204 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23205 &:= ((1^2) - (-((345 \times 67)) - 89)) & 23205 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 23206 &:= (1 \times (2 - (-((345 \times 67)) - 89))) & 23206 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23207 &:= (1 + (2 - (-((345 \times 67)) - 89))) & 23207 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23208 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -(4 + (56 \times (78 - 9)))) & 23208 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23209 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + (56 \times (78 - 9)))))) & 23209 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6^5) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 23210 &:= (-1 - ((-(-2) - (34 \times (5 + 678))) + 9)) & 23210 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\ 23211 &:= ((-1 \times (-(-2) - (34 \times (5 + 678)))) - 9) & 23211 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23212 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((-(-34)) \times (-5 - 678)) + 9)) & 23212 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23213 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(67 + (8 \times 9))) & 23213 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23214 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4) \times -(5 - (6 \times 7))) + 89) & 23214 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 23215 &:= (-1 + 23) \times 4^5 + 678 + 9 & 23215 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6^5) - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23216 &:= (12 + ((345 \times 67) + 89)) & 23216 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 + ((4^3) + 2))) - 1) \\ 23217 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + 5))) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 23217 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times ((5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 23218 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6!) - 7! - 8 - 9 & 23218 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23219 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + (4^5))/6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)) & 23219 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 23220 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) - 5) \times -(6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 23220 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23221 &:= (-(-1) + ((2 - ((34 - 5) \times -(-6))) \times ((7 + 8) \times -9))) & 23221 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 23222 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times ((45 - 6) \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) & 23222 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23223 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) & 23223 &:= -98 + 7 + (6^5 - 4) \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\ 23224 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 23224 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23225 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 23225 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 23226 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 23226 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - ((6^5) - 4)) \times 3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 23227 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times (78 + 9)))) & 23227 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23228 &:= (-1 + (-2 + ((34 \times (5 + 678)) + 9))) & 23228 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23229 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9) & 23229 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23230 &:= (-(-1) + (-2 + ((34 \times (5 + 678)) + 9))) \\ 23231 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (34 \times (5 + 678))) + 9) \\ 23232 &:= (-((-12^3)) - (-4 \times (56 \times (7 + 89)))) \\ 23233 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((34 \times (5 + 678)) + 9))) \\ 23234 &:= (((1 + 2) - (34 \times -(5 + 678))) + 9) \\ 23235 &:= (((-1 - ((23 + 4) \times (5 + 6))) \times -(78)) - 9) \\ 23236 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 23237 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 23238 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 \times 3))^4) - 5) \times -(6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 23239 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 + 67))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 23240 &:= (((12 \times -3) - 4) \times (-5 - (-6 \times (-7 - 89)))) \\ 23241 &:= (((-12 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 23242 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 23243 &:= (12 + ((34 \times (5 + 678)) + 9)) \\ 23244 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\ 23245 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times ((5 \times 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9) \\ 23246 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 23247 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) + ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) \times 9)) \\ 23248 &:= ((1 \times ((2 + (345)) \times 67)) + (8 - 9)) \\ 23249 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (345)) \times 67)) + (8 - 9)) \\ 23250 &:= ((1 \times ((2 + (345)) \times 67)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 23251 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (345)) \times 67)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 23252 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 - 9)))))) \\ 23253 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 23254 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 23255 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)^4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 \times 9 \\ 23256 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) - 5)) \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 23257 &:= (1 - (-((2 + 34) \times (-56) + (78 \times 9)))) \\ 23258 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 23259 &:= (((-12 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 23260 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4! \times 5! + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 23261 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3! - 4 - 5!) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 23262 &:= ((-12 \times 34) - ((5 \times -6) \times 789)) \\ 23263 &:= ((((-12 \times (3^{4-5+6})) + 7) \times -8) - 9) \\ 23264 &:= 1 + ((-2 + 3 + 4)^5 \times 67 - 8) / 9 \\ 23265 &:= ((1 + 234) \times (((5 \times 6) + 78) - 9)) \\ 23266 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (345)) \times 67) + (8 + 9) \\ 23267 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9) \\ 23268 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23230 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23231 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times ((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) + (2 - 1)))) \\ 23232 &:= -98 - 7 + (6^5 + 4) \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 23233 &:= -98 - 7 + (6^5 + 4) \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\ 23234 &:= -98 - 7 + (6^5 + 4) \times 3 - 2 + 1 \\ 23235 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23236 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23237 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 23238 &:= -9 + (-8 - 7 + 6^5 - 4 \times 3) \times (2 + 1) \\ 23239 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (((7 - (6 - 5))^4) + 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 23240 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23241 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 + 1) \\ 23242 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23243 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 - 1) \\ 23244 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 23245 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23246 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23247 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1) \\ 23248 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23249 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + ((6^5) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 23250 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 23251 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + (6^5 - 4) \times 3 \times (2 - 1) \\ 23252 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23253 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23254 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + (6^5 - 4) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 23255 &:= (98 + (((-7 - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times (-2 - 1)))) \\ 23256 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23257 &:= ((-9 + (-8)) + (((7 - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - 21)) \\ 23258 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23259 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23260 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23261 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23262 &:= ((((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23263 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (543 - (2 \times (1)))) \\ 23264 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23265 &:= (((98 + 7654) + 3) \times -((-2 - (1)))) \\ 23266 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23267 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23268 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23269 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23270 &:= (-(((1 \times (-23 \times (((4^5) - 6) - 7))) - 8)) + 9) \\ 23271 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4 + ((5 + 6) \times 78)) \times 9))) \\ 23272 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4 + ((5 + 6) \times 78)) \times 9)))) \\ 23273 &:= (1 + (2 \times 3)^4 + 5 + 67) \times (8 + 9) \\ 23274 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times -(5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 23275 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4) \times (-5 + (6 + 7) \times 8 \times 9) \\ 23276 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9))) \\ 23277 &:= (1 + (23 \times (4 + ((56 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 23278 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 23279 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4567 + 89))) \\ 23280 &:= (1 \times ((2 + 3) \times (4567 + 89))) \\ 23281 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4567 + 89))) \\ 23282 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3) \times (4 \times 5! - (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 23283 &:= (1 + 2)^3 \times (4 + (5 + 6) \times 78) + 9 \\ 23284 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((6 + 78) \times 9)) \\ 23285 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9) \\ 23286 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 23287 &:= (((((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\ 23288 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 23289 &:= -1 + 2 \times (-((3 + 4)!/5! + 6! + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 23290 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 456)) + 7) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 23291 &:= -((1 + (((23 \times 4) + (-5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 23292 &:= (-12 \times (3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7 \times 8)/9)) \\ 23293 &:= (1 - (((23 \times 4) + (-5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 23294 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - 6))) - (-7 \times (-8 - 9))) \\ 23295 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 \times 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8))) - 9) \\ 23296 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (67 - 8))) - 9) \\ 23297 &:= (((-1 - ((2^3) \times ((4 - 56) \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 23298 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((45 \times 6) + 789)) \\ 23299 &:= -((1 \times (-23 \times ((4 \times 56) + 789))) \\ 23300 &:= (1 - (-23 \times ((4 \times 56) + 789))) \\ 23301 &:= ((((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4))/5) \times (6 \times (7 + 8))) - 9) \\ 23302 &:= (1 + (((234 \times (5 + 6)) + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 23303 &:= -1 + (2^{31} \times 4 - 5 + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 23304 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))))) \\ 23305 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) \\ 23306 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((34 \times ((5 \times 67) + 8)) - 9))) \\ 23307 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((34 \times ((5 \times 67) + 8)) - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23269 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23270 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23271 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23272 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23273 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 23274 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23275 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7 - ((6^5) - 4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 23276 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 23277 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23278 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23279 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7 - ((6^5) - 4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1))) \\ 23280 &:= (((-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6)^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23281 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7 - ((6^5) - 4)) \times 3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 23282 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23283 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23284 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23285 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23286 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6^5 - 4) - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\ 23287 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23288 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23289 &:= ((9 - (((8 + 7) - (6^5)) - (-4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23290 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 23291 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (((7 - ((6^5) - 4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 23292 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23293 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23294 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23295 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23296 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23297 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23298 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6)^5 - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23299 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23300 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23301 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23302 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + 2) \times -1) \\ 23303 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23304 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 23305 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23306 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 23307 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23308 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!^4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\23309 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\23310 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3 + 4)) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 78)) - 9)) \\23311 &:= (-1 + (2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 + 9 \\23312 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3)^4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\23313 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 \times 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8))) + 9) \\23314 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (67 - 8))) + 9) \\23315 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times (34 \times ((5 \times 67) + 8))) - 9)) \\23316 &:= -((((1 - 2) + 3) - (45 \times 6)) \times (78 + 9)) \\23317 &:= (-1 + (((2 - ((3 - (45 \times 6)) + 7)) \times 89))) \\23318 &:= (1 \times ((2 - ((3 - (45 \times 6)) + 7)) \times 89)) \\23319 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 - (45 \times 6)) + 7)) \times 89)) \\23320 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) \\23321 &:= ((-1 \times -(23456)) + ((7 + 8) \times -9)) \\23322 &:= ((1 + 23456) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\23323 &:= (-1 + 23) \times 4^5 + 6 + 789 \\23324 &:= (((1 - (2^3)) \times -4) \times (56 - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\23325 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) + -((67 - 8) \times -9)) \\23326 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9))) \\23327 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\23328 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3^4) \times ((5 - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\23329 &:= -1 + 2 + 3^4 \times (5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 \times 9 \\23330 &:= 1 + (2 \times 3)^4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) - 8 + 9 \\23331 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4 \times (((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9))) \\23332 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - 6)) + (7 - 89)) \\23333 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times (34 \times ((5 \times 67) + 8))) + 9)) \\23334 &:= (1 - (-((2 \times 34) \times ((5 \times 67) + 8))) - 9) \\23335 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\23336 &:= (1 - (((-23 \times ((4^5) - 6)) + 7) - (-8 \times -(-9)))) \\23337 &:= ((1 \times 23456) + (7 \times -((8 + 9)))) \\23338 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) + (-6 \times ((-7 - 8) \times 9)) \\23339 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 345) \times 67)) + 89) \\23340 &:= -(((12 \times (3 - 4)) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9)) \\23341 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4 \times ((5^6) + 7)/8 - 9 \\23342 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3 \times 4) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9)) \\23343 &:= (((-1 + (2^3) \times (4 - 56))) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9 \\23344 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3)^4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\23345 &:= (((-((1 \times -23)) \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 78) - (-9)) \\23346 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 8))) \times 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23308 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) - 2) \times -1) \\23309 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\23310 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 - (6^5)))/(4 + 3)) \times 21 \\23311 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\23312 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 + (6^5)) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\23313 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 - ((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - 21) \\23314 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\23315 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (((7 - ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\23316 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\23317 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\23318 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\23319 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\23320 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + ((6^5) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\23321 &:= (((-98 \times (-76 - (54 \times 3))) - 2) - (1)) \\23322 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\23323 &:= (((-98 \times (-76 - (54 \times 3))) - 2) + (1)) \\23324 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 + 5))) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\23325 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\23326 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\23327 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\23328 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6^5)/(4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\23329 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - 54))) \times -32) + (1)) \\23330 &:= 98 \times 7 \times (6 \times 5 + 4) + 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\23331 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\23332 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + (6^5 + 4) \times 3 \times (2 - 1) \\23333 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (((7 + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\23334 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - 7) \times 6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\23335 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + ((6^5) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\23336 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\23337 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\23338 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\23339 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\23340 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\23341 &:= (-9 + 8)^7 + (6^5 + 4) \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\23342 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\23343 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\23344 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + (6^5 + 4) \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\23345 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 + (6^5)) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\23346 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - 7) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3)))/(2 + 1)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23347 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times -(5 + (6 + 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 23348 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - 6)) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 23349 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(3 + (4 \times (((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9))) \\
 23350 &:= (1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - 6)) + (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 23351 &:= (((-1 + (23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\
 23352 &:= (12 \times 3^4 - 5 + 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 23353 &:= (1 + ((2 - (34 \times 5)) \times (-67) + (-8 \times 9))) \\
 23354 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times ((45 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 23355 &:= (((1 \times 2) + 3) \times (-((4 + 56) \times -(78)) - 9)) \\
 23356 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times (((4 + 56) \times 78) - 9))) \\
 23357 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (678 + 9)))) \\
 23358 &:= (1 + (2 \times 3)^4 + (5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 23359 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 23360 &:= (1 \times ((23456 - 7) - 89)) \\
 23361 &:= (1 + ((23456 - 7) - 89)) \\
 23362 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 23363 &:= (-1 + (((-2 - (-3 + 45)) \times (67 - 8)) \times -9)) \\
 23364 &:= ((1 + ((23 + (4 + 5)))) \times (6 + (78 \times 9))) \\
 23365 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 - 45)) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 23366 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - 6))) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 23367 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times ((-4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 23368 &:= (((-123) - 4) \times (5 + (-((6 + ((7 + 8)))) \times 9))) \\
 23369 &:= (1 \times ((23456 - 78) - 9)) \\
 23370 &:= (1 + ((23456 - 78) - 9)) \\
 23371 &:= ((-12 \times 3) + (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 89)) \\
 23372 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 23373 &:= (-1 + (23456 + (7 - 89))) \\
 23374 &:= -((-1 \times (23456 + (7 - 89)))) \\
 23375 &:= ((1 + (23456)) + ((7 - 89))) \\
 23376 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 - 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 23377 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 23378 &:= (((1 + 23456) - 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 23379 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times 8 \times 9) \\
 23380 &:= (((-1 - 2345) - 6) \times -(((7 - 8) - 9))) \\
 23381 &:= 1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) \times 8 \times 9) \\
 23382 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 23383 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times -8) - 9) \\
 23384 &:= ((-1 + ((23 + 4) \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 23385 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times ((-4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8)))) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23347 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - (((-6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (-21))) \\
 23348 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 23349 &:= -987 + (-6 + 54 \times 3)^2 \times 1 \\
 23350 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 23351 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23352 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) - (6^5)) \times -((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23353 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23354 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23355 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3))) + 21) \\
 23356 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23357 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 + 6^5 - 4) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 23358 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23359 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 23360 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 23361 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 23362 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) - 2) \times -1) \\
 23363 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 23364 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 23365 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 23366 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 23367 &:= -((((9 - 8) - ((7 + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) + 21))) \\
 23368 &:= (((9 - 8) \times ((7 + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) + 21))) \\
 23369 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23370 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 23371 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23372 &:= (((-(9 - ((87 \times 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times (3^2)) - (1)) \\
 23373 &:= (((-(9 - ((87 \times 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times (3^2) \times 1)) \\
 23374 &:= (((-(9 - ((87 \times 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times (3^2)) + (1)) \\
 23375 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 23376 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - 7) \times 6)^5) + (4 + 3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 23377 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 23378 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23379 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 23380 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + 4) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 23381 &:= ((((((9 \times 8) + 7) - 6) \times 5) \times (4^3)) - ((-21))) \\
 23382 &:= (((9 \times 8) - 7) + (-6 - 5)) \times -((-432 - 1))) \\
 23383 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + (6^{5-4+3})) \times 2))) + 1) \\
 23384 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23385 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23386 &:= ((-1 + 23456) - (78 - 9)) & 23386 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23387 &:= -((1 \times (-((23456 - 78) - 9))) & 23387 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23388 &:= (1 - (-((23456 - 78) - 9)) & 23388 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) - ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23389 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - 6))) - (7 + (8 + 9))) & 23389 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23390 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - 6)) - (7 + (8 + 9))) & 23390 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23391 &:= (1 \times ((23456 + 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 23391 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times -6) - 5) + 4) \times 32) + (-1)) \\ 23392 &:= ((1 + (23456 + 7)) - (8 \times 9)) & 23392 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23393 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)))) & 23393 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + ((6^5) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 23394 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)))) & 23394 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) - ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23395 &:= (-12 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 89)) & 23395 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 23396 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - (67 + 89)) & 23396 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23397 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 23397 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23398 &:= -((1 - (-((2^3) - (((-45) \times 6) + 7) \times 89)))) & 23398 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23399 &:= ((1 \times -((2^3))) - (((-45) \times 6) + 7) \times 89) & 23399 &:= ((-9 \times -8) \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + (4 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 23400 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times -(6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 23400 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times ((7 + (6 + 5)) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\ 23401 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 23401 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23402 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 + (-45) \times 6)) \times (78 + 9))) & 23402 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23403 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - 6)) + (7 - (8 + 9)))) & 23403 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23404 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - 6)) + (7 - (8 + 9))) & 23404 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23405 &:= -(((1 - (2 - 3)) + (((-45) \times 6) + 7) \times 89)) & 23405 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 23406 &:= -((-1 \times ((23 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 23406 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -((5 \times 4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 23407 &:= ((1 + (2 - ((3 - (45 \times 6)) + 7))) \times 89) & 23407 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + ((6^5) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 23408 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 23408 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23409 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (((-45) \times 6) + 7) \times 89) & 23409 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\ 23410 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3) + 45) \times 6) \times 78) + 9) & 23410 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times (((65 \times 4) \times (3^2)) - (-1))) \\ 23411 &:= ((-1 - (-2 - 3)) - (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times -(89))) & 23411 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23412 &:= (12 \times ((34 \times 56) - ((-7 \times 8) + 9))) & 23412 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23413 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - (67 + (8 \times 9))) & 23413 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23414 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 89))) & 23414 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23415 &:= ((-12 \times -((34 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) - 9) & 23415 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23416 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + 89) & 23416 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23417 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 23417 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((8 - 7) + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 23418 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 \times 3))^4) + 5) \times -(6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 23418 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + (6^5)) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23419 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 23419 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 23420 &:= (-1 \times (((-23 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7) - 8) - (-9)) & 23420 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) - 4) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 23421 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - 6))) + (7 - (8 - 9))) & 23421 &:= (((((9 \times 8) - 7) \times ((6 \times 5) \times 4)) \times 3) - (-21)) \\ 23422 &:= ((-1 \times (((-23 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7) + 8)) - (-9)) & 23422 &:= ((98 - (-76 \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 23423 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 \times 7) \times 89)) & 23423 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 23424 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 + 4) + ((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9)) & 23424 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23425 &:= (1 - ((2 - 34) \times ((5 \times 6) + (78 \times 9)))) \\ 23426 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 23427 &:= ((-1 \times (-2 - ((34 + 5) \times -(67)) + 8)) \times -9) \\ 23428 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8))) - 9) \\ 23429 &:= -(((1 - 23) - (((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 89))) \\ 23430 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + (4 \times (((5^6) + 7)/8))) - 9)) \\ 23431 &:= (((12 + 3) \times 4) \times (56 \times 7)) - 89) \\ 23432 &:= (1 \times ((23456 - 7) - ((8 + 9)))) \\ 23433 &:= (1 + ((23456 - 7) - ((8 + 9)))) \\ 23434 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - 45) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 23435 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 23436 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 23437 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3 \times 4) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8))) - 9) \\ 23438 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) + 4) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8))) - 9) \\ 23439 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4)) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8)) - 9) \\ 23440 &:= -(((1 - (23 \times (4^5))) - (((6 + 7) \times -8) - 9))) \\ 23441 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + ((3 \times 4) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8))) - 9) \\ 23442 &:= ((1 + 2) - (-3 \times ((4^5) + 6789))) \\ 23443 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 23444 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((45 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 23445 &:= -(((1 - (23456 + 7)) + ((8 + 9)))) \\ 23446 &:= ((1 \times (23456 + 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 23447 &:= ((-1 + (23456)) - (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 23448 &:= ((1 \times 23456) + ((-7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 23449 &:= ((1 + 23456) + ((-7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 23450 &:= (((1 \times 23456) - 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 23451 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 - 4) - (((5^6) + 7)/8))) - 9) \\ 23452 &:= (-(((1 - 23) - 4) \times (5 + 6)) \times (-7 + 89)) \\ 23453 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\ 23454 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times 4) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8)) + 9)) \\ 23455 &:= -(((1 - (23456 \times ((-7 + 8)^9)))) \\ 23456 &:= (1 \times (23456 \times ((-7 + 8)^9))) \\ 23457 &:= (1 + (23456 \times ((-7 + 8)^9))) \\ 23458 &:= (((1 + 2) + (34)) \times (5 - (-6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 23459 &:= ((1 \times ((-23 \times (-4^5)) - (6 + 78))) - (-(-9))) \\ 23460 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 - (456 + 7))) \times (-8 - 9)) \\ 23461 &:= (-(((1 - 23456) - 7)) - (-8 + 9)) \\ 23462 &:= (-(((1 - 23456) - 7)) \times (-8 + 9)) \\ 23463 &:= (-(((1 - 23456) - 7)) + (-8 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23425 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4 + 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23426 &:= (((-9 \times (((87 \times (6 \times -5)) + 4) + 3)) - 2) + (1)) \\ 23427 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\ 23428 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6^5) + (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23429 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4^3 + 2) - 1 \\ 23430 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4^3 + 2 \times 1) \\ 23431 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 + 6) \times 5 \times (4^3 + 2) + 1 \\ 23432 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23433 &:= (((9 + 87) + ((-((6^5)) + 4) \times -3)) + 21) \\ 23434 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23435 &:= (((9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (543 + (2 \times (1)))) \\ 23436 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) \times (5^4 / (3 + 2) - 1) \\ 23437 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23438 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23439 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23440 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times (6 \times 5))) - (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 23441 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23442 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23443 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23444 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23445 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 23446 &:= ((-9 + (-8 \times 76)) \times -((((5 \times 4) - 3) + 21)))) \\ 23447 &:= (((9 \times 87) \times 6) \times 5) + ((-43 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 23448 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1) \\ 23449 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23450 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23451 &:= (((9 - 8) - 7) - (((6^5) + 43) \times (-2 - 1))) \\ 23452 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23453 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23454 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23455 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23456 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1) \\ 23457 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5 + 4) \times 3) \times 21 \\ 23458 &:= (((9 \times ((87 \times 6) \times 5)) - (-4 \times -(((3^2) - 1)))) \\ 23459 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 23460 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23461 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23462 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23463 &:= ((-9 \times ((-87 \times 6) \times 5)) + (4 - ((32 - 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23464 &:= ((1 \times 23456) - ((-7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 23465 &:= ((1 + 23456) - ((-7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 23466 &:= (((-1 - 23456) \times (7 - 8)) + 9) \\ 23467 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times (4^5)) - 67) - (8 + 9))) \\ 23468 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - (67 + (8 + 9))) \\ 23469 &:= (-((-1 - ((23 \times (4^5)) - 67))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 23470 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((6 - (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 23471 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) - 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 23472 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 23473 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 23474 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\ 23475 &:= ((-12 - 3) - (-45 \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 23476 &:= ((-1 - (-23 \times (4^5))) - (6 + (78 - 9))) \\ 23477 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times ((4 \times (((5^6) + 7)/8)) + 9))) \\ 23478 &:= (1 - ((23 \times (-4^5)) + ((6 + 78) - 9))) \\ 23479 &:= (((-1 - (-23456) - 7) + 8) + 9) \\ 23480 &:= ((1 \times (23456 + 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\ 23481 &:= ((1 \times -((23 \times -((4^5)))) - ((6 - 7) - (8 \times -9))) \\ 23482 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 23483 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 + ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 23484 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) - (45 \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 23485 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - ((67 + 8) - 9)) \\ 23486 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - ((67 + 8) - 9)) \\ 23487 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 23488 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 23489 &:= (((-1 - 2)/3) - (-45 \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 23490 &:= (-1 - ((2 - 3) + (-45 \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 23491 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - 3) + (-45 \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 23492 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times (4^5)) + 6) - ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 23493 &:= (-123) \times (-((45 \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23494 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23495 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 23496 &:= (((-(-1) + 23) - (4 \times (5 + 67))) \times -(89)) \\ 23497 &:= (-(-1) - ((2 \times -3) - (45 \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 23498 &:= ((1 + (2 - 34)) \times -((56 + (78 \times 9)))) \\ 23499 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((-6 + (-7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 23500 &:= (((-1 - 2345) + 6) \times -((7 - 8) - 9)) \\ 23501 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) \\ 23502 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23464 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\ 23465 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 - 1))) \\ 23466 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) - (4 + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23467 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + ((7 - (6 - 5))^4))) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\ 23468 &:= ((-9 \times ((87 \times 6) \times -5)) + (-43 + 21)) \\ 23469 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23470 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 23471 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 23472 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 23473 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23474 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23475 &:= -9 + (8 \times 7 + 6^5 - 4) \times 3 \times (2 - 1) \\ 23476 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23477 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23478 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23479 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2})) + 1)) \\ 23480 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2} \times 1))) \\ 23481 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4))/3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23482 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23483 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23484 &:= ((9 \times (8 + 7)) - (((-6^5) - 4) - 3) \times (2 + (1))) \\ 23485 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23486 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) \times (4 - (3 - 2)))) - 1) \\ 23487 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (6^5)) \times ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 23488 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times (4^3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 23489 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2)))) - 1) \\ 23490 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 + (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1))))))) \\ 23491 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23492 &:= 9 \times 87 \times 6 \times 5 - 4 + 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\ 23493 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6)^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23494 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times (6 \times 5))) + ((4 + 3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 23495 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) - 1) \\ 23496 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23497 &:= 9 \times 87 \times 6 \times 5 + 4 \times 3/2 + 1 \\ 23498 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23499 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23500 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23501 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) \times 2) - 1) \\ 23502 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23503 &:= (-((-1 - ((23 \times (4^5)) - 67))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 23504 &:= (((-1 \times -23) \times (4^5)) + (-6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\ 23505 &:= 1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\ 23506 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 + 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 23507 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9) \\ 23508 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 + (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9) \\ 23509 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23510 &:= (1 \times ((2345 + 6) \times -(((7 - 8) - 9)))) \\ 23511 &:= (1 \times (((23 \times (4^5)) + 6) - (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 23512 &:= (1 + (((23 \times (4^5)) + 6) - (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 23513 &:= (((1 - (-23 \times ((4^5) + (6 - 7)))) - 8) - 9) \\ 23514 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -(4 - (5 \times (6 - 789)))) \\ 23515 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\ 23516 &:= (-12 - (34 \times -((5 + 678) - 9))) \\ 23517 &:= (((-(-1) + 2)^3) - (-45) \times (6 \times (78 + 9))) \\ 23518 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (((6 + 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 23519 &:= (-1 + (((234 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 89)))) \\ 23520 &:= ((1 \times (234 + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 89)) \\ 23521 &:= (1 + ((234 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 23522 &:= (1 + (-((-23456) - (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 23523 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (6 - ((-7 - 8) - 9))) \\ 23524 &:= (-1 - (-23456) - ((78 - 9))) \\ 23525 &:= (-1 + ((-2 + (34 \times (5 + (678 + 9)))))) \\ 23526 &:= ((1 + 23456) + (78 - 9)) \\ 23527 &:= ((1 - 2) + (34 \times (5 + (678 + 9)))) \\ 23528 &:= (-((1 - 2) \times (34 \times (5 + (678 + 9)))) \\ 23529 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times ((5 + 6) \times (-78 + 9))) \\ 23530 &:= (((-(-(1 \times 23))) \times -((-4)^5)) + (67 - 89)) \\ 23531 &:= ((1 + 2) + (34 \times (5 + (678 + 9)))) \\ 23532 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - 6))) + (-7 \times (-8 - 9))) \\ 23533 &:= 1 \times 23 \times (4^5 - 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 23534 &:= -(((1 - (23456 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 23535 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4^5))) + (6 + ((-7 - 8) - 9))) \\ 23536 &:= ((1 + (23456 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 23537 &:= (-1 - (-((23456 - 7) - 89)) \\ 23538 &:= (-1 \times (-((23456 - 7) - 89)) \\ 23539 &:= ((1 + (23456)) - ((7 - 89))) \\ 23540 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - ((6 + (7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 23541 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23503 &:= (((((9 \times (87 \times 6)) \times 5) + (4 \times 3)) + 2) - (1)) \\ 23504 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 23505 &:= (((((9 \times (87 \times 6)) \times 5) + (4 \times 3)) + 2) + (1)) \\ 23506 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 23507 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4))/3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23508 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23509 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4))/3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23510 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23511 &:= (-9 + (((((8 - 7) \times 6)^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23512 &:= ((-9 \times ((87 \times 6) \times -5)) - (-43 + 21)) \\ 23513 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23514 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) + ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23515 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times 7) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - 2) \times -1) \\ 23516 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 23517 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + ((6^5) + (4 + 3)))/(2 + 1))) \\ 23518 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 - (3 - 2)))) + 1) \\ 23519 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)))) + 1))) \\ 23520 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23521 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2)) + 1) \\ 23522 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^5) \times (4 - 3 + 2) - 1 \\ 23523 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^5) \times (4 - 3 + 2) \times 1 \\ 23524 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7 + 6^5) \times (4 - 3 + 2) + 1 \\ 23525 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5) \times -((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 23526 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23527 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23528 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + (6^5 + 4^3) \times (2 + 1) \\ 23529 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23530 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 23531 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\ 23532 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 23533 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23534 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2})) + 1)) \\ 23535 &:= ((-9 + 87) + (((6^5) + 43) \times (2 - (-1)))) \\ 23536 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\ 23537 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 23538 &:= 9 \times 87 \times 6 \times 5 + (4 + 3)^2 - 1 \\ 23539 &:= 9 \times 87 \times 6 \times 5 + (4 + 3)^2 \times 1 \\ 23540 &:= 9 \times 87 \times 6 \times 5 + (4 + 3)^2 + 1 \\ 23541 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23542 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8))) - 9) \\ 23543 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times -(34)) \times -5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 23544 &:= -(((1 + 23) \times ((-(4^5)) - (6 \times -7)) - (8 - 9))) \\ 23545 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 23546 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 23547 &:= -((((1 \times -((23 \times (4^5)))) - 67) + ((8 \times 9))) \\ 23548 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (-67) + ((8 \times 9))) \\ 23549 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - 6)) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\ 23550 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 23551 &:= (((1 \times (23 \times -((4^5)))) - (6 - 7)) \times (8 - 9)) \\ 23552 &:= (((1 \times 23456) + 7) + 89) \\ 23553 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)))))) \times -9) \\ 23554 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3 \times 4) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8) + 9))) \\ 23555 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + 4) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8) + 9))) \\ 23556 &:= -1 + 23 \times 4^5 + 6 + (7 - 8)^9 \\ 23557 &:= (((1 + (23 \times (4^5))) + ((-6 - 7))) - (-8 - 9)) \\ 23558 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4^5))) + (-67) + ((8 \times 9))) \\ 23559 &:= (1 + 23 \times 4^5 + 6) \times (-7 + 8)^9 \\ 23560 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -(((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 23561 &:= ((-1 - (23 \times -((4^5)))) + (((6 - 7)^8) + 9)) \\ 23562 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 23563 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9))) \\ 23564 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\ 23565 &:= (-(((1 - ((23 \times (4^5)))) - 6)) - ((-7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 23566 &:= (-((((1 \times -23) \times (4^5)) - 6) + (-7 + 8)) + 9) \\ 23567 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + (((6 - 7) + 8) + 9))) \\ 23568 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -3 + (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 23569 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) \times -8) + 9) \\ 23570 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 23571 &:= (12 + (-((3 \times (((-4^5) + ((6 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 23572 &:= (1 - ((2 - (((34 + 5) \times 67) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 23573 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) + (8 - 9))) \\ 23574 &:= (((1 + 23) \times -4) - ((-5 \times 6) \times 789)) \\ 23575 &:= ((1 \times 23456) - (7 \times -((8 + 9)))) \\ 23576 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\ 23577 &:= ((1 + ((2 - 3) \times (-45) \times 6)) \times (78 + 9)) \\ 23578 &:= ((-1 \times (23 \times 4)) + (((5 \times 6) \times 789))) \\ 23579 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 34) \times (-5 \times ((6 \times -7) - 89)))) \\ 23580 &:= (1 \times -((((2 + 34) \times 5) \times ((6 \times -7) - 89)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23542 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 \times 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23543 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3)) - 2))) - 1) \\ 23544 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\ 23545 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) - 2))) - 1)) \\ 23546 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 23547 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - 7) \times 6)^5) + (4^3)) \times -2 + 1) \\ 23548 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 23549 &:= ((((-9 + 87) + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - (2 - 1) \\ 23550 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23551 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 - 6 + 5) \times 4^{3+2} - 1 \\ 23552 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 - 6 + 5) \times 4^{3+2} \times 1 \\ 23553 &:= (9 + 8 + 7 - 6 + 5) \times 4^{3+2} + 1 \\ 23554 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\ 23555 &:= (((9 \times (87 \times (6 \times 5))) + ((4^3) + 2)) + (-1)) \\ 23556 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 23557 &:= (((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5))) + ((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 23558 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 23559 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times -2 + 1) \\ 23560 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\ 23561 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) - 2)))) - 1) \\ 23562 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times -2 + 1) \\ 23563 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) - 2)))) + 1) \\ 23564 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (6^5)) \times -4) - (3 - 2)) - 1) \\ 23565 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (6^5)) \times -((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23566 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) - 1) \\ 23567 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23568 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23569 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2}))) \times -1) \\ 23570 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) \times -2 \times 1) \\ 23571 &:= -((((9 - 87) - (6^5)) + 4) \times 3) - 21) \\ 23572 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 23573 &:= ((((-9 + 87) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23574 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 23575 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 + 5)))) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1)) \\ 23576 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23577 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23578 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23579 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 23580 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23581 &:= (1 - (((2 + 34) \times 5) \times ((6 \times -7) - 89))) \\ 23582 &:= (1 \times (((23 \times (4^5)) + 6) - ((-7 - 8) - 9))) \\ 23583 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4^5))) + (6 - ((-7 - 8) - 9))) \\ 23584 &:= (-1 - (((23 + (4 \times (-5 - 67))) \times 89))) \\ 23585 &:= (1 \times -(((23 + (4 \times (-5 - 67))) \times 89))) \\ 23586 &:= (1 - ((23 + (4 \times (-5 - 67))) \times 89)) \\ 23587 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) \\ 23588 &:= ((1 - 2) + (-((3^4)) + ((5 \times 6) \times 789))) \\ 23589 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)))))) \times -9 \\ 23590 &:= (((1^2) - (3^4)) - (5 \times (-6 \times 789))) \\ 23591 &:= (1 \times (23456 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 23592 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9))) \\ 23593 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9))) \\ 23594 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) - 6)) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 23595 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times 4)) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23596 &:= (-(-1) \times ((2 + (345)) \times (67 - (8 - 9)))) \\ 23597 &:= (-(-1) + ((2 + (345)) \times (67 - (8 - 9)))) \\ 23598 &:= ((12 + (34)) \times (((56 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 23599 &:= ((-1 \times (-23 \times (4^5))) - ((6 \times 7) - 89)) \\ 23600 &:= (((-1 \times -23) \times (4^5)) - (-6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\ 23601 &:= (((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) + 67) - (8 + 9)) \\ 23602 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (67 - (8 + 9))) \\ 23603 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) - (78 + 9)) \\ 23604 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -3 + (((4^5) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9))) \\ 23605 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 23606 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - (6 \times ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 23607 &:= (-(((1 - (23 \times ((4^5) + 6))) - 7)) + (-89))) \\ 23608 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) + (7 - 89)) \\ 23609 &:= (((((12 + 3) \times 4) \times (56 \times 7)) + 89)) \\ 23610 &:= -((((12 + 3) \times 4) + (-5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23611 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 23612 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 23613 &:= (-12 + (((3 + 4) \times 5) \times ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 23614 &:= (-1 + (((-23 \times (4^5))) - (6 - 78)) - 9)) \\ 23615 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3 + 45) \times 6) \times (-7 + 89))) \\ 23616 &:= ((1 + (234 + (5 + 6))) \times (7 + 89)) \\ 23617 &:= -(((1 - 2) - (((3 + 45) \times 6) \times (-7 + 89)))) \\ 23618 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (((3 + 45) \times 6) \times (-7 + 89))) \\ 23619 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23581 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 23582 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (765 + 4)) \times (32 - 1))) \\ 23583 &:= (((-9 + 87) + ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23584 &:= ((-9 - (((87 + (6^5)) - 4) \times 3) - 2)) \times -1 \\ 23585 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6^5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23586 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23587 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 23588 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23589 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 23590 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23591 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23592 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23593 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - 2))) - 1) \\ 23594 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\ 23595 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 23596 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 \times 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23597 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) + (6^{5-4+3})) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 23598 &:= (((9 \times 876) + (-54/3)) \times ((2 + 1))) \\ 23599 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 43) - 2)) + (1)) \\ 23600 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times 4)^{3-2+1})) \\ 23601 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6^5) + (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23602 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - (6^5)) \times -(4 - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 23603 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 23604 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 23605 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23606 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23607 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23608 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 - (5 - 4)) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 23609 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - 2))) - 1) \\ 23610 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23611 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5 + 4)^3 - 2) - 1 \\ 23612 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5 + 4)^3 - 2 \times 1) \\ 23613 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 \times ((6 + 5 + 4)^3 - 2) + 1 \\ 23614 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23615 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\ 23616 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) / (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 23617 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 23618 &:= (-98 \times ((-76 - (54 \times 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 23619 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 \times (65 - 4 - 3)^2 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23620 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - (6 + ((7 - 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 23621 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 23622 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 23623 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) + 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 23624 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3^4)/5) \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
 23625 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4)/5) \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 23626 &:= ((-1 - (-23 \times (4^5))) + (6 + (78 - 9))) \\
 23627 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((67 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 23628 &:= ((1 - (23 \times (-4^5))) + ((6 + 78) - 9)) \\
 23629 &:= ((1 - 2) + (34 \times (5 \times (67 + (8 \times 9))))) \\
 23630 &:= (-((12 \times 3)) - (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\
 23631 &:= (-((1 - 2) + ((34 \times 5) \times (67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 23632 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - ((6 - (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 23633 &:= (-((1 + (2 + 34))) - (-5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\
 23634 &:= ((-1 - (((2 + 3^4)/5) \times (6 + (7 + 8)))) \times -9) \\
 23635 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) - (-5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\
 23636 &:= (((1^2) \times -(34)) - (5 \times (-6 \times 789))) \\
 23637 &:= (((-(-1) + (23 \times (4^5))) + 67) + (8 + 9)) \\
 23638 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) \times -4) + (5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\
 23639 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) + (5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\
 23640 &:= ((-1 - (-23 \times (4^5))) - ((6 - 7) \times 89)) \\
 23641 &:= (-1 \times ((-23 \times (4^5)) + ((6 - 7) \times 89))) \\
 23642 &:= (-1 - ((23 + 4) - (((5 \times 6) \times 789)))) \\
 23643 &:= (-((1 \times (23 + 4))) + (-((5 \times 6)) \times -(789))) \\
 23644 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 23645 &:= (-1 \times (((2 - 3) - 4) \times -((5 + (-6 \times 789)))))) \\
 23646 &:= ((-(-1) - ((-23 \times (4^5)))) - (-6 - (78 + 9))) \\
 23647 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 23648 &:= ((12 - 34) + (5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\
 23649 &:= -(((1 + 2) \times (-3 - 4)) + (-5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\
 23650 &:= (-1 - ((23 - 4) - (((5 \times 6) \times 789)))) \\
 23651 &:= (-1 \times ((23 - 4) - (((5 \times 6) \times 789)))) \\
 23652 &:= (-(-1) - ((23 - 4) - (((5 \times 6) \times 789)))) \\
 23653 &:= 1 + (2 + 34) \times (5 \times (6 + 7) + 8) \times 9 \\
 23654 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (6 + (7 + 89))) \\
 23655 &:= (((-12 - (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 7)))) \times -8) - 9) \\
 23656 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times (3 + 4)) - (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\
 23657 &:= ((-12 + (3 - 4)) - (5 \times (-6 \times 789))) \\
 23658 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + ((6 + 7) - 8))) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23620 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 \times (65 - 4 - 3)^2 \times 1 \\
 23621 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 \times (65 - 4 - 3)^2 + 1 \\
 23622 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 23623 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -7) \times ((-6 - 5) - (-432 - (1)))))) \\
 23624 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 - (5 - 4)) \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 23625 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -5^{(4-3) \times (2+1)}) \\
 23626 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -((5^4)/(3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 23627 &:= (((98 - 7) \times (65 \times 4)) + (-32)) - (1) \\
 23628 &:= (((-98 - (76 + 5)) \times 4) \times -((32 + 1))) \\
 23629 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 23630 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (((4^3) \times 2) - 1)))) \\
 23631 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
 23632 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 23633 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 + (3^2))) - 1) \\
 23634 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1))))) \\
 23635 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 + (3^2))) + 1) \\
 23636 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 76) \times -(((5^4) - 3)/(2 \times 1))) \\
 23637 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) - 1) \\
 23638 &:= (((-((9 \times 876)) + 5) \times -((4 - (3 - 2)))) + (1)) \\
 23639 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + (6^5 + 4^3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 23640 &:= ((-(-9) + ((876 \times (5 + 4)) \times 3)) - 21) \\
 23641 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) + 5) \times -4) - (3^{2+1})) \\
 23642 &:= ((-(((98 + 7) \times 65) \times 4)) - (-3)) + (-21)) \\
 23643 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times 4) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\
 23644 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 23645 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 23646 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 23647 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
 23648 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) - (5^4)) \times -(32 \times 1)) \\
 23649 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 23650 &:= ((-98 + ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2}))) \times -1) \\
 23651 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times 4)) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\
 23652 &:= (((9 \times (8 - 7)) \times 6) \times (5 + ((432 + 1)))) \\
 23653 &:= (98 - 7) \times 65 \times 4 - 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 23654 &:= (98 - 7) \times 65 \times 4 - 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 23655 &:= (98 - 7) \times 65 \times 4 - 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 23656 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) \times -1) \\
 23657 &:= ((((-98 - 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 23658 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23659 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times 4) - (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23660 &:= ((1 + (2 \times 3)) \times -((-4 \times (56 + 789)))) \\ 23661 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 + 4) - (((5 \times 6) \times 789)))) \\ 23662 &:= (((-1 + (2 - 3)) \times 4) + ((5 \times 6) \times 789)) \\ 23663 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 23664 &:= ((1 + 23) \times (((45 + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 23665 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + 6))) - (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 23666 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 - 4)) - (5 \times (-6 \times 789))) \\ 23667 &:= (-((1 \times ((2 - 3) + 4))) - (-5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23668 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times 678) - 9))) \\ 23669 &:= (-((1^{234}) + (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23670 &:= ((1^{234}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23671 &:= ((1^{234}) + (5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23672 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 78) / 9))) \\ 23673 &:= ((1 \times ((2 - 3) + 4)) - (-5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23674 &:= (1 + (((2 - 3) + 4) - (-5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23675 &:= ((1 \times (-((2 - 3) + 4)) + (5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23676 &:= (1 + ((-((2 - 3) + 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23677 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 23678 &:= (((12/3) + 4) - (5 \times (-6 \times 789))) \\ 23679 &:= (-(-1) \times (2 + ((3 + 4) + ((5 \times 6) \times 789)))) \\ 23680 &:= (-(-1) + (2 + ((3 + 4) + ((5 \times 6) \times 789)))) \\ 23681 &:= (((12 + 3) - 4) - (-5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23682 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - 4)) - (5 \times (-6 \times 789))) \\ 23683 &:= (((-12) - ((3 - 4))) - (5 \times (-6 \times 789))) \\ 23684 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) - ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 23685 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (-3 \times 4)) - (-5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23686 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23687 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3 + 4) \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 23688 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times -(6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 23689 &:= ((12 + 3) + (4 - (-5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23690 &:= (((1 + 23) - 4) + ((-5 \times 6) \times -(789))) \\ 23691 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (67 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 23692 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (-67 - ((8 \times 9)))) \\ 23693 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 23694 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 23695 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + 4) \times (-5 - (6 \times 789)) \\ 23696 &:= (-1 - (-((23 + 4) - (((5 \times 6) \times 789)))) \\ 23697 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times ((-4^5) - 6)) - 7) \times (8 - 9) \\ 23698 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) + (7 - (8 - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23659 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 23660 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) + 4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 23661 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\ 23662 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) + 5) \times -4) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 23663 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 65) \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 23664 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23665 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 65) \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) + 1) \\ 23666 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) + 5) \times -4) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 23667 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) / 5) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\ 23668 &:= (((-98 + 7) - 6) \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\ 23669 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 23670 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23671 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 23672 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23673 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 23674 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23675 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23676 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 23677 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) + 5) \times -4) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23678 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) + 5) \times -4) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 23679 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times (7 + 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23680 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 76) \times 5) \times -((4^3) / (2 \times 1))) \\ 23681 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) - 2)) + 1))) \\ 23682 &:= (((-9) + ((876 \times (5 + 4)) \times 3)) + 21) \\ 23683 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\ 23684 &:= (((987 \times 6) - (5 - 4)) \times ((3 + (2 - 1)))) \\ 23685 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\ 23686 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) - 2 \times 1 \\ 23687 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) - 2 + 1 \\ 23688 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (6 + 5 + 4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23689 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) + 2 - 1 \\ 23690 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) + 2 \times 1 \\ 23691 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\ 23692 &:= (((-987 \times 6) - (5 - 4)) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 23693 &:= (((98 - 7) \times (65 \times 4)) - (-32)) + (1) \\ 23694 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 23695 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23696 &:= ((98 - ((765 \times 4))) \times -((3^2) + (1))) \\ 23697 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 \times 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23698 &:= (9 + 8) \times (-7 \times 65 + 43^2 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23699 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))))) \\ 23700 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 23701 &:= (-(((1 + 2) - 34)) + ((5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23702 &:= ((12 \times 3) - (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23703 &:= (((1 - 2) + 34) + (-5 \times (-6 \times 789))) \\ 23704 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 - (7 - 8)))) - 9) \\ 23705 &:= (-1 + (2 - (-34) - (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23706 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 23707 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) - (-5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23708 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) - (45 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 23709 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (3 + (45 \times (-((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 23710 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 23711 &:= -(((12/3) + (45 \times (-((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 23712 &:= ((12 \times -(34)) - ((-5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 23713 &:= ((-1 - (-23 \times ((4^5) + 6))) + (7 - (-8 - 9))) \\ 23714 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) + (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 23715 &:= (((1^{23}) \times 45) \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 23716 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (-((4^5) - ((-6 \times (-7 + 8)) \times -9))) \\ 23717 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + (45 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 23718 &:= -(((1 + 2) - (((-3 - 4) \times 5) \times -(678) - 9))) \\ 23719 &:= ((12/3) - (45 \times (-((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 23720 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times ((5 \times 6) - (7 \times 89))) \\ 23721 &:= ((1 \times (2 \times 3)) + (45 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 23722 &:= -((1 - ((2^3) + (45 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 23723 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) + (45 \times ((67 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 23724 &:= (-12 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)))) \\ 23725 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) \times 45) + 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 23726 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 23727 &:= (((1 - 2) + 34) \times (5 - (-6 \times (-7 \times -(8 + 9)))) \\ 23728 &:= ((1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 23729 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 - 4!) \times 5 \times (6 - 7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 23730 &:= (((12 + 3) \times 4) - (-5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23731 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - (4 + 5 + 6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 23732 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3! - 4 - 5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 23733 &:= (12 - (((3 + 4) \times (5 \times -(678))) + 9)) \\ 23734 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!}) \times (4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 23735 &:= (-1 - (23 \times -(((4^5) + (-((6 - (78)) / 9)))) \\ 23736 &:= 1 \times 23 \times (4^5 - (6 - 7)^8 + 9) \\ 23737 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 23738 &:= (-((1 - 23)) \times (456 + (7 \times 89))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23699 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 23700 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 23701 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 2)))) + 1) \\ 23702 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) - 5) \times -4) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 23703 &:= (((((987 \times 6) + 5) \times 4) + (3 \times -2)) - (-1)) \\ 23704 &:= ((-(((987 \times 6) + 5) \times -4)) - 3) + (-((2 - 1))) \\ 23705 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\ 23706 &:= ((-(((987 \times 6) + 5) \times -4)) - 3) - (-((2 - 1))) \\ 23707 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times -7) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))))^2 \times 1)) \\ 23708 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times -7) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))))^2 + 1)) \\ 23709 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23710 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) - 1) \\ 23711 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\ 23712 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23713 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times -(6 - (5 \times ((4^3) - 2)))) + 1) \\ 23714 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times 6) + 5) \times ((4 + 3) - 2)) - 1) \\ 23715 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 76)) + (-5 - 4)) \times -((32 - 1))) \\ 23716 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + (7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2 \times 1) \\ 23717 &:= ((((-9 \times -(8 + (7 + 6))) - (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2 + 1) \\ 23718 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 23719 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23720 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23721 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23722 &:= (((98 - (-7 \times ((6 - (-5 - 4))^3))) - 2) + (1)) \\ 23723 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times (43 + 2)) - 1)) \\ 23724 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 23725 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times -7) + (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))))^2)) \times -1) \\ 23726 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) - 5) \times -4) - (3 - 21)) \\ 23727 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(((4^3) / 2) + 1)) \\ 23728 &:= (-9 + 8! / 7 + 6 - 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 23729 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times ((6 \times (5 - 43)) + 2)) - 1) \\ 23730 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23731 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -(((76 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 23732 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6^5)) \times -(4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 23733 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6^5)) \times -((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23734 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6^5)) \times -(4 - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 23735 &:= (((-9 \times ((87 \times 6) + 5)) - 4) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 23736 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23737 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) \times -1) \\ 23738 &:= (98 + ((7 \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2)) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23739 &:= ((-12 + (3^4)) - (5 \times -((6 \times 789)))) \\ 23740 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 23741 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (((-3 - 4) \times 5) \times -(678)) + 9) \\ 23742 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times -9 \\ 23743 &:= (1 - ((2 - (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 23744 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 23745 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -(((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 23746 &:= (1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 23747 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 23748 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) + ((5 \times 6) \times 789))) \\ 23749 &:= (((-1 + (2^3)) \times (4 + (5 \times 678))) - 9) \\ 23750 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times (78 + 9))) \\ 23751 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)))))) - 9 \\ 23752 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times (78 + 9))) \\ 23753 &:= ((1 \times (2 + (3^4))) - ((5 \times -6) \times 789)) \\ 23754 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + 6))) - (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 23755 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 23756 &:= 1 + 23 \times (4^5 + 6) + 7 \times 8 + 9 \\ 23757 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 23758 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 23759 &:= 1 \times 23 \times (4^5 + (6 - 7)^8 \times 9) \\ 23760 &:= (((12 + 3) \times (-(-45) - 67)) \times (-8 \times 9)) \\ 23761 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 23762 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -4) + ((5 \times 6) \times 789)) \\ 23763 &:= (((-12/3) - ((45 \times 6) - 7)) \times -(89)) \\ 23764 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 34) - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\ 23765 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - ((5 \times 678) + 9))) \\ 23766 &:= (-(((1 + 23) \times -4)) - ((-5 \times 6) \times 789)) \\ 23767 &:= (((-1 + (2^3)) \times (4 + (5 \times 678))) + 9) \\ 23768 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\ 23769 &:= (((1 - 2) + (34 \times -5)) \times -((67 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23770 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 789)))) \\ 23771 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + 6))) - (7 - 89)) \\ 23772 &:= (((1 + 2) \times 34) + (5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23773 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 23774 &:= (1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 23775 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\ 23776 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) \\ 23777 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times -((-4^5) - 6)) + (78 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23739 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 76) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23740 &:= (987 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 + 32 \times 1 \\ 23741 &:= ((((((987 \times 6) + 5) \times 4) - (-32)) + 1)) \\ 23742 &:= ((9 \times ((-87 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4 - 32))) \times (-1)) \\ 23743 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23744 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23745 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23746 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 23747 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23748 &:= -9 + (-87 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\ 23749 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((76 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 23750 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 23751 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 \times 3)^2 \times 1))) \\ 23752 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 23753 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 - (5 \times (43 \times 2)))))) \times -1) \\ 23754 &:= ((-9 + (8 - ((-76 + 5) - 4))) \times 321) \\ 23755 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((76 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23756 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6 \times 5!) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 23757 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23758 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) + 5) \times -43) - 21) \\ 23759 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 23760 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times -(((7 + 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1))) \\ 23761 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1) \\ 23762 &:= ((-9 \times 87) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\ 23763 &:= ((-9 \times 87) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 23764 &:= (((((-98 + 7) - 6) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 23765 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - 6) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 23766 &:= (((9 \times 876) - (5 - 43)) \times ((2 + 1))) \\ 23767 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times 54) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 23768 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 76 - (54 + 3)^2) - 1 \\ 23769 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 76 - (54 + 3)^2 \times 1) \\ 23770 &:= -9 \times (8 \times 76 - (54 + 3)^2) + 1 \\ 23771 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((76 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23772 &:= ((-98/7) \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 23773 &:= ((((-9 \times (876 + 5)) + 4) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23774 &:= ((((-9 \times (876 + 5)) + 4) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 23775 &:= (((9 \times (8 - 7)) + 6) \times ((-5 \times (4 - 321)))) \\ 23776 &:= (-98 - (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23777 &:= 9 \times (87 \times 6 \times 5 + 4^3/2) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$23778 := 1 \times 2 \times (-3 + 4 \times (-5 + 6 \times 7 \times 8)) \times 9$$

$$23779 := 1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 \times (5 - 6 \times 7 \times 8)) \times 9$$

$$23780 := ((1 \times (234 + 56)) \times -((7 - 89)))$$

$$23781 := (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times (7 + 8))/9))))$$

$$23782 := ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + ((6 \times (7 + 8))/9)))$$

$$23783 := (1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times (7 + 8))/9))))$$

$$23784 := (-12 \times (-3 + (-((45 \times 6) \times 7)) - 89)))$$

$$23785 := ((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))))$$

$$23786 := (-1 - (((2 + 3) + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9))$$

$$23787 := (((-1 - 2) + (-34) - ((5 \times 67) \times 8)) \times 9)$$

$$23788 := (1 + (((2 + 3) + ((-4 + (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times -9))$$

$$23789 := -((-123) + (4 + (5 \times (6 \times -(789))))))$$

$$23790 := (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times -6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))$$

$$23791 := (((((-123 \times 4) - 5) \times 6) + 7) \times 8) - 9$$

$$23792 := ((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times 678) + 9)))$$

$$23793 := (-12 - ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9))$$

$$23794 := ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) \times ((5 \times 678) + 9)))$$

$$23795 := (-1 - (((2^3) - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 78)) \times 9))$$

$$23796 := ((((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) + 8) \times -9)$$

$$23797 := (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (5 \times (6 \times 789))))$$

$$23798 := ((1 \times (2^{3+4})) + (5 \times (-6 \times -(789))))$$

$$23799 := (((1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (45 + 6))) \times -78) + 9)$$

$$23800 := (((((12/3)^4) - (56)) \times 7) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$23801 := (1 + (2 \times (34 \times (5 + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))))$$

$$23802 := ((-1 - 2) - ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9))$$

$$23803 := (-1 \times (2 + ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9)))$$

$$23804 := (-1 + (23 \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (78 - 9))))$$

$$23805 := ((1 \times -23) \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (-78 + 9)))$$

$$23806 := ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9))$$

$$23807 := (-1 \times -2 - ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9))$$

$$23808 := (-12 \times -(((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7) \times 8/9)$$

$$23809 := (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) + (7 \times (8 + 9)))$$

$$23810 := ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times (7 \times 89))))$$

$$23811 := ((-1 - 2) - ((34 - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))$$

$$23812 := (-1 \times (2 + ((34 - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)))$$

$$23813 := (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 78)) \times 9))$$

$$23814 := ((12 \times (3 \times 4)) - (5 \times (-6 \times 789)))$$

$$23815 := (((-1 - ((234 - 5) \times (6 + 7))) \times -8) - 9)$$

$$23816 := ((12/3) \times ((-4 - 5) + (67 \times 89)))$$

$$23817 := ((12 - (-3 \times (456 + 7))) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$23778 := 9 \times (87 \times 6 \times 5 + 4^3/2 \times 1)$$

$$23779 := 9 \times (87 \times 6 \times 5 + 4^3/2) + 1$$

$$23780 := ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) + 5) \times -43) + (2 - 1))$$

$$23781 := ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$23782 := ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) \times (43 + (2 + 1))))$$

$$23783 := ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times 54) - 3) \times 2 + 1))$$

$$23784 := (((-9 \times 8) + (((7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4))^3)) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$23785 := ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1)))$$

$$23786 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 54)))) - (3 + 2)) - 1)$$

$$23787 := ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$23788 := (((-9 + 8) \times 76) \times -(((5^4) + 3)/2) - 1))$$

$$23789 := ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) + 2))) - 1)$$

$$23790 := ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + (2 - 1)))$$

$$23791 := (-9 - ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) - 1)))$$

$$23792 := ((-9 \times 8) + (76 \times (((5^4) + 3)/(2 \times 1))))$$

$$23793 := ((((-9 \times 876) - 54) \times -3) + (-21))$$

$$23794 := -9 + (8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1$$

$$23795 := (-9 - (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times ((5 + (4^3))^2)) + 1))$$

$$23796 := -9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 - 2 - 1$$

$$23797 := -9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$23798 := -9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 - 2 + 1$$

$$23799 := ((-98 \times -(7 \times 6)) + (((5 + 4) \times 3)^{2+1}))$$

$$23800 := -9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 + 2 - 1$$

$$23801 := -9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 + 2 \times 1$$

$$23802 := (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6) \times (5 + 4^3) - 2 - 1$$

$$23803 := (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6) \times (5 + 4^3) - 2 \times 1$$

$$23804 := (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6) \times (5 + 4^3) - 2 + 1$$

$$23805 := (-(((98 \times -((-76 - 5))) - 4) \times 3)) + (-21))$$

$$23806 := (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6) \times (5 + 4^3) + 2 - 1$$

$$23807 := (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6) \times (5 + 4^3) + 2 \times 1$$

$$23808 := (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 6) \times (5 + 4^3) + 2 + 1$$

$$23809 := (((((-9 \times 8) - 76) \times 5) - 4) \times -32) + 1)$$

$$23810 := (98 - (76 \times ((5 + 4) - 32)))$$

$$23811 := (9 \times (-8 + 7 - 6) + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$23812 := ((-98 \times -(((7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1))$$

$$23813 := 98 \times (76 + 5) \times (4 - 3 + 2) - 1$$

$$23814 := 98 \times (76 + 5) \times (4 - 3 + 2 \times 1)$$

$$23815 := 9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$23816 := 9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 - 2 + 1$$

$$23817 := 9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6^5 - 4) \times 3 - 2 - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23818 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times 6)) - 789) \\
 23819 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5! - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 23820 &:= (-(((-1 - 23) \times (4^5))) + ((6 + 78) \times -9)) \\
 23821 &:= ((-1 + (2^3)) \times ((4 + (5 \times 678)) + 9)) \\
 23822 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) - (45 \times (67 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 23823 &:= (((-((1 - (2 - 34))) - ((5 \times 67) \times 8)) \times 9) \\
 23824 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 23825 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 + (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 23826 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 + (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 23827 &:= (((1 \times -2) - 3) + (4 \times (-5 + (67 \times 89)))) \\
 23828 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9))) \\
 23829 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (34 \times 5)) \times -(6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 23830 &:= (((-12 - 345) \times -(67)) - (89)) \\
 23831 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 23832 &:= (((1 - 2) + (345 - 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 23833 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 23834 &:= ((-1 - (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times (5 + 6)) - 7)) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 23835 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 23836 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\
 23837 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 23838 &:= -((((12/3) + (45 \times 6)) \times -((78 + 9)))) \\
 23839 &:= ((-1 + (2^3)) - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 23840 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 23841 &:= ((12 - 3) + (-4 \times (5 - (67 \times 89)))) \\
 23842 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 78)) \times 9)) \\
 23843 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6)) - (78 \times 9)) \\
 23844 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) - (78 \times 9)) \\
 23845 &:= ((1 \times -23) - (-((4 + (5 \times 6))) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 23846 &:= (12 + (34 \times ((5 - 6) + (78 \times 9)))) \\
 23847 &:= (12 + (3 + (-4 \times (5 - (67 \times 89)))) \\
 23848 &:= ((-1 - 23) - (4 \times (-5 - (67 \times 89)))) \\
 23849 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) + (8 - 9))) \\
 23850 &:= ((1 \times ((2 + 3) + 45)) \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)) \\
 23851 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 - ((45 - 6) \times 7))) \times -(89))) \\
 23852 &:= (((((1 + 23) - 4)/5) \times 67) \times 89) \\
 23853 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 - (4 \times ((5 - 67) \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 23854 &:= ((-1 + 23) - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 23855 &:= ((-1 - (((2^3) \times 45) + 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 23856 &:= (-12 \times -((345 \times 6) - (7 - 89))) \\
 23857 &:= ((-12 - 3) - (-4 \times (5 + (67 \times 89))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23818 &:= 9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 + 2 - 1 \\
 23819 &:= 9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 23820 &:= 9 + (-8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 23821 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 23822 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 23823 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 23824 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + ((6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 23825 &:= ((((-9 \times (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4)) + 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 23826 &:= (((-9 \times (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4)) + 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 23827 &:= ((((-9 \times (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4)) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 23828 &:= (((((-98 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) - 4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 23829 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) - (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23830 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times 54)))) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 23831 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times -(7 + ((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2))) - 1) \\
 23832 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 23833 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times -(7 + ((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2))) + 1) \\
 23834 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) \times ((4^3) \times 2)) + 1))) \\
 23835 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + (4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23836 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times 54)))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 23837 &:= ((((-9 \times (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4)) - 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 23838 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 - 7) \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 23839 &:= ((((-9 \times (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4)) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 23840 &:= ((-((-98 - 7))) + 654) \times (-32 \times (-1)) \\
 23841 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times ((6 - (5 - 4))^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23842 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 23843 &:= ((((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 23844 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 23845 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -(5 - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\
 23846 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 23847 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23848 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + ((4^3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
 23849 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((76 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) - 2))) - 1) \\
 23850 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (7 - (6 \times -54))) - ((3 - 21))) \\
 23851 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 23852 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 76) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23853 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 + (6^5 + 4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 23854 &:= ((-98 \times 7) - (6 \times (5 - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 23855 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) \times (-65 + (432 \times (1)))) \\
 23856 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23857 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23858 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 23859 &:= ((1 \times ((2 \times 3) \times -((45 + 6) \times -(78)))) - 9) \\ 23860 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 - ((4 - (5 \times 67) \times 8)) \times 9)) \times 9) \\ 23861 &:= ((1 - (2^3)) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 23862 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -(4^5)) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 23863 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 - ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\ 23864 &:= (12 + ((3 - (4 - 5)) \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 23865 &:= (-((1 - (-2 \times 3))) + (4 \times (5 - (67 \times -(89)))))) \\ 23866 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 23867 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3^4)) - 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 23868 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 23869 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 23870 &:= (-1 - (-(2 - 3) - (-4 \times (-5 - (67 \times 89)))))) \\ 23871 &:= (-((1 + 23)) - (-(45 \times (67 - 8))) \times 9) \\ 23872 &:= ((-1^{23}) \times (4 \times (-5 - (67 \times 89)))) \\ 23873 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9)))))) \\ 23874 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\ 23875 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times (4 + ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 23876 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) - ((4 - (5 \times 67) \times 8)) \times 9)) \times 9) \\ 23877 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))))))) \times 9) \\ 23878 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 23879 &:= (-1 - ((23 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 23880 &:= (12 - ((-34) \times (-5 + 6)) \times (78 \times 9)) \\ 23881 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -3) + (4 \times (5 + (67 \times 89)))) \\ 23882 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 23883 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5 \times (67 - 8) - 9 \\ 23884 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5 \times (67 - 8) - 9 \\ 23885 &:= 1 - 2 + 3^4 \times 5 \times (67 - 8) - 9 \\ 23886 &:= (1 - 23 - 4 + 5 \times 67 \times 8) \times 9 \\ 23887 &:= 1^2 + 3^4 \times 5 \times (67 - 8) - 9 \\ 23888 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5 \times (67 - 8) - 9 \\ 23889 &:= 1 + 2 + 3^4 \times 5 \times (67 - 8) - 9 \\ 23890 &:= ((-1 + 23) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 23891 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 23892 &:= (-12 - (((3^4) \times 5) \times -((67 - 8))) - 9) \\ 23893 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))))) \\ 23894 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (3 - ((45 \times (67 - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 23895 &:= ((12 - 3) \times (-(-45)) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 23896 &:= (-((-1 - 23)) - (4 \times (-5 - (67 \times 89)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23858 &:= (((((-9 - (87 \times 6)) \times 5) + 4) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\ 23859 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23860 &:= ((-98 \times 7) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 23861 &:= ((-98 \times 7) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\ 23862 &:= (((-98 + 7) - 6) \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\ 23863 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23864 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) - 1) \\ 23865 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23866 &:= (((((-98 + 7) + 6) \times -5) \times -43) + (((2 - 1)))) \\ 23867 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\ 23868 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (((-7 - 6) \times 54) \times (-3 + ((2 - 1)))))) \\ 23869 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times -((4^3) - 2)) - 1) \\ 23870 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times -((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 23871 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\ 23872 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - (6 \times ((5^4) \times 3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 23873 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23874 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 23875 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23876 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 54))) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 23877 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 23878 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (6 \times 54))) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 23879 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + 43)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23880 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 23881 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3)/(2 \times 1)))) \\ 23882 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3/2 + 1 \\ 23883 &:= ((((-((9 \times 8) \times 7)) + 6) \times (-5 - 43)) - 21)) \\ 23884 &:= ((-9 \times -876) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 23885 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 23886 &:= (((9 \times -((876 + 5) + 4))) + 3) \times -((2 + (1)))) \\ 23887 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\ 23888 &:= -9 + 8! - 7 + (6 - 5!) \times 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 23889 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23890 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!) - 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 23891 &:= (((-98 + 7) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23892 &:= (((98 - 76) \times 543) \times ((2 \times 1))) \\ 23893 &:= ((-9 \times -((876 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 23894 &:= (9 + 87 \times 6) \times (54 - 3^2) - 1 \\ 23895 &:= (9 + 87 \times 6) \times (54 - 3^2) \times 1 \\ 23896 &:= (9 + 87 \times 6) \times (54 - 3^2) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23897 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))))) \\ 23898 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times 6) - (78 \times 9)) \\ 23899 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (34 \times ((5 - 6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 23900 &:= -(((1 - (2 \times 3)) - ((45) \times (-((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 23901 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times 3) + ((45 \times (67 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 23902 &:= ((1 + (2 \times 3)) + ((45 \times (67 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 23903 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (((5 + 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 23904 &:= ((1 \times 234) - ((5 \times 6) \times -(789))) \\ 23905 &:= ((1 + 2) - (34 \times ((5 - 6) - (-78) \times -9))) \\ 23906 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 + 45) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 23907 &:= ((12 + (3^{4+5})) + ((6 \times 78) \times 9)) \\ 23908 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3^4) + 5) \times (67 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 23909 &:= 1 + 2 \times (3^4 + 5) \times (67 + 8 \times 9) \\ 23910 &:= (12 - (-3 + ((-45) \times (67 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 23911 &:= (((-12 - 34) \times -(5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9) \\ 23912 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6 \times 78)) \times 9)) \\ 23913 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (-((4^5) - 67)) - 89) \\ 23914 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 23915 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) \times (4 - ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 23916 &:= (12 + ((345 - (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 23917 &:= (-((1 - 23)) - (45 \times ((-67) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 23918 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times (4 + 5)) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 23919 &:= ((1 + 23) - (-((45 \times (67 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 23920 &:= ((1 \times -23) \times ((4 \times -5) \times ((6 \times 78)/9))) \\ 23921 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - ((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 23922 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times 45) \times (-67) + 8) - 9)) \\ 23923 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3 \times (4^5))/6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 23924 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3 + (45 \times (67 - 8))) \times 9)) \\ 23925 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 - (45 \times (-67) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 23926 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 23927 &:= (-1 \times (((23 - (45 \times 67)) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 23928 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 23929 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5)) \times -6) - (7 \times 89)) \\ 23930 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + 67)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 23931 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9) \\ 23932 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times ((4 \times 5) + (67 \times 89))) \\ 23933 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 \times 67) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 23934 &:= (12 + ((3 + (45 \times (67 - 8))) \times 9)) \\ 23935 &:= (((1 - 23) - (-45) \times 67) \times 8) - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23897 &:= ((-9 \times -((876 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23898 &:= ((-9 - (87 + 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23899 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 + (6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\ 23900 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (43^2 \times 1)))) \\ 23901 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23902 &:= (-98 + (((7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23903 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23904 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4 + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 23905 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) + (5^4) - 3)/2)) + 1) \\ 23906 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 + 43)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 23907 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 76)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23908 &:= -98 + 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3 / 2 - 1 \\ 23909 &:= -98 + 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3 / 2 \times 1 \\ 23910 &:= -9 - 87 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\ 23911 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 - 6) - (5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\ 23912 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 23913 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2 \times 1))) \\ 23914 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 23915 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23916 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23917 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23918 &:= (9 \times (-8 \times 7 + 6!) + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 23919 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23920 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - ((7 - 6)^5)^4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 23921 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7^{(6-5) \times 4})) \times ((3^2) + 1))) \\ 23922 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times 65) - 4))) \times ((-3 \times 2) \times (-1))) \\ 23923 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 76) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23924 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 76) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23925 &:= (9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\ 23926 &:= ((-98/7) \times (6 - (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\ 23927 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\ 23928 &:= (-9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23929 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23930 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 + 5))) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})) \\ 23931 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 - 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 23932 &:= (((-9 \times 87) + (6 + 5)) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 23933 &:= ((-98 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1)) \\ 23934 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) - 1) \\ 23935 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + (-6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$23936 := (-((-1 \times 2) \times 34)) \times ((5 \times 67) + (8 + 9))$$

$$23937 := (((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (45 + 6)))) \times -78) - 9)$$

$$23938 := (1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((56 \times 7) - 89)))$$

$$23939 := ((-1 - (-23 \times (((4^5) + 6) + 7))) + 89)$$

$$23940 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))$$

$$23941 := ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))$$

$$23942 := (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))))$$

$$23943 := ((((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times 8) - 9)$$

$$23944 := (-1 - (((23 - (45 \times 67)) \times 8) - 9))$$

$$23945 := (((1 \times 23) - (45 \times 67)) \times -8) + 9$$

$$23946 := (1 - (((23 - (45 \times 67)) \times 8) - 9))$$

$$23947 := (1 + 23) \times 4^5 - 6 - 7 \times 89$$

$$23948 := (-1 - (((23 - 4) - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))$$

$$23949 := ((((-1 - (((2 \times 34) - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) - 8) \times -9)$$

$$23950 := (-1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times 8) + 9))$$

$$23951 := ((((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times 8) - 9)$$

$$23952 := -((-12 \times (3 + (((4 \times (-5 + 67)) \times 8) + 9))))$$

$$23953 := (((12/3) \times ((4^5) \times 6)) + (-7 \times 89))$$

$$23954 := (((1^2) - ((-3^4) \times -5)) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))$$

$$23955 := -12 + 3^4 \times (-5 + 6 \times 7) \times 8 - 9$$

$$23956 := 1 + 2 - 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8) + 9$$

$$23957 := (-1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$23958 := (((1 - 23) + (4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8)))) \times 9)$$

$$23959 := ((((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times -8) - 9)$$

$$23960 := ((-1 + 2^3)^4 - 5) \times 6 \times (7 + 8) / 9$$

$$23961 := (1 + 2 \times 3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) \times 78 - 9)$$

$$23962 := (1 + 2 + 3!) \times 4! - 5 + (6! + 7 + 8) \times 9$$

$$23963 := ((((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (67 - 8)) + 9)$$

$$23964 := ((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))$$

$$23965 := ((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))$$

$$23966 := ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 - (7 + (8 + 9))))$$

$$23967 := ((-1 - ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) \times 9)$$

$$23968 := ((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))$$

$$23969 := (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) / 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))$$

$$23970 := (((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) + 5)) \times -(6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))$$

$$23971 := ((-1 + 2) + (34 \times (5 \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))))$$

$$23972 := (-1 \times -(2 + (34 \times (5 \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))))$$

$$23973 := -12 + 3^4 \times (-5 + 6 \times 7) \times 8 + 9$$

$$23974 := ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4 + 5) \times (6! + 7) - 8 - 9$$

$$23936 := (-9 + (-8 + 765)) \times 4 \times (3^2 - 1)$$

$$23937 := (9 \times (8 - 7) - 6) \times ((5 \times 4)^3 - 21)$$

$$23938 := ((-9 \times 8) + ((7^{(6-5)^4}) \times ((3^2) + 1)))$$

$$23939 := (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23940 := (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23941 := (((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23942 := ((-9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - ((43^2) - 1))))$$

$$23943 := (((-98 - 7) \times (6 \times (5 - 43))) + (2 + 1))$$

$$23944 := ((-9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23945 := (9 + (8 \times (76 + (54^{3-2+1}))))$$

$$23946 := (((-9 - ((8 + 7) - 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$23947 := (((-9 + 8) - 76) \times -(((5^4) - 3) / (2 \times 1)))$$

$$23948 := ((((-9 + 8) - 76) \times -(((5^4) - 3) / 2)) + 1)$$

$$23949 := (((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - 5)) + 4) \times -(3^{2+1}))$$

$$23950 := ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) - 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)$$

$$23951 := (((-987 - (6 + 5)) \times -(4 \times (3 \times 2))) - 1)$$

$$23952 := ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23953 := ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23954 := ((((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times 4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))$$

$$23955 := ((-9 \times -(8 - (7 + 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23956 := ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -((5 \times 43) - (2 + 1)))$$

$$23957 := -9 + 8 - 7 \times 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$23958 := ((((-9 + 8) - (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$23959 := 9 - 8 - 7 \times 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1)$$

$$23960 := ((-9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23961 := (9 - 8) \times (-7 - 6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$23962 := ((-98 - (76 \times (((5^4) + 3) / 2))) \times -1)$$

$$23963 := ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) - 1)$$

$$23964 := ((((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1))$$

$$23965 := ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) + 1)$$

$$23966 := ((((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times 4)) + 3) \times (2 \times 1))$$

$$23967 := ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23968 := ((-98/7) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23969 := (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times 54) + 3) \times 2) - 1)$$

$$23970 := ((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23971 := (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times 54) + 3) \times 2) + 1)$$

$$23972 := ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$23973 := ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - (6 - (5 + 4)))^3))) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$23974 := -9 + 8 - 7 + (-6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23975 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 23976 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) + ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9) \\
 23977 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) \times -8) + 9 \\
 23978 &:= (((1 + 2)^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9)) \\
 23979 &:= 12 + 3^4 \times (-5 + 6 \times 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 23980 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -(((4^5) + (67 + 8)) - 9)) \\
 23981 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 23982 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 23983 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 23984 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times ((45 \times 67) - (8 + 9))) \\
 23985 &:= (-123) \times ((-4 - (56)) + (-((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 23986 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 23987 &:= (((12 \times (3 \times -((45 - 6)))) - 7) \times (-8 - 9)) \\
 23988 &:= -12 + 3 \times (4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9} \\
 23989 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\
 23990 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\
 23991 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3 + (4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9}) \\
 23992 &:= (-1 \times ((2^{3+4}) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 23993 &:= ((-123) - 4) - (5 \times (67 \times (-8 \times 9))) \\
 23994 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 4)) \times (((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 23995 &:= (123 + (4 \times (5 + (67 \times 89)))) \\
 23996 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! \times 4 + 5!)) \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 23997 &:= -(1 + 2) + 3 \times (4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9} \\
 23998 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9} \\
 23999 &:= 1 - 2 + 3 \times (4 \times 5)^{-6 + (-7+8) \times 9} \\
 24000 &:= (((-1 + 23)) \times (4 \times 5)) \times (-67) - (-8 - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24001 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (-((4^5) - 67)) - (-8 + 9)) \\
 24002 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (-((4^5) - 67)) \times (-8 + 9)) \\
 24003 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4 - 5})) \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 24004 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times -(8 + 9) \\
 24005 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (67 - 8))) - 9) \\
 24006 &:= (-123 + ((45 \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 24007 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - 67) \times 8) - 9 \\
 24008 &:= (((-12 - 345) \times -67) + 89) \\
 24009 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + (4 \times 5)^{6 \times (7-8)+9}); \\
 24010 &:= (((-1 + (2^3))^4) \times ((5 - 6) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 24011 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (4 \times (((5 \times 6) + (7 - 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 24012 &:= (((1 + 23) + (4 \times (5 - 678))) \times -9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23975 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23976 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 23977 &:= ((-9 \times -8) \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1 \\
 23978 &:= (((-98 + 76) + ((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23979 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 + 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 23980 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7 - 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23981 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3))/2)) - 1) \\
 23982 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) - 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23983 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23984 &:= ((-9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23985 &:= (-9 \times -((8 - (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)/(2 + 1))) \\
 23986 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 + 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23987 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23988 &:= (((-9 - (8 - (7 + 6))) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 23989 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3 / 2 - 1 \\
 23990 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + (-6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 23991 &:= -9 + (8 + 7 + 6 - 5 + 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\
 23992 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7)^6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 23993 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 23994 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23995 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3 / 2 + 1 \\
 23996 &:= (((-9 - (8 - (7 + 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 23997 &:= (9 - 8) \times (-7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 23998 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\
 23999 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\
 24000 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4))))^3) \times (2 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24001 &:= 98 \times 7 + (6^5 - 4) \times 3 - 2 + 1 \\
 24002 &:= (-9 - (-(((87 \times 6) \times ((5 + 43) - 2))) + (1))) \\
 24003 &:= ((-9 + (((87 \times 6) \times ((5 + 43) - 2)) \times 1))) \\
 24004 &:= (-9 - (-(((87 \times 6) \times ((5 + 43) - 2))) - (1))) \\
 24005 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + ((((-6^5) - 4) \times -3) - 21))) \\
 24006 &:= (9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 24007 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3 / 2 + 1 \\
 24008 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24009 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times -(((5 \times 4)^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 24010 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\
 24011 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24012 &:= ((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24013 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) & 24013 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -(7 + 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24014 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - (((3 \times 4) - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) & 24014 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\
 24015 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 78 - 9 & 24015 &:= 9 \times (8 - 7) + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\
 24016 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (67 - 8)) + 9)) & 24016 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\
 24017 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3 \times (4+5-6)})) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) & 24017 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 - 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24018 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -(4^5)) - ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) & 24018 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) - 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24019 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) - 8)) + 9) & 24019 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)/2)) + 1) \\
 24020 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) - (5 - 6)) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) & 24020 &:= (((98/7) + 6) + (((-5 \times 4)^3) \times (-2 - (1)))) \\
 24021 &:= -(((1 \times (23 - (4 \times -((5 - 678)))))) \times 9)) & 24021 &:= (-(-9) + (((87 \times 6) \times ((5 + 43) - 2)) \times 1)) \\
 24022 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(67 - 8)) + 9) & 24022 &:= (-(-9) + (((87 \times 6) \times ((5 + 43) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 24023 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - 67)) \times -8) - 9) & 24023 &:= (((-98 \times -7) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24024 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times 4)) \times (-5 + (-67) \times (8 + 9))) & 24024 &:= ((-9 + 87) \times ((6 + 5) \times ((4 + (3 + 21)))))) \\
 24025 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 + 8)))))) - 9) & 24025 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24026 &:= (((1 \times 23) - (-45) \times 6) \times (-7 + (89))) & 24026 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 + (6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 24027 &:= (-12 - ((3^4) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 24027 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - (6 - (5 + 4)))^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24028 &:= (1 \times -((23 \times 4) + (((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 24028 &:= (-98 + (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24029 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times ((3^4) + 5)) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 24029 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24030 &:= ((-1 \times -2) \times ((3 \times 45) \times ((6 - 7) \times -(89)))) & 24030 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - 7)^6) + ((5 \times 4)^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24031 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 24031 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 24032 &:= (1 - (-((-((-2^3) \times 45)) \times 67)) + (89)) & 24032 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 24033 &:= (((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - 67) \times 8) + 9) & 24033 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (((7 + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24034 &:= (((1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - 67) \times 8)) - 9) & 24034 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 - ((5 + 4) \times 3))))^2)) \times -1) \\
 24035 &:= -1 - 2 + (-3!! + 4) \times 5 - 6 + 7! \times (8 + 9) & 24035 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) - 1) \\
 24036 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 24036 &:= (((-9 + (8 + (7 + 6))) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24037 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 24037 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) + 1) \\
 24038 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6)) + 7)) \times (8 + 9)) & 24038 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24039 &:= ((-((1 \times 2)) - ((3 + 4))) \times ((-5 \times 67) \times 8) + 9) & 24039 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 24040 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 24040 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1) \\
 24041 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) & 24041 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24042 &:= (((-1 - 2) - 3) \times (-((4^{5-6+7})) + 89)) & 24042 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\
 24043 &:= (1 - ((-2 \times 3) \times ((4^{5-6+7}) - 89))) & 24043 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\
 24044 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 + (7 + 8)))) + 9) & 24044 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (43^2 \times 1)))) \\
 24045 &:= (((1^2) \times 3) + 4) \times (5 \times (678 + 9)) & 24045 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24046 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 - 4) + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 24046 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) - 1) \\
 24047 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 24047 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24048 &:= ((-(((1 \times 2)^3) \times (45 \times -(67)))) + (8 \times -9)) & 24048 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 + (3^{2+1})))))) \\
 24049 &:= (1 - ((2 + (-3 \times (45 + 67))) \times (8 \times 9))) & 24049 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - 2)) + 1) \\
 24050 &:= ((((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) - (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 24050 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + (((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24051 &:= ((12 - (3^4)) - (-5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 24051 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (((7 - 6) \times (5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24052 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times 34) + (((5 \times 67) \times -8) \times 9))) \\ 24053 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 45)) \times -(67 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 24054 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 24055 &:= (1 \times (-2 - ((-3 + (-4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8)))) \times -9))) \\ 24056 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3 - 4)^5) \times ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) \\ 24057 &:= (((-((1 - 2)) + ((3 \times (4^5) - 67)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 24058 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9) \\ 24059 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - (((3 + 4) - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 24060 &:= (-12 \times -(((345 \times 6) + 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 24061 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) - ((34 + 5) \times (6 + (-7 \times 89)))) \\ 24062 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5))/6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 24063 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3 \times (4+5-6)}) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 24064 &:= 1 \times 2^{3 \times (4+5-6)} \times (7 \times 8 - 9) \\ 24065 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5))/6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 24066 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times (5 - ((6 + 7) \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 24067 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 - 4) + (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 24068 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -(45 - (67 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 24069 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 24070 &:= (((-1 + ((2^3) \times 45)) \times 67) + (8 + 9)) \\ 24071 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) \times 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 24072 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24073 &:= 1 + 2^{3+4+5} \times 6 - 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\ 24074 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24075 &:= (12 - ((34 + 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 24076 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) + ((4 - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 24077 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) + ((4 - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 24078 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4+5})) \times -6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 24079 &:= (1 \times (23456 + (7 \times 89))) \\ 24080 &:= (1 + (23456 + (7 \times 89))) \\ 24081 &:= (-((1 \times (2 + (-345) - 6))) \times (78 - 9)) \\ 24082 &:= (1 - ((2 + (-345) - 6) \times (78 - 9))) \\ 24083 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 34) - (-((5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times -9)))) \\ 24084 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 34) - (-((5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times -9)))) \\ 24085 &:= (((1 - 2) - 34) + ((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 24086 &:= (((1 - 2) \times 34) + ((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 24087 &:= ((-12 - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 24088 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) - ((4 - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 24089 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) - ((4 - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 24090 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24052 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 - 1 \\ 24053 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 \times 1 \\ 24054 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 + 1 \\ 24055 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) - 1))) \\ 24056 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 - 1 \\ 24057 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 \times 1 \\ 24058 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\ 24059 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - (7 + 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24060 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24061 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24062 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 + 6 + 5 \times (4^{3!} + (2 + 1)!!) \\ 24063 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - (7 - 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24064 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 - (5 - (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\ 24065 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24066 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 24067 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4^3))) + (2 - 1)) \\ 24068 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 24069 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (((7 - 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24070 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 - 1 \\ 24071 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 \times 1 \\ 24072 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 - 2 + 1 \\ 24073 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 - 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24074 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 - 1 \\ 24075 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 \times 1 \\ 24076 &:= 9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\ 24077 &:= (((-9 + 87) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) - 1) \\ 24078 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) - 1) \\ 24079 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 24080 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + ((6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3)/2)) + 1)) \\ 24081 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4^{3 \times 2 + 1} \\ 24082 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7^{(6-5) \times 4}) \times ((3^2) + 1))) \\ 24083 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 - 4) \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\ 24084 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 - 4) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\ 24085 &:= 9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6 \times 5 - 4) \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\ 24086 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times (5 - (4 \times (3^2)))) - 1) \\ 24087 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6^5) \times 4)/(3^2)) - 1))) \\ 24088 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times (5 - (4 \times (3^2)))) + 1) \\ 24089 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) + 1))) \\ 24090 &:= (-(((9 \times -8) - 7) + 6)) \times (5 + (4 - (-321))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24091 &:= (((1 - 23) \times (-((4^5) - 67)) + 89) \\
 24092 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 - 4)) - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 24093 &:= (((12 - 3) \times -((4 + (-((5 \times 67)) \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 24094 &:= -12 + 34 \times (-5 + 6 \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
 24095 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times -(((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 24096 &:= ((1 \times ((2 \times 3) \times -4)) - (5 \times ((67 \times -8) \times 9))) \\
 24097 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + ((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 24098 &:= (((-1 - ((2^3) \times 45)) \times -67) - 89) \\
 24099 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24100 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 24101 &:= ((1 \times -((23 - 4))) - ((5 \times (67 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 24102 &:= (((1 - 23) + 4) + ((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 24103 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (34 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 24104 &:= -((1 - (-((-2 - (3456 \times 7))) - 89))) \\
 24105 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 + 4)) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24106 &:= (1 + (-((-2 - (3456 \times 7))) - 89)) \\
 24107 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (34 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 24108 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\
 24109 &:= (((1 - (2^3)) - 4) - (((5 \times 67) \times 8) \times -9)) \\
 24110 &:= ((1 \times (2 - 3)) + (((45 \times 67) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 24111 &:= -1 + 2^3 \times (45 \times 67 + 8 - 9) \\
 24112 &:= 1 \times 2^3 \times (45 \times 67 + 8 - 9) \\
 24113 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24114 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24115 &:= (((-1^{23}) - 4) + (5 \times ((67 \times 8) \times 9))) \\
 24116 &:= (((-1^{23}) \times 4) + (5 \times ((67 \times 8) \times 9))) \\
 24117 &:= (-(((1 + 2) - ((3456 \times 7)))) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 24118 &:= (((1 + 2) - 34) \times ((5 + 6) - 789)) \\
 24119 &:= (1 + (-2 + ((3456 \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24120 &:= ((-1^{234}) \times (-5 \times ((67 \times 8) \times 9))) \\
 24121 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3456 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 24122 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 - 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24123 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24124 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24125 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - (3 + 4)) - (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24126 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 24127 &:= (((-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6))) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 24128 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - 6)) \times 7) / 8) \times 9)) \\
 24129 &:= (((1 + 2) / 3) \times (((45 \times 67) \times 8) + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24091 &:= 98 - 7 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3 / 2 \times 1 \\
 24092 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 76) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 24093 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24094 &:= (-98 + (((-((-76 \times 5)) + 4) \times 3) \times 21)) \\
 24095 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24096 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1))) \\
 24097 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24098 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 - 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24099 &:= ((-9 \times -87) + (((6^5) - 4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 24100 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - ((7 - 6)^5))^4)) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 24101 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24102 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 24103 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + ((7 + ((6 - 5) \times 4)^3))) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 24104 &:= (9 - (((8 - (765 - 4)) \times 32) + 1)) \\
 24105 &:= (((-98 - 7) - (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) \times -1) \\
 24106 &:= (9 - (((8 - (765 - 4)) \times 32) - 1)) \\
 24107 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 - 6) + (5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 24108 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24109 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24110 &:= (((-9 \times -87) + ((6^5) \times (4 - (3 - 2)))) - 1) \\
 24111 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times -7) - ((6 \times (5 + 432)) + (1)))) \\
 24112 &:= ((-9 \times -87) + (((6^5) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\
 24113 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 - 6 + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\
 24114 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24115 &:= -(((((-98 + 7) \times ((65 \times 4) - (-3 - 2))) \times (1))) \\
 24116 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -((65 \times 4) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 24117 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24118 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) - 1) \\
 24119 &:= (((-(9 + ((87 \times 6) + 5))) \times -((43 + 2))) - 1) \\
 24120 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (((7 + 6) - 5) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 24121 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 + 6) + ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2))) + 1) \\
 24122 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5 - (4 \times 3)^{2+1}) \\
 24123 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 24124 &:= ((-9 \times -87) + (((6^5) + 4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 24125 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24126 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24127 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (((6^{(5+4)/3}) \times 2) - 1))) \\
 24128 &:= ((-9 - (((-8 \times -7) \times ((6 - 5) - 432)) - 1)) \\
 24129 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) - 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24130 &:= (((1+2)/3) - (-(((45 \times 67) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 24131 &:= (1 - (((2-3) - (45 \times (67 \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 24132 &:= ((-1+2) \times ((3 \times 4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24133 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3+4)) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24134 &:= ((1 \times ((2+3456) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 24135 &:= (1 + (((2+3456) \times 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 24136 &:= (((-1 + (2+3)) \times 4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24137 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) - (45 \times (-67 \times 8))) - (-9) \\ 24138 &:= -(((1+2) + (((-2^3) \times 45) \times 67)) + ((-8-9))) \\ 24139 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (34 \times (5 \times ((6-7) + (8 \times 9))))) \\ 24140 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (34 \times (5 \times ((6-7) + (8 \times 9))))) \\ 24141 &:= (-12 + (-3 + ((-4 - ((5 \times 67) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\ 24142 &:= ((-12+34) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24143 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4^{5-6+7}) - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24144 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) \times -((4^{5-6+7}) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 24145 &:= (((-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4+5) \times 6))) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 24146 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) \\ 24147 &:= ((1 \times (23+4)) - (-5 \times ((67 \times 8) \times 9))) \\ 24148 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24149 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (-4 - ((5-67) \times (8+9)))) \\ 24150 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 + (8+9)))) \\ 24151 &:= (-1 + (-(-23) + ((45 \times (67 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 24152 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3+4))) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24153 &:= (1 - (2 + (-34) - ((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24154 &:= (((-1+2) - 3) + ((4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 24155 &:= (-1 + ((2+34) + (-((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times -9)))) \\ 24156 &:= ((1 \times (2+34)) - ((5 \times 67) \times -((8 \times 9)))) \\ 24157 &:= (((1 - (23+5)) \times 6) + 7) \times -((8+9)) \\ 24158 &:= ((1 \times 23456) - (-78 \times 9)) \\ 24159 &:= (1 - (-23456) + (-78 \times 9)) \\ 24160 &:= ((-1 + (2+3)) + ((4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 24161 &:= (-1 \times -((2+3) + ((4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 24162 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times 3) + ((4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 24163 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + ((4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 24164 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 24165 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times ((3^4) + 5)) + 6)) \times -((7+8) \times 9)) \\ 24166 &:= ((12+34) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 24167 &:= (-1 - ((23 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8+9)))) \\ 24168 &:= -(((1 + (-23 \times (4^5)))) - (6 - (7 \times 89))) \\ 24169 &:= (((-1+23) \times ((4^5) + (67+8))) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24130 &:= (-98 + ((76 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24131 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times (5^4 - 3!^{2+1}) \\ 24132 &:= ((-9 \times -87) + (((6^5) + (4+3)) \times (2+1))) \\ 24133 &:= (9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4!) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 24134 &:= (((-9 \times -(8+7)) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) - 1) \\ 24135 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7+6))) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2+1)) \\ 24136 &:= ((-9 - (8+7)) + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2+1}))) \\ 24137 &:= (9+8) \times 7 + (6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2+1) \\ 24138 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times ((4+3) - (2-1)))) \\ 24139 &:= (((-9-8) \times -((76-5) \times (4 \times (3+2)))) - 1) \\ 24140 &:= ((-9-8) \times -((76-5) \times (4 \times ((3+2) \times 1)))) \\ 24141 &:= (((-9 \times -(8+7)) + 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2+1))) \\ 24142 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! \times 6/5) \times 4 + 3 \times (2+1)! \\ 24143 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 \times 6 + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2+1) \\ 24144 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (((7+6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 + (2+1))) \\ 24145 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (((7+6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 24146 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times 4) + 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 24147 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7+6) \times ((5 + (4^3)) \times (2+1)))) \\ 24148 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 76) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2+1))) \\ 24149 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -5) \times ((4+3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 24150 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7+6) \times 5^4 - 3) \times (2+1) \\ 24151 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -5) \times ((4+3) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 24152 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 + 6^5 + 4^{3 \times 2+1} \\ 24153 &:= (9-8) \times (-7 + 6^5 + 4^{3 \times 2+1}) \\ 24154 &:= ((9 - (8+7)) + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2+1}))) \\ 24155 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7-6!)) \times 5 - (4+3)! + (2+1)!! \\ 24156 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + ((7+6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) - (2+1)) \\ 24157 &:= (((-9-8) \times 7) \times -((6+5) + ((4^3) \times (2+1)))) \\ 24158 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6+5)) \times -((4+3)^2)) + 1) \\ 24159 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (-6+54) - 32 - 1 \\ 24160 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (-6+54) - 32 \times 1 \\ 24161 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (-6+54) - 32 + 1 \\ 24162 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + ((7+6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) + (2+1)) \\ 24163 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7 - 6) \times (5 \times (4^3 + 2) + 1) \\ 24164 &:= ((-9 \times ((-8-76) - ((54-3)^2))) + (-1)) \\ 24165 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (((6+5) - 4)^3))) + (2+1))) \\ 24166 &:= ((-9 \times ((-8-76) - ((54-3)^2))) - (-1)) \\ 24167 &:= (((-9+8) \times -7) + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2+1}))) \\ 24168 &:= (-9 \times 8 + (7+6) \times 5^4 + 3) \times (2+1) \\ 24169 &:= 9 \times (8-7) + 6^5 + 4^{3 \times 2+1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24170 &:= ((1 - ((-(-2 - 3)) + (45 \times 67)) \times -8)) + 9) \\
 24171 &:= (-(((1 + (2 - 3456)) \times 7)) \times -((8 - 9))) \\
 24172 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5 - (6 + 78)) \times 9)))) \\
 24173 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 24174 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 34) \times -((5 - (6 + (78)))))) \times 9) \\
 24175 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (34 \times (-((5 - (6 + (78)))) \times 9))) \\
 24176 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - (34 \times ((5 - (6 + 78)) \times 9)))) \\
 24177 &:= ((1 \times 2) + ((3456 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 24178 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (((-4^5) - (6 + 78)) + 9)) \\
 24179 &:= ((1 \times 23) - ((4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times -9)) \\
 24180 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\
 24181 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 + 4) + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 24182 &:= (-(((1 - (2 + 3456)) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 24183 &:= ((-((12^3)) \times ((45 - 67) + 8)) - 9) \\
 24184 &:= ((1^2) - (((-3 - 4) - (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 24185 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3 + 4) + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 24186 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -(4^5)) + (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24187 &:= (12 + ((3456 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 24188 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((-3456) \times -7) + (8 - 9)) \\
 24189 &:= (-((1 + 2)) + (((3 - (45 + 6)) \times (7 \times -8)) \times 9)) \\
 24190 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((3456 \times 7) + 8)) + 9)) \\
 24191 &:= (((12^3) \times -((4 - ((5 + 6) + 7)))) - (-8 + 9)) \\
 24192 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24193 &:= (-(((1 \times 2)^3) - (45 \times 67)) \times 8) + 9) \\
 24194 &:= (-((1 \times -2)) - ((-3 + 45) \times (6 \times (-7 - 89)))) \\
 24195 &:= (((((1 \times 2) - (3456)) \times -7) + 8) + 9) \\
 24196 &:= -(((12 + 34) \times (5 - ((67 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 24197 &:= ((-12 + (3456 \times 7)) - (-8 - 9)) \\
 24198 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 24199 &:= (-1 + (-((-23 \times (4^5))) + ((6 - 78) \times -9))) \\
 24200 &:= ((1 - 23) \times (-(((4^5) - 6)) - (-7 + 89))) \\
 24201 &:= ((-(-1) - ((-23 \times (4^5)))) + ((6 - 78) \times -9)) \\
 24202 &:= (((((-12^3)/4) \times -(56)) - 7) - (-8 - 9)) \\
 24203 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 24204 &:= (((12 + 3456) \times 7) + ((-8 \times 9))) \\
 24205 &:= (1 + 2 + 3 \times 4^5/6) \times (7 \times 8 - 9) \\
 24206 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3456 \times 7) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 24207 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - ((3456 \times 7) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 24208 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((3456 \times 7) + 8)) - 9)) \\
 24209 &:= (((-1 - ((2^3) \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7)))) \times -8) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24170 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((76 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 24171 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
 24172 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (76 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\
 24173 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3}))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 24174 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 24175 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) \times 4)/(3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 24176 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times (((6^5) \times 4)/(3^2)))) + 1) \\
 24177 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24178 &:= ((-98/7) \times ((6 - 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 24179 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + 2))) - 1) \\
 24180 &:= ((((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24181 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + 2))) + 1) \\
 24182 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times ((6^{(5+4)/3}) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 24183 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) - (6 - 5)) \times ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 24184 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times ((6^{(5+4)/3}) \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 24185 &:= (-((9 \times ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - 54)))) - ((3 \times 2) + (1))) \\
 24186 &:= (-((9 \times ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - 54)))) - ((3 \times 2) \times (1))) \\
 24187 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -(65 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\
 24188 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 - 54)))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 24189 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24190 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 24191 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) \times 4)/(3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 24192 &:= ((9 + 87) \times -(((65 + 4) - 321))) \\
 24193 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 - 5) - ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1) \\
 24194 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 24195 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24196 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 - 54)))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 24197 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 - 54)))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 24198 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24199 &:= (-((9 \times ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - 54)))) + ((3 \times 2) + (1))) \\
 24200 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (5 - 4)) \times -(3^2 - 1)) \\
 24201 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) \times ((6 - 5) - ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1)) \\
 24202 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times (6 - 54)))) - (3 - 2)) + 1) \\
 24203 &:= -9 \times (8 + 7 + 6) + (5 + 4!)^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 24204 &:= (-9 + (8! - 7!)/(6!/5!)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 24205 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 + ((4 + 3) \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 24206 &:= (-98 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 24207 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24208 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - 5) \times -43) - (2 - 1)) \\
 24209 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3}))) \times -2) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24210 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (34 \times ((56/7) \times 89))) \\
 24211 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times 4)) + (5 \times ((67 \times 8) \times 9))) \\
 24212 &:= ((1 \times (23 \times 4)) + ((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 24213 &:= ((1 + (23 \times 4)) + ((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 24214 &:= (((1 + (2 + 3456)) \times 7) - 8) + 9 \\
 24215 &:= (((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9) \\
 24216 &:= (-(((1 - (2 + 3456)) \times 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\
 24217 &:= ((1 \times -2) + (-((-345) - 6) \times (78 - 9))) \\
 24218 &:= (1 + (-2 - ((-345) - 6) \times (78 - 9))) \\
 24219 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - ((4^5) - (6 + 7))) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 24220 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 + ((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 24221 &:= ((12 + (3456 \times 7)) - (-8 - 9)) \\
 24222 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -(4 - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 24223 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (3 - (4 \times ((5 - 678) \times -9)))))) \\
 24224 &:= ((-12/3) - (4 \times ((5 - 678) \times 9))) \\
 24225 &:= ((1 - (23 \times ((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)))) \times -((8 + 9))) \\
 24226 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 24227 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times (4^5)) + ((67 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 24228 &:= ((1 + (-2 + (-3))) \times (45 - (678 \times 9))) \\
 24229 &:= ((1^{23}) - (4 \times ((5 - 678) \times 9))) \\
 24230 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3 \times 4) + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 24231 &:= (-123) \times ((-4 - ((-5 \times (-6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
 24232 &:= ((12/3) - (-4 \times ((5 - 678) \times -9))) \\
 24233 &:= (-(-1) \times ((2 + 3) + (4 \times ((5 - 678) \times -9)))) \\
 24234 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 24235 &:= (((1 + 2) + 34) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\
 24236 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (((3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times 7)/8) \times 9)) \\
 24237 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 24238 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4^5))) + (678 + 9)) \\
 24239 &:= ((123 - 4) - ((5 \times 67) \times -((8 \times 9)))) \\
 24240 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) - ((4^5) - 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 24241 &:= (-1 + (-23 \times (((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times (-8 - 9)))) \\
 24242 &:= ((((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 24243 &:= (((1 + (2 - 3456)) \times -7) - (8 \times -9)) \\
 24244 &:= ((-1 + 23456) + (789)) \\
 24245 &:= ((1 \times 23456) + 789) \\
 24246 &:= ((1 + 23456) + 789) \\
 24247 &:= (((-1 - (-23 \times (4^5))) - 6) + (78 \times -(-9))) \\
 24248 &:= (((1 \times 2)^{3+4}) - ((-5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 24249 &:= (((-(-1) + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24210 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3}))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 24211 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3}))) \times -2) + 1) \\
 24212 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - 5) \times -43) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24213 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24214 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 765) \times ((4^3)/2)) + 1)) \\
 24215 &:= (-9 - ((8 - 765) \times ((4^3)/(2 \times 1)))) \\
 24216 &:= (9 \times 8 \times (7 - 6) + (5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 24217 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -(5 \times (4 + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24218 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -(5 \times (4 + 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 24219 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 24220 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -(5 \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 24221 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) \times (6 - 54)) - 3)) - (2 \times (-1))) \\
 24222 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times ((4^3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 24223 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (-6 + 54) + 32 - 1 \\
 24224 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (-6 + 54) + 32 \times 1 \\
 24225 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times (-6 + 54) + 32 + 1 \\
 24226 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times 4) + 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 24227 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times 4) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 24228 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 76) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24229 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + (6 \times (5 \times 43))) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 24230 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - 5) \times -43) + 21) \\
 24231 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 24232 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((4 + (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 24233 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 24234 &:= (-9 + (((87 - 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24235 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 76)) + (5^4)) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 24236 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 76)) + (5^4)) \times -3) + 2) + 1) \\
 24237 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 \times (-6 + 54) + 3 + 2 \times 1) \\
 24238 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times 4) - 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 24239 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6^5 + 4^{3 \times 2 + 1} \\
 24240 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 - 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 24241 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 24242 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 + 5) \times (((4^3) \times 2) + 1)))) \\
 24243 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24244 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 76) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
 24245 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times 5) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 24246 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 24247 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((76 \times 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 24248 &:= (((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times 5) - 4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 24249 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((76 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + (2 - 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$24250 := -((1 - 23) + (4 \times ((5 - 678) \times 9)))$$

$$24251 := ((1 \times 23) - (4 \times ((5 - 678) \times 9)))$$

$$24252 := ((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3^4) + 5) \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))))$$

$$24253 := ((1 - (-((2 \times 3) + 45)) \times 6) \times (7 - (8 \times -9)))$$

$$24254 := ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))))$$

$$24255 := ((1 + 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))))$$

$$24256 := (((1 \times -2) + 34) \times (56 + (78 \times 9)))$$

$$24257 := (((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7)))) \times 8) + 9$$

$$24258 := (((-1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))$$

$$24259 := ((-1 - ((-23 \times (4^5)) - 6)) - (78 \times -9))$$

$$24260 := ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9))))$$

$$24261 := (-(((1 + 2) - ((3456 \times 7)))) + (8 \times 9))$$

$$24262 := (-1 \times (2 - ((3456 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))))$$

$$24263 := (1 - (2 - ((3456 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))))$$

$$24264 := (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (4^5)) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9))$$

$$24265 := ((1^2) - (-((3456 \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)))$$

$$24266 := (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))$$

$$24267 := -(((1 - (2 + (3456 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9)))$$

$$24268 := (1 - (((2 - 3456) \times 7) - 89))$$

$$24269 := (-12 + (((3456 \times 7) + 89)))$$

$$24270 := ((-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times 5))) \times (6 + (7 + (8 + 9))))$$

$$24271 := ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times 8)) + 9)$$

$$24272 := (-1 + ((-2 + (-34) + 5) \times (6 - 789)))$$

$$24273 := (((-1 + 23) + (4 + 5)) \times (-6 + 789))$$

$$24274 := ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + 7)) \times 8)) + 9)$$

$$24275 := (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))))$$

$$24276 := (((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))$$

$$24277 := (-1 + (((2 + 3456) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))$$

$$24278 := ((1 \times ((2 + 3456) \times 7)) + (8 \times 9))$$

$$24279 := (-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))))$$

$$24280 := (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9)))$$

$$24281 := (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7)))) \times 8) + 9$$

$$24282 := ((-((123 \times (45 - 67))) - 8) \times 9)$$

$$24283 := (-1 \times -(2 + ((3456 \times 7) + 89)))$$

$$24284 := (1 - ((-2 - (3456 \times 7)) - 89))$$

$$24285 := (-123) - (((-4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 8) \times 9)$$

$$24286 := -1 \times 2 + (-3! + 4^5 - 6) \times (7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$24287 := ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9))))))$$

$$24288 := (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (4^5)) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9))$$

$$24250 := ((((-98 + 7) - 6) \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1))$$

$$24251 := (9 + (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times ((43 + 2) + (1))))$$

$$24252 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1))$$

$$24253 := (((9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times (-4^3)) - ((2 + 1))$$

$$24254 := (-9 + 8 + 76 \times 5) \times 4^3 - 2 \times 1$$

$$24255 := (((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$24256 := ((((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)$$

$$24257 := ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times (2 + 1))))$$

$$24258 := (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$24259 := ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1))$$

$$24260 := (9 + 8 + 7! \times 6/5) \times 4!/(3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$24261 := (9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5^4 - 3)) \times (2 + 1)$$

$$24262 := (((-9 + 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$24263 := 9 \times 876 - 5 + 4^{3 \times 2 + 1}$$

$$24264 := ((-9 \times 8) \times ((7 - (6 - 5)) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$24265 := ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5 + (4 + 3)))^2) + 1))$$

$$24266 := ((-9 + ((8 + 76) \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1)$$

$$24267 := (-9 + ((8 + 76) \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1)))$$

$$24268 := (-98 + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$24269 := ((-9 \times 8) + (((76 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 21))$$

$$24270 := (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1}))$$

$$24271 := ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6^5) \times 4)/(3^2)) + 1))$$

$$24272 := (((-98 \times 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 \times (3^2)) + 1))$$

$$24273 := (-9 + ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$24274 := ((-98 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 + 1))$$

$$24275 := ((((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1)$$

$$24276 := (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))$$

$$24277 := ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1))))$$

$$24278 := ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1))$$

$$24279 := (-9 + (8 \times (((765 \times 4) - 3) - 21)))$$

$$24280 := (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times 4) \times ((3^2) + 1))$$

$$24281 := ((-9 \times 8) + ((76 - 5) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$24282 := (-9 \times -((8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)))/(2 + 1)))$$

$$24283 := ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 65) - 4) \times (3 \times 2)))) + 1)$$

$$24284 := ((-98 - 7) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1}))$$

$$24285 := (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$24286 := (-98 + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$24287 := (((-9 + (8 \times (76 + (5 \times 4)))) \times 32) - 1)$$

$$24288 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - ((4^{3+2}) - 1)))$$

$$24289 := (1 - ((2 \times ((34 \times 5) + 6))) \times (78 - 9))$$

$$24290 := (-1 + (-((2 \times 3)) - ((45 - 6) \times -((7 \times 89))))$$

$$24291 := ((1 \times -((2 \times 3))) - ((45 - 6) \times -((7 \times 89))))$$

$$24292 := (1 + (-((2 \times 3)) - ((45 - 6) \times -((7 \times 89))))$$

$$24293 := ((12 + (3456 \times 7)) + (89))$$

$$24294 := (-1 + (((2 + 3456) \times 7) + (89)))$$

$$24295 := ((1 \times ((2 + 3456) \times 7)) + (89))$$

$$24296 := -((-1 - ((2 + 3456) \times 7) + (89)))$$

$$24297 := ((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9))))))$$

$$24298 := -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times 5 \times 6 \times (-7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$24299 := (-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))))))$$

$$24300 := (((1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -4) - (5 \times (67 \times -8))) \times 9$$

$$24301 := ((12/3) - ((45 - 6) \times (7 \times -89)))$$

$$24302 := ((-1 \times (-2 - 3)) + ((-45) + 6) \times (-7 \times 89))$$

$$24303 := (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (((5^6) + (7 - 8))/9)))$$

$$24304 := ((1 + (2 \times 3)) + ((45 - 6) \times (7 \times 89)))$$

$$24305 := (((-1 \times -2)^3) + ((45 - 6) \times (7 \times 89)))$$

$$24306 := (((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times 6)))) \times -(7 + 8)) - 9)$$

$$24307 := ((-1 - 2) - (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))$$

$$24308 := (-1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))))$$

$$24309 := ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times 8 - 9))$$

$$24310 := ((1 - 23) \times ((-4^5) - (-6 - (-78) - 9)))$$

$$24311 := ((-1 + 2) + (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (-7 + (8 \times 9))))$$

$$24312 := (12 + (3 + (((45 - 6) \times 7) \times 89)))$$

$$24313 := (((1 \times 23) \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 \times -89))$$

$$24314 := (1 + (((23 + (45 \times 67)) \times 8) + 9))$$

$$24315 := (1 + 2 \times (34 + 5^6 \times 7 + 8))/9$$

$$24316 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4^5 \times 6 - 7 \times 8 - 9)$$

$$24317 := (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times 7)/8) \times 9)$$

$$24318 := (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (456 - 7)) - 8) \times -9$$

$$24319 := (-1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9))))$$

$$24320 := (((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - (8 + 9)))$$

$$24321 := -(((((-1 - 23) + (-45) \times 67) \times 8) - 9))$$

$$24322 := (12 - (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))$$

$$24323 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))))))$$

$$24324 := ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -4 + (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))))$$

$$24325 := (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9)$$

$$24326 := ((-1 + ((2^3) \times ((45 - 6) \times 78))) - 9)$$

$$24327 := (((12 + 34) + 5) \times ((6 \times 78) + 9))$$

$$24328 := ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times -((4 \times 5) - (678 \times 9)))$$

$$24289 := (((-9 - (8 \times ((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3))) \times -2) - 1)$$

$$24290 := ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1))))$$

$$24291 := (-9 \times -8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))))$$

$$24292 := ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))) + 2)) + 1)$$

$$24293 := ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1))$$

$$24294 := ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$24295 := ((-9 \times -8 + 7) + ((6^5) + (4^{3 \times 2 + 1})))$$

$$24296 := (((-9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))$$

$$24297 := (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1))$$

$$24298 := ((-98 + 7) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1}))$$

$$24299 := (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times -5 + ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)$$

$$24300 := (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))$$

$$24301 := (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times -5 + ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)$$

$$24302 := (987 - (((6^5) - 4) \times -3) + ((2 - 1))))$$

$$24303 := (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$24304 := ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1))$$

$$24305 := ((-98 \times (76 - ((54 \times 3) \times 2))) + ((1)))$$

$$24306 := -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 + 2 + 1$$

$$24307 := (((-9 + ((8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4))) + 3)) \times 2) - 1)$$

$$24308 := ((-9 + ((8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4))) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1))$$

$$24309 := ((9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 54)) \times (3 - (2 \times -1))))$$

$$24310 := (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1}))$$

$$24311 := (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3+2}))) - 1)$$

$$24312 := ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$24313 := (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3+2}))) + 1)$$

$$24314 := ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 32)) + 1)$$

$$24315 := ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) - 3) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$24316 := ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1))))$$

$$24317 := ((-9 \times 8) + (((((7 + 6) - 5) \times 4) - 3)^{2+1}))$$

$$24318 := (((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5 + (4 + 3)))^2)) - 1)$$

$$24319 := ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 + 1))))$$

$$24320 := (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^{3+2-1}))$$

$$24321 := ((-(-9) \times ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 54) \times 3))) + 21)$$

$$24322 := ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) - (2 \times 1))$$

$$24323 := ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) - (2 - 1))$$

$$24324 := (-((9 \times 8)) - (-((-76 \times (5 - 4))) \times -321))$$

$$24325 := ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) + (2 - 1))$$

$$24326 := ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1)$$

$$24327 := ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) + (2 + 1))$$

$$24328 := (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24329 &:= ((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\
 24330 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) \times 5))) \times -(6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24331 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5)) \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\
 24332 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))) \\
 24333 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times 5))^{6 \times (7-8)+9})) \\
 24334 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 + (4 \times 5))^{6 \times (7-8)+9})) \\
 24335 &:= ((-1 \times (23 \times (-4^5))) - (6 - 789)) \\
 24336 &:= ((12 \times (345 \times 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 24337 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - 67) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 24338 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - 67) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 24339 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((34 \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 24340 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) \times (4 - (56 \times (78 + 9)))) \\
 24341 &:= (((123 \times 4) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + 8)) - 9) \\
 24342 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - 8))) + 9)) \\
 24343 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 24344 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times ((5 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 24345 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 24346 &:= ((-1 - (23 \times (-4^5))) + (6 + 789)) \\
 24347 &:= ((-1 \times (23 \times (-4^5))) + (6 + 789)) \\
 24348 &:= (((12 + 3456) \times 7) - ((-8 \times 9))) \\
 24349 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5) + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 24350 &:= -((((123 \times -4) + 5) \times ((67 - 8) - 9)) \\
 24351 &:= -1 - 2^3 \times 4 \times (-5 + (-6 - 78) \times 9) \\
 24352 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times ((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 24353 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 24354 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -((45 \times (6 \times (7 + 8))) + 9)) \\
 24355 &:= ((1 + 234) - (-5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24356 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((45 \times 6) + 789))) \\
 24357 &:= ((1 \times 23) \times ((45 \times 6) + 789)) \\
 24358 &:= -((-1 - (23 \times ((45 \times 6) + 789)))) \\
 24359 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7)) \times -8) - 9) \\
 24360 &:= ((-12 + ((-3 + (4^5)) - (-6))) \times (7 - (-8 - 9))) \\
 24361 &:= ((1^2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 - (78 \times 9))))) \\
 24362 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3 - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24363 &:= ((12 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 - (678)))) - 9) \\
 24364 &:= -(((1 + 23) + (-4 \times (-5 + (678 \times 9)))) \\
 24365 &:= -((((12 + 3456) \times -7) - 89)) \\
 24366 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3)^4 \times (5 + 6 \times 7 - 8) - 9 \\
 24367 &:= -(((((-1 + 23) \times ((-4^5) - (6 + 78))) + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24329 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 24330 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 24331 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - 2))) - 1) \\
 24332 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 + 5) \times (4 \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
 24333 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24334 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 - 6)) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^{2+1})) \\
 24335 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 24336 &:= (-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (((65 + 4) \times ((3 \times 2) - 1)))))) \\
 24337 &:= ((9 + 8) - (76 \times (((5 - 4) - 321)))) \\
 24338 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times -(3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 24339 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24340 &:= (-9 - (((8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 24341 &:= (-9 - (((8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 24342 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 24343 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 24344 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 24345 &:= ((9 \times ((8 - 7) - 6)) \times ((543 - 2) \times (-1))) \\
 24346 &:= ((-98/7) \times -((6 + 5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 24347 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - 2))) - 1) \\
 24348 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
 24349 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24350 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1) \\
 24351 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24352 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (5 \times 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 24353 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 - 6)^5)) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\
 24354 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\
 24355 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 24356 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 24357 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 - 2 + 1 \\
 24358 &:= 9 - (8 - (7 + 6) \times 5^4) \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 24359 &:= (98 + 76) \times 5 \times (-4 + 32) - 1 \\
 24360 &:= (98 + 76) \times 5 \times (-4 + 32) \times 1 \\
 24361 &:= (98 + 76) \times 5 \times (-4 + 32) + 1 \\
 24362 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1))) \\
 24363 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24364 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (76 - 5)) \times 43) + 2)) + 1) \\
 24365 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24366 &:= (((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 24367 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times (5^4 \times 3 - 2) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24368 &:= (((-1+2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 24369 &:= (((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 24370 &:= (((1+2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 24371 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3+4)!) \times 5 - 6! - 7 \times (8+9) \\
 24372 &:= ((1 + (23 + (4 + (5 \times (67 \times 8)))))) \times 9) \\
 24373 &:= ((-12 - 3) + (4 \times (-5 - (-678) \times 9))) \\
 24374 &:= (-12 + (((3 - (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times -(89))) \\
 24375 &:= (((-1 \times -(2+3))^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - ((7-8) \times 9))) \\
 24376 &:= ((-1+23) \times -(4 \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\
 24377 &:= ((((-1+2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7)) \times -8) + 9) \\
 24378 &:= ((-1-2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
 24379 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times (-5 + (6 \times 7 - 8) \times 9) \\
 24380 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times ((7+8) - 9)))) \\
 24381 &:= ((12 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 - (678)))))) + 9) \\
 24382 &:= ((-1+2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\
 24383 &:= (-1 + (((2+3)^4) \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) - 8)) + 9) \\
 24384 &:= (((1 \times -2) - ((3 - 45) \times -6)) \times (-7 - 89)) \\
 24385 &:= (((((-1+2) \times 3) \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 24386 &:= ((-1+2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 24387 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 24388 &:= (((1 \times (2^3)) - 4) \times (-5 + (678 \times 9))) \\
 24389 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4 + 5))^{6 \times (7-8)+9} \\
 24390 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3)^4) - (5 \times 6))) \times (7 + (8 - 9))) \\
 24391 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4^5))) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9) \\
 24392 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) + (78 \times 9)) \\
 24393 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) + 5))) \times -(6 + ((7+8) \times 9))) \\
 24394 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times 3) - (4 \times (5 - (678 \times 9)))))) \\
 24395 &:= -(((123 - 4) \times (-5 \times (((6 \times 7) + 8) - 9)))) \\
 24396 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times ((7+8) - 9)) \\
 24397 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (4^{5-6+7})) - 89))) \\
 24398 &:= ((-1+23) \times (4 + (5 \times ((6+7) \times (8+9)))))) \\
 24399 &:= (((1+2) + (-34) + ((5 \times 67) \times -8)) \times -9) \\
 24400 &:= ((((-1+2) - (3^4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 24401 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - 7)) \times -8) + 9) \\
 24402 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6))) \times -((7+8) - 9)) \\
 24403 &:= (-1 \times ((2+3) - ((4 + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24404 &:= ((-12/3) + ((4 + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 24405 &:= (((1 + (-((-2 \times 3)) \times -((4 - 56)))) \times 78) - 9) \\
 24406 &:= ((1 - 23) + (-4 \times (-5 - (-678) \times -9))) \\
 24407 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times ((-4 + (5 \times 67)) + 8)) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24368 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times 6) + (5 - 4)))^3) - 21) \\
 24369 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24370 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 24371 &:= ((-9 \times (87 - ((65 \times 43)))) + ((-2 + (1)))) \\
 24372 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24373 &:= ((-9 \times (87 - ((65 \times 43)))) - ((-2 + (1)))) \\
 24374 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))))) \\
 24375 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24376 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\
 24377 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4))))^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24378 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24379 &:= ((9 - (-((876 - 5)) \times (4 - 32))) \times (-1)) \\
 24380 &:= (-9 + ((8 - ((7 \times 6) / (5 - (4 + 3))))^{2+1})) \\
 24381 &:= ((9 \times (-8 - (7 - 6))) \times -((5 \times -4) + 321))) \\
 24382 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 24383 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4))))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 24384 &:= ((9 + 87) \times (((65 \times 4) - (3 + 2)) - (1))) \\
 24385 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 24386 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times 6) + (5 - 4)))^3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24387 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
 24388 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((((7 + 6) - 5) \times 4) - 3)^{2+1})) \\
 24389 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))^{2+1})) \\
 24390 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) - 3) / (2 + 1))) \\
 24391 &:= (-9 + (((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times 3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 24392 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times 6) + (5 - 4)))^3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24393 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 + 2 - 1 \\
 24394 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 24395 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 24396 &:= -(((-98 + (76 - 54)) \times 321)) \\
 24397 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 24398 &:= ((9 + (-8 \times (7 \times (654/3)))) \times ((2 \times -1))) \\
 24399 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24400 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5 + 4))))^3) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 24401 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 24402 &:= (-98 \times ((76 - ((54 \times 3) \times 2)) - (1))) \\
 24403 &:= ((-98 / -7) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 24404 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6! \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 24405 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4) \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 24406 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4) \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 24407 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4) \times 3 - 2 + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24408 &:= (((1 \times (2 - 3)) \times 4) + (-5 \times 67)) \times (-8 \times 9) & 24408 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 - (6 + 5)) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 24409 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4^5))) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9 & 24409 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4) \times 3 + 2 - 1 \\
 24410 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 6)) \times - (7 - (8 + 9))) & 24410 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4) \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 24411 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) & 24411 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (-7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 24412 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + ((4 + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) & 24412 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\
 24413 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) + ((4 + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 24413 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 24414 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -((5 \times 6) - ((7 - 8) \times 9))) & 24414 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 24415 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) & 24415 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (6 + (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) + 1))) \\
 24416 &:= 1 \times 2^3 + (4 + 5 \times 67) \times 8 \times 9 & 24416 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))))/3) + 2)) - 1 \\
 24417 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5)) \times -6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) & 24417 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
 24418 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (6 \times 789))) & 24418 &:= (98 + (-76 \times ((5 - (4 + 321)))))) \\
 24419 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))))) & 24419 &:= (9 + (((87 / - (6 - (5 + 4)))^3) + 21)) \\
 24420 &:= -((((1 + 23) \times (-4^5)) + (67 + 89))) & 24420 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 24421 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 + 9))) & 24421 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
 24422 &:= (((1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (-7 - (-8 - 9))) & 24422 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 24423 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24423 &:= (-9 - (-8 \times ((765 \times 4) - ((3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 24424 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) - (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 24424 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 24425 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24425 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\
 24426 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24426 &:= -(((((-9 + (8 \times 765)) \times -4) - 3) - ((-21)))) \\
 24427 &:= ((-1 \times -((2 - 3)) + (4 \times (5 + (678 \times 9)))) & 24427 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 24428 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 - 4))) \times (-5 - (678 \times 9))) & 24428 &:= ((98 - ((76 \times (54 \times 3)))) \times (-2 \times (1))) \\
 24429 &:= -(((((-1 \times -((2 - 3))) - (4 \times (5 + (678 \times 9)))))) & 24429 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24430 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24430 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times 4)) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 24431 &:= (-1 + (((((2 - 3) \times -4)^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24431 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 \times 6 + 5) \times (4^3 + 2 - 1) \\
 24432 &:= (-12 \times ((34 \times -((-5 + 67))) + (8 \times 9))) & 24432 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times - (2 + 1)) \\
 24433 &:= (-((-1 \times 2)) + (3 + ((4 \times (5 - (678 \times -9)))))) & 24433 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1 \\
 24434 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) & 24434 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 24435 &:= (((1 - (2 + 34)) \times 5) - 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times -9) & 24435 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 24436 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24436 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 24437 &:= ((-1 \times -(2 + 3)) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24437 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1))) \\
 24438 &:= ((-1 \times -(2 \times 3)) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24438 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24439 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 24439 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times - (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 24440 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24440 &:= ((-98 - 7) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 24441 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times -3) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) & 24441 &:= ((9 + (-8 \times ((-765 \times 4) - ((-3 \times 2) \times 1)))))) \\
 24442 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - 6)) - (7 - (8 + 9))) & 24442 &:= ((-98 - 7) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\
 24443 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 24443 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times (4 + 3))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 24444 &:= (((1 + 2) \times -(-3)) \times (-4 \times -((56 + (7 \times 89)))))) & 24444 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 24445 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((-6 \times -7) + (89))) & 24445 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 - 2 \times 1 \\
 24446 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + 7))) \times 8) + 9)) & 24446 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 - 2 + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24447 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4+5})) \times -6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 24448 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - 6))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 24449 &:= -(((((-12^3) - ((4 \times 5678))) - 9)) \\
 24450 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(5 \times (6 + (7 + (8 + 9))))) \\
 24451 &:= ((1 - ((((-2^3)^4) - 5) \times -6)) + (-7 - (89))) \\
 24452 &:= -((-((1 + 23)) - (4 \times -((-5 - (678 \times 9))))) \\
 24453 &:= (((1 + 2) + 34) + ((5 \times 67) \times 8) \times 9) \\
 24454 &:= ((-1 + 23) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24455 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) - ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24456 &:= ((((-1 + 2)^3) + ((4^5) - 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 24457 &:= (((1 \times (2^{3+4+5})) \times 6) + (-7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24458 &:= (-1 + ((-2 - (-((34 + 5)) + 6)) \times 789)) \\
 24459 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) - (78 + 9)) \\
 24460 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 24461 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 24462 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 24463 &:= (1 + 23) \times 4^5 - (6 + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 24464 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 24465 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 24466 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 24467 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 24468 &:= ((-12 \times -3) + (((4^5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24469 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\
 24470 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times 6)) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 24471 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times 6) - ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 24472 &:= (-1 + ((((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - 67) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 24473 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4^{5-6+7}) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 24474 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -((4^{5-6+7}) - (8 + 9))) \\
 24475 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 24476 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 24477 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (34 \times ((5 \times -6) \times ((7 + 8) + 9)))) \\
 24478 &:= -(((1 \times 2)) - ((3 + 45) \times (-6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 24479 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 24480 &:= (((((1 \times 2) - (3 + 4)) + (-5 \times 67)) \times 8) \times -9) \\
 24481 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24482 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\
 24483 &:= -(((1 - 2) + (34 \times ((5 \times -6) \times ((7 + 8) + 9)))) \\
 24484 &:= 1 + 2 - (-3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24485 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24447 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1))))) \\
 24448 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 + 2 - 1 \\
 24449 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 24450 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 24451 &:= ((-9 - 87) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\
 24452 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 765)) \times 4) + (3^2)) - 1) \\
 24453 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 76) + 5) \times -((4 \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 24454 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 24455 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 24456 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 24457 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (765 \times 4)) - 32)) \times -1) \\
 24458 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times (5 - (4 \times (3^2)))) - 1) \\
 24459 &:= (-9 - ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24460 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
 24461 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((((7 + 6) - 5) \times 4) - 3)^{2+1})) \\
 24462 &:= -(((((-9 + (8 \times 765)) \times -4) + 3)) - (-21)) \\
 24463 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 24464 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2))) + 1) \\
 24465 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1))) \\
 24466 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 24467 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 24468 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 24469 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (765 \times 4))) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 24470 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 24471 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 24472 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
 24473 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
 24474 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 24475 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 24476 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (76 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 24477 &:= (-9 + (((-8 \times 765) \times -4) - (-3 \times (2 \times (1)))))) \\
 24478 &:= (98 - 7) \times (65 \times 4 + 3^2) - 1 \\
 24479 &:= (98 - 7) \times (65 \times 4 + 3^2) \times 1 \\
 24480 &:= (98 - 7) \times (65 \times 4 + 3^2) + 1 \\
 24481 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\
 24482 &:= 98 + ((7 + 6) \times 5^4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 24483 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -(5 + 43)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24484 &:= (-98 + ((7 - (6 - 5)) \times ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 24485 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 76) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24486 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 \times (4^{5-6+7}))) - 89)) \\
 24487 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times (3 \times (4^{5-6+7}))) - 89)) \\
 24488 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 24489 &:= (-1 \times (((-(2^{3+4+5})) \times 6) + 78) + 9)) \\
 24490 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 4)) \times -(5 - (6 + 789))) \\
 24491 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) \times 6) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 24492 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((67 + 8) + 9)) \\
 24493 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times -6) - (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24494 &:= -(((1 - (2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) \times 6)) - (7 - 89)) \\
 24495 &:= ((-12 + (3^{4+5})) - (67 \times (-8 \times 9))) \\
 24496 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4+5} \times 6 - 7 - 8 \times 9 \\
 24497 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + 7))) \times -8) + 9) \\
 24498 &:= -(((-((-1 - 2))^3) - (45 \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\
 24499 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 24500 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (6 \times 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 24501 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 \times -7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 24502 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24503 &:= (1 - (23 - (45 \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\
 24504 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((-3^{4+5}) - (-67) \times (-8 \times 9)))) \\
 24505 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 + (4^5)) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24506 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3^{4+5})) - (67 \times -((8 \times 9)))) \\
 24507 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) + (4 \times (-5 - 678)))) \times -9) \\
 24508 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (((4^5) - (6 - 7)) + 89)) \\
 24509 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
 24510 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
 24511 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
 24512 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 24513 &:= (-12 - (-3 \times (((4^5) + (6 - 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 24514 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24515 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 24516 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 5) \times 6) - (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 24517 &:= (1 + (-(((2^3) + (4 \times (-5 - 678)))) \times 9)) \\
 24518 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4^{5-6+7}) - 8))) - 9) \\
 24519 &:= (((-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 + 5))) \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 24520 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - 6)) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 24521 &:= ((1 - 2) - (3 - (-45) \times ((67 \times -8) + (-9)))) \\
 24522 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (3 - (-45) \times ((67 \times -8) + (-9)))) \\
 24523 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 24524 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\
 24525 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3 + 4)) \times 5 \times (6 \times 7 \times 8 - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24486 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 24487 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1) \\
 24488 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2}) + 1 \\
 24489 &:= (-9 \times (((-876 + 5) - ((43^2))) - (1))) \\
 24490 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) - 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 24491 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 24492 &:= (-((-9 + 87)) \times (6 + (5 - (((4 + 321)))))) \\
 24493 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (5 + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 24494 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -(5 + ((4^3) + 2))) - 1) \\
 24495 &:= (-9 - (-8 \times ((765 \times 4) + (-3 \times (-2 - (-1))))) \\
 24496 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -(5 + ((4^3) + 2))) + 1) \\
 24497 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + (3^2)))) - 1) \\
 24498 &:= (((9 + 8) + (765 \times ((4^3)/2))) + 1) \\
 24499 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2})))) \times -1) \\
 24500 &:= (-98 \times ((7 - (6 - 5)) - (4^{3+2-1})) \\
 24501 &:= ((-98 - 7) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 24502 &:= ((-98 - 7) + ((6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\
 24503 &:= (-((98 \times ((7 - (65 \times 4)) + 3))) + ((2 + 1))) \\
 24504 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 24505 &:= (9 - (-(((-8 \times 765) - 4) \times (-3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 24506 &:= (((((-987 + 6) \times 5) + 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 24507 &:= (-9 + ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24508 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 24509 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
 24510 &:= (-98 - ((((-765 - 4) \times 32) \times 1))) \\
 24511 &:= ((-98 - ((((-765 - 4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
 24512 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5 \times 43 + 2 \times 1 \\
 24513 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24514 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
 24515 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
 24516 &:= ((9 - (-8 \times 765)) \times (-4 \times (-3 + (2 \times (1)))) \\
 24517 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 24518 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\
 24519 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 24520 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)) \\
 24521 &:= (-9 - 8 + 76 \times 54) \times 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 24522 &:= (-9 - 8 + 76 \times 54) \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \\
 24523 &:= (-9 - 8 + 76 \times 54) \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 24524 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 24525 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 \times ((4 \times 3) + (2 + 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24526 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (-67) - (-8 - 9)) \\ 24527 &:= (1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} + 5) \times 6 - 7 - 8 \times 9 \\ 24528 &:= (((((1^2) + 3) - (-4^5)) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24529 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((-6 \times -7) - (89))) \\ 24530 &:= ((1 \times (2 + 3)) + (45 \times ((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 24531 &:= -(((1 + 2) + (3 - 45)) \times (6 - (7 \times -(89)))) \\ 24532 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 24533 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 24534 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 24535 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) + ((6 - (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\ 24536 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 24537 &:= (((-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 + 5))) \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 24538 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 24539 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4+5}) - 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\ 24540 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (-6 \times (-7 - ((8 - 9)))) \\ 24541 &:= (1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} + 5) \times 6 + 7 - 8 \times 9 \\ 24542 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5)) \times -6) + (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 24543 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24544 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 24545 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5)) \times -6) + (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 24546 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) \times 6) - (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24547 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 24548 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3^{(-4+5) \times 6}) - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 24549 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 24550 &:= (-1 + 2^{3 \times 4} - 5) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 24551 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) \times 6)) - (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24552 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3-4+5+6})) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24553 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times (5 - (6 - 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 24554 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) + (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 24555 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6)) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 24556 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24557 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24558 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24559 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 + 4) - 5)^{6+7})) - (8 + 9)) \\ 24560 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24561 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24562 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24563 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 - (4 - 5))^6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\ 24564 &:= (((1 + 23) + (4 \times (56 + 7))) \times 89) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24526 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 24527 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24528 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - 5) - ((4^{3+2}) - 1))) \\ 24529 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) - 5^4))))/3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 24530 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 \times (5 - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\ 24531 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) - (5 - (4 - 3)))^2) - 1)) \\ 24532 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 - 4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\ 24533 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5 - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\ 24534 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 24535 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\ 24536 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24537 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7) \times 6) \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24538 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 - 4^{3 \times 2 \times 1}) \\ 24539 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24540 &:= (((-9 + ((8^{(7-6) \times 5})/4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 24541 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24542 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5^4) \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 24543 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 5) - 4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\ 24544 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 - 4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\ 24545 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (((7 + 6) - 5^4)) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 24546 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (-5 + 4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\ 24547 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (((7 + 6) - 5^4)) \times 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 24548 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 24549 &:= (((-(9 + 8)) \times -((765 - 43) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 24550 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 24551 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - 5) - (4^{3+2}))) - 1) \\ 24552 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24553 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24554 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2})))) \times -1) \\ 24555 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 - (4^3)^2) - 1 \\ 24556 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 + 6 \times (-5 + (4^3)^2 \times 1) \\ 24557 &:= 9 + 8 - 7 - 6 \times (5 - (4^3)^2) + 1 \\ 24558 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6) + (5 \times 4)^3 \times (2 + 1) \\ 24559 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 24560 &:= (9 - ((8 \times -((765 \times 4)) - (3^2))) + ((1))) \\ 24561 &:= (-9 \times ((-876 - 5) + (-((43^2)) + (1)))) \\ 24562 &:= (9 + ((8 \times ((765 \times 4) + (3^2))) + 1)) \\ 24563 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 76) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1))) \\ 24564 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24565 &:= (1 - (((2 - 3) + ((45 \times 6))) + 7) \times -(89)) \\ 24566 &:= ((1 - (2 + 345)) \times ((-6 - (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 24567 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4^5 \times 6 + (7 - 8) \times 9 \\ 24568 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) \times 6) - (7 - (8 - 9)) \\ 24569 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24570 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4}))/5) \times (6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 24571 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - 8))) - 9) \\ 24572 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4^5))) \times -((6 + 7) - (8 + 9))) \\ 24573 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((-6 \times (-7 + 8)) + 9)) \\ 24574 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 24575 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 24576 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 24577 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\ 24578 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 24579 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 24580 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 24581 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times 6)) - (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24582 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -((5 \times 6) - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 24583 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4+5}) \times 6) + (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\ 24584 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) \times 6) + (7 - (8 - 9)) \\ 24585 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times 4^5 \times 6 - (7 - 8) \times 9 \\ 24586 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) \times 6) - (7 - (8 + 9)) \\ 24587 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 24588 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + 6) - (-7 - ((8 - 9))) \\ 24589 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + 6) - (-7 \times -((8 - 9))) \\ 24590 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 - 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 24591 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4^5 - (6 - 7)) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24592 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4+5})) \times -6) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 24593 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + 4) - 5)^{6+7}) + (8 + 9)) \\ 24594 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) \times 6) + (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24595 &:= (-1 - (-((2^3)) - (-((4 \times (-5 - 678))) \times 9))) \\ 24596 &:= (-1 \times (-((2^3)) - (-((4 \times (-5 - 678))) \times 9))) \\ 24597 &:= (((1^{23}) + (4 \times (5 + 678))) \times 9) \\ 24598 &:= ((1 + ((-2 - (34)) \times (-5 - 678))) + 9) \\ 24599 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4+5}) \times 6) + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 24600 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3-4+5+6})) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24601 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7)))) \times -8) + 9 \\ 24602 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times -6) + (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 24603 &:= ((12 + 3) - (-((4 \times (5 + 678))) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24565 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - (((5 + 4)^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\ 24566 &:= 98/7 + 6 \times (-5 + 4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\ 24567 &:= (-9 + ((8^{7+6-5-4}) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 24568 &:= (-9 + (((8^{7+6-5-4}) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 24569 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 + (5 \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))))) \\ 24570 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 24571 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1 \\ 24572 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 65)))/4) \times -3) + (2 \times 1) \\ 24573 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) \times 2) - 1 \\ 24574 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 24575 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 24576 &:= ((9 + 87) \times (((65 \times 4) - (3 + 2)) + (1))) \\ 24577 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times -(4^{3+2})) + 1 \\ 24578 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 24579 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) \times -2) + 1 \\ 24580 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 24581 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1 \\ 24582 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6 - 5)^4 \times 3) \times 2 - 1 \\ 24583 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6 - 5)^4 \times 3) \times 2 \times 1 \\ 24584 &:= -9 + (8 + (7 + 6 - 5)^4 \times 3) \times 2 + 1 \\ 24585 &:= ((-9 - ((8^{7+6-5-4}) \times (3 \times 2))) \times -1) \\ 24586 &:= ((-98/7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1))) \\ 24587 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (-5 + (4^3)^2 - 1) \\ 24588 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 + 1) \\ 24589 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 24590 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times -3) - (2 - 1) \\ 24591 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times -3) \times (2 - 1)) \\ 24592 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (5^4))) \times -3) + (2 - 1) \\ 24593 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24594 &:= 9 - 8 - 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\ 24595 &:= (((-9 - ((8^{7+6-5-4}) \times 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 24596 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24597 &:= (-9 + (((8 - 7) \times 6) \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24598 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24599 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24600 &:= (9 \times 8 + (7 + 6) \times 5^4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\ 24601 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 - 5) + (4^{3+2}))) + 1) \\ 24602 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\ 24603 &:= ((-9 - ((8^{7-6} \times 5)/4)) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24604 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\
 24605 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\
 24606 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times ((-3 \times -(456)) + (7 - 8))) \times 9) \\
 24607 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 24608 &:= -1 + (2 + 3 \times 4^5 - 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24609 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4^5 - 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24610 &:= 1 + (2 + 3 \times 4^5 - 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24611 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4+5}) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
 24612 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4^5 \times 6 - (7 - 8) \times 9) \\
 24613 &:= ((-1 - (-2 \times -(3^4))) \times ((5 - 67) - 89)) \\
 24614 &:= ((1 \times ((((((3^3)^4) + 5) \times 6) + 7) - 8)) + 9) \\
 24615 &:= (-12 - (-3 \times (((((4^5) - 6) + 7) \times 8) + 9))) \\
 24616 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) \times 6) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 24617 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 24618 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6)) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
 24619 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) + ((8 - 9)))) \\
 24620 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) \times 6) - 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 24621 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -(4^5)) - (((6 + 7) - 8) \times -9)) \\
 24622 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times -6) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 24623 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - ((-6 \times -7) - (89))) \\
 24624 &:= (((((1 \times -2) \times 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 + ((7 - 8) + 9)))) \\
 24625 &:= (1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} - 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 \\
 24626 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) - (-67) - (-8 - 9)) \\
 24627 &:= (1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4 - 5)^{6+7} + 8 + 9) \\
 24628 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 - 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 24629 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 24630 &:= (1 + 23) \times 4^5 + 6 \times (-7 + 8) \times 9 \\
 24631 &:= ((1 - 23) + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 89)) \\
 24632 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 24633 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24634 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5)) \times -6) - (7 - 89)) \\
 24635 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) \times 6) - (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 24636 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times -6) + (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 24637 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9))) \\
 24638 &:= (1 + (((-2) + 345) \times (6 + (-7 - (-8 \times 9)))) \\
 24639 &:= (-(((1 - 23) \times (4^5))) + ((-6 + 78) - 9)) \\
 24640 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) \times 6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 24641 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\
 24642 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24604 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times (5 + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 24605 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3) - 2)) - 1) \\
 24606 &:= (((-9 - ((8^{(7-6) \times 5})/4)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24607 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} - 1)) \\
 24608 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - 4) \times -(32 \times 1)) \\
 24609 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 24610 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 24611 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 24612 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2})) - 1 \\
 24613 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1)) \\
 24614 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2})) + 1 \\
 24615 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 24616 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 24617 &:= (9 - ((-8 \times (765 + 4)) \times (3 + ((2 - 1)))) \\
 24618 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (-76 \times -54)) \times ((3 + 2) + (1))) \\
 24619 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} + 1)) \\
 24620 &:= ((-98 / -7) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 24621 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24622 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 24623 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 24624 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + (4^3)^2 - 1) \\
 24625 &:= (9 - (((-8) + ((-76 \times 54) \times (3 \times (2 \times 1)))))) \\
 24626 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 \times (5 - (4^3)^2) + 1 \\
 24627 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24628 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 24629 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + (4^3)^2) - 1 \\
 24630 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + (4^3)^2 \times 1) \\
 24631 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + (4^3)^2) + 1 \\
 24632 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))/2)) - 1) \\
 24633 &:= (-9 \times (((-8 \times (-7 \times -65)) - (-43 \times 21)))) \\
 24634 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))/2)) + 1) \\
 24635 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 24636 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + (4^3)^2 + 1) \\
 24637 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24638 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) - 5) \times -(((4^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 24639 &:= (((9 + 876) - 5) \times -((4 - 32))) + (-1) \\
 24640 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))/4) + 3)^2 \times 1) \\
 24641 &:= ((-9 \times (((-87 \times 6) \times 5) - (4 \times 32))) - (1)) \\
 24642 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 + 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24643 &:= -(((1+23) \times -(4^5)) + (67 \times (8-9))) \\ 24644 &:= (-1 - ((-2 - (34-5)) \times (6+789))) \\ 24645 &:= (-1 \times ((-2 - (34-5)) \times (6+789))) \\ 24646 &:= -((-1 + ((-2 - (34-5)) \times (6+789))) \\ 24647 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times ((6 + (7+8)) - 9)))) \\ 24648 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) - ((4^5) + 6)) \times -(7 + (8+9))) \\ 24649 &:= ((-1+2) - ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8+9)))) \\ 24650 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8+9)))) \\ 24651 &:= ((1^2) - 3) + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 89) \\ 24652 &:= ((1 \times (2-3)) + ((-(45 \times 6) - 7) \times -(89))) \\ 24653 &:= -((1 + ((2-3) - ((-(45 \times 6) - 7) \times -(89)))) \\ 24654 &:= (1 \times -((2-3) - ((-(45 \times 6) - 7) \times -(89)))) \\ 24655 &:= (1 - ((2-3) - ((-(45 \times 6) - 7) \times -(89)))) \\ 24656 &:= (((-1+2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 24657 &:= (((-1-2) \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times ((6-7) \times 8))) + 9) \\ 24658 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) \times 6) - (7-89) \\ 24659 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8+9))) \\ 24660 &:= (((1+23) \times (4^5)) + ((67+8) + 9)) \\ 24661 &:= (1 + 2^{3+4+5}) \times 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 \\ 24662 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4+5}) \times 6) + (78+9))) \\ 24663 &:= (((-1+2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6+7))) \times -8) - 9) \\ 24664 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8+9))) \\ 24665 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8+9))) \\ 24666 &:= (-1 + 2^{3+4+5}) \times 6 + 7 + 89 \\ 24667 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3^{(-4+5) \times 6})) + 7) \times -(8+9) \\ 24668 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24669 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24670 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24671 &:= (1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} + 5) \times 6 - 7 + 8 \times 9 \\ 24672 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24673 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24674 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24675 &:= -((1-23) + (((45 \times 6) + 7) \times 89)) \\ 24676 &:= (((-1 + (2+3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 24677 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4^{5-6+7}) + (8+9)))) \\ 24678 &:= ((12 - (((-34) + 5) - 6)) \times -(78)) \times 9) \\ 24679 &:= (((-1+2) + ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6+7))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 24680 &:= (((1 - (2+34)) - 5) \times (6 - (7 \times 89))) \\ 24681 &:= (1 + ((-2 - (3-45)) \times (-6 + (-7 \times -(89)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24643 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times -(4^3)) + (2+1)) \\ 24644 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (765+4))) \times -((3+2) - 1)) \\ 24645 &:= -(((9 \times -8) - (((76+5) - 4) \times 321))) \\ 24646 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6-5)) \times -((4+3)^2)) - 1) \\ 24647 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (((5^4) \times (3+2)) - 1)))) \\ 24648 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7+6) - 5)^4) \times (3 + (2+1))) \\ 24649 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + (7+6))) \times -5) + (4+3)^2) \times 1) \\ 24650 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6+5)) \times -((4+3)^2 + 1)) \\ 24651 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 + (6+5)) - 4)^3) + (2+1))) \\ 24652 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 24653 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24654 &:= (((9+8) \times (-7 \times -((65+4) \times 3))) + 21) \\ 24655 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\ 24656 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) - 1)) \\ 24657 &:= ((((-9-8) - (76 \times (54 \times 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 24658 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times (7 \times (6+5)))/4) + 3)^2) \times -1) \\ 24659 &:= (((-9-8) \times -7) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 24660 &:= ((-98 - (((7+6) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times -(2+1)) \\ 24661 &:= ((-98+7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3+2)))) + 1)) \\ 24662 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (76 \times 54)) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\ 24663 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7+6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2+1)) \\ 24664 &:= (((-9-8) \times -7) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\ 24665 &:= (((-9-8) \times -7) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24666 &:= (((-9-8) \times -7) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\ 24667 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - ((6 \times (5+4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\ 24668 &:= ((-98 \times -7) - ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2+1))) \\ 24669 &:= 9 \times (8 \times 7^{6/(-5+4+3)} - 2 - 1) \\ 24670 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 24671 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 24672 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + ((6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\ 24673 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) \times -1) \\ 24674 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7-6)) \times (5 - ((4+3)^{2+1})) \\ 24675 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5+4)^3) - (2+1)))) \\ 24676 &:= -((-987 \times (-6 - ((5-4) - 32))) + ((1))) \\ 24677 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7^{6/(-5+4+3)})) - 2)) - 1) \\ 24678 &:= (((-9-8) - (((7+6) - 5)^4)) \times -(3 + (2+1))) \\ 24679 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5 + (4^3)^2 - 1) \\ 24680 &:= 9 \times (8+7) + 6 \times (-5 + 4^{3 \times 2}) - 1 \\ 24681 &:= 9 \times (8+7) + 6 \times (-5 + 4^{3 \times 2}) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24682 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) - 9) \\
 24683 &:= ((12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 + 7)) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 24684 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (((4 - 5) + 67) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24685 &:= (1 \times 2^{3 \times 4} + 5) \times 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 \\
 24686 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24687 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24688 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24689 &:= 1^2 \times (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24690 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24691 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24692 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9 \\
 24693 &:= (-12 - (3^4) \times (((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 24694 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) - ((3 + 4) \times ((56 - 7) \times (8 \times -9)))) \\
 24695 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24696 &:= ((1 \times ((23 + ((4 \times 5) + 6)) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 24697 &:= (1 + (((23 + ((4 \times 5) + 6)) \times 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 24698 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((56 - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 24699 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((-3 + (4 - 56))) \times 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 24700 &:= (((-12 \times 3) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 24701 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4+5})) \times -6) + (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24702 &:= ((1 \times -23) \times (((4^5) - 67) + (8 + 9))) \\
 24703 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 24704 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
 24705 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) + (5 + 6)))) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 24706 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - ((-6 \times (7 + 8)) - 9))) \\
 24707 &:= (((1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + ((-6 \times -7) + (89))) \\
 24708 &:= (-12 + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 24709 &:= (-1 \times ((-23 \times (4^5)) + ((-6 - 7) \times 89))) \\
 24710 &:= (1 - ((-23 \times (4^5)) + ((-6 - 7) \times 89))) \\
 24711 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24712 &:= (-1 + 2 - 3 \times (4^5 + 6)) \times (-7 + 8 - 9) \\
 24713 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24714 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24715 &:= (((1 + 23) \times -((4^5))) + (67 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 24716 &:= ((-12/3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24717 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times -3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24718 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24719 &:= (-1 + (((((2 - 3) \times -4)^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24720 &:= ((((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24682 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times (-5 + 4^{3 \times 2}) + 1 \\
 24683 &:= (((-9 + 87) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\
 24684 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 \times (-5 - (4^3)^2) - 1 \\
 24685 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 \times (-5 - (4^3)^2) \times 1 \\
 24686 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 - 6 \times (-5 - (4^3)^2) + 1 \\
 24687 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times (-5 + 4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\
 24688 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (((6 + 5) - 4) \times 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 24689 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7^{-6+5+4} - 3 \times 2 - 1 \\
 24690 &:= (((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 - 4)) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 24691 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (6 \times (5 + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 24692 &:= (((-98 \times -7) + 6) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24693 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(7^{6/(-5+4+3)})) - (2 + 1)) \\
 24694 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 24695 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(7^{(6+5+4)/(3+2)})) - 1) \\
 24696 &:= 9 \times 8 \times 7^{6 \times 5 / (4+3+2+1)} \\
 24697 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(7^{(6+5+4)/(3+2)})) + 1) \\
 24698 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(7^{6/(-5+4+3)})) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 24699 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(7^{6/(-5+4+3)})) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24700 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 24701 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
 24702 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2))) + 1) \\
 24703 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1))) \\
 24704 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 24705 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5))) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 24706 &:= (98 - ((((-765 - 4) \times 32) \times 1))) \\
 24707 &:= ((98 - (((-765 - 4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
 24708 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 24709 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
 24710 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 24711 &:= (((-98 - 7) - (6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2})))) \times -1) \\
 24712 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 76)) \times 5) - 4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 24713 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\
 24714 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24715 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7^{6/(-5+4+3)})) + 2)) + 1) \\
 24716 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((76 + 5) - 4) \times 321)) \\
 24717 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 76) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 24718 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 - ((6 - ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 24719 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\
 24720 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24721 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6) \times (7 - 8 + 9) \\
 24722 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) \\
 24723 &:= (123 \times ((45 + 67) + 89)) \\
 24724 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24725 &:= ((-1 \times -(2 + 3)) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24726 &:= ((-1 \times -(2 \times 3)) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24727 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\
 24728 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24729 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -3) + (((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24730 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) + 6)) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 24731 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times -6) + (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24732 &:= (-12 \times -(((345 \times -6) \times (7 - 8)) - 9))) \\
 24733 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 24734 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 24735 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 24736 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times -(7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 24737 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 24738 &:= (-1 + 23^4) / (5 + 6) - 78 \times 9 \\
 24739 &:= ((-12 \times -((345 \times 6) - 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 24740 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times 6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 24741 &:= (((1 + 2) - (((345 + 6) - 7) \times 8)) \times -9) \\
 24742 &:= (-(((1^2) \times -(345 + 67))) \times 89) \\
 24743 &:= ((1^2) + ((-345) + 67) \times -(89)) \\
 24744 &:= ((((-1 + 2)^3) + ((4^5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24745 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6))) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
 24746 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + (5 \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 24747 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times -6) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 24748 &:= 1 \times 23 \times (4^5 + 6 \times 78/9) \\
 24749 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3 + 4) \times (56 \times 7)) + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 24750 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6))) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
 24751 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24752 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 24753 &:= (((12 \times 345) \times 6) - (78 + 9)) \\
 24754 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 \times (4^{5-6+7})) + 89)) \\
 24755 &:= ((12 \times ((345 \times 6) - 7)) - (-8 + 9)) \\
 24756 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
 24757 &:= ((-12 \times -((345 \times 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
 24758 &:= -(((12 \times (345 \times -6)) + (-7 + (89)))) \\
 24759 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) - ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24721 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 24722 &:= (98 + (-((76 \times (54 \times 3))) \times (-2 \times (1)))) \\
 24723 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7^{6/(-5+4+3)})) + (2 + 1))) \\
 24724 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2}) - 1 \\
 24725 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} \times 1) \\
 24726 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2}) + 1 \\
 24727 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 24728 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 765) \times ((4^3)/2)) + 1)) \\
 24729 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 - 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24730 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)))) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 24731 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} + 1) \\
 24732 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 24733 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5 + 4)^3)))/2)) + 1) \\
 24734 &:= -(((9 - 8) - (((76 + 5) - 4) \times 321))) \\
 24735 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2} - 1) \\
 24736 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 76) - (5^4)) \times -(32 \times 1)) \\
 24737 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times 43) + 2)) - 1) \\
 24738 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times 43) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 24739 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times 43) + 2)) + 1) \\
 24740 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2}) - 1 \\
 24741 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2}) \times 1 \\
 24742 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 \times (5 + 4^{3 \times 2}) + 1 \\
 24743 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) - (2 - 1)))) \\
 24744 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 - 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 24745 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 - 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 24746 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 - 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 24747 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (6 \times (5 + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 24748 &:= (-9 - 8 \times 7 + 6! \times 5) \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
 24749 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3)) - 2)) - 1) \\
 24750 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 24751 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) - 2))) - 1) \\
 24752 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 24753 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) - 2))) + 1) \\
 24754 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6! \times 5 - 4^3) + 2 + 1 \\
 24755 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
 24756 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 24757 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\
 24758 &:= ((-9 \times -(876 + ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 24759 &:= -(((9 \times 87) + (654 \times 3)) \times -21))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24760 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\
 24761 &:= (((1 \times (2 \times ((3 + (-4 \times 56))) \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\
 24762 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\
 24763 &:= -123 \times 4 + 5 \times (-6 + 7! + 8 + 9) \\
 24764 &:= 12/3 \times (4^5 \times 6 + 7 \times 8 - 9) \\
 24765 &:= (-((1 + 2)) + (((345 + 6) - 7) \times -8) \times -9)) \\
 24766 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 + 4) \times (56 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\
 24767 &:= (-((1^2)) + (((345 + 6) - 7) \times (-8 \times -9))) \\
 24768 &:= (((1^2) \times ((345 + 6) - 7)) \times -8) \times -9) \\
 24769 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 45))) \times -((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 24770 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 24771 &:= ((12 \times (345 \times 6)) + (-78) + 9) \\
 24772 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 + 89)))) \\
 24773 &:= ((-12 \times ((345 \times -6) + 7)) - (-8 - 9)) \\
 24774 &:= (-12 + ((3^4) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 24775 &:= (((12 \times 345) \times 6) - ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 24776 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(56 + (7 + 89))) \\
 24777 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 78 \times 9) \\
 24778 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 78 \times 9) \\
 24779 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 78 \times 9) \\
 24780 &:= 1^2 \times (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 78 \times 9) \\
 24781 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 78 \times 9) \\
 24782 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 78 \times 9) \\
 24783 &:= 1 + 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6 + 78 \times 9) \\
 24784 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times (5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 24785 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (((5 + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9)))) \\
 24786 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^4) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24787 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 24788 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 \times ((-4^5) - 6)) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 24789 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24790 &:= -(((1 - (2 + 34)) \times (-5 + ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 24791 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 24792 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\
 24793 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((-3 - (4^5)) - 6) \times ((-7 - 8) - 9))) \\
 24794 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3 + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 24795 &:= (((12 + 3) + (45 \times 6)) \times (78 + 9)) \\
 24796 &:= (1 + ((23 + (4 \times (5 + 678))) \times 9)) \\
 24797 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -(4^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 24798 &:= (12 + ((3^4) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24760 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 24761 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 24762 &:= ((-9 - (-8 \times ((-7 - 65) \times -43))) + ((2 + 1))) \\
 24763 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times 76) + 5)) \times (43 - 2)) - 1) \\
 24764 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 76) + 5)) \times ((43 - 2) \times 1)) \\
 24765 &:= (((9 \times -8) + 7) \times -(((6 - (-54 - 321)))))) \\
 24766 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 24767 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 24768 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + 6) - 5) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 24769 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 24770 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2))) + 1) \\
 24771 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24772 &:= ((-98 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 24773 &:= (((-98 - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4) \times 3) \times -2) + 1) \\
 24774 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 24775 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 24776 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 24777 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 24778 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
 24779 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 24780 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 24781 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5! + 4^{3!} \times (2 + 1)! \\
 24782 &:= 9 \times 87 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3 / 2 - 1 \\
 24783 &:= 9 \times 87 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3 / 2 \times 1 \\
 24784 &:= 9 \times 87 + 6 \times (5 \times 4)^3 / 2 + 1 \\
 24785 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) \times (5 + 4))^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 24786 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 24787 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (65 \times 4))) - ((3 \times 2) - (-1))) \\
 24788 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (65 \times 4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 24789 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((76 + 5) - 4) \times 321))) \\
 24790 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (65 \times 4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 24791 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 \times 4)^{3-2+1}))) \\
 24792 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 765) \times 4) + (-321))) \\
 24793 &:= (((-98 \times (7 - (65 \times 4)))) + (-3 / (2 + 1))) \\
 24794 &:= (-98 \times (((7 - (6 + 5)) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 24795 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + (6 + 5)) - 4)^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 24796 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (65 \times 4))) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 24797 &:= ((98 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + 43)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 24798 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) - 21))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24799 &:= (((-1-23) \times -(4^5) - (6+7)) - (89)) & 24799 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (65 \times 4))) + ((3 \times 2) + (-1))) \\ 24800 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + 7)) \times 8) + 9)) & 24800 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 4)))) \times (32 \times 1)) \\ 24801 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + 7)) \times -8) + 9 & 24801 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (65 \times 4))) + ((3 \times 2) - (-1))) \\ 24802 &:= (((-1-23) \times -(4^5) + 6) - (7-89)) & 24802 &:= 98 \times (-7 + 65 \times 4) + 3^2 - 1 \\ 24803 &:= (((-1+2) + ((3^4) \times (5 + (6+7)))) \times (8+9)) & 24803 &:= 98 \times (-7 + 65 \times 4) + 3^2 \times 1 \\ 24804 &:= ((-12 \times (-34) - 5) \times (6 - ((-7 \times 8) + 9))) & 24804 &:= 98 \times (-7 + 65 \times 4) + 3^2 + 1 \\ 24805 &:= (-1 + (23 + 4) \times (5^6 - 7)) / (8 + 9) & 24805 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 24806 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!) - 4! - 5^6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 & 24806 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 24807 &:= (((-1-2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) + (6+7))) \times 8) - 9) & 24807 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 24808 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))) & 24808 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 24809 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times 8))) + 9) & 24809 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 24810 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3))! \times (4 + 5!) / 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 24810 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24811 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! + 4! \times (5! - 6) + 7 + 8) \times 9 & 24811 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\ 24812 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + 45) \times (6 \times 78) + 9)) & 24812 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (65 \times 4))) - (3 - 21)) \\ 24813 &:= (((-1-2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - ((6+7) \times 8)))) \times 9) & 24813 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (((6 + 5) \times 4) \times (3^2)) - 1))) \\ 24814 &:= (1 + (((2^3) + 45) \times (6 \times 78) + 9)) & 24814 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (76 - 5))) \times -43) + (2 + 1)) \\ 24815 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3^4) + 5)) \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) & 24815 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 - (((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 24816 &:= (((-(-1) - (23 \times -4)) - 5) \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 24816 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 + 5) + (4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\ 24817 &:= (1 \times (23 \times (456 + (7 \times 89)))) & 24817 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - (5 \times 4)) \times -3) + 2) + 1 \\ 24818 &:= (1 + (23 \times (456 + (7 \times 89)))) & 24818 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (65 \times 4))) + (3 + 21)) \\ 24819 &:= -(((12 + (345 \times (6 - 78))) + 9)) & 24819 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 24820 &:= ((1 \times (2 \times (34))) \times (5 \times ((-6 + 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 24820 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 24821 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -34) \times (5 \times ((-6 + 7) + (8 \times 9)))) & 24821 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 24822 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times ((6 - 78) + 9)) & 24822 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 24823 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) \times -((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9) & 24823 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times (4^3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 24824 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times ((456 \times 7) - 89)) & 24824 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\ 24825 &:= -((-1) - ((-2^3) \times ((456 \times 7) - (89)))) & 24825 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 24826 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3! \times (4 + 5) + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 24826 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 24827 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (-4 + (5! + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 24827 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 24828 &:= (-12 \times ((345 \times -6) - ((7 - 8)^9)) & 24828 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) \times (2 - 1)) \\ 24829 &:= (((1 \times -2) - (345 \times (6 - 78))) - 9) & 24829 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 24830 &:= (((12 \times 345) \times 6) + 7) - (8 + 9) & 24830 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 24831 &:= -(((12 \times (345 \times -6) \times (7 - 8))) + 9) & 24831 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 24832 &:= -((((12 \times 345) \times -6) + 7) + (-8 + 9)) & 24832 &:= (((9 \times ((-8 - 7) - 6)) - 5) \times ((4 \times 32) \times (-1))) \\ 24833 &:= -((((12 \times 345) \times -6) + 7) \times (-8 + 9)) & 24833 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5^4 - 32) - 1 \\ 24834 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (345 \times 6))) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 24834 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5^4 - 32 \times 1) \\ 24835 &:= ((-12 \times -((345 \times 6) + 7)) - 89) & 24835 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5^4 - 32) + 1 \\ 24836 &:= 12/3 \times (4^5 \times 6 - 7 + 8 \times 9) & 24836 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43))) + 2)) - 1) \\ 24837 &:= (((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)) & 24837 &:= ((((-9) + ((8 \times 765))) \times 4) - ((-321))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24838 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 24839 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 24840 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (345 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) \\ 24841 &:= 1 + (2^3 + 4) \times 5 \times 6 \times (78 - 9) \\ 24842 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 24843 &:= ((12 - (345 \times (6 - 78))) - 9) \\ 24844 &:= (1 - 2) \times (3! - 4) + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 \times 9) \\ 24845 &:= ((-12 \times -((345 \times 6) - 7)) + 89) \\ 24846 &:= -((((12 \times 345) \times -6) - 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 24847 &:= (((12 \times 345) \times -6) - 7) \times (8 - 9) \\ 24848 &:= -((((12 \times 345) \times -6) - 7) + (8 - 9)) \\ 24849 &:= -(((12 \times ((345 \times -6) \times (7 - 8))) - 9)) \\ 24850 &:= ((-(((12 \times 345) \times -6) + 7)) + 8) + 9 \\ 24851 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 24852 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 24853 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 24854 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 24855 &:= ((12 + 3) \times (((4 \times -(56)) \times -7) + 89)) \\ 24856 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3^4) - 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 24857 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) - ((6 + 7) \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 24858 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 \times (4^5 - (6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9 \\ 24859 &:= 1 + (2 + 3 \times (4^5 - (6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9 \\ 24860 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -((4 + 5) - (67 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 24861 &:= ((12 - (345 \times (6 - 78))) + 9) \\ 24862 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 24863 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 24864 &:= -(((1 + (2 + 34))) \times ((5 \times 6) - (78 \times 9))) \\ 24865 &:= ((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9 \\ 24866 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3^4) + (5 \times (67 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 24867 &:= (1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 - (6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9 \\ 24868 &:= 12^3 + 4 \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times 89 \\ 24869 &:= -1^{234} + 5 \times (6 + 7! - 8 \times 9) \\ 24870 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 24871 &:= (1 \times ((23 - 4) \times -((5 + 6)) \times (7 \times -((8 + 9)))))) \\ 24872 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3^4) - 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 24873 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7)))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 24874 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3^4) - 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 24875 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 34) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 24876 &:= (-12 - (-34) \times ((-5 \times -6) - (78 \times -9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24838 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43))) + 2)) + 1) \\ 24839 &:= ((-9 \times (-8 \times 7)) + (((6 - (54 \times 3))^2) + (-1))) \\ 24840 &:= 9 \times 8 \times ((7 - 6 + 5) \times 4 + 321) \\ 24841 &:= ((-9 \times (-8 \times 7)) + (((6 - (54 \times 3))^2) - (-1))) \\ 24842 &:= (9 + (((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\ 24843 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 24844 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\ 24845 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\ 24846 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 6) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 24847 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (32 + 1)))) \\ 24848 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times 43) - 2)))) - 1) \\ 24849 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times -(((65 + 4) \times ((3 + 21)))))) \\ 24850 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 24851 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 24852 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 24853 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 24854 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1))) \\ 24855 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 24856 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (765 + 4)) \times 32) + 1)) \\ 24857 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 24858 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 24859 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times (3 \times 2)))) + 1) \\ 24860 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times 5) + 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\ 24861 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 24862 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 24863 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 24864 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 + 5) + ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 24865 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times -((65 \times 4) - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 24866 &:= (((-987 + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\ 24867 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) \times (3^2)) - 1))) \\ 24868 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 \times 43) - 2 - 1 \\ 24869 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 \times 43) - 2 \times 1 \\ 24870 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 \times 43) - 2 + 1 \\ 24871 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))))) \\ 24872 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 \times 43) + 2 - 1 \\ 24873 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 \times 43) + 2 \times 1 \\ 24874 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 \times (6 - 5 \times 43) + 2 + 1 \\ 24875 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) \times (3^2)))) - 1) \\ 24876 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1))))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24877 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) - 9) & 24877 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) \times (3^2)))) + 1) \\
 24878 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) - 9) & 24878 &:= (-9 + 8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4)) \times 3! / (2 + 1) \\
 24879 &:= ((((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5)) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9) & 24879 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 24880 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8))) - 9) & 24880 &:= (((-98/7) - 6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 24881 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7)))) \times 8) + 9) & 24881 &:= ((((-98/7) - 6) \times -(((5^4) - 3) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 24882 &:= ((((-1 + 23) + 4) \times (5 + 6)) \times -((-78) - 9))) & 24882 &:= (98 + 76) \times ((5 + 4 + 3)^2 - 1) \\
 24883 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((3 + 45) \times 6)) \times (78 + 9))) & 24883 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times ((6 \times 54) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 24884 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)))) & 24884 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times 54) - (3^2))) - 1) \\
 24885 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9))) & 24885 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) \times (3^2)) + 1))) \\
 24886 &:= ((-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times 8)) - 9) & 24886 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 24887 &:= (((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) - (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9) & 24887 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\
 24888 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - ((4^5) + 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) & 24888 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
 24889 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -(34)) \times ((5 \times (67 + 8)) - 9))) & 24889 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (32 \times 1)))) \\
 24890 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) & 24890 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 32)) + 1)) \\
 24891 &:= ((-12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9) & 24891 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) - 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 24892 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 24892 &:= (-9 + 87 \times 6 - 5) \times (4 + 3)^2 \times 1 \\
 24893 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 24893 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 24894 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times ((-3 \times 456) - (7 + 8))) \times 9) & 24894 &:= (-9 \times -(8 - (7 \times (6 - ((5 \times 4)^{3-2+1})))) \\
 24895 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times -8) - 9) & 24895 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)))) \\
 24896 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) \times (-4 \times ((5 + 6) - (789)))) & 24896 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 32)) + 1))) \\
 24897 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))) & 24897 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (((4^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 24898 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8)) + 9)) & 24898 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 24899 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) - (-67 + 8))) - 9)) & 24899 &:= (9 \times 8 \times 7 - 6) \times 5 \times (4 + 3 \times 2) - 1 \\
 24900 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))))) & 24900 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 + (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 24901 &:= -(((1 - (23 \times ((4^5) - (-67 + 8)))) + 9)) & 24901 &:= -(((1 - ((98 \times -7) \times 6)) \times -5) - (4321)) \\
 24902 &:= 1 - 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 \times 7) \times 8 - 9 & 24902 &:= (9 + (8 - 7 + 6)!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
 24903 &:= (((1 - (2 + 345)) \times (6 - 78)) - 9) & 24903 &:= (-9 \times -((((87 + 6) \times 5) - 4) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 24904 &:= (-((1 - (2 + 3))) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 7) + 89)) & 24904 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43))) - 2)) - 1) \\
 24905 &:= -((((12 \times 345) \times -6) + 7) + (8 \times -9))) & 24905 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times (5^4 - 32) - 1 \\
 24906 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9))) & 24906 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times (5^4 - 32) \times 1 \\
 24907 &:= ((-12 \times -((345 \times 6) + 7)) - (8 + 9)) & 24907 &:= (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6 \times (5^4 - 32) + 1 \\
 24908 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))))) & 24908 &:= 9 - 8 + 7 \times 6 \times (5^4 - 32) + 1 \\
 24909 &:= ((12 \times (345 \times 6)) - (-78) + 9) & 24909 &:= (-987 - (6 \times (5 - 4321))) \\
 24910 &:= (-12 - (-34 \times (-56) + 789)) & 24910 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2) + 1) \\
 24911 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + ((4^5) + 6)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24911 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -(((5 + 4) - 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 24912 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) + 5))) \times -(6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 24912 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times -((7^{6/(-5+4+3)} + (2 + 1)))) \\
 24913 &:= (-(-1) + (((2^3)^4) + 56) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) & 24913 &:= 9 \times 8 \times (7^{-6+5+4} + 3) + 2 - 1 \\
 24914 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((345 - (6 - 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) & 24914 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 24915 &:= -((-((1 + 2)) + (((345 - 6) + 7) \times (8 \times -9)))) & 24915 &:= (((((98 \times 7) + 65) + 4) \times (32 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24916 &:= 1^2 + 3 \times ((4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9) \\ 24917 &:= -((-(-1) - ((23 \times (4^5) - (-67) + 8))) + 9)) \\ 24918 &:= -((((-1 - (2^3)^4) - 56) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\ 24919 &:= -((1 - (((2 + 345) - 67) \times 89))) \\ 24920 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times -(7 \times 89)) \\ 24921 &:= (1 + (((2 + 345) - 67) \times 89)) \\ 24922 &:= (((1 - 2) \times 34) \times (56 - 789)) \\ 24923 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4^5 + 6 \times 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 24924 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(3 + (((4^5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 24925 &:= ((1 + 2) - (34 \times (56 - 789))) \\ 24926 &:= -1 - 2^{3!} \times 4 + 5 \times 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 24927 &:= (((12 \times 345) \times 6) + (78 + 9)) \\ 24928 &:= (1 - 2 + 3) \times 4 \times (5^{6+7-8} - 9) \\ 24929 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 24930 &:= -((((1 \times 2) - (((345 - 6) + 7) \times -8)) \times -9)) \\ 24931 &:= -(((1 - 234) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) + 89)))) \\ 24932 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9))))) \\ 24933 &:= (1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9) \\ 24934 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(3 + (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) - 9)))) \\ 24935 &:= (((((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^{4-5+6} - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\ 24936 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) - ((4^5) + 6)) \times -(7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 24937 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4^5 + 6 \times 7) \times 8 + 9 \\ 24938 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\ 24939 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3^4) \times ((5 + 6 + 7) \times 8 + 9) \\ 24940 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\ 24941 &:= ((-12 \times -(345 \times 6) + 7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 24942 &:= -1 - (2 - 3!) \times 4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 24943 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)^4) \times 5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\ 24944 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 24945 &:= (((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 + 7)) \times -8) + 9) \\ 24946 &:= -1 - (2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 24947 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\ 24948 &:= ((-1 + (-23 - (4 + 5))) \times ((6 + 78) \times -9)) \\ 24949 &:= (1 + ((2 + 34) \times ((5 - (6 - 78)) \times 9))) \\ 24950 &:= (1 - 2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5! + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 24951 &:= (-1 + (((((-2 + 3) + 4)^5) - 6) \times ((7 - 8) + 9))) \\ 24952 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 24953 &:= (((((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^{4-5+6} - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\ 24954 &:= (1 + (((((2 + 3)^{4-5+6} - 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 24955 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24916 &:= 9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 \times (5^4 - 32) - 1) \\ 24917 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7!/6) + 5 + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 24918 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times 6))) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 24919 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (76 \times (5 + (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 24920 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 76) \times (5 + (4 \times (3^2)))) + 1)) \\ 24921 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 24922 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times (6 - (5 \times 43))) - (2 + 1))) \\ 24923 &:= ((-9 + (-8 + 7 + 6)^5) \times 4 - 3) \times 2 + 1 \\ 24924 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 32)) + 1)) \\ 24925 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 - 5 \times (4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!)) \\ 24926 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 - 65) \times (432 - 1))) \\ 24927 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) - 1)))) \\ 24928 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 24929 &:= ((((-9 + 87)) \times -65) \times 4) - (32 - (1)) \\ 24930 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 24931 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 24932 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (76 \times ((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\ 24933 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times -(65 \times 4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 24934 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}))) + 1)) \\ 24935 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2} \times 1)))) \\ 24936 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + 6))) + (((5 \times 4)^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 24937 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times 76) \times (5 + (4 \times (3^2)))) \times -1) \\ 24938 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (76 \times (5 + (4 + 32)))) + 1)) \\ 24939 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 + 1))) \\ 24940 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 24941 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6) \times 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 24942 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((65 \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 24943 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) + 1)))) \\ 24944 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 24945 &:= (9 + (8 \times (((7 + 65) \times 43) + 21))) \\ 24946 &:= -9 \times 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5 \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)) \\ 24947 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 76) \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) - 2))) - 1) \\ 24948 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -((5 + ((4^3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\ 24949 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 76) \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) - 2))) + 1) \\ 24950 &:= (((9 + 87) \times -((-65 \times 4)) - (3^2)) - (1)) \\ 24951 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times -((76 + 54))) \times (3 + 21))) \\ 24952 &:= (((((-9 - 87) \times -65) \times 4) - (((3^2) - 1)))) \\ 24953 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 24954 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5^4))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 24955 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$24956 := ((1 \times (2 \times 34)) \times (((5 - (-6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))$$

$$24957 := (((-12 + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)$$

$$24958 := (-1 - (((2^3) \times (4 - (5^{6+7-8}))) + 9))$$

$$24959 := (-1 - (-((2+3) \times ((4-56) \times -((7+89))))))$$

$$24960 := (((1 \times (2 - 34)) \times -5) \times (67 + 89))$$

$$24961 := ((-1 + (2 + 3)^4) \times 5 + 6 - 7) \times 8 + 9$$

$$24962 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))))$$

$$24963 := 1 \times (2 + 3) \times (-4 \times (5 + 6) + 7!) - 8 - 9$$

$$24964 := (-12 + 34 \times 5)^{-6+7-8+9}$$

$$24965 := (-1 - ((2 - (((3 \times 4) + (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9))$$

$$24966 := (-1 \times (-(((2 \times 3)^4) - (((5 \times 6) \times 789))))$$

$$24967 := (((((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times 5)) + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)$$

$$24968 := ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) - 9$$

$$24969 := (((1 \times 23) \times ((4^5) - (-6 - ((7 \times 8)))))) - 9$$

$$24970 := ((1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) - 9$$

$$24971 := -1 \times 2 + (-3 - 4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$24972 := (-12 + (((-3 \times -4) + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9)))$$

$$24973 := ((1 + 2)^3 \times 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$24974 := ((-1 + (-((2 + 345)) \times (6 - 78))) - 9)$$

$$24975 := -(((1 \times (-((2 + 345)) \times (6 - 78))) + 9))$$

$$24976 := ((1 + (-((2 + 345)) \times (6 - 78))) - 9)$$

$$24977 := -((1 + ((-2 \times -3) \times (4 - ((-5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))))))$$

$$24978 := (-12 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))))$$

$$24979 := (1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (78 - 9)))$$

$$24980 := -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 5 - (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$24981 := (((12^3) \times ((4 \times 5) - 6)) + (789))$$

$$24982 := (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) - 9))$$

$$24983 := (-1 + ((-2^3) \times (4 - (((56 \times 7) \times 8) - 9))))$$

$$24984 := (((1 + 2) + (345 + 6)) - 7) \times -((8 \times -9))$$

$$24985 := (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (4 \times (5^{6+7-8})))) - 9)$$

$$24986 := ((1 \times 2) - (((3 \times 4) - (-5 \times 67)) \times -8) \times 9)$$

$$24987 := (((1 \times 23) \times ((4^5) - (-6 - ((7 \times 8)))))) + 9$$

$$24988 := -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times 6 \times 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$24989 := (123 - 4) \times 5 \times 6 \times 7 + 8 - 9$$

$$24990 := (-1 + 2) \times (3 + 4) \times 5 \times 6 \times 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$24991 := (-1 + 2) + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times 6 \times 7 \times (8 + 9)$$

$$24992 := ((-1 + (-((2 + 345)) \times (6 - 78))) + 9)$$

$$24993 := (-((-1 \times (-((2 + 345)) \times (6 - 78)))) + 9)$$

$$24994 := ((1 + (-((2 + 345)) \times (6 - 78))) + 9)$$

$$24995 := (-((((12 \times 34) + 5) \times (6 - (-7 \times 8)))) + 9)$$

$$24956 := (((-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5^4))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)$$

$$24957 := (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$24958 := ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 65) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1))$$

$$24959 := (-9 - (8 \times (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))$$

$$24960 := ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))$$

$$24961 := (((-9 + 87) \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3)/2))) + 1)$$

$$24962 := ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1))$$

$$24963 := ((((-9 \times - (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3)))^2) - 1)$$

$$24964 := (((-9 \times - (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3)))^2 \times 1)$$

$$24965 := ((((-9 \times - (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3)))^2) + 1)$$

$$24966 := (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 - (4^3)))))) + (2 \times 1)))$$

$$24967 := (((9 + 87) \times -((-65 \times 4))) - (3 \times -2)) + (1)$$

$$24968 := ((((-9 - 87) \times - (65 \times 4)) + (3^2)) - 1)$$

$$24969 := (9 - ((8 \times -((76 + 54))) \times (3 + 21)))$$

$$24970 := ((-98 \times (7 + 6)) + ((54 \times 3)^2 \times 1))$$

$$24971 := (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((65 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)$$

$$24972 := ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((65 \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1)))$$

$$24973 := (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times - (5 + (4 \times (3^{2+1}))))$$

$$24974 := ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (((65 - 4) \times 3) + 2))) - 1)$$

$$24975 := (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))))$$

$$24976 := ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (((65 - 4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1)$$

$$24977 := ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 65))) + 4) \times - (3 \times 2)) - 1)$$

$$24978 := (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 65))) + 4) \times - (3 + (2 + 1)))$$

$$24979 := ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 65))) + 4) \times - (3 \times 2)) + 1)$$

$$24980 := (((((-9 - 87) \times 6) - 5) \times -43) - (2 + 1))$$

$$24981 := (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1))$$

$$24982 := -9 + 8 \times (-7 + 6 + 5^4 \times (3 + 2)) - 1$$

$$24983 := -9 + 8 \times (-7 + 6 + 5^4 \times (3 + 2)) \times 1$$

$$24984 := -9 + 8 \times (-7 + 6 + 5^4 \times (3 + 2)) + 1$$

$$24985 := (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 + (6 \times (5 - (4^3)))))) + (2 - 1))$$

$$24986 := (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 + (6 \times (5 - (4^3)))))) + (2 \times 1))$$

$$24987 := (((-9 - 8) \times - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) - (2 + 1))$$

$$24988 := (((-9 - 8) \times - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) - (2 \times 1))$$

$$24989 := (((-9 - 8) \times - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) - (2 - 1))$$

$$24990 := (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (((5 + 4) - 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$24991 := (-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5)^{4+3/(2+1)})))$$

$$24992 := (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) - 1))$$

$$24993 := (((-9 - 8) \times - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))))) + (2 + 1))$$

$$24994 := (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)$$

$$24995 := ((-9 - 8)^7 + 6)^5 \times 4 - 3) \times 2 + 1$$

$$24996 := -((-12 - (((-3 \times -4) + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$24997 := -12 + ((3 + 45) \times 6 - 7) \times 89$$

$$24998 := -1 + ((-2 + 3 + 4)^5 - 6 + 7) \times 8 - 9$$

$$24999 := (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times ((56 - 7) - 89)))$$

$$25000 := (1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) \times -((56 - 7) - 89)))$$

$$25001 := (1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times -((56 - 7) - 89)))$$

$$25002 := (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4 \times 56) - (78 \times -9)))$$

$$25003 := -((1 - ((23 \times ((4^5) + 67)) - 89)))$$

$$25004 := (1 \times ((23 \times ((4^5) + 67)) - 89))$$

$$25005 := (1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + 67)) - 89))$$

$$25006 := ((-1 - 2) + (((3 + 45) \times 6) - 7) \times 89)$$

$$25007 := (((-1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$25008 := -((1^2) - (((3 + 45) \times 6) - 7) \times -89)$$

$$25009 := -((1^2) \times (((3 + 45) \times 6) - 7) \times -89)$$

$$25010 := ((1^2) - (((3 + 45) \times 6) - 7) \times -89)$$

$$25011 := ((-12 \times (((345 \times -6) - 7) - 8)) - 9)$$

$$25012 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - ((4 \times (5^{6+7-8})) + 9)))$$

$$25013 := -((12 \times ((345 \times -6) - 7)) + 89)$$

$$25014 := ((1 - 23) \times ((4 \times 5) - ((6 + 7) \times 89)))$$

$$25015 := (((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 + (4 \times (5^{6+7-8})))) + 9)$$

$$25016 := (-1 + ((((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6 - 7)) \times 8) + 9))$$

$$25017 := (((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) - (6 - 7)) \times 8) + 9)$$

$$25018 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))))$$

$$25019 := (-1 + (((2 + 34) \times ((5 + 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$25020 := (12 \times (-3 \times ((-4 + 5) + (6 + (-78 \times 9))))$$

$$25021 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times ((56 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))))$$

$$25022 := ((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + (5^{6+7-8})))) - 9)$$

$$25023 := (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 + 9)))$$

$$25024 := (-1 \times -((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 + 9)))$$

$$25025 := (((1^2) + 34) \times (-5 - 6)) \times (7 + ((-8 \times 9)))$$

$$25026 := (((-1 - 23) \times (-4^5)) - ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9))$$

$$25027 := (1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 - ((5 - (6 \times 78)) \times 9))))$$

$$25028 := (-1 + 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9)$$

$$25029 := ((12 - 3) \times -((45 \times (-6 - (7 \times 8)))) + (-9))$$

$$25030 := (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times 8)) + 9))$$

$$25031 := (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) \times 8)) - 9)$$

$$25032 := (-12 \times (3 - ((4 \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)))$$

$$25033 := 1 + 2^3 \times (4 + 5^{-67+8 \times 9});$$

$$25034 := 1 \times 2 + (3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6! - 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$24996 := (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)$$

$$24997 := ((-9 + 8) + ((-7 + 65) \times ((432 - 1))))$$

$$24998 := ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)$$

$$24999 := ((9 - 8) - ((7 - 65) \times (432 + (-1))))$$

$$25000 := ((-9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times -(5^{4+3/(2+1)}))$$

$$25001 := ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2})) + 1)$$

$$25002 := (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 - (4^3)))))) - (2 \times 1))$$

$$25003 := -((((9 + (87 \times (6 - 54))) \times -(-3)) \times 2) - 1)$$

$$25004 := (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1)$$

$$25005 := ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1))$$

$$25006 := (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1)$$

$$25007 := (-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))))$$

$$25008 := (((-9 \times 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5^4)) \times -(3 + (2 + 1)))$$

$$25009 := ((-9 - (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1)$$

$$25010 := ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times (5^4))/3) \times 2) + 1)$$

$$25011 := (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 - (4^3)))))) - (2 + 1))$$

$$25012 := (9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5! - 4) - 3!! - (2 + 1)!!$$

$$25013 := ((((-9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1)$$

$$25014 := (((-9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + (2 \times 1)))$$

$$25015 := ((((-9 + 8) + (76 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1)$$

$$25016 := (-98 - ((7 - 65) \times (432 + 1)))$$

$$25017 := ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1)$$

$$25018 := ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1))$$

$$25019 := ((-9 \times -((8 + ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) \times (3^2)))) - 1)$$

$$25020 := (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))))))$$

$$25021 := ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1))$$

$$25022 := ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1))$$

$$25023 := (-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))$$

$$25024 := ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 \times 1)))$$

$$25025 := (((-9 + ((8 \times 7))) + (6 \times 5)) \times -((-4) + (321)))$$

$$25026 := (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) - 5) \times -(((4^3) \times 2) + 1))$$

$$25027 := ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))$$

$$25028 := (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (6 \times 54))) \times (3^2)) - 1)$$

$$25029 := ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4)))) \times (3^{2+1}))$$

$$25030 := (-9 + ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$25031 := (-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))))$$

$$25032 := (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1))$$

$$25033 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - 65))) - 4) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)$$

$$25034 := (-9 - (((8 + 76) - 5) \times (4 - 321)))$$

- 25035** := $(-(((-1 - 23) \times (4^5))) + ((6 \times 78) - 9))$
25036 := $((1 - 23) \times (-4 + (5 - (67 \times (8 + 9))))$
25037 := $(-1 + (234 \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) + 89)))$
25038 := $((((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)$
25039 := $(-((-1 \times (2 - 345))) \times (-((-6 + 7)) + (8 \times -9)))$
25040 := $((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times ((56 - 7) - 89))$
25041 := $(-(((-(-12 - (-3 - 456))) \times -7) \times -8) - 9))$
25042 := $(1 + (((2^3) \times (4 + (5^{6+7-8}))) + 9))$
25043 := $((-1 + (((2^3) + 45) \times 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))$
25044 := $(-12 - (((-3 - 45) \times 6) \times (78 + 9)))$
25045 := $-1 + (-2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 - 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9)$
25046 := $((-1 + (((2 + 3)^{4-5+6}) + 7) \times 8) - 9)$
25047 := $((1 + 2) - (-((-3 \times -4)) \times (5 \times 6)) \times (78 - 9))$
25048 := $((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9)))$
25049 := $(((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) \times 8))) + 9)$
25050 := $((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))$
25051 := $((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (45 \times 6)))) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))$
25052 := $((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 + 9))))$
25053 := $(-((1 + 2) + (((3 + 45) \times -6) \times (78 + 9))))$
25054 := $(-1 \times (2 - ((3 + 45) \times (6 \times (78 + 9))))$
25055 := $((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9)$
25056 := $(((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)))) \times (8 \times 9))$
25057 := $((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) + (6 - 7)) \times -8) + 9)$
25058 := $((1 + (23 \times (4 - 5))) \times (67 \times (-8 - 9)))$
25059 := $(1 - ((23 - 45) \times (67 \times (8 + 9))))$
25060 := $((-1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
25061 := $-1 + 2 + (3!! - 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
25062 := $((-1 - 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9))$
25063 := $((-1 \times 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9))$
25064 := $(-1 + (((((2 + 3)^{4-5+6}) + 7) \times 8) + 9))$
25065 := $((1 + 2) + (3 \times 4)) \times (((5 \times 6) \times 7) \times 8) - 9)$
25066 := $((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9))))$
25067 := $((-1 \times -2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9))$
25068 := $(12 - (((-3 - 45) \times 6) \times (78 + 9)))$
25069 := $(-1 + (-23 \times (((-4^5) - (67 + 8)) + 9)))$
25070 := $((1 \times 23) \times ((4^5) - (-((67 + 8)) + 9)))$
25071 := $(((-1 - 23) \times ((-((4^5)) - (6 + 7)) - 8)) - 9)$
25072 := $((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) \times ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9))$
25073 := $((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9)$
25074 := $((((-((1 \times 2)) \times -3) \times (-456 - 7)) - 8) \times -9)$
- 25035** := $(((-9 \times 87) \times (-((-6 - 5)) - (43))) + (-21))$
25036 := $(((-9 + 87) \times ((6 \times 54) - 3)) - (2 \times 1))$
25037 := $(((-9 + 87) \times ((6 \times 54) - 3)) - (2 - 1))$
25038 := $(((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)$
25039 := $((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - 5))) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1}))$
25040 := $(((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1))$
25041 := $((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 + 1)))$
25042 := $(-((-9 \times -8)) + ((7 - 65) \times ((432 + 1))))$
25043 := $(((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times (6 - ((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))))$
25044 := $((9 - ((87 \times 6) \times (-5 - (43)))) - (21))$
25045 := $((-9 - (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1))$
25046 := $((-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2})))) - 1)$
25047 := $((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -6 + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)$
25048 := $(((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -6 + (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))$
25049 := $(-9 + (((87 \times (6 \times (5 + 43))) + 2) \times 1))$
25050 := $(-9 + (((87 \times (6 \times (5 + 43))) + 2) + 1))$
25051 := $((-9 \times -8) \times 7) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1))$
25052 := $(9 - ((8 + 76) - 5) \times (4 - 321))$
25053 := $(-98 - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))))$
25054 := $((-9 \times (87 \times ((6 + 5) - 43))) - (2 \times 1))$
25055 := $(-9 + (8 \times (7 + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) + 1))))$
25056 := $((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 - 6) \times 5) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))$
25057 := $(((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1)$
25058 := $((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1)))$
25059 := $(((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)$
25060 := $((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -6 + ((5^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))$
25061 := $(-98 - ((7 \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1))$
25062 := $(((-9 - 8) + ((76 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2))) - 1)$
25063 := $((-9 - 8) + ((76 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 \times 1))))$
25064 := $((-9 \times -((8 - 76) + (5^4))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)$
25065 := $(9 \times ((8 - (76 - (5^4))) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))$
25066 := $((-9 \times -((8 - 76) + (5^4))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)$
25067 := $(-98 - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))))$
25068 := $(-9 + ((87 \times (6 \times (5 + 43))) + 21))$
25069 := $-9 - 8 + (7! + 6) \times 5 - 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1)$
25070 := $((-9 \times -8) - ((7 - 65) \times (432 - 1)))$
25071 := $(-9 + (8 \times (((((7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3))^2) - 1)))$
25072 := $((-9 + ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4))) \times -((3^2) - 1))$
25073 := $((((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times -3^2) - 1)$
25074 := $(((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times -3 \times (2 + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned} 25075 &:= ((-1 + (-23 \times (-((4^5) - 67))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 25076 &:= ((1 \times (-23 \times (-((4^5) - 67))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 25077 &:= ((1 + ((-23 \times (-((4^5) - 67)) - 8)) - 9) \\ 25078 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(3 + (4 \times ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9)))) \\ 25079 &:= (((1 \times (2^3)) - 456) \times -((7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 25080 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) \times 6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 25081 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) \\ 25082 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9) \\ 25083 &:= ((((((1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) - 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\ 25084 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 25085 &:= ((1 \times 2) + ((-3 + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 25086 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4+5})) \times -6) + (7 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 25087 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 + 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 25088 &:= (1 - (23 - (45 \times ((-6 - (-7 \times -8)) \times -9)))) \\ 25089 &:= ((-12 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 25090 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\ 25091 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times (3 - (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\ 25092 &:= (1 \times ((-23 \times (-((4^5) - 67)) + (8 - 9))) \\ 25093 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (67 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 25094 &:= (1 - ((-23 \times (-((4^5) - 67)) \times (8 - 9))) \\ 25095 &:= ((1 + ((-23 \times (-((4^5) - 67)) - 8)) + 9) \\ 25096 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) - 456) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\ 25097 &:= (((1 \times (2^3)) - 456) \times -((7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 25098 &:= ((-12 - (-(((3 \times 4) - 5)) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 89) \\ 25099 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 25100 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 25101 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8)) - 9) \\ 25102 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 25103 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 + 7))) \times -8) - 9) \\ 25104 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 + ((5^{6+7-8}) + 9))) \\ 25105 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 3)) - (45 \times -(((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 25106 &:= ((1 - (-2 - (-((3 \times (4^5))) - 67) \times -8))) - 9) \\ 25107 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times -(((4 \times -5) + 6)) \times 78)) - 9) \\ 25108 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) + (45 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 25109 &:= (-1 + (-2 \times (3 \times -(((4^{5-6+7}) + 89)))))) \\ 25110 &:= ((-1 + (2^{(3-4) \times -5})) \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 25111 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + (45 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 25112 &:= (-1 + ((((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 + 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 25113 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 34) \times (-5 + (-((6 + 78) \times 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25075 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 25076 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (76 \times ((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\ 25077 &:= ((-9 \times (87 \times ((6 + 5) - 43))) + 21) \\ 25078 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 25079 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 25080 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (((7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 25081 &:= ((9 + (-8)) - ((76 \times (-((5 + 4)) - (321)))))) \\ 25082 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 43)))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 25083 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (((6 + 5) \times 4) \times (3^2)) + 1))) \\ 25084 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (5^4)))) \times -3) + 2) - 1) \\ 25085 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 25086 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times 6) \times (-5 - (43)))) + (21)) \\ 25087 &:= ((98 \times (76 + ((5 \times 4) \times (3^2)))) + (-1)) \\ 25088 &:= (-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\ 25089 &:= ((98 \times (76 + ((5 \times 4) \times (3^2)))) - (-1)) \\ 25090 &:= (((-98 \times (7 - (6 + 5))) \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25091 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4^3))))/2)) - 1) \\ 25092 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 25093 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4^3))))/2)) + 1) \\ 25094 &:= (((98 \times (((7 - 6) - 5)^4)) + (3 + 2)) - ((-1))) \\ 25095 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\ 25096 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\ 25097 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times -((4 + (321)))))) \\ 25098 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6 - ((5 \times 4) \times (3^{2+1}))) \\ 25099 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3^{2+1})))) \\ 25100 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 25101 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\ 25102 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 25103 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)))) \\ 25104 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1))) \\ 25105 &:= (9 - (8 \times ((7 \times ((6 - (5 \times 4)) \times 32)) - 1))) \\ 25106 &:= (((98 \times ((7 - (6 + 5))^4)) - 3) + (21)) \\ 25107 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 76) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 21))) \\ 25108 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 25109 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))))) - 1) \\ 25110 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 25111 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))))) + 1) \\ 25112 &:= ((-9 \times -((876 + 54) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25113 &:= (((-9 \times -((876 + 54) \times 3)) + 2) - (-1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25114 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + (45 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 25115 &:= (-1 - (23 \times ((-4^5) + (-67 - (-8 + 9)))) \\ 25116 &:= ((1 \times 23) \times (-((-4^5) - 67)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 25117 &:= (1 + (23 \times (-((-4^5) - 67)) - (8 - 9))) \\ 25118 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 25119 &:= (((12^3) - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9 \\ 25120 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 25121 &:= ((-((1 + 23)) \times -((4^5))) - ((-67 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 25122 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25123 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + 67) \times 8) + 9) \\ 25124 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (((4 \times 5) - 6) \times 78)) + 9)) \\ 25125 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -((4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\ 25126 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times 8))) - 9) \\ 25127 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 25128 &:= (1 \times ((2^3) \times (-4 - ((56 \times -((7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\ 25129 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9 \\ 25130 &:= (1 + (((2^3) \times (4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 25131 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 25132 &:= ((-1 + 23) + (45 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 25133 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + (45 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 25134 &:= ((1 + 23) + (45 \times ((-6 - (-7 \times -8)) \times -9))) \\ 25135 &:= ((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times -8) - 9 \\ 25136 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) + 5) \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 25137 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) + 5) \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 25138 &:= ((1^2) - ((-3 - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 25139 &:= ((1 \times 2) + ((-3 - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times -9)) \\ 25140 &:= -(((((-12 - 3) \times -4) \times (-5 - (-6 \times (-78 + 9)))) \\ 25141 &:= (1 - 2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25142 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (-4 - 5 - 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 25143 &:= ((-((1 - 234)) + 56) \times (78 + 9)) \\ 25144 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times 8)) + 9)) \\ 25145 &:= -((((1 - 234) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) + 89))) \\ 25146 &:= ((-123 - 4) \times -((-56 + 78) \times 9)) \\ 25147 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 \times (456 + 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\ 25148 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((56 \times 7) - 89))) \\ 25149 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 25150 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((56 \times 7) - 89))) \\ 25151 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))) \\ 25152 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times 3) \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 25153 &:= ((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times -8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25114 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (-((7 - 65)) \times (432 - (-1)))) \\ 25115 &:= ((9 - 8) + (-((7 - 65)) \times (432 - (-1)))) \\ 25116 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 25117 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -(6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3) \times 2))) + 1) \\ 25118 &:= ((9 + ((87 + 6) \times (54 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 25119 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 25120 &:= (((-98/7) - 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 25121 &:= ((((-98/7) - 6) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 25122 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5 + ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\ 25123 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6) \times (54 - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 25124 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times 6) + 5) \times -((43 + 2) - 1)) \\ 25125 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 76)) \times 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 25126 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6 \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1))) \\ 25127 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 25128 &:= ((9 \times 8) \times (((7 - (6 \times -54)) - (3 - 21)))) \\ 25129 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\ 25130 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times (54 + 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25131 &:= (((-9 \times (876 + 54)) \times -3) + ((21))) \\ 25132 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7! - 6! \times 5 - 4) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 25133 &:= ((((-9 \times ((87 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times -3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 25134 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1)))) \\ 25135 &:= ((((-9 \times ((87 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times -3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 25136 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 25137 &:= (-9 \times (87 - (((6 \times 5) \times 4) \times ((3 + 21)))) \\ 25138 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\ 25139 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (76 \times ((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1))) \\ 25140 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\ 25141 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) \times 1)))) \\ 25142 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\ 25143 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) - 1) \\ 25144 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 25145 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - (65 \times 43))) - 2) + 1) \\ 25146 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - 7) - ((65 \times 43) \times (2 - (1)))) \\ 25147 &:= ((((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\ 25148 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)))) \\ 25149 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - (65 \times 43))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25150 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 - 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 25151 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\ 25152 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((76 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\ 25153 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((76 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25154 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 25155 &:= (((1 - 234) \times -((5 \times 6) - 78)) - 9) \\ 25156 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 25157 &:= (1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 25158 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 \times (-6 + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 25159 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 25160 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 25161 &:= (-1 - (23 \times (45 - (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\ 25162 &:= (-1 \times (23 \times (45 - (67 \times (8 + 9))))) \\ 25163 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 25164 &:= -(((((-12^3) + (45 + 6)) \times (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\ 25165 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 34)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\ 25166 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (3 + (4 \times ((56 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\ 25167 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 89))))))) \\ 25168 &:= ((1 - 23) \times -((4 \times ((5 \times (67 - 8)) - 9))) \\ 25169 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) + (7 \times 89)) \\ 25170 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) + (7 \times 89)) \\ 25171 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4)! \times 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25172 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9))) \\ 25173 &:= (((1 - 234) \times -((5 \times 6) - 78)) + 9) \\ 25174 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (45 + 6)))) \times (7 - 89)) \\ 25175 &:= (-(((1 \times 2) + 3)) \times (-4 - ((567 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 25176 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\ 25177 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - 5) \times 6) + 7) \times -(8 + 9) \\ 25178 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4! + 5 + 6) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25179 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 25180 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25181 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 25182 &:= (1 \times ((23 \times ((4^5) + 67)) + 89)) \\ 25183 &:= (((1 - (2 - (3 + 45))) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9) \\ 25184 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))))) \\ 25185 &:= ((1 \times 23) \times ((4^5) - ((-6 - ((7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 25186 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times 6)) + 7) \times 89)) \\ 25187 &:= (((1 \times (234 + 56)) - 7) \times 89) \\ 25188 &:= (1 + ((-234) - (56 - 7)) \times -89) \\ 25189 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 25190 &:= (-1 - (((((-2 - 3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\ 25191 &:= (((123 - 4) + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9) \\ 25192 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 25193 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25154 &:= (((9 \times (8 - 7)) \times 65) \times 43) - ((2 - 1)) \\ 25155 &:= (((9 \times 8) - 7) \times (((6 \times 54) - (-3 \times 21)))) \\ 25156 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1)) \\ 25157 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1)))) \\ 25158 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 25159 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1) \\ 25160 &:= (((-98) \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 - (43 - 2)) - 1) \\ 25161 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + 6) \times -((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 25162 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + (65 \times 43))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25163 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1))) \\ 25164 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 25165 &:= ((98 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5 \times -43))) - (21)) \\ 25166 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + (65 \times 43))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25167 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6 + 5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))) \\ 25168 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times (6 \times 5)) + 4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\ 25169 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) - 1) \\ 25170 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 25171 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1)) \\ 25172 &:= ((-9 \times -87) + (((6 \times 5) - (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 25173 &:= (-9 \times ((-8 + 7) + ((65 \times -43) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 25174 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\ 25175 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5^4) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 25176 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + 5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\ 25177 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (6 + (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)))) \\ 25178 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times 6)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 25179 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times 6)) + ((5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + 1)) \\ 25180 &:= (9 - 8) \times (7! - 6) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 25181 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7)) - ((65 \times 43) + 2)) - 1) \\ 25182 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 25183 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 25184 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) - 1))) \\ 25185 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 25186 &:= (-98 \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25187 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 25188 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3^{2+1})))) \\ 25189 &:= ((-98 \times -(((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25190 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) \times -((5^4) - 3)/2)) - 1) \\ 25191 &:= (987 - 6 \times (5 + 4)) \times 3^{2+1} \\ 25192 &:= (-(((9 - (8 \times -7)) - 6) \times (5 - 432))) - 1) \\ 25193 &:= (-(((9 - (8 \times -7)) - 6) \times (5 - 432))) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$25194 := ((-123 + (4 + 5)) \times (-6 - 7)) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$25195 := -1 + 2 + 3! \times (4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$25196 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (-4 + 5 \times 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$25197 := (-12 + ((((((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$25198 := (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + 4) \times ((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9))))$$

$$25199 := (((12/3) \times ((4^5) \times 6)) - (-7 \times 89))$$

$$25200 := (((-1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9))))))$$

$$25201 := (((1 - (2 - (3 + 45))) \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)$$

$$25202 := (-1 \times -(2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9))))$$

$$25203 := ((-12 \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 - 7)/8)) - 9)$$

$$25204 := (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9$$

$$25205 := (((-1 - (2^{3+4+5})) \times -6) + (7 \times 89))$$

$$25206 := ((-1 - 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$25207 := ((-1 \times 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$25208 := (-1 - ((2 - (((3^{4+5}) - 6)/7) - 8)) \times 9)$$

$$25209 := (((1 + 2) + (3 \times 4)) \times (((5 \times 6) \times 7) \times 8)) + 9)$$

$$25210 := ((-1 + 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$25211 := ((-1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))$$

$$25212 := (-12 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 - ((67 - 8) \times 9))))$$

$$25213 := (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 \times 789)))$$

$$25214 := (((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (6 \times 789))$$

$$25215 := (-1 + ((2 - 34) \times -((5 - 6) + 789))))$$

$$25216 := (-((1 \times 2) - 34)) \times ((5 - 6) + 789))$$

$$25217 := (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times ((56 \times 7) + 8))) \times 9))$$

$$25218 := (((((12^3) - (-4^5)) + (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9)$$

$$25219 := ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))))$$

$$25220 := (((1 - ((2 - ((3^4)) \times -5)) + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))$$

$$25221 := ((-12 \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 - 7)/8)) + 9)$$

$$25222 := -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4! + 5 + 6) + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$25223 := (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times 6) + (7 \times 89))$$

$$25224 := ((-1 - 2) + ((((((3^{4+5}) - 6)/7) - 8) \times 9))$$

$$25225 := ((-1 \times 2) + ((((((3^{4+5}) - 6)/7) - 8) \times 9))$$

$$25226 := (-1 + ((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$25227 := (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))$$

$$25228 := (-1 \times -((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))$$

$$25229 := ((-1 \times -2) + ((((((3^{4+5}) - 6)/7) - 8) \times 9))$$

$$25230 := (((-1 \times 234) - 56) \times (-78 - 9))$$

$$25231 := (1 - (-((234 + 56)) \times (78 + 9)))$$

$$25232 := (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times ((-5 \times (67 - 8)) - 9))$$

$$25233 := (123 + (45 \times ((6 + (7 \times 8) \times 9)))$$

$$25194 := (-(((9 - (8 \times -7)) - 6) \times (5 - 432))) + 1$$

$$25195 := (((((-98 - 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) + 3) \times -2) + 1)$$

$$25196 := (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6! \times 5 - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$25197 := (((9 \times 8) \times (7 + ((6 + (5 - 4))^3))) - (2 + 1))$$

$$25198 := (((-9 \times 8) \times -(7 + (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) - (2 \times 1))$$

$$25199 := (((9 \times 8) \times (((7 + 6) + (54 \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1)$$

$$25200 := (-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (((6 + 5) \times 4) + (3 + (2 + 1))))))$$

$$25201 := ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 \times (3 + 2)))))) + 1)$$

$$25202 := (((9 \times 8) \times (7 + ((6 + (5 - 4))^3))) + ((2 \times 1)))$$

$$25203 := (((9 - (876 - 54)) \times -((32 - 1)))$$

$$25204 := (9 - 8) \times 7 \times 6! \times 5 + 4! / (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$25205 := ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2))) - 1)$$

$$25206 := (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2 \times 1)))$$

$$25207 := ((98 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5 \times -43))) + (21))$$

$$25208 := ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 \times 3)^2))) - 1)$$

$$25209 := (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - ((6 + 5) \times (4^{3+2-1}))))$$

$$25210 := ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 \times 3)^2))) + 1)$$

$$25211 := (((98 + (-76) \times -54)) \times -((3 \times -2))) - 1)$$

$$25212 := ((-9 + (8 + 765)) \times (((4^3)/2) + 1))$$

$$25213 := (((-98 - (76 \times 54)) \times -3 \times 2) + 1)$$

$$25214 := (98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3^{2+1}))))$$

$$25215 := (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - ((3^2) + 1)))$$

$$25216 := (((-98 \times ((7 + 6) - 5)) - 4) \times -32 \times 1))$$

$$25217 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) + 2)) - 1)$$

$$25218 := (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) + (2 \times 1)))$$

$$25219 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) + 2)) + 1)$$

$$25220 := ((-9 + (87 \times ((6 \times (5 + 43)) + 2))) - 1)$$

$$25221 := (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2) + 1)))$$

$$25222 := (-9 + ((87 \times ((6 \times (5 + 43)) + 2)) + 1))$$

$$25223 := ((((-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) / 4) \times -3 \times 2) - 1)$$

$$25224 := ((((-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) / 4) \times -3 + (2 + 1)))$$

$$25225 := ((((-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)) / 4) \times -3 \times 2) + 1)$$

$$25226 := ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1))$$

$$25227 := (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) + (2 + 1)))$$

$$25228 := ((-9 - 8) \times -7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + (2 \times 1)))$$

$$25229 := (((-9 - 8) \times -7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + 2))) + 1)$$

$$25230 := ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)$$

$$25231 := ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1))$$

$$25232 := (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))$$

$$25233 := ((-98 \times -7) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25234 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 34)) \times (5 - (678 + 9))) \\ 25235 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 34) \times ((5 - 6) - ((-78 \times 9)))) \\ 25236 &:= (((-((1 + 2)) \times 3) \times 4) \times ((-5 + 6) - (78 \times 9))) \\ 25237 &:= (1 - ((2 + (((3 - 45) \times 67) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 25238 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 25239 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 25240 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25241 &:= -1 + 2 - 3 - 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 25242 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 25243 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 25244 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) / 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 25245 &:= (((12 + 3) - (45 \times (-6 - (7 \times 8)))) \times -(-9)) \\ 25246 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - 456) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 25247 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) + (78 \times 9)) \\ 25248 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (34 + (-5 + 6))) \times 789) \\ 25249 &:= ((-123 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 89) \\ 25250 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!)! + 4) \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25251 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 25252 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (((3 - 45) \times 67) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 25253 &:= (-1 - (23 \times (-((-4 \times (5 + 6)) - 78)) \times -9)) \\ 25254 &:= ((1 \times -2) \times ((3 \times ((-4 - 5) \times (6 \times 78))) + 9)) \\ 25255 &:= (((-1 + (((2 - (3 - 4)^5) \times (6 + 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 25256 &:= (((1 - 23) \times ((-4 \times 5) + 6)) \times -((7 - 89))) \\ 25257 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 25258 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 345)) \times -((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 25259 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 + 4) \times 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25260 &:= (-12 - ((3 - (45 - 6)) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 25261 &:= -1 + (-2 - 3 \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 25262 &:= (((-((-1 - 2) - 34)) \times (5 + (678))) - 9) \\ 25263 &:= (((1 \times -2) \times (3 \times ((-4 - 5) \times (6 \times 78)))) - 9) \\ 25264 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - 456) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\ 25265 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 4)) \times (5 + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 25266 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -((4 - 5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 25267 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (67 + 8)))) - 9) \\ 25268 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (67 + 8))) - 9) \\ 25269 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25270 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 25271 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)) - 9)))) \\ 25272 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (3^4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times (-7 - 8))) + 9)) \\ 25273 &:= (1 - (234 \times ((5 + 6) + (7 \times (-8 - 9))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25234 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 25235 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 25236 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 + 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\ 25237 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)))) \\ 25238 &:= (((98 \times 7) - (6 \times ((5 - (4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\ 25239 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 25240 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 25241 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 25242 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times -7) \times (6 \times (((5^4) - 3) - (21)))) \\ 25243 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1) \\ 25244 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 43)) + 2))) - 1) \\ 25245 &:= (9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\ 25246 &:= (9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) - 2 \times 1 \\ 25247 &:= (9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) - 2 + 1 \\ 25248 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\ 25249 &:= (9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) + 2 - 1 \\ 25250 &:= (9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) + 2 \times 1 \\ 25251 &:= (9 + 87) \times (65 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\ 25252 &:= (((-987) - (6 - ((54 \times 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 25253 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 25254 &:= -((((9 - (87)) \times -6) \times -54) + (-((3 - 21)))) \\ 25255 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 25256 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 25257 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3^2))) + 1) \\ 25258 &:= (-987 + (((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 25259 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) \times -1) \\ 25260 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - 543)) + 21) \\ 25261 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! + 6) \times (-5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1) \\ 25262 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 \times 54)) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 25263 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4)))) + 3) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 25264 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 - (6 + 54)) \times -3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 25265 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 25266 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 \times 54)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 25267 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 \times 54)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 25268 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 \times 54)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 25269 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 25270 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25271 &:= (-((9 \times (8 \times ((76 + 5) - 432)))) - (1)) \\ 25272 &:= (((-9 \times -8) \times (7 + 6)) \times (54 - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 25273 &:= (-((9 \times (8 \times ((76 + 5) - 432)))) + (1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 25274** := $(-1 \times -(2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))))$ **25274** := $((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) + (2 \times 1))$
25275 := $((-12 - 3) \times (4 - ((5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)))$ **25275** := $((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) + (2 + 1))$
25276 := $(((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7)) \times 89)$ **25276** := $(((-9 + 87) \times (6 \times 54)) + ((3 + 2) - 1))$
25277 := $(-1 \times (23 \times ((-4^5) - ((6 + 78) - 9))))$ **25277** := $(-(((9 - 87) \times (6 \times 54))) - ((-3 - (2 \times 1))))$
25278 := $((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))$ **25278** := $(((((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) - 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1))$
25279 := $(-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times ((56 \times 7) - (8 \times 9))))$ **25279** := $(-9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)))$
25280 := $(-1 \times -(((2 - 34) \times ((5 - 6) - 789))))$ **25280** := $(((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) / (5 - (4 + 3))))^2) - 1)$
25281 := $((1 \times -2) \times (3 \times ((-4 - 5) \times (6 \times 78)))) + 9$ **25281** := $((9 + 87) - (-6 - (54 + 3)))^2 \times 1$
25282 := $(1 - ((234 \times ((5 \times -6) - 78)) - 9))$ **25282** := $(((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) / (5 - (4 + 3))))^2) + 1)$
25283 := $(-1 \times 2 + 3 + 4) \times (5! / 6 + 7!) - 8 - 9$ **25283** := $(((((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) - 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1))$
25284 := $(12 - ((3 - (45 - 6)) \times (78 \times 9)))$ **25284** := $((98 + (7 \times 6)) / 5) \times ((43 \times 21))$
25285 := $((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (((5^6) + 7) / 8) - 9)$ **25285** := $((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times (4 + (3^2))) - 1))$
25286 := $(-1 \times ((23 \times ((-4^5) - (67 + 8))) - 9))$ **25286** := $((98 \times 7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1)))$
25287 := $((-(-1) - (23 \times ((-4^5) - (67 + 8)))) + 9)$ **25287** := $(-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))))$
25288 := $(1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) + 5 \times 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9$ **25288** := $(-9 + ((8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1))$
25289 := $(-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)))) \times 9))$ **25289** := $((987 \times (6 \times 5)) - (4321))$
25290 := $((-((1 \times 2)) + ((34 + 5) \times (6 - 78))) \times -9)$ **25290** := $(-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + (6 / (5 - (4 + 3))))^2) + 1))$
25291 := $(1 + ((2 - ((3 - (45 - 6)) \times 78)) \times 9))$ **25291** := $((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) + 2)) + 1)$
25292 := $(1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9$ **25292** := $((-98 \times -7) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1}))))$
25293 := $((-12 \times -(3 + ((45 \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) + 9)$ **25293** := $((-98 \times -7) + ((6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1))$
25294 := $(-1 \times (2 - ((3 + 45) \times ((67 \times 8) - 9))))$ **25294** := $9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! \times 5 + 4) - 3 - 2 - 1$
25295 := $((12 \times -34) \times (5 - 67)) + (8 - 9)$ **25295** := $(((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2}))) - 1)$
25296 := $((1 \times 2) \times (3 \times 4)) \times ((-5 + 67) \times (8 + 9))$ **25296** := $((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2} \times 1)))$
25297 := $((12 \times -34) \times (5 - 67)) - (8 - 9)$ **25297** := $(((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2}))) + 1)$
25298 := $(-((12 - (34 \times -5)) \times (-67 - ((8 \times 9))))$ **25298** := $((-98) + 7) \times (-((65 \times 4) - ((-3 + (21))))$
25299 := $((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))$ **25299** := $(-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))) + (2 + 1)))$
25300 := $((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 89)))$ **25300** := $((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) - 6) \times (5^4) - 3) / 2) + 1)$
25301 := $(1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 89))))$ **25301** := $(((((9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) - 5) \times -(4^3)) + 21)$
25302 := $((-1 + 2) - (3 + 4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))$ **25302** := $9 \times 8 + (7! + 6) \times (-5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1)$
25303 := $(-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9))))$ **25303** := $(-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times (4 + 3)) - (2 + 1))))$
25304 := $((1 \times 2)^{3 \times 4} \times 5) + ((-67 \times -8) \times 9)$ **25304** := $(-(((9 - 87) \times 6) \times 54) - 32) \times 1$
25305 := $((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9$ **25305** := $((98 + 7) \times ((-6 - 5) - ((4 \times (-3 \times 21))))$
25306 := $-1 \times (2 + 3 + 4) + 5 \times (6 + 7! + 8 + 9)$ **25306** := $(9 + ((8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1))$
25307 := $(-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times 6) + (78 \times 9))$ **25307** := $((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1)))$
25308 := $(((-1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) / (6 - (7 - 8))) \times 9$ **25308** := $(-9 \times -(((8 + 7) - 6) \times (5^4) - 3) / 2) + 1)$
25309 := $((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4})) \times -5) + (67 \times (8 \times 9))$ **25309** := $((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + (((54 \times 3)^2) + 1))$
25310 := $((12 + 3)^4 - 5) / (-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$ **25310** := $-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5 \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!))$
25311 := $(((((1 + 2)^3) - (456 \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)$ **25311** := $(((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times (43 \times 2)) - 1))$
25312 := $((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 + 9))))$ **25312** := $((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) - 1))$
25313 := $((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 - 67)))) \times -(8 + 9))$ **25313** := $(((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 25314 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) & 25314 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1)))) \\ 25315 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times (((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) & 25315 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1)) \\ 25316 &:= (-1 + ((23 + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) & 25316 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times 43) + 2)))) - 1) \\ 25317 &:= ((1 + (234 + 56)) \times (-(-78) + 9)) & 25317 &:= (-9 \times -((((((8 + 7) - 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)/2) - 1)) \\ 25318 &:= (1 + ((2345 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)) & 25318 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times 43) + 2)))) + 1) \\ 25319 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3^4) \times 5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9) & 25319 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1))) \\ 25320 &:= (-12 \times -((((3 + 4)^5) - (6 - 7))/8) + 9) & 25320 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times 5) + ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 25321 &:= (((-123 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - 8) - 9) & 25321 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)))) \\ 25322 &:= (-1 - (23 \times (4 - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) & 25322 &:= -9 + 8 + 7! \times 6 + 5! - (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\ 25323 &:= ((1 \times 23) \times (-(((4 \times -5) + 6) \times 78) + 9)) & 25323 &:= ((-9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 25324 &:= (((-123 \times 4) + 5) \times -((6 \times 78)/9)) & 25324 &:= (-9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\ 25325 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 + 5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))) & 25325 &:= ((-9 \times -((((((8 + 7) - 6) \times (5^4)) + 3)/2) - 1)) \\ 25326 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times ((-3 \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times 78))) \times 9)) & 25326 &:= (9 - (87 \times (((6 \times -54) + 32) + 1))) \\ 25327 &:= (((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9) & 25327 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))) \\ 25328 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3^4) \times 5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9) & 25328 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\ 25329 &:= ((-123 \times -((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 8)) - 9) & 25329 &:= ((-9 \times -87) - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 25330 &:= ((-1 + (((23 \times (4 + 5)) + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)) & 25330 &:= ((-9 \times -87) - ((6 \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\ 25331 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 345) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) & 25331 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times 65) - 4) \times (3 + 2) + 1) \\ 25332 &:= (-12 \times -((3 + (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (78 + 9)))))) & 25332 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 25333 &:= -1 + (-2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7 + 8 + 9) & 25333 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 25334 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3)^4) - 5) \times 6) + (789)) & 25334 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 25335 &:= (((1 \times 2) + 3) \times (4 + (567 - 8))) \times 9 & 25335 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times -((4 \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 25336 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 5) \times 6) + 789) & 25336 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 25337 &:= ((-123 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (-8 + 9)) & 25337 &:= (9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1))) \\ 25338 &:= (-123 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))))) & 25338 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\ 25339 &:= ((-123 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 - 9)) & 25339 &:= ((-9 \times -87 \times (6 \times 5)) + (43^2 \times 1)) \\ 25340 &:= 12 \times (3^{4+5} - 678)/9 & 25340 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) \times -1) \\ 25341 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)))) \times -78) - 9) & 25341 &:= ((987 \times (6 - (-5 \times 4))) + (-321)) \\ 25342 &:= (-1 - (((23 - (456 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) & 25342 &:= ((-9 - (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) \times -1) \\ 25343 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times (4 + (5 + 6))) + 7) \times (8 \times 9))) & 25343 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 + (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) + 2))) - 1) \\ 25344 &:= ((12 \times (34 - 56)) \times -((7 + 89))) & 25344 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (((5 + 4) - 3)^{2+1})))) \\ 25345 &:= (((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9) & 25345 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\ 25346 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times (4 + 5)) + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 25346 &:= (((-9 + ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25347 &:= ((-123 \times (-4 - ((-5 \times (-6 \times 7)) - 8))) + 9) & 25347 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 25348 &:= (1 + (((23 \times (4 + 5)) + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 25348 &:= (9 \times (-8 - 7 + 6!) - 5) \times 4 - 3! - (2 + 1)! \\ 25349 &:= (-1 + ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times 56)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 25349 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2)) - 1) \\ 25350 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times -((5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) & 25350 &:= ((9 - (8 \times -7)) \times -((-65) + ((4 + 321)))) \\ 25351 &:= ((((-1 + 23) - ((456 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9) & 25351 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2)) + 1) \\ 25352 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3^{4+5}) - 6)/7) + 8)) \times 9) & 25352 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 \times 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 25353 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + ((4 + 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9) & 25353 &:= ((9 \times 8) + ((((-7 + 6) + 54) \times -3)^2 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25354 &:= (1234 + ((5 \times 67) \times (8 \times 9))) & 25354 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 \times 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 25355 &:= ((-123 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 + 9)) & 25355 &:= (9 + 8) \times 7 + 6 + 5 \times ((4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!) \\ 25356 &:= (-12 \times (3 - (4 \times ((5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9)))) & 25356 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2) + 1) \\ 25357 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (((3 - 456) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) & 25357 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times 54) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25358 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3 - 456) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)) & 25358 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times (4 + 3)) - 2)))) - 1) \\ 25359 &:= (((1^2) \times -((3 - 456) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) & 25359 &:= (((9 + 8) - 76) + (-5 \times 4)) \times -(321)) \\ 25360 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times -((5 + 6) + (7 \times 89))) & 25360 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times (4 + 3)) - 2)))) + 1) \\ 25361 &:= (((1 \times -23) + (456 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9 & 25361 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times 54) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25362 &:= -(((-(-1) + 2) - ((3 + ((4 \times (-5 - 67)))) \times -89))) & 25362 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 25363 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 67))) \times 89))) & 25363 &:= -9 - 8 - 7! + (6 \times 5 + (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)! \\ 25364 &:= ((-1 - (((23 \times (4 + 5)) + 6) \times 7)) \times -8) + 9 & 25364 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times (5! + 4) - 3! / (2 + 1)!) \\ 25365 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7)) \times 89)) & 25365 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) - (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 25366 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) - (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) & 25366 &:= (9 \times (-8 - 7 + 6!) - 5) \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 25367 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) - 9) & 25367 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times ((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1))) \\ 25368 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^{4+5}) - 6) / 7) + 8) \times 9 & 25368 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - ((6 + 5) \times (4^3))) \times -21) \\ 25369 &:= ((((-1 + 23) - ((456 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) & 25369 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) \times -5 \times (43 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 25370 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3^{4+5}) - 6) / 7) + 8) \times 9 & 25370 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) \times -5 \times (43 \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 25371 &:= (((12 \times ((3 \times -45) - 6)) \times (-7 - 8)) - 9) & 25371 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) + (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1)) \\ 25372 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^{4+5}) - 6) / 7) + 8) \times 9 & 25372 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25373 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^{4+5}) - 6) / 7) + 8) \times 9 & 25373 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 25374 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 - 456)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 25374 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3 \times (2 - 1)) \\ 25375 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) & 25375 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times 5)))) \times ((4 \times 3)^2) + 1) \\ 25376 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3 - 456) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 25376 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25377 &:= (((1^2) \times -((3 - 456) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9) & 25377 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25378 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + 78) \times 9))) & 25378 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((-765) - 4) \times (32 + 1))) \\ 25379 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + -((3 - 456)) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) & 25379 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 25380 &:= ((-1 + ((23 - 4))) \times ((5 \times 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) & 25380 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -5 \times (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25381 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) & 25381 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 \times 5) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\ 25382 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + 78)) \times 9))) & 25382 &:= ((98 \times 7) \times (((-6 + (54)) / 3) + (21))) \\ 25383 &:= ((-12 \times -(((34 \times -((5 - 67))) + 8)) - 9) & 25383 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) - (4 - 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 25384 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9) & 25384 &:= (((98 \times 7) \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) + 3)) - (2 \times (-1))) \\ 25385 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9) & 25385 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25386 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -(4^5)) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) & 25386 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - (6^5)) \times -((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 25387 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 + (45 \times (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) & 25387 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - (6^5)) \times -4 - (3 - 2)) + 1) \\ 25388 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3^{4+5}) + 6)) / 7) + 8) \times 9) & 25388 &:= ((((-9 \times -87) + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 25389 &:= (((12 \times ((3 \times -45) - 6)) \times (-7 - 8)) + 9) & 25389 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25390 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) - (678 \times 9))) & 25390 &:= ((-9 \times -87) + ((6 \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2})))) + 1) \\ 25391 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))))) & 25391 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) - 1) \\ 25392 &:= (12 + ((-3 \times -((4^5)) + 6) + 78) \times 9) & 25392 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times -((4 + 3)^2) - 1) \\ 25393 &:= (((1 \times (-2 - ((-3 + 456) \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) & 25393 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25394 &:= ((12^3) - (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 25395 &:= (-((12 + 3)) \times ((-4^5) - (678 - 9))) \\ 25396 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (((3 - 45) \times 67) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 25397 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 25398 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 25399 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) - (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\ 25400 &:= ((1 \times (2^3)) \times ((456 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\ 25401 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) - (-5 \times -6)) \times (7 + 8)) - 9) \\ 25402 &:= ((12^3) + (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 789)))) \\ 25403 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6) + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 25404 &:= (((-1 - 23) - (45 \times -6)) \times (78 + 9)) \\ 25405 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 25406 &:= (-1 + ((23 + 4) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25407 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)))) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 25408 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) \times (4 - 567)) - 8) \times 9) \\ 25409 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25410 &:= ((-123 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 25411 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times ((5^6) + 7) / 8) + 9) \\ 25412 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 25413 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 25414 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25415 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) \times - (8 + 9)) \\ 25416 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + 7)))) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 25417 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 25418 &:= (-1 \times - (2 + (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25419 &:= (((((12^3) - 4) - (-5 \times -6)) \times (7 + 8)) + 9) \\ 25420 &:= ((((-1 \times - (2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9))) \\ 25421 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9))) \\ 25422 &:= (-((123 - (456 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 25423 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) \times -8) - 9) \\ 25424 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (45 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 25425 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\ 25426 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times (45 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 25427 &:= ((-123 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + 89) \\ 25428 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)) - 9) \\ 25429 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 25430 &:= (-1 + 23^4) / (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25431 &:= (((-12 + (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 25432 &:= (-1 - (((23 \times (4 \times 5)) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25394 &:= ((-9 + (876 \times (((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2))) - 1) \\ 25395 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 25396 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25397 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + 2) - 1) \\ 25398 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 25399 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + 2) + 1) \\ 25400 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3^2)) + 1)) \\ 25401 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25402 &:= -9 + 8 + 7 \times (-6 + 5 \times (4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!)) \\ 25403 &:= ((-98 \times - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3)))) + 21) \\ 25404 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 - 6)) \times - (5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 25405 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times - (4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 25406 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times - (4^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25407 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 5)) + 4) \times - (3^{2+1})) \\ 25408 &:= (((-9 \times 87) - (6 + 5)) \times - ((4^3) / (2 \times 1))) \\ 25409 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times - ((4^3) + 2)) - 1) \\ 25410 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times - ((4^3) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 25411 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times - ((4^3) + 2)) + 1) \\ 25412 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((6 \times 54) - 32))) - 1) \\ 25413 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times - (5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 25414 &:= -(((9 + (-87) \times ((6 \times 54) - 32))) - 1)) \\ 25415 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times (4 - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 25416 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times - (7 + (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 25417 &:= ((-9 \times - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 25418 &:= (((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times (-4 - 3)) + 2) - 1) \\ 25419 &:= (((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times (-4 - 3)) + 2) \times 1) \\ 25420 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 25421 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 25422 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times - (2 + 1) \\ 25423 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((65 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)))) \\ 25424 &:= ((-9 + ((87 - 6) \times (((5^4) + 3) / 2))) - 1) \\ 25425 &:= (-9 \times - ((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 25426 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25427 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 25428 &:= ((-9 + 87) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 25429 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 - 65)) \times (432 + (-1))) \\ 25430 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25431 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3^2)))) - 1)) \\ 25432 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times - ((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - (3 + 21))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25433 &:= (((-1 - ((-2 + 3) - 456)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) & 25433 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) \times -(((5^4) + 3)/2)) - 1) \\ 25434 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(3 \times ((4 + (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) & 25434 &:= -(((9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + (((54 \times 3)^2) \times (-1)))) \\ 25435 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((456 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)))) & 25435 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) \times -(((5^4) + 3)/2)) + 1) \\ 25436 &:= (1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 + (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 25436 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) + 5 \times ((4 + 3)! + 2 + 1) \\ 25437 &:= (-1 - (-23 \times (((4 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 + ((8 \times 9)))))) & 25437 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43))) \times 2) - 1) \\ 25438 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) & 25438 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\ 25439 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 + 89))) & 25439 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2 \times 1)))) \\ 25440 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) & 25440 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^2 + 1)) \\ 25441 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - (((3^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) & 25441 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) + 4) \times -32) + 1) \\ 25442 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) & 25442 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times 65) - (4 - 3)/2)) - 1) \\ 25443 &:= (-((-((12^3)) - ((4^5) + (67 + 8)))) \times 9) & 25443 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times (6 + (5 + 4))) \times (3^{2+1}))) \\ 25444 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) \times 567) + 8) \times 9) & 25444 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times 65) - (4 - 3)/2)) + 1) \\ 25445 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!! + 4) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 25445 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 65)) + 4)) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 25446 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times (456 \times 7))) - 89) & 25446 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (43 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 25447 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (456 \times 7)) - 89) & 25447 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\ 25448 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (456 \times 7))) - 89) & 25448 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (43 \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 25449 &:= (((-12^3) + (((4 \times 56) + 7))) \times -((8 + 9))) & 25449 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times ((6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2)) - 1)) \\ 25450 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) & 25450 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times -(5 - ((4^3+2) - 1))) \\ 25451 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)))) & 25451 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4 + 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\ 25452 &:= ((1 + (-2 - ((3^4) \times -5))) \times ((-6 + 78) - 9)) & 25452 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times -7) + (-6 \times ((-5 - 4321)))) \\ 25453 &:= -((1 - ((-23 - ((45 \times 6) - 7)) \times -89))) & 25453 &:= (-((98 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times -4)))) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 25454 &:= (((1 - 23) + ((4 \times (5 + 6)) \times 7)) \times 89) & 25454 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3))) - 2))) - 1) \\ 25455 &:= (((-12 + ((-3 + 456) \times -7)) \times -8) - 9) & 25455 &:= (((-9 \times 87) - 6) + ((54 \times -3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 25456 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5 \times (6! + 7)) - 8 - 9 & 25456 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3))) - 2)) + 1)) \\ 25457 &:= (((-1 + ((2^3) \times 456)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) & 25457 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)))) \times -1) \\ 25458 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6! + 7! + 8 + 9 & 25458 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)))) + 1)) \\ 25459 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5 + 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) & 25459 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((76 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 25460 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) \times (-5 \times ((-6 - 7) + 89))) & 25460 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times 5) + 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\ 25461 &:= (((1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - 5) \times (-6 - ((-7 \times 8) + 9))) & 25461 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 25462 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times ((456 \times 7) - 8)) - 9)) & 25462 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + (((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 25463 &:= ((12 \times (345 \times 6)) - (7 \times -89)) & 25463 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2) - 1))) \\ 25464 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (456 \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) & 25464 &:= (((-98 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 25465 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (456 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9)) & 25465 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2)) - 1) \\ 25466 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) & 25466 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 25467 &:= -1 - 2 + 3! \times ((4 - 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9) & 25467 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2)) + 1) \\ 25468 &:= (-12 - ((3 + 4) \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) & 25468 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 25469 &:= (-1 + ((-2 + (((3 + 45) \times (67 - 8)))) \times 9)) & 25469 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25470 &:= 12^{3-4+5} + 6 \times 789 & 25470 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 25471 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) & 25471 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 25472 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3 - 456)) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) & 25472 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25473 &:= (((-12 + ((-3 + 456) \times -7)) \times -8) + 9) \\ 25474 &:= (-1 + (-((23 \times ((-4^5) - (6 + 78)))) - 9)) \\ 25475 &:= (((1 \times -23) \times ((-4^5) - (6 + 78))) - 9) \\ 25476 &:= (-12 - ((3 - ((45 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 25477 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 25478 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 + 4) \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 25479 &:= (((1 - 2) - ((3 + 45) \times -((67 - 8)))) \times 9) \\ 25480 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 25481 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 25482 &:= ((-1 \times -2) \times ((34 \times (5 \times (67 + 8))) - 9)) \\ 25483 &:= (((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 25484 &:= (-1 \times (23 \times (4 \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))))) \\ 25485 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 25486 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - ((45 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25487 &:= (1 \times (((-2 + (-3 + (456 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 25488 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) - 45)) \times (6 - (78 \times -9))) \\ 25489 &:= -((1 - 2) - ((3 - ((45 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 25490 &:= (1 - (((2 - 3) + 456) \times -((7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 25491 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times -((34 \times 5))) \times (-67 - 8)) - 9) \\ 25492 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 78))) + 9)) \\ 25493 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 + 78))) + 9) \\ 25494 &:= (1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 78))) + 9)) \\ 25495 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) - 89) \\ 25496 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 - 8)))))) \times 9) \\ 25497 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 - 8)))))) \times 9) \\ 25498 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4 \times 5) + (67 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 25499 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (34 \times (-5 \times (-6 - (78 - 9)))))) \\ 25500 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) - (4^5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\ 25501 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 34) \times 5) \times (6 + (78 - 9)))) \\ 25502 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (-3 \times (4 - 56)))) \times (7 - 89)) \\ 25503 &:= ((-1 - 23) + (-((456 \times 7)) \times -8) - 9) \\ 25504 &:= ((-1 \times 23) - (((456 \times 7) \times -8) + 9)) \\ 25505 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + ((-3 + (456 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 25506 &:= (((1 + 2) + (-((3 - (456 \times 7))) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 25507 &:= (-1 \times -((23 \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 25508 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (34 \times (5 \times (67 + 8)))))) + 9) \\ 25509 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times -((34 \times 5))) \times (-67 - 8)) + 9) \\ 25510 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 25511 &:= (-(((1 - 2) - (-3 + (456 \times 7))) \times 8)) + (-9) \\ 25512 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25473 &:= (-9 - ((876 - 54) \times -((32 - 1)))) \\ 25474 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 25475 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 25476 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 25477 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 25478 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 25479 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + 7) + ((6 + 5) \times (4^{3+2-1})))) \\ 25480 &:= (-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) - (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25481 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) + (3 / (2 + 1))) \\ 25482 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 25483 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 + (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1})))))) \\ 25484 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 25485 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 25486 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 25487 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + ((4 \times 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 25488 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25489 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) \times -1) \\ 25490 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4))) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 25491 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3)))) + 2)) \times -1) \\ 25492 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3)))) + 21)) \\ 25493 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 - 21)))) \\ 25494 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -((2 + 1)) \\ 25495 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 25496 &:= (((-98 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 25497 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + ((4 \times 3)^2))) + 1)) \\ 25498 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 - 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 25499 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 25500 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -((5 \times (4 + (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25501 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times 6) + (((5 + 4)^3) \times 2))) + 1) \\ 25502 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 25503 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\ 25504 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25505 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25506 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25507 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times -((4 + (3^2))) + 1) \\ 25508 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times ((6 \times 54) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25509 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times ((6 \times 54) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25510 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 25511 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times -((76) \times -5)) - (((43^2) \times 1))) \\ 25512 &:= ((-9 \times (-8 \times (76 \times 5))) - (((43^2) - 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25513 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 25514 &:= (-1 + ((23 + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 25515 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (-3 \times 45)) \times (6 - (78 - 9))) \\
 25516 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 25517 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) \times (6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 25518 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) \times 456) \times -7) + 8 + 9) \\
 25519 &:= (-1 \times (((2^3) \times 456) \times -7) + 8 + 9) \\
 25520 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times 456) \times -7) + 8 + 9) \\
 25521 &:= (((-1 - 2) - 3) + (((456 \times 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 25522 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (-((-3 + ((456 \times 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 25523 &:= (1 - ((23 - ((456 \times 7) \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 25524 &:= (((1 + 2) + (-((3 - (456 \times 7))) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 25525 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) - (4^5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 25526 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 25527 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times ((456 \times -7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
 25528 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) \times ((456 \times -7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
 25529 &:= (-(((1 - 2) - (-3 + (456 \times 7))) \times 8)) - (-9) \\
 25530 &:= -(((1 - (2 \times -34)) + 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times -8)) - 9)) \\
 25531 &:= (-12 - ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 89))) \\
 25532 &:= (((1 \times (2 + 3)) + (456 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 25533 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 - 8)))))) \times -9 \\
 25534 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -34 \times (5 - ((6 + 78) \times 9))) \\
 25535 &:= -(((1 \times (2^3)) \times (456 \times -7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
 25536 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 25537 &:= -(((1 \times (((2^3) \times 456) \times -7) + 8)) - 9) \\
 25538 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 25539 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 25540 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 89))) \\
 25541 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 89)))) \\
 25542 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times 6) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
 25543 &:= (((12 + (3 - 4)) + (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 89)) \\
 25544 &:= (1 \times (-((2^3) \times ((456 \times -7) + (8 - 9)))) \\
 25545 &:= ((123 + (45 \times 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\
 25546 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\
 25547 &:= (1 + ((-2 + 3) - ((-456) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 25548 &:= (-(((1 + 2) - ((3 + (456 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9) \\
 25549 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) + (((3 + (456 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\
 25550 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - 3) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 25551 &:= -(((1 - 2) \times ((3 + (456 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 25552 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25513 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 - 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 25514 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -((6^5)/((4^3)/2))) - 1) \\
 25515 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4)))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 25516 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -((6^5)/((4^3)/2))) + 1) \\
 25517 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 7) \times 65) + 4) \times -(((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
 25518 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 - 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 25519 &:= (((9 + 8) \times (-76 \times 5)) \times -4) - ((321)) \\
 25520 &:= ((-9 - (876 - 5)) \times (4 - (32 + 1))) \\
 25521 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -(((5 \times 4) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
 25522 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times -(4 + 3)) - 21) \\
 25523 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times 4) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\
 25524 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 25525 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times 4) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\
 25526 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (65 \times ((4 + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 25527 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 25528 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + (65 \times ((4 + 3)^2)))) + 1)) \\
 25529 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\
 25530 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 25531 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) + (((54 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 25532 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 - 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + 2) - 1) \\
 25533 &:= (-9 \times -(((87 - 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 25534 &:= ((-9 \times -(((87 - 6) \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + 2) + 1) \\
 25535 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((65 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)))) \\
 25536 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 25537 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times -((65 \times 4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\
 25538 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 25539 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times 6)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 25540 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) + 65) \times -(43))) - (-2 \times -(1))) \\
 25541 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (76 - 5))) + 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 25542 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (6 \times 5))) \times -(((4^3)/2) + 1)) \\
 25543 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 25544 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times -(4 + 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\
 25545 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times -(4 + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 25546 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times -(4 + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 25547 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 - 65)) \times (432 - (-1))) \\
 25548 &:= (((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) - 43)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 25549 &:= (9 + (8!/7! + 6!) \times 5) \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
 25550 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 25551 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 25552 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) + ((54 \times 3)^2 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25553 &:= ((-(1 \times 2^3)) \times -((456 \times 7))) - (-8 - 9) & 25553 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))))) \times -2) - 1 \\
 25554 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) \times 456) \times -7) - 8) + 9) & 25554 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))))) \times -(2 \times 1) \\
 25555 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times -(((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9)) & 25555 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((54 \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 25556 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times (((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)) - 9))) & 25556 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times 6!) \times 5 - 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 25557 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9) & 25557 &:= (((-98 \times 7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\
 25558 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) & 25558 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\
 25559 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) & 25559 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)) - 2))) - 1) \\
 25560 &:= (((1 + 2) + (-345) - ((6 + 7))) \times (-8 \times 9)) & 25560 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
 25561 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9 & 25561 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)) - 2))) + 1) \\
 25562 &:= (1 + (((2 + ((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) & 25562 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3 \times 21)) \\
 25563 &:= ((12 \times 3) - ((456 \times 7) \times -8) - 9) & 25563 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + 6) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 25564 &:= ((-12 \times 3) + ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 25564 &:= (((9 \times 8) + 7) \times (6 \times 54)) + (-32 \times 1) \\
 25565 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + ((5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) & 25565 &:= (((9 \times 8) + 7) \times (6 \times 54)) + (-32 + 1) \\
 25566 &:= (-(((1 + (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times (-67 - 8))) - 9) & 25566 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 25567 &:= ((1 + (2 + 34)) \times -(((5 + 6) - (78 \times 9)))) & 25567 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) \times -((4^3)/2)) - 1) \\
 25568 &:= ((1 \times 23) + (((456 \times 7) \times 8) + 9)) & 25568 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) \times -((4^3)/(2 \times 1))) \\
 25569 &:= (-((-1 - 23)) + ((-((456 \times 7)) \times -8) + 9)) & 25569 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 25570 &:= ((1^2) + (((3 + (456 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) & 25570 &:= (-9 + ((87 \times (6 \times (54 - (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 25571 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (((3 + (456 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) & 25571 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 \times 65)) + 4)) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 25572 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9) & 25572 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6 \times 54) - (3 + 21)) \\
 25573 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9) & 25573 &:= (9 + 8 + 7!/6) \times (5 + 4!) + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 25574 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 25574 &:= (9 - 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (5 \times (4 + 3) + 2 + 1) \\
 25575 &:= (-1 - (-23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 - 7) + 89)))) & 25575 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 + 6)) - 5)) \times -((4^{3+2}) - 1)) \\
 25576 &:= (-1 \times (-23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 - 7) + 89)))) & 25576 &:= -9 + 8! + 7 + (6 + 5! - (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1) \\
 25577 &:= (-((1 \times 23)) - ((4^5) \times ((6 \times -7) + (8 + 9)))) & 25577 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 25578 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) & 25578 &:= (-98 \times -(((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\
 25579 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 8))) \times 9)) & 25579 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 25580 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times (4! + (5 + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9) & 25580 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -(4 \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 25581 &:= (((12 \times 3) - ((456 \times 7) \times -8)) + 9) & 25581 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 25582 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 456)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)) & 25582 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times (4 + 3)) + 2)))) - 1) \\
 25583 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) & 25583 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\
 25584 &:= (((1 \times -2)^3) \times ((45 - 6) \times (7 - 89))) & 25584 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3/(2 + 1)))) \\
 25585 &:= (1 - (-2 \times (3 \times ((-4 + 56) \times -((7 - 89)))))) & 25585 &:= (((9 \times -8) - 7) - 6) \times ((5 \times 4) + (-321)) \\
 25586 &:= ((1 - (((2 + 3) - (456 \times -7)) \times -8)) + 9) & 25586 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times ((5 \times (4^{3+2}) - 1))) \\
 25587 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 8)))) \times -9) & 25587 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + ((7 \times (6 + (5 + 4))) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 25588 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) \times 567) - 8) \times 9) & 25588 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6 \times 54) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
 25589 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3!^4 - 5) \times 6 + 7!) + 8 + 9 & 25589 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6 \times 54) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 25590 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - 8)))) - 9) & 25590 &:= ((((-((9 \times 8)) - 7) \times (-6 \times 54)) - (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 25591 &:= ((1 \times (2^3) \times ((456 \times 7) + 8))) - 9 & 25591 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times (4^{3+2} \times 1))) \\
 25592 &:= ((1 + (2^3) \times ((456 \times 7) + 8))) - 9 & 25592 &:= ((((-((9 \times 8)) - 7) \times (-6 \times 54)) - (3 + 2)) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25593 &:= (((((1+2)+3)+(456 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 25594 &:= ((-1 - (2+3)) + ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))) \\ 25595 &:= ((-1 \times (2+3)) + ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))) \\ 25596 &:= (((((1+2)+3) \times ((4+5) \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times -9))) \\ 25597 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (4+5)) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25598 &:= (-1 - (-23 \times ((4^5) - ((6-7) \times 89)))) \\ 25599 &:= (-1 \times (-23 \times ((4^5) - ((6-7) \times 89)))) \\ 25600 &:= (((-1 \times (2-3)) \times (4^5)) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) - 9)) \\ 25601 &:= (1 - ((2^3) \times (-4 \times ((5+6) + (789)))) \\ 25602 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (((34 \times 5) - 6) \times 78) + 9) \\ 25603 &:= (1 - (-2 \times ((-((34 \times 5) + 6)) \times 78) + 9)) \\ 25604 &:= ((-1 + (2+3)) + ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))) \\ 25605 &:= ((-1 \times -(2+3)) + ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))) \\ 25606 &:= ((1+2) - (-3 - ((4^5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) - 9)))) \\ 25607 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))) \\ 25608 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) + ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))) \\ 25609 &:= ((1 \times (2^3) \times ((456 \times 7) + 8)) + 9) \\ 25610 &:= ((1 + (2^3) \times ((456 \times 7) + 8)) + 9) \\ 25611 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 25612 &:= ((-1+2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 25613 &:= (1 \times ((-23 \times (-((4^5) - (-6 \times (-7-8)))) - 9)) \\ 25614 &:= (((-1 - ((2+3) \times (4^5))) \times -((6+7) - 8)) + 9) \\ 25615 &:= ((1 - (2 - (3+45))) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 25616 &:= (-1 \times (((2+3)^4) \times (-56 + (7+8)) + 9) \\ 25617 &:= ((-12 \times ((-34 \times (56+7)) + 8)) + 9) \\ 25618 &:= (((1 - ((2^3) \times 456)) \times -7) + 89) \\ 25619 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8+9)) \\ 25620 &:= (-((((12^3)/4) - 5) \times 6) \times (7 - (8+9)) \\ 25621 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (67+8)) \times 9))) \\ 25622 &:= ((-1+23) + ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))) \\ 25623 &:= ((-((12-3)) + (((45+6) \times 7) \times 8)) \times -(-9)) \\ 25624 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) \times 456) \times 7)) + 89) \\ 25625 &:= ((-(((1 \times 2)^3)) \times (456 \times 7)) + 89) \\ 25626 &:= (-((-1 - (((2^3) \times 456) \times 7))) + 89) \\ 25627 &:= (-1 \times ((2+3) - (4 \times ((5+67) \times 89)))) \\ 25628 &:= ((-12/3) + (4 \times ((5+67) \times 89))) \\ 25629 &:= ((12 \times (345 \times 6)) + 789) \\ 25630 &:= ((1 - 234) \times (5 \times (67 - 89))) \\ 25631 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25593 &:= -((((9-87) \times 6) \times 54) - (321)) \\ 25594 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times 54)) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 25595 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2)) - 1) \\ 25596 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times ((5+4) \times (3 + (2+1)))) \\ 25597 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2)) + 1) \\ 25598 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 25599 &:= (((98+7) \times -((-6-5)) + (4^3)) \times (21)) \\ 25600 &:= (((9 \times (8+7)) + 65) \times 4) \times -((-((32 \times 1)))) \\ 25601 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + (7+6)) - 5)) \times -(4^{3+2})) + 1) \\ 25602 &:= ((-9 - (87+6)) \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 25603 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 \times (4+3)) + 2)) - 1) \\ 25604 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 \times (4+3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 25605 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((-7 + (6 \times 54)) \times (3^2)))) \times 1) \\ 25606 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + ((7 - (6 \times 54)) \times (3^2)))) + 1) \\ 25607 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (76 + (((5^4) \times (3+2)) + 1)))) \\ 25608 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7+6))) - 5) \times -(4 \times (32+1))) \\ 25609 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - (7+6)) \times 5) \times (4^{3+2}))) \times -1) \\ 25610 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 - ((5 \times 4)^{3-2+1}))) \\ 25611 &:= (-9 + (((8+76) \times 5) \times ((4^3) - (2+1)))) \\ 25612 &:= (9 \times (-8!/7! + 6!) - 5) \times 4!/(3+2+1) \\ 25613 &:= (((-98+7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 25614 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + ((7 - (6 \times 54)) \times (3^2))) - 1)) \\ 25615 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 25616 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2+1))) \\ 25617 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 25618 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 25619 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3 + (2+1))) \\ 25620 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) \times 5) \times -((4^3) - (2+1))) \\ 25621 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - ((3+2) - 1)) \\ 25622 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2-1))) \\ 25623 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + (7+6)) \times 5)) - 4) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\ 25624 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3/(2+1))) \\ 25625 &:= (((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^{4+3-2-1})) \\ 25626 &:= (-9 - ((8+7) \times (6 - (5 \times ((4+3)^{2+1})))) \\ 25627 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3 - (2-1))) \\ 25628 &:= (((9 \times 8) + 7) \times (6 \times 54)) - (-32 \times 1) \\ 25629 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + ((3+2) - 1)) \\ 25630 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + ((3+2) \times 1)) \\ 25631 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times ((76+5) \times 4) + 32) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25632 &:= (((-1^{23}) \times 4) \times ((-5 - 67) \times 89)) \\ 25633 &:= (-1 + (((2+3)^4) \times (56 - (7+8))) + 9) \\ 25634 &:= ((1 - (2-3)) - (4 \times ((5+67) \times -89))) \\ 25635 &:= (((1-2) \times -3) + (4 \times ((5+67) \times 89))) \\ 25636 &:= ((-12 \times -3) + ((4^5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))) \\ 25637 &:= (-1 \times -((2+3) + (4 \times ((5+67) \times 89)))) \\ 25638 &:= ((1+2) + (3 - (4 \times ((5+67) \times -89)))) \\ 25639 &:= ((((-1+2) - (3+456)) \times 7) \times -8) - 9 \\ 25640 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 - (7-8)) \times 9))) \\ 25641 &:= ((12-3) + (-4 \times -((5+67) \times 89))) \\ 25642 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 - (78-9)))) \\ 25643 &:= ((-1-2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (67 \times 89))) \\ 25644 &:= (12 + (-((3 - (45 \times 6))) \times (7+89))) \\ 25645 &:= (((-123-4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (-8))) - 9 \\ 25646 &:= ((((-1+2) \times 3)^{4+5}) + (67 \times 89)) \\ 25647 &:= (-(((12+3) + ((456 \times 7))) \times -8)) - 9 \\ 25648 &:= ((-1 + (2+3)) \times (4 + ((5+67) \times 89))) \\ 25649 &:= -(((1+(-2 - (3^{4+5}))) - ((67 \times 89)))) \\ 25650 &:= (((1^2) + (-34-5)) \times (-67-8)) \times 9 \\ 25651 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 \times (45 \times (((6+7) \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 25652 &:= ((-1+23) \times ((4+5) + ((6+7) \times 89))) \\ 25653 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times ((34 \times 5) - 6))) \times -78) - 9) \\ 25654 &:= ((-1+23) + ((4 \times (5+67)) \times 89)) \\ 25655 &:= (-(-1) \times (23 + ((4 \times (5+67)) \times 89))) \\ 25656 &:= (-(-1) + (23 + ((4 \times (5+67)) \times 89))) \\ 25657 &:= ((((-1+2) - (3+456)) \times 7) \times -8) + 9 \\ 25658 &:= (-((-12 + (-3^{4+5}))) + ((67 \times 89))) \\ 25659 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7+8)))) \times 9) \\ 25660 &:= (1 - (((2+3) - ((45+6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 25661 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 25662 &:= ((-12 - (34 \times 5)) \times (-6 + ((-7-8) \times -(-9)))) \\ 25663 &:= (((-123-4) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (-8))) + 9 \\ 25664 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4 - 5 + (6! - 7) \times (8+9)) \\ 25665 &:= (-(((12+3) + ((456 \times 7))) \times -8)) + 9 \\ 25666 &:= ((1 - (-((2^3) \times (45-6))) \times -((7-89))) \\ 25667 &:= (-1 - (-((23 \times 4) \times (((-5 \times 6) + 7) - 8) \times -9))) \\ 25668 &:= (12 \times ((345 \times 6) + (78-9))) \\ 25669 &:= (1 + ((2+34) \times ((5+6) + (78 \times 9)))) \\ 25670 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 + (-4+5!) \times (6+7)) \times (8+9) \\ 25671 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times ((456 \times -7) - (8+9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25632 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (((76+5) \times 4) + 32)) \times 1) \\ 25633 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (((76+5) \times 4) + 32)) + 1) \\ 25634 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2+1))) \\ 25635 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 25636 &:= (9+8) \times (7+6) \times (5! - 4! / (3+2+1)) \\ 25637 &:= (((-9 \times 87) - ((6+5) \times 4)) \times - (32-1)) \\ 25638 &:= ((((-98+7) \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times - (2+1)) \\ 25639 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times (4+3)) + (2+1)))) \\ 25640 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times -((5 \times (4+3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 25641 &:= (((9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 65) + 4))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1))) \\ 25642 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times -((5 \times (4+3)) - 2)) + 1) \\ 25643 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3-21)) \\ 25644 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - 21) \\ 25645 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (((4^3) \times 2) - 1))) \\ 25646 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((54+3)^2))) + 1)) \\ 25647 &:= (((-9 \times (87 \times (6+5))) + (4^3)) \times - (2+1)) \\ 25648 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (54+3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25649 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - ((4^3) - 2))) - 1) \\ 25650 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - (2+1)))) \\ 25651 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - ((4^3) - 2))) + 1) \\ 25652 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1})) \\ 25653 &:= ((-9-8) \times -((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - (2+1))) \\ 25654 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 65) + 4) \times - (3+2)) - 1) \\ 25655 &:= (-98 + (7 \times ((6^5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 25656 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) - (4+3))) \times - (2+1)) \\ 25657 &:= (-9 + ((87 \times (6 + ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1)) \\ 25658 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5^4)) + (32+1)) \\ 25659 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 25660 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 + (5 \times 4))) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 25661 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 25662 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5 \times 4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\ 25663 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3 \times 2})))) + 1) \\ 25664 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) - 4)) \times -3) - (2-1)) \\ 25665 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3-2))) - 1) \\ 25666 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3/(2+1)))) \\ 25667 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3-2))) + 1) \\ 25668 &:= (((9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (-6 \times -(-54))) \times ((32-1))) \\ 25669 &:= ((((-9-8) \times -((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - 2)) - 1) \\ 25670 &:= ((-9-8) \times -((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 25671 &:= (((-9-8) \times -((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - 2)) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25672 &:= ((-1-2) + ((3 + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 25672 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 + (5 \times 4))) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 25673 &:= (-(-1) - (((2^3) \times ((456 \times -7) - (8 + 9)))) & 25673 &:= (9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (((54 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\
 25674 &:= ((-1-2) - ((3 - ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) & 25674 &:= (((9 \times -(87)) + ((6 - 5) + 4)) \times ((-32) - 1)) \\
 25675 &:= ((1^2) \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) - 9))) & 25675 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + (4 + 3)))^2) + 1)) \\
 25676 &:= ((1^2) + ((3 + (4^5)) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) - 9))) & 25676 &:= (-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
 25677 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3 + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) & 25677 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 25678 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) & 25678 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - (6^5)) \times -(4 - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\
 25679 &:= ((1 \times 2) + ((-3 + (((45 + 6) \times 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 25679 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4 \times (3 \times 21)))))) \\
 25680 &:= ((-1 - 23) + ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25680 &:= (((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) + (4 - 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 25681 &:= (-1 \times (23 - ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25681 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 25682 &:= ((1 - 23) + ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25682 &:= 9 + 8 + (7 \times (-6 + 5!) + 4) \times 32 + 1 \\
 25683 &:= ((-12 - ((-3 - 456) \times 7) \times -8) - 9) & 25683 &:= ((((-98) \times 7) + 6) - 543) \times -(21)) \\
 25684 &:= -12^3 + 4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 \times 89 & 25684 &:= (9 + (((8 + 76) - 5) \times (4 + 321))) \\
 25685 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) & 25685 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3))) - 2)) - 1) \\
 25686 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) & 25686 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times -7) - 6)) + ((54 \times -3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 25687 &:= -((((1^2) + ((-3 - 456) \times 7)) \times 8) + 9) & 25687 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - (2 - 1))) \\
 25688 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + (-4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) & 25688 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 25689 &:= ((-12 - 3) - ((45 + 6) \times -((7 \times 8) \times -(-9)))) & 25689 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 25690 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + (78 + 9)))) & 25690 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 25691 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 + (78 + 9)))) & 25691 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 25692 &:= (-12 \times ((-34 \times (56 + 7)) - (8 - 9))) & 25692 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) + 4)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 25693 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 + 456) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) & 25693 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 + (5 \times 4))) + (32 - 1)) \\
 25694 &:= ((-(-1) - (2 + (((-3 - 456) \times 7) \times 8))) - 9) & 25694 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 65) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 25695 &:= ((123 + (4 \times (5 + 678))) \times 9) & 25695 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))))) - 1)) \\
 25696 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) & 25696 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 65) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 25697 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) - ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25697 &:= ((-((98 - 7)) \times 6) + (((54 \times 3)^2) + (-1))) \\
 25698 &:= (-((123 \times ((4 \times -56) + ((7 + 8)))) - 9) & 25698 &:= (((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) + (4 + 3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 25699 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) - ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25699 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times 6) + (((54 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 25700 &:= (-((12/3)) - ((45 + 6) \times ((7 \times 8) \times 9)) & 25700 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + (4^{3+2})) - 1)) \\
 25701 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25701 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -6^{(5+4)/3}) - (2 + 1)) \\
 25702 &:= (-(((1 - 2) + 3)) + (((45 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 \times 9))) & 25702 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -6^{(5+4)/3}) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 25703 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^{4+5-6}) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 25703 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))))) - 1) \\
 25704 &:= (((((1 + ((2 \times 3))) \times 45) + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) \times 9) & 25704 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -6^{5+4-3-2-1}) \\
 25705 &:= -(((12 + 34) \times (567 - 8)) + 9) & 25705 &:= -((((9 \times (8 + 76)) \times (5 + ((4 \times 3)))) \times -2) - 1) \\
 25706 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25706 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -6^{(5+4)/3}) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 25707 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25707 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -6^{(5+4)/3}) + (2 + 1)) \\
 25708 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25708 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 543) - 2)) - 1) \\
 25709 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) + ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) & 25709 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times (5 + (43 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 25710 &:= (-((1 + ((-23 - (456 \times 7)) \times 8))) - 9) & 25710 &:= (((-9 \times (87 \times (6 + 5))) + 43) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 25711 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) + (((3 + 456) \times 7) \times 8) + 9) & 25711 &:= (-98 + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times 21))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25712 &:= (-1 - (((2-3) - ((45+6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 25713 &:= ((1^2) \times (-((-(3+456) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 25714 &:= ((-1+2) + (((3+456) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\ 25715 &:= (-1 - (((2-345) \times (67+8)) + 9)) \\ 25716 &:= (-1 \times (((2-345) \times (67+8)) + 9)) \\ 25717 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3+45) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 25718 &:= ((1 - (2 - ((3+45) \times (67 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 25719 &:= (-12 + ((3 + ((45+6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 25720 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 25721 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^{4+5-6} \times 7)) \times -(8+9)) \\ 25722 &:= (-1 \times -((2 - ((3 - ((4+5) \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 25723 &:= (((-12-34) \times -(567-8)) + 9) \\ 25724 &:= (-1 + ((-2 + (345)) \times ((6+78) - 9))) \\ 25725 &:= (((-1 \times (2+3)) - (4^5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8+9))) \\ 25726 &:= ((-1+23) + ((45+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25727 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + ((45+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25728 &:= ((-1-23) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times (7 - (8-9)))) \\ 25729 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + ((45+6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 25730 &:= ((-1 + (234 \times (5+6))) \times -(7 - (8+9))) \\ 25731 &:= (((-1-2) + ((3 - ((4+5) \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times -9) \\ 25732 &:= ((-1+2) + ((3 + ((45+6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 25733 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((-3 - (((45+6) \times 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 25734 &:= ((-1-2) + (((3+45) \times (67 \times 8)) + 9)) \\ 25735 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3+45) \times (67 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 25736 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((3+45) \times (67 \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 25737 &:= -((1 \times 23) \times ((4 \times 5) + (67 \times (-8-9)))) \\ 25738 &:= ((((-1+2) - (3^{4+5}))/ (6+7)) \times -(8+9)) \\ 25739 &:= -(((1 \times -2) - ((-(3+45) \times (67 \times -8)) + 9))) \\ 25740 &:= ((1-23) \times (((4-56) - 78) \times 9)) \\ 25741 &:= (1 - (234 \times (5 \times (67-89)))) \\ 25742 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3!! - 4) \times (5+6+7) - 8-9) \\ 25743 &:= (((((1+2)^3) - (456 \times -7)) \times 8) - 9) \\ 25744 &:= -1 + (-2+3+4) \times (5!+6+7! - 8-9) \\ 25745 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times -(((6+7) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 25746 &:= (-12 + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - (8+9)))) \\ 25747 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!)^4 - 5 - 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 25748 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) + ((45+6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 25749 &:= (((1+2) + ((34 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times -9) \\ 25750 &:= (((-1 - (2+3)) - (4^5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8+9))) \\ 25751 &:= (((-1 + ((2+3) + 456)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25712 &:= ((-9 \times -(((87 \times (6+5)) - 4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1) \\ 25713 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))))) + 1)) \\ 25714 &:= (((-9+8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 25715 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2))) - 1) \\ 25716 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2 \times 1))) \\ 25717 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2)) + 1)) \\ 25718 &:= (((-98/7) \times ((6+5) - ((43^2) - 1))) \\ 25719 &:= -9 + (-8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 25720 &:= (9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!) - 5) \times 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 25721 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 - (6 \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1})))) \\ 25722 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 25723 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\ 25724 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + (4^{3+2}))) - 1) \\ 25725 &:= (-((98 - (7 \times (-6 - 5)))) \times (((-4 - 3) \times 21))) \\ 25726 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + (4^{3+2}))) + 1) \\ 25727 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - 21) \\ 25728 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 - 5)) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 25729 &:= ((-9 \times -(((87 \times (6 + 5)) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25730 &:= ((-9 \times -(((87 \times (6 + 5)) - 4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 25731 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 25732 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3^2) + 1)))) \\ 25733 &:= ((-9 \times -(((87 \times (6 + 5)) - 4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25734 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times 7) - 6) - (((54 \times 3)^2) \times -(1))) \\ 25735 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) + (((54 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 25736 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 25737 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) + 1))) \\ 25738 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 25739 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) + 2)) + 1) \\ 25740 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6+5) \times (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25741 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 25742 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 25743 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 25744 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\ 25745 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 25746 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))) \\ 25747 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 25748 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 25749 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) - 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\ 25750 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 + ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 25751 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25752 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))) \\
 25753 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 + ((3 + 45) \times 67)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 25754 &:= (1 + (((2 + ((3 + 45) \times 67)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 25755 &:= (123 + ((4 \times (5 + 67)) \times 89)) \\
 25756 &:= (((123 \times 4) + 56) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 25757 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 25758 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times 3) \times ((4 + 5) + (6 \times 78))) \times 9 \\
 25759 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))))) \\
 25760 &:= (-12 - (-34 \times (56 - (-78 \times 9)))) \\
 25761 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) - (456 \times -7)) \times 8) + 9) \\
 25762 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4 \times (5 \times (67 - 8))) - 9)) \\
 25763 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5 - 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 25764 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\
 25765 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 67)) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 25766 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4 + 567)) + 8) \times 9) \\
 25767 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times 8))) \times 9) \\
 25768 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 67)) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 25769 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (-34 \times (-56 - (78 \times 9)))) \\
 25770 &:= ((1 \times -2) + (34 \times (56 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
 25771 &:= ((1 - 2) + (34 \times (56 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
 25772 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (34 \times (56 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
 25773 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((345 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 25774 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (-34 \times (56 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
 25775 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - (4^5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\
 25776 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 25777 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((345 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 25778 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((345 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 25779 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((34 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 25780 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3) \times ((4! - 5 + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 25781 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3!)^4 - 5 - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 25782 &:= -1 - 2 + 3^{4+5} + 678 \times 9 \\
 25783 &:= ((1 \times -2) + ((3^{4+5}) - (-678) \times 9)) \\
 25784 &:= ((1 + (-2 + (3^{4+5}))) - (-678) \times 9) \\
 25785 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{(3-4) \times -5}) \times 6)) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 25786 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (678 \times 9))) \\
 25787 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^{4+5}) + (678 \times 9))) \\
 25788 &:= (1 - (-2 - ((3^{4+5}) - (-678) \times 9))) \\
 25789 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 + 34) + 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times 89))) \\
 25790 &:= (1 + ((2 + (34 + 5)) \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 25791 &:= ((-12 \times -((34 \times (56 + 7)) + 8)) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25752 &:= (((9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((-(6 - 543)) \times 2) - 1))) \\
 25753 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6^5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\
 25754 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times (((-6 \times 54) - 3) + (2 - 1))) \\
 25755 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) + (2 + 1))) \\
 25756 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times -7)) \times (6 + ((543 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 25757 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6) + (5 \times (4^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 25758 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 - (5 \times 4)))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 25759 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 25760 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6^5) - (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 25761 &:= ((9 + (876 - 54)) \times ((32 - 1))) \\
 25762 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 25763 &:= (-9 + 8! + 7 - 6 - 5) - 4!^3 - (2 + 1)!! \\
 25764 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times (43 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 25765 &:= -9 + 8! - (7 + 6!) \times (5 \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 25766 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 25767 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3)))/2) + 1)) \\
 25768 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)) - 21) \\
 25769 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) + ((54 \times 3)^2) - 1) \\
 25770 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) + ((54 \times 3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 25771 &:= ((-98 \times -(((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 25772 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((765 - ((4 + 3))) \times (-2 \times 1))) \\
 25773 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2))))) - 1) \\
 25774 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 25775 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3))/2) - 1) \\
 25776 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 25777 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (((7 + 6) - ((5 + 4)^3))/2) + 1) \\
 25778 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 25779 &:= 9 \times (-8 - 7 + 6 \times 5! \times 4) - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 25780 &:= (((-98/7) - 6) \times -(5 + (4 \times 321))) \\
 25781 &:= (-98 + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3^2))) + 1))) \\
 25782 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 + 6)) \times -5) + 432) - 1) \\
 25783 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times (32 - 1))) \\
 25784 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((65 - (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\
 25785 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - 5) - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 25786 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 25787 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 25788 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 25789 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
 25790 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\
 25791 &:= (((98 \times 7) - ((6 \times 5) \times -4)) \times 32) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25792 &:= (((((12^3)/4) + 5) \times (67 - 8)) + 9) \\ 25793 &:= ((12 \times 34) \times (56 + 7)) + 89 \\ 25794 &:= (-12 - (-34 \times -(((5 \times 6) - 789)))) \\ 25795 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 25796 &:= 12 \times (3^{4+5} - 6 \times 7 \times 8)/9 \\ 25797 &:= (-123 + (45 \times (6 \times (7 + 89)))) \\ 25798 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 25799 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\ 25800 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\ 25801 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 25802 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9) \\ 25803 &:= -((((1 + 2) - ((34 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\ 25804 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 25805 &:= -(((((-12 \times -34) + (-5 - 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times -9)))))) \\ 25806 &:= -(((((-1 - ((23 + 4) \times -56) - 7)) \times (-8 - 9))) \\ 25807 &:= (1 \times (((((2 + 3) + 456) \times 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 25808 &:= (1 + (((((2 + 3) + 456) \times 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 25809 &:= -(((((-1 - 2) + (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (-78 + 9)))))) \\ 25810 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 7)) \times -89) \\ 25811 &:= (((123 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 - ((7 \times -8) + 9))) \\ 25812 &:= ((12 \times 3) \times (4 + (5 + (6 - (-78 \times 9)))))) \\ 25813 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 25814 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 25815 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times (4 - (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8) + 9)))))) \\ 25816 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6)!! - 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 25817 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + (3 + 456)) \times 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 25818 &:= (-(((((-1234) + 5) \times ((6 + 7) + 8))) + 9) \\ 25819 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 25820 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 25821 &:= (((((12/3)^4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times -9) \\ 25822 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 25823 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^{4+5-6})) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 25824 &:= (12 \times ((345 \times 6) - (7 - 89))) \\ 25825 &:= (((12 - 3) - (-4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\ 25826 &:= (1 + (((2 + (3 + 456)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\ 25827 &:= (123 - ((((-45 + 6) \times -((7 \times 8))) \times -9)) \\ 25828 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - ((-6 \times (7 + 8)) - 9)))) \\ 25829 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))))) \\ 25830 &:= (((((1 - 2) - ((3^4))) \times 5) \times ((6 - 78) + 9)) \\ 25831 &:= (1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25792 &:= (((-9 \times (87 + 6)) + 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 25793 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3^2))) - 1))) \\ 25794 &:= (-9 \times -((87 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 25795 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5))) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 25796 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 25797 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 76)) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 25798 &:= -(9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! + 5 \times (4 + 3)! - 2 - 1 \\ 25799 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3^2)))) - 1) \\ 25800 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25801 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3^2))) + 1)) \\ 25802 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 25803 &:= (((-98 - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1) \\ 25804 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (65 - 4)) \times (3^2)) + 1) \\ 25805 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((((6 + 5) \times 4) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\ 25806 &:= ((-9 + (-8 - (765))) \times (-(((4^3)/2)) - 1)) \\ 25807 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3) + 2)) + 1) \\ 25808 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times 21)))) \\ 25809 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times 21))) \\ 25810 &:= ((-9 - (876 + 5)) \times (4 - (((32 + 1)))))) \\ 25811 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times ((54 \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\ 25812 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - (5 \times 4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\ 25813 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3^2) + 1)))) \\ 25814 &:= (-9 + (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\ 25815 &:= (-9 + (((87 \times 6) + 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 25816 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3^2) - 1)))) \\ 25817 &:= (987 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3 \times 2) - 1 \\ 25818 &:= (987 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3 \times 2 \times 1) \\ 25819 &:= (987 + 6) \times (5 \times 4 + 3 \times 2) + 1 \\ 25820 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times (6 + ((5 + 4) \times 3))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 25821 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5 + (4 + 3))^{2+1})))) \\ 25822 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3)))^2)) - 1) \\ 25823 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) + (2 - 1))) \\ 25824 &:= (-98 + (((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3)))^2) + 1)) \\ 25825 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - ((4^3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\ 25826 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times (6 + 5))) + 4) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 25827 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times (6 + 5))) + 4) \times -3) \times (2 - 1)) \\ 25828 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times (6 + 5))) + 4) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\ 25829 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 25830 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 25831 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 25832** := $1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (-4 - 5 - 6! + 7!)) - 8 - 9$
25833 := $((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) - 5)) \times -((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)$
25834 := $-1 - (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5! + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$
25835 := $((-1 + 2 + 3)!/4!) + 5 \times (6! \times 7 - 8 - 9)$
25836 := $((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)))$
25837 := $((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)))$
25838 := $((12^3) \times (4 - (-5 - 6))) - (-7 + 89)$
25839 := $((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) + 5) \times ((6 \times (7 + 8)) + 9))$
25840 := $((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)))$
25841 := $(1 + (((2 \times 34) \times 5) \times (-6 - (7 - 89))))$
25842 := $((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) + 9)$
25843 := $(1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) - 9))$
25844 := $(((-123 \times 4) - 5) \times -((6 \times 78)/9))$
25845 := $((12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 + (-7 \times -8))) - 9$
25846 := $((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8))) - 9)$
25847 := $(-1 + (((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7) \times (8 \times 9))$
25848 := $((1 + (-2 + (-345) - ((6 + 7)))) \times (-8 \times 9))$
25849 := $(1 - ((2^3) \times ((45 \times (6 - 78)) + 9)))$
25850 := $((-1 + (23 \times 45)) \times ((6 \times 7) - ((8 + 9))))$
25851 := $((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (45 - (6 \times (7 \times 89))))$
25852 := $((12^3) + (4 + (((5 \times 67) \times 8) \times 9)))$
25853 := $1 \times 2 \times 3! \times (4! \times 5! - 6! - 7) + 8 + 9$
25854 := $(-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - ((567 + 8) \times 9))))$
25855 := $((-1 + (((2 \times 3) + 456) \times 7) \times 8) - 9)$
25856 := $(-1 + (((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times 67) - 8) \times 9)$
25857 := $((-((1 + 2)) \times (34 + 5)) \times ((-6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))$
25858 := $(1 + (((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times 67) - 8) \times 9)$
25859 := $-1 + (-2 + 3! \times (4! + 5!)) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$
25860 := $((12^3 - 4) \times (5 + ((6 \times (7 + 8))/9)))$
25861 := $(-1 + 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 + 9)$
25862 := $((-1 + (((2 \times 3) + 456) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)$
25863 := $(-12 + (345 \times (6 + (78 - 9))))$
25864 := $(((-1 \times 2) + (345 \times (67 + 8))) - 9)$
25865 := $((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) + 9)$
25866 := $((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)$
25867 := $(((-1 + 2) + (345 \times (67 + 8))) - 9)$
25868 := $(-((-1 \times 2) - ((345 \times (67 + 8)) - 9)))$
25869 := $((1 + 2) + (345 \times (67 + 8))) - 9$
25870 := $(((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))$
25871 := $((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))$
25832 := $((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6^5) - (4^{3+2+1}))))$
25833 := $(((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 + ((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 - 1))))$
25834 := $(((-9 - 8) \times -(76 \times (5 \times 4))) - (3 + (2 + 1)))$
25835 := $(((-9 - 8) \times -(76 \times (5 \times 4))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))$
25836 := $((-9 \times -(87 \times (6 + ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) - (2 + 1))$
25837 := $(((((98 \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 - 43))) - 2) - (1))$
25838 := $((-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) \times (2 \times 1))$
25839 := $((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times -(5 + (4^{3+2-1})))$
25840 := $((-9 - 8) \times -((((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))/3^2) - 1))$
25841 := $(-9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)))$
25842 := $(((((9 + 8) \times 76) \times (5 \times 4)) + 3) - ((2 - 1)))$
25843 := $(((-9 - 8) \times -(76 \times (5 \times 4))) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))$
25844 := $((-98 + 7) \times (6 - (((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)))$
25845 := $((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times (5 - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))$
25846 := $(-9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) \times 2)) + 1))$
25847 := $((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)) + 2))) - 1)$
25848 := $((-(9 \times 87) + (65)) \times (-4 \times ((3^2) \times 1)))$
25849 := $((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3)))^2 \times 1))$
25850 := $(((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1))$
25851 := $(((-9 \times (87 \times (6 + 5))) - 4) \times -(3 \times (2 - 1)))$
25852 := $((((-9 \times (87 \times (6 + 5))) - 4) \times -3) + (2 - 1))$
25853 := $((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1)$
25854 := $(((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3^2)))) - 1)$
25855 := $((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))))$
25856 := $(((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))/3^2)) - 1)$
25857 := $((-9 - 8) \times -((((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))/3^2) \times 1))$
25858 := $(((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4))/3^2)) + 1)$
25859 := $(9 + (((87 \times 6) - 5) \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)))$
25860 := $(((-9 \times (87 \times (6 + 5))) - (4 + 3)) \times -(2 + 1))$
25861 := $((((-98 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 - 43)) + 21)$
25862 := $((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3^2)))) + 1)))$
25863 := $(-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (43 - (2 - 1)))))$
25864 := $(((-(((-9 - 8) \times 76)) \times (5 \times 4)) + (3 + 21)))$
25865 := $(((-98) + 7) - (-6 \times (5 + 4321)))$
25866 := $((-9 \times ((87 \times (6 + 5)) + (4 - 3))) \times (-2 - 1))$
25867 := $(((-9 - 8) \times -(76 \times (5 \times 4))) + (3^{2+1}))$
25868 := $((((-9 - 8) \times (765 - 4)) + 3) \times -(2 \times 1))$
25869 := $(((-9 \times 87) - ((6^5) + (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1))$
25870 := $((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1)$
25871 := $(((-98 \times (-((7 + (65 \times 4))) + 3))) - 2) + 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 25872 &:= (-12 \times (3 - (((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 25873 &:= (((-1 + (((2 \times 3) + 456) \times 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 25874 &:= ((1 - 2) - (-345) \times (6 + (78 - 9))) \\ 25875 &:= (-((1 + (2 \times 34))) \times (((56 \times -7) + 8) + 9)) \\ 25876 &:= (-1 - (-2 + (-345) \times ((6 + 78) - 9))) \\ 25877 &:= (-1 \times ((234 - 5) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 25878 &:= ((12 + (345 \times (67 + 8))) - 9) \\ 25879 &:= -1 + (2 - 3!^4) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 25880 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + 456) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 25881 &:= (((((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 25882 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((345 \times (67 + 8)) + 9))) \\ 25883 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 34) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 25884 &:= (12 \times ((3 \times 456) + 789)) \\ 25885 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((345 \times (67 + 8)) + 9)) \\ 25886 &:= (-1 \times -2 + ((345 \times (67 + 8)) + 9)) \\ 25887 &:= (12 + (345 \times (6 + (78 - 9)))) \\ 25888 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times -(4 + (5 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) \\ 25889 &:= (((-1 - (((2 \times 3) + 456) \times 7)) \times -8) + 9) \\ 25890 &:= (1 - 23 \times 4 + 5^6) \times (7 + 8) / 9 \\ 25891 &:= (1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25892 &:= -((1 + (((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - 67))) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 25893 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 25894 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4 \times 5) + ((6 + 7) \times 89))) \\ 25895 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) \times (4 + ((567 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 25896 &:= (((12^3) \times ((4 + 5) + 6)) - 7) + (-8 - 9) \\ 25897 &:= -(((1 \times 23) - ((-45 \times 6) \times (-7 - 89))) \\ 25898 &:= ((1 - 23) + ((45 \times 6) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 25899 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 - ((5 + 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25900 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times -(5 \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\ 25901 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 + ((45 + 6) \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 25902 &:= (-12 + ((-3 + 45) \times (-6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\ 25903 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((3 + ((45 + 6) \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 25904 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!^4) \times 5! / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25905 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -(((4 \times 56) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\ 25906 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 25907 &:= (((1 + (2 \times 3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 25908 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 67)) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 25909 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 67)) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 25910 &:= (-1 + ((23 + ((45 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 25911 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{(3-4) \times -5}) \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25872 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 25873 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3^2))) + 1) \\ 25874 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + (7 \times 6)) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 25875 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 25876 &:= ((9876 - (((-5 \times 4)^3) \times -(-2))) \times -((-1))) \\ 25877 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) - (6 - 5)) \times (43^2 \times 1))) \\ 25878 &:= (9 + ((-87) + (-6 \times (-5 - 4321)))) \\ 25879 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - (3^2))) + 1)) \\ 25880 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6^5) - (4 \times 3)) / (2 + 1))) \\ 25881 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times 21)))) \\ 25882 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 765) + (4^3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 25883 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\ 25884 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 25885 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times 4) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\ 25886 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - 7)^6) \times 5)) \times -(43^2 \times 1)) \\ 25887 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (((54 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\ 25888 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 7) - (6 \times (5 - (4321))))) \\ 25889 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3^2)))) \times -1) \\ 25890 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times 6) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 25891 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 25892 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 25893 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 25894 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25895 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 25896 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 25897 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 25898 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 25899 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 25900 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\ 25901 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 25902 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((-7) - (-6 \times (-5 + 4321)))) \\ 25903 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3)))^2)) - 1) \\ 25904 &:= (((9 - 8) + 7) - ((6 \times (5 - 4321)))) \\ 25905 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7))) - (6 \times (5 - (4321)))) \\ 25906 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) - (6 \times (5 - 4321))) \\ 25907 &:= (-98 + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1))) \\ 25908 &:= ((-9 + (((87 - 6) \times 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 25909 &:= ((-9 + (((87 - 6) \times 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25910 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6^5) / (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1)) \\ 25911 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times -5 - (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25912 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((-3 + 45) \times (6 + (7 \times -89)))) \\ 25913 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3))) + (45 \times (6 \times (7 + 89)))) \\ 25914 &:= (((1 \times -2) \times 3) + ((45 \times 6) \times -((-7 - 89)))) \\ 25915 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) - (45 \times (6 \times (7 + 89)))) \\ 25916 &:= ((1 - 2) + (-3 - (45 \times (6 \times (-7 - 89)))) \\ 25917 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + ((45 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 25918 &:= -(((1 - 2) - (-3 - (45 \times (6 \times (-7 - 89)))))) \\ 25919 &:= (-1 - ((23 + (4 + 5)) \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times -9)))) \\ 25920 &:= (((1^{23}) + 4) \times ((5 + 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 25921 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4)))^{5+6+(7-8) \times 9}) \\ 25922 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - (-((45 \times 6) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 25923 &:= (-12 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 25924 &:= ((12/3) + ((45 \times 6) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 25925 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 25926 &:= (1 \times -(((2 \times 3) + (-(-45) \times (6 \times (-7 - 89)))))) \\ 25927 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + (45 \times (6 \times (7 + 89)))) \\ 25928 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 \times ((4^5) - 67)) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 25929 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3 - 45)) \times -((6 - 78)))) \times -9) \\ 25930 &:= (((12^3) \times ((4 + 5) + 6)) - 7) - (-8 - 9) \\ 25931 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6! + 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 25932 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 25933 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 25934 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 25935 &:= (((((-1 + 2) \times 3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times -((7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25936 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 25937 &:= (((1 + 2) + 34) \times ((5 - 6) + (-78 \times -9))) \\ 25938 &:= ((-12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (67 + (8 - 9))) \\ 25939 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + ((5 + 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 25940 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 + 7) - (8 + 9)))) \\ 25941 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 25942 &:= -(((1 - 23) - ((45 \times 6) \times (7 + 89)))) \\ 25943 &:= ((1 \times 23) + ((-45 \times 6) \times (-7 - 89))) \\ 25944 &:= -((((1 \times -2) - (-34 \times (5 + 6))) \times (-78 + 9))) \\ 25945 &:= (1 + ((2 + (34 \times (5 + 6))) \times (78 - 9))) \\ 25946 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9) \\ 25947 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (-45 \times (6 \times (-7 - 89)))) \\ 25948 &:= (1 + (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9) \\ 25949 &:= (-1 + 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 25950 &:= ((1 - (2 + 345)) \times (-6 - (78 - 9))) \\ 25951 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4 \times 5) \times (67 - 8))) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25912 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 25913 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 25914 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\ 25915 &:= (((-98 + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 25916 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 \times (32 - 1))) \\ 25917 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5))) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 25918 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5))) \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 25919 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + (6 + 5)) \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))))) - 1) \\ 25920 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times -((5 + (4 + 3))^{2+1})) \\ 25921 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times -((76 - (54 + 3))))^2 \times 1) \\ 25922 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 + 5)))) \times (4 + 3))^2) + 1) \\ 25923 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5))) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25924 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 25925 &:= -(((9 - 8) - (((7 - 6) + 5) \times (4321)))) \\ 25926 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6) + 5) \times (4321))) \\ 25927 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 - 6) + 5) \times (4321))) \\ 25928 &:= (9 - ((8 \times ((-7 - 65) \times (43 + 2)))) + (1))) \\ 25929 &:= (-98) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (32))) + 1)) \\ 25930 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (((7 \times 6) + (5 + 4)) \times 3))^2)) \times -1) \\ 25931 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 25932 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 25933 &:= ((9 + 8) - (-76) \times ((5 \times 4) + (321))) \\ 25934 &:= (9 \times (8 - 7) \times 6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 25935 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2) + 1))) \\ 25936 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 - (((54 + 3)^2) - 1))) \\ 25937 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1) \\ 25938 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times (3^{2+1}))) \\ 25939 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 25940 &:= (-9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 25941 &:= (-9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 25942 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 25943 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 - 6) + 5) \times (4321))) \\ 25944 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 25945 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2)))) \times -1) \\ 25946 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 25947 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) - (6 + 5)) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 25948 &:= (-((9 + (-8 + 7))) + ((6 \times (5 + (4321)))) \\ 25949 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 25950 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7) - (-6 \times (-5 - 4321)))) \\ 25951 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3^2))) + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25952 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 25953 &:= (((-12 + (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 25954 &:= (1 + ((23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 25955 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) \times 9) \\
 25956 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (((((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) + 8)) \times -9) \\
 25957 &:= (1 - ((2 - (((3 + 4) + (5 \times 6)) \times 78)) \times 9)) \\
 25958 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times -7) - 89) \\
 25959 &:= ((((-1) - 2) - 345) \times (-67 + (-8))) + 9) \\
 25960 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))))) \\
 25961 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 25962 &:= (-12 + (((-3 - 4) - (5 \times 6)) \times (-78 \times 9))) \\
 25963 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 25964 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (((45 \times (6 + 7)) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 25965 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - ((4 - 56) \times -((7 \times 8)))) \times -9) \\
 25966 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((((((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 25967 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 25968 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((((((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times -7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 25969 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times ((4 \times 5) \times (67 - 8))) + 9) \\
 25970 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 789))) \\
 25971 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 25972 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 25973 &:= (-1 + ((23 - 4) - 56) \times (-78 \times 9)) \\
 25974 &:= (((-1 + (23 + (4 + 5))) + 6) \times (78 \times 9)) \\
 25975 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times -7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 25976 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 25977 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 + 4) + (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 25978 &:= -12 + 345 \times 678/9 \\
 25979 &:= (((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))^5) - 6789) \\
 25980 &:= ((12 + 3) \times ((4^5) + (6 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
 25981 &:= ((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 25982 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) + 8)) \times 9) \\
 25983 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) \times 9) \\
 25984 &:= (1 + ((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) + 8)) \times 9) \\
 25985 &:= (((-1 + (((2^3) + 456) \times 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\
 25986 &:= (12 + (((3 + 4) + (5 \times 6)) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 25987 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3^4) + (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times 89))) \\
 25988 &:= (((-1 + 2) + 3) \times ((-4 + ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times 89)) \\
 25989 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 + ((4 - 56) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 25990 &:= (((12 + 34) \times -5) \times -(((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25952 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 76)) + (5 \times (4^{3+2+1}))) \\
 25953 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + ((3^2) - 1))) \\
 25954 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (32 \times 1)))) \\
 25955 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
 25956 &:= ((9 - (((87 + 6)) \times (5 + 4)) \times (32 - 1))) \\
 25957 &:= (((((-9 - 87) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\
 25958 &:= (9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 25959 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times ((6^{(5+4)/3}) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 25960 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6^5) + (4 \times 3)) / (2 + 1))) \\
 25961 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) - 1))) \\
 25962 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6) + ((54 \times 3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 25963 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 25964 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 25965 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) - (2 + 1)))))) \\
 25966 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) + 1) \\
 25967 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) \times (3^{2+1})))))) \\
 25968 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\
 25969 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 25970 &:= (-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 25971 &:= ((-98 \times -(((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 4)) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 25972 &:= (-9 - (((8 + (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 25973 &:= (-9 - ((8 + (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 25974 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\
 25975 &:= (((9 \times 8) + (7 - (-6 \times (-5 + 4321)))))) \\
 25976 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + (3^2)) - 1)) \\
 25977 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - 21)) \\
 25978 &:= (((-9 \times (87 + 6)) - (5 - 4)) \times -(32 - 1)) \\
 25979 &:= (9 - 8 + 7! + 6) \times 5 + 4! + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 25980 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 25981 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 25982 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times -(6 - 5)) + (4^3))^2))) - 1) \\
 25983 &:= ((987 \times (6 - (-5 \times 4))) - (-321)) \\
 25984 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2) - 1) \\
 25985 &:= ((((-9 + 876) \times 5) - 4) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
 25986 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1))) \\
 25987 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (76 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 25988 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1))) \\
 25989 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3^{2+1})))) \\
 25990 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) - 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25991 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5) - (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)) & 25991 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times (6 - (5 \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25992 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5 + (6 + 7)))))) \times -(8 \times 9) & 25992 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 25993 &:= (-(((1 \times (2^3) + 456)) \times -7) \times -(-8)) + 9 & 25993 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (-((765 \times (4 + (-3 \times 2)))) + (-1))) \\ 25994 &:= ((-1 - (((-2^3) - 45) \times 6)) \times (-7 + 89)) & 25994 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 25995 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + (4 \times (5 + (67 \times 8)))))) - 9 & 25995 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 25996 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!!) \times (4 + 5)) \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9) & 25996 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 25997 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9) & 25997 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 25998 &:= (-12 + (-34 \times (-(((5 + 6) \times -7) - 8)) \times -9)) & 25998 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 25999 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9) & 25999 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\ 26000 &:= ((1 - (23 \times -((4 + 5)))) \times (6 - (-7 \times (8 + 9)))) & 26000 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ \\ 26001 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) \times -9 & 26001 &:= (-9 + ((-8 - 7) \times (-6 - ((54 \times 32) \times 1)))) \\ 26002 &:= (1 + (((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times 67) + 8) \times 9) & 26002 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 26003 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 - 5 + 6) \times (7! + 8 + 9) & 26003 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) + (-6 \times (-5 - (4321)))))) \\ 26004 &:= (12 \times (((-34 \times 56) / 7) \times -8) - 9) & 26004 &:= (-9 + (-87) \times (((6 \times (5 \times (-4 - (3 \times 2)))) + 1)))) \\ 26005 &:= (12 - 34 + 5^6) \times (7 + 8) / 9 & 26005 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 26006 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 - 5 \times 6 \times 7 + 8) / 9 & 26006 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26007 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (34 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) & 26007 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26008 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) & 26008 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26009 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + 45) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) & 26009 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 26010 &:= ((1 + (2 + (3 + 45))) \times (6 + ((7 \times -8) \times -9))) & 26010 &:= (((9 + 8) \times (765 \times (4 + (-3 \times 2)))) \times (-1)) \\ 26011 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (34 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) & 26011 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -(((6 \times (5 + 4)) - 3)^2)) + 1) \\ 26012 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - (34 \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) & 26012 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 765) + ((4 - 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 26013 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3 \times 4)) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (78 + 9)) & 26013 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26014 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! \times (4 - 5 - 6! + 7! + 8 + 9) & 26014 &:= (-987 + (((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) + 1)) \\ 26015 &:= ((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9)) & 26015 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (-7 + (6 \times 543))) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 26016 &:= (((12^3) \times ((4 + 5) + 6)) + (7 + 89)) & 26016 &:= ((9 - (876 - 54)) \times (-32) \times 1) \\ 26017 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 345) \times (67 + 8))) - 9) & 26017 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) / 2)) + 1) \\ 26018 &:= (-1 - ((234 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) & 26018 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (-7 + (6 \times 543)))) + 2) - 1) \\ 26019 &:= (((12 \times 34) + 5) \times ((6 - 7) + 8)) \times 9 & 26019 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (-7 + (6 \times 543)))) + 2) \times 1) \\ 26020 &:= (1 - ((234 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) & 26020 &:= (((9 + (8 \times (-7 + (6 \times 543)))) + 2) + 1) \\ 26021 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 - 5 - 6 - 7 \times 8) / 9 & 26021 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times 2) - 1) \\ 26022 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) & 26022 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 26023 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) & 26023 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 26024 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 345) \times ((6 + 78) - 9))) & 26024 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 26025 &:= ((12^3) + (((45 - 6) \times 7) \times 89)) & 26025 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26026 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) & 26026 &:= ((-98 + 7) \times -((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 26027 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (34 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times 9) & 26027 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3))) + 2))) - 1) \\ 26028 &:= ((-12 \times 3) \times ((-4 - 5) - ((6 \times 7) \times (8 + 9)))) & 26028 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times 4) \times (3^{2+1})) \\ 26029 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 \times 456) + 78) \times 9))) & 26029 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3))) + 2))) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26030 &:= (((-1 - (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times -7) - (8+9)) \\ 26031 &:= ((((-1-2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 26032 &:= (((-1 + (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) + (8-9)) \\ 26033 &:= ((-1 + (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times 6) \times -(7 \times (8-9))) \\ 26034 &:= ((1+2) \times (3 - (4 + ((5+6) \times -(789)))))) \\ 26035 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8-9)))) \\ 26036 &:= ((-12 - 34) \times -((567 - (-8+9)))) \\ 26037 &:= (-((1-2) \times ((34 + (5-6)) \times 789))) \\ 26038 &:= (-((1-2) + ((34 + (5-6)) \times 789))) \\ 26039 &:= (-1 - (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8-9)))) \\ 26040 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3+4))) \times -(((5^6) + (7-8))/9)) \\ 26041 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2+3))^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8-9)) \\ 26042 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times (34 \times 5)) - 6) \times 78)) - 9) \\ 26043 &:= (123 + ((45 \times 6) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 26044 &:= ((-1 + (((2+3) \times 45) - 6) \times 7) \times (8+9)) \\ 26045 &:= (1 + (2 \times (34 \times ((56-7) \times 8) - 9))) \\ 26046 &:= (((-1 - (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times -7) + (8-9)) \\ 26047 &:= ((-1 - (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times 6) \times (7 \times (8-9))) \\ 26048 &:= (((-1 - (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times -7) - (8-9)) \\ 26049 &:= (((1^2) \times 3) \times (4 - ((5+6) \times -(789)))) \\ 26050 &:= (((-1 + (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) + (8+9)) \\ 26051 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times (67 + 89))) \\ 26052 &:= (((-1-2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times 67) + (8-9))) \\ 26053 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (67-8)) \times 9))) \\ 26054 &:= (-1 + ((2+3) \times ((4 + (567+8)) \times 9))) \\ 26055 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3-4} \times -5) \times 6)) \times -((7+8) \times 9)) \\ 26056 &:= (-1 + (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + (8+9)) \\ 26057 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2+3))^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + (8+9)) \\ 26058 &:= ((((-1-2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26059 &:= 1 + 23 + (-4 + 5^6) \times (7+8)/9 \\ 26060 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) \times 45) - 6) \times (7 \times (8+9))) \\ 26061 &:= (((((1 \times 2) + 3) + (-4 \times 56)) \times -7) \times (8+9)) \\ 26062 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (34 \times 5)) - 6) \times 78) + 9) \\ 26063 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((34-5) \times 6) + 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 26064 &:= (((-1 - (((2+3)^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times -7) + (8+9)) \\ 26065 &:= (((-1 - (((2+3)^4) - 5)) \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8+9)) \\ 26066 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 26067 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) + 9) \\ 26068 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 \times (5 - ((6+7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26030 &:= ((-9-8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3+2))) + 1))) \\ 26031 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2+1)))) \\ 26032 &:= ((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3+2))) - 1))) \\ 26033 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - (3+2))) - 1)) \\ 26034 &:= (((((9-876) \times 5) - 4) \times 3) \times -(-2) \times -(1)) \\ 26035 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times (((4^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 26036 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\ 26037 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26038 &:= (((-9+8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3+2)))) - 1) \\ 26039 &:= ((-9+8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3+2) \times 1)))) \\ 26040 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - ((3+2) \times 1))) \\ 26041 &:= ((((-9+8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3+2))) + 1) \\ 26042 &:= (((9+8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 32))) - 1) \\ 26043 &:= (((-9-8) - (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 32))) \times -1) \\ 26044 &:= ((-9-8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3^{2+1})))) \\ 26045 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2-1)))) \\ 26046 &:= ((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3+2))) + 1))) \\ 26047 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - (3+2))) + 1)) \\ 26048 &:= ((((-9+8) - 7) \times -(6 + (((54+3)^2) + 1))) \\ 26049 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) - (2+1)) \\ 26050 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26051 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) - (2-1)) \\ 26052 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2-1))))) \\ 26053 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2-1))) \\ 26054 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 26055 &:= ((-9 \times (8+7)) \times -((6-5) + ((4^3) \times (2+1)))) \\ 26056 &:= ((-9 \times (((((8 \times 7) - (6^5))/4) \times 3)/2)) + 1) \\ 26057 &:= ((((-9-8) - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3+2)))) \times -1) \\ 26058 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 + (((6+54) - 3)^2))) + 1)) \\ 26059 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2-1)))) \\ 26060 &:= ((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3^{2+1})))) \\ 26061 &:= (-(((((-9-8) \times 76) + (54-3))) \times -(-21))) \\ 26062 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26063 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2-1)) \\ 26064 &:= (((9+8) + (-7+6)) \times (543 \times (2+1))) \\ 26065 &:= ((-9-8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3+2) - 1)))) \\ 26066 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 26067 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2+1)) \\ 26068 &:= (((-9+8) + (7 \times (6+5))) \times ((4+3)^{2+1})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26069 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((67 + 8) - 9)))) \\ 26070 &:= (-((-(1 - 2) - 34) \times (-5 + (6 + (789)))) \\ 26071 &:= (((-1 + (2^3))^4) + (5 \times (6 \times 789))) \\ 26072 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) - (67 - 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 26073 &:= ((-12 - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times 7 + 8) \times -9) \\ 26074 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) - (67 - 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 26075 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) + 45) \times (6 \times (7 - 89)))) \\ 26076 &:= (-1 \times (((-2^3) - 45) \times 6) \times (-7 + 89)) \\ 26077 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) + (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times -89) \\ 26078 &:= (1 - (((-2^3) \times 45) + 67) \times 89) \\ 26079 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\ 26080 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 26081 &:= (1 + ((2 - 34) \times (-5 + (6 \times ((-7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 26082 &:= (1 \times (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 + (67 + 89)))) \\ 26083 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 + (67 + 89)))) \\ 26084 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3^4) \times (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 26085 &:= (-123 + (((4 - 56) \times (7 \times -8) \times 9)) \\ 26086 &:= ((-1 + (((23 \times (4 \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 26087 &:= (-1 \times -(((23 \times (4 \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 26088 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) + ((6 - (7 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 26089 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((34 + 5) \times (678 - 9)))) \\ 26090 &:= (-(-1) - (2 + (((34 + 5) \times (-678) + 9)))) \\ 26091 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) - 8))) \times 9) \\ 26092 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((34 + 5) \times (678 - 9))) \\ 26093 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((34 \times ((56 \times 7) - 8) - 9))) \\ 26094 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((34 \times ((56 \times 7) - 8) - 9))) \\ 26095 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (4^{5+6-7}))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26096 &:= ((-1 + 234) \times ((5 \times 6) - (7 - 89))) \\ 26097 &:= (((-1 + (((23 \times (4 \times 5) + 6) \times 7) \times 8) + 9) \\ 26098 &:= (-1 - 2 + (34 + 5^6) \times (7 + 8))/9 \\ 26099 &:= (-1 - ((-2 - (3 + 45)) \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 26100 &:= (-1 \times ((-2 - (3 + 45)) \times (6 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 26101 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + 56) \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 26102 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (34 \times ((56 \times 7) - 8)))) - 9) \\ 26103 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8)) - 9) \\ 26104 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times (4 \times 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 26105 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 26106 &:= (((1 - 2) + 34) + 5) \times (678 + 9) \\ 26107 &:= (1 + ((234 - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26069 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 26070 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\ 26071 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 26072 &:= ((-9 + ((87 - 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2))) - 1) \\ 26073 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26074 &:= (-9 + (((87 - 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\ 26075 &:= (-98 - (7 \times (((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1))) \\ 26076 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 26077 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 26078 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times ((5 - (4^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 26079 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times 543) + 2))) - 1) \\ 26080 &:= (-(((-(9 - 8) - 7) \times ((6 \times 543) + 2))) \times 1) \\ 26081 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 26082 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 26083 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 26084 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - 3!) + (2 + 1)! \\ 26085 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7) - 6) \times 5) \times -((4 \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\ 26086 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 26087 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\ 26088 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3^2)))) - 1) \\ 26089 &:= (-98 + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26090 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3^2))) + 1)) \\ 26091 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26092 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - 2))) - 1) \\ 26093 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)))) \\ 26094 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 26095 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1})))) \\ 26096 &:= (98 + ((7 \times (6 - (5^4))) \times (-3 + (-2 - 1)))) \\ 26097 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 32))) - 1) \\ 26098 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times 43) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26099 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 26100 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26101 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 26102 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 26103 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 26104 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26105 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) - 1))) \\ 26106 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 26107 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times 2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26108 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! + (-4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26109 &:= ((-123 - ((4 + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) \times -8))) \times 9) \\ 26110 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4!) \times (5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26111 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times ((4^{5+6-7}) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 26112 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -((4^{5+6-7}) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 26113 &:= ((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 26114 &:= 1 \times 2 - (3! \times 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26115 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3 - (4! - 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26116 &:= ((12^3) - (4 \times (5 - (678 \times 9)))) \\ 26117 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 26118 &:= ((1 \times (234 - (-56 \times (-7 \times 8)))) \times -9) \\ 26119 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7))) + (-89)) \\ 26120 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times -(5 - ((6 - 78) \times 9))) \\ 26121 &:= ((-12 \times (3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) - 8)) + 9) \\ 26122 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (-34 \times ((56 \times 7) - 8)))) + 9) \\ 26123 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4!) \times (5 + 6!) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 26124 &:= (-12 - (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 \times 7)) \times -((8 \times 9))) \\ 26125 &:= ((12 \times (-(-3)^{-4+5+6})) + ((7 \times -((8 + 9)))) \\ 26126 &:= -1 - 2^{3+4+5} + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 26127 &:= -(((1 + 2) \times (3 \times (((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8) + 9))) \\ 26128 &:= ((12 + 34) \times (567 - (8 - 9))) \\ 26129 &:= (((((1 \times (2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times (-6 \times -7)) + 89) \\ 26130 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 26131 &:= (1 - ((-2 \times -3) \times (4 - ((56 \times 78) - 9))) \\ 26132 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\ 26133 &:= ((1 \times 2) + ((-3 - 4) \times (5 - ((6 \times -7) \times -89)))) \\ 26134 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 26135 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + ((45 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 26136 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 26137 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 26138 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 26139 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 26140 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 26141 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 - ((56 - 7) \times 89)))) \\ 26142 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 - ((56 - 7) \times 89))) \\ 26143 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + (-((56 - 7) \times 89)))) \\ 26144 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - 345))) \times ((-(-6) + 7) - 89)) \\ 26145 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) \times (-45 - (67 \times 8))) \times -9)) \\ 26146 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) \times (-45 - (67 \times 8))) \times -9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26108 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 26109 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - ((6 \times (5 + 4))^{3-2+1}))) \\ 26110 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26111 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 26112 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - 5)) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26113 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 26114 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\ 26115 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26116 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6 + ((54 \times 3)^2)) + 1))) \\ 26117 &:= (((98 - 7) \times -(((6 \times 5) - (-4 + 321)))) \\ 26118 &:= ((9 \times (((8765 + 4)/3) - 21))) \\ 26119 &:= (-9 - (-8 \times (((7 + (6 \times 543) + 2) - 1))) \\ 26120 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26121 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26122 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26123 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 26124 &:= (((987 + (65 \times 4)) - 3) \times (21)) \\ 26125 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 26126 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26127 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26128 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26129 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 - 2))) - 1))) \\ 26130 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (((6 + (5 \times (4 \times 3)))^2) - 1)) \\ 26131 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\ 26132 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 26133 &:= ((98 \times (7 + (65 \times 4))) + (-32) - 1) \\ 26134 &:= ((98 \times (7 + (65 \times 4))) + (-32) \times 1) \\ 26135 &:= ((98 \times (7 + (65 \times 4))) + ((-32) + 1)) \\ 26136 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 26137 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 + ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2)) + 1) \\ 26138 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 26139 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 26140 &:= (-9 - (((8 + (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26141 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 26142 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 26143 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 26144 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26145 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26146 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26147 &:= (((-1-2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) + (8+9) \\ 26148 &:= (-12 - (-((-3-45) \times ((67 \times -8) - 9))) \\ 26149 &:= 1 + ((2 \times (3+4)^5 + 6) \times 7 - 8)/9 \\ 26150 &:= (((-1+23) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9))) \\ 26151 &:= ((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times (8+9)))) \\ 26152 &:= (1 - (23 \times ((4 \times 5) - ((6+7) \times 89)))) \\ 26153 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 26154 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9 \\ 26155 &:= (((((1+2) \times 3)^4) \times ((5+6) - 7)) - 89) \\ 26156 &:= ((12^3) + (4 \times (5 + (678 \times 9)))) \\ 26157 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\ 26158 &:= ((1 - (((-2^3) - 45) \times 6)) \times (-7 + 89)) \\ 26159 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + 67))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 26160 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\ 26161 &:= (-1 + (2 - ((3 + 45) \times -(((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 26162 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) + ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26163 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((-3 - (45 - 6)) \times -((-7 \times -89)))) \\ 26164 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\ 26165 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 89)))) \\ 26166 &:= ((1 - (-2 - (3 - (4 - 5)))) \times (6 \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 26167 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 67))) \times -8) - 9) \\ 26168 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\ 26169 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((-(((3 + 45) - 6)) \times -7) \times 89)) \\ 26170 &:= (1 - (2 + 3)! + 4! \times (5! - 6)) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26171 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 26172 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) + 8) \times -9) \\ 26173 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26174 &:= ((1 \times -23) \times (-4 + (5 - (67 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 26175 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times ((4^5) + 67))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 26176 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + 67) \times 8))) - 9) \\ 26177 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + 67))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 26178 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 + ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26179 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 26180 &:= (((((1 + 23) - 4) \times -((5 + 6))) \times 7) \times (-8 - 9)) \\ 26181 &:= (((1^2) \times 3) + (-(((4 - 56) \times -7)) \times 8) \times -9) \\ 26182 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26183 &:= -((((1 - 23) \times ((4^5) + 67)) - (8 - 9))) \\ 26184 &:= (-((1 + 23)) + ((-4 + 56) \times ((7 \times 8) \times 9))) \\ 26185 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + 67))) \times -8) + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26147 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 26148 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times ((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 26149 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 26150 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 26151 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 26152 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26153 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26154 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 26155 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))))) + (2 - 1)) \\ 26156 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26157 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3)))))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26158 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1))) \\ 26159 &:= (((98 \times (7 + (65 \times 4))) - (3 \times 2)) - (1)) \\ 26160 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26161 &:= (((98 \times (7 + (65 \times 4))) - (3 \times 2)) + (1)) \\ 26162 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 26163 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26164 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 26165 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (-7 + (((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2) \times 1))) \\ 26166 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 26167 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\ 26168 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 26169 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26170 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26171 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26172 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26173 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 26174 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26175 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 26176 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 26177 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 26178 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^{4+3-2-1}))) \\ 26179 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26180 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 26181 &:= (-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times 6) \times (5 + (4^3))) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26182 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 26183 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 26184 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26185 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26186 &:= ((1 - 23) - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26187 &:= ((1 + (((2 + 3) + 45) \times 6)) \times (78 + 9)) \\ 26188 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!) \times (4 + 5) \times (6! + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 26189 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((34 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\ 26190 &:= (((((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times 5) + 6) \times -((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\ 26191 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 26192 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 \times (4 - (56 \times 78)))) - 9)) \\ 26193 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times (3 \times (4 - (56 \times 78)))) - 9)) \\ 26194 &:= (-(-1) - ((2 \times (3 \times (4 - (56 \times 78)))) - 9)) \\ 26195 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) - 45) \times (6 - (78 \times -9)))) \\ 26196 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times (4 - 5)) \times 67) \times (-8 - 9))) \\ 26197 &:= (1 \times (((23 \times (4 - 5)) \times 67) \times (-8 - 9))) \\ 26198 &:= (1 + (((23 \times (4 - 5)) \times 67) \times (-8 - 9))) \\ 26199 &:= (-1 \times ((-2 - (-3 - (((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26200 &:= (((1 \times -2)^3) - (((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8) \times 9) \\ 26201 &:= (((((-1 - 2) - (3^{4+5}))/6) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\ 26202 &:= (-1 \times (-2 \times ((-3 \times (4 - (56 \times 78))) + 9))) \\ 26203 &:= ((1 \times -2) - (3 + (((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8) \times 9)) \\ 26204 &:= ((-12/3) - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26205 &:= ((1^2) \times (-3 - (((4 - 56) \times 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26206 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26207 &:= (-((1 \times -2)) - (3 + (((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8) \times 9)) \\ 26208 &:= ((123 + 45) \times (67 + 89)) \\ 26209 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 26210 &:= (-1 \times -2 + ((3 + (45 \times 6)) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 26211 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26212 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26213 &:= ((1 \times (2 + 3)) + (((4 - 56) \times -7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 26214 &:= ((1 + (2 + 3)) + (((4 - 56) \times -7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 26215 &:= ((-1 + (2^3)) - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26216 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) + (((-4 - 56) \times -7) \times (-8 \times 9))) \\ 26217 &:= (1 \times (((-(-2 + 3)) + (((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\ 26218 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 26219 &:= (-1 - (23 \times ((4 - 5) - (67 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 26220 &:= (((12 - (3^4)) \times 5) \times (6 + (7 - 89))) \\ 26221 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 26222 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 26223 &:= (-12 + ((3 - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26224 &:= ((1 - (-2 \times (-3 \times -((4 - (-56 \times 78)))))) + (-9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26186 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26187 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26188 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - (3^2))) + 1) \\ 26189 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 26190 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\ 26191 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 26192 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 26193 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26194 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26195 &:= ((9 - (-8 \times 7)) \times (-((6 \times 5)) + (432 + 1))) \\ 26196 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26197 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26198 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 26199 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (-6 \times -((54 + 3)) - (21)))) \\ 26200 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 - 2))) - 1))) \\ 26201 &:= (((9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) - ((54 \times -3)^2))) \times -1) \\ 26202 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26203 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 - 1)))) \\ 26204 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3^2)))) \times -1) \\ 26205 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 26206 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 26207 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 26208 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26209 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26210 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26211 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26212 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 26213 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 26214 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 26215 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26216 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 26217 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))/3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26218 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + (((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) + 1)) \\ 26219 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 26220 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - 7) + (((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2) \times 1)) \\ 26221 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 26222 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 26223 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 26224 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26225 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) \\ 26226 &:= ((1234 + (((5 \times 6) \times 7) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 26227 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) \times ((5 + 6) - 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 26228 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 26229 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + 67)) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 26230 &:= ((-1 + 23) - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26231 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times 3) \times (4^5))/6) - 7) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 26232 &:= (-12 \times -(((3^{4+5}) + (6 - (7 + 8)))/9)) \\ 26233 &:= ((1 \times -2) + ((3 - ((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 26234 &:= ((-12 \times (-3^{-4+5+6})) + (7 - ((8 + 9)))) \\ 26235 &:= ((-(((1 + 2) \times 3)^4)) \times (5 + ((6 - 7) - 8))) - 9) \\ 26236 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26237 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((3 - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 26238 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 - ((56 \times 78) + 9))) \\ 26239 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9))))) \\ 26240 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}))/6) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 26241 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -(4 + (56 \times 78))) + 9) \\ 26242 &:= (((-12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) - 89) \\ 26243 &:= (-1 + (((((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))/8) \times 9)) \\ 26244 &:= (-((-12 \times 3)) \times -((4 + (56 - 789)))) \\ 26245 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) \times ((5 + 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 26246 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -((4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 26247 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -((3 + ((4^5) + 67)) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 26248 &:= ((-((-1 - 23)) + ((4 \times -56) \times 7)) \times (-8 - 9)) \\ 26249 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) - 89))) \\ 26250 &:= ((12 \times (3^{-4+5+6})) + (7 - (-8 + 9))) \\ 26251 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (4 + (56 \times 78))) + 9))) \\ 26252 &:= (-1 - ((-2 + (-3 + ((4 - 56) \times 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26253 &:= ((-(((1 + 2) \times 3)^4)) \times (5 + ((6 - 7) - 8))) + 9) \\ 26254 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times ((4 - (56 + 7)) \times 89))) \\ 26255 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) - 5) \times 6) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) \\ 26256 &:= (-((1 - 2)) - (((3 + 45) \times 6) + 7) \times -89)) \\ 26257 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (((3 + 45) \times 6) + 7) \times 89)) \\ 26258 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 + 45) \times 6) + 7) \times 89)) \\ 26259 &:= (((-12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26260 &:= (((((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 26261 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) \times ((5 + 6) - 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\ 26262 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((3 - ((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 26263 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + (((4 + 5) - 6)^7))) - (8 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26225 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26226 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 26227 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26228 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times ((6 + 5) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 26229 &:= ((((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26230 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 26231 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) - ((54 \times 3)^2)) - (-1))) \\ 26232 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26233 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 + 6) - ((54 \times 3)^2)) + (-1))) \\ 26234 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26235 &:= (-9 + (((8 + ((7 - 6)^5))^4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 26236 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 26237 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 26238 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 26239 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26240 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26241 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\ 26242 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26243 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26244 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26245 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26246 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26247 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26248 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 26249 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^{4+3-2-1}))) \\ 26250 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^{4+3-2-1})) \\ 26251 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) + (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 26252 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) - ((6 + 5)^4))/(3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 26253 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -((5^4) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26254 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) - ((6 + 5)^4))/(3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 26255 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26256 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26257 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26258 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26259 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 26260 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 26261 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 26262 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times ((6 \times ((5 + 4)^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26263 &:= ((((-9 - (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) - 3)) \times -2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 26264** := $((-(((12-3)^4) - 5) \times (-(-6) + (7 - (8+9))))$
26265 := $(-1 \times ((2 + ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times (8+9)))$
26266 := $(((-1+23) \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))$
26267 := $(12 + (((3+45) \times 6) + 7) \times 89)$
26268 := $(-12 \times -(3 + (((4+5) - 6)^7) + (8-9)))$
26269 := $-1 + (2 + (3+4) \times 5) \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9)$
26270 := $(1 + (-2+3!) \times (4+5)) \times (6! + 7 - 8 - 9)$
26271 := $(-(1+2)) \times (((3^4) \times ((-5 \times 6) - 78)) - 9)$
26272 := $12 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 + 7 + 8)/9$
26273 := $(((-1 - ((2 + (3^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9)$
26274 := $(1 + (2+3)!/4) \times (5! + 6! + 7) + 8 + 9$
26275 := $((((1+2)^3) + (4^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8+9)))$
26276 := $(-1 - (((-2 + (345 - 6)) \times -78) + 9))$
26277 := $(-1 \times (((2 - (345 - 6)) \times 78) + 9))$
26278 := $(1 - (((2 - (345 - 6)) \times 78) + 9))$
26279 := $(-1 - ((2+3) \times ((4 - ((5+6) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))))$
26280 := $(12 \times (3 - (((-((4+5) + 6)^7) \times (-8+9))))$
26281 := $((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8-9)))$
26282 := $(((-1+2) + ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times -(8+9))$
26283 := $((-1-2) \times -(((3 + ((4^5) + 67)) \times 8) + 9))$
26284 := $1 \times 2 \times (-3 + 4^5 + (6! - 7) \times (8+9))$
26285 := $((-1 + (2+34)) \times -(5 - ((6+78) \times 9)))$
26286 := $(-12 + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))$
26287 := $(((((1-2) + (3^{4+5}))/6) + 7) \times 8) - 9$
26288 := $-1 + (2 + (3! \times 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8)) \times 9$
26289 := $((((-1 + (2^3))^4) + (5 \times ((6+7) \times 8))) \times 9)$
26290 := $(1 - 2 + 3) \times (4^5 + (6! - 7) \times (8+9))$
26291 := $-(((12 \times (-3^-(-((-4+5) - 6)))) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)))$
26292 := $(12 \times (3 - (((-((4+5) + 6)^7) - (-8+9))))$
26293 := $-1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9)$
26294 := $(-1 - (((2 - (345 - 6)) \times 78) - 9))$
26295 := $(((((1-2) - (3^{4+5}))/6) - 7) \times -8) - 9$
26296 := $(-((-1 + (2+345))) \times -(((6-7) + 89)))$
26297 := $((-12 \times (3 - (((4+5) - 6)^7)) - (-89))$
26298 := $(((-123 \times -4) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7-8)) \times -9))$
26299 := $((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times ((6+7) \times (8+9)))$
26300 := $((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)))$
26301 := $(-1 \times -(2 - ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times (8+9))))$
26302 := $((1+2) - ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times (8+9))))$
26264 := $(((-9+8) - (7+6)) \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + (2-1)))$
26265 := $(-9 + ((8 + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))/3)) \times (2+1)))$
26266 := $(((-9-8) - (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) - (3-2))) \times -1)$
26267 := $(((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3))) - (2+1))$
26268 := $((((-9+8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) - (2+1))$
26269 := $((-9-8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3+2))) + 1))$
26270 := $(((-9 \times (8 + (7+6))) \times (5 - ((4 \times 3)^2))) - 1)$
26271 := $(-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 \times (6+5)) - 4) \times (3+2))) - 1))$
26272 := $(((-9-8) - (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3+2))) \times -1)$
26273 := $((9 + (((876 \times 5) - 4) \times 3)) \times 2) - (1)$
26274 := $((9 + (((876 \times 5) - 4) \times 3)) \times 2) \times -(-1))$
26275 := $((9 + (((876 \times 5) - 4) \times 3)) \times 2) + (1)$
26276 := $((-9+8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1})))$
26277 := $((((-9+8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) + (3^{2+1}))$
26278 := $(((-9+8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) + ((3+2) - 1)))$
26279 := $((-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 \times (6+5)) - 4) \times (3+2)))) - 1)$
26280 := $((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2+1))))))$
26281 := $((-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 \times (6+5)) - 4) \times (3+2)))) + 1)$
26282 := $((-9-8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3-2))) + 1)))$
26283 := $((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2+1))))$
26284 := $(-9 - ((-8 \times 7) + (6 - (((54 \times -3)^2) - 1))))$
26285 := $(((-9+8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) + ((3+2) \times 1)))$
26286 := $(-9 - (8765 \times ((4 - (3 \times 2)) - 1)))$
26287 := $((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - ((3+2) \times 1))))$
26288 := $((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3+2))) + 1))$
26289 := $(((-9 + 8765) + (4+3)) \times ((2+1)))$
26290 := $(((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times ((5+4) \times 3))^2)) - 1)$
26291 := $((-9+8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times (3 + (2+1))))))$
26292 := $(((-9+8) \times 7) \times -(6 + ((5^4) \times (3 + (2+1))))))$
26293 := $((((-9+8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3-2))) + 1)$
26294 := $((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - ((3+2) - 1))))$
26295 := $((9 + ((8765 + 4) \times 3)) - (21))$
26296 := $((-9-8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2+1))))))$
26297 := $((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2-1))))$
26298 := $(-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)))) \times (2+1)))$
26299 := $((-9-8) \times -((7 \times (((6+5) \times (4 \times (3+2))) + 1)))$
26300 := $(((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3))) - (2-1))$
26301 := $(((-9-8) - (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))/3)) \times -(2+1))$
26302 := $(((-9-8) - (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3+2)))) \times -1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 26303 &:= (-1 - (-2 \times (((3^4) + 56) \times (7 + 89)))) \\ 26304 &:= (-12 + (((3^4) + 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 26305 &:= (((((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}))/6) + 7) \times 8) + 9 \\ 26306 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -((4 \times 5) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))) \\ 26307 &:= ((-((-1 - 2) + 34) \times -((5 - (6 + 78)) \times 9)) \\ 26308 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((34 + 5) \times (67 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26309 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times 67) - 89) \\ 26310 &:= (12 + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 26311 &:= (-(-12) - ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 26312 &:= ((1 \times (23 \times -4)) \times -((5 \times (67 - 8))) + 9) \\ 26313 &:= (1 + ((23 \times 4) \times ((5 \times (67 - 8)) - 9))) \\ 26314 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 26315 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 26316 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 \times -4) - 5)) \times (-6 - ((7 + 8) \times -9))) \\ 26317 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 26318 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 26319 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 4)) \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\ 26320 &:= ((-1 - (2 + (3 + 4))) \times -((56 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 26321 &:= ((-123 \times -(-4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 - 9)) \\ 26322 &:= (-123 \times -((4^5) - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 26323 &:= ((-123 \times -(-4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 - 9)) \\ 26324 &:= ((1 - 2) - ((34 + 5) \times -((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 26325 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 + 7)))) + 8)) \times -9) \\ 26326 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times 67) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26327 &:= (-1 \times -(-2 + ((34 + 5) \times ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 26328 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) - ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26329 &:= (((1 + 234) \times (56 + (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 26330 &:= (((-12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) + (8 - 9)) \\ 26331 &:= ((-12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (67 \times -((8 - 9)))) \\ 26332 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 26333 &:= -(((1 \times (2 - ((3 + (-4 \times 56)) \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 26334 &:= (((12 - (3 \times ((4^5) + (-6 \times 7)))) + 8) \times -9) \\ 26335 &:= (1 + ((2 + (34 \times ((5 \times 6) + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 26336 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times (56 \times 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 26337 &:= (12 - ((34 + 5) \times -((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 26338 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 + (4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) \\ 26339 &:= ((-123 \times -(-4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 26340 &:= (-12 \times -(((3^{4+5}) - (6 - 78))/9)) \\ 26341 &:= (((-123 \times 4) - 5) \times -((6 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26303 &:= -(((9 \times 87) \times -6) + (-5 \times (4321))) \\ 26304 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5^4))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26305 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + ((3^2) - 1)))) \\ 26306 &:= ((-9 \times -(-8 - (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 26307 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26308 &:= (-(((9 + (8765 - 4)) \times -3)) - (2 \times -(-1))) \\ 26309 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 26310 &:= (-(((9 + (8765 - 4)) \times -3)) \times (2 - (1))) \\ 26311 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3^2)))) - 1) \\ 26312 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26313 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26314 &:= (((9 - (-8 \times 7)) + (6 + ((54 \times 3)^2))) + ((-1))) \\ 26315 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26316 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26317 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 26318 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26319 &:= (-9 + (((8765 + 4) \times 3) + (21))) \\ 26320 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) + ((3^2) + 1))) \\ 26321 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^4))) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 26322 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times (5^{4+3-2-1}))) \\ 26323 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26324 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 26325 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5 + 4))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\ 26326 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 26327 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 26328 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26329 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26330 &:= (98 + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + 3) + (-21)) \\ 26331 &:= ((((-9 - 8765) - 4) \times -3) - ((2 + 1))) \\ 26332 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6^5) + 4)/(3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 26333 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6^5) + 4)/((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 26334 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6^5) + 4)/(3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 26335 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 26336 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 26337 &:= ((9 + ((8765 + 4) \times 3)) + (21)) \\ 26338 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 26339 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 26340 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26341 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26342 &:= (((-1 + (2^3)^4) \times (5 + 6)) - (78 - 9)) \\ 26343 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times 8)))) \times 9) \\ 26344 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times 89) \\ 26345 &:= (1 + ((234 - (5 - 67)) \times 89)) \\ 26346 &:= (((1 + (2 \times 3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + (7 - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26347 &:= -1 - 2 - (3! + 4 - 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26348 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26349 &:= ((-12 \times -(3^{4 \times 5 - 6 - 7}) + 8)) + 9) \\ 26350 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 26351 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26352 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times ((-3 \times ((4 \times 5) + (6 \times 78))) \times -9)) \\ 26353 &:= ((-1 - (2^3) \times 45) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 26354 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3! + (-4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26355 &:= (((1 - 2) + ((345 - 6)) \times 78) - 9) \\ 26356 &:= 12 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 + 78) / 9 \\ 26357 &:= (-1 + 2) + 3! + (-4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26358 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times (5! - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26359 &:= (((12^3) + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 26360 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7)) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 26361 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times 8)))) \times -9) \\ 26362 &:= (1 + (((23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times 6)) + 7)) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 26363 &:= -(((12 \times (-3^{-4+5+6})) + ((7 \times -((8 + 9)))))) \\ 26364 &:= (((-1 + (2^3)^4) \times (5 + 6)) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 26365 &:= (-1 - 2^{3 \times 4} + 5! + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9)) \\ 26366 &:= -1 + (-2 - 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26367 &:= ((1 - (2 - 34)) \times ((5 - (-6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 26368 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times ((56 + (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 26369 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + (((4 + 5) - 6^7))) + 89) \\ 26370 &:= ((-1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + 8)) \times 9) \\ 26371 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 345) \times ((-6 - 7) + 89))) \\ 26372 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 345) \times ((6 + 7) - 89))) \\ 26373 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (345 - 6)) \times -78) + 9) \\ 26374 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26375 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 - ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))) \\ 26376 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 - ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) \\ 26377 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) + 89)) \\ 26378 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9) \\ 26379 &:= ((-12 \times (-3^{-4+5+6})) + ((-7 - 8) \times -9)) \\ 26380 &:= (1 + (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26342 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26343 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (76 - (5^4))) \times -(3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26344 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\ 26345 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4) + 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\ 26346 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26347 &:= ((-98 - (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) - (3 - 2))) \times -1) \\ 26348 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5) \times -(4 \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\ 26349 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 26350 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 26351 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) - ((6 + 5)^4)) / (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 26352 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26353 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) - ((6 + 5)^4)) / (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 26354 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4) + 3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 26355 &:= (-((-9 + (8765 + 4))) \times 3) + (21) \\ 26356 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26357 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 26358 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 26359 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times 2) + 1) \\ 26360 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4) + 3) - 2))) - 1) \\ 26361 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 26362 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26363 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 26364 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 26365 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\ 26366 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (((5^4) + 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\ 26367 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26368 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (((5^4) + 3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 26369 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) + 3) - (2 - 1))) \\ 26370 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) + (((6^5) / 4) \times 3) / 2)) - 1) \\ 26371 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4) + (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\ 26372 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26373 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26374 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26375 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 26376 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -(((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26377 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 26378 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26379 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5)) + 4) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\ 26380 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

- 26381** := $((1 + (2 + 34)) \times ((5 + 6) + (78 \times 9)))$
26382 := $-1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4 \times 5! + 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9$
26383 := $-1 - (2 + 3! - 4! \times 5 \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9)$
26384 := $((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times -((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))$
26385 := $((-12 \times -(3 + (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + 8))) + 9$
26386 := $(-1 \times -(((2 \times (34 \times 5)) - 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))$
26387 := $((((1 - (2^3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) - ((8 + 9))$
26388 := $((12 - 3) \times -((4 \times (56 - 789))))$
26389 := $(1 - ((2 + 34) \times (56 - 789)))$
26390 := $((((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))$
26391 := $-1 - 2^{3+4} + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$
26392 := $(-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 \times 9)))$
26393 := $(-1 - (((2^3) + 45) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
26394 := $((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$
26395 := $(((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + 5) \times 6)) \times -7) - (8 \times 9)$
26396 := $(-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (45 \times (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)$
26397 := $((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((45 \times -((6 + 78))) + 9))$
26398 := $((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -(67 \times (8 - 9)))$
26399 := $(-1 + ((2 - (-3 - (45 \times 6))) \times (7 + 89)))$
26400 := $((1 \times (2 - (-3 - (45 \times 6)))) \times (7 + 89))$
26401 := $(1 + ((2 - (-3 - (45 \times 6))) \times (7 + 89)))$
26402 := $((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))$
26403 := $(-1 + (-23 \times (((-4 \times 5) + 6) \times -((7 - 89))))$
26404 := $((((1 - (2^3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + (7 \times (8 - 9)))$
26405 := $((((1 - (2^3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) - ((7 + 8) - 9))$
26406 := $((-1 - 1) - (((2 + 3) \times 45) \times (-6 - 7) - 8) \times 9)$
26407 := $(1 - ((2 - ((3 - ((4 - 56) \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9))$
26408 := $-1 - 2 + 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! \times 7 - 8 - 9)$
26409 := $(1 + 2) \times (3!!/4 + 5 \times 6! + 7! - 8 - 9)$
26410 := $((-(((1 + (2^3))^{-4})) \times -((5 + 6))) - ((-7 + 8)^9))$
26411 := $(((-1 + (2^3))^4) \times -(5 - (6 - (7 - (8 + 9))))$
26412 := $(-12 \times (3 - (((4 + 5) - 6)^7) + (8 + 9)))$
26413 := $((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + 5)) \times -(6 \times 7)) - 89$
26414 := $(-1 + ((23 - ((4 - 56) \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))$
26415 := $(((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) - 8) \times 9)$
26416 := $(-1 \times (2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 + (7 \times 89))))$
26417 := $((1 + (-2)) + ((3 - 45) \times (-6 - (-7 \times -89))))$
26418 := $((1 + (-2)) \times -(((3 - 45) \times (-6 - (-7 \times -89))))$
26419 := $(1 - (((2 - 34) - 5) \times ((-6 \times 7) \times -((8 + 9))))$
26381 := $((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1)))$
26382 := $((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 - 1))))$
26383 := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 - 1)))$
26384 := $((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - ((6^5) - 4)) / (3 + 2)) + 1))$
26385 := $((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2 + 1))))$
26386 := $((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3^2))) + 1))$
26387 := $(((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2)))) - 1)$
26388 := $((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))))$
26389 := $((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1))$
26390 := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)))$
26391 := $((((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))$
26392 := $((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + ((3^2) + 1))))$
26393 := $(((-9 - ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times -2) - 1)$
26394 := $((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$
26395 := $((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1)))$
26396 := $((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1))))$
26397 := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1)))$
26398 := $((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (43 + 2)))) + 1)$
26399 := $((((1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))$
26400 := $(((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))$
26401 := $((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3 + 2) - 1))))$
26402 := $(((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - ((6^5) - 4)) / (3 + 2))) + 1)$
26403 := $((-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2)))) - 1)$
26404 := $(-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + (2 + 1))))$
26405 := $((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) - 2)) - 1)$
26406 := $((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 - (2 - 1))))$
26407 := $(((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + 2))) \times -1)$
26408 := $((9 + 8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + 2)) + 1))$
26409 := $((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (32 + 1))))$
26410 := $((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$
26411 := $(((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$
26412 := $((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 65) + 4) \times 3) - 21)$
26413 := $((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 + ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1)))$
26414 := $((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 65) + 4) \times 3) - 2) - 1)$
26415 := $(-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) - (2 - 1)))$
26416 := $((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 65) + 4) \times 3) - 2) + 1)$
26417 := $(((98 + 76) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1)$
26418 := $(((98 + 76) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) \times 1)$
26419 := $(((98 + 76) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) + 1)$

- 26420** := $((1 \times -(-2)) - ((3 - 45) \times -((-6 - (-7 \times -89))))$ **26420** := $-9 \times 8 - (7 + 6 \times 5) \times (4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!)$
26421 := $((((-1 + (2^3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 - (8 + 9)))$ **26421** := $((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) - (2 + 1))$
26422 := $-(((1 \times 2) + (((-34 \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times (8 \times 9))))$ **26422** := $((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1}))))$
26423 := $((1 - 2) + ((3 - ((4 - 56) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))$ **26423** := $((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) - (2 - 1))$
26424 := $((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 7)))))) \times -(8 \times 9))$ **26424** := $((-9 \times -(8 \times (((7 + (6 \times (5 + 4))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)))$
26425 := $((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))$ **26425** := $((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 - 1))$
26426 := $((1 \times 2) - (((-34 \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))$ **26426** := $((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 \times 1))$
26427 := $((-1 \times 23) \times -((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))$ **26427** := $((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 + 1))$
26428 := $(1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))$ **26428** := $((9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$
26429 := $(1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (-4! + (5! - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))$ **26429** := $(((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2)))) - 1)$
26430 := $(-1 + (-2 + (((345 - 6) \times 78) - 9)))$ **26430** := $((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + (2 + 1))))$
26431 := $((-12 \times -(34 \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) - 89)$ **26431** := $((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1))$
26432 := $-((-1 - (-2 + (((345 - 6) \times 78) - 9))))$ **26432** := $((((9 \times (8 + 76)) \times 5) - 4) \times ((3 \times 2) + (1)))$
26433 := $(((-12 + (345 + 6)) \times 78) - 9)$ **26433** := $(-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 - 1)))$
26434 := $(((-1 + 2) + ((345 - 6) \times 78)) - 9)$ **26434** := $((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -(((5^4) - 3)/2)) - 1)$
26435 := $-(((1 \times -2) - (-((-34 - 5) \times 678) - 9)))$ **26435** := $((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2))) + 1))$
26436 := $-((-1 + (-2 - (((345 - 6) \times 78) - 9))))$ **26436** := $((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1)))$
26437 := $-1 \times 2 - 3^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$ **26437** := $((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1)))$
26438 := $(((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) \times 5) + (67 \times 89))$ **26438** := $((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1}))))$
26439 := $(-1 - (-2 \times (-3 - (((4^5) \times -((6 + 7))) + 89))))$ **26439** := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1})))$
26440 := $((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9))$ **26440** := $((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2))) - 1)$
26441 := $(-1 + ((2 + (((3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6))) + 7) \times 8)) \times 9))$ **26441** := $((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 - 1))))$
26442 := $((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))$ **26442** := $(((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2)))) - 1)$
26443 := $((((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9))$ **26443** := $((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))))$
26444 := $((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9))$ **26444** := $((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1))$
26445 := $((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9))))$ **26445** := $((-9 + ((8 \times 7) - 6)) \times (((5 \times 43) \times (2 + 1))))$
26446 := $(((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - 89))$ **26446** := $(((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) - (2 \times 1))$
26447 := $(-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 + 9)))$ **26447** := $(((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) - (2 - 1))$
26448 := $(12 \times ((34 - 5) \times -((6 + 7)) + 89))$ **26448** := $((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 - 1))))$
26449 := $(-1 \times (2 - (((345 - 6) \times 78) + 9)))$ **26449** := $((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 - 1)))$
26450 := $((1 - 2) - (-((345 - 6) \times 78) - 9))$ **26450** := $((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1)))$
26451 := $(((-12 + (345 + 6)) \times 78) + 9)$ **26451** := $(-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))))) + (2 + 1))$
26452 := $((1^2) \times 34) \times -((5 + 6) + 789)$ **26452** := $((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1)))$
26453 := $((1 \times 2) - (((-34 - 5) \times 678) - 9))$ **26453** := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1))$
26454 := $((1 \times 2) + (34 \times -((5 + 6) + 789)))$ **26454** := $((((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))))) / 3) \times (2 \times 1))$
26455 := $((1 + 2) + (-34 \times ((5 + 6) - 789))$ **26455** := $(((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + 5)) \times -((4 \times (3^2)) + 1))$
26456 := $(-1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + 89))$ **26456** := $(((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 32))) - 1)$
26457 := $((-1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 + 78) \times 9))))$ **26457** := $((-9 + (87 \times (6 - (5 \times ((4^3) - 2)))))) \times -1)$
26458 := $((-1 \times 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (-5 \times ((6 + 78) \times 9))))$ **26458** := $((9 \times (8 + 76)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) - ((2 \times 1))$
26459 := $(-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9))))$ **26459** := $((9 \times (8 + 76)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) - ((2 - 1))$

$$\begin{aligned} 26460 &:= (-((1 + (-2^3)) \times 45)) \times (67 - (-8 - 9)) \\ 26461 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26462 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 + 78) \times 9)))) \\ 26463 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) - (8 - 9))) \\ 26464 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (67 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 26465 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times (34 \times 5)) - 6)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 26466 &:= 1 + (-2 + 3^4) \times 5 \times 67 \times (-8 + 9) \\ 26467 &:= 1 + (-2 + 3^4) \times 5 \times 67 - 8 + 9 \\ 26468 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + 5) \times 6)) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 26469 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^{4+5})) - 6789)) \\ 26470 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - (3^{4+5})) - 6789)) \\ 26471 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3^{4+5})) - 6789)) \\ 26472 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3)^{4+5} + 6789) \\ 26473 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 26474 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26475 &:= (((1 + 2) + (3^{4+5})) + (6789)) \\ 26476 &:= (((1 + (2 \times 3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26477 &:= (((((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\ 26478 &:= ((((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 + (6 + 7))) - 8) \times -9) \\ 26479 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) - 9) \\ 26480 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 26481 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) - (8 + 9))) \\ 26482 &:= ((((((1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -5) \times 67) + 8) + 9) \\ 26483 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) - (8 + 9))) \\ 26484 &:= (12 \times (((3 - ((-(4 + 5)) + 6^7)) + 8) - (-9))) \\ 26485 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + 5)) \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 26486 &:= ((-1 - (-23 \times ((-4 \times 5) + 6))) \times (7 - 89)) \\ 26487 &:= (1 \times ((23 + 4) \times ((-5 - ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times -9))) \\ 26488 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\ 26489 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 26490 &:= (12 + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) - 9)) \\ 26491 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times 89) \\ 26492 &:= -12^3 - 4 + 56 \times 7 \times 8 \times 9 \\ 26493 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) + 9)) \\ 26494 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) + 9)) \\ 26495 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (4 \times (((5 + 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26496 &:= ((1 \times 23) \times (((4^5) / -(((6 - 7) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26497 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) + 9)) \\ 26498 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26460 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 26461 &:= (((9 \times (8 + 76)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + ((2 - 1))) \\ 26462 &:= (((9 \times (8 + 76)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + ((2 \times 1))) \\ 26463 &:= (-((-9 \times ((8 + 76) \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + ((2 + 1))) \\ 26464 &:= (-9 + ((((-8 \times 7) - 6) \times (-(-5) - 432)) - 1)) \\ 26465 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) - 5) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26466 &:= (-9 + ((((-8 \times 7) - 6) \times (-(-5) - 432)) + 1)) \\ 26467 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 26468 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 26469 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26470 &:= ((-98 + (((7 - 6) + (54 \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 26471 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 26472 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 26473 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 26474 &:= ((-98 - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 3))) \times -(2 - 1)) \\ 26475 &:= (((-98/7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 26476 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26477 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\ 26478 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - (5 + 4)) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\ 26479 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1))) \\ 26480 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43))) + (2 - 1))) \\ 26481 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43))) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 26482 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26483 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times (6 + 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 26484 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 26485 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26486 &:= ((((-987) + 6) \times (5 + 4)) \times -3) + (-2 - (-1)) \\ 26487 &:= -(((987) + 6) \times (54 / (((3 - 2) + 1)))) \\ 26488 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26489 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3^2))) + 1) \\ 26490 &:= ((((-987) + 6) \times (5 + 4)) \times -3) - (-2 + (-1)) \\ 26491 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 26492 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1))) \\ 26493 &:= ((((-98/7) \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 26494 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) - 1))) \\ 26495 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) + 5) \times -((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 26496 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26497 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) + 1)) \\ 26498 &:= (((-9 - ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26499 &:= ((1+2) + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8)) + 9)) \\
 26500 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - (4^5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8+9))) \\
 26501 &:= (((-1 - ((2+3)^4) + 5)) \times (-6 \times 7)) + (8-9) \\
 26502 &:= ((-1 - (((2+3)^4) + 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8-9)))) \\
 26503 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6+7)))))) \times (8+9)) \\
 26504 &:= -(-1+2+3) \times 4+5! \times (6+7) \times (8+9) \\
 26505 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 4)) \times ((5 + (6 \times (7+8)))) \times 9) \\
 26506 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3+4) + 5! \times (6+7) \times (8+9) \\
 26507 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) \times (5+6)) + (7+89)) \\
 26508 &:= ((12 + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) - 8))) + 9) \\
 26509 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times (4^5)) - (67 \times (8+9)) \\
 26510 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4 + 5! \times (6+7) \times (8+9) \\
 26511 &:= (((1-2) - ((345-6))) \times -78) - 9) \\
 26512 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6+7)) + (8+9))) \\
 26513 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((45 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 26514 &:= ((-1-2) \times -(((3^4) \times (5 + ((6+7) \times 8))) + 9)) \\
 26515 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -67) - (8+9)) \\
 26516 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times (6+7)) - (8+9)) \\
 26517 &:= ((-1-2) + (34 \times (5 \times (67+89)))) \\
 26518 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) - (6 - ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\
 26519 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times ((6+7) \times (8+9)))))) \\
 26520 &:= (((1+2) \times -((34 \times 5)) \times ((6 \times -78)/9)) \\
 26521 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6+7)) + 8)) - 9) \\
 26522 &:= (((1+234) + (56+7)) \times 89) \\
 26523 &:= ((1+2) + (-34 \times (5 \times (-67-89)))) \\
 26524 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) - 89)) \\
 26525 &:= (((-1 + (((2+3)^4) + 5) \times 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 26526 &:= (-1+2+3)!/4+5! \times (6+7) \times (8+9) \\
 26527 &:= (-1+2) \times (3+4) + 5! \times (6+7) \times (8+9) \\
 26528 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6+7))) + (8+9))) \\
 26529 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6+7))) - (8+9)) \\
 26530 &:= ((-1 + (2+34)) \times (56 + ((78 \times 9)))) \\
 26531 &:= (-((1 + (-2 + (3 - 45)))) \times (-6 + (-7 \times -89))) \\
 26532 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times (6+7)) + (8-9)) \\
 26533 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times -((6+7) \times (8-9))) \\
 26534 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times (6+7)) - (8-9)) \\
 26535 &:= ((((-1-2) - ((3^4) - 5)) \times -6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 26536 &:= (-1 + (-(((234-5) - 6) \times -7)) \times (8+9)) \\
 26537 &:= (((((12 \times -34) \times -5) \times (6+7)) + 8) + (-(-9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26499 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 26500 &:= ((((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 26501 &:= ((-9+8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 + (2+1)))) \\
 26502 &:= (((-9+8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3 + (2+1)))) \\
 26503 &:= ((-9-8) \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
 26504 &:= (((-9+8) - (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 26505 &:= ((-((98/7)) \times ((-6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) - ((-2 - 1))) \\
 26506 &:= ((-9-8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + 21))) \\
 26507 &:= ((((-9+8) - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
 26508 &:= (((-9+8) - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -(3 + (2+1))) \\
 26509 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 26510 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 26511 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1})))) \\
 26512 &:= ((9 + (8 \times ((7 \times ((6+5) \times 43)) + 2))) - 1) \\
 26513 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) - (4 \times 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 26514 &:= ((9 + (8765 + (4^3))) \times (2+1)) \\
 26515 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) - (4 \times 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\
 26516 &:= ((-98/7) \times -(((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) + (2-1))) \\
 26517 &:= (((-9 \times ((8+7) \times 65)) - (4^3)) \times -(2+1)) \\
 26518 &:= (9 + ((8 \times (7 \times ((6+5) \times 43))) + 21)) \\
 26519 &:= (((-9-8) \times -((7+6) \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 26520 &:= ((-9-8) \times -((7+6) \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 + (2+1)))))) \\
 26521 &:= (((-9-8) \times -((7+6) \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) + 1) \\
 26522 &:= ((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + 21))) \\
 26523 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (4^3))) + (2+1))) \\
 26524 &:= ((9-8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 3)) + 21))) \\
 26525 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3+2))) - 1))) \\
 26526 &:= (-9 - (87 \times (6 - (((5^4) - 3)/(2 \times 1)))) \\
 26527 &:= ((-9-8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
 26528 &:= ((((-9 \times (8-76)) + 5) \times 43) - (2+1)) \\
 26529 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2)))) - 1) \\
 26530 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2+1)))) \\
 26531 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3+2)))) - 1) \\
 26532 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3+2) \times 1)))) \\
 26533 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3+2))) + 1)) \\
 26534 &:= ((((-9 \times (8-76)) + 5) \times 43) + (2+1)) \\
 26535 &:= ((((-9-8) - (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\
 26536 &:= (((-9-8) - (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 26537 &:= ((-9-8) \times -(7 \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4+3)) + 2)) + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26538 &:= ((1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 56)) \times ((-7 - 8) + 9)) \\
 26539 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + 8)) + 9) \\
 26540 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7)))))) - 89) \\
 26541 &:= ((1 \times (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7)))))) - 89) \\
 26542 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7)))))) - 89) \\
 26543 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 - 9)))) \\
 26544 &:= (-((1 + 23)) \times (((4 \times 5) - 6) \times (-7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26545 &:= (1 - (-(((2 - (3^4)) \times 56)) \times ((-7 - 8) + 9))) \\
 26546 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 26547 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 26548 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 - 9))) \\
 26549 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -67) + (8 + 9)) \\
 26550 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\
 26551 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) + 45) \times ((67 - 8) \times -9))) \\
 26552 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 26553 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 8)) - 9) \\
 26554 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 26555 &:= (1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) - 89)) \\
 26556 &:= (-12 - ((-34 + (-5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 26557 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26558 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times -(6 + 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 26559 &:= (-(((123 \times -4) \times (5 - (67 - 8)))) - 9) \\
 26560 &:= ((-((12 \times 3) - 4) \times ((5 - 678) + 9)) \\
 26561 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((56 \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26562 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9))) \\
 26563 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\
 26564 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\
 26565 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times 4)) \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 26566 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((34 + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26567 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 34) \times (56 \times 7)) - 89)) \\
 26568 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 26569 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((34 + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 26570 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 8)) - 9)) \\
 26571 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((-34 - (5 \times 67)) \times (-8 \times -9))) \\
 26572 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 26573 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 \times 4^5 - 6) \times 78/9 \\
 26574 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 26575 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26576 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times -((7 \times 8))) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26538 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times (6 + ((5 \times 43) + 2)))) + 1) \\
 26539 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1))) \\
 26540 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 26541 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 26542 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\
 26543 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\
 26544 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 26545 &:= ((9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 32)) + (-1))) \\
 26546 &:= ((9 \times 8) - ((7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + 32)) \times (-1))) \\
 26547 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 26548 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 26549 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\
 26550 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4^3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 26551 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4^3))) + (2 - 1)) \\
 26552 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 26553 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - (4^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 26554 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (((6^5) + 4)/(3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
 26555 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2)))) - 1) \\
 26556 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 + 1))))) \\
 26557 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2))) + 1)) \\
 26558 &:= (-98) \times (((7 - (6 + 543))/2) \times 1) \\
 26559 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -5) - (4 + 3))^2)) - 1) \\
 26560 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -5) - (4 + 3))^2 \times 1) \\
 26561 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -5) - (4 + 3))^2 + 1) \\
 26562 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! + 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 26563 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3^2)))) + 1))) \\
 26564 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5) \times (-4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 26565 &:= (((9 \times -((8 + 7))) \times -6) - 5) \times (((4 \times 3) + 21))) \\
 26566 &:= (((-9 \times 87) + 65) \times -((4 \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
 26567 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - (3^2))) - 1) \\
 26568 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 26569 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 + 3)))^2 \times 1) \\
 26570 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6^5) + 4)/(3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 26571 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6^5) + 4)/(3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 26572 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6^5) + 4)/(3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 26573 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 26574 &:= ((((-9 + 876) \times 5) + 4) \times 3) \times ((2 \times 1)) \\
 26575 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 27576 &:= (9 - 8 + 765) \times (4 + 32 \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26577 &:= (-((-123 \times -4) \times (5 - (67 - 8)))) + 9 \\
 26578 &:= (((1 + (2 \times (3^4)))^{5 \times 6 / (7+8)}) + 9) \\
 26579 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 26580 &:= (12 - ((-34 + (-5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 26581 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - 89) \\
 26582 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) \times 5) + (678 \times 9)) \\
 26583 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 26584 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)))) \\
 26585 &:= (((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 26586 &:= (((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9) \\
 26587 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 26588 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 26589 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 26590 &:= (-((-1 + (-((2 + 345) - 6)) \times 78))) - 9) \\
 26591 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) - 9)))) \\
 26592 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times 45)) - 6) \times (-7 - 89)) \\
 26593 &:= (-12 + ((3 - (-4 \times (56 \times -7))) \times (-8 - 9))) \\
 26594 &:= (-1 + ((((((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 26595 &:= (((-1 - (((2 - 3) + 45) \times -67)) + 8) \times 9) \\
 26596 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9))) \\
 26597 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((67 + 8) - 9))) \\
 26598 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 26599 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - 8)) - 9) \\
 26600 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (6 + 7)))) + (8 + 9))) \\
 26601 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 26602 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 26603 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 26604 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 + 7))) + 8) \times -9) \\
 26605 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 26606 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 26607 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 26608 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 89))) \\
 26609 &:= (-(((12 \times (34 \times 5)) \times (-6 - 7))) + 89) \\
 26610 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - 8))) - 9)) \\
 26611 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) - 8))) + 9) \\
 26612 &:= (-(-1) - ((234 + (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times -89)) \\
 26613 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) \times -3 + ((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 26614 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 89))) \\
 26615 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 - 9)))) \\
 26616 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 - 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26577 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 - (4^3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 26578 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 6)) \times -5) - (4 + 3)^2)) \times -1) \\
 26579 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 26580 &:= ((-9 - (87 \times (65 - 4))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 26581 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4) + (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 26582 &:= ((-98 \times -7) - (6 \times (5 - 4321))) \\
 26583 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 26584 &:= (9 \times (-8 + 7 + 6!) - 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 26585 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3^2) - 1)))) \\
 26586 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 - (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 26587 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 76) \times -5) + (43 \times 2))) - (-1)) \\
 26588 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -7 + (((6^5) + 4) / (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 26589 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) \times ((4^{3+2}) - 1))) \\
 26590 &:= ((((-9 - (87 \times 6)) \times 5) - 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 26591 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 26592 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 26593 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 26594 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 26595 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times ((-6 - 5) + (432)))) \times (-1)) \\
 26596 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 26597 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3 - 2)) - 1) \\
 26598 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times ((4^{3+2}) - 1)) \\
 26599 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3 - 2)) + 1) \\
 26600 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + (6 \times 5)))) + 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 26601 &:= (((-9 + 876) + ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 26602 &:= -9 + 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5) \times (-4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!) \\
 26603 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 26604 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 26605 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 26606 &:= -9 + 8 - 7! + (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3!! - 2 - 1) \\
 26607 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + 6)) - (5 - (4 \times 3))) \times -21) \\
 26608 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 + ((54 + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 26609 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43) + 2))) \times -1) \\
 26610 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2)))) - 1) \\
 26611 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 26612 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2))) + 1)) \\
 26613 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 26614 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) \times (4^{3+2}))) - 1) \\
 26615 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) \times (4^{3+2} \times 1))) \\
 26616 &:= (((9 \times 87) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) - (3 \times ((2 \times 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26617 &:= (((-1+2)-3) \times -((4^5) \times (6+7)) - 8) + 9) \\ 26618 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 + ((4^5) \times ((6+7) \times (8-9)))))) \\ 26619 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (6+7)))) - (8-9)) \\ 26620 &:= ((12 \times -3) + ((4 \times (56 \times 7)) \times (8+9))) \\ 26621 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times 4) - 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 26622 &:= (((-12 - (34 + 5)) \times 6) \times (-78 - 9)) \\ 26623 &:= (1 + (-2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (-6 + (789)))))) \\ 26624 &:= (1 - ((2 - (345 - 6)) \times (7 - (-8 \times 9)))) \\ 26625 &:= (((-1+2)-3) \times -((4^5) \times (6+7))) - (8-9)) \\ 26626 &:= (((-1+2)-3) \times -((4^5) \times (6+7)) - (8-9)) \\ 26627 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + (8-9)))))) \\ 26628 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -3 + (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + (8-9))) \\ 26629 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times ((6+7) \times (8-9)))))) \\ 26630 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -3 - ((4^5) \times ((6+7) \times (8-9)))) \\ 26631 &:= (((-1+2)-3) \times -((4^5) \times (6+7)) + 8) - 9) \\ 26632 &:= (-((1+23)) - (-4 \times ((56 \times 7) \times (8+9)))) \\ 26633 &:= (-1 \times (23 - (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times (8+9)))))) \\ 26634 &:= ((12 + ((34 \times (5+6)))) \times (78 - 9)) \\ 26635 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (6+7)))) + (8+9)) \\ 26636 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + 8)))) - 9) \\ 26637 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times -3 + (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + 8))) - 9) \\ 26638 &:= (-1 + (((2-3) + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8+9))) \\ 26639 &:= ((-1 \times (((2 \times 34) \times 56) \times -7) + 8) - 9) \\ 26640 &:= (((12 - 34) + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 26641 &:= (((-1+2)-3) \times -((4^5) \times (6+7))) + (8+9)) \\ 26642 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times (3 - ((4^5) \times (6+7)) + 8))) - 9) \\ 26643 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times -6) + 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26644 &:= (1 - ((2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + 8))) - 9)) \\ 26645 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! - 5) - 6! + 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 26646 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 34) \times 56)) \times -7) + (-8 - 9)) \\ 26647 &:= ((-12 + 3) + (4 \times ((56 \times 7) \times (8+9)))) \\ 26648 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) - (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times (8+9)))))) \\ 26649 &:= (((1+2) \times (3 - ((4^5) - ((6 \times 7) - 8)))) \times -9) \\ 26650 &:= (((-123 \times (4 \times 5))/6) \times (7 + (-8 \times 9))) \\ 26651 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + (8+9)))))) \\ 26652 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + (8+9)))) \\ 26653 &:= (((123 + 4) \times 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + (-8 - 9) \\ 26654 &:= (((1^2) - 3) - ((-((-4 \times 56)) \times 7) \times -((8+9)))) \\ 26655 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times -3 + (((4^5) \times (6+7)) + 8))) + 9) \\ 26656 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) \times (56 \times (7 \times (8+9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26617 &:= (((-9+8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26618 &:= (((9 \times 87) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26619 &:= (((-9 \times 87) \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26620 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3^2)))) - 1)) \\ 26621 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) + (3^2)))) - 1)) \\ 26622 &:= (((9 \times 87) \times (((6 \times 5) + ((4 - 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\ 26623 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2})) - 1) \\ 26624 &:= (((9 \times 87) \times ((-6 \times 5) - (-4^3))) + ((2 \times 1))) \\ 26625 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2})) + 1) \\ 26626 &:= (((9 \times 87) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26627 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 26628 &:= (((9 \times 87) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + (3 \times ((2 \times 1))) \\ 26629 &:= ((-((98 + 765)) + 4) \times (-32 + 1)) \\ 26630 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 26631 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + (3 \times 2)))) - 1)) \\ 26632 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 26633 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) \times (4^{3+2}))) \times -1) \\ 26634 &:= ((-9 - (((87 \times 6) \times -((54 - 3))) - (21)))) \\ 26635 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^4)))) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 26636 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^4)))) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 26637 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times ((6 + 54) \times 3))) \times 21)) \\ 26638 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (65 \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 26639 &:= ((-9 \times -8) \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 26640 &:= (-9 \times -8) \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26641 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 + (6 + 5))) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 26642 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 - 6) + (54 \times 3))^2 + 1)) \\ 26643 &:= (((-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 43))) \times 2) + 1) \\ 26644 &:= (((9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2)))) - 1) \\ 26645 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2)))) \times -1) \\ 26646 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times -2) \times 1) \\ 26647 &:= (((9 \times ((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26648 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26649 &:= (9 \times ((87 + (6 \times (5 - 43)))) \times -((21))) \\ 26650 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5)) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1)) \\ 26651 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 26652 &:= (9 - (-((8 - ((-76) + 5) - 4))) \times (321)) \\ 26653 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (((4^3) \times 2) - 1))) \\ 26654 &:= ((-9 \times -8) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + (32 \times 1) \\ 26655 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4^3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 26656 &:= (-98) \times (((7 - (6 + 543))/2) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26657 &:= (1 - (-((-(2^3) \times (-4 \times (56 - 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 26658 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
 26659 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
 26660 &:= (((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 26661 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) + (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 26662 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times 3) + (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 26663 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 26664 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 26665 &:= (-((-12 + 3)) + (4 \times ((56 \times 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 26666 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 26667 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
 26668 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9))) \\
 26669 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\
 26670 &:= (-((123 + 4)) \times -(((5 \times (6 \times 7)) \times (-8 + 9)))) \\
 26671 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\
 26672 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times (6 + 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 26673 &:= ((-1 \times (((2 \times 34) \times 56) \times -7)) + (8 + 9)) \\
 26674 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((34 \times ((56 - 7) \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 26675 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 26676 &:= (((1^2) - (-34 \times 5)) \times (67 + 89)) \\
 26677 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) - 8)) - 9) \\
 26678 &:= ((-1 + 23) + (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 26679 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7) - 8) - 9) \\
 26680 &:= ((1 + 23) - (-4 \times ((56 \times 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 26681 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times ((34 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9)) \\
 26682 &:= (1 + ((2 \times ((34 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9)) \\
 26683 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 26684 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 26685 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 26686 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
 26687 &:= (((123 + 4) \times 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (-8 - 9) \\
 26688 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 26689 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 - 9))) \\
 26690 &:= -(((((-1 + 2) - (3 - ((-4 \times 56) \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 26691 &:= -((123 \times ((4 \times -56) + (7 \times (-8 + 9)))) \\
 26692 &:= ((-12 \times -3) + (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 26693 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9) \\
 26694 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9) \\
 26695 &:= (-12 + ((-3 - (-4 \times (56 \times -7))) \times (-8 - 9))) \\
 26696 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -((4^5) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26657 &:= ((-98 \times -(((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4^3)) - 2)) + 1) \\
 26658 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + ((3^2) - 1)))) \\
 26659 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 26660 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 26661 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 26662 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5! + 4!/3) + (2 + 1)! \\
 26663 &:= (-((98 - 7)) \times -((6 \times 54) - (-32) + (1))) \\
 26664 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times 5! + 4! \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 26665 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43)) + 21))) \\
 26666 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 26667 &:= (-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 26668 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 26669 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (((4^3) \times 2) - 1))) \\
 26670 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 26671 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\
 26672 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 26673 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times ((6 + 5) - 4) \times 32)) + 1) \\
 26674 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 \times 21)))) \\
 26675 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times 6) \times -5 - ((4^3) - 2)) - 1) \\
 26676 &:= (-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4)) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 26677 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times 6) \times -5 - ((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\
 26678 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times 43)) \times -2 \times 1) \\
 26679 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 26680 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) + 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 26681 &:= (9 + (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 26682 &:= (-9 + ((87 + 6) \times (((5 + 4) \times 32) - 1))) \\
 26683 &:= (((-98 + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 26684 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 26685 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^3))) + (2 + 1))) \\
 26686 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times 43) + 2)) + 1) \\
 26687 &:= ((9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times ((4 \times 32) - 1)))) \\
 26688 &:= ((-(-9) + 87) \times ((65 \times 4) + (-((3 - 21)))) \\
 26689 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\
 26690 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -(((5^4) + 3)/(2 \times 1))) \\
 26691 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -(((5^4) + 3)/2)) + 1) \\
 26692 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 \times 21)))) \\
 26693 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 26694 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 26695 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^3))) + 2)) + 1) \\
 26696 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3 \times 21)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26697 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3-4) + (5^6))/7) - 8)) + 9) \\ 26698 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times -(6+7)) - (8+9)) \\ 26699 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) + (8-9)))) \\ 26700 &:= ((-(-1) + (234 + (5 \times (6+7)))) \times 89) \\ 26701 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times ((6+7) \times (8-9)))) \\ 26702 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times ((6+7) \times (8-9)))) \\ 26703 &:= (1 \times -((-23 \times (((4 + (5+6)) \times 78) - 9)))) \\ 26704 &:= (1 - (-23 \times (((4 + (5+6)) \times 78) - 9))) \\ 26705 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8+9)))) \\ 26706 &:= (((1 - (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5+6)))) \times (-7-8)) - 9) \\ 26707 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times ((3 + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8+9))) \\ 26708 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) + 8))) - 9) \\ 26709 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - ((6+7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26710 &:= (((1 \times (-2 \times -3)) + 4) \times ((5 \times (67 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 26711 &:= (-1 + (((-(-2-34)) + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 26712 &:= ((-123 - (-4 \times (5 - 67))) \times (-8 \times 9)) \\ 26713 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - ((6+7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26714 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times -(6+7)) + (8-9)) \\ 26715 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times ((6+7) \times (8-9))) \\ 26716 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times -(6+7)) - (8-9)) \\ 26717 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 26718 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times (6+7))) + (8+9))) \\ 26719 &:= ((1 \times (2 \times (3 + ((4^5) \times (6+7)))) + 89) \\ 26720 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times (7+8)))) - 9) \\ 26721 &:= ((1 - (2 - (-3 \times ((-4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - 8)))) \times 9) \\ 26722 &:= (1 + (((234 - 5) \times (6+7)) - 8) \times 9) \\ 26723 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (((3 - (4^5)) \times (6+7)) - 89))) \\ 26724 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times (5+6)))) \times (7+8)) + 9) \\ 26725 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\ 26726 &:= ((-12 - 34) \times (-5 + ((-6 \times (7+8)))) \\ 26727 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) + 8)) + 9) \\ 26728 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 26729 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3+4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\ 26730 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times ((5+6) \times (7 - (8+9)))) \\ 26731 &:= (-1 - (-2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times -(((67+8) - 9)))) \\ 26732 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times -(6+7)) + (8+9)) \\ 26733 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((67+8) - 9)))) \\ 26734 &:= (1 + 2 + 3!!) \times (4 \times (5+6) - 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 26735 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6+7)) + (8+9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26697 &:= (((-98 - (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 26698 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 26699 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2)))) - 1) \\ 26700 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 26701 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2))) + 1)) \\ 26702 &:= (((-9 - (87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4))) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\ 26703 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times -((5 + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26704 &:= (((98 \times 7) - 65) \times 43) - (-2 + 1)) \\ 26705 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26706 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times 43)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26707 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + (3^2))) + 1))) \\ 26708 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times ((43 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26709 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26710 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26711 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(((7 + 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)/2)) - 1) \\ 26712 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + 4)) - (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26713 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(((7 + 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)/2)) + 1) \\ 26714 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 26715 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26716 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\ 26717 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 26718 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 26719 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -6) + (((54 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 26720 &:= ((-9 + (((87 - 6) \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2))) - 1) \\ 26721 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (((-7 + 6) + 54) \times (3 \times 21)))) \\ 26722 &:= (-9 + (((87 - 6) \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1) \\ 26723 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7! + 6 + 5 + (4! + 3!) \times (2 + 1)!! \\ 26724 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 26725 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 26726 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + (5^4)))) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 26727 &:= (98 + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^2))) + 1)) \\ 26728 &:= (9 + 8 + 7! - 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! + 2 + 1 \\ 26729 &:= (((98 + (7 - 6)) \times 54) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 26730 &:= (((98 + (7 - 6)) \times 54) \times (3 + 2)) \times 1) \\ 26731 &:= (((98 + (7 - 6)) \times 54) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 26732 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 26733 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4))) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26734 &:= -9 - 8 + (-7 + (6 + 5) \times 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)!!) \\ 26735 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) \times 2) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26736 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\
 26737 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 26738 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)))) + 9)) \\
 26739 &:= -((((12 \times 3) - ((45 \times 67) - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 26740 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 26741 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 26742 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 26743 &:= ((-1 + ((23 - 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 26744 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (34 \times (56 \times 7))) + 89)) \\
 26745 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times 34) \times (56 \times 7)) + 89 \\
 26746 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (34 \times (56 \times 7))) + 89)) \\
 26747 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))) + 9))) \\
 26748 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3^4) \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))) + 9)) \\
 26749 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - 89) \\
 26750 &:= (1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + (67 + (8 \times 9))))) \\
 26751 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)))) \\
 26752 &:= (((1 - 23) \times -4) \times -((-(5 \times (67 - 8))) - 9)) \\
 26753 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (678 - 9)))))) \\
 26754 &:= -(((1 \times 2) \times (3 + (4 \times -((5 \times (678 - 9)))))) \\
 26755 &:= ((-12 \times -((34 + (5^6))/7)) - 89) \\
 26756 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!!) \times 4) \times (5 + 6) - 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 26757 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4^5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 26758 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 26759 &:= (((-((1 - 23)) + 456) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 26760 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 + ((5 - 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26761 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) \times (4 + ((5 - 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26762 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26763 &:= (-((123 \times ((-4 \times 56) + 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\
 26764 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4!) \times 5 + (6! + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 26765 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 + 45) \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 26766 &:= ((((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9) \\
 26767 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 26768 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -(((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 26769 &:= (-12 - ((345 - 6) \times (-7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26770 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3 + 4 \times 5^6) / 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 26771 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times 3!! + 4) \times (-5 + 6 \times 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 26772 &:= (-12 \times -((((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7) + (8 - 9))) \\
 26773 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7))) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 26774 &:= (-1 + ((-2 + (3 - (-4 \times 56))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 26775 &:= (((1 + (2 \times 3)) \times 45) \times ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26736 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5)))) \times (4 \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\
 26737 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) \times 2) + 1) \\
 26738 &:= ((987 - 65) \times (-4 + ((32 + 1)))) \\
 26739 &:= ((9 \times 87) - (-6 \times (5 + (4321)))) \\
 26740 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times ((4^3) \times 2)) - 1))) \\
 26741 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (6 \times (5 + (4^{3+2-1})))) \\
 26742 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times -(76)) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^2))) - (1))) \\
 26743 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 26744 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 26745 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 26746 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 26747 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\
 26748 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((6 \times (5 + 4))^{3-2+1})) \\
 26749 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 26750 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - 6) \times -((5 \times 43) - (2 - 1))) \\
 26751 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 26752 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 26753 &:= (((-9 \times -8) \times 7) + ((6 + ((54 \times -3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 26754 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\
 26755 &:= ((-98 \times (7 \times (6 - (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))))) + 1) \\
 26756 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 26757 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times 4))) \times (3^{2+1})) \\
 26758 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (((6 - (5 - 4)) \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 26759 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (65 \times (4 \times 3))) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 26760 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1)) \\
 26761 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 76) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^2)))) \times -1) \\
 26762 &:= (9 - (((8 \times 76) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1)) \\
 26763 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) - (5 - 4)) \times -(32 + 1)) \\
 26764 &:= -9 + 8! + (-7 + 6!) \times (5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1)) \\
 26765 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + ((4^3) + 2)))) - 1) \\
 26766 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times ((5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2)) + 1)))) \\
 26767 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times 6) \times (5 + ((4^3) + 2)))) + 1) \\
 26768 &:= ((-98/7) \times -(((6^5)/4) - (32 \times 1))) \\
 26769 &:= (((-98/7) \times -(((6^5)/4) - 32)) + 1) \\
 26770 &:= (9 - (((8 + 7) \times (65 - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
 26771 &:= -9 - 8 + (7 + 6 \times 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\
 26772 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7!) / 6 + 5 \times (4 + 3)! + (2 + 1)!! \\
 26773 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (65 \times (4 - (3 \times 21)))) \\
 26774 &:= (((-98 + 7)) \times ((-((65 \times 4) + 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 26775 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 + 5) + (4^3)) \times (2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26776 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - 789))) \\ 26777 &:= (((-1 + (23 + 456)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 26778 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((345 - 6) \times (7 - (-8 \times 9)))))) \\ 26779 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((345 - 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 26780 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 26781 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((-345) + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 26782 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + 45) \times ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 26783 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 26784 &:= ((1 + (-2 + (3 + 4))) \times -(((5 - 67) \times 8) \times 9))) \\ 26785 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3 - 4) + (5^6)/7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 26786 &:= (-1 + (-2 - ((-34 + (5 \times 67)) \times -89))) \\ 26787 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((-34 + (5 \times 67)) \times -89))) \\ 26788 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 + 7))) \times 89)) \\ 26789 &:= (((12/3) + (45 - 6)) \times 7) \times 89 \\ 26790 &:= (1 + (((-2^3) + (45 + 6)) \times -((-7 \times 89)))) \\ 26791 &:= ((1 \times -2) + ((34 + 5) \times (678 + 9))) \\ 26792 &:= (((1 \times -2)^3) \times (-4 - (5 \times (678 - 9)))) \\ 26793 &:= ((12 - (3 \times (-4 - 5))) \times (678 + 9)) \\ 26794 &:= -(((1 - 2) - ((34 + 5) \times (678 + 9)))) \\ 26795 &:= -(((1 \times -2) - ((34 + 5) \times (678 + 9)))) \\ 26796 &:= -(((1 \times 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 89)))) \\ 26797 &:= ((123 + 4) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (-8 + 9))) \\ 26798 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -7) - 89) \\ 26799 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\ 26800 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\ 26801 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26802 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))))) \times 9 \\ 26803 &:= (1 - (-2 \times ((-3 - (((-4^5) - (6 \times 78)))) \times 9))) \\ 26804 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\ 26805 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((((3^4) + 5) \times (6 + 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 26806 &:= (1 + 2 + 3 \times (4^5 + 6)) \times 78/9 \\ 26807 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26808 &:= ((1 \times (2^3)) \times (((4 + 56) \times 7) \times 8) - 9) \\ 26809 &:= (((-12 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))) + 7) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 26810 &:= (1 + ((((-2 \times -3) + 4) \times (5 \times (67 \times 8)))) + 9) \\ 26811 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 26812 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 26813 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3! + 4^5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\ 26814 &:= -((123 \times (((4 \times -56) + ((7 + 8))) - 9))) \\ 26815 &:= (((-((-1 \times 23)) + (456)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26776 &:= ((-((98 + 7)) \times ((-((65 \times 4)) + 3) + 2)) + 1) \\ 26777 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 26778 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 26779 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 26780 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 26781 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 26782 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\ 26783 &:= (-98) + (((7 \times -6) \times ((5 \times -4) \times 32)) + 1))) \\ 26784 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 26785 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - (3 \times 2)))) + 1) \\ 26786 &:= (-9 - ((87 \times (6 - (((5^4) + 3)/2))) + 1)) \\ 26787 &:= (-9 + (87 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)))))) \\ 26788 &:= (((-9 \times (87 - 6)) + 5) \times -((4 \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\ 26789 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 26790 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times (5 \times ((4 \times (3 + 2)) - 1)))) \\ 26791 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 - (76 \times 5)) \times 4)) + 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 26792 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1))) \\ 26793 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 26794 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 32)) + 1)) \\ 26795 &:= (((-987 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 - 32)) - 1) \\ 26796 &:= (((9 - 87) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1)) \\ 26797 &:= (((987 + (-6 \times 5)) \times -((4 - 32))) - (-1)) \\ 26798 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6) \times (5! + 4 - 3!) + (2 + 1)!! \\ 26799 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!) \times 6 + 5 \times (4! - (3 + 2 + 1)!) \\ 26800 &:= ((-9 - ((87 \times 6) + 5)) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 26801 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) \times 2)) - 1))) \\ 26802 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\ 26803 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26804 &:= (9 - ((87 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 - 32))) + 1)) \\ 26805 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times (6 - (((5^4) + 3)/2)))) \times -1) \\ 26806 &:= (9 - ((87 \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 - 32))) - 1)) \\ 26807 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) \times 2))) - 1) \\ 26808 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 26809 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2 \times 1)))) \\ 26810 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 26811 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times ((4 \times 3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 26812 &:= (((-((-987) - 6)) \times (-5 + ((4^3)/2))) + 1)) \\ 26813 &:= (((-987 - 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 26814 &:= (((9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times (5 - ((43 \times 2) + 1)))) \\ 26815 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) \times 2)) + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26816 &:= ((1 + ((23 + 456) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 26817 &:= (-((12 - 3) - (-((4 + (5 \times 6))) \times 789)) \\ 26818 &:= ((1 \times -(-23)) \times (4 + (5 + ((6 + 7) \times 89)))) \\ 26819 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 26820 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 26821 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - 3) - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times - (789))) \\ 26822 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\ 26823 &:= (-1 - (-(-2) - (((-34 \times (5 - 6)) \times 789)))) \\ 26824 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 789)) \\ 26825 &:= ((1 - 2) - (34 \times ((5 - 6) \times 789))) \\ 26826 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (34 \times ((5 - 6) \times 789))) \\ 26827 &:= (-1 - (-2 - ((-34 \times (5 - 6)) \times 789))) \\ 26828 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (-34 \times ((5 - 6) \times 789))) \\ 26829 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times -9) \\ 26830 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 789)) \\ 26831 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3^4) + 5) \times (67 + 89)))) \\ 26832 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times - (5 - (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) \\ 26833 &:= (((-((-1 \times 23)) + (456)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 26834 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times ((34 \times (56 \times 7)) + 89)) \\ 26835 &:= ((12 - 3) - (-((4 + (5 \times 6))) \times 789)) \\ 26836 &:= (-((((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times 5) \times (67 - 8))) - 9) \\ 26837 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\ 26838 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (((4^5) + (6 \times 7)) + (8 \times -9))) \\ 26839 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26840 &:= (-((-1 + 23)) \times (-4 \times (((5 \times 6) + 7) \times 8 + 9))) \\ 26841 &:= (((1 + 2) \times ((3^4) + 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 8) + 9) \\ 26842 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times -3)^4) \times 5) - (67 \times 89)) \\ 26843 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((45 \times 6) - 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 26844 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\ 26845 &:= (((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times 5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 26846 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3 + (4^5)) \times (6 + 7)) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 26847 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 26848 &:= -((12 + (34 \times (5 - (6 + 789)))))) \\ 26849 &:= ((-1 \times -23) - (-((4 + (5 \times 6))) \times 789)) \\ 26850 &:= (12 - (((-3 \times (4^5)) - (-6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 26851 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + (6 \times 78)) \times 9)))) \\ 26852 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 + 4!) \times (5! + 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26853 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) - (6 + 789) \\ 26854 &:= (((-1 + (23 \times 4)) \times (5 \times (67 - 8))) + 9) \\ 26855 &:= (-1 - (((-23 + 4) - (56 \times -7)) \times (8 \times -9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26816 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (76 \times 5))) + 4) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 26817 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + 6)) - ((5 + 4)/3)) \times -21) \\ 26818 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7!/6 - 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 26819 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times -6) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 26820 &:= (-9 \times -((((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times (4 + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 26821 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times ((4^3) \times 2)) - 1))) \\ 26822 &:= 9 \times (-8 - 7 + 6!) + 5 \times 4^{3!} - 2 - 1 \\ 26823 &:= ((-98 \times -76) + ((5^4) \times (32 - 1))) \\ 26824 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times ((4^3) \times 2)) + 1))) \\ 26825 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 26826 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 + 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1))) \\ 26827 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 26828 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (65 \times (43 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 26829 &:= ((9 - (876 - 54)) \times -(32 - 1)) \\ 26830 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (65 \times (43 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 26831 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 26832 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) - (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 26833 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times ((6 \times -((54 + 3))) - 2)) - (-1))) \\ 26834 &:= -9 + 8! - (7 + 6 \times 5 + (4!/3)!/(2 + 1)) \\ 26835 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) - (4 + 3)))) - 21) \\ 26836 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! \times 5 + 4 + 3!)/(2 + 1) \\ 26837 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times ((4^3) \times 2)) - 1))) \\ 26838 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + 6)) \times ((5 - 432) + (1))) \\ 26839 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) - (4 + 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 26840 &:= (9 + 8 - 7) \times (6 + 5) \times (4 + 3!)/(2 + 1) \\ 26841 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7! \times 6/(5 + 4) - 3) - (2 + 1)! \\ 26842 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times - (5^4)) - (32 + 1)) \\ 26843 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times - (5^4)) - (32 \times 1)) \\ 26844 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26845 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) - (2 - 1))) \\ 26846 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 26847 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5)) - 4) \times - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26848 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times - (5^4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 26849 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26850 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5 \times ((4^3) \times 2)) + 1))) \\ 26851 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26852 &:= (-98) \times (((7 \times ((6 - 54) + (3^2))) - 1)) \\ 26853 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times 5)) + (4^3))) + (2 - 1)) \\ 26854 &:= (-9 - (((8 - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26855 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2)))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26856 &:= (-1 \times (((-23 + 4) - (56 \times -7)) \times (8 \times -9))) \\ 26857 &:= (-1 - (2 + (34 \times ((5 - 6) - 789)))) \\ 26858 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (34 \times ((5 - 6) - 789)))) \\ 26859 &:= ((1 - 2) + (-34 \times ((5 - 6) - 789))) \\ 26860 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times - (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 26861 &:= (-1 + (2 - (34 \times ((5 - 6) - 789)))) \\ 26862 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 26863 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 26864 &:= ((-1 \times -23) \times ((4^5) - (-6 \times ((7 + 8) + 9)))) \\ 26865 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times (((-4 \times -5) \times (6 \times (-7 - 8))) - (-9))) \\ 26866 &:= (1 + (((234 - 5) \times (6 + 7)) + 8) \times 9) \\ 26867 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times (((56 - 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 26868 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times (45 \times 67)) - 89)) \\ 26869 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4567 - 89)))) \\ 26870 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 26871 &:= ((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\ 26872 &:= (12 - (34 \times (5 - (6 + 789)))) \\ 26873 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 26874 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 26875 &:= (((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9))))) \\ 26876 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + 45) \times ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 26877 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times ((67 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 26878 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 - 9))) \\ 26879 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9))))) \\ 26880 &:= (((1 + 23) - 4) \times 56) \times ((7 + 8) + 9) \\ 26881 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\ 26882 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26883 &:= (((1 - (2^3)) \times 45) + 6) \times (-78 - 9) \\ 26884 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -((4 - (5 \times 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\ 26885 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3^{4+5} + 6! \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 26886 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))) - 9) \\ 26887 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 26888 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 26889 &:= ((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\ 26890 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 26891 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 26892 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -((((3^4) - 5) \times (6 + 7)) + 8) \times 9) \\ 26893 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\ 26894 &:= (((1 - 234) - 5) \times (((6 + 7) \times -8) - 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26856 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 26857 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 26858 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 \times 5) - (4 + 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 26859 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26860 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 26861 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (54 + 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\ 26862 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) \times 2))) - 1) \\ 26863 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\ 26864 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2})) - 1) \\ 26865 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 26866 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26867 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 26868 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26869 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26870 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 26871 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 26872 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 26873 &:= (98 + (-765) \times (-(((4 + 32) - 1)))) \\ 26874 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 26875 &:= (((((-98) - 7) \times 6) + 5) \times 43) \times (-2 + 1) \\ 26876 &:= (-(((((-98) - 7) \times 6) + 5) \times 43)) - (-2 + 1) \\ 26877 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26878 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) + (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 26879 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26880 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times 5)) \times -(4^{3+2-1})) \\ 26881 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26882 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 26883 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26884 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26885 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4)) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 26886 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + (4 + 3))))^2)) - 1) \\ 26887 &:= (-9 + (((87 + (65)) + (4 \times 3))^2) \times 1) \\ 26888 &:= (-9 + (((87 + (65)) + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1) \\ 26889 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 76) \times 5) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 - 1)) \\ 26890 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -54) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 26891 &:= ((9 + (((8 + 76) \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2)) \times 1) \\ 26892 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 26893 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 + ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 26894 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3+2-1}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26895 &:= ((-1 - (-2 + 34)) \times (-5 + ((-6 \times (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 26896 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) \times (((34 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 - 89))) \\ 26897 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 26898 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9) \\ 26899 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9) \\ 26900 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 78))) - 9) \\ 26901 &:= (((12^3)/4) - 5) \times -(((-6 + 7) - 8) \times -(-9))) \\ 26902 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9) \\ 26903 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9) \\ 26904 &:= (((1 - 2) + (34 + 5)) \times (6 + (78 \times 9))) \\ 26905 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times - (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 26906 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3!)) \times (4 + 5!) + (6! + 7!/8) \times 9 \\ 26907 &:= -(((12 \times ((-3^{-4+5+6}) + (-7 \times -(-8)))) + 9)) \\ 26908 &:= (1 - 2 - 3! - 4^5) \times (6 + 7) + 8! - 9 \\ 26909 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3^4)) - 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 26910 &:= ((((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9) \\ 26911 &:= (((12 + 3) - ((-4 \times 56) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26912 &:= (((1 \times -2) - ((3^4) \times -5)) \times 67) - 89 \\ 26913 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) + 89)) \\ 26914 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3! + 4) \times (5! + 6!) + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 26915 &:= (((1 + (2 \times 3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + (7 \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 26916 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\ 26917 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) - (8 + 9)) \\ 26918 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))))) \\ 26919 &:= -(((-1 + 2)) \times ((3 \times (45 \times 67)) + (-8 \times 9))) \\ 26920 &:= (1 + ((23 \times ((4 + (5 + 6)) \times 78)) + 9)) \\ 26921 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times - (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\ 26922 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 26923 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times - (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 26924 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 \times 6 \times 7/8 + 9) \\ 26925 &:= ((-1 - ((-2^3) \times 45)) \times (6 + (78 - 9))) \\ 26926 &:= 1 + (2 + 3) \times (4^5 \times 6 \times 7/8 + 9) \\ 26927 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times -3)^4) - ((56 \times -7) \times (-8 \times 9)))) \\ 26928 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times - (8 \times 9)) \\ 26929 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\ 26930 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 26931 &:= ((-12 \times -(((34 + (5^6))/7) + 8)) - 9) \\ 26932 &:= (-1 - (-23 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (67 - 8)))) - 9)) \\ 26933 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) + (8 - 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26895 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2) - 1))) \\ 26896 &:= ((((-9 \times - (8 + 7)) - (6 - (5 \times (4 + 3))))^2 \times 1) \\ 26897 &:= (((((-98) \times 7) + (6 \times 5)) \times -((43 - 2))) + 1)) \\ 26898 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -54) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 26899 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -54) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 26900 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -54) + (3^2)) - 1) \\ 26901 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 26902 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times - (5^4)) + (3^{2+1})) \\ 26903 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 26904 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 26905 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times (5 + (4 + 3))))^2)) \times -1) \\ 26906 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times - (5^4)) + (32 - 1)) \\ 26907 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times - (5 + (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26908 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times - (5 + (4^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26909 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times - (5 + (4^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 26910 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 26911 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 + 1)))))) \\ 26912 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times - (5 + (4^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 26913 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times - (5 + (4^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 26914 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) \times - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26915 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 26916 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 26917 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (((7 \times 65) \times (4 - ((3 \times 21)))))) \\ 26918 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3/(2 + 1)))))) \\ 26919 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times 4) - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 26920 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - 2))) - 1)) \\ 26921 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 26922 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 26923 &:= ((((-98 \times -7) - 6) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 26924 &:= (((9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times 54) + ((32 \times 1)) \\ 26925 &:= ((((-98 \times -7) - 6) + (((54 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 26926 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - (6 \times (5 \times 43))) \times 21)) \\ 26927 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 - 1)))))) \\ 26928 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5 + (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\ 26929 &:= ((((-98 \times -7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 26930 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + ((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 26931 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + (((6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 26932 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26933 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + (2 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26934 &:= (((-1-2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -(67 \times (8-9))) \\
 26935 &:= (((-1-2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) - (8-9) \\
 26936 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3! + (4! + 5! \times (6+7)) \times (8+9) \\
 26937 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + ((3^4) + 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) \times -9) \\
 26938 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 345) - 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26939 &:= (((1 \times (2 + 345)) - 6) \times (7 - (8 \times -9))) \\
 26940 &:= (-123 + (((45 \times 67) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 26941 &:= (-1 + 2)^3 + 4 \times (5! + (6! + 7 + 8) \times 9) \\
 26942 &:= -1 + (2^{3+4+5} - 6! - 7) \times 8 - 9 \\
 26943 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} \times (4 \times 5! - 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\
 26944 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3 + 4! + 5! \times (6+7)) \times (8+9) \\
 26945 &:= (-((((123 \times 4) - 5) - 6) \times (7 \times -8))) + 9 \\
 26946 &:= ((-12 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 \times (7+8)))) \times -9) \\
 26947 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\
 26948 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 26949 &:= (-(-123) - ((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times -(789))) \\
 26950 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6! / (7+8) - 9) \\
 26951 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 26952 &:= ((1 \times (2^3)) \times (((4+56) \times 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 26953 &:= (1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 \times (56 \times (7+8))) + 9))) \\
 26954 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (67+8))) \times 9)) \\
 26955 &:= (-12 - ((345 - (6 \times 7)) \times -89)) \\
 26956 &:= (1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (67+8))) \times 9)) \\
 26957 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3^4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 \times (8+9))) \\
 26958 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3^4 + 5! \times (6 - 7 \times (8+9))) \\
 26959 &:= (((12 - (3^4)) \times (-(-56) \times -7)) + (-89)) \\
 26960 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times -((5+678) - 9)) \\
 26961 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8-9))) \\
 26962 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4})) - 5) \times ((6+7) \times (8+9))) \\
 26963 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 26964 &:= (((-(1+2))^3) + (((45 \times 67) + 8)) \times 9) \\
 26965 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((345 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) \\
 26966 &:= (1 + (-2 - ((345 - (6 \times 7)) \times -89))) \\
 26967 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 - (5 \times ((67+8) \times 9)))) \\
 26968 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) \times (-4 + ((5 \times (67+8)) \times 9))) \\
 26969 &:= (((((1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times -5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 89) \\
 26970 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 26971 &:= (1 - ((2 \times -3) \times (4567 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 26972 &:= (-1 - (((2^{3+4}) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26934 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 26935 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\
 26936 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 - 1))) \\
 26937 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 26938 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 26939 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 26940 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3 - 2)) + 1) \\
 26941 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! + 6) \times 5 + (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1) \\
 26942 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - (6 \times (5 \times 43))) \times 21)) \\
 26943 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
 26944 &:= (((-9 \times (87 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4^3) / (2 \times 1))) \\
 26945 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 26946 &:= (-9 \times -((((8 \times 76) - (5 + 4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 26947 &:= -9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + (5! / 4)^3 + (2 + 1)! \\
 26948 &:= (9 \times (8! / 7! + 6!) + 5) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 26949 &:= (((-98 + 76) \times -((5 \times (4 + 3))^2)) - 1) \\
 26950 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) + 1)) \\
 26951 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 26952 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) - 1)) \\
 26953 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)))) \times -(2 - 1)) \\
 26954 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 26955 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)))) - 2) \times -1) \\
 26956 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 26957 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times 6)) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 26958 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((65 - (4 + 3))^2)))) - 1) \\
 26959 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 26960 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + ((65 - (4 + 3))^2))) + 1)) \\
 26961 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 26962 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (((4^3) \times 2) - 1))) \\
 26963 &:= ((-9 \times -(((876 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 26964 &:= (((((9 \times 8) + 7) + ((6 - (5 - 4)))) \times 321)) \\
 26965 &:= ((-9 \times -(((876 + (5^4)) - 3) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 26966 &:= -9 + (8 - 7 - 6) \times 5 + (4! + 3!)^{2+1} \\
 26967 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (((65 - (4 + 3))^2) + 1)))) \\
 26968 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4^3)) / 2) - 1)) \\
 26969 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2)))) \times -1) \\
 26970 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 76)) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2 + 1)) \\
 26971 &:= (-98 - ((7 - (6^{5-4+3})) \times 21)) \\
 26972 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 - 6) \times ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2))) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26973 &:= ((12 - 345) \times ((6 - 78) - 9)) \\ 26974 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (67 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26975 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 - 56))) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 26976 &:= ((1 + (-2 - 3)) \times (45 - (6789))) \\ 26977 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3 + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 26978 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4 + (5 \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 26979 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26980 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26981 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26982 &:= ((12 - 3) \times (((45 \times 67) - 8) - 9)) \\ 26983 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26984 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 26985 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3 + 45) \times 6) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\ 26986 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times ((6 \times 7) + 89)) \\ 26987 &:= -1 + 2 \times (-3 \times 4! + (5! - 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 26988 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 - 4) + (5^6))/7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 26989 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!^4 - 5 \times 6) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 26990 &:= -(1234 + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26991 &:= (((1 \times (2^3)) \times (45 \times (67 + 8))) - 9) \\ 26992 &:= ((1 + ((2^3) \times (45 \times (67 + 8)))) - 9) \\ 26993 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((67 + 8) \times 9))))) \\ 26994 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times 5)) \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 26995 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times ((67 + 8) \times 9))))) \\ 26996 &:= ((-1 - (23 \times (4 + (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 26997 &:= (((1 \times ((2 \times -((34 \times 5))) - 6)) \times -78) + 9) \\ 26998 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 26999 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) + 4) \times (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 27000 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3 - ((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27001 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 27002 &:= (((-((12 \times -34)) - 5) \times 67) - (8 - 9)) \\ 27003 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 - 78)) \times 9)) \\ 27004 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 27005 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times ((67 + 8) \times 9))))) \\ 27006 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (3 - ((4 \times -5) \times ((67 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 27007 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times (6 \times -7)) + (8 - 9)))) \\ 27008 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9))) \\ 27009 &:= (((1 \times (2^3)) \times (45 \times (67 + 8))) + 9) \\ 27010 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 - (-4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 27011 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26973 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 26974 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4^3))/2))) - 1) \\ 26975 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2})) - 1) \\ 26976 &:= (((9 - 8) - (-7)) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 26977 &:= ((98 - (((7 \times 6) \times 5) \times (-4 \times 32)) + 1)) \\ 26978 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 26979 &:= (((((98 + 7) \times 65) \times -(-4)) - 321)) \\ 26980 &:= (((-98/7) - 6) \times -(5 + ((4^3) \times 21))) \\ 26981 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - 3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 26982 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 26983 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5 + (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\ 26984 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 26985 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 26986 &:= ((-98/7) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 26987 &:= (((98 + 7) \times ((65 \times 4) - 3)) + ((2 \times 1))) \\ 26988 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + (6 + (5 + 4))))^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 26989 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + (6 + (5 + 4))))^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26990 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 26991 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 + 6) - (5 - (4 + 3)))^{2+1}))) \\ 26992 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 26993 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 26994 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + (6 + (5 + 4))))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 26995 &:= ((9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) + 1)) \\ 26996 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + 5) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)))) \\ 26997 &:= ((((((98 - 7) - 65) + 4)^3) - 2) - 1) \\ 26998 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 26999 &:= ((((((98 - 7) - 65) + 4)^3) - 2) + 1) \\ 27000 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times 6))^{5+4-3-2-1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27001 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27002 &:= (((-(((98 - 7) - 65) + 4)^3) - 2) \times (-1)) \\ 27003 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27004 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 27005 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2})) - 1) \\ 27006 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 27007 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 27008 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 - 1))) \\ 27009 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 27010 &:= (((9 + (((8 + 76) - 54)^3)) + (-(-2) - 1)) \\ 27011 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + (7 + (6 + (5 + 4))))^3) + 2)) \times -1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27012 &:= (-12 \times ((3 - 4) + (5 \times ((6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 27013 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times ((3 + (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 27014 &:= -((1 - ((2 \times (3 \times ((4 - 567) \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 27015 &:= (((1 + (2 + 3)) \times -(((4 - 567) \times 8))) - 9) \\ 27016 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (4 + ((5 + 67) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 27017 &:= (-1 + ((2 - ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27018 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 345) - 6)) \times (-7 + (-(-8) \times -9))) \\ 27019 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - ((45 \times 67) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27020 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (56 \times (78 - 9)))) \\ 27021 &:= (1 + 2)^3 \times (4^5 + 6) - 789 \\ 27022 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 - (5! - 6!) \times (7 + 8)) + 9 \\ 27023 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 - 567)))) \times -8) - 9) \\ 27024 &:= (-12 - (((3 - (45 \times 67)) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27025 &:= (-1 \times (23 \times ((4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 27026 &:= (-1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 27027 &:= (((12/3) - (((45 \times 67) - 8))) \times -9) \\ 27028 &:= (1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 27029 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -((6 + 789)))) \\ 27030 &:= (1 \times (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -((6 + 789)))) \\ 27031 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -((6 + 789)))) \\ 27032 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) \times (4 + ((5 \times (67 + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27033 &:= (((1 + (2 + 3)) \times -(((4 - 567) \times 8))) + 9) \\ 27034 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3))^4) \times (5 + 6)) + (7 \times 89)) \\ 27035 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 34) \times (5 - ((6 + 78) \times 9)))) \\ 27036 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7)))) - 8) \times -9) \\ 27037 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - ((45 \times 67) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27038 &:= -(((1234 - 5) \times (67 - 89))) \\ 27039 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 + (45 \times -67)) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27040 &:= -(((1 \times 2) - 34) \times (56 + 789)) \\ 27041 &:= ((1 - 23) + (((-45 \times 67) + 8) \times -9)) \\ 27042 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9) \\ 27043 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 - (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9) \\ 27044 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 67))) - 89) \\ 27045 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((-3 - 4) \times (-56 \times (78 - 9)))) \\ 27046 &:= (-1 - ((23 - (4 \times -5)) \times (-6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27047 &:= (-((((1 + (2 \times 34)) \times 56) \times -7) - 8) - 9) \\ 27048 &:= (12 - (((3 - (45 \times 67)) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27049 &:= (((-12 + (3^4)) \times (56 \times 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 27050 &:= (-1 \times (-2 - ((-3 - 4) \times (-56 \times (78 - 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27012 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 43) - 2)) - 1) \\ 27013 &:= (((-98 / -7) + ((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2})) - 1) \\ 27014 &:= ((-98 / -7) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 27015 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2)) - 1) \\ 27016 &:= (((9 - 8) + 7) \times (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 27017 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2)) + 1) \\ 27018 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times ((6 - 5) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 27019 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - 3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 27020 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times ((6^5) / 4))) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 27021 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times - (6 \times (54 + 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27022 &:= (((-9 \times -87) - 6) + (((54 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 27023 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 27024 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 27025 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (((6 \times (5 - (4 - 3)))^2) - 1)) \\ 27026 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times ((6^5) / 4)) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 27027 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 27028 &:= (-987) + ((65 \times (432 - 1))) \\ 27029 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 27030 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -((5 + ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\ 27031 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 27032 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\ 27033 &:= ((-9 \times -87) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\ 27034 &:= ((-98 / 7) \times -((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\ 27035 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times 4)) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\ 27036 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times 4)) \times -(3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27037 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + (5 \times 4)) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\ 27038 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 76) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2))) - 1) \\ 27039 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 27040 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 27041 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) + 2)) + 1) \\ 27042 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) - 4)) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27043 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) - 4)) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 27044 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27045 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 27046 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 27047 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 27048 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + (2 - 1))) \\ 27049 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 27050 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + (2 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27051 &:= -(((123 \times -((-4 \times ((-56 - 7) + 8)))) + 9)) \\ 27052 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) + (8 - 9)))) \\ 27053 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times (67 + 8)))) \times 9))) \\ 27054 &:= (1 \times (-2 \times ((3 - (-4 \times (5 \times (67 + 8)))) \times -9))) \\ 27055 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) + (8 - 9)))) \\ 27056 &:= (1 - (-((-2^3)) + (((45 \times 67) - 8) \times -9))) \\ 27057 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times 6)) \times 78) - 9) \\ 27058 &:= (((1 \times -2) - 3) + (-(((45 \times 67) - 8) \times -9))) \\ 27059 &:= ((-12/3) + (((45 \times 67) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 27060 &:= (-12 \times -(3 + (4 \times (5 + ((6 + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 27061 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 27062 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) \times ((45 \times 67) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27063 &:= ((((((1 \times 2) - 3) \times 45) \times 67) + 8) \times -9) \\ 27064 &:= (-(-1) - (((2 - 3) \times ((45 \times 67) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27065 &:= (-((((1 + (2 \times 34)) \times 56) \times -7) - 8) + 9) \\ 27066 &:= (12 - ((3^4) \times (-((5 \times 67)) - (8 - 9)))) \\ 27067 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -67) + (8 - 9)) \\ 27068 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (67 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 27069 &:= -(((123 \times -((-4 \times ((-56 - 7) + 8)))) - 9)) \\ 27070 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4 \times 5) + ((6 + 7) \times 89)))) \\ 27071 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (((4 + 5) \times 6) - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 27072 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3)) \times 4) \times (5 - (6 \times -7))) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 27073 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -5) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 27074 &:= (1 - (((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 27075 &:= (((-1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times 6)) \times 78) + 9) \\ 27076 &:= (((1 - 2) - 3) \times ((4 \times 5) - 6789)) \\ 27077 &:= (-1 + (-((-2 \times 3)) \times (((4 - 567) \times -8) + 9))) \\ 27078 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 27079 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 27080 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + 45) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 27081 &:= -(((1 + (2 \times (34 - 5))) \times ((-6 \times 78) + 9))) \\ 27082 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) - 45) \times ((67 - 8) \times 9))) \\ 27083 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 27084 &:= -(((1 + (2 + 34))) \times ((5 \times 6) + (78 \times 9))) \\ 27085 &:= (-((1 - 23)) + (((-45 \times 67) + 8) \times -9)) \\ 27086 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + (((45 \times 67) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 27087 &:= (1 - (-23 + (((45 \times 67) - 8) \times -9))) \\ 27088 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27089 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -5) \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\ 27090 &:= (((1 \times -2) - ((3^4) \times -5)) \times 67) + 89) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27051 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27052 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - (6^{5-4+3})) \times 21)) \\ 27053 &:= (((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times 6)) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 27054 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) - 4)) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 27055 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\ 27056 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 76) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2))) - 1) \\ 27057 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (65 + 4)) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\ 27058 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (543 - 2))) - 1) \\ 27059 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (543 - 2))) \times -1) \\ 27060 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 \times (32 + 1)))) \\ 27061 &:= (((-98 + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\ 27062 &:= ((98 - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times (2 \times (-1))) \\ 27063 &:= ((9 \times -((-8 - (76 \times 5))/4)) \times (32 + (-1))) \\ 27064 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) + 1)) \\ 27065 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 27066 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) + 1)) \\ 27067 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 + ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + 2)) \times -1) \\ 27068 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 \times 5) - 4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 27069 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/2) - 1)) \\ 27070 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 \times 5) - 4))) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 27071 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 27072 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times 6) - (5 + (4 + 3)))^{2+1})) \\ 27073 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) \times -(43) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 27074 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 \times 5) - 4))) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 27075 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/2))) - 1) \\ 27076 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/(2 \times 1))) \\ 27077 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 76))) - (-((5 \times 4321)))) \\ 27078 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + 7) + ((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) - 1) \\ 27079 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 27080 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) + 1)) \\ 27081 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times 4)) + 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27082 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times (5 \times 4))/3)^2))) + 1) \\ 27083 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27084 &:= ((-98 - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\ 27085 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 + 432) \times 1))) \\ 27086 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 + 432)) + 1) \\ 27087 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27088 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 76) - 5) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\ 27089 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 27090 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27091 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\ 27092 &:= (1 \times -((-2 - (((-3 + (-45 \times 67)) + 8) \times -9)))) \\ 27093 &:= (-123 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27094 &:= -1 + 2^{3 \times 4} \times 5 + (6! + 7 + 8) \times 9 \\ 27095 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - ((4 \times (5 \times 678)) - 9)))) \\ 27096 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - 78) \times 9)) \\ 27097 &:= (((-1 + (2^3))^{4+5-6}) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 27098 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + (7 + 8)))))) \times 9) \\ 27099 &:= (((12/3) + ((45 \times 67) - 8)) \times 9) \\ 27100 &:= ((-12 \times 3) - (4 \times (5 - 6789))) \\ 27101 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)^4 - 5) \times (6 + 7 + 8) - 9 \\ 27102 &:= -(((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times (45 \times 67)) - 8)) + 9) \\ 27103 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27104 &:= ((1 \times (2^3)) \times (4 - (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) \times -9))) \\ 27105 &:= -(((12 - 3) \times -(((4^5) + 6) - 789))) \\ 27106 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times 67) + 8)) + 9) \\ 27107 &:= (((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 27108 &:= -(((12 \times 3) \times -(((45 + 6) + (78 \times 9)))) \\ 27109 &:= -(((1 + 2)^3) - (4 \times -((5 - 6789)))) \\ 27110 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - 78) \times 9)) \\ 27111 &:= (1 \times ((((-2 - 3) + 45) \times 678) - 9)) \\ 27112 &:= ((-1 - 23) - (4 \times (5 - 6789))) \\ 27113 &:= (1 \times (-23 - (-4 \times (-5 + 6789)))) \\ 27114 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (67 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27115 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (34 \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 27116 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 27117 &:= (-(((1 \times 23) \times (-4 - 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) - (-89))) \\ 27118 &:= (((12 - 3) \times 45) \times 67) + (-8 - 9) \\ 27119 &:= (-1 + (((((2 \times 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9)) \\ 27120 &:= (((1 \times 2) - (((3^4) \times -5) \times 67)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 27121 &:= ((-12 - 3) - (4 \times (5 - 6789))) \\ 27122 &:= (-12 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 - 9))) \\ 27123 &:= (-12 + (((3^4) \times 5) \times (67 \times -((8 - 9)))) \\ 27124 &:= ((-12 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 - 9)) \\ 27125 &:= (-1 + (-(-2) \times (((34 - 5) \times 6) \times 78) - 9)) \\ 27126 &:= ((-(((1 - 2) - (3 \times (4^5)))) + (-67 + 8)) \times 9) \\ 27127 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - (4 \times (5 - 6789))) \\ 27128 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - 45) \times 678) - 9) \\ 27129 &:= (1 \times ((((-2 - 3) + 45) \times 678) + 9)) \\ 27130 &:= (1 + ((((-2 - 3) + 45) \times 678) + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27091 &:= (-9 - ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (-543) - (-2 + 1))) \\ 27092 &:= ((-987 + (65 \times 432)) - 1) \\ 27093 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 43)))) \times - (2 + 1)) \\ 27094 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27095 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 27096 &:= (((-9 \times -(-8)) \times -(((76 \times 5) - 4))) + ((3 + 21))) \\ 27097 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 - 5) \times (4 + 3))^{2+1})) \\ 27098 &:= ((9 - (8 - 7)) + ((-6 \times -(-5)) \times -(((43 \times 21)))) \\ 27099 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27100 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27101 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/2))) - 1) \\ 27102 &:= (9 + (-(((8 \times -7) - 6) \times (5 + (432)))) - 1) \\ 27103 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/2)) + 1)) \\ 27104 &:= (9 + (-(((8 \times -7) - 6) \times (5 + (432)))) + 1) \\ 27105 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 + (4^3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27106 &:= (((98 + 7) - ((-6 \times 5)^{4-3+2})) + 1) \\ 27107 &:= ((-9 \times -(((87 \times 6) - (5 \times 4)) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\ 27108 &:= (-9 \times -(((87 \times 6) - (5 \times 4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 27109 &:= -((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (-543) - (-2 + 1)))) \\ 27110 &:= (((-9 + 876) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 27111 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6^5)/(4 - 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\ 27112 &:= (-98 + (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 27113 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times 2) - 1) \\ 27114 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 27115 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1))) \\ 27116 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) - 4)) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 27117 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 + 1))) \\ 27118 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -7) + ((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2})) - 1) \\ 27119 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 27120 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 27121 &:= (9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (54 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\ 27122 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times (-5 + 4!) \times 3! / (2 + 1) \\ 27123 &:= ((-98 + (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) + 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 27124 &:= (-98 + (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 27125 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (-7 \times -6)) \times ((543 \times 2) - 1)) \\ 27126 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - ((3^2) + 1))) \\ 27127 &:= (((9 + (-((8 + 76)) \times 5)) \times ((-4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 27128 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times 32) + 1)) \\ 27129 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - 43)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27130 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - 4)/(3 - (2 - 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27131 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (34 \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 27132 &:= (-12 + (-((34 + 5)) \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 27133 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times -5) \times 67)) \times (8 - 9)) \\ 27134 &:= ((-(((12 - 3) \times 45)) \times -67) + (8 - 9)) \\ 27135 &:= (((12 - 3) \times 45) \times 67) \times (-8 + 9)) \\ 27136 &:= (((1 + (2 - 3)) - 4) \times (5 - 6789)) \\ 27137 &:= ((1^{23}) + (4 \times (-5 + 6789))) \\ 27138 &:= (-((1 + (2 + 3))) \times ((4 - (567 \times 8)) + 9)) \\ 27139 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))))) \\ 27140 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times 4) \times 5) \times -((6 - ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 27141 &:= (((1 \times 2) + 3) - (4 \times (5 - 6789))) \\ 27142 &:= ((1 + (2 + 3)) + (4 \times (-5 + 6789))) \\ 27143 &:= -((1 + ((2^3) \times -((45 - 6) \times (78 + 9)))))) \\ 27144 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27145 &:= (-((1 - 234)) - (-5 - 67)) \times 89 \\ 27146 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((34 - 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27147 &:= ((12 \times ((3 + (4 \times 567)) - 8)) - 9) \\ 27148 &:= ((1 + (23 + (4 \times 5))) \times (-6 - (7 \times -89))) \\ 27149 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (34 \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 27150 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 + 9))) \\ 27151 &:= ((12 + 3) - (4 \times (5 - 6789))) \\ 27152 &:= (((12 - 3) \times 45) \times 67) - (-8 - 9)) \\ 27153 &:= (((-((1 + 2)) - 3) + (((45 \times 67) + 8))) \times 9) \\ 27154 &:= (((1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times -5) \times 67) + (8 + 9)) \\ 27155 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) - (4 + 5)) \times 6789)) \\ 27156 &:= (-12 \times -(3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\ 27157 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -67) + 89) \\ 27158 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((3 - (4 - 5)) \times 6789))) \\ 27159 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 - ((5 \times 678) + 9)))) \\ 27160 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) \times (4 + (5 \times 678))) + 9)) \\ 27161 &:= (-12 - (3 - (4 \times (5 + 6789)))) \\ 27162 &:= (-((-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 + (5 \times 678)))) + 9)) \\ 27163 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (4 \times -((5 - 6789)))) \\ 27164 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (34 \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 27165 &:= ((12 \times ((3 + (4 \times 567)) - 8)) + 9) \\ 27166 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3+4}) - 5) \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 27167 &:= (-12 - (-3 - (4 \times (5 + 6789)))) \\ 27168 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((-34 \times (5 - (-6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 27169 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3^{4-5+6}))) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 27170 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times -3) - (-4 \times (5 + 6789))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27131 &:= (((-98/7) \times -(((6^5)/4) - (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\ 27132 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 76) \times (-54 + ((32 + 1)))) \\ 27133 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 27134 &:= ((9 - ((-876) + (5 - 4)) \times (32 - 1))) \\ 27135 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) \times (3 \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27136 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) \times (3^2)) + 1) \\ 27137 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5)/(4 - 3) \times 2)) - 1)) \\ 27138 &:= (9 + (((8 \times 7) - 6) \times 543) - (21)) \\ 27139 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (-7 \times 6)) \times 543) - 2) \times 1)) \\ 27140 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 27141 &:= ((-9 \times -8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27142 &:= ((-9 \times -8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 27143 &:= ((-9 \times -8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2))) - 1) \\ 27144 &:= (-9 \times -8 \times ((7 + 6) \times (5 + (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 27145 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 27146 &:= ((-9 \times -8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27147 &:= ((-9 \times -8 + (((7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27148 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27149 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - 3))) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 27150 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/2) - 1)) \\ 27151 &:= (((-987) + (6^5)) \times 4) - (3 + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27152 &:= (((-987) + ((6^5))) \times 4) - (3 + (2 - 1)) \\ 27153 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2))) + 1) \\ 27154 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 76) - 5)) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 27155 &:= (((-987) + (6^5)) \times 4) - (3 - (2 \times 1)) \\ 27156 &:= (((9 + 876) - (5 + 4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\ 27157 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/(2 \times 1)))) \\ 27158 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + 4)/(3 - (2 - 1)))))) \\ 27159 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2))) - 1) \\ 27160 &:= ((-98/7) \times -(((6^5)/4) - ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 27161 &:= (((-987) + (6^5)) \times 4) + (3 + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27162 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 27163 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\ 27164 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/2) + 1)) \\ 27165 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27166 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 27167 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/2) - 1) \\ 27168 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + 6) \times 5) + 4) \times -((3^2) - 1) \\ 27169 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times (6 - ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1) \\ 27170 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(4 + (3 + 2))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27171 &:= -((1 \times ((23 - ((45 - 6) \times 78)) \times 9))) \\ 27172 &:= ((12 \times 3) - (4 \times (5 - 6789))) \\ 27173 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times (4 - (567 \times 8))) + 9))) \\ 27174 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times ((3 \times (4 - (567 \times 8))) + 9))) \\ 27175 &:= (((1 \times 2) - 3) - (-4 \times (5 + 6789))) \\ 27176 &:= (((1^{23}) \times -4) \times (-5 - 6789)) \\ 27177 &:= (-12 - ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 27178 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - ((45 \times 67) + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27179 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3 + (45 \times -67)) - 8) \times -9)) \\ 27180 &:= ((12 \times -3) + (((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 27181 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((34 \times ((56 \times 7) + 8)) - 9))) \\ 27182 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) - 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 27183 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) - 5) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 27184 &:= (-1 \times (23 - (((45 \times 67) + 8) \times 9))) \\ 27185 &:= (-(-12) - ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6789)))))) \\ 27186 &:= ((-(-1) \times -2) \times (3 - (-4 \times ((-5 \times 678) - 9)))) \\ 27187 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9))) \\ 27188 &:= (-12 - (-34 \times ((5 + 6) + 789))) \\ 27189 &:= -((((1 + 2) + ((3 - 45) \times -((6 - 78)))) \times 9)) \\ 27190 &:= ((-((1 - (-23 \times (4 \times 5)))) \times -((67 - 8))) - 9) \\ 27191 &:= ((12 + 3) + ((4 \times (5 + 6789)))) \\ 27192 &:= ((12/3) \times (4 + (5 + 6789))) \\ 27193 &:= (-1 \times (23 - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27194 &:= ((1 - 23) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27195 &:= (-12 - (((3^4) \times (5 \times 67)) - ((8 \times 9)))) \\ 27196 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27197 &:= (((12 \times (-3 + (4 \times 567))) + 8) + 9) \\ 27198 &:= (((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times -56)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 27199 &:= ((1 - 2) + (-34 \times (-((5 + 6) - 789))) \\ 27200 &:= (((1 \times 2) - (-34 \times (5 - (-6 \times 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 27201 &:= ((-12 - 3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27202 &:= (-((1 \times (2 + 3))) + (((45 \times 67) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27203 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times 56)) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\ 27204 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times (4 \times 5)) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27205 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 56)) \times ((-7 - 8) + 9))) \\ 27206 &:= (-(((1 + 2)/3) + (((45 \times 67) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27207 &:= (((1 + 2)/3) \times (((45 \times 67) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27208 &:= (((1 + 2)/3) + (((45 \times 67) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27209 &:= (((1 - 2) + 3) - (((45 \times -67) + (-8)) \times 9)) \\ 27210 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27171 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -((4 \times 3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 27172 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(4 + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 27173 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/(2 \times 1)))) \\ 27174 &:= (((9 - 8) \times 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 27175 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (-7 \times -6)) \times ((543 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27176 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 - 5) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 27177 &:= (((98/7) \times (((6^5)/4) - 3)) - (-2 - 1)) \\ 27178 &:= (-9 + (((876 + 5) - 4) \times (32 - 1))) \\ 27179 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + (7 + 6)) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 27180 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 27181 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + (7 + 6)) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 27182 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times 2))) - 1) \\ 27183 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27184 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times (5 - ((4^3) \times 2))) + 1) \\ 27185 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - 4)/(3 - (2 - 1)))))) \\ 27186 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27187 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 27188 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 27189 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27190 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 27191 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27192 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27193 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 27194 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 27195 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27196 &:= (-9 - (((8 - ((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) + 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27197 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27198 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\ 27199 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (((6^5)/(4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 27200 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) + (5 - (4 + 3)))^2 \times 1)) \\ 27201 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times 6) + (5 - (4 + 3)))^2)) + 1) \\ 27202 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27203 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27204 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) + 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 27205 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 27206 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 27207 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 27208 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 27209 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27210 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27211 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27212 &:= ((-12/3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27213 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) \times -56) \times ((7 + 8) - 9))) \\ 27214 &:= (-((1 + (-2^3))) - (((45 \times 67) + 8) \times -9)) \\ 27215 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 27216 &:= (((-1 \times -(2 \times 3))^4) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 - (8 + 9)))) \\ 27217 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27218 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times ((-34 \times (-((56 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\ 27219 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27220 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27221 &:= (-1 + (-2 + (((3^4) \times (5 \times 67)) + 89))) \\ 27222 &:= (-12 - (34 \times (-(((5 + 6) + 78)) \times 9))) \\ 27223 &:= (-1 - (-((2^3)) \times ((4 + (5 \times 678)) + 9))) \\ 27224 &:= (-1 \times (-((2^3)) \times ((4 + (5 \times 678)) + 9))) \\ 27225 &:= ((12 - 3) - ((((-4 - 5) \times 6) \times 7) \times 8) \times 9) \\ 27226 &:= (-1 \times (-2 - (((3^4) \times (5 \times 67)) + 89))) \\ 27227 &:= (((1 + 2) - (-(-((3^4))) \times (5 \times -67))) + 89) \\ 27228 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times 56)) \times -((7 + 8) - 9)) \\ 27229 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4) \times ((5^6 + 7)/8 - 9) \\ 27230 &:= ((1 - (2 + 34)) \times ((5 + 6) - 789)) \\ 27231 &:= (((1 + (23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 6) + 7)))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 27232 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (34 \times ((5 + (6 + 78)) \times 9)))) \\ 27233 &:= (-1 - ((-2 \times 3) \times (((4 \times (5 + 6)) + 7) \times 89))) \\ 27234 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (-3 \times (-((4 \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times 89))) \\ 27235 &:= (((12 \times -34) - 5) - 6) \times ((-7 \times 8) + (-9)) \\ 27236 &:= (((1 - 2) - 3) \times (-((4 \times 5) - 6789)) \\ 27237 &:= ((1 + 2) - (-3 - (((45 \times 67) + 8))) \times 9) \\ 27238 &:= ((-1 + 23) + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27239 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27240 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9) \\ 27241 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 27242 &:= ((1 + ((23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 6) + 7))) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 27243 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7))) - 8)) \times -9) \\ 27244 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9) \\ 27245 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 - ((567 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 27246 &:= (12 - (34 \times (-(((5 + 6) + 78)) \times 9))) \\ 27247 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -67) - 89) \\ 27248 &:= ((-1 - (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times -((6 \times 7) + 89)) \\ 27249 &:= (((1 + (23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 6) + 7)))) \times 8) + 9) \\ 27250 &:= (((1 \times (2 + 3)) + 45) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27211 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1) \\ 27212 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) - ((3 + 2) - 1) \\ 27213 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27214 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) - (3 - (2 - 1)) \\ 27215 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6^5)/(4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 27216 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6^5)/(4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 27217 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) + (3/(2 + 1)) \\ 27218 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) + (3 - (2 - 1)) \\ 27219 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 27220 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) + ((3 + 2) - 1) \\ 27221 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1) \\ 27222 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) + (3 + (2 + 1)) \\ 27223 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) + ((3 \times 2) + 1) \\ 27224 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2)) - 1) \\ 27225 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))))) + (3 \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27226 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2)) + 1) \\ 27227 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (((7 \times ((6^5)/4) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 27228 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + ((7 \times ((6^5)/4) + 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 27229 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + 4)/(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 27230 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6^5) + 4)/(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 27231 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27232 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times 2) + 1) \\ 27233 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6^5)/((4 - 3) \times 2)))) \times -1) \\ 27234 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2) + 1) \\ 27235 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2))) - 1)) \\ 27236 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 765)) - 4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 27237 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 76) - 5) \times -((4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27238 &:= (-987 + (((6 + (54 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 27239 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (((7 \times ((6^5)/4) + 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 27240 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27241 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) + 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 27242 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) + 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 27243 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) \times 3)))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 27244 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) + 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 27245 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27246 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27247 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times (((6^5) - (4 \times 3))/2)) + 1)) \\ 27248 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2) + 1)) \\ 27249 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5) - (4 \times 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27250 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27251 &:= (-1 \times -(((2+3) + (4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times (8+9)))) \\
 27252 &:= (((-1-2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) - (6+7))) - 8)) \times -9) \\
 27253 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + (4 \times 567))) - (8-9)) \\
 27254 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4 + (5+6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 27255 &:= ((1 \times 23) \times ((4 + ((5+6))) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 27256 &:= (1 + (23 \times ((4 + (5+6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 27257 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (4 + (567 \times 8))) + 9))) \\
 27258 &:= ((1234+5) \times (-67+89)) \\
 27259 &:= (123 - (4 \times (5 - 6789))) \\
 27260 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) + ((4+5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 27261 &:= ((1 - 234) \times ((5 \times -6) - (78 + 9))) \\
 27262 &:= (((-1+23) \times (4^5)) + (6 \times 789)) \\
 27263 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3^{4-5+6}))) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 27264 &:= (12 \times (((3 + (4 \times 567)) - 8) + 9)) \\
 27265 &:= -1 + 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 27266 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! + 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 27267 &:= (-1 + (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) + (8 - 9))) \\
 27268 &:= (((12 \times -3) - (4 \times (56 \times 7))) \times -((8 + 9))) \\
 27269 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + ((4+5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 27270 &:= ((((-1 + ((2+3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 27271 &:= ((((-1+2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 27272 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 \times 4^5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\
 27273 &:= ((12^3) + ((456 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)) \\
 27274 &:= ((((-1+2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 27275 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3!! + (4 - 5 + 6) \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 27276 &:= (-12 \times -(((3+4) \times (5 \times 67)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 27277 &:= (1 - (2+3)!) \times 4! - 5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 27278 &:= (-((-12-34)) \times ((5 \times -6) - (7 \times -89))) \\
 27279 &:= (-1 \times (((-((2^3)) + (45 \times -67)) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 27280 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times (5 - (678 + 9))) \\
 27281 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3^{4-5+6}))) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\
 27282 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)! - 4! \times 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 27283 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!!) \times (4 \times 5 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 27284 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 45)) \times -((6+7) - 89)) \\
 27285 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (45 \times 6)) - 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 27286 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -67) + (8 + 9)) \\
 27287 &:= (-1 - (((2-3) - ((4+5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 27288 &:= (((1+2) \times 3) \times (((45 \times 67) + 8) + 9)) \\
 27289 &:= -((1 + ((-23) \times (-4^5)) + ((-6 \times 7) \times 89))) \\
 27290 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (6 \times (7 \times 89)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27251 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times -(((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2) - 1)) \\
 27252 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5+4)))) + ((3+2) - 1))) \\
 27253 &:= (-(((((-9 \times (8 - 765)) \times 4) + 3) - 2)) \times -(1)) \\
 27254 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 - 765)) \times 4) + 3) - 2) + (1)) \\
 27255 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((((6+5) - 4)^3) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 27256 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - 765)) \times 4) + (3+2)) - 1) \\
 27257 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 - 765)) \times 4) + ((3 \times 2) - 1))) \\
 27258 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times -(((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/(2 \times 1))) \\
 27259 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times -(((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2)) + 1) \\
 27260 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -(4 + (3+2))) - 1) \\
 27261 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((4 \times 3) - (2+1))) \\
 27262 &:= (-98) - ((76 \times (5 \times 4)) \times ((3-21))) \\
 27263 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (((6 \times (5+4)) \times (3^2)) + 1))) \\
 27264 &:= ((-9+8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2) + 1))) \\
 27265 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times -(((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2) + 1)) \\
 27266 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 27267 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6^{5-4+3}))) \times -(2+1)) \\
 27268 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - 765)) + 4) \times ((3+2) - 1)) \\
 27269 &:= (((-9 + (-((8+76) \times 54)) \times (-3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
 27270 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5+4)))) + (3 + (2+1)))) \\
 27271 &:= (((-9 + (-((8+76) \times 54)) \times (-3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 27272 &:= ((-98/7) \times -(((6^5)/4) + ((3+2) - 1))) \\
 27273 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -(65 \times 4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\
 27274 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6^5) - 4)/(3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 27275 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2))) \times -1) \\
 27276 &:= (-9 - ((8+7) \times ((6 \times 5) - (43^2 \times 1)))) \\
 27277 &:= (-9 - (((8+7) \times ((6 \times 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\
 27278 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 765) \times 4) - 3)) - ((2 - 1))) \\
 27279 &:= (((-9 \times (-8 + 765)) \times -4) - (-3^-((-2 - 1)))) \\
 27280 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (76 \times 5))) \times (4 + (3+2))) + 1) \\
 27281 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6^5)/(4-3) \times 2) - 1))) \\
 27282 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 27283 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 27284 &:= ((((-98 - 7) \times 65) + 4) \times -((3+2) - 1)) \\
 27285 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7+6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 27286 &:= (-((-9+8)) + ((76 - (-5-4)) \times (321))) \\
 27287 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + (3-2)))) - 1) \\
 27288 &:= ((-(((9 \times 8) \times 76) \times 5) - (-4 \times (3 - (21)))) \\
 27289 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + (3-2)))) + 1) \\
 27290 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 \times 5) - (4-3)))) + (2 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27291 &:= (1 - ((-(-23) \times (-4^5)) + ((-6 \times 7) \times 89))) \\
 27292 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3!! \times (4! - 5) - 6 \times 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 27293 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (-3 \times (4 + ((567 \times 8) + 9)))))) \\
 27294 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (-3 \times (4 + ((567 \times 8) + 9)))))) \\
 27295 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + ((567 \times 8) + 9)))))) \\
 27296 &:= (-1 - (((23 \times 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 27297 &:= ((-1 + (((2 - 3) - ((4 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times -9) \\
 27298 &:= (1 - (((23 \times 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 27299 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))))) \\
 27300 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))))) \\
 27301 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 \times (45 \times 6)) - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 27302 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 27303 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27304 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27305 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\
 27306 &:= -((((1 + 2)^3) + (45 \times 67)) - 8) \times -9) \\
 27307 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27308 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27309 &:= (((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 27310 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3!! + (4 + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
 27311 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
 27312 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3) \times 4567)) - 89) \\
 27313 &:= ((1 \times ((2 \times 3) \times 4567)) - 89) \\
 27314 &:= ((1 + ((2 \times 3) \times 4567)) - 89) \\
 27315 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 27316 &:= (1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27317 &:= (-1 + (-2 + (3 + 4)^5) \times (6 + 7)) / 8 + 9 \\
 27318 &:= (12 - (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 27319 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3 \times (45 \times 6)) - 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 27320 &:= (12 + 3) \times (4^{(-5+6) \times 7} + 8) / 9 \\
 27321 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 27322 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 89)) \\
 27323 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27324 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (((4 + 56) + 78) \times 9)) \\
 27325 &:= (1 - ((2 + 34) \times ((5 \times 6) - 789))) \\
 27326 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3) + 45) \times (67 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 27327 &:= (((12 + 34) + 5) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9 \\
 27328 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3) + 45) \times (67 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 27329 &:= (-1 + (((((2 \times 3)^4) + 5) \times (6 + (7 + 8))) + 9)) \\
 27330 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (3 \times 4567)) + ((-8 \times 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27291 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\
 27292 &:= (((98 \times -(76)) + (5^4)) \times -((3 + (2 - 1)))) \\
 27293 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\
 27294 &:= -(((9 + (((-8 + 76) \times -5)/4) \times 321))) \\
 27295 &:= -((((98 + 7) \times -((65 \times 4))) + (3 + 2)) \times 1) \\
 27296 &:= -((((98 + 7) \times -((65 \times 4))) + (3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 27297 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4)))) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 27298 &:= ((9 \times 8) - (-(((7 - (6 - 54)) \times -3)^2)) - 1) \\
 27299 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6 \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\
 27300 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6 \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
 27301 &:= ((-((-9 \times 8)) \times (76 \times 5)) - (-4 + (3 \times (21)))) \\
 27302 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + 4)/(3 - (2 - 1)))))) \\
 27303 &:= ((((-987 + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 27304 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 27305 &:= (((98 + 7) \times -((65 \times 4))) - ((3 + 2))) \times -1) \\
 27306 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times 6) - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
 27307 &:= (((((98 + 7) \times (65 \times 4)) + (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 27308 &:= ((-98 - (((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 27309 &:= (-9 - (87 \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3 \times (2 - 1)))))) \\
 27310 &:= (-9 - ((87 \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 - 1))) \\
 27311 &:= (-9 - ((87 \times (6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 27312 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^{2+1})))) \\
 27313 &:= (((-987 + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 27314 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 27315 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times 6) - (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
 27316 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 27317 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\
 27318 &:= (((9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5)/4) - 3))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 27319 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4))/3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 27320 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4))/3)^2)) + 1) \\
 27321 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) - 4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 27322 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) - 4)) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 27323 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2) - 1)) \\
 27324 &:= (((98 \times 7) - 65) \times (43 - (-2 + 1))) \\
 27325 &:= (((-9 - ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1) \\
 27326 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) - 4)) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 27327 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -((76 \times 5))) - (((4 \times 3) + 21))) \\
 27328 &:= ((-98/7) \times -(((6^5)/4) + ((3^2) - 1))) \\
 27329 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2))) - 1) \\
 27330 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/(2 \times 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27331 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4567))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 27332 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5) - 6)) - (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27333 &:= (((-1 - (((2 \times 3)^4) + 5)) \times -(6 + (7 + 8))) - 9) \\ 27334 &:= ((-1 - (23 \times (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 27335 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 + 5)) \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 27336 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times (((-3 - 4) - 5) \times 67)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 27337 &:= (1 + (((-23 - 4) - 5) \times (67 \times (-8 - 9)))) \\ 27338 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3 + 4) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8)) - 9)) \\ 27339 &:= (-12 + ((-3 + ((45 - 6) \times 78)) \times 9)) \\ 27340 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27341 &:= ((12 \times (3 - (4 \times -(567)))) - (-89)) \\ 27342 &:= (-(((12/3) + 45)) \times ((-6 - (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27343 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27344 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27345 &:= (((12 + 34) + 5) \times (67 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 27346 &:= (-1 - (23 \times -(((4 \times (5 \times (67 - 8))) + 9)))) \\ 27347 &:= (-1 \times (23 \times -(((4 \times (5 \times (67 - 8))) + 9)))) \\ 27348 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27349 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27350 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7))) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27351 &:= (((-((12/3)) \times 456) \times (-7 - 8)) - 9) \\ 27352 &:= (((1 - 23) \times -((4^5))) + ((-67 \times 8) \times -9)) \\ 27353 &:= (-1 + ((-2 \times -3) \times (((4 + 567) \times 8) - 9))) \\ 27354 &:= -((1 + 23)) + ((45 - 6) \times (78 \times 9)) \\ 27355 &:= (-1 \times (23 - ((45 - 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 27356 &:= ((1 - 23) + ((45 - 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 27357 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27358 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (((3 \times 4) - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27359 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)))) \\ 27360 &:= (((1 + 234) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) - (-8 \times 9))) \\ 27361 &:= ((1^2) + (((3 \times 4) - (56 \times 7)) \times 8) \times -9)) \\ 27362 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (4567 - 8)) + 9)) \\ 27363 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times (67 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 27364 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) \times (4567 - 8)) + 9)) \\ 27365 &:= (((12^3)/4) - (5 + 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 27366 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((-345) - 6) \times 78) + 9)) \\ 27367 &:= ((1 \times (-2 - ((345 + 6) \times -78))) - 9) \\ 27368 &:= (((1 - 23) \times -4) \times (5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 27369 &:= ((-12 + 3) + (((45 - 6) \times 78) \times 9)) \\ 27370 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times 3) - (-4 \times 56)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27331 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (76 \times 5)) - (-4 + ((32 + 1)))) \\ 27332 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (76 \times 5)) - ((-4 + 32) \times 1)) \\ 27333 &:= (-9 \times (87 - (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) - 1))) \\ 27334 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + 5) - 4)^3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27335 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2) - 1)) \\ 27336 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6 \times (5 \times 4))/3)^2) + 1)) \\ 27337 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2) + 1)) \\ 27338 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) - (4 - (3 - 21))) \\ 27339 &:= (-(((9 \times 8) \times 76) \times (5 \times (4 - 3)))) - (21)) \\ 27340 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\ 27341 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - 2)) - 1) \\ 27342 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\ 27343 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 27344 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) - (4 \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 27345 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) - ((4 \times 3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 27346 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) - ((4 + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 27347 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) - (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 27348 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) - (4 - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 27349 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2) + 1)) \\ 27350 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 27351 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27352 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 27353 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times 76) \times 5) - (((4 + 3) \times (2 - 1))) \\ 27354 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 27355 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 27356 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times (((6^5) + (4 \times 3))/2))) \times -1) \\ 27357 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) - ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27358 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + (4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 27359 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((76 \times (5 \times 4)) \times (3 - (21)))) \\ 27360 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times -((7 + (6 \times 5)) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 27361 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3}))) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 27362 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) - (4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 27363 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + ((4 - 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27364 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + ((4 + 3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 27365 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 27366 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 27367 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times 76) \times 5) + (((4 + 3) \times (2 - 1))) \\ 27368 &:= (((98 - 76) \times (((5^4) - 3) \times -2) \times -1)) \\ 27369 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (7 \times (6^{(5+4)/3}))) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27370 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27371 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27372 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - (34 \times (5 - (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\ 27373 &:= (1 + ((-2 \times 3) + ((45 - 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 27374 &:= ((-12/3) + (((45 - 6) \times 78) \times 9)) \\ 27375 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -(3 - ((45 - 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 27376 &:= ((-12 \times 3) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27377 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 27378 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (4^5))) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 27379 &:= (1 \times (-((2 - 3) + (-((45 - 6) \times (78 \times -9)))))) \\ 27380 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + ((45 - 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 27381 &:= (12 + (((345 + 6) \times 78) - 9)) \\ 27382 &:= ((12/3) - ((45 - 6) \times (78 \times -9))) \\ 27383 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 78) - 9))) \\ 27384 &:= ((1 + 2) + (3 + (((45 - 6) \times -(-78)) \times 9))) \\ 27385 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + ((45 - 6) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 27386 &:= ((1 - (-2 \times (3 \times 4567))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 27387 &:= (-((-12 + 3) + (((45 - 6) \times 78) \times 9))) \\ 27388 &:= ((((-((1 \times 2)) \times 34) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 - 89)) \\ 27389 &:= ((1 \times -23) + (((-4 \times (5 + 6)) \times 7) \times -89)) \\ 27390 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27391 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 27392 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times (78 - 9))) \\ 27393 &:= -((((12 \times 34) + (-5 - 6)) \times -((78 - 9)))) \\ 27394 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 27395 &:= (-1 - (((23 \times 4) - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27396 &:= (-12 \times (-((3^-(4 - (5 + 6)))) - (7 + 89))) \\ 27397 &:= (-12 + (-3 - ((4 \times (-5 - 6)) \times (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27398 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3^4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 27399 &:= (((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -((4 + 567) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 27400 &:= (-12 - (((3 \times 4) - 56) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 27401 &:= (-(((1 \times -2) \times (3 \times 4567))) + (8 - 9)) \\ 27402 &:= ((1 + 23) + ((45 - 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 27403 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 27404 &:= (-((1^2)) + (((3 + 4) \times -5) \times (6 - 789))) \\ 27405 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) + (((45 - 6) \times -(-78)) \times 9)) \\ 27406 &:= -((((1^2)) - (((3 + 4) \times -5) \times (6 - 789)))) \\ 27407 &:= (-1 + ((-2 \times -3) \times ((4567 - 8) + 9))) \\ 27408 &:= ((1 - 2) + (-3 + (4 \times (((5 + 6) \times 7) \times 89)))) \\ 27409 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (3 \times 4567) + 8) - 9) \\ 27410 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 89)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27371 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 27372 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4 - 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 27373 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 27374 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + ((4 + 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 27375 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2) + 1))) \\ 27376 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + (4 \times ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 27377 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + ((4 - 3) \times 2))) - 1) \\ 27378 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (76 \times (5 \times 4))) \times (3 - (21))) \\ 27379 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + ((4 \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\ 27380 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + (4 \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 27381 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + ((4 + 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27382 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + (4 - (3 - 21))) \\ 27383 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^{2+1})))) \\ 27384 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 27385 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 76)) - 5) \times (4 - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 27386 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 76)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 27387 &:= (-9 \times (8 + ((7 - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\ 27388 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (76 \times 5)) + ((-4 + 32) \times 1)) \\ 27389 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times (76 \times 5)) + (-4 + ((32 + 1)))) \\ 27390 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -((5 + (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\ 27391 &:= ((-98 + 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 2)))) + 1)) \\ 27392 &:= ((-9 - (87 + (6 + 5))) \times -(4^{3+2-1})) \\ 27393 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 27394 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 27395 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (5 \times 4)) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\ 27396 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (5 \times 4)) \times -(3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27397 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (5 \times 4)) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\ 27398 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 27399 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) + (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 27400 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + (6 - 5)) \times 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\ 27401 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 27402 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times -2) \times 1) \\ 27403 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (((6^5)/4) + 3))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 27404 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -(((5^4)/(3 + 2)) - 1)) \\ 27405 &:= -((((98 + 7) \times ((65 \times 4) - (((-3 + 2) \times 1)))))) \\ 27406 &:= ((-98 - ((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 27407 &:= (((-98 - ((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) - 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 27408 &:= ((((-9 - 87) \times 6) + 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 27409 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + ((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 27410 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$27411 := (-1 \times -((2-3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times 89))))))$$

$$27412 := (((12 + ((3-4) \times 56)) \times -(-7)) \times -89)$$

$$27413 := (-1 + (((23 - (-45 \times 67)) + 8) \times -(-9)))$$

$$27414 := (((12/3) + ((45-6) \times 78)) \times 9)$$

$$27415 := ((-1+2) \times (3 + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times 89))))))$$

$$27416 := ((-1 + (2+3)) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times 89))))$$

$$27417 := (-1 \times -((2+3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times 89))))))$$

$$27418 := (-1 \times -((2 \times 3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times 89))))))$$

$$27419 := (-1 + ((2^3) + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times 89))))))$$

$$27420 := (((1 \times 2)^3) + ((4 \times (5+6)) \times (7 \times 89)))$$

$$27421 := (12 + (-3 - ((4 \times (-5-6)) \times (7 \times 89))))$$

$$27422 := (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + (6 - (7+8)))))) \times 9)$$

$$27423 := ((-1 - ((23 - (-45 \times 67)) + 8)) \times -9)$$

$$27424 := (12 - (((3 \times 4) - 56) \times (7 \times 89)))$$

$$27425 := (-1 + (2 \times ((3 \times ((4+567) \times 8)) + 9)))$$

$$27426 := (((-12 - (3^4)) \times -5 \times (67-8)) - 9)$$

$$27427 := (((1 \times 2) \times ((3 \times 4567) + 8)) + 9)$$

$$27428 := ((-1 + (2+3)) \times (4 + ((5+6) \times (7 \times 89))))$$

$$27429 := (((1 \times 2) + 34) + 5) \times (678-9)$$

$$27430 := (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + ((4+5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$27431 := (-1 - (-2 \times ((3 \times (4567+8)) - 9)))$$

$$27432 := ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times -5 - ((6+7) \times (8+9)))$$

$$27433 := (-((1 - (2 \times -3))) \times (-4 - ((5 \times (-6 + (789))))))$$

$$27434 := (-((1-23)) + ((4 \times (5+6)) \times -((-7 \times 89))))$$

$$27435 := ((1 \times 23) - ((4 \times (5+6)) \times (7 \times -89)))$$

$$27436 := ((-1 - ((2^3) \times 45)) \times ((6+7) - 89))$$

$$27437 := (-1 + (2 \times (((34 \times 5) + 6) \times 78) - 9))$$

$$27438 := ((1 - ((2 \times (3 \times 45)))) \times (-6 - (7+89)))$$

$$27439 := (-1 \times (23 \times ((4 \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) - 9)))$$

$$27440 := (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7+8)))) \times 9))$$

$$27441 := ((((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - (6 + (7+8))) \times 9)$$

$$27442 := ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4567+8)))) - 9)$$

$$27443 := -(1 + (2+3)!) \times 4! + 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8+9)$$

$$27444 := (-12 \times ((-34 \times (-5 - ((6-78)))) - 9))$$

$$27445 := (1+2) \times 3!! + (4-5+6) \times (7! + 8+9)$$

$$27446 := (-1 - (((2^3) \times -4) \times ((5+6) \times 78)) + 9)$$

$$27447 := (-12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7+8))) \times 9))$$

$$27448 := ((12 \times 3) - ((4 \times (-5-6)) \times (7 \times 89)))$$

$$27449 := (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + ((4+5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times 9))$$

$$27450 := (((-1+2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7+8)))) \times -9)$$

$$27411 := ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3))) - 21)$$

$$27412 := ((-98 - (7 \times ((6^5)/4))) \times -(3 - (2-1)))$$

$$27413 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3)) - 2)) - 1)$$

$$27414 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times (-76) \times 5) - 4)) - (3 - ((21))))$$

$$27415 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3)) - 2)) + 1)$$

$$27416 := ((-9-8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2) - 1))$$

$$27417 := (((-98 - ((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) + 3)) \times -2) - 1)$$

$$27418 := ((-98 - ((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))$$

$$27419 := (((-98 - ((7 \times ((6^5)/4)) + 3)) \times -2) + 1)$$

$$27420 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5) + (4+3))) - (2+1))$$

$$27421 := (((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5))) + (4^3)) - (2+1))$$

$$27422 := (((-9-8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2))) - 1)$$

$$27423 := (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) + 3) \times -(2+1))$$

$$27424 := ((-9-8) + ((7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2)) + 1))$$

$$27425 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5) + (4+3))) + (2 \times 1))$$

$$27426 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5) + (4+3))) + (2+1))$$

$$27427 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5))) + ((4^3) + (2+1)))$$

$$27428 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5) + 4)) + (32 \times 1))$$

$$27429 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3))) - (2+1))$$

$$27430 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3))) - (2 \times 1))$$

$$27431 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3))) - (2-1))$$

$$27432 := ((-(((-9 \times 8) \times 76)) \times 5) + (-4 \times (3 - (21))))$$

$$27433 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3))) + (2-1))$$

$$27434 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3))) + (2 \times 1))$$

$$27435 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3))) + (2+1))$$

$$27436 := (((-9-876) \times (5 - (4 \times (3^2)))) + 1)$$

$$27437 := ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))/3)) - (2+1))$$

$$27438 := (((-9+8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2))) - 1)$$

$$27439 := ((-9+8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/(2 \times 1))))$$

$$27440 := ((98 \times ((7+6) - (54 - 321)))$$

$$27441 := (-9 + (((8+7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2+1))))$$

$$27442 := ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))/3)) + (2 \times 1))$$

$$27443 := ((-98 \times -((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))/3)) + (2+1))$$

$$27444 := ((-9 \times (8 - ((765 \times 4) - 3))) + (2+1))$$

$$27445 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5))) + ((43 \times 2) - 1))$$

$$27446 := ((-9+8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2) + 1))$$

$$27447 := (((98/7) \times (654 \times 3)) - (21))$$

$$27448 := ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((65 \times (4 + (3+2))) - 1))$$

$$27449 := ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3)) + 2)) - 1)$$

$$27450 := (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + 3)) + (2 \times 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27451 &:= (1 + (((2^3) + ((45 - 6) \times 78)) \times 9)) \\
 27452 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + (4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
 27453 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) - (8 + 9) \\
 27454 &:= -1 - (2 + (3 - 4!) \times (5 + 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 27455 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 \times (5 + (67 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\
 27456 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27457 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27458 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 27459 &:= ((12 - 3) \times ((4 - ((5 \times 67) + 8)) \times -9)) \\
 27460 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27461 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27462 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) - 6)) \times -(78 - 9)) \\
 27463 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
 27464 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 27465 &:= (-((123 \times (4 \times -56))) - (78 + 9)) \\
 27466 &:= (1 - (((2 - 34) \times ((5 + 6) \times 78)) - 9)) \\
 27467 &:= (-1 + (-2 \times (-((3 \times (4567 + 8))) - 9))) \\
 27468 &:= ((-((1 + 23)) - 4) \times ((5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 27469 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((3 \times (4567 + 8)) + 9))) \\
 27470 &:= ((-(-123) \times (4 \times 56)) - (-7 + 89)) \\
 27471 &:= (12 - (-3 \times (((4^5) - 6) + 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 27472 &:= (((12^3) + (-45 - 67)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 27473 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4567))) - (-8 \times 9)) \\
 27474 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (3 \times 4567)) - ((-8 \times 9))) \\
 27475 &:= ((1 - (2 \times -((3 \times 4567)))) - ((-8 \times 9))) \\
 27476 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27477 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7 + 8)))) \times -9) \\
 27478 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) + (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27479 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) + (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27480 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) \times (5 \times (678 + 9))) \\
 27481 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4)) \times (((5^6) + 7)/8) + 9)) \\
 27482 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times -(((5^6) + 7)/8) + 9)) \\
 27483 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 27484 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 27485 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (45 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) \times 9))) \\
 27486 &:= -((((12 + (-3 \times (4^5))) + (-6 \times (7 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27487 &:= -((((12 - (3456 - 7)) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 27488 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (3 \times (((4^5) - 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 27489 &:= (-(((1 - 2) + 34)) \times -((56 - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 27490 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 \times 4567)) + 89))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27451 &:= (-((9 + 8)) + (((7 \times 654) \times (-3 \times -2)) \times 1)) \\
 27452 &:= ((-98 + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 27453 &:= (((-98 + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
 27454 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\
 27455 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 27456 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3^{2+1})))) \\
 27457 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/2))) \times -1) \\
 27458 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 76) \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 27459 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times (6 + (5 + 4)))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 27460 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 76)) - (5 \times 4)) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 27461 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 76)) - (5 \times 4)) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 27462 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (765 \times 4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 27463 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (765 \times 4))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 27464 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (765 \times 4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 27465 &:= (((98/7) \times 654) \times 3) - ((2 + 1)) \\
 27466 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times (654 \times 3))) \times ((2 \times -1))) \\
 27467 &:= ((9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 654) \times (-3 \times -2)) - 1)) \\
 27468 &:= (-9 \times (8 + (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\
 27469 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 27470 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4 \times 3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 27471 &:= (((98/7) \times 654) \times 3) + ((2 + 1)) \\
 27472 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times (6 + (5 \times (43 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
 27473 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (765 \times 4))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 27474 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (765 \times 4))) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 27475 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (765 \times 4))) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 27476 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\
 27477 &:= (9 \times (((8 \times 76) \times 5) + (((4 \times 3) + (2 - 1)))))) \\
 27478 &:= (((-9 - ((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\
 27479 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (76 + 5))) \times 43) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 27480 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 27481 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times 5 \times (4 + 3) + (2 + 1)! \\
 27482 &:= -9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times (4^3 - 2)) - 1 \\
 27483 &:= (-9 + (87 \times (6 + (5 \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1)))))) \\
 27484 &:= (-9 + ((87 \times (6 + (5 \times ((4^3) - 2)))) + 1)) \\
 27485 &:= ((9 + 8) + (((7 \times 654) \times (-3 \times -2)) \times 1)) \\
 27486 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + ((4 + 3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\
 27487 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + ((4 + 3) \times 2))) + 1) \\
 27488 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (76 \times 5))) + ((4^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 27489 &:= (((98/7) \times (654 \times 3)) + (21)) \\
 27490 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 \times (6 + (5 \times (43 + 2)))) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27491 &:= ((1 \times ((2 \times 3) \times 4567)) + 89) \\ 27492 &:= (-(1 + 2) + (345 + 6) \times (7 - (8 \times -9))) \\ 27493 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27494 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 27495 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8)))) \times 9) \\ 27496 &:= (-(-1) - ((-2 - 3) \times (((4 + 5) \times 67) + 8) \times 9))) \\ 27497 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - 6)) - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27498 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27499 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 27500 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 3) + (-4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 89)) \\ 27501 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((34 \times 5) - 67) \times -89)) \\ 27502 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3^4)) - (56 \times 7)) \times 89)) \\ 27503 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) + (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 27504 &:= (((-1 - 2) - 3) \times (-4567 - (8 + 9))) \\ 27505 &:= ((((-123 \times 4) - (5 - 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 27506 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3) \times 45) + 6) \times 7) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 27507 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 89)))) \\ 27508 &:= (-1 \times -(23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 89)))) \\ 27509 &:= (1 + (23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 89)))) \\ 27510 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27511 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27512 &:= (-1 + (((2 - ((3^4))) - ((56 \times -7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27513 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27514 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27515 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27516 &:= ((1 + 2) - (-3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27517 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) + 89) \\ 27518 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!^4 + 5 \times (6! + 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 27519 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))))) \\ 27520 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\ 27521 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8))) - 9))) \\ 27522 &:= ((1 + 2) \times -(((3 \times (4^5)) + (-678) \times 9))) \\ 27523 &:= ((((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times 45))) \times 6) + 7) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 27524 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (345 + 6)) \times 78)) - 9) \\ 27525 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((34 \times 5) - 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\ 27526 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (345 + 6)) \times 78)) - 9) \\ 27527 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 78)) + 9))) \\ 27528 &:= ((-1 + (-2 - 3)) \times (4 + ((56 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\ 27529 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (78 - 9)) \\ 27530 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) - ((6 + 7) - 8)))) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27491 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2))) - 1) \\ 27492 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 27493 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2))) + 1) \\ 27494 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (65 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 27495 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\ 27496 &:= ((98/7) \times (((654 \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\ 27497 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + 3) \times -2) - 1) \\ 27498 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 27499 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\ 27500 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times -((43 + 2) - 1)) \\ 27501 &:= ((-9 - (87 \times (6 + (5 \times ((4^3) - 2)))) \times -1) \\ 27502 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (654 \times 3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 27503 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2})) - 1) \\ 27504 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + ((6 \times 5)^{(4-3) \times (2+1)})) \\ 27505 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) + 1)) \\ 27506 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (65 \times ((4 \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)))) \\ 27507 &:= (((((-98 + 76) \times (5^4)) - 3) \times -2) + 1) \\ 27508 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times 654)) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 27509 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (76 \times (5 \times 4)))) - 3) \times -2) - 1) \\ 27510 &:= ((98/7) \times (((654 \times 3) + 2) + 1)) \\ 27511 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times -7) - ((65 \times -((432 - 1)))))) \\ 27512 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6^5) + (4^3))/(2 \times 1)))) \\ 27513 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 + (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) + 3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27514 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 76) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 27515 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 32)) - 1))) \\ 27516 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -54) - (3 + 21)) \\ 27517 &:= (((-98 \times -(7 + 6)) + ((54 \times 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 27518 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + 6)) + ((54 \times 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 27519 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 27520 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 27521 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 27522 &:= (-9 \times -((8 - 76) + (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\ 27523 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((76 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\ 27524 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((765 \times 4) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\ 27525 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times 654)) \times (3 \times 2))) \times -1) \\ 27526 &:= (9 + (((8 + (7 \times 654)) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 27527 &:= ((-987 \times -6) + (5 \times 4321)) \\ 27528 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((76 - 5) \times 43))) - 21) \\ 27529 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times ((5^4) + 32)) + 1))) \\ 27530 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 65) + 4) \times (3^2)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27531 &:= ((((((1+2) \times (34 \times 5)) \times -6) - 7) + 8) \times -9) \\ 27532 &:= ((-1+2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - 6) \times (78 - 9))) \\ 27533 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (45 \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 27534 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (45 \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 27535 &:= (123 + (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 27536 &:= -1 \times 2 \times (3!^4 + 5) + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 27537 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\ 27538 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\ 27539 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 34) \times 5) \times -((-6 + (78 + 9)))) \\ 27540 &:= (-1 \times (((2 \times 34) \times 5) \times -((-6 + (78 + 9)))) \\ 27541 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 34) \times 5) \times -((-6 + (78 + 9)))) \\ 27542 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3^4) \times (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\ 27543 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 27544 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -((5 \times (6 - (7 - 8))) + 9)) \\ 27545 &:= (((123 \times 4) \times -56) + 7) \times (8 - 9) \\ 27546 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) - (6 + (7 + 89)) \\ 27547 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 - 7))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 27548 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 27549 &:= ((1 + ((234 + (5 \times -6)) \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 27550 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 - 7))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 27551 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 - 7))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 27552 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4 \times (5 + (6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 27553 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) - (((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9) \\ 27554 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!)^4 + 5 \times (-6 + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\ 27555 &:= (-12 + (((-3 \times -((4^5))) + (6 - 7)) - 8) \times 9) \\ 27556 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 27557 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) + ((6 - 7) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27558 &:= (((-123 \times -4) \times 56) + ((7 + 8))) - 9) \\ 27559 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) + 89) \\ 27560 &:= ((-123 \times -(4 \times 56)) + (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 27561 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 27562 &:= ((-123 \times -(4 \times 56)) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 27563 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3+4} \times 5)) \times -((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9))) \\ 27564 &:= -((-12 \times -((34 + ((-5 \times 6) \times 78))) - 9)) \\ 27565 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27566 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -(((3 + 4)^5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27567 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 27568 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (-3456) + 7)) \times -8)) - 9) \\ 27569 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27570 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (345 + 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27531 &:= (-9 \times -(8 - ((7 - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\ 27532 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 65) + 4) \times (3^2)) + 1) \\ 27533 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -54) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27534 &:= ((-9 + 87) \times (((6 + 5) \times (4^3))/2) + 1)) \\ 27535 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -54) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 27536 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -54) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 27537 &:= (((98/7) \times ((6^-(-5))/4)) + ((321))) \\ 27538 &:= (-98 \times -((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 27539 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) - 4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 27540 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -((5 + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 27541 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) - 4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 27542 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((65 \times (4 + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 27543 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4) \times (3^2)) + 1))) \\ 27544 &:= ((((((9 \times 8) \times 7) + 6) \times 54) + (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 27545 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -54) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 27546 &:= ((((((9 \times 8) \times 7) + 6) \times 54) + (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 27547 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 - 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 27548 &:= (-9 + (((((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 - 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 27549 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) - 4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 27550 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 27551 &:= (-98 + (((((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27552 &:= ((-9 - 87) \times -(((6 \times (5 + 43)) - 2) - 1)) \\ 27553 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times ((5 \times 4) + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 27554 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times ((5 \times (4 + (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 27555 &:= (-9 - ((-8 + (765 \times (4 \times -3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27556 &:= (9 + (8 + ((765 \times (4 + 32)) - 1))) \\ 27557 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + 3))))^2) + 1) \\ 27558 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 27559 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + ((76 \times (5 \times 4)) + 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 27560 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) - (43^2))) + 1)) \\ 27561 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6 + (54 \times (3^2)))) \times -1) \\ 27562 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) - (43^2))) - 1)) \\ 27563 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 27564 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 76) + 5)) + 4) \times -((3 + 2) - 1) \\ 27565 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 - 3)^2)) \times -1) \\ 27566 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times 7) + 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 27567 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times -((6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27568 &:= ((-9 - (8 - (7 - 6))) \times (5 - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 27569 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times ((6 + ((5^4) + 3))/2))) - 1) \\ 27570 &:= (-9 - (87 \times (6 - ((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27571 &:= (-1 \times (-(-(2 - (345 + 6)))) \times (7 - (8 \times -9))) \\
 27572 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 27573 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27574 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27575 &:= ((-(((12^3) - 4)) \times ((5 - 6) - (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
 27576 &:= ((((-123 \times -4) \times 56) + ((7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 27577 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27578 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27579 &:= (-((1 + (((-2^3) - 45) \times 6))) \times (78 + 9)) \\
 27580 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3456 - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 27581 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3456 - 7) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 27582 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 - (7 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27583 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 - (7 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27584 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 27585 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times -9) \\
 27586 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 - (7 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27587 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 - (7 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27588 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - (3 - 4))^5)) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 27589 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)) - 7) \times 89))) \\
 27590 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times -(7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 27591 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3 \times (4^5)) - 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 27592 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3 \times (4^5)) - 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 27593 &:= ((-(((12^3) - 4)) \times ((5 - 6) - (7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 27594 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 - (4^5)) \times (6 - (7 + 8))) + 9)) \\
 27595 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3 \times (4^5)) - 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 27596 &:= (1 \times (2 + (((-3 \times (4^5)) + 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 27597 &:= (12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 - (7 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27598 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 27599 &:= (-1 - (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 + 9)))))) \\
 27600 &:= (((-1 \times (23 \times 4)) \times (5 \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\
 27601 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27602 &:= ((-1 - (-2 + ((-3456) + 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\
 27603 &:= ((-12 + ((3^4) - ((56 \times 7) \times -(-8)))) \times -9) \\
 27604 &:= (-((-1 - 2)) - (((-3456) + 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 27605 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - ((6 + 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27606 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times (((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times 89)))) \\
 27607 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((34 + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 27608 &:= ((1 \times (((-2^3) + (-4 \times 56)) \times 7)) \times -((8 + 9))) \\
 27609 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 27610 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3)) \times -((4 - ((5 - 67) \times 89))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27571 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 27572 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 27573 &:= ((-98 + 7) \times (6 - ((5 \times ((4^3) - 2)) - 1))) \\
 27574 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (((6 \times 543) / (2 \times 1)))) \\
 27575 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) + (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 27576 &:= (((-9 - (-8 + 765)) \times -4) \times (-3^2 \times 1)) \\
 27577 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 + 4))) + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 27578 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 32)) + 1)) \\
 27579 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) - (43^2)))) \times -1) \\
 27580 &:= ((9 \times (8 - (-765) \times 4)) + ((32 \times -1))) \\
 27581 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (765 \times 4))) - (32 - 1)) \\
 27582 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (((6^5) \times 4) / (3^2)))) + 1)) \\
 27583 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (((6^5) \times 4) / (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 27584 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) + 4) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\
 27585 &:= ((-9 \times (-8 + (-765) \times 4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\
 27586 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\
 27587 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 27588 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 27589 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -((4^3) - 2)) - 1) \\
 27590 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 27591 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\
 27592 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 32))) - 1) \\
 27593 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) - (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 27594 &:= ((-98/7) \times -(((6^5)/4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 27595 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) - (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\
 27596 &:= ((9 - 8) + (((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + 32)) + 1)) \\
 27597 &:= (-9 + ((87 - ((6 - 5)^4)) \times 321)) \\
 27598 &:= (9 - 8 + 7 \times 6) \times 5^4 + 3 + (2 + 1)!! \\
 27599 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 27600 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 \times (4 \times ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\
 27601 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (((6^5) \times 4) / (3^2)))) \times -1) \\
 27602 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 27603 &:= (-9 \times -(8 - (((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 27604 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 27605 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 76) + 5)) - 4) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 27606 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times 76) + 5)) - 4) \times -((3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 27607 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (765 \times 4))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 27608 &:= ((-987) + (6 - 5)) \times (((4 - 32) \times 1)) \\
 27609 &:= (((987 - ((6 - 5))) \times -((4 - 32))) + (1)) \\
 27610 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times 6) \times -((5 - (4^3))) - (2 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27611 &:= (-(1^2)) - ((34+5) \times (-6 + (78 \times -9))) \\
 27612 &:= -(((1+2) - ((-(34-5) - 6) \times -(789)))) \\
 27613 &:= -((-12 + (-(3456-7)) \times -(-8)) - 9) \\
 27614 &:= -((1 + (((2+34) + 5) - 6) \times -(789))) \\
 27615 &:= -((1 \times (((2+34) + 5) - 6) \times -(789))) \\
 27616 &:= (1 - (((2+34) + 5) - 6) \times -(789)) \\
 27617 &:= (1 \times (((2+3456) - 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 27618 &:= ((1+2) + ((-(34-5) - 6) \times -(789))) \\
 27619 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 - (7+8))) + 9))) \\
 27620 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times (6 - (7+8)))) - 9) \\
 27621 &:= -((1+2) \times ((-345) - (678)) \times -(-9)) \\
 27622 &:= ((-1+2) - (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 - (7+8))) + 9))) \\
 27623 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 - (7+8))) + 9))) \\
 27624 &:= (-1 + (((2+3)^4)/5) \times ((6+7) \times (8+9))) \\
 27625 &:= (((-1 \times -(2+3))^4)/5) \times ((6+7) \times (8+9)) \\
 27626 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times (4^5)) + (67-89) \\
 27627 &:= (12 - (((34-5) + 6) \times -(789))) \\
 27628 &:= ((-(((12^3) \times 4)) + 5) \times (((6+7) - 8) - 9)) \\
 27629 &:= ((1-2) + (((3^4) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
 27630 &:= (((-1+2) - (3 \times (4^5))) \times (6 - (7+8))) - 9) \\
 27631 &:= (((-(((12^3) \times 4)) \times (-5 - (6-7))) - 8) - 9) \\
 27632 &:= ((((-1-2)^3) \times (-4^5)) + (-6 - (-7 + (8+9)))) \\
 27633 &:= ((-123 \times 4) + (5^{6+7-8} \times 9)) \\
 27634 &:= ((-(-123) \times (4 \times 56)) + (-7 + 89)) \\
 27635 &:= (1 + ((2 - (345 - 6)) \times (7 - 89))) \\
 27636 &:= ((-1-2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times (6 - (7+8)))) + 9)) \\
 27637 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times (6 - (7+8)))) + 9)) \\
 27638 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3 \times (4^5))) \times (6 - (7+8))) + 9)) \\
 27639 &:= -(((123 \times (4 \times -56)) - (78 + 9))) \\
 27640 &:= -(((1-2) + 3456) \times (-((7-8) - 9))) \\
 27641 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times (6 - (7+8)))) + 9)) \\
 27642 &:= ((1234 + (56 \times 7)) \times -((-8-9))) \\
 27643 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times (4^5)) + (67 - (8 \times 9)) \\
 27644 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times (4^5)) + ((6+7) - (8+9)) \\
 27645 &:= (-12 - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times (6 - (7+8)))) - 9)) \\
 27646 &:= (1 \times (-2 - ((3+45) \times (6 \times (-7-89)))) \\
 27647 &:= ((1-2) - ((3+45) \times (6 \times (-7-89)))) \\
 27648 &:= ((1-2) \times ((3+45) \times (6 \times (-7-89)))) \\
 27649 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\
 27650 &:= (((1-2) - 34) \times ((5-6) - 789))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27611 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - (((7+6) - (5^4)) \times (3+2)))) - 1) \\
 27612 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4 + (3+2))) - 1) \\
 27613 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - (((7+6) - (5^4)) \times (3+2)))) + 1) \\
 27614 &:= ((-9 \times (-8 + (-765 \times 4))) + (3 - (2 - (1)))) \\
 27615 &:= ((((-9-8) + (((7 - (6-5)) \times 4^3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
 27616 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times -(5 \times (4+3))) + (2-1)) \\
 27617 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times -(5 \times (4+3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 27618 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - 6) \times -(5 \times (4+3))) + (2+1)) \\
 27619 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 27620 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4 + (3+2)))) - 1) \\
 27621 &:= (((98+7) \times 65) \times -(-4)) + (321) \\
 27622 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4 + (3+2)))) + 1) \\
 27623 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (((7 - (6-5)) \times 4^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 27624 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7+6)) \times -((5^4)/(3+2))) - 1) \\
 27625 &:= (((-9-8) \times (7+6)) \times -5^{(4-3) \times (2+1)}) \\
 27626 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7+6)) \times -((5^4)/(3+2))) + 1) \\
 27627 &:= (-9 + ((8+76) \times ((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\
 27628 &:= (9+8) \times (7+6) \times (5!/4!)^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 27629 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - ((7 - (6+5)) \times 4)^3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 27630 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times (4 + (3+2))) + 1) \\
 27631 &:= (((-9 + ((8 - ((7 - (6+5)) \times 4)^3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
 27632 &:= ((-9-8) + (((7 - (6-5)) \times 4)^3 \times 2) + 1) \\
 27633 &:= (((-98+76) \times -((5^4) + 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 27634 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6+5))) \times (4+321))) \\
 27635 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 - (6 \times (5+4))) \times (3 \times 2))) - 1) \\
 27636 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 27637 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 - (6 \times (5+4))) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\
 27638 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - ((7 - (6+5)) \times 4)^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 27639 &:= ((-9 \times (-8 + (-765 \times 4))) + (3^{2+1})) \\
 27640 &:= (-9 + (((8 - ((7 - (6+5)) \times 4)^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 27641 &:= (((-9-8) \times ((7 - ((6+5)^4))/(3^2))) - 1) \\
 27642 &:= ((9+8) \times ((7-6) + (5 \times (4 - (-321)))))) \\
 27643 &:= (((-9-8) \times ((7 - ((6+5)^4))/(3^2))) + 1) \\
 27644 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4))) - ((3+2) - 1)) \\
 27645 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (6-5)))) \times -(4^3)) - (2+1)) \\
 27646 &:= (((-9+8) + (((7 - (6-5)) \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 27647 &:= (((-9 - (((8+7) \times 6)/5)) \times -(4^{3+2})) - 1) \\
 27648 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5+4))) + (3 + (2+1)))))) \\
 27649 &:= (((9+87) \times (-6 \times (-5-43))) + 2) + (-1) \\
 27650 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) + 5) \times -(((4+3)^2) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27651 &:= ((1+2) - ((3+45) \times (6 \times (-7-89)))) \\
 27652 &:= ((1 + (2 \times ((3+4)^5))) - (67 \times 89)) \\
 27653 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 27654 &:= (((-((-((12 \times 34) - 5)) \times 67) - (8 + 9))) \\
 27655 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times (6 - (7 + 8)))) - 9)) \\
 27656 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8))) + 9)) \\
 27657 &:= -((((12^3) \times -4) \times (-5 - (6 - (7 + 8)))) - 9)) \\
 27658 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times (6 - (7 + 8)))) - 9)) \\
 27659 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3 \times ((4^5) \times (6 - (7 + 8)))) - 9)) \\
 27660 &:= (-12 \times (((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 27661 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5) - ((6 + 7) \times (8 - 9))) \\
 27662 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5) + ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) \\
 27663 &:= (-12 - (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 - (7 + 8))) - 9))) \\
 27664 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 \times (67 - 8)) + 9)) \\
 27665 &:= (-1 + (((((2 \times 34) + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 27666 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) \times -6 - (7 + 8)) + 9) \\
 27667 &:= (-12 + ((3 + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 89)) \\
 27668 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) - 6) \times (78 - 9)) \\
 27669 &:= (((((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times (78 - 9)) \\
 27670 &:= ((((-12 \times 34) - 5) \times -67) + (8 - 9)) \\
 27671 &:= ((-123 \times -(4 \times 56)) + (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 27672 &:= ((-123 - ((4^5) + 6)) \times (-7 + (-8 - 9))) \\
 27673 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 - (7 + 8))) - 9))) \\
 27674 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3 \times (4^5))) \times (6 - (7 + 8))) - 9)) \\
 27675 &:= (((1^2) - (-3 + 45)) \times ((-67 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 27676 &:= (-((1 + (23 + (4 \times 5)))) \times (-6 + (7 \times -89))) \\
 27677 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (3 \times (((4^5) \times (6 - (7 + 8))) - 9))) \\
 27678 &:= (-1 + (((((2^3) + 45) \times 6) - 7) \times 89)) \\
 27679 &:= (((((1 - 2) - 3)^4) - (567)) \times -89) \\
 27680 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 + (((56 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 27681 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) + ((6 + 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27682 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3^4) - (56 \times 7)) \times 89)) \\
 27683 &:= ((((-(-123) - 4) \times 5) - 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 27684 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) - (7 + 8)) \times 9) \\
 27685 &:= (1 + ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) + 6)) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 27686 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3!! - 4! - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 27687 &:= ((-123 \times -(4 \times 56)) + ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\
 27688 &:= ((((-12 \times 34) - 5) \times -67) + (8 + 9)) \\
 27689 &:= (((-1 - (2 - (3456 + 7))) \times 8) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27651 &:= (((-((9 + 87)) \times 6) \times (-5 - 43)) - (-2 + (-1))) \\
 27652 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 27653 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\
 27654 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 27655 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 27656 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(((6^5) \times 4)/(3^2)) + 1)) \\
 27657 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) - 4) \times -(3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 27658 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) - 4) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\
 27659 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - ((6 + 5)^4))/(3^2)) - 1)) \\
 27660 &:= (((-98 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) - 4) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 27661 &:= ((((-98 \times ((7 \times 6) + 5)) - 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 27662 &:= -9 + 8! - 7 + 6 - (5! + 4^3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 27663 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times (6 - (5 \times ((4^3) - 2)))) - 1) \\
 27664 &:= ((-98 + 7) \times (6 - (5 \times ((4^3) - 2 \times 1)))) \\
 27665 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - ((7 - (6 + 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 27666 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 6)) - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
 27667 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - ((7 - (6 + 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 27668 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6! - 5! + 4) - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 27669 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 - (6 - 5)))) \times -(4^3)) + 21) \\
 27670 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times 6)) \times 54) - (32 \times 1)) \\
 27671 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) + 5) \times (4 - (3 \times 21))) \\
 27672 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 27673 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\
 27674 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 27675 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 + (6 + 5))) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 27676 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 27677 &:= -((((9 \times 8) \times -(76)) \times 5) - (-((4 - 321)))) \\
 27678 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 27679 &:= -((((98 \times 7) + 6) \times ((5 - 43) - 2)) + 1) \\
 27680 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -(5 \times ((4 + (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\
 27681 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 27682 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 27683 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 27684 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + (7 \times 6)) - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\
 27685 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\
 27686 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 27687 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (((6^5) \times 4)/(3^2))) - 1))) \\
 27688 &:= (-9 + 8 - 7) \times (6! + 5 - 4^3) + (2 + 1)!! \\
 27689 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times -(5 + ((4^3) + 2))) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27690 &:= ((-1-2) + (((3 \times 4^5) + ((6+7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27691 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times 4^5) + ((6+7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27692 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4^5 + 6))) - (7+8)) \times 9)) \\ 27693 &:= (((-1 \times -(-2)) + ((3456 + 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 27694 &:= (((1-2) - (((-3456) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 27695 &:= (((1^2) \times (3456 + 7)) \times 8) - 9) \\ 27696 &:= (((1^2) + ((3456 + 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 27697 &:= (((12 + (3456 - 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 27698 &:= (-12 + (34 \times (5 + (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\ 27699 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (4 - ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27700 &:= (-1 \times ((2+3) \times (4 - ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27701 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times 4^5) - ((6-7) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27702 &:= ((-1-2) \times -((3^4) \times ((5 \times (6 + (7+8))) + 9))) \\ 27703 &:= ((-1+2) - (((3 \times 4^5) + 6) \times ((7-8) \times 9))) \\ 27704 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3 \times 4^5) + 6) \times ((7-8) \times 9))) \\ 27705 &:= (((-1+2) - (3456 + 7)) \times -8) + 9) \\ 27706 &:= (1+2) \times (3^4 \times (5! - 6) + 7) - (8+9) \\ 27707 &:= ((-1-2) + (34 \times (5 + (6 \times ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\ 27708 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (34 \times (5 - ((-6 \times (7+8)) \times 9)))) \\ 27709 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times 4^5) + (6 - (7-8))) \times 9)) \\ 27710 &:= (((12^3) - (((4 \times 5) - 6) \times 7)) \times (8+9)) \\ 27711 &:= (((-1 \times -(-2)) + ((3456 + 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 27712 &:= (((1-2) - (((-3456) - 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 27713 &:= (((1^2) \times (3456 + 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 27714 &:= (((1^2) + ((3456 + 7) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 27715 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67))) - 89) \\ 27716 &:= ((1+2) + (((3456 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 27717 &:= (-12 - ((345 + 6) \times (-7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27718 &:= -((1 \times (2 + (((3+4) - (-56 \times -7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27719 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3+4)) \times ((5+6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27720 &:= ((12 - (3+4)) \times ((-5-6) \times -(((7 \times 8) \times 9))) \\ 27721 &:= ((-1+2) + (((3 \times 4^5) - ((6-7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27722 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times 4^5) - ((6-7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27723 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times ((4^5) + 6) - (78+9)) \\ 27724 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times 4^5) - ((6+7) - 89) \\ 27725 &:= (12 + (((3456 + 7) \times 8) + 9)) \\ 27726 &:= (-1 + ((234 + (5-6)) \times (7 \times (8+9)))) \\ 27727 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 \times (8+9))) \\ 27728 &:= (-1 + (((-2 - (3456 + 7)) \times -8) + 9)) \\ 27729 &:= ((12 + (345 - 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27690 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -6 \times ((5 \times ((4+3) \times 2)) + 1))) \\ 27691 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times -5 + ((4^3) + 2))) + 1) \\ 27692 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4)) + (3+2))) - 1) \\ 27693 &:= ((-9 - ((8+7) \times (6 - ((5^4) - 3)))) \times (2+1)) \\ 27694 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (((6^5) \times 4)/(3^2)))) - 1) \\ 27695 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (((6^5) \times 4)/(3 \times (2+1)))))) \\ 27696 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + (((6^5) \times 4)/(3^2)))) + 1)) \\ 27697 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times 6)) \times 54) - ((3+2) \times 1)) \\ 27698 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times 6)) \times 54) - ((3+2) - 1)) \\ 27699 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6+5)))) + 4) \times -3 + 2) - 1) \\ 27700 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6+5)))) + 4) \times -((3+2) \times 1)) \\ 27701 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6+5)))) + 4) \times -3 + 2) + 1) \\ 27702 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times (5+4)) \times -3^{2+1}) \\ 27703 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 27704 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times ((4^3) - 2)) + 1)) \\ 27705 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\ 27706 &:= ((-98/7) \times -(((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\ 27707 &:= (((-9 + (87 \times 6)) \times 54) + ((3+2) \times 1)) \\ 27708 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (32+1)))) \\ 27709 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + ((6+5)^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 27710 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (((6+5) - 4) \times 3^2)))) - 1) \\ 27711 &:= (((9 - (87 \times 6)) \times -54) - (-3 \times ((2+1)))) \\ 27712 &:= ((9 + (-876) + (5-4)) \times (32 \times (-1))) \\ 27713 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + (((6^5) \times 4)/(3^2)))) \times -1) \\ 27714 &:= (((-9 \times (8+7)) + 6) \times -5 \times 43) - 21) \\ 27715 &:= (9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6+5) + (4! + 3!)^{2+1} \\ 27716 &:= (((-9 \times 87) + ((6+5)^4) \times (3 - (2-1))) \\ 27717 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 4)) + 321) \\ 27718 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (54+3))^2) + 1))) \\ 27719 &:= ((-9 \times (((8+7) - 6) - (5^4)) \times (3+2)) - 1) \\ 27720 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 \times (5+4)) + (3/(2+1)))) \\ 27721 &:= ((-9 \times (((8+7) - 6) - (5^4)) \times (3+2)) + 1) \\ 27722 &:= (((-9 \times 87) + (((6+5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 27723 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + (((6+5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\ 27724 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times ((4^3) - 2)) - 1)) \\ 27725 &:= ((-9 + ((8+7) \times (((6-5) \times 43)^2)) - 1) \\ 27726 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (((6-5) \times 43)^2 \times 1))) \\ 27727 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 + (5 \times 4)) \times (3^2)) - 1)) \\ 27728 &:= ((-9 - (8 - (7-6))) \times -5 + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})) \\ 27729 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3) \times (2+1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27730 &:= ((1 + ((-2 - (3456 + 7)) \times -8)) + 9) \\ 27731 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27732 &:= (-((123 \times 4) - (56 \times ((-7 \times 8) \times 9))) \\ 27733 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times 67)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 27734 &:= ((1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 27735 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -(5 \times ((6 \times 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\ 27736 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) + (6 - (7 - 89))) \\ 27737 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4^5)))) - ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 27738 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4^5))) - (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 27739 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27740 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27741 &:= ((-1 - 23) - (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27742 &:= (-1 \times (23 + (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27743 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 \times (((5 + 6) \times 78) + 9)))) \\ 27744 &:= -((((1 - 234) - 56) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 27745 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27746 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4^5)))) - (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 27747 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times -9) \\ 27748 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27749 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27750 &:= ((-12 - 3) - (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27751 &:= (1 \times 2)^{3!+4+5} + 6 - 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 27752 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (-3 - 4 + 5^6 - 7)) \times 8/9 \\ 27753 &:= ((1 - (((-2^3) - 45) \times 6)) \times (78 + 9)) \\ 27754 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!!/4 \times (5 + 6) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27755 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times (((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 27756 &:= ((-12 \times 3) \times (((-4 + 56) \times (-7 - 8)) + 9)) \\ 27757 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) + (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27758 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) + (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27759 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27760 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) + (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27761 &:= (((-12 \times (3 \times 45)) - ((6 + 7))) \times (-8 - 9)) \\ 27762 &:= ((-12 + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) + 8))) - 9) \\ 27763 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 27764 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + ((6 + 7) - 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 27765 &:= (((12 \times 3)/4) \times -5) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)) \\ 27766 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 27767 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 + 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 89)))) \\ 27768 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((3 + (4 + 5)) \times ((6 + 7) \times 89)))) \\ 27769 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) - (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27730 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((76 \times 5) + 4))) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\ 27731 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (-7 + 6!)) \times 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 27732 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4))))^3) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27733 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3) \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 27734 &:= (-98 \times -(((7 \times (6 \times (5 \times 4)))/3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 27735 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -(((4^3) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27736 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times 43)) + (2 - 1)) \\ 27737 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times 43)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27738 &:= ((-9 - ((87 - 6) \times 5)) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 27739 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 27740 &:= (((9 + 8) - 7) \times ((-65) \times -(43)) - (21)) \\ 27741 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 27742 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) - 5) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 27743 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 \times -5) + (4^3))^2)) - 1) \\ 27744 &:= ((98 - (-765) - 4) \times ((32 \times 1))) \\ 27745 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 \times -5) + (4^3))^2)) + 1) \\ 27746 &:= ((-98 - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3 \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 27747 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) - 3)))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 27748 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 765) \times 4)) \times (3^2)) + 1) \\ 27749 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + 43)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27750 &:= (-9 - ((8 - ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4))))^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27751 &:= (((-9876 + (5^4)) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 27752 &:= (((-9876 + (5^4)) \times -3) - (2 - 1)) \\ 27753 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times 7) + 6) \times 5)) \times -((43 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 27754 &:= 9 + (876 - 5 - 4) \times 32 + 1 \\ 27755 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 27756 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 + 6))^{(5+4)/3})) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27757 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5 + 4)^3)))/2)) + 1) \\ 27758 &:= ((9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 - 5) + (43^2)))) - 1) \\ 27759 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (54 + 3))^2) - 1))) \\ 27760 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) + (-((43^2) - 1)) \\ 27761 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (76 - 5)) \times (4 - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 27762 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) - ((6 - 5) \times 4))^3) \times 21) \\ 27763 &:= (9 + ((87 \times ((6 \times 54) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 27764 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 27765 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 27766 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4))))^3) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27767 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times -((6 \times (5 - (4^3)))) - 2) - 1) \\ 27768 &:= ((9 - 87) \times ((6 \times -(54)) + (32 \times -(1)))) \\ 27769 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times -((6 \times (5 - (4^3)))) - 2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27770 &:= (-1 \times -((2+3) - (45 \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))))) \\ 27771 &:= (-12 + (3 \times (((4^5) + ((6+7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27772 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) + 8))) - 9) \\ 27773 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7)) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27774 &:= (((-1+2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + ((6+7) - 8)))) \times -9) \\ 27775 &:= (((-1+2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) + 8))) - 9) \\ 27776 &:= (((-1 + (2+3)) \times 4) \times (((5^6) + (7-8))/9)) \\ 27777 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times (8+9)))) \\ 27778 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (((3 \times (45 \times 6)) + 7) \times (8+9)))) \\ 27779 &:= (((1+2)^3) \times (4^5)) + ((6 \times 7) + 89) \\ 27780 &:= (-12 - (((3^4) \times ((5 \times -67) - 8)) - 9)) \\ 27781 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + ((6+7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27782 &:= (-1 + ((-2 + 345) \times ((6 \times (7+8)) - 9))) \\ 27783 &:= ((12 + (3 \times 45)) \times ((-6 - (7+8)) \times -9)) \\ 27784 &:= -((-1 - ((-2 + 345) \times ((6 \times (7+8)) - 9))) \\ 27785 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + ((6+7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27786 &:= (-12 - ((345 - 6) \times (7 - 89))) \\ 27787 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67))) - (8+9)) \\ 27788 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times 67)) - (8+9)) \\ 27789 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7-8)) \times 9)) \\ 27790 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) + 8)) + 9)) \\ 27791 &:= (-1 + (((2^3) + ((4+5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 27792 &:= (((-1+2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + ((6+7) - 8)))) \times 9) \\ 27793 &:= ((-1+2) + (((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) + 8)) + 9)) \\ 27794 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + 45) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 27795 &:= (((12 + 34) + 5) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 27796 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((345 - 6) \times (7 - 89)))) \\ 27797 &:= ((1 - (2^3)) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\ 27798 &:= (((12 - 345) - 6) \times -((-7 + 89))) \\ 27799 &:= ((-1+2) - ((345 - 6) \times (7 - 89))) \\ 27800 &:= (-1 - (((-2 - 34) + ((5^{6+7-8}))) \times -9)) \\ 27801 &:= ((1+2) - ((345 - 6) \times (7 - 89))) \\ 27802 &:= ((-1+2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7-8)) \times 9)) \\ 27803 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7-8)) \times 9)) \\ 27804 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (67 \times (8-9)))))) \\ 27805 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times (67 \times (8-9)))) \\ 27806 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times 67)) - (8-9)) \\ 27807 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 27808 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 \times ((5+6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27770 &:= -9 - 8 - 7 \times (6 + 5! - 4^{3!}) - 2 - 1 \\ 27771 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 65) \times 43))) - 21) \\ 27772 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times 65) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 27773 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (54 + 3))^2) + 1))) \\ 27774 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 + 6))^{(5+4)/3}) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27775 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + (54 + 3))^2) - 1))) \\ 27776 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 + (54 + 3))^2) - 1)) \\ 27777 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -(5 + ((4^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 27778 &:= (-9 - 8!/7!) \times (6 + (5! - (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)) \\ 27779 &:= (-9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!)) \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 27780 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 27781 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (54 + 3))^2))) - 1) \\ 27782 &:= ((9 \times 87) + (((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) + (-1))) \\ 27783 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + ((7 - 6)^5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 27784 &:= ((-9 \times -87) + (((6 \times 5)^{4-3+2}) + 1)) \\ 27785 &:= (9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((65 + 432) - 1)))) \\ 27786 &:= (((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 27787 &:= (-(((98 \times 7) + 65) \times ((-4 - 32) - 1))) \\ 27788 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! + 5!)) \times 4 + (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 27789 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\ 27790 &:= (((-9 \times 87) - (6 + 5)) \times -((4 \times (3^2)) - 1)) \\ 27791 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 27792 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times ((4 + 3) - 2))) + 1))) \\ 27793 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - (6 - 5)) \times 4)^3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 27794 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 + 65) \times 43))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27795 &:= (((-9 \times (-8 - (765)))) \times 4) - ((32 + 1))) \\ 27796 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 765) \times 4)) - (32 \times 1)) \\ 27797 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 765) \times 4)) - (32 - 1)) \\ 27798 &:= (-9 + ((8 + ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 27799 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 765) \times 4) - 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 27800 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 27801 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 27802 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 27803 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 765) \times 4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 27804 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) + 1)) \\ 27805 &:= ((-98 \times -((76 - 5) \times 4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 27806 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7! - 6)/(5 + 4)/3 - (2 + 1)!! \\ 27807 &:= ((9 + (8 + 76)) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + -(21))) \\ 27808 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) \times -((4^3)/(2 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27809 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times ((3 + (4 \times 5)) \times 67)) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 27810 &:= (((1 - 2) - 34) - (-5^{6+7-8})) \times 9) \\
 27811 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 27812 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (3 \times (((4^5) + 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 27813 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 27814 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!^4 + 5! \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 27815 &:= -(1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4^5 + 6^7 / 8 + 9 \\
 27816 &:= ((-12 \times 34) - ((-56 \times (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27817 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27818 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 27819 &:= ((12 - 3) \times (4 - ((-(5 \times 67)) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 27820 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27821 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) - (7 - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 27822 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times 67)) + (8 + 9) \\
 27823 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
 27824 &:= ((1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
 27825 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27826 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 789)))) \\
 27827 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 6))) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9)) \\
 27828 &:= (1 - (-2 + (((-3 - 4) \times -5) \times -((6 + 789)))) \\
 27829 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 27830 &:= (-1 \times -(23 \times (4 + ((56 + 78) \times 9)))) \\
 27831 &:= (1 + (23 \times (4 + ((56 + 78) \times 9)))) \\
 27832 &:= (1 \times 2 \times (34 + 5^6) - 7) \times 8 / 9 \\
 27833 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (-4567) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 27834 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27835 &:= (1 - (-2 \times (-3 \times (-4567) + (-8 \times 9)))) \\
 27836 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) \times 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9) \\
 27837 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 27838 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27839 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 27840 &:= (((1 \times -2) - ((3 + 45) \times 6)) \times (-7 - 89)) \\
 27841 &:= (1 - ((-234 - 56) \times (7 + 89))) \\
 27842 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! - 4) - 5) \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9 \\
 27843 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((34 + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) \times (-8 - 9)))) \\
 27844 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((34 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 27845 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 27846 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) / 5)) \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 27847 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((34 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27809 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 - 6)) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 27810 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 + 6))^{(5+4)/3})) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 27811 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 - 6)) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 27812 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 765)) + 4) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 27813 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + ((6 \times 543) / 2))) + 1) \\
 27814 &:= ((-98 \times -((76 - 5) \times 4)) + (3 - 21)) \\
 27815 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 27816 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 27817 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 27818 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - (7 \times 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 27819 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 27820 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 765) \times (-4 - 32)) - (-(-1)))) \\
 27821 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 765) \times 4)) - (3 \times 2) + 1) \\
 27822 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + 6)) - ((5 \times 4)^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 27823 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (76 - 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\
 27824 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - (3^{2+1})))) \\
 27825 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 27826 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 27827 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\
 27828 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) / 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 27829 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 27830 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 27831 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 27832 &:= (-98 \times -((7 \times (6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 27833 &:= ((-98 \times -((76 - 5) \times 4)) + (3 / (2 + 1))) \\
 27834 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 27835 &:= ((-98 \times -((76 - 5) \times 4)) + (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 27836 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) / 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 27837 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 27838 &:= (((-9 \times ((-8 - 765) \times 4)) + ((3^2))) - (-1)) \\
 27839 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times -5) + (4^3))^2 \times 1)) \\
 27840 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 \times (65 + 432) - 1 \\
 27841 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 \times (65 + 432) \times 1 \\
 27842 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 \times (65 + 432) + 1 \\
 27843 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 27844 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 27845 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 27846 &:= (-((98 - 7) \times ((6 + 5) + (4 - (321)))) \\
 27847 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27848 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((34 + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) & 27848 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 27849 &:= ((1 + 2) + (34 \times ((5 \times 6) + 789))) & 27849 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\
 27850 &:= (((-12 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -67) - 89) & 27850 &:= ((-98 \times -((76 - 5) \times 4)) - (3 - 21)) \\
 27851 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) & 27851 &:= (-9 + 8) \times 7 + 6! \times 5 \times 4! / 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 27852 &:= (12 \times (((3 - (4 - (5^6))) / 7) + 89)) & 27852 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) / 3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 27853 &:= ((1 - (2^3)) \times -((4 + (5 \times (6 + 789)))))) & 27853 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) / 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 27854 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 + (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) & 27854 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 27855 &:= (((((12 + 3) - 456) \times 7) - 8) \times -9) & 27855 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 27856 &:= (-1 - ((((-2 \times 3) \times (45 + 6)) - 7) \times 89)) & 27856 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 27857 &:= (-1 \times ((((-2 \times 3) \times (45 + 6)) - 7) \times 89)) & 27857 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) / 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 27858 &:= (12 + (34 \times ((5 \times 6) + 789))) & 27858 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) / 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 27859 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3!! - 4!) \times 5! / 6 - 7 + 8 + 9) & 27859 &:= (-98 - ((7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) + 1)) \\
 27860 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (-3!! + 4!)) \times 5 \times (6 + 7 - 8 - 9) & 27860 &:= ((9 \times ((8 + (765)) \times -(-4))) - ((32 \times (-1)))) \\
 27861 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((345 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) & 27861 &:= ((-((9 \times (-8 - (765)))) \times 4) + ((32 + 1))) \\
 27862 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) & 27862 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 27863 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times 7))) \times -(8 + 9)) & 27863 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) - ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 27864 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times (5 - ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) & 27864 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) - 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 27865 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) & 27865 &:= ((-98) \times -((76 - 5) \times 4)) - ((32 + 1))) \\
 27866 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9))) & 27866 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3))) - 2) \times -1) \\
 27867 &:= (((-12 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -67) - (8 \times 9)) & 27867 &:= (-98 - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2) + 1))) \\
 27868 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3) + 4! \times (5! - 6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 & 27868 &:= (9 - 8 \times 7) \times (-6! + 5! + 4 + 3) - 2 - 1 \\
 27869 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)) & 27869 &:= (9 + 8 \times (-7 + 6!)) \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 27870 &:= (1 + (2 + 3!)) \times (-4 + 5!) \times (6 + 7 + 8 + 9) & 27870 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((76 + 5) \times 43) + 2))) - 1) \\
 27871 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -67) + (8 - 9)) & 27871 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 43)^2)) - 1) \\
 27872 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) & 27872 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) / 3) - 2) - 1) \\
 27873 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times 9) & 27873 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3)) \times -2 + 1)) \\
 27874 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) & 27874 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) / 3) - 2) + 1) \\
 27875 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (4 \times ((56 \times 7) - 89)))) & 27875 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 27876 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 \times 9))) & 27876 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
 27877 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 \times 67)) + (8 \times 9)) & 27877 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 27878 &:= (1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 \times 9))) & 27878 &:= -9 - 8 + 7 + 6 \times (5! + 4!^3) / (2 + 1) \\
 27879 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) + 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) & 27879 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 27880 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) & 27880 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 27881 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) - ((6 - 7) \times 8)))) \times 9)) & 27881 &:= (((((9 \times 8) \times -7) - 65) \times (((4 + 3)^2) \times -1))) \\
 27882 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times -9) & 27882 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 27883 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((345 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 27883 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 27884 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3!! - 4!)) \times 5! / 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 & 27884 &:= 9 \times 876 + 5^4 \times 32 \times 1 \\
 27885 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times 4)) \times -(56 + 789)) & 27885 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 27886 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (345 + 6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) & 27886 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / (2 \times 1))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27887 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 \times (5 + 6)))) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 27888 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 27889 &:= (-1 - 2 + 34 \times 5)^{-6+7-8+9}; \\ 27890 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) + ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27891 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) - (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 27892 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 27893 &:= ((-1 - ((-2 - ((3^4))) \times (5 \times 67))) + 89) \\ 27894 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8))) - 9) \\ 27895 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)^4) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8))) - 9) \\ 27896 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4 \times (5 \times 67)) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 27897 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) + 5)) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 27898 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4^5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 27899 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 + 45)) \times (6 + (-7 \times -8))) \times 9)) \\ 27900 &:= (((12 + 3) \times -4) \times -5) \times (6 + (78 + 9)) \\ 27901 &:= (1 - (((2 + 34) - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27902 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4^5) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27903 &:= ((-12 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 27904 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)^4) \times ((5 \times 6) + (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 27905 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4^5) \times (6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 27906 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 + ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27907 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 + ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27908 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 27909 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - (7 + 8)))) \times -9) \\ 27910 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 27911 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 + ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\ 27912 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + 8)) + 9)) \\ 27913 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)^4) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times 8))) + 9) \\ 27914 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times 78) + 9)) \\ 27915 &:= ((12 + 3) \times -(((4 \times (5 - (6 \times 78))) - 9))) \\ 27916 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((34 - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 27917 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 27918 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 + (4^5)) + (6 - 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 27919 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((34 - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 27920 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((34 - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 27921 &:= ((-12 - 3) - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 27922 &:= ((-12 - 34) \times -(((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 27923 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! - 4) \times (5! + (6 - 7 - 8) \times 9) \\ 27924 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 27925 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 27926 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27887 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 + 5) \times (4^3))/2) + 1)) \\ 27888 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 27889 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times (4 + 3))))^2 \times 1) \\ 27890 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 27891 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (((5^4) - 3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 27892 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 27893 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3)/2) + 1))) \\ 27894 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 - (5^4)) \times 3) - 2))) \times -1) \\ 27895 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + 6)) + 5) \times (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 27896 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (76)) + 5) \times ((4 - 321)) \\ 27897 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3))) - 21) \\ 27898 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - ((7 - (6 + 54)) \times 3))^2)) \times -1) \\ 27899 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 27900 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 27901 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 27902 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + ((6^{5-4+3}) \times 21)) \\ 27903 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 27904 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + (6 \times 5))) \times -(4^{3+2-1})) \\ 27905 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 27906 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) - 2)) + 1))) \\ 27907 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3))/(2 \times 1)))) \\ 27908 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3))/2)) - 1)) \\ 27909 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 27910 &:= (-98) + (-7 + (65 \times (432 - 1))) \\ 27911 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 - (4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\ 27912 &:= ((9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4 \times 32))) - 1) \\ 27913 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) \times 2))) \times -1) \\ 27914 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3))/2) - 1))) \\ 27915 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 27916 &:= (((-98 \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 27917 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\ 27918 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times (3 + 2))) - 1))) \\ 27919 &:= ((-9 \times -(((87 \times 6) - 5) \times (4 \times 3))/2) + 1) \\ 27920 &:= (-9 + ((87 \times ((6 \times 54) - 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 27921 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 27922 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 27923 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (4^3))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 27924 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3))/2)) + 1)) \\ 27925 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 27926 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times ((65 + 4) \times 3)) - 2)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 27927** := $(((-12 \times (3 - (-4 \times (5 + 67)))) \times -8) - 9)$
- 27928** := $((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) - 8) \times 9))$
- 27929** := $((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) - 8) \times 9))$
- 27930** := $((-1 - (2 + 3)) - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))$
- 27931** := $((-1 \times ((2 + 3) + ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))))$
- 27932** := $((-1 - (((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times 78) - 9))$
- 27933** := $((-12 + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7 + 8)) \times 9))$
- 27934** := $(((-1 + 2) - 3) - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))$
- 27935** := $((1 \times 2) - 3) - ((4 + (-56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))$
- 27936** := $((1 \times 2) - 3) \times ((4 + (-56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))$
- 27937** := $(((-1 + 2)^3) - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))$
- 27938** := $(((-12 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -67) + (8 - 9))$
- 27939** := $((-1 + 2) \times (3 - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))))$
- 27940** := $((-1 + (2 + 3)) - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))$
- 27941** := $((-1 \times -((2 + 3) - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))))$
- 27942** := $((1 \times 2) \times 3) - ((4 + (-56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))$
- 27943** := $((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7 + 8)) \times 9))$
- 27944** := $((-1 - (((2 + 3) \times 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9))$
- 27945** := $(((-12 \times (3 - (-4 \times (5 + 67)))) \times -8) + 9)$
- 27946** := $((-((-1 - 2)) - ((3^4) - ((56 \times 7)))) \times 89)$
- 27947** := $((-(-1) - (-2 \times ((-(-34 \times 5)) + (-6 - 7)) \times 89)))$
- 27948** := $((-12 \times -((3 + 4)^{5+6-7}) - (8 \times 9))$
- 27949** := $((1 + (2 \times (34 \times ((5 \times (6 + 78)) - 9))))$
- 27950** := $((1 + 2 \times 3!) \times (4! \times 5! - 6! + 7 - 8 - 9))$
- 27951** := $((12 - (-3)) - (((-4 + (56 \times 7)) \times -8) \times 9))$
- 27952** := $((1 \times -2) - (((-3 \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9))$
- 27953** := $((1 - 2) - (((-3 \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9))$
- 27954** := $(((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7 + 8))) \times 9)$
- 27955** := $((-1 - (-2 + (((-3 \times (4^5)) - ((6 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9)))$
- 27956** := $(((-(-12) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) + (8 + 9))$
- 27957** := $((12 - (345 \times (6 - (78 + 9))))$
- 27958** := $((-1 + 23) - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))$
- 27959** := $((-1 \times -(23 - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))))$
- 27960** := $(((-1 - (234 \times 5)) + 6) \times (-((7 + 8)) - 9))$
- 27961** := $((-1 \times (2 - ((3 - ((4 - (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9)))$
- 27962** := $(((-1 \times -2) + ((345 - 6))) \times (-7 - (-89)))$
- 27963** := $((-(-1) + ((-(-((2 + 345))) - 6) \times (-7 + 89)))$
- 27964** := $((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - (5 \times 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))$
- 27965** := $(((-(-1 - (-2 - 34)) \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (-8 - 9))))$
- 27927** := $((((9 \times 87) \times 6) / 54) \times (321))$
- 27928** := $(((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5^4)) \times -((3^2) - 1))$
- 27929** := $((98 \times 76) + (5 \times (4^{3 \times 2})) + (-(-1)))$
- 27930** := $((-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))$
- 27931** := $(((((9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)$
- 27932** := $((((-98 \times (76 \times 5)) / 4) \times -3) + (2 \times 1))$
- 27933** := $((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4^3))) - (2 + 1))$
- 27934** := $((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2) - 1)))$
- 27935** := $((-9 \times ((8 + (7 + 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)$
- 27936** := $((-9 \times ((8 + (7 + 6)) - (5^{4+3/(2+1)})))$
- 27937** := $((-9 \times ((8 + (7 + 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)$
- 27938** := $((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4^3))) + (2 \times 1))$
- 27939** := $((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4^3))) + (2 + 1))$
- 27940** := $((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) + 1))$
- 27941** := $((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / (2 \times 1))))$
- 27942** := $((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) - 1))$
- 27943** := $((-98 + (7 \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2)))) - 1)$
- 27944** := $(((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 + 4))) \times -(3^2)) - 1)$
- 27945** := $((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) - (2 + 1))))$
- 27946** := $(((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 + 4))) \times -(3^2)) + 1)$
- 27947** := $((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times ((65 + 4) \times 3))) + (2 \times 1))$
- 27948** := $((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2) + 1)))$
- 27949** := $((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) / (2 \times 1))))$
- 27950** := $((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2) - 1)))$
- 27951** := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2) - 1))$
- 27952** := $(((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times -65) \times 43) + (2 \times 1))$
- 27953** := $((-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + ((4^3) + 2))) - 1)$
- 27954** := $((-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 + 4)) \times (3^2)) + 1))$
- 27955** := $((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) / 2) + 1)))$
- 27956** := $((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) + 1))$
- 27957** := $((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / (2 \times 1))))$
- 27958** := $(((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / (2 \times 1))))$
- 27959** := $((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) + 1)$
- 27960** := $((-9 + ((8 \times (76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3) \times 2))) + 1))$
- 27961** := $((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) / 2)) + 1))$
- 27962** := $((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) / (2 \times 1))))$
- 27963** := $((-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)))$
- 27964** := $((-9 + 8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2) + 1)))$
- 27965** := $(((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -((5 \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))$

$$\begin{aligned} 28005 &:= (-12 - (((3 \times 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28006 &:= ((-123 + 4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28007 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 34) \times (-5 - 6)) + 7) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 28008 &:= (((12 - 3) \times -4) \times ((5 + 6) - 789)) \\ 28009 &:= (((-12 + ((3 \times 4^5))/6)) \times (7 \times 8) + 9) \\ 28010 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4)^5))/6) \times (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 28011 &:= (((-(-12) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times 67) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 28012 &:= ((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 28013 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (((4 \times 5) - 6) \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 28014 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\ 28015 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 28016 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times -((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 28017 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4)) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times -9) \\ 28018 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3 \times 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28019 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3 \times 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28020 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 \times 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28021 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!! + (4! \times 5! - 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28022 &:= (1 + 2 + ((3 + 4)^5 + 6) \times (7 + 8))/9 \\ 28023 &:= (-12 + (((34 + 5) + 6) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 28024 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 28025 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((45 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 28026 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3 + ((4^5) + 6))) - (7 + 8)) \times -9) \\ 28027 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 \times (((4 + 56) \times 78) - 9)))) \\ 28028 &:= (((-12 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -67) + 89) \\ 28029 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times 4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28030 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! + 4^5 \times (6 + 7) - 8 - 9) \\ 28031 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 \times (6! - 7 - 8 - 9)) \\ 28032 &:= (-12 - ((3^4) - ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 28033 &:= (-1 \times ((23 \times 4) + (((5^{6+7-8}) \times -9)))) \\ 28034 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3) + (45 - 6)) \times 7) \times 89) \\ 28035 &:= (1 \times (((2 \times 3) + (45 - 6)) \times 7) \times 89) \\ 28036 &:= (1 + (((2 \times 3) + (45 - 6)) \times 7) \times 89) \\ 28037 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times -4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28038 &:= (-123 + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28039 &:= -1 + (2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6! - 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 28040 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times -((5 - 6) + (78 \times 9))) \\ 28041 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) - ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 28042 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) - ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 28043 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28005 &:= ((-((9 + 8)) + 7) - (65 \times -(((432 - 1)))))) \\ 28006 &:= (-9 + ((8 - 7) \times (65 \times (432 - 1)))) \\ 28007 &:= (-(((9 \times 8) + (((-7 - 6) \times 5) \times 432)) + 1)) \\ 28008 &:= ((9 \times 8) \times (((7 \times 65) - (4^3)) - ((2 \times 1)))) \\ 28009 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28010 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (65 \times (432 + 1))) \\ 28011 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1)))))) \\ 28012 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7) \times (6! - 5! - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1)) \\ 28013 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)) / 2) - 1))) \\ 28014 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (((5^4) \times 3) - 2)))) \times -1) \\ 28015 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6^{(5+4)/3}) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 28016 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\ 28017 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 28018 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2)) - 1))) \\ 28019 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) - 1) \\ 28020 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3) / (2 \times 1)))) \\ 28021 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3) / (2 \times 1))) \\ 28022 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3) / 2)) + 1) \\ 28023 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 28024 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 28025 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) + (2 - 1))) \\ 28026 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))))) \\ 28027 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 - 1))) \\ 28028 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 28029 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) - (2 + 1))) \\ 28030 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / (2 \times 1)))))) \\ 28031 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times (6 - (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) - 1)) \\ 28032 &:= (-((9 + 87)) \times -((((6 \times 54) - 32) \times 1))) \\ 28033 &:= (((-98 + 7) - 6) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 28034 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2)) - 1))) \\ 28035 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) - 6) - (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 28036 &:= (((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -((5^4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 28037 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 28038 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4)))) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 28039 &:= (((9 + 8) + 7) + ((65 \times (432 - 1)))) \\ 28040 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2)))) - 1) \\ 28041 &:= (-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))))) \\ 28042 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) + 2)) \times -1) \\ 28043 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) - 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28044 &:= ((1 + ((23 - 4) - ((56 \times 7) \times -8))) \times -9) \\
 28045 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) - ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\
 28046 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3^4) - ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\
 28047 &:= (12 + ((34 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 89))) \\
 28048 &:= (1 + 2) \times ((3 + 4)! - 5 - 6! + 7!) - 8 - 9 \\
 28049 &:= ((1 - (-2 \times 3)) \times ((4^{5-6+7}) - 89)) \\
 28050 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) \times -(6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28051 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 78))) - 9)))) \\
 28052 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28053 &:= ((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 - (7 + 8))) \times -9) \\
 28054 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 78))) - 9))) \\
 28055 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 28056 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times (4 - (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28057 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times 34)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\
 28058 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 34)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\
 28059 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3 + 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 28060 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3 + 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 28061 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6 - (7 - 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28062 &:= -(((1 \times 2) \times (3^4)) + (-56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28063 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3 + 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 28064 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - (((3 + 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 28065 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times 4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\
 28066 &:= ((-1 \times 23) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 28067 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4 - 5})) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28068 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28069 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28070 &:= (-1 - (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - 6) \times ((7 - 8) \times 9))) \\
 28071 &:= (-(((12 + 3) + 45) \times (-6 \times 78)) - 9) \\
 28072 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28073 &:= (-((-1 + (2 \times 34))) \times (-5 + (-6 \times (78 - 9)))) \\
 28074 &:= ((-12 - 3) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 28075 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 28076 &:= 12 \times (-3 + 45 \times 6 \times 78) / 9 \\
 28077 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times 78)))) + 9) \\
 28078 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!! \times (4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 28079 &:= ((-12 - 34) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\
 28080 &:= (((12/3) \times 4) - 56) \times -((78 \times 9)) \\
 28081 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) + ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9))) \\
 28082 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 28083 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28044 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 28045 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) - 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 28046 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3)))) - 2) \times -1) \\
 28047 &:= (-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times 3))) - 21)) \\
 28048 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2) + 1))) \\
 28049 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 28050 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -(5 + (((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 28051 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) + 2)) + 1) \\
 28052 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 28053 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 - 6) \times 5)^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
 28054 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 28055 &:= (((-9 - 8) - 7) + (((65 \times 432) - 1))) \\
 28056 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 28057 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) + 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 28058 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (((6 - ((5 \times 4)^3)) / 2) - 1))) \\
 28059 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2)))) \times -1) \\
 28060 &:= ((9 + 8) + ((7 \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) + 1)) \\
 28061 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 - 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 28062 &:= (-9 \times ((8 - (7 - 6)) - (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
 28063 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 - 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 28064 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 432)) + 1)) \\
 28065 &:= ((-98/7) + (((65 \times 432) - 1))) \\
 28066 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times 432) - 1))) \\
 28067 &:= -((((98/7) - (65 \times 432)) - 1)) \\
 28068 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\
 28069 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) + (5 \times 4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 28070 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) \times 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 28071 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 28072 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((65 \times 432 \times 1))) \\
 28073 &:= (9 + (-8 + ((-7 + ((65 \times 432) - 1)))) \\
 28074 &:= (9 + (-8 + ((-7 + (65 \times (432 \times 1)))) \\
 28075 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 65) \times -(4^3)) - 21) \\
 28076 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times 432) + 1))) \\
 28077 &:= ((-98 - ((7 \times -(6 - (5 + 4)))^3)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 28078 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28079 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - (7 + 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 28080 &:= (((9 \times 8) - 7) \times ((6 \times (54 - (3 - 21)))) \\
 28081 &:= -((((9 - 8) \times (((-7 - 6) \times 5) \times 432) - 1))) \\
 28082 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 28083 &:= (((-9 + 87) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) + (2 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28084 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - (3 - 4))^5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 28085 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28086 &:= ((1 \times -2) \times (-3 + ((4^5) - (67 \times -8)) \times -9))) \\ 28087 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28088 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) \times 4) + (5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28089 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (-3 \times 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28090 &:= (((-1 + 2)^3) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28091 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times -34) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28092 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28093 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28094 &:= ((-1 \times -(2 + 3)) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28095 &:= ((-1 \times -(2 \times 3)) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28096 &:= ((-1 + (2^3)) - ((4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28097 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 - 4)) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28098 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 28099 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 28100 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((3 - 45) \times (678 - 9))) \\ 28101 &:= (((-1 + (-2 \times (-3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)))) \times (78 + 9)) \\ 28102 &:= ((1 - (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28103 &:= -((-12 - (-34 + ((-5^{6+7-8}) \times -9))) \\ 28104 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28105 &:= -(((123 - 4) - ((56 \times -7) \times (-8 \times 9)))) \\ 28106 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3 - 4)) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28107 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5)) \times -(6 - (7 + 8))) - 9) \\ 28108 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 78))) + 9))) \\ 28109 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times -4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28110 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4))) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28111 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times (3 + 4))) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28112 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) - 4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28113 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times -(3 \times 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28114 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28115 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 + 8)))) + 9) \\ 28116 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) \times -(6 - (7 + 8))) - 9) \\ 28117 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3^4) \times (5 \times 67 + 8) - 9 \\ 28118 &:= ((1 - ((2 + 3) \times (-4 + (5 \times 67)))) \times (-8 - 9)) \\ 28119 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 + 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28120 &:= (1 \times ((2 - 3) - (4 - ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)))) \\ 28121 &:= (1 + ((2 - 3) - (4 - ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)))) \\ 28122 &:= (((1 + 2) \times -34) + (56 \times ((-7 \times 8) \times -9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28084 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (76 - ((5 + (4 + 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 28085 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (76 + (5^4)))) \times -((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 28086 &:= (((-9 + 8) + 7) + ((65 \times (432 \times 1)))) \\ 28087 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6) \times (5 \times (432 - 1)))) \\ 28088 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 + 7) \times 65) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 28089 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 - (((65 \times 432) - 1)))) \\ 28090 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2) + 1) \\ 28091 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 - ((65 \times 432) + 1)))) \\ 28092 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)/2))) - 1) \\ 28093 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 + ((5 \times 4)^3)/(2 \times 1)))) \\ 28094 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - 2)) - 1) \\ 28095 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28096 &:= ((9 - (-8 + (((-7 - 6) \times 5) \times 432))) - 1) \\ 28097 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28098 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 28099 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28100 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 28101 &:= -((((9 - 87) \times (-6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times -3) - ((21))) \\ 28102 &:= (9 + 8!/7 - 6) \times 5 + 4 + 3 - (2 + 1)!! \\ 28103 &:= ((-((-9 - 8)) - (-7 - ((65 \times 432)))) - (1)) \\ 28104 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) - 4) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 28105 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5))) - 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 28106 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6 + (54 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 28107 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) - 6) \times (((5^4) \times (3 + 2)) - 1))) \\ 28108 &:= (((-9 \times (87 + (65 \times 4))) \times -(3^2)) + 1) \\ 28109 &:= ((9 + (87 \times ((6 \times 54) - (3 - 2)))) - 1) \\ 28110 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times -(((5^4) \times 3) - (2 - 1))) \\ 28111 &:= ((-98) + ((7 \times 65) \times ((4^3) - 2))) - 1) \\ 28112 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times 65) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\ 28113 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3)/2)))) - 1) \\ 28114 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3)/(2 \times 1)))) \\ 28115 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) - 6) \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28116 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 28117 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) - 6) \times ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28118 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 28119 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 28120 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 28121 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 28122 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times -(((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28123 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) - 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28124 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3) + (45 - 6)) \times 7)) \times 89) \\ 28125 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3)^4) \times (((-5 + 67) - 8) - 9))) \\ 28126 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (((-5 + 67) - 8) - 9))) \\ 28127 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 - 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28128 &:= ((1 \times ((2 - 3) + 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28129 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28130 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28131 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3 - 4) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28132 &:= (((1 \times 23) \times -4) + ((-56 \times -7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 28133 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) - ((56 \times 7) \times (-8 \times 9))) \\ 28134 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times 3) \times -((45 - (6 \times 789)))))) \\ 28135 &:= (1 + ((2 \times 3) \times -((45 - (6 \times 789)))))) \\ 28136 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times -4) - ((-((56 \times 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 28137 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28138 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4))) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28139 &:= ((-1 \times -(2 \times (3 + 4))) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28140 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))) \\ 28141 &:= (1 \times -(((2 + (3^4)) - ((56 \times 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 28142 &:= ((1 - (2 + (3^4))) + ((56 \times 7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 28143 &:= (1 \times (((2^3) + 45) \times -((67 - 8) \times -9))) \\ 28144 &:= (1 + (((2^3) + 45) \times -((67 - 8) \times -9))) \\ 28145 &:= ((-1 \times -((2 + 3) \times 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28146 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(3 + 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28147 &:= ((-12 + 34) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28148 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28149 &:= (1 \times (((-2 \times 3) \times -4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 28150 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 - 4) + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28151 &:= -(((1 - (-23 \times (-4 \times (((5 + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9))))))) \\ 28152 &:= ((1 + 2345) \times ((6 + 7) - (-8 + 9))) \\ 28153 &:= (1 + (-23 \times (-4 \times (((5 + 6) + 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 28154 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3 + (-4 - (-56 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 28155 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28156 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times 34)) + (56 \times -(((7 \times 8) \times 9)))) \\ 28157 &:= -((((12 \times -((3 + 4))) \times (-5 \times -67)) - (8 + 9))) \\ 28158 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times -3) + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28159 &:= ((((((123 \times 4) + 5) + 6) \times 7) \times -(-8)) - 9) \\ 28160 &:= (-(((1 - 2) - 34)) - ((-5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28161 &:= ((1 \times (2 - 3)) \times ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times -9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28123 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 28124 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) - (3 / (2 + 1))) \\ 28125 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^{4+3-2-1})) \\ 28126 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\ 28127 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 28128 &:= (-((9 + 87)) \times (-((6 \times 54)) + (32 - 1))) \\ 28129 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 28130 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 28131 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 28132 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 28133 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}))) - 1) \\ 28134 &:= (-9 \times (((8 \times (7 + 6)) - (5^4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 28135 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}))) + 1) \\ 28136 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (6 \times 54)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 28137 &:= ((-98 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 28138 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 65) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\ 28139 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 \times 65) \times ((4^3) - 2)) + 1)) \\ 28140 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) / 6) \times 5) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 28141 &:= (98 + ((7 \times (6 + (((5 \times 4)^3) / 2))) + 1)) \\ 28142 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times (4 + 3)) + 2)) - 1) \\ 28143 &:= (-9 \times -((8 - 7) + (((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2}) + 1))) \\ 28144 &:= ((9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((65 \times 432) - 1))) \\ 28145 &:= ((9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times (-5 \times -((432 + 1)))))) \\ 28146 &:= ((9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (-5 \times -((432 + 1)))))) \\ 28147 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times ((4^3) - 2)) - 1) \\ 28148 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 28149 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) - 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28150 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + 6)) - 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 28151 &:= (((9 \times 8) - (((-7 - 6) \times 5) \times 432)) - 1) \\ 28152 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times (5^4)) + (3^{2+1})) \\ 28153 &:= ((-9 - ((-8 \times 76))) \times (((54 - (3 \times 2)) - 1))) \\ 28154 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times ((7 \times 65) - (4^3))) + ((2 \times 1))) \\ 28155 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 28156 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - 7) \times 6)) \times -(((5^4) \times 3) + 2)) + 1) \\ 28157 &:= (-((((9 - 87) + (65 \times -432)))) - (-(-1))) \\ 28158 &:= (((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) + 5) \times -((4 + 3) - (2 - 1))) \\ 28159 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (-(-(65) \times (432 \times 1)))) \\ 28160 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) \times (6 + 5)) \times -4^{3+2-1}) \\ 28161 &:= ((98 \times ((7 + 65) \times 4)) - (3 \times (21))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28162 &:= (((1 + 2) + 34) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28163 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28164 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28165 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28166 &:= ((-1 \times -(2 + 3)) + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28167 &:= ((-1 \times -(2 \times 3)) + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28168 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9))) \\ 28169 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) - (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28170 &:= (((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4))) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9) \\ 28171 &:= (12 + (34 + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 28172 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times 4 + 5 \times (6! \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28173 &:= ((-12 - 3) - ((4 - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 28174 &:= (1 + 2) \times (-3!! + 4!) + 5 + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 28175 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\ 28176 &:= (-12 \times (-3 + (4 - (((-5 \times 6) \times -78) + 9)))) \\ 28177 &:= ((((((123 \times 4) + 5) + 6) \times 7) \times -(8)) + 9) \\ 28178 &:= (-12 + (-34 + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28179 &:= (-(((12 \times (3^4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) + 8))) - 9) \\ 28180 &:= (-1 \times ((2^3) + ((4 - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 28181 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) + ((4 - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 28182 &:= (((12^3)/4) + (-5)) \times ((67 + 8) - 9) \\ 28183 &:= ((-1 + 23) + ((4 + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28184 &:= ((-12/3) - ((-4 + ((56 \times -7) \times -8)) \times -9)) \\ 28185 &:= ((1 + 23) + ((-4 - (5^{6+7-8})) \times -9)) \\ 28186 &:= ((-1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) - 6) \times 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 28187 &:= ((-((1 + 2) - 34) - (-56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28188 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 + 8)))) \times 9) \\ 28189 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 + 4) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28190 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((3 \times 4) \times ((5 \times -6) \times 78) - 9)) \\ 28191 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 - ((4 - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 28192 &:= (((1 \times 2) - 34) - (56 \times (-((7 \times 8) \times 9))) \\ 28193 &:= ((1 + (2 - 34)) - ((56 \times 7) \times (8 \times -9))) \\ 28194 &:= (-12 + ((3^4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 28195 &:= ((-1 + (2^3)) - ((4 - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 28196 &:= (((-1 - 23) - 4) - (-((56 \times (-7 \times 8)) \times -9)) \\ 28197 &:= (((-1 \times (-2 - (3 \times (4^5)))) + (67 - 8)) \times 9) \\ 28198 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - 56)) \times -7) - 89) \\ 28199 &:= -(((1 + (2 \times (3 \times 4))) + (56 \times ((7 \times -8) \times 9))) \\ 28200 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times -(((4^5) \times 6) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28201 &:= (((-1 + (23 \times 4)) \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28162 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + 6))) \times -(5 + ((4 \times 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 28163 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times (4 + 3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 28164 &:= (9 - (((87 \times (-6 \times 54)) - (-32) - 1))) \\ 28165 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 \times 432) + 1))) \\ 28166 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -(43 - 2)) - 1) \\ 28167 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -((43 - 2) \times 1)) \\ 28168 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6) - 5^4)) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 28169 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 + 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28170 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\ 28171 &:= (((98 - 7) + (65 \times (432 \times 1))) \\ 28172 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times (6 \times 54))) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 28173 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) - 3)) + 21) \\ 28174 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times (6 \times 54))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 28175 &:= ((-9 + (-((-87) \times 6)) \times 54) + ((-3 - 2) + 1)) \\ 28176 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + ((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)))) \\ 28177 &:= (98 + (((7 + 6) \times (5 \times 432)) - 1)) \\ 28178 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) \times 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 28179 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times (5^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 28180 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) \times 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 28181 &:= (((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) + (5 - 4)) \times -(3 \times 2) - 1) \\ 28182 &:= (((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) + (5 - 4)) \times -(3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 28183 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) + (5 - 4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 28184 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (76 - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1)) \\ 28185 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) - 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28186 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) - 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 28187 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - (7 - 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28188 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 28189 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - (7 - 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28190 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times (6 \times ((5 + 4) - 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 28191 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + ((5^4) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 28192 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 65) \times ((4^3) - 2))) - 1) \\ 28193 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - (5 - 4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 28194 &:= (((((9 \times 87) \times 6) + 5) - 4) \times ((3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 28195 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - (5 - 4)) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 28196 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 - 6) \times 5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28197 &:= (-9 \times (((-87) \times ((65 + 4) + 3))/2) + (-1)) \\ 28198 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 - 6) \times 5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28199 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28200 &:= (((98 \times ((7 + 65) \times 4)) - 3) - (21)) \\ 28201 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28202 &:= -((-12 - (-34 + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 28203 &:= (((-1 \times -(2 - (3 - 4)))^5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 28204 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 28205 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) - (6 - (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 28206 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 + 8)))))) \times -9 \\ 28207 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 28208 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\ 28209 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + 4)) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28210 &:= ((((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times 5)) - 6) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 28211 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 3) - (4 - (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 28212 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (-3 \times 4)) + (((56 \times 7) \times 8) \times 9)) \\ 28213 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 28214 &:= ((1 \times (2 - (3 \times 4))) + ((-56 \times -7) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 28215 &:= (-(((1^2)^{3^4}) - (56 \times (7 \times 8)))) \times 9 \\ 28216 &:= (((-12/3) - 4) - (((56 \times -7) \times -8) \times -9)) \\ 28217 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times 3) - 4) - (((-56 \times 7) \times 8) \times 9)) \\ 28218 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 + 4)) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28219 &:= ((-(((1 - (23 \times 4)) \times 5)) \times (6 - (-7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 28220 &:= ((-1 - (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) - 6) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9) \\ 28221 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 28222 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 28223 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28224 &:= (((1^{2+3^4}) \times (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 28225 &:= ((1^{2+3^4}) - ((56 \times 7) \times -((8 \times 9)))) \\ 28226 &:= (((1 + 2) + 3) - 4) + ((56 \times 7) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 28227 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -34) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28228 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28229 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - (3 + 4)) - (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28230 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 - (-4 + (56 \times -((7 \times (8 \times 9))))))) \\ 28231 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times 4) + (5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28232 &:= (-1 + (((2 - ((3^4) + 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) \times -8)) + 9)) \\ 28233 &:= -(((1 + 2) - ((3 \times 4) - (56 \times ((7 \times -8) \times 9)))) \\ 28234 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times 4) - (56 \times ((7 \times -8) \times 9)))) \\ 28235 &:= ((1 + (2 \times 3)) - (-4 + (56 \times -((7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 28236 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times ((3 \times 4) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28237 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((45 \times 6) + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 28238 &:= ((1 \times 2) + ((3 \times 4) - (56 \times ((7 \times -8) \times 9)))) \\ 28239 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -((45 \times (6 \times 7)) - 8)) + 9) \\ 28240 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times 4) - ((56 \times -7) \times (8 \times 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28202 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((65 \times ((4^3) - 2)) - 1))) \\ 28203 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (6 - ((5 + 4) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\ 28204 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 28205 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) - 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28206 &:= ((98 \times ((7 + 65) \times 4)) + (3 - (21))) \\ 28207 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) - 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28208 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 28209 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + ((5^4) \times 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 28210 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 28211 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 28212 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 - (5 \times 43)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28213 &:= (((-9 - (8 - 7)) + ((6 + (54 \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\ 28214 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) / - (5 - (4 + 3)))^2)) - 1) \\ 28215 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 28216 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) / - (5 - (4 + 3)))^2) + 1) \\ 28217 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times 3) / 2)) - 1) \\ 28218 &:= (((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3) - (2 - 1))) \\ 28219 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 \times 6)) - 5) \times -((4 \times 3) / 2)) + 1) \\ 28220 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5)) \times ((43 \times 2) - 1)) \\ 28221 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7)^{6/((5+4)/3)})) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28222 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7)^{6/((5+4)/3)})) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 28223 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7)^{6+5-4-3-2})) - 1) \\ 28224 &:= ((9 \times (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5 \times ((4 \times 3) - ((2 \times 1)))))) \\ 28225 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7)^{6+5-4-3-2})) + 1) \\ 28226 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7)^{6/((5+4)/3)})) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 28227 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7)^{6/((5+4)/3)})) + (2 + 1)) \\ 28228 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 \times -54))) - 32)) - 1) \\ 28229 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 \times -54))) - 32) \times 1) \\ 28230 &:= ((9 - ((87 \times (6 \times -54))) - 32) + 1) \\ 28231 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6 + (54 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\ 28232 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) - ((6 + (54 \times 3))^2)) \times -1) \\ 28233 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 28234 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 28235 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28236 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (((5^4) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\ 28237 &:= ((9 + 8) \times ((-(-76)) - (5 \times (4 - 321)))) \\ 28238 &:= ((-98 / -7) + ((6 + (54 \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\ 28239 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - 21) \\ 28240 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + 65)) - 4) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28241 &:= (-1 - (((-2^3)/4) - ((56 \times 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28242 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 + 8)))))) \times -9) \\
 28243 &:= ((1 \times (23 - 4)) - (((-56 \times 7) \times -8) \times -9)) \\
 28244 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 + 3) \times 4) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 28245 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -(3 + 4)) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28246 &:= ((-12 + 34) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28247 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 28248 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times 3) \times 4) - ((-56 \times 7) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 28249 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 345)) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9))) \\
 28250 &:= ((-1 + (23 + 4)) + ((-56 \times (-7 \times -8)) \times -9)) \\
 28251 &:= ((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) + (6 - (7 + 8))) \times -9) \\
 28252 &:= (((-1) + 23) - (-4 - ((56 \times 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28253 &:= (-((1 - (2 \times -3))) + ((4 - ((56 \times -7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28254 &:= (((-123 \times 4) \times -56) + (78 \times 9)) \\
 28255 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) - ((4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28256 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 56) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28257 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -3 - ((4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28258 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -((-34 + (-56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 28259 &:= ((1 \times (-(-2) - 3)) + ((4 + ((56 \times 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28260 &:= (-(((12 + 3) \times -(-4)) - ((56 \times 7) \times (-8 \times 9))) \\
 28261 &:= (-((-1 + 2) - 34) - (-56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28262 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 56) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28263 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 56) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28264 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + ((4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28265 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + 3) + ((4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28266 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times 3) + ((4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28267 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) + ((4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28268 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 4)) - (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28269 &:= (-((12 - 3) \times (((45 + 6) \times 7) - 8)) \times -9) \\
 28270 &:= ((12 + 34) - (56 \times (7 \times -((8 \times 9)))))) \\
 28271 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 28272 &:= ((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - 5) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 28273 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 56) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9))) \\
 28274 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 56) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 28275 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times 6)))) \times -(78 + 9)) \\
 28276 &:= (-1 + 2 \times 3!! - 4!) \times 5! / 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 28277 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times ((56 - 7) \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28278 &:= (-1 - (-(((2^{3 \times 4}) + 56) \times -7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
 28279 &:= (-1 - (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 56) \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 28280 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 56) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9))) \\
 28241 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 28242 &:= ((98 \times ((7 + 65) \times 4)) - (3 - (21))) \\
 28243 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 28244 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -((65 \times 4) + (3^2))) - 1) \\
 28245 &:= ((-98 - 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
 28246 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times -((65 \times 4) + (3^2))) + 1) \\
 28247 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 28248 &:= (((98 \times ((7 + 65) \times 4)) + 3) + (21)) \\
 28249 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times 43)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28250 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 28251 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7)^{6 / ((5 + 4) / 3)}) + (2 + 1))) \\
 28252 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - 7) - 6^5)) - (-(((4 \times 32) - 1)))) \\
 28253 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5)) \times 43)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 28254 &:= (((-(-9) + (-8 \times (-76) - 5)) \times 43) + ((2 + 1))) \\
 28255 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 65) \times 4)) + (32 - 1)) \\
 28256 &:= ((-98 \times -((7 + 65) \times 4)) + (32 \times 1)) \\
 28257 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 28258 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28259 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) + ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 + 2}))) - 1) \\
 28260 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times ((6 + (5^4) - 3)) / (2 + 1))) \\
 28261 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) + ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3 + 2}))) + 1) \\
 28262 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 28263 &:= (-9 - ((-87) - 6) \times (((5^4) - 321))) \\
 28264 &:= ((-9 - ((876 + 5) \times 4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 28265 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times (65 \times ((4 + 3) - 2)))) - 1) \\
 28266 &:= (((987 \times -6) \times -5) - (((4^3) \times 21))) \\
 28267 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 28268 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 28269 &:= (9 - ((8 + 7) \times (-6 \times (((5^4) + 3) / (2 \times 1)))) \\
 28270 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + (54 \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\
 28271 &:= ((9 + 8) \times (7 + ((65 + 4) \times ((3 + 21)))) \\
 28272 &:= ((-9 + ((87 + 6) \times 5)) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 28273 &:= (((-9 + ((87 + 6) \times 5)) \times ((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\
 28274 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 28275 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((65 \times ((4^3) - 2)) - 1))) \\
 28276 &:= -9 - 8 + (7! - 6^5 / 4!) \times 3! - 2 - 1 \\
 28277 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 + 6)) \times ((5^4) + 3)) - 2)) - 1) \\
 28278 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (7 \times (6 \times (5 \times ((4 \times 3) + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 28279 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 28280 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28281 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 56) \times (-7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 28282 &:= ((-1 + 23) - (-((4 - ((56 \times 7) \times -8))) \times 9)) \\
 28283 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + ((4 + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28284 &:= (1 \times ((2 \times -3) \times ((4 \times 5) + (-6 \times 789)))) \\
 28285 &:= (1 + ((2 \times -3) \times ((4 \times 5) + (-6 \times 789)))) \\
 28286 &:= (-(((1 \times 23) \times (-4^5))) + (6 \times 789)) \\
 28287 &:= (-((1 - (((23 \times (4 \times 5)) - 67) \times 8))) \times 9) \\
 28288 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4 - 5}) \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28289 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) + 5)) \times 6)) \times -7 \times 8) + 9) \\
 28290 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 56) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 28291 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times 34) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 28292 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times -34) - (-56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28293 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 28294 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 28295 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 + (5 \times ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9)))) \\
 28296 &:= (-12 \times (-3 \times (-4 + (-5 + (6 + (789))))) \\
 28297 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 56) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 28298 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - (((3 - 4) - (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28299 &:= ((-123 \times -((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - 8) + 9) \\
 28300 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) - (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 89))))) \\
 28301 &:= ((1 + (-2 - 3)) - (45 \times (-6 - (-7 \times -89)))) \\
 28302 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 6)) + (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28303 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))) \\
 28304 &:= (-((1^{23})) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 28305 &:= ((1^{23}) \times (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 28306 &:= ((1^{23}) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 28307 &:= (1 \times ((2 + (3^4)) + ((56 \times 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28308 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + 4)) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28309 &:= ((12/3) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 28310 &:= ((-1 \times (-2 - 3)) + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 28311 &:= ((((-1 - 23) \times -4) \times (5 \times (67 - 8))) - 9) \\
 28312 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9) \\
 28313 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28314 &:= (-(((1 - 2) + ((3 \times (4^5)) + (67 + 8)))) \times -9) \\
 28315 &:= -(((1 - (23 \times 4)) + ((56 \times 7) \times (-8 \times 9)))) \\
 28316 &:= (((-((1 \times 23)) \times -4) - (-((56 \times 7) \times (-8 \times -9)))) \\
 28317 &:= (((((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) + (678 - 9)) \\
 28318 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4) + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\
 28319 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (34 \times ((56 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 28320 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28281 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
 28282 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 28283 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\
 28284 &:= ((-9 - (87 \times (65 \times ((4 + 3) - 2)))) \times -1) \\
 28285 &:= ((-9 + (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 28286 &:= (-9 + (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 28287 &:= ((98 \times ((7 + 65) \times 4)) + (3 \times (21))) \\
 28288 &:= (((9 + 876) + (-5 + 4)) \times (32 \times 1)) \\
 28289 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times (65 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28290 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times 6))) \times -(((5 + 4) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\
 28291 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!)) \times 5 - 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 28292 &:= -9 + 8! + 7 \times (6 + 5 - (4 \times 3)^{2+1}) \\
 28293 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) + (6^5)) \times 4) + 321) \\
 28294 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -(5^4) + (32 + 1))) \\
 28295 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3))^2)) - 1) \\
 28296 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 28297 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + 6) - 5) \times (4 + 3))^2)) + 1) \\
 28298 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! - 6^5/4!) \times 3! + 2 + 1 \\
 28299 &:= (((-9 - ((87 \times 65) - 4)) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 28300 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times ((6 - ((5^4) + 3))/2)) - 1) \\
 28301 &:= -((((9 + (87 \times 65)) - 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\
 28302 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times ((6 - ((5^4) + 3))/2)) + 1) \\
 28303 &:= (((9 + (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 28304 &:= (9 + (((((87 \times 65) + 4) \times (3 + 2)) \times 1))) \\
 28305 &:= ((9 + (((87 \times 65) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 28306 &:= ((9 - 8) + (-(-765)) \times (4 + ((32 + 1)))) \\
 28307 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times 65) \times ((4^3) - 2))) - 1) \\
 28308 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times 65) \times ((4^3) - 2))) \times 1) \\
 28309 &:= ((98 + ((7 \times 65) \times ((4^3) - 2))) + 1) \\
 28310 &:= ((-9 + ((876 + (5 + 4)) \times 32)) - 1) \\
 28311 &:= (-9 + ((876 + (5 + 4)) \times (32 \times 1))) \\
 28312 &:= (-9 + (((876 + (5 + 4)) \times 32) + 1)) \\
 28313 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 + 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 28314 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 + 6)) + (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
 28315 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 + 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 28316 &:= ((98 - 7) + (((6 + (54 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\
 28317 &:= ((9 \times (((-8 + 7) + 6^5)) + (((4^3) \times (2 + (1)))))) \\
 28318 &:= (9 \times 8 - 7 - 6) \times 5! \times 4 - 3! / (2 + 1) \\
 28319 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times -(6 + ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\
 28320 &:= ((-9 - 87) \times -(6 + ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28321 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times 4^5) + (67 + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28322 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((3 \times 4^5) + (67 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
 28323 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((3 \times 4^5) + (67 + 8)) \times -9)) \\
 28324 &:= (-1 - ((-(-2) + 3) \times (4 - (5678 - 9)))) \\
 28325 &:= ((1 + (-2 \times 3)) \times ((4 - 5678) + 9)) \\
 28326 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (78 \times 9))))))) \\
 28327 &:= (((-12 - 34) \times -((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\
 28328 &:= (-1 \times -(23 + (45 \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))))) \\
 28329 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -4) \times (5 \times (67 - 8))) + 9) \\
 28330 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 \times 4) + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28331 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times 9) \\
 28332 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8)))))) \times 9) \\
 28333 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times 4) + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28334 &:= (-(-12) + (-((-34 \times (56 - 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28335 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times -((45 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 - 9))) \\
 28336 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -((4^5) + (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 28337 &:= (1 - 2 - 3) \times 4 \times 5! + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 28338 &:= (-12 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 28339 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (34 \times (56 - 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 28340 &:= ((1 + ((-2^3) - 45)) \times ((67 \times -8) - 9)) \\
 28341 &:= (((123 \times 4) \times 56) + (789)) \\
 28342 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) - 456) \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\
 28343 &:= ((123 - 4) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28344 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 67)) + (8 + 9))) \\
 28345 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4}) - 56) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 28346 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 + 4)) \times (5678 - 9))) \\
 28347 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 28348 &:= (1 \times (-2 + ((3 - 45) \times (-((67 + 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 28349 &:= (1 + (-2 + ((3 - 45) \times (-((67 + 8)) \times 9)))) \\
 28350 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) - (5 + 6)) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 28351 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 28352 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \\
 28353 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((3 - 45) \times ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 28354 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3!!/4 + 5 \times (6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\
 28355 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (34 \times (56 - 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28356 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 \times (4 \times (5 + 6))) + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28357 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times (78 - 9)) \\
 28358 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times (6 + 7)) - 8) \times 9) \\
 28359 &:= (((1^2) - ((-3 + 45) \times (-67 - 8))) \times 9) \\
 28360 &:= (((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28321 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times -7)^{6/((5+4)/3)}) \times 2) - 1) \\
 28322 &:= (98 \times (-((-7 - (6 - 5)) \times (4 + 32))) - (-1)) \\
 28323 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 + 1))) \\
 28324 &:= (9 + 8 + 7)/6 + 5! \times (-4 + 3!!/(2 + 1)) \\
 28325 &:= -9 - 8 \times ((7 - 6!) \times 5 + 4!) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 28326 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) - (4 \times 321)) \\
 28327 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (43 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 28328 &:= ((9 + (((876 + 5) + 4) \times 32)) - 1) \\
 28329 &:= ((9 + (((876 + 5) + 4) \times 32)) \times 1) \\
 28330 &:= (9 + (((876 + (5 + 4)) \times 32) + 1)) \\
 28331 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - 2)) - 1) \\
 28332 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 28333 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - 2)) + 1) \\
 28334 &:= ((((-98/7) \times 65) - 4) \times -(32 - 1)) \\
 28335 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! - 6^5/4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28336 &:= ((-98/7) \times -(((6 + (5 + 4)) \times 3)^2) - 1) \\
 28337 &:= (-9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5) \times (4 + 3) - (2 + 1)!! \\
 28338 &:= (9 + ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times (5 + ((4^3) \times 21)))) \\
 28339 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 + (5 \times (43 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 28340 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (43 - 2)))) - 1) \\
 28341 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (((5^4) + 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\
 28342 &:= (-((-9 - 8) - 765) \times ((4 + 32) + 1)) \\
 28343 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + ((6 + (54 \times 3))^2 \times 1)) \\
 28344 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + (6^5)) - 4) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 28345 &:= (9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times (43 + (2 + 1)))))) \\
 28346 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7!) + (6^5 - 4 - 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 28347 &:= ((-98 + 765) + 4) \times -(32 - 1) \\
 28348 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28349 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 28350 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (((5 + 4) - 3)^{2+1})) \\
 28351 &:= (((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 28352 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 28353 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 28354 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + (6^5)) \times 4) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 28355 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2))) - 1) \\
 28356 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
 28357 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 28358 &:= (((98 - (76)) \times (5 + ((4 \times 321)))) \\
 28359 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) \times (5 + 4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 28360 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) - ((6 - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28361 &:= (((1 + (-2 \times 3)) \times (4 - 5678)) - 9) \\ 28362 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)) + 9)) \\ 28363 &:= ((((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 28364 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + 5678) - 9))) \\ 28365 &:= ((-12 - (3^4)) \times (((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 28366 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - 89) \\ 28367 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8))))) \times 9)) \\ 28368 &:= (((1 \times 2) + 34) \times ((5 - 6) + 789)) \\ 28369 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - 56) \times 7) + 89) \\ 28370 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - 56) \times 7) + 89)) \\ 28371 &:= ((-((-12 \times (3^4))) \times (5 \times 6)) - 789) \\ 28372 &:= -(((1 \times ((2 \times 34) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 - 89))) \\ 28373 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 28374 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - 3))) - 4) \times (5 - (6 \times 789))) \\ 28375 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28376 &:= (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (67 \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 28377 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4^5))) - (67 \times -(8 \times 9))) \\ 28378 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 + (5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 28379 &:= (((1 + (-2 \times 3)) \times (4 - 5678)) + 9) \\ 28380 &:= (-12 \times (-((34 - ((-5 \times 6) \times 78))) + 9)) \\ 28381 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3))^4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\ 28382 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 - (7 \times 89))) \\ 28383 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28384 &:= ((12^3) + (4 \times (56 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 28385 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28386 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (3^4)) - (-56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28387 &:= ((-12 \times -((345 - 6) \times 7)) - 89) \\ 28388 &:= 1 \times 2 + (-3! + 4!) \times (5! \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9) \\ 28389 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28390 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28391 &:= (((-1 + (((2^3) + 45) \times 67)) \times 8) - 9) \\ 28392 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 + 78)) \times 9)) \\ 28393 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3!^4 \times (5 + 6) - 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 28394 &:= (-1 + (((23 - 4) + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 28395 &:= ((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) + 5)) \times -(((6 + 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28396 &:= ((-123 \times -((4 \times 56) + 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28397 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6))) \times -7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28398 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) + 45) \times (67 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 28399 &:= (1 \times (((-(-2) + (-3 - 4)) \times -(5678)) + 9)) \\ 28400 &:= (1 + (((-(-2) + (-3 - 4)) \times -(5678)) + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28361 &:= (((9 \times -8) - 7) \times (-((6 \times (54 - (-3 \times 2)))) + 1)) \\ 28362 &:= ((-98) - 76) \times (-(((54 \times 3) + 2)) + 1) \\ 28363 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1}))) \\ 28364 &:= (-98 - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28365 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28366 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 28367 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + 2)) - 1) \\ 28368 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (((-76) \times 5) - (-4 - 3)) - (21)) \\ 28369 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + 2)) + 1) \\ 28370 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 28371 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times 3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 28372 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -(5 + (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 28373 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times -(5 + (4 \times (3^2)))) + 1) \\ 28374 &:= ((-9 + (-87) \times (-6 - (5 \times (4^3)))) + (21)) \\ 28375 &:= (9 + (((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) - 2)) + 1)) \\ 28376 &:= ((9 \times (((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))/3) - 2) - 1) \\ 28377 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 28378 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -(3 \times 2 + 1)) \\ 28379 &:= (-9 + 8 \times 7 + 6!) \times (-5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)!) \\ 28380 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 28381 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 76)) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 28382 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 76)) \times -((5 \times (4 + (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28383 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28384 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 28385 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28386 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) - 3)/(2 + 1)) \\ 28387 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28388 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 28389 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 28390 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28391 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\ 28392 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 28393 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - (-(-6)^5)) \times 4) + ((32 + 1)) \\ 28394 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - 7) \times 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 28395 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 + 6))) \times ((5^4) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 28396 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - 7) \times 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 28397 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))/3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 28398 &:= (-9 - ((8 - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 28399 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - (32 \times 1))))) \\ 28400 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 - 6)) \times -((5 \times 4)^{3-2+1})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28401 &:= (-1 - (2 - (((3 - 45) + 6) \times -(789)))) \\
 28402 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 - 45) + 6) \times -(789))) \\
 28403 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 4) + (56 \times (7 \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28404 &:= (-1 \times ((-(2^3) + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times -(789))) \\
 28405 &:= (-1 - (-2 + ((3 - (4 + 5)) \times (6 \times 789))) \\
 28406 &:= (-1 \times (-2 + ((3 - (4 + 5)) \times (6 \times 789))) \\
 28407 &:= ((1 + 2) - (((3 - 45) + 6) \times 789)) \\
 28408 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times 34)) \times ((5 \times 67) + 89)) \\
 28409 &:= (((-1 + (((2^3) + 45) \times 67)) \times 8) + 9) \\
 28410 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times 789))) \\
 28411 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times 789)))) \\
 28412 &:= ((123 \times ((4 \times 56) + 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\
 28413 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) \times 4) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9) \\
 28414 &:= ((123 \times ((4 \times 56) + 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\
 28415 &:= (1 \times (-((2 + 3)) \times ((4 - 5678) - 9))) \\
 28416 &:= (12 - (((-3 - 4) + 5) \times -(6 \times 789))) \\
 28417 &:= (1 \times ((((-2^3) - 45) \times (67 \times -8)) + 9)) \\
 28418 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4 + 5678)) + 9)) \\
 28419 &:= (-1 \times (((-2 - 3) \times (4 + 5678)) - 9)) \\
 28420 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) \times (4 + 5678)) + 9)) \\
 28421 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + ((4 \times (56 \times 7)) + 8)) \times 9))) \\
 28422 &:= ((-1 - (((2^3) \times 4) + (5^{6+7-8}))) \times -9) \\
 28423 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) - 456) \times 7 - 8) \times 9) \\
 28424 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -4 - ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 28425 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3)^4 \times (5! + 6 - 7 - 8) + 9 \\
 28426 &:= -1 - 2 \times 3! \times 4! + (5 \times (6! + 7! - 8 - 9)) \\
 28427 &:= -(12 - 3)^4 + 5 + 6^7 / 8 - 9 \\
 28428 &:= (123 + (-(-45) \times (6 + (7 \times 89)))) \\
 28429 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 28430 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + ((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9) \\
 28431 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9) \\
 28432 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28433 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 28434 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 + 4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times 789))) \\
 28435 &:= ((-1 - 234) \times -((56 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 28436 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28437 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))))) \\
 28438 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28439 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28401 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)))) \\
 28402 &:= ((-98) + (76 \times (54 + 321))) \\
 28403 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 28404 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) + 3) / (2 + 1)) \\
 28405 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 28406 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6 + (5^4)) \times 3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 28407 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) - 32)) + 1)))) \\
 28408 &:= -9 + (-8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
 28409 &:= (9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) - 32)) - 1)))) \\
 28410 &:= (9 \times (8 \times 7 + 6!) + 5!) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\
 28411 &:= (-9 + 8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4^3 \times (2 + 1)! \\
 28412 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) / 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 28413 &:= (((9 \times -8) + 765) \times ((43 - 2) \times 1)) \\
 28414 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5 + 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 28415 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) + 2))) - 1) \\
 28416 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 28417 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (((6 + (5^4)) \times 3) + 2)) + 1)) \\
 28418 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - 32)))) - 1)) \\
 28419 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -3) - (2 + 1)) \\
 28420 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -3) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28421 &:= ((((-98) \times (76 + (5 + (4^3)))) \times -2) + 1) \\
 28422 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4))) / 3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 28423 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 28424 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times (6 - (5 \times ((4 + 3)^2)))) + 1)) \\
 28425 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5^4)))) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\
 28426 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! + (6^5 + 4!) \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 28427 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\
 28428 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5 + 4)^3))) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 28429 &:= (9 + 8 \times (7 + 6!)) \times 5 + 4! - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 28430 &:= (9 + (-(-8) - (((7 \times 65) - 4) \times (-((3 \times 21)))))) \\
 28431 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times (7 + 6)) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 28432 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 \times 6)) - ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 28433 &:= ((((-9 \times ((87 \times 6) + 5)) + 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\
 28434 &:= (((-9 + 8) - ((7 + 6) \times (((5 + 4)^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 28435 &:= ((((-9 \times ((87 \times 6) + 5)) + 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) + 1) \\
 28436 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 28437 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 28438 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4^3 \times 2) - 1)))) \\
 28439 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6)) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28440 &:= (((-1-2) \times -(-3)) \times (4 \times (5 - (6 + 789)))) \\ 28441 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 28442 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))))) \\ 28443 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) + (6 + 789) \\ 28444 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28445 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9) \\ 28446 &:= (-12 + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 28447 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3)! + 4!) \times (-5! + 6! - 7) - 8 - 9 \\ 28448 &:= (-1 - (((23 \times 4) - 5) \times (((-6 \times 7) \times 8) + 9))) \\ 28449 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times -9) \\ 28450 &:= (1 - ((23 - ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 28451 &:= (1 - 2 \times 3!) \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 28452 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6))) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28453 &:= -1 + (-2 + 3!! - 4!) \times ((5 + 6 - 7)! + 8 + 9) \\ 28454 &:= ((-(-123) + (4 \times 56)) \times (-7 + 89)) \\ 28455 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 28456 &:= ((((-1 + ((2^3)^4)) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) - ((8 - 9))) \\ 28457 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 28458 &:= (-((12 - 3) + 45)) \times ((67 \times -8) + 9) \\ 28459 &:= (((12 \times (345 - 6)) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28460 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3)^4) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) + (8 - 9) \\ 28461 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3 \times 456) \times 7) - 89)) \\ 28462 &:= ((-1 \times (((2^3)^4) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) \times (8 - 9) \\ 28463 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 8) - 9) \\ 28464 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3 - 456) \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\ 28465 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (((3 - 456) \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 28466 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) - ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 28467 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3 \times (4^5)) + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9) \\ 28468 &:= (1 - ((-((23 + 4)) + ((56 \times 7) \times -8)) \times 9)) \\ 28469 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 28470 &:= (1 - ((-2 - ((3 - 45) \times -(678)) + 9)) \\ 28471 &:= ((-1234 \times -((5 \times 6) - 7)) + 89) \\ 28472 &:= (((12 - 3) + 4)^{5+6-7}) - 89) \\ 28473 &:= (-12 + (((3 - 45) \times -(678)) + 9)) \\ 28474 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times (67 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 28475 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 28476 &:= (((1 + 23) + (4 - ((56 \times 7) \times -8))) \times 9) \\ 28477 &:= (((12 \times (345 - 6)) \times 7) - 8) + 9) \\ 28478 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28440 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 - (7 - 6)) + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 28441 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) - (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\ 28442 &:= (-98) + (((7 + 6)^{5-4+3}) - (21)) \\ 28443 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 28444 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\ 28445 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28446 &:= (-9 + ((8 + ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 28447 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2 \times 1))) \\ 28448 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2)) + 1)) \\ 28449 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times (6 \times (5 \times 4))) - 3) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 28450 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 65) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 28451 &:= (-9 + 8 \times (-7 + 6!)) \times 5 - 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 28452 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 28453 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\ 28454 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\ 28455 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 28456 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1)) \\ 28457 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3))^2))) - 1) \\ 28458 &:= ((987 - ((65 + 4))) \times (32 - 1)) \\ 28459 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - ((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3))^2))) + 1) \\ 28460 &:= ((-9 + 8) - ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\ 28461 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28462 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 28463 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\ 28464 &:= (-98 + (((7 + 6)^{5+4-3-2}) + 1)) \\ 28465 &:= (-98 + (((7 + 6)^{5-4+3}) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 28466 &:= (-98 + (((7 + 6)^{5-4+3}) + (2 + 1))) \\ 28467 &:= ((-98 - 7) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\ 28468 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 28469 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 28470 &:= (((((-9 - 87) \times 6) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\ 28471 &:= ((-9 - 87) + ((6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2)) + 1)) \\ 28472 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 32)) + 1)) \\ 28473 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) \times -1) \\ 28474 &:= (((-98 + 7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2))) - 1) \\ 28475 &:= (((98 - 7) - 6) \times -5) \times -((4 + ((3 \times 21)))) \\ 28476 &:= (((9 + (-8)) + ((7 \times 65) - 4)) \times ((3 \times 21))) \\ 28477 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28478 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28479 &:= (-(-12) - (((-3 + 456) \times -7) + 8) \times -(-9)) \\
 28480 &:= -((((12 - 345) + 6) + 7) \times 89) \\
 28481 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - 8) + 9) \\
 28482 &:= (((-((1 + 23)) \times 4) - 5) \times (-6 \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))) \\
 28483 &:= ((1 \times (-2 + ((3 - 45) \times -(678)))) - (-9)) \\
 28484 &:= ((1 + (-2 + ((3 - 45) \times -(678)))) - (-9)) \\
 28485 &:= ((123 \times ((4 \times 56) + 7)) - (8 \times -9)) \\
 28486 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (-((3 - 45)) \times 678)) - (-9))) \\
 28487 &:= (-((1 \times (-2 - ((3 - 45) \times -(678)))) + 9)) \\
 28488 &:= ((-1 - 23) + ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 28489 &:= (((12 - 3) + 4)^{5+6-7} - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28490 &:= -((-1 - (-23 + ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times -((-8 \times 9)))))) \\
 28491 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (34 \times (5 + (6 \times (78 - 9)))))) \\
 28492 &:= ((-1 \times (2 \times 34)) \times (-5 - (6 \times (78 - 9)))) \\
 28493 &:= (((12 \times (345 - 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 28494 &:= ((-1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 8) \times 9) \\
 28495 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + ((3 \times (4^5))/6)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 28496 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times (78 - 9))) \\
 28497 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\
 28498 &:= (1 + ((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) + 6)) \times (78 - 9))) \\
 28499 &:= (((12 - ((-3 + (4 - 5))^{-(-6)})) \times -7) - 89) \\
 28500 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) - 5) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 28501 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!^4 \times (5 + 6) + 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 28502 &:= ((-(-123) \times ((4 \times 56) + 7)) + 89) \\
 28503 &:= (((((-1 \times -(2 - (3 - 4)))^5) \times (6 + 7)) + 8) \times 9) \\
 28504 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times -(((4^5) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 28505 &:= (((12/3) \times ((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (-8 + 9)) \\
 28506 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) + ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 28507 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) - ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28508 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 28509 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3 \times 4 - 5})) \times -((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28510 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))))) - 9) \\
 28511 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times (5 - ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 28512 &:= ((1 + 2) \times ((3 \times (456 \times 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 28513 &:= ((1^{23}) - (((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times -8) \times 9)) \\
 28514 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times 67) + (8 + 9)))) \\
 28515 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (3 + ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28516 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28517 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (-3 - ((4 - (-56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28479 &:= (-((98 + 765)) \times ((4 \times -3) + (-21))) \\
 28480 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(4^3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 28481 &:= (-(((9 + (876 + 5)) \times -((4^3)/2))) + (1)) \\
 28482 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 28483 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 28484 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 28485 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 28486 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6)^{5-4+3})) - (2 + 1)) \\
 28487 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6)^{5-4+3})) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28488 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6)^{5+4-3-2})) - 1) \\
 28489 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6)^{(5+4+3)/(2+1)})) \\
 28490 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6)^{5+4-3-2}) + 1)) \\
 28491 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6)^{5-4+3}) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 28492 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + 6)^{5-4+3}) + (2 + 1))) \\
 28493 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\
 28494 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1)) \\
 28495 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) - 1))) \\
 28496 &:= (-98 - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 28497 &:= (-98 - (7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28498 &:= (-98 - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\
 28499 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + (((6 + 5)^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 28500 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 - 1 \\
 28501 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 28502 &:= -9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 + 1 \\
 28503 &:= (-(-9) \times (((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4 \times 32)) + ((-1)))) \\
 28504 &:= (-98 - (7 \times ((6 + 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 28505 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 28506 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2 + 1) \\
 28507 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\
 28508 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
 28509 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(76 + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 28510 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(76 + (5 \times (4^3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28511 &:= (98 + (((7 \times 65) - 4) \times ((3 \times 21)))) \\
 28512 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 28513 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - 5)) \times -((4^3)/2)) + 1) \\
 28514 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(76 + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 28515 &:= (((98 \times (76 + (5 \times 43))) - 2) + (-1)) \\
 28516 &:= (((98 \times (76 + (5 \times 43))) + (2 \times -1)) \\
 28517 &:= ((-98 \times -(((7 + 65) \times 4) + 3)) - (2 - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28518 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89)) \\
 28519 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\
 28520 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89)) \\
 28521 &:= (((1^{23}) - ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times -8)) \times 9) \\
 28522 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6)) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28523 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9) \\
 28524 &:= (-12 \times -((3 + 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 28525 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(((5 \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 28526 &:= ((-12 + (-34 \times (56 - 7))) \times -((8 + 9))) \\
 28527 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\
 28528 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times -4 - (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 28529 &:= (-1 - (((2 - ((3^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\
 28530 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6))) \times -7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28531 &:= ((1^2) + ((34 + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28532 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((34 + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28533 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 28534 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times -5 - ((6 - 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28535 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times 34) + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 28536 &:= (-12 \times ((3 + (-4 + (5 \times 6))) \times (7 - 89))) \\
 28537 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 28538 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (34 \times 56)) \times (7 + 8)) - 9)) \\
 28539 &:= (((1^2) + 34) + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9) \\
 28540 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3 + ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28541 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 \times 6))) \times -7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 28542 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 28543 &:= ((1 \times 23) \times ((4 - ((5 + 6) \times 7)) \times -((8 + 9)))) \\
 28544 &:= (((1 - (2 \times (3 + 4)))^{5+6-7}) - 8) - 9) \\
 28545 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + 8) + 9) \\
 28546 &:= -1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4!) \times (-5 + 6!) - 7!) + 8 + 9) \\
 28547 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 34) + ((56 \times 7) \times 8)) \times -9)) \\
 28548 &:= (-12 \times (-3 + ((4 + (5 - (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28549 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((34 \times (56 \times (7 + 8))) - 9))) \\
 28550 &:= -(((1^2) - ((34 \times -56)) \times (7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 28551 &:= -((((12 \times -34) \times ((5 - 67) - 8)) + 9)) \\
 28552 &:= (((1^2) + -((34 \times -56)) \times (7 + 8))) - 9) \\
 28553 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -((4^{5-6+7}) - (8 + 9))) \\
 28554 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))))) \\
 28555 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))))) \\
 28556 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) + ((4 + (56 \times 7)) \times 8)) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28518 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 - 1 \\
 28519 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 28520 &:= 9 - 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 + 1 \\
 28521 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\
 28522 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 28523 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28524 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\
 28525 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\
 28526 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)))) - 1) \\
 28527 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 28528 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 28529 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 28530 &:= ((-((98 - 7)) + ((6 - 5))) \times (4 - (321))) \\
 28531 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 28532 &:= -9 - 8 \times (7 - 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\
 28533 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 28534 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28535 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\
 28536 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -6 - (((5 + (4^3))^2) + 1)) \\
 28537 &:= ((((-98 / -7) - (6 - 5))^4) - (3 + 21)) \\
 28538 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4) - 32)) \times -1) \\
 28539 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) - 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\
 28540 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + 6)^{5-4+3}) - (21)) \\
 28541 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6)^{5-4+3})) - (2 + 1)) \\
 28542 &:= (((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6)^{5-4+3})) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28543 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 28544 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6)^{(5+4+3)/(2+1)})) \\
 28545 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6)^{5+4-3-2}) + 1)) \\
 28546 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 28547 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + 6)^{5-4+3}) + (2 + 1))) \\
 28548 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\
 28549 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 28550 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4)) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\
 28551 &:= ((-((9 - 876)) + 54) \times (32 - 1)) \\
 28552 &:= (-9 + ((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^{4+3-2-1})) \\
 28553 &:= (-9 + (((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4) + (3 / (2 + 1)))) \\
 28554 &:= (-9 + (((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 28555 &:= (-9 + (((8 + ((7 - 6) \times 5))^4) + (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 28556 &:= (((9 - 87) + 65^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28557 &:= (-12 - ((34 \times 56) \times -((7+8))) - 9) & 28557 &:= (((9 - (87 - 65))^4) - ((3+2) - 1)) \\
 28558 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) - 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9) & 28558 &:= ((-9 \times (87 + ((6 \times -(543)) - 2))) + 1) \\
 28559 &:= (((-1 + ((2 - ((3 \times (4^5))/6)) \times 7)) \times -8) - 9) & 28559 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7+6)^{5+4-3-2})) - 1) \\
 28560 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 28560 &:= ((-9 + 8) + ((7+6)^{(5+4+3)/(2+1)})) \\
 28561 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))^{5-6/(7+8-9)}) & 28561 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -(7+6))^{(5+4+3)/(2+1)}) \\
 28562 &:= (((((1+2) \times 3) + 4)^{5+6-7}) - (8 - 9)) & 28562 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times -(7+6))^{5+4-3-2}) + 1) \\
 28563 &:= ((-12 \times (((345 - 6) \times -7) - 8)) - 9) & 28563 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (((7+6)^{5-4+3}) + (2 + 1))) \\
 28564 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) + ((6 \times 7) - 8))) \times 9))) & 28564 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times -(7+6))^{5-4+3}) + (2 + 1)) \\
 28565 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8+9)))))))) & 28565 &:= (((9 - (87 - 65))^4) + ((3+2) - 1)) \\
 28566 &:= ((((-1^2) + (34 \times -56)) \times -((7+8))) - 9) & 28566 &:= (((9 - 87) + 65)^4) + ((3+2) \times 1) \\
 28567 &:= (1 \times ((-2 - (34 \times (56 \times (-7-8)))) + 9)) & 28567 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) - 1))) \\
 28568 &:= -((((1^2) - (-((34 \times -56)) \times (7+8))) - 9)) & 28568 &:= ((((-98 / -7) - (6 - 5))^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 28569 &:= (-((1^2)) \times (((34 \times -56) \times (7+8)) - 9)) & 28569 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + ((7-6) \times 5))^4) - (3-2))) \times -1) \\
 28570 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((34 \times (56 \times (7+8))) + 9)) & 28570 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + ((7-6) \times 5))^4)) \times -(3/(2+1))) \\
 28571 &:= (1 \times (2 - ((34 \times (56 \times (-7-8))) - 9))) & 28571 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6+5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 28572 &:= ((1 + 2) - ((34 \times (56 \times (-7-8))) - 9)) & 28572 &:= ((-9 + (8+7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2 \times 1))) \\
 28573 &:= (((-1 - (23 \times (4 \times 5))) \times -(6 + (7 \times 8))) - 9) & 28573 &:= ((-9 + (8+7)) + ((6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2) + 1)) \\
 28574 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (4^5)))) \times ((6+7) - (8-9))) & 28574 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) - 1) \\
 28575 &:= ((12 - (3 + ((456 \times 7) - 8))) \times -9) & 28575 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) + (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
 28576 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) & 28576 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) + 1) \\
 28577 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5+6)) \times 7)) - (8+9)) & 28577 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 28578 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (3 + 4)))^{5+6-7}) + (8+9)) & 28578 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6+5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28579 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + ((3 - (4 - 5))^6)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) & 28579 &:= (-9 + (((8 + ((7-6) \times 5))^4) + (3^{2+1}))) \\
 28580 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + ((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times 7) - 89) & 28580 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (((7+6)^{5-4+3}) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 28581 &:= ((-12 \times (((345 - 6) \times -7) - 8)) + 9) & 28581 &:= (((-9 \times (87 + 65))) - (4+3)) \times -((-21))) \\
 28582 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + ((6+7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 28582 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times ((6-5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 28583 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 + ((4+5) \times 6)) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) & 28583 &:= ((9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((65 \times 432) - 1))) \\
 28584 &:= ((((-1^2) + (34 \times -56)) \times -((7+8))) + 9) & 28584 &:= (-((9 \times 8)) \times ((-76) \times (5-4) - ((321)))) \\
 28585 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5+6))) \times -7) - (8+9)) & 28585 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5+4)) + 3)) - 2))) + 1) \\
 28586 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 \times (4^5)) + ((6+7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 28586 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times ((6-5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 28587 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times ((6+7) - (8-9)))) & 28587 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6+5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 28588 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 - (4^5)) \times ((6+7) - (8-9)))) & 28588 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6+5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\
 28589 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4}) - (5+6)) \times 7) - (8-9)) & 28589 &:= (((-98 \times 7) + (((6+5)^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 28590 &:= ((((-1 - ((2 + (3+4) - 5)^6)) \times -7) - 89) & 28590 &:= (((-9 - (8+7)) - (6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2))) \times -1) \\
 28591 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8+9))))))) & 28591 &:= ((-98 \times 7) + (((6+5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 28592 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 \times (8+9)))))) & 28592 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7+6) \times 5) \times ((4+3)^2)))) - 1) \\
 28593 &:= -(((1 - ((-2 \times 3) + (456 \times 7) - 8)) \times -(-9))) & 28593 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times ((6-5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28594 &:= -((((12^3) - (45 - 6)) - 7) \times (-8 - 9)) & 28594 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6+5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28595 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - (5+6)) \times -(7 \times (8-9))) & 28595 &:= (-((9 - (8 \times (7+6)))) \times ((5 \times -4) + (321)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28596 &:= (12 \times (((3^4) \times 5) \times 6) + ((7 \times -8) + 9)) \\
 28597 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28598 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28599 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + (3 + 4)) - 5)^6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28600 &:= ((((-1 \times ((2 + 3) - (4 + 5)))^6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28601 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 \times (4^5)) + ((6 + 7) \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28602 &:= ((1 \times ((-((2 \times 3)) + (456 \times 7)) - 8)) \times -(-9)) \\
 28603 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6))) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 28604 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 - 5))^6)) \times -7) - 89) \\
 28605 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 28606 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28607 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3 \times (4+5-6)})) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9) \\
 28608 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 + 4)^{5+6-7}) - (8 + 9))) \\
 28609 &:= (-1 \times (2 + (((3 - 456) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 28610 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) - ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9) \\
 28611 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 28612 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 28613 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) - 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28614 &:= (((12/3)^4 - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 28615 &:= ((1 + ((2 + ((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 28616 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5! / 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 28617 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))))) \\
 28618 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times ((6 \times 78) + 9)))))) \\
 28619 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6))) \times -7) + (8 + 9)) \\
 28620 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4+5}) - 6)) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28621 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3 \times 4})) - 5) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) - 9) \\
 28622 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - 6) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
 28623 &:= (((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - 6) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9))) \\
 28624 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - 6) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 28625 &:= (-1 \times (-((234 - 5) \times (6 - (-7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 28626 &:= (((-(((12^3)/4) + 5) \times -67) + (8 + 9)) \\
 28627 &:= -(((1 \times 2) + ((3 - ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\
 28628 &:= ((1 - 2) - (((-3 + (456 \times 7)) - 8) \times -9)) \\
 28629 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (((-3 + (456 \times 7)) - 8) \times -9)) \\
 28630 &:= -(((1 - 2) + (((-3 + (456 \times 7)) - 8) \times -9))) \\
 28631 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((3 - ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28632 &:= -(((12 \times 34) + ((-56 \times (7 \times 8)) \times 9))) \\
 28633 &:= ((1 \times -23) + (((456 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 28634 &:= -(((1 - 23)) + ((-((456 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28596 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\
 28597 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 28598 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 28599 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\
 28600 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3+2+1}))) \\
 28601 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 28602 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2) + 1))) \\
 28603 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + ((5 + (4^3))^2))) + 1) \\
 28604 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!) \times 6 + 5 - (4 + 3)! / (2 + 1) \\
 28605 &:= ((9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\
 28606 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 - 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\
 28607 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 - 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28608 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 28609 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) + 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 28610 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 6)) \times -((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1) \\
 28611 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + 2)) - 1)) \\
 28612 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 - 1 \\
 28613 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 28614 &:= -9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 + 1 \\
 28615 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 \times 3)))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 28616 &:= (-98 \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1)))))) \\
 28617 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 \times 3)))) + 2)) + 1) \\
 28618 &:= (9 - (((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1))) \\
 28619 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + 2))) - 1) \\
 28620 &:= (((9 + (8 \times -7)) - 6) \times -((543 - 2) + 1)) \\
 28621 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + 2))) + 1) \\
 28622 &:= (((987 \times (65 - (4 + 32))) - 1)) \\
 28623 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -((5^4) - ((3^2) + 1))) \\
 28624 &:= ((-987 \times -((6 \times 5) + (4 - (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 28625 &:= (((-((9 - 87) \times -(65 + 432))) - 1) \\
 28626 &:= (((987 \times (6 + ((5 \times 4) + 3))) + 2) - (-1)) \\
 28627 &:= (((-((9 - 87) \times -(65 + 432))) + 1) \\
 28628 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5 - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28629 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1)) \\
 28630 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 - 1 \\
 28631 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 \times 1 \\
 28632 &:= 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times (5 + 4^3)^2 + 1 \\
 28633 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + 6)^{(5+4+3)/(2+1)})) \\
 28634 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + 6)^{5+4-3-2}) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28635 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6)) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28636 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4+5}) - 6)) \times -7) + (8 - 9)) \\ 28637 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3+4+5}) - 6)) \times (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 28638 &:= (((1^2) + (-3 + ((456 \times 7) - 8))) \times 9) \\ 28639 &:= -((((1 + (2^3)) \times (456 \times -7)) + 89)) \\ 28640 &:= ((((-1 + (2^{3+4+5})) - 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 28641 &:= (12 + ((3 - ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times -9)) \\ 28642 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) + 6) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28643 &:= ((-12 + (((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28644 &:= (-12 + (((((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28645 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times 7)))))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 28646 &:= -((1 - (((2 - 3) + ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 28647 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) - 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 28648 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + (3 + 4)) - 5)^6) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28649 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) + (((456 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28650 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + ((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\ 28651 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times -7) \times (8 - 9))) \\ 28652 &:= (((-1 - 2) + (((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28653 &:= (((1 - 2) \times 3) + (((456 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28654 &:= (-1 + ((2 - 3) + (((456 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 28655 &:= -((((1 + 2)/3) + (((456 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28656 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (3 \times (456 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28657 &:= (((1 + 2)/3) + (((456 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28658 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 - 6))) \times -7) \times (8 - 9)) \\ 28659 &:= (-(-123) \times ((-4 \times ((5 - 6) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 28660 &:= (-1 - (-2 + (-3 - (((456 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\ 28661 &:= (-1 - (-((2 \times 3)) - (((456 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 28662 &:= (-1 \times (-((2 \times 3)) - (((456 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 28663 &:= (-1 - (((((2^3)^4) + (5 - 6)) \times -7) - ((8 - 9)))) \\ 28664 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + (3 + 4)) - 5)^6) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\ 28665 &:= -((((1 \times 2) - (3 + (456 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 28666 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - ((4^5) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9)))) \\ 28667 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) - (5 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 28668 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + ((3 - (4 - 5))^6) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 28669 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 - 6))) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28670 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28671 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) \times (5 - ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9)))) \\ 28672 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3) \times 4^{5 \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9} \\ 28673 &:= ((((-1 \times ((2 + 3) - (4 + 5)))^6) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28635 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + 6)^{5-4+3}) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 28636 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + 6)^{5-4+3}) + (2 + 1))) \\ 28637 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28638 &:= (-9 \times (8 - (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 28639 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - (3^{2+1})))))) \\ 28640 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\ 28641 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 - 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\ 28642 &:= (((-9 - (87 \times 6)) \times -54) - (32 \times 1)) \\ 28643 &:= (((-9 + 87) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2))) - 1) \\ 28644 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2))) - 1) \\ 28645 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3)/2) - 1)) \\ 28646 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5 - (4^{3 \times 2})))) \times -1) \\ 28647 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - ((7 + 6) \times ((5 + 4)^3))) \times -(2 + 1)) \\ 28648 &:= ((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 - 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28649 &:= ((-9 - 8) - ((7 \times ((6 - 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\ 28650 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 28651 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) + 1))) \\ 28652 &:= ((987 + ((6 - 5))) \times -((4 - 32) + 1)) \\ 28653 &:= (9 + ((8 + 76) \times ((5 \times 4) + 321))) \\ 28654 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3 \times 2}))) - 1) \\ 28655 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3+2+1}))) \\ 28656 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + ((76 \times -5) \times 4)) \times (3 - ((21)))) \\ 28657 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 - 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\ 28658 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6 - 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 28659 &:= ((-98 - ((7 + 6)^{5+4-3-2})) \times -1) \\ 28660 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)))) \\ 28661 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 - 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 28662 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 - 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28663 &:= ((-9 + (8^{(7-6) \times 5})) - (4^{3+2+1})) \\ 28664 &:= ((-9 + 8) - (7 \times ((6 - 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28665 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times ((6 - 5) - (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 28666 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((((6 + 5) - 4) \times 3)^2)) + 1) \\ 28667 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28668 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\ 28669 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 - 5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 28670 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6 - ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 28671 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3+2+1}))) \\ 28672 &:= ((-9 - (8/(7 - (6 + 5)))) \times -4^{3+2+1}) \\ 28673 &:= (((-9 - (8/(7 - (6 + 5)))) \times -4^{3 \times 2}) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28674 &:= ((-1-2) \times -((3^4) \times ((5-6) + (7 \times (8+9)))))) \\ 28675 &:= (1 + ((2 \times 3) \times (45 + (6 \times 789)))) \\ 28676 &:= (((-1-2) - ((3 - (4-5))^6)) \times -7) - (8+9) \\ 28677 &:= ((1+2) \times (((3 \times (456 \times 7)) - 8) - 9)) \\ 28678 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3^{4-5+6})) \times (7 \times (8+9)))) \\ 28679 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^{4-5+6})) \times (7 \times (8+9))) \\ 28680 &:= (-12 \times (((345 - 6) \times -7) - 8) - 9) \\ 28681 &:= -((-(-1) \times (2 - ((3 + ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 28682 &:= (-(-1) - (2 - ((3 + ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 28683 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 - (3+4)))^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9) \\ 28684 &:= ((-1+2) - (-((3 + ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 28685 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5-6))) \times -7) + (8-9)) \\ 28686 &:= ((1+2) + ((3 + ((456 \times 7) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 28687 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 - (4-5))^6) \times 7) + (8+9)) \\ 28688 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + (3+4)) - 5)^6) \times 7) + (8+9))) \\ 28689 &:= ((((-1 \times ((2+3) - (4+5)))^6) \times 7) + (8+9)) \\ 28690 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6)) \times 7) - (8+9)) \\ 28691 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (((3 - (4-5))^6) \times 7) + (8+9)) \\ 28692 &:= ((-1 - (((2+3)^4) \times 5) + (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times -9) \\ 28693 &:= (((-1-2) - ((3 - (4-5))^6)) \times (7 \times (8-9))) \\ 28694 &:= ((((-1-2) - ((3 - (4-5))^6)) \times -7) - (8-9)) \\ 28695 &:= (((1+2) \times ((3 \times (456 \times 7)) - 8)) - 9) \\ 28696 &:= ((1 - (2 - (-3 \times (4 - (567)))))) \times -((-8-9)) \\ 28697 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3+4+5}) + 6) \times 7) - (8+9)) \\ 28698 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times (6 - (7-8))) - 9) \\ 28699 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 - ((5 - (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 28700 &:= (((-1+2) + (3^4)) \times (5 + ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\ 28701 &:= ((12 + (((-3 - (-4+5))^6) \times 7)) + (8+9)) \\ 28702 &:= ((-1 + (2^{3+4})) \times (5 + ((6+7) \times (8+9)))) \\ 28703 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5-6))) \times -7) + (8+9)) \\ 28704 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6)) \times -7) - (8+9)) \\ 28705 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times -(6 - (7-8))) - 9) \\ 28706 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6)) \times 7) + (8-9)) \\ 28707 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6)) \times -(7 \times (8-9))) \\ 28708 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6)) \times 7) - (8-9)) \\ 28709 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4+5}) - 6)) \times -7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 28710 &:= ((((-1-2) - ((3 - (4-5))^6)) \times -7) + (8+9)) \\ 28711 &:= ((-1+2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28712 &:= ((1-2) + ((-3 \times (4 - (567)))) \times -((-8-9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28674 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) + ((5^4) \times (3+2))) - 1) \\ 28675 &:= (((-9 - (87 \times 6)) \times -(5 + ((4+3)^2))) + 1) \\ 28676 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6+5) + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 28677 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6+5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28678 &:= ((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6-5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28679 &:= (((-9+8) \times 7) \times -((6-5) + (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 28680 &:= ((((-9+8) \times 7) \times -((6-5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\ 28681 &:= ((-9 - ((8^{(7-6) \times 5}) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1) \\ 28682 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) + ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) - 1) \\ 28683 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) + (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\ 28684 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) + ((5^4) \times (3+2)))) + 1) \\ 28685 &:= ((-9+8) + (7 \times ((6-5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 28686 &:= (((9-8) \times 7) \times ((6 - (5 - ((4^3)^2))) + 1)) \\ 28687 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7+6) - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1))) \\ 28688 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7+6) - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1)) \\ 28689 &:= (((-9-8) - (7 \times (((6-5) \times 4)^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1) \\ 28690 &:= (9 + (((8+7) \times (((6^5)/4) - 32)) + 1)) \\ 28691 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7-6)) \times ((5 + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1))) \\ 28692 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times 7) + 6) + (((5^4) \times (3+2)) + 1))) \\ 28693 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times ((6+5) - (4^{3 \times 2})))) \times -1) \\ 28694 &:= (98 - ((7 \times ((6+5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\ 28695 &:= (((-9-8) \times -(7 + ((6 + (5 \times (4+3)))^2))) - 1) \\ 28696 &:= ((-9-8) \times -(7 + ((6 + (5 \times (4+3)))^2 \times 1))) \\ 28697 &:= (((-9-8) \times -(7 + ((6 + (5 \times (4+3)))^2))) + 1) \\ 28698 &:= (-9 + ((8 - (7-6)) \times (5 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28699 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7-6)) \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\ 28700 &:= ((-9 \times -((8+7) + (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\ 28701 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times ((6 \times 54) - (-3 \times (2 \times 1)))))) \\ 28702 &:= ((((-9-8) \times (7+6)) - 5) \times -(((4^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 28703 &:= ((9+8) + (7 \times ((6-5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 28704 &:= ((((-9+8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5^4) - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 28705 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7+6) - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) \times -1) \\ 28706 &:= ((987 - (65 - 4)) \times (32 - 1)) \\ 28707 &:= ((987 \times (6 \times 5)) + (-43) \times (21)) \\ 28708 &:= (((((9-8)^7) + 6) \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\ 28709 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5+4)) + 3))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 28710 &:= (-9 \times (8 - ((7+6) \times ((5 \times ((4+3)^2) + 1)))) \\ 28711 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5+4)) + 3))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 28712 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 76) \times -((5 \times 43) - 21)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28713 &:= (((1+2) \times ((3 \times (456 \times 7)) - 8)) + 9) \\ 28714 &:= (((((1^2) + 3) \times (4^5)) + 6) \times (-7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 28715 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) + 6) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 28716 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) + 9) \\ 28717 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5) \times (6 - (7 - 8))) + 9) \\ 28718 &:= (-12 + (-(-34) \times -((-56 - 789)))) \\ 28719 &:= (((((1 \times 2) - (3 + 456)) \times 7) + 8) \times -9) \\ 28720 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6)) \times -7) + (8 - 9)) \\ 28721 &:= (1 + 2^{3+4+5} + 6) \times 7 \times (-8 + 9) \\ 28722 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3+4+5}) + 6)) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 28723 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 5)) \times -(6 - (7 - 8))) + 9) \\ 28724 &:= ((-(((123 \times -4) + 5)) \times (67 - 8)) - 9) \\ 28725 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((3 \times (456 \times 7)) + 8) - 9)) \\ 28726 &:= (-1 + (((((2^3) \times -((456 - 7))) \times -8) - 9))) \\ 28727 &:= ((1 \times (((2^3) \times -((456 - 7))) \times -8)) - 9) \\ 28728 &:= (((1 \times (2^3)) - (456 \times 7)) - 8) \times -9) \\ 28729 &:= ((1 - 2) - (34 \times (-56 - 789))) \\ 28730 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4+5}) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 28731 &:= ((-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6)) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28732 &:= (1 + (((2^{3+4+5}) + 6) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 28733 &:= (((-123 \times 4) + 5) \times -((6 \times 7) + (8 + 9))) \\ 28734 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 + (4! \times 5! - 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28735 &:= (-12 + (-((3 \times 4) - (5 \times 67))) \times 89) \\ 28736 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 - 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 28737 &:= (1 \times (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 - 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 28738 &:= (1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 - 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 28739 &:= (((((-1 - ((2^3)^4) - 5) - 6) \times -7) - 8) - 9) \\ 28740 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 + 4)^{5+6-7})) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28741 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6))) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\ 28742 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4^5)))) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))) \\ 28743 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6))) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 28744 &:= (-1 - (2 + (-((3 \times 4) - ((5 \times 67)))) \times -89))) \\ 28745 &:= ((1 \times (((2^3) \times -((456 - 7))) \times -8)) + 9) \\ 28746 &:= ((-12^3) + ((4 + (5 \times -(678))) \times -9)) \\ 28747 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times (-((3 \times 4) + ((5 \times 67)))) \times 89) \\ 28748 &:= (-1 - (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 28749 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + ((5^{6+7-8} \times 9))) \\ 28750 &:= ((1 + 2) - (-((3 \times 4) + (5 \times 67)) \times -89)) \\ 28751 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + (3 + 4) - 5)^6)) \times -7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 28752 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3)^4) - 5) \times ((6 + (7 + 8)) - 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28713 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(7 + (((6 + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^2) + 1))) \\ 28714 &:= (-98 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 + (2 + 1))))))) \\ 28715 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 2)))))) + 1) \\ 28716 &:= ((-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5 + (4^{3 \times 2})))) \times -1) \\ 28717 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - ((3^2) - 1)))) \\ 28718 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((65 \times (4 + 3)) + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28719 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3))) - (2 - 1))) \\ 28720 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((65 \times (4 + 3)) + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28721 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (76 \times 54)) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 28722 &:= (-9 + 8! / (7 \times 6) \times 5 - 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 28723 &:= (9 + ((8 - (7 - 6)) \times (5 + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 28724 &:= -9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 28725 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28726 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 28727 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 28728 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times (6 + ((5 + (4 \times 3)) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 28729 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)))) + (2 - 1)) \\ 28730 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times (5 - ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 28731 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 28732 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28733 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})))) + 1) \\ 28734 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28735 &:= (-(((-9 + 8) - (76 \times 54))) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 28736 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 28737 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (7 \times ((6 - 5) - (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28738 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 28739 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 28740 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 28741 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2}) - 1))) \\ 28742 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2}) - 1)) \\ 28743 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3 \times 2})) - 1) \\ 28744 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3+2+1}))) \\ 28745 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\ 28746 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 28747 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 28748 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28749 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + 5) + (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 28750 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\ 28751 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 - 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28752 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

- 28753** := $(-((-1 + ((-2^3) \times (456 - 7))) \times 8)) + 9$
28754 := $(-1 + (((23 \times (4 + 5)) + 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))$
28755 := $(((-1 - 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 \times 6))) \times -((7 + 8) \times 9))$
28756 := $((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 + (4^5)) \times ((6 + 7) - (8 - 9))))$
28757 := $(((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6))) \times -7) - (8 - 9))$
28758 := $(((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 - 6))) \times -7) + (8 \times 9))$
28759 := $(12 + (-(((3 \times 4) - (5 \times 67))) \times 89))$
28760 := $(((-12 \times 3) - 4) \times -(5 + (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))$
28761 := $(-12 + (((3 - (456 \times 7)) - 8) \times -9))$
28762 := $((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))$
28763 := $(-1 + ((2 + 34) \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))))$
28764 := $(((-1 - (2^3)) \times (4 \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times (-8 - 9))$
28765 := $(-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9))$
28766 := $((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)$
28767 := $(12 - ((3^-(4)) \times (-5 \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times -9))))$
28768 := $(1 + ((23 - (4 \times -5)) \times (678 - 9)))$
28769 := $(1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) - (5 - 6)) \times 7) + 89))$
28770 := $(-((1 + 2) - (((-3 + (456 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9)))$
28771 := $(-1 \times (2 + ((3 - ((456 \times 7) + 8)) \times 9)))$
28772 := $((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9))$
28773 := $((-1 \times 23) \times (-(((4 \times 5) \times 67)) + 89))$
28774 := $(-((1 - 2) - (-((3 - ((456 \times 7) + 8))) \times -9))$
28775 := $(-((1 \times -2) + (((-3 + (456 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))$
28776 := $(-((1 + 23) - (-(((456 \times 7) + 8)) \times -9))$
28777 := $(-((1 \times 23) - (((456 \times 7) + 8) \times -(-9)))$
28778 := $((1 - 23) + (((456 \times 7) + 8) \times 9))$
28779 := $((1 + 2) \times (((3 \times (456 \times 7)) + 8) + 9))$
28780 := $(-1 \times (2 + ((3 - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (78 \times 9))))$
28781 := $((-1 + ((-2 - 34) \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) \times (-8 - 9))$
28782 := $(((-1 - 2) \times -(-3)) \times ((45 - 6) \times -((7 - 89))))$
28783 := $(((-1 - ((2 + ((3 \times (4^5))/6)) \times 7)) \times -8) - 9)$
28784 := $(-((-1 \times 2) + ((-345) - 6) \times (7 - 89)))$
28785 := $(12 + (((3 - (456 \times 7)) - 8) \times -9))$
28786 := $((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4+5}) + 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9))$
28787 := $((((1 + 2)^3) \times (4^5)) + (67 \times (8 + 9)))$
28788 := $(-12 + (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9)$
28789 := $(-1 - ((-2 - 3) \times ((4^5) + (-6 \times -(789))))$
28790 := $(((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 + 4)^5)) - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))$
28791 := $((12^3) - (((45 \times 67) - 8) \times -9))$
28792 := $((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) - 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9))$
- 28753** := $((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1)$
28754 := $((-9 \times -(8 + ((7 \times (65 \times (4 + 3))) + 2))) - 1)$
28755 := $(-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times (5 \times (4 + 3))) + (2 + 1))))$
28756 := $(-((98 - 7)) \times ((6 - 5) + (4 - (321))))$
28757 := $(((-98 + 7) \times -(6 + (5 \times ((4^3) - 2)))) + 1)$
28758 := $((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 - 5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))))$
28759 := $(-9 - ((8 \times (7 - 65)) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1))))$
28760 := $((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - 2))) - 1)$
28761 := $(-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1))))$
28762 := $(-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1))$
28763 := $((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 4) \times -(3^2)) - 1)$
28764 := $((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times (54 - 3)) \times (2 \times 1))$
28765 := $((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) + 5) \times 4) \times -(3^2)) + 1)$
28766 := $(((-9 - 8) - (7 \times ((6 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})))) \times -1)$
28767 := $(-9 - (8 \times (((76 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1)))$
28768 := $(9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! \times 5 - 4! / (3 + 2 + 1))$
28769 := $((98 + (7 \times ((65 - (4 - 3))^2))) - 1)$
28770 := $((-98 - (7 \times (((6 - 5) \times 4)^{3 \times 2}))) \times -1)$
28771 := $(((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1)$
28772 := $((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))$
28773 := $(-9 \times -((8 + ((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)$
28774 := $((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -(4 + 3)) - (2 + 1))$
28775 := $(-9 + ((-8 + (-76) \times 54)) \times ((3 \times -2) - 1))$
28776 := $(-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1))))$
28777 := $(((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -((4 + 3) \times (2 - 1)))$
28778 := $((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1))))$
28779 := $((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) - 2))) \times -1)$
28780 := $((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times -(4 + 3)) + (2 + 1))$
28781 := $((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)$
28782 := $(-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1))))$
28783 := $((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)$
28784 := $((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1))$
28785 := $((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2) + 1)$
28786 := $(9 + 8 - 7) \times 6! - 5 \times 4 + 3 + 2 + 1$
28787 := $(9 - 8 + (7! + 6!)) \times 5 - 4! + 3 + 2 + 1$
28788 := $((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) - (2 + 1))$
28789 := $((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times 1))$
28790 := $((-9 + (8 \times (((7 - (6 + 5)) + (4^3))^2))) - 1)$
28791 := $(-9 \times -(8 + (((7 + 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))$
28792 := $(-9 + ((8 \times (((7 - (6 + 5)) + (4^3))^2)) + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28793 &:= ((1 - 2^3) + (((456 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28794 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 28795 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) - 5)) \times 6)) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 28796 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -(5 + ((6 \times 7) + (8 - 9)))) \\
 28797 &:= (((1 - 2) \times 3) - (-((456 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28798 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3^{4-5+6})) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28799 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 \times (((6 + 7) - 8) \times 9)))) \\
 28800 &:= (((1 + 2) \times (3 \times (456 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 28801 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28802 &:= (((1 - 2) + 3) - (-((456 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28803 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3)^4) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 - 8))) - 9) \\
 28804 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) + (((456 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28805 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 28806 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (3 + (4 \times (((56 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 28807 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (((456 - 7) \times 8) + 9))) \\
 28808 &:= ((1 \times (2^3)) + (((456 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28809 &:= (((1 \times 2) - (3 + (456 \times 7))) - 8) \times -9) \\
 28810 &:= (-(-1) + ((-2 + (3 + ((456 \times 7) + 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28811 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) - (5 + 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\
 28812 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - 345)) \times ((67 + 8) + 9)) \\
 28813 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 + 4)^{5+6-7})) - (8 - 9)) \\
 28814 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6))) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 28815 &:= ((1 - ((-2 \times 34) \times -5)) \times ((-6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 28816 &:= (1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4 + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 28817 &:= (((-1 - (2^3)) \times (456 \times -7)) + 89) \\
 28818 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times -9) \\
 28819 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times ((5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)) \\
 28820 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 + 6)) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 28821 &:= ((((-1 + (2^3)^4) \times ((5 + 6) - (7 - 8))) + 9) \\
 28822 &:= ((-1 + 23) + (((456 \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 28823 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28824 &:= ((1 + 23) + (-(((456 \times 7) + 8) \times -9)) \\
 28825 &:= ((1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4^5) - 6789)) \\
 28826 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 28827 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 - (-((456 \times 7) + (-8))) \times -9)) \\
 28828 &:= (-1 - (-2 + (-((3 + ((456 \times 7) + 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28829 &:= (-1 \times (-2 + (-((3 + ((456 \times 7) + 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28830 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + ((456 \times 7) + 8)) \times 9)) \\
 28831 &:= (((-((-1 - (((-2^3)^4) + 5))) + 6) \times 7) + 89)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28793 &:= (-9 + (((((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 28794 &:= (-9 + (((((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 28795 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(((6 + (5 \times 43)) \times 2) + 1)) \\
 28796 &:= (((-987 - 6) \times -(((5 + 4) \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \\
 28797 &:= ((((-9 - (87 - 6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 28798 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) - 1) \\
 28799 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 - (6 + 5)) + (4^3))^2) + 1)) \\
 28800 &:= (((-9 - (8 + (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times -((4^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 28801 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times -(((7 + 6) - 5) + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1) \\
 28802 &:= ((((-9 - (87 - 6)) \times 5) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 28803 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1))) \\
 28804 &:= (-987 + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 28805 &:= (((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 - 4)) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\
 28806 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + (2 - 1)))) \\
 28807 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times (4^3)) - 2) \times -1) \\
 28808 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times -(((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)) \\
 28809 &:= ((9 \times -((-8 - (76 \times 5))/4)) \times (32 - (-1))) \\
 28810 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28811 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 28812 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 - ((5^4) - (3 \times 2)))) + 1) \\
 28813 &:= (((-98 \times (7 - (6 - 5))) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 28814 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1))) \\
 28815 &:= ((-98 \times (7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 \times 3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 28816 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (6 \times 543))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28817 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) \times -1) \\
 28818 &:= (-9 \times (((8 + 7) - 65) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28819 &:= (-98) - (-(((7 \times 65) + 4)) \times (3 \times (21))) \\
 28820 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\
 28821 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28822 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((6 + 5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\
 28823 &:= -9 + 8 + (7! + 6!) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28824 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 21)))) \\
 28825 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) + (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)))) \\
 28826 &:= ((98 + ((76 \times 54) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\
 28827 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + (5 \times 4)) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\
 28828 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 + 5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 28829 &:= (((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -(((4^3) \times 2) - 1)) \\
 28830 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 76)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 28831 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 76)) \times 5) \times -((4^3) - 2)) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28832 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (34 \times ((5 \times 67) + 89))) \\ 28833 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 + 6) - 7) \times 89))) \\ 28834 &:= ((1 \times -2) - ((3^4) \times (((-5 - 6) + 7) \times 89))) \\ 28835 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) + (5^{6+7-8}))) \times 9)) \\ 28836 &:= ((-((1 \times 2)) \times (3 \times (456 + 78))) \times -9) \\ 28837 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 + 6) - 7) \times 89))) \\ 28838 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 + 6) - 7) \times 89))) \\ 28839 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 - 9)) \\ 28840 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times -(((4^5) + 6) \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 28841 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 28842 &:= (-12 + (((3^4) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28843 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 + 456) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28844 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((-3 - 456) \times 7) + 8) \times -9)) \\ 28845 &:= (((12 - 3) \times ((45 + 6) \times 7)) - 8) \times -(-9)) \\ 28846 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 + 456) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28847 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3 + 456) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28848 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28849 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) + 5) \times 6) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 28850 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28851 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 28852 &:= (1 \times (-2 - ((3 - 45) \times (678 + 9)))) \\ 28853 &:= (1 - (2 + ((3 - 45) \times (678 + 9)))) \\ 28854 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4^5) + (6 \times 7))) - (8 \times -9)) \\ 28855 &:= ((1^2) - ((3 - 45) \times (678 + 9))) \\ 28856 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((3 - 45) \times (678 + 9))) \\ 28857 &:= (1 - (-2 + ((3 - 45) \times (678 + 9)))) \\ 28858 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28859 &:= (-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) - 5)) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28860 &:= (((1 - (2 \times -34)) + 5) \times (6 \times (-7 - (-8 \times 9)))) \\ 28861 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 4)) \times -(5 - ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28862 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3 + 456)) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28863 &:= (((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) + (5^{6+7-8}))) \times 9) \\ 28864 &:= (((12 \times -34) + 56) \times (7 - 89)) \\ 28865 &:= (1 - (((2^3) \times -((4 \times (5 + 6)))) \times (-7 + 89))) \\ 28866 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 28867 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (34 \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) + 9))) \\ 28868 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (34 \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) + 9)))) \\ 28869 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 + 45) \times 67) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28870 &:= ((1 \times -2) + (((-3 - 45) \times 67) + 8) \times -9)) \\ 28871 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3^4) + (5^{6+7-8}))) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28832 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times 65))/4)) \times (32 \times 1)) \\ 28833 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) - (4^3)) \times -21) \\ 28834 &:= -9 + 8 \times (7 + 6! \times 5) - 4 - 3 - (2 + 1)! \\ 28835 &:= (((9 \times -((8 + 76) + 5))) \times (-4 - (32))) - (1)) \\ 28836 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)))) \\ 28837 &:= (((9 \times -((8 + 76) + 5))) \times (-4 - (32))) + (1)) \\ 28838 &:= ((9 + (((87 + 6) \times 5) \times ((4^3) - 2))) - 1) \\ 28839 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2))) \times -1) \\ 28840 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) - 1)) \\ 28841 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 28842 &:= ((((-98 - 76) \times 5) - 4) \times -(32 + 1)) \\ 28843 &:= (9 + 8!/(7!/6!)) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 28844 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 + 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 28845 &:= ((-(-9) \times ((8 - 7) - 6)) \times ((-5 \times (4 \times 32)) - 1)) \\ 28846 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 + 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 28847 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\ 28848 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1))) \\ 28849 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1) \\ 28850 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 28851 &:= (9 + 8!/7) \times (6 - 5 + 4) + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 28852 &:= -9 + (8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 + (4 + 3) \times (2 + 1) \\ 28853 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times 6) + 5) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 28854 &:= (((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 65) + 4))) \times (-3 \times (21))) \\ 28855 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 - 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28856 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -(6 + (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\ 28857 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28858 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 28859 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28860 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 + (5 + (432 + 1)))) \\ 28861 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) + 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 28862 &:= ((-9 \times -(87)) - (-((65 \times 432) + 1)) \\ 28863 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)) + 2)) - 1)) \\ 28864 &:= (((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 28865 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 28866 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1)) \\ 28867 &:= (9 + 8 + 7! + 6!) \times 5 - 4! + 3 + 2 + 1 \\ 28868 &:= ((((-98 \times (7 \times 6)) - 5) \times -(4 + 3)) + 21) \\ 28869 &:= (9 + 8!/(7!/6!)) \times 5 + 4 \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 28870 &:= 9 \times 8 + (7! + 6!) \times 5 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 1 \\ 28871 &:= (((-9 \times -8) \times ((7 \times ((6 + 54) - 3)) + 2)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28872 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6))) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 28873 &:= (1 + (((2^3) + ((456 \times 7) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 28874 &:= (1 \times (2 - (((3 + 45) \times -67) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 28875 &:= ((1 + 2) + (-(((3 + 45) \times -67) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 28876 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 28877 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4 \times 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 28878 &:= (12 + (34 \times (((5 + 6) \times 78) - 9))) \\ 28879 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) - 9 \\ 28880 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\ 28881 &:= (-(-(1 + 2)) \times (3 \times ((456 \times 7) + (8 + 9)))) \\ 28882 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 28883 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 28884 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((-34 + 5) \times (-6 - (7 \times (-8 \times 9)))) \\ 28885 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 28886 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 28887 &:= (((((-1 + 2) \times 3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 28888 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 28889 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 28890 &:= (((12 + 3) \times ((45 \times -6) + (7 \times 8))) \times -9) \\ 28891 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times (345 \times (6 \times 7))) - 89)) \\ 28892 &:= ((-(-1) - (-((2 \times 345) \times (6 \times 7))) - 89) \\ 28893 &:= (-12 - (3 \times (4 - (567 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 28894 &:= 1 \times 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 28895 &:= ((((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 28896 &:= (-12 \times ((-34 \times 56) - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 28897 &:= ((((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) \\ 28898 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) \\ 28899 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 + 9) \\ 28900 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 28901 &:= ((-12 \times -((3 + 4)^{5+6-7})) + 89) \\ 28902 &:= (-1 - (2 - (3 \times (-4 + (567 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 28903 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (3 \times (-4 + (567 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 28904 &:= ((12^3) + (4 \times (5 + 6789))) \\ 28905 &:= ((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 + ((5 \times -((6 + 7))) \times 89))) \\ 28906 &:= (-1 + (2 + (3 \times (-4 + (567 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 28907 &:= (-1 - (-((2 \times (345 \times 6))) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 28908 &:= (-1 \times (-((2 \times (345 \times 6))) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 28909 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (345 \times (6 \times 7)))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 28910 &:= ((1 \times 2 + 3)! \times 4! + 5 + 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 28911 &:= ((-((12 \times 34)) - (5 + 6)) \times -((78 - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28872 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\ 28873 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times ((7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)) + 2))) + 1) \\ 28874 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1))) \\ 28875 &:= ((-9 + (8 - 76)) \times (-54 - ((321)))) \\ 28876 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})) - 1))) \\ 28877 &:= (-9 - ((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) - 1))) \\ 28878 &:= -9 - 8 + 7! \times 6 - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 28879 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 \times 6) \times ((5^4) + (3 \times 21)))) \\ 28880 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 28881 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + ((6 \times 5) + 4)) \times 321)) \\ 28882 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 28883 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\ 28884 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 28885 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\ 28886 &:= (((-9 + ((8 \times 7) + 6)) \times (543 + 2)) + 1) \\ 28887 &:= (-9 + (-8 \times (((7 \times 6) \times (54 + 32)) \times -1))) \\ 28888 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\ 28889 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2)) - 1) \\ 28890 &:= ((9 - ((8 + 7))) \times -(((6 + 5) + 4) \times (321))) \\ 28891 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) - 2)) + 1) \\ 28892 &:= (-9 + (((((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4))/3)^2) + 1)) \\ 28893 &:= (9 + (87 \times (((6 \times 54) + (3^2)) - 1))) \\ 28894 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) - 1) \\ 28895 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1))) \\ 28896 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + 6) + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2))) + 1)) \\ 28897 &:= ((((-9 \times 87) - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times -32) + 1) \\ 28898 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 28899 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 28900 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + ((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\ 28901 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times (5 - (4 + 3)))^2) + 1) \\ 28902 &:= (9 + 8 + 7! - 6! + 5! \times 4) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 28903 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)))) \\ 28904 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -5 \times (43 - 2)) - 1) \\ 28905 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6 - ((5^4) - ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 28906 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 6) \times -5 \times (43 - 2)) + 1) \\ 28907 &:= ((-9 \times -87 + ((6 - (5 - 4))^{3+2})) - 1) \\ 28908 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (((6 + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1))) \\ 28909 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times 5) + 4))/3)^2) \times -1) \\ 28910 &:= (-98 \times -(((7 - (6 - 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1)) \\ 28911 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (((7 - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times 32) + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28912 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times ((4^5) + 6) \times 7)) + (8 \times 9) \\
 28913 &:= (-1 + ((((-2^3) \times -45) - (-6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28914 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3^{4-5+6}) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 28915 &:= (1 + ((((-2^3) \times -45) - (-6)) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28916 &:= (-1 + ((23 + 4) \times ((56 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 28917 &:= ((((-1 + 2) \times 3)^{4-5+6}) \times (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28918 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((3^{4-5+6}) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 28919 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^{4-5+6}) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 28920 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times (-4 \times (-(-5) + (((6 \times 78) + 9)))) \\
 28921 &:= (((-((12 \times 345)) + 6) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28922 &:= (1 + (((2 + (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) + 9)) \\
 28923 &:= ((-12 - (3^4)) \times -(-5 + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 28924 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4 + 5))) \times ((6 + 7) \times 89))) \\
 28925 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) - 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 28926 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 28927 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 28928 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 28929 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) \\
 28930 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -((4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\
 28931 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (3 \times (4 + (567 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\
 28932 &:= (-12 - ((3 - (4 + 5)) \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28933 &:= (((-(-1) + (2 \times 345)) \times (6 \times 7)) - 89) \\
 28934 &:= (((12 + 34) \times ((5 \times 6) + 7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 28935 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 28936 &:= ((1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times (67 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 28937 &:= (((12 \times 345) - 6) \times 7) + (8 - 9) \\
 28938 &:= -((((12 \times 345) - 6) \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\
 28939 &:= (((12 \times 345) - 6) \times 7) - (8 - 9) \\
 28940 &:= (-1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4)) \times 5 \times (-6 - 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 28941 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (4 + 5)) \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28942 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - (4 + 5)) \times (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28943 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 28944 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (((3 \times 4) \times (-56 - 78)) \times -9)) \\
 28945 &:= (-1 - (-2 \times (((345 \times 6) \times 7) - 8) - 9)) \\
 28946 &:= (-1 \times (-2 \times (((345 \times 6) \times 7) - 8) - 9)) \\
 28947 &:= (1 - (-2 \times (((345 \times 6) \times 7) - 8) - 9)) \\
 28948 &:= ((1 + 2) \times 3 + 4!) \times (5 + 6!) + 7! - 8 - 9 \\
 28949 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - 5) - (67 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 28950 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\
 28951 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28912 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 + (6 \times (5 + 43)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 28913 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) \times -1) \\
 28914 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times 5)) \times -((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 28915 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) + 2))) + 1) \\
 28916 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -((6^5)/((4^3)/2))) - 1) \\
 28917 &:= (((9 \times -(87)) + (6 \times 54)) \times -((3 \times 21))) \\
 28918 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times -((3 \times 21)))) \\
 28919 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times (32 \times 1)))) \\
 28920 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\
 28921 &:= (9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) + (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)))) \\
 28922 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 76)) \times -(((5^4) - 3)/2)) - 1) \\
 28923 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 76)) \times -(((5^4) - 3)/(2 \times 1))) \\
 28924 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 76)) \times -(((5^4) - 3)/2)) + 1) \\
 28925 &:= (-(((-(9 + 8)) - 7) - (65))) \times ((4 + 321))) \\
 28926 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 28927 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 28928 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 28929 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times (7 + 6)) - 5) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) + 1) \\
 28930 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 28931 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - (76 \times 5)) \times -(4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 28932 &:= ((-9 - ((87 + 6) \times (((5^4) - 3)/2))) \times -1) \\
 28933 &:= (9 + (((87 + 6) \times (((5^4) - 3)/2)) + 1)) \\
 28934 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\
 28935 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 6) + (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
 28936 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 28937 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - (6 \times (5 \times 4))) \times 32))) \times -1) \\
 28938 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times 6) \times -((5 + ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1)) \\
 28939 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -(6 \times (54 - (3 - 2)))) + 1) \\
 28940 &:= (9 + 8 - 7) \times ((6! + 5) \times 4 - 3 - 2 - 1) \\
 28941 &:= -9 + (8!/(7 \times 6) + 5) \times (4! + 3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28942 &:= ((-987 - (6 + 5)) \times (4 - (32 + 1))) \\
 28943 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 - (5 + 4)) \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 28944 &:= ((9 \times 8) \times (((7 - (-6 - 54)) \times 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\
 28945 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times ((76 - (5 + 4)) \times (3 \times 2)))) + 1) \\
 28946 &:= (9 - 8 - 7 \times 6) \times (5 \times 4 - 3! - (2 + 1)!) \\
 28947 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times (((6 \times 5) + (4^{3 \times 2}))) - 1)) \\
 28948 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 - (5! + (4 + 3)!)/(2 + 1)! \\
 28949 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 28950 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28951 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28952 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times 4) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\
 28953 &:= (((-12 - 3) + 45) \times 67) \times -8 + 9 \\
 28954 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((-(345 \times 6)) \times 7) + 8)) + 9) \\
 28955 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times ((-(345 \times 6)) \times 7) + 8)) + 9) \\
 28956 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (345 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\
 28957 &:= 1 + 2 \times ((3 + 4)^5 \times 6/7 + 8 \times 9) \\
 28958 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 \times 4! + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9) \\
 28959 &:= ((-12 \times -(34 \times (56 + (7 + 8)))) - 9) \\
 28960 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!) \times (-4 + 5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 28961 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9 \\
 28962 &:= -((((1 + 2) + ((-3 - 456) \times 7)) - 8) \times 9) \\
 28963 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times (345 \times (6 \times 7))) - (8 + 9))) \\
 28964 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6))) \times 7) + 89) \\
 28965 &:= (12 + (((3^4) + (56 \times (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\
 28966 &:= -1 \times 2 + (3! \times 4! + 5! \times (6 + 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\
 28967 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!) \times (4! + 5 \times 6!) - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 28968 &:= (((-1 - 2) - ((3^{4-5+6}) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 28969 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((345 \times (6 + 78)) - 9))) \\
 28970 &:= (-(-1) + (-2 - ((-345) \times (6 + 78)) + 9)) \\
 28971 &:= (-((123 - (456))) \times (78 + 9)) \\
 28972 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (345 \times 6))) \times 7) + (8 - 9)) \\
 28973 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (345 \times 6))) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9))) \\
 28974 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 + 4)) \times -(5 + (67 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 28975 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4}) + 56) \times 7) - 89 \\
 28976 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 56) \times 7)) - 89) \\
 28977 &:= (-((1 + 2)) + (345 \times (67 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 28978 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4}) + (5 \times 6))) \times -7) + 89) \\
 28979 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (345 \times 6)) \times 7) + (8 - 9) \\
 28980 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times -((345 \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\
 28981 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((345 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9)))) \\
 28982 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times ((345 \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 - 9)))) \\
 28983 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((345 \times 6) \times 7) - 8) + 9)) \\
 28984 &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3! + 4) \times 5!/6) + 7 + 8 + 9 \\
 28985 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (34 \times 5))) \times -((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 28986 &:= (-12 + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\
 28987 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7)) - 89) \\
 28988 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (345 \times 6))) \times -7) - (8 - 9)) \\
 28989 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times ((-(-345)) \times (6 + 78)) + 9) \\
 28990 &:= ((((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times 5)) + 6) \times -(7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 28991 &:= (((-1 \times -2) + (-(-345)) \times (6 + 78)) + 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28952 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 28953 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - 3))) + (2 - 1)) \\
 28954 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\
 28955 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 28956 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) - 1))) \\
 28957 &:= (9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5 \times (4 + 3)^{2+1} \\
 28958 &:= -9 + 8 - 7 \times (6 \times (5!/4 - 3!)) + 2 + 1 \\
 28959 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times ((65 - 4) \times 3))) \times -21) \\
 28960 &:= ((((-9 \times (87 - 6)) + 5) \times 4) \times -((3^2) + 1)) \\
 28961 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 28962 &:= (-9 \times -((87 + 6) + (5^{4+3/(2+1)}))) \\
 28963 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 + 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) + 1) \\
 28964 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5! - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\
 28965 &:= -9 - (8 - 7 \times (6! - 5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\
 28966 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7! + 6) \times 5 + 4^{3+2+1} \\
 28967 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 - 5) \times (4 \times (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\
 28968 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 28969 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3)))) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 28970 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2))) - 1) \\
 28971 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 28972 &:= ((9 \times (87 \times (((6 \times 5) + 4) + 3))) - (-2 + 1)) \\
 28973 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 28974 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\
 28975 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 28976 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) + 4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\
 28977 &:= (9 + ((8 - 76) \times (5 - (432 - 1)))) \\
 28978 &:= (-9 - 8 + 7!) \times 6 + 5 \times (4! - 3!)/(2 + 1) \\
 28979 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times 6) \times ((5 + 43) - 2)) + (-1) \\
 28980 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6)) + 5) \times -(4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\
 28981 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times 6) \times ((5 + 43) - 2)) - (-1) \\
 28982 &:= 9 \times (8 + 7 + 6!) \times 5 - 4^{3!} + 2 + 1 \\
 28983 &:= ((-9876 + (5 \times 43)) \times -(2 + 1)) \\
 28984 &:= (9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! \times 5 + 4! - (3 - 2 - 1)!) \\
 28985 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 \times 5)) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 28986 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6 \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1))) \\
 28987 &:= (98 + (7 \times ((6 \times 5) + ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1)))) \\
 28988 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))) + 2)) - 1) \\
 28989 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2))) \times -1) \\
 28990 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))) + 2)) + 1) \\
 28991 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (65 - 4))) \times 32) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28992 &:= ((1+2) - (((-3-456) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 28993 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + (3^4)) \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 28994 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\ 28995 &:= -(((1+2) \times ((-(3 \times 456)) \times 7) - 89))) \\ 28996 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 28997 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3^4) \times ((5 \times ((6 \times 7) - 8)) + 9)))) \\ 28998 &:= (((-1+2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 28999 &:= ((-1+2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 29000 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29001 &:= (((-12 - (((3^4) + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) \times -8) + 9) \\ 29002 &:= (((12^3) + (45 - 67)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29003 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 \times (5 \times 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 29004 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 29005 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 345)) \times -(6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 29006 &:= ((-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 - 78))) - 9) \\ 29007 &:= (((-1+2) + (3 \times ((4^5) - (6 - (7 \times 8)))) \times 9) \\ 29008 &:= (1 + ((23 + ((456 \times 7) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 29009 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + (((3^4) + 5) \times 6)) \times 7)) \times 8) + 9) \\ 29010 &:= (((-12 \times (3^4)) + 5) \times -(6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 29011 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3! + 4 \times (5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29012 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4} + 5 \times (6! + 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29013 &:= (-1 + ((-(2+3)) - (4 - (5 \times 67))) \times 89) \\ 29014 &:= ((1 \times (((2+3) + 4) - ((5 \times 67)))) \times -89) \\ 29015 &:= (1 + (((2+3) + 4) - ((5 \times 67))) \times -89) \\ 29016 &:= (((1 - (-23 - (456 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9) \\ 29017 &:= (1 + (((2+34) \times (-5-6)) - 7) \times -((8 \times 9))) \\ 29018 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3+45) \times 67) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 29019 &:= ((1+2) \times (34 + (567 \times (8+9)))) \\ 29020 &:= -1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4 \times 5 + (6+7) \times (8+9) \\ 29021 &:= (((12 \times -(345)) - 6) \times -7) + (8-9) \\ 29022 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 345)) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8-9)))) \\ 29023 &:= (((12 \times -(345)) - 6) \times -7) - (8-9) \\ 29024 &:= (-1 - ((2+3) \times (45 \times (6 - ((7+8) \times 9)))) \\ 29025 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^{4+5-6})) \times ((7+8) \times 9)) \\ 29026 &:= (1 - (((2 - (34 \times (5+6))) \times 78) - 9)) \\ 29027 &:= -((((12 \times 345) - 6) \times -7) - 89) \\ 29028 &:= ((12 + (34 - 5)) \times (6 - (78 \times -9))) \\ 29029 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times 4)) \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)) \\ 29030 &:= (((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))^5) - (6 \times (7 \times 89))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28992 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 76) + 5)) \times (((4+3)^2) - 1)) \\ 28993 &:= (-(((9 \times -(-8)) + 7) \times (65 - (432 \times 1)))) \\ 28994 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times (65 - 432)) + 1) \\ 28995 &:= (((-9 - (87 \times 6)) \times -54) + 321) \\ 28996 &:= (9 - 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5^4 \times 3! / (2 + 1) \\ 28997 &:= (9 + 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5^4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 28998 &:= (-9 \times -((87 \times ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 28999 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29000 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - 65) \times -(((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 29001 &:= (-98) + (((7 \times 65) \times (4^3)) - (21)) \\ 29002 &:= (987 + (65 \times (432 - 1))) \\ 29003 &:= ((((-98 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4)) + 3) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29004 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) + (6 + 5)) \times -43) - 21) \\ 29005 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29006 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29007 &:= (((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29008 &:= (-98 \times (((7 \times 6) + 5) - ((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\ 29009 &:= ((-98 \times ((7 \times (6 \times (5 - (4 \times 3)))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 29010 &:= (-9 \times 8 + 7 \times (6! + 5 - 4!)) \times (3 + 2 + 1) \\ 29011 &:= ((((-((9 - 87)) - 6) - 5) \times (432 + 1))) \\ 29012 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29013 &:= ((((-98 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4)) - 3) \times -2) - 1) \\ 29014 &:= (((-98 \times ((7 + (6 \times 5)) \times 4)) - 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29015 &:= (-(-98) + (((7 \times 65) + 4) \times (3 \times (21)))) \\ 29016 &:= (-9 \times -(8 \times (7 + ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29017 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29018 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29019 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29020 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 29021 &:= ((-98 + ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 29022 &:= (-98 + ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\ 29023 &:= (-((98 - ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3)))) + ((2 - 1))) \\ 29024 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (43 + 2))) - 1) \\ 29025 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) \times (3^{2+1}))) \\ 29026 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (43 + 2))) + 1) \\ 29027 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((65 \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 29028 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) - 21)) \\ 29029 &:= ((-98 + 7) \times (6 - (5 \times ((4^3) + (2 - 1)))) \\ 29030 &:= (((98 - 7) \times ((6 \times 54) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29031 &:= -1 + 2 + (3 + 4 \times (5 + 6!)) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29032 &:= (1 - 2 + 3! \times (-4! - 5 + 6!)) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 29033 &:= (-1 + (((((2 \times 3) + 456) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 29034 &:= -((((((1 + ((2 + 3) + 456)) \times -7) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 29035 &:= (1 + ((2 + ((3 + 45) \times 67) + 8)) \times 9)) \\ 29036 &:= (((((1 - 234) - 5) - 6) \times (-7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 29037 &:= (-123 - (45 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9))) \\ 29038 &:= (1 - 2 + 3) \times (4 \times 5 \times 6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29039 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 345)) \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\ 29040 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times (-4 - ((-56 - 78) \times -9))) \\ 29041 &:= ((-12 \times -(3^4 \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 29042 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!^4 - 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29043 &:= ((1 + (23 \times (4 \times 5))) \times (-6 + (-(-78) - 9))) \\ 29044 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!^4 + 5! + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29045 &:= (((-1 + (2 \times (345 \times 6))) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 29046 &:= ((-1 + (23 \times (4 + 5))) \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 29047 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4} + 56) \times 7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 29048 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) + 6) \times (78 - 9)) \\ 29049 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 + ((6 \times (7 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 29050 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (3^4)) \times -(5 + ((6 \times (7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29051 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (34 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 29052 &:= (-1 \times ((-(2 \times (345 \times 6))) \times 7) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 29053 &:= (1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - (5 \times 678)) \times 9)) \\ 29054 &:= (((-1 - ((2^{3 \times 4} + 56)) \times -7) - (8 + 9)) \\ 29055 &:= -(((1 - ((-2^3) + 456)) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29056 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4} \times ((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\ 29057 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4} + 56)) \times -(7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 29058 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4} + 56)) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 29059 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\ 29060 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) \times 5) + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 29061 &:= ((((-1 \times (2 - (3 + 4)))^5) + ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 29062 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4} + 56) \times 7) + (8 - 9))) \\ 29063 &:= (-1 - (((2^{3 \times 4} + 56) \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))) \\ 29064 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (345)) \times (67 + (8 + 9))) \\ 29065 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3 \times 4} + 56) \times 7) - (8 - 9)) \\ 29066 &:= ((1 + (((2^{3 \times 4} + 56) \times 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 29067 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (34 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 29068 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 345)) \times (6 \times 7)) + 89) \\ 29069 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3^4) \times 5) + (6 - 7)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29031 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 + 5) \times 4)^{3-2+1}))) \\ 29032 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times ((6 - (5 - 43))^2) + 1)) \\ 29033 &:= (((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((65 \times (4^3)) - 2))) - 1) \\ 29034 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - (3^2)))) \times -1) \\ 29035 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times ((65 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\ 29036 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times (6 - (5 \times (((4 + 3)^2) + 1)))) \\ 29037 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29038 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29039 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29040 &:= (((-98 \times (7 + (6 \times 5))) - 4) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\ 29041 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times ((65 \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29042 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times 65))) \times 4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29043 &:= (-9 \times -(((87 + 6) \times 5) - 4) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29044 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29045 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - (3 - 2)))) - 1) \\ 29046 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 6) \times -(5 - (4 \times (3^{2+1})))) \\ 29047 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) - (3 - 2)))) + 1) \\ 29048 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 29049 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29050 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29051 &:= (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29052 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 + 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\ 29053 &:= ((-9 \times ((87 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)))) + 1) \\ 29054 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 29055 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29056 &:= (((9 - 8) - (7 \times 65)) \times (-43) + (-21)) \\ 29057 &:= ((((-9 - 8) - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 29058 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29059 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29060 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + 6)) + ((5^4) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 29061 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 29062 &:= ((-9 + (-8 \times (((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - 3) \times -2))) - 1) \\ 29063 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 \times (65 \times 4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\ 29064 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (((5 + (4^3))^2) - 1))) \\ 29065 &:= (((((-98 - 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29066 &:= (987 + ((65 \times 432) - 1)) \\ 29067 &:= (((((-98 - 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29068 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -(54 + 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 29069 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + (7 + 6)) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29070 &:= -((((1-2) \times (34 \times (5 + (-(-6) \times (7+8)))))) \times 9)) & 29070 &:= ((-9-8) \times ((7+(6+5)) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29071 &:= ((-1+2) + (34 \times ((5+(6 \times (7+8))) \times 9))) & 29071 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8+(7+6)) + (5^4)) \times (3+2))) + 1) \\ 29072 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (34 \times ((5+(6 \times (7+8))) \times 9)))) & 29072 &:= (((9 \times -8) - 7) \times ((65 - (432 + 1)))) \\ 29073 &:= -(((((-((-12 \times (3^4)))) \times -5) \times 6) + 78) + 9) & 29073 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -(54 + 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29074 &:= (((-1 + ((2^{3 \times 4}) + 56)) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) & 29074 &:= -9 + 8! + 7 + 6 - 5^4 \times 3 \times (2 + 1)! \\ 29075 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7)) + (8 - 9)) & 29075 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 29076 &:= (-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + (7 \times (8 - 9)))) & 29076 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))) \\ 29077 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) & 29077 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\ 29078 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (7 - 89)) & 29078 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) + 5) \times -((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 29079 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) \times 5) + (6 - 7) \times 8)) \times -9) & 29079 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 29080 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3 \times 4}) + 56) \times 7) + (8 + 9)) & 29080 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) - 1)) \\ 29081 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 + (8 \times 9))) & 29081 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29082 &:= (12 + (34 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9))) & 29082 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29083 &:= -(-1 + 2 + 3!)/4 + 5! + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 & 29083 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 29084 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3! - 4 \times 5 \times (6! + 7)) + 8 + 9 & 29084 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 29085 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + (6 - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) & 29085 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 29086 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + (6 - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) & 29086 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29087 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7)))))) \times (8 + 9) & 29087 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29088 &:= (((((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 + 7)) - 8) \times -9 & 29088 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times ((4 + 3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 29089 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + (6 - 7) \times (8 \times 9))) & 29089 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) + (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 29090 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (((3 \times -4) - (56 \times 7)) \times 8) \times 9) & 29090 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29091 &:= ((12 \times ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - (78 - 9)) & 29091 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 29092 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4! + 5) \times 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) & 29092 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 29093 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7)) + (8 + 9)) & 29093 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^{4+3-2-1}))) \\ 29094 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times 345)) \times -(6 \times 7)) + (8 \times 9)) & 29094 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29095 &:= (((-12 \times ((3^4) \times (5 \times -6))) + 7) - (8 \times 9)) & 29095 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29096 &:= -1 + (-2 + (3 + 4)!/5!) \times (6! + 7) + 8 + 9 & 29096 &:= -(((9 + ((87 - ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3)) \times ((-2 \times -1)))) \\ 29097 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (((3^4) \times 5) + (6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9) & 29097 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 29098 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4!) + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9 & 29098 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 29099 &:= -1 - (2 + 3 + 4 \times 5!) \times 6 \times (7 - 8 - 9) & 29099 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29100 &:= (-12 \times (3 - (4 \times (((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) & 29100 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29101 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! \times 4 + 5 \times 6) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) & 29101 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) + ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 29102 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 34) \times 5) - 6) - 7) \times -89) & 29102 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 29103 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) & 29103 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29104 &:= ((((-1 \times -2)^3) \times ((4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)))) & 29104 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + ((6^5) + 4)) \times ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 29105 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) + (6 - 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 29105 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2))) - 1) \\ 29106 &:= ((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5) - ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times -9) & 29106 &:= (-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2 \times 1))) \\ 29107 &:= (1 - (((2 \times 3) + (45 \times (6 - 78))) \times 9)) & 29107 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 29108 &:= -1 - 2 - 3 - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) & 29108 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29109 &:= (-12 + (3 \times ((4 + 567) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 29110 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29111 &:= (((-(-1) + (2 \times 345)) \times (6 \times 7)) + 89) \\ 29112 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4^5) + ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 29113 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 29114 &:= (-1 - (-((-2 - 3) - (45 \times (6 - 78)))) \times 9) \\ 29115 &:= ((12 + 3) \times (-((4 - ((5^6) + 7)/8)) - 9)) \\ 29116 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) + (45 \times (6 - 78))) \times 9)) \\ 29117 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29118 &:= ((-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times 5) + 6)) \times -(78 - 9)) \\ 29119 &:= (1 \times (-2 - ((3 \times -((4 + 567))) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 29120 &:= ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) \times -(56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29121 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times 7)))) \times -(8 + 9)) \\ 29122 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times ((4 + 567) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 29123 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((345 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29124 &:= (-((1 + (2^3))) \times (4 + (5 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9)))) \\ 29125 &:= (1 - (-2 \times (((345 \times 6) \times 7) - (8 \times -9)))) \\ 29126 &:= (-1 \times -(2 \times (3 - (4 \times (56 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))))) \\ 29127 &:= (((-1 - (((2^3) \times 456) - 7)) \times -8) - 9) \\ 29128 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 3)) \times (((4^5) + 6) \times 7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 29129 &:= (((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times 5)/6) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 29130 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 + (45 \times (6 - 78))) \times 9)) \\ 29131 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 + (45 \times (6 - 78))) \times 9)) \\ 29132 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 29133 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times (456 + (7 \times 89))) \\ 29134 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + (45 \times (6 - 78))) \times 9)) \\ 29135 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((3 - (45 \times -((6 - 78)))) \times 9)) \\ 29136 &:= ((-1 - 23) + (-45 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9))) \\ 29137 &:= ((1 \times -23) + ((45 \times (6 - 78)) \times -9)) \\ 29138 &:= ((1 - (((2^3) \times 456) - 7) \times -8) + 9) \\ 29139 &:= ((((-1 \times -2) - (-345)) \times (6 + 78)) - 9) \\ 29140 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4) - 5) \times -((6 \times 7) - 89)) \\ 29141 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 29142 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) \times 8)))) \times 9) \\ 29143 &:= (((-1 - ((2^3 \times 4) + 56)) \times -7) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 29144 &:= ((-1 + ((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times 678)) - 9) \\ 29145 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times (34 \times 5)) - 6)) \times -(78 + 9)) \\ 29146 &:= (((-1 + ((2^3 \times 4) + 56)) \times 7) + 89) \\ 29147 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 345) \times (67 + (8 + 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29109 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 29110 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (65 + (4^{3+2+1})))) \\ 29111 &:= ((-9 + ((87 - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 29112 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times ((65 \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29113 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -((65 \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1))) \\ 29114 &:= ((9 - 8) + (7 \times ((65 \times (4^3)) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29115 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6^5)) \times 4) + (3^{2+1})) \\ 29116 &:= (((-9 + 8) + ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29117 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) - 5) \times -(4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29118 &:= ((9 - (8 + ((7 \times 65) \times -((4^3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29119 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29120 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - (5^4))) + (3^{2+1})) \\ 29121 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29122 &:= (((-9 + (8 + ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3)))) + 2) + 1) \\ 29123 &:= ((9 - 8) - (((7 \times -(65)) \times (4^3)) - 2) \times 1) \\ 29124 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5)/4))) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 29125 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (65 + (4^{3 \times 2})))) - 1) \\ 29126 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - 3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\ 29127 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1)))) \\ 29128 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 \times 6) + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)) + 1)) \\ 29129 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29130 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29131 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29132 &:= (987 + (65 \times (432 + 1))) \\ 29133 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - (2 + 1))) \\ 29134 &:= ((9 + ((8 + ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3))) - 2)) - 1) \\ 29135 &:= ((9 + ((8 + ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3))) - 2)) \times 1) \\ 29136 &:= ((9 + ((8 + ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3))) - 2)) + 1) \\ 29137 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) - (3 - 2))) + 1)) \\ 29138 &:= (9 + (8 - (((7 \times 65) \times -((4^3))) - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29139 &:= (((9 + 8) - ((7 \times 65) \times -((4^3)))) + ((2 \times 1))) \\ 29140 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) + (3/(2 + 1)))))) \\ 29141 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - 2)) - 1) \\ 29142 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5)/4))) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 29143 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) - 2)) + 1) \\ 29144 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5)/4))) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29145 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5)/4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29146 &:= (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29147 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5)/4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29148 &:= (-12 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29149 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) \times (5 \times (6 - 78))) + 9)) \\ 29150 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 29151 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^{4+5-6}) \times (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\ 29152 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 29153 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (7 \times (8 - 9))) \\ 29154 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 29155 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - 345)) \times (-((-6 - 7) - (8 \times -9))) \\ 29156 &:= ((-12/3) - (45 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9))) \\ 29157 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29158 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29159 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^{4+5-6}) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 29160 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times ((3^4) \times ((5 - 6) - (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 29161 &:= (((1 + 2) / -(-3)) + ((-45 \times (6 - 78) \times 9)) \\ 29162 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29163 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 - 8)) - 9) \\ 29164 &:= ((-1 - (-2 - 3)) - ((45 \times (6 - 78) \times 9)) \\ 29165 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - 7) + 89) \\ 29166 &:= ((1 + 2) + (-(-3) + ((-45 \times (6 - 78) \times 9))) \\ 29167 &:= (1 + ((2 \times 3) + (45 \times ((6 - 78) \times -9)))) \\ 29168 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (7 - (8 - 9))) \\ 29169 &:= (((12 \times ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((-6 \times (-7 + 8)))) + 9) \\ 29170 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 - (8 + 9))) \\ 29171 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times 4)) \times (5 + ((6 + 7) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29172 &:= (((12^3) - 4) + ((5 - 6) - 7)) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29173 &:= (1 + (2 \times (34 \times ((5 \times (6 + 78)) + 9)))) \\ 29174 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3 \times 4 + 5) \times (6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29175 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times -(((5^6) + 7) / 8) - 9) \\ 29176 &:= ((1 + (-((2^3) \times 456)) \times (-7 + ((8 - 9)))) \\ 29177 &:= (-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) \times 8)))) \times 9) \\ 29178 &:= (((((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\ 29179 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((34 \times ((5 + 6) \times 78)) + 9))) \\ 29180 &:= (-12 - (((3 + 4) - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\ 29181 &:= (12 + (((3^4) \times -5) \times (6 - 78)) + 9) \\ 29182 &:= ((-1 + 23) + (-45 \times ((6 - 78) \times 9))) \\ 29183 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((34 \times ((5 + 6) \times 78)) + 9))) \\ 29184 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -4) \times ((5 \times (67 - 8)) + 9)) \\ 29185 &:= (((1 + (2 \times 3)) - 456) \times ((7 \times -8) - 9)) \\ 29186 &:= (-1 + (23 \times ((4 + 5) \times (6 + ((7 + 8) \times 9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29148 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4))) - (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 29149 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4))) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29150 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4))) - (3 / (2 + 1))) \\ 29151 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / ((4 + 3) - (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29152 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4)) + (3 / (2 + 1)))) \\ 29153 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29154 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2 + 1) \\ 29155 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) - ((5 + (4 + 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29156 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4)) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 29157 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4)) + (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 29158 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -6^{(5+4)/3}) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 29159 &:= ((-9 \times -8) \times (((7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 29160 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -6^{(5+4-3-2-1)}) \\ 29161 &:= ((-9 \times -8) \times (((7 \times (6 + 5)) + 4) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 29162 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -6^{(5+4)/3}) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29163 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -6^{(5+4)/3}) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29164 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4)) - (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\ 29165 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5) / 4) + (3 - 2)))) - 1) \\ 29166 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5) / 4) + (3 / (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29167 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29168 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29169 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4))) \times -3 / (2 + 1)) \\ 29170 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2 + 1) \\ 29171 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - 5) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 29172 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - 6) + (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))) \\ 29173 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 29174 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4)) + (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\ 29175 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4)) + (3 \times 2))) \times -1) \\ 29176 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (((7 + 6) - 5)^4)) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29177 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) + 2)) - 1) \\ 29178 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times ((6^5) / 4)) + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 29179 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) + 2)) + 1) \\ 29180 &:= (((-98 / 7) - 6) \times -(((5 + 4)^3) \times 2 + 1)) \\ 29181 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 29182 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2 \times 1) \\ 29183 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29184 &:= ((9 \times (-8 + (-7 + (6 \times 543)))) - ((2 + 1))) \\ 29185 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 29186 &:= ((9 \times -((8 - (-7 + (6 \times 543)))))) - (2 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29187 &:= (((-1-2) + ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6-7) \times 8)))) \times -9) \\ 29188 &:= ((-1+2) + ((3 - (45 \times (6-78))) \times 9)) \\ 29189 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 - ((5 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))) \\ 29190 &:= ((-12-3) \times (4 + (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))) \\ 29191 &:= (-1 + ((2^3) \times (((4-5) + (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) \\ 29192 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4 + (5 + 6)))) \times 7)) \times 89) \\ 29193 &:= ((-1+2) - (((3+4) - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\ 29194 &:= (1 - (((23-4) - 56) \times 789)) \\ 29195 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + (((3+4) + (5 \times 6)) \times 789))) \\ 29196 &:= ((12 - (((-3 \times -4) + (56 \times 7)) \times -8)) \times 9) \\ 29197 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 - ((5 - (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\ 29198 &:= -1 \times (2+3)! - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29199 &:= (12 + ((3 - (45 \times (6-78))) \times 9)) \\ 29200 &:= (((-1+2) - (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6-7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29201 &:= (-1 \times 2 + 3!! \times 4!/5 + 6!) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 29202 &:= ((-123 \times -((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 29203 &:= -1 + 2 + 3 - 4^5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29204 &:= (-1 + (((2+3) - (45 \times (6-78))) \times 9)) \\ 29205 &:= (((1^2) - (3 \times 4)) \times ((5 \times (67-8)) \times -9)) \\ 29206 &:= (1 + (((2+3) - (45 \times (6-78))) \times 9)) \\ 29207 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 29208 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - (56 \times (78 + 9)))) \\ 29209 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 - (56 \times (78 + 9))))) \\ 29210 &:= (1 - 23)^4 / (-5 + 6 + 7) - 8 \times 9 \\ 29211 &:= (-1 + 2^{3!} - 4!) \times (5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29212 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4)! / 5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29213 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (-45 + (67 \times -((8 \times 9))))) \\ 29214 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times 3) \times (-45 + (67 \times -((8 \times 9))))) \\ 29215 &:= (1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (-45 + (67 \times -((8 \times 9))))) \\ 29216 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\ 29217 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times 67) + (8 + 9)))) \\ 29218 &:= (1 + 2) \times (3! - (4 + 5 - 6)!!) + 7 \times 8! / 9 \\ 29219 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3)! \times 4) \times (5! - 6 \times 7 - 8 - 9) \\ 29220 &:= ((12 + 3) \times (4 \times -((5 + (6 \times (7 - 89))))) \\ 29221 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3!) \times (-4 - 5! + 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 29222 &:= ((-1 + (((23 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\ 29223 &:= (((-((-1+2)) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6-78)) - 9) \\ 29224 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + (67-8)))) \times 9)) \\ 29225 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) - (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\ 29226 &:= (-1 - 2) \times 3 \times (4 + 5!) + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29187 &:= (-9 \times -(((8+7) \times (6^{(5+4)/3})) + (2+1))) \\ 29188 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - ((6+5)^4)) \times -(3 - (2-1))) \\ 29189 &:= ((9 \times -((8 - (-7 + (6 \times 543)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29190 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 - (((6+5)^4) - 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29191 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - (((6+5)^4) - 3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 29192 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times 6))) - (5^4)) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\ 29193 &:= (9 + ((-8 \times -(76)) \times ((54 - (3 \times (2 \times 1))))) \\ 29194 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (((6+5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29195 &:= -(((9 \times ((8-7) - (6 - ((54+3)^2)))) + 1)) \\ 29196 &:= -(((9 - (((876+5) + 4) \times (32+1)))) \\ 29197 &:= -(((98 - (7-6)) \times ((5 \times 4) - (321)))) \\ 29198 &:= 9 \times 8 + 7 \times (65 + 4^{3 \times 2}) - 1 \\ 29199 &:= 9 + (8 + 7) \times (6^5 / 4 + 3 - 2 + 1) \\ 29200 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7-6)) \times -((5 \times 4)^{3-2+1})) \\ 29201 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - (((7 - (((6+5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29202 &:= ((-9 \times 8) - ((7 - (((6+5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29203 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (((6+5)^4) \times (3 - (2-1)))) \\ 29204 &:= (-98 \times -(((7 \times 6) - (5+4)) \times (3^2)) + 1)) \\ 29205 &:= (-98 + (((7 + (((6+5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29206 &:= (((-9 + (87654/3)) - 2) + (-1)) \\ 29207 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 \times ((65 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1)) \\ 29208 &:= ((-9 \times (-8 \times (76 \times 5))) + (((43^2) - 1))) \\ 29209 &:= ((9 \times ((8 \times -(76)) \times -5)) + (((43^2) \times 1))) \\ 29210 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6+5)^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29211 &:= (-9 + ((8+7) \times (((6^5)/4) + ((3+2) - 1))) \\ 29212 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6+5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29213 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3^2)) - 1) \\ 29214 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3 \times (2+1))) \\ 29215 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times (3^2)) + 1) \\ 29216 &:= ((-9 - (((8+7) \times (((6^5)/4) + 3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\ 29217 &:= ((9 \times -(87)) + ((6 \times (5^4)) \times ((3^2) - 1))) \\ 29218 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (((7 + (((6+5)^4) - 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29219 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) - 5) \times -((4^3) - (2+1))) \\ 29220 &:= ((-9 - (8-7)) \times -(6 + (54^{3-2+1}))) \\ 29221 &:= (((-9 - ((8-76) \times (5 \times 43))) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29222 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6+5)^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29223 &:= (-9 + (((-87) \times -((6-54)/3)) \times -(21))) \\ 29224 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + ((6+5)^4)) \times (3 - (2-1)))) \\ 29225 &:= (((9 + (87654/3)) - 2) \times 1) \\ 29226 &:= (((9 + (87654/3)) - 2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$29227 := ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7) - (8 + 9))$$

$$29228 := (1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4! + 5) \times (6 + 7) + 8 + 9$$

$$29229 := ((12 \times ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (78 - 9))$$

$$29230 := (((-1 - 2) - 34) \times ((5 - 6) - (789)))$$

$$29231 := ((1 - 2) - ((-3 + 45) \times (6 + (-78 \times -(-9))))))$$

$$29232 := ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 + ((5 + 6) \times 7)))) \times -(8 \times 9))$$

$$29233 := (1 + (((2 \times (3 + 4)) - (56 \times -7)) \times (8 \times 9)))$$

$$29234 := ((-1 \times -2) + (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 - 7)) \times (8 \times 9))$$

$$29235 := ((-12 - 3) \times -((4 + ((5^5) + 7)/8) - 9))$$

$$29236 := (1 + 2 - (3 + 4)^5 + 6^7 - 8)/9$$

$$29237 := (-1 + (2 \times (3 \times (4 + ((5 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9))))))$$

$$29238 := ((-1 - (2 + 3)) \times -(4 + ((5 + (67 \times 8)) \times 9)))$$

$$29239 := (((-12 \times ((3^4) \times (5 \times -6))) + 7) + (8 \times 9))$$

$$29240 := (-1 + (((23 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))$$

$$29241 := -((((1 - 2) \times (-3 \times ((4^5) + (67 - 8)))) \times -9))$$

$$29242 := ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (67 - 8)) \times 9)))$$

$$29243 := ((-12 \times (((3^4) \times (5 \times -6)) - 7)) + (8 - 9))$$

$$29244 := (-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 \times (8 - 9))))$$

$$29245 := ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7)) - (8 - 9))$$

$$29246 := -1 - 2 - (3 + 4)!/5 + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9$$

$$29247 := ((-12 \times -((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (78 + 9))$$

$$29248 := (-1 + (((2^3) \times 456) + 7) \times 8) + 9))$$

$$29249 := (-1 + ((2 + (((3^4) \times 5) - (6 - 7)) \times 8)) \times 9))$$

$$29250 := ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))))$$

$$29251 := (1 + (234 \times ((56 + 78) - 9)))$$

$$29252 := 1 \times 2 \times (3^{4+5} - 6! \times 7 - 8 - 9)$$

$$29253 := ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 89)))$$

$$29254 := -1 - 2 + ((3 + 4)!/5 + (6! - 7)) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$29255 := (-1 + (23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times 67) - (8 + 9))))))$$

$$29256 := (((-1 \times 23) \times -(-4)) \times ((5 \times -67) - (-8 - 9)))$$

$$29257 := ((1 - (((2 + 34) + 5) \times (-6 \times -7))) \times (-8 - 9))$$

$$29258 := (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + (67 - 8)))) \times 9))$$

$$29259 := (((1 \times 2) + (3 \times ((4^5) + (67 - 8)))) \times 9)$$

$$29260 := ((-1 + 23) \times ((4^5) + (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9)))$$

$$29261 := ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) + 7)) + (8 + 9))$$

$$29262 := (((((12^3)/4) + 5) \times 67) - (8 + 9))$$

$$29263 := -1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$29264 := 1 \times 2 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$29265 := 1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} + 6 - 7! - 8 - 9)$$

$$29227 := (9 - (((87654/3) \times -((2 - 1))))))$$

$$29228 := ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))$$

$$29229 := (((((-9 - (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1)$$

$$29230 := ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)))$$

$$29231 := (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) + 3))) - (2 + 1))$$

$$29232 := (((-9 \times (8 \times 7))/6) \times -(5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$29233 := ((-9 \times (8 \times (7 \times ((6 - (5 \times (4 + 3))) \times 2)))) + 1)$$

$$29234 := ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 + 1))))$$

$$29235 := (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) + 3))) + (2 - 1))$$

$$29236 := (-9 - (((8 + 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times 2) + 1)$$

$$29237 := (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) + 3))) + (2 + 1))$$

$$29238 := (-9 - (((8 + 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times 2) - 1)$$

$$29239 := (-((-98) - ((7 \times 65) \times (4^3)))) + (21))$$

$$29240 := ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 + 6) - 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$29241 := ((-9 + ((87 \times 6)) \times (((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2) - 1)))$$

$$29242 := (((-9 \times -(8 - (7 - (6 + (5 + (4 + 3))))))^{2+1}) + 1)$$

$$29243 := (-9 - (((8 + 7) - ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))))$$

$$29244 := ((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) + (3 + 2)))) \times -1)$$

$$29245 := ((-9 - 8) - ((7 - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times (2 \times 1)))$$

$$29246 := ((-9 - 8) - (((7 - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times 2) - 1))$$

$$29247 := (((((-98/7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) - 1)$$

$$29248 := (9 - (-((87654/3)) - (21)))$$

$$29249 := ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2))) - 1)$$

$$29250 := (-9 \times -((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times (2 + 1))))))$$

$$29251 := ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2))) + 1)$$

$$29252 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))$$

$$29253 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1)$$

$$29254 := (((-98/7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))$$

$$29255 := (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2))) - 1)$$

$$29256 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2 \times 1)))$$

$$29257 := ((-9 - 8) - (((7 - ((-6 - 5)^4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)))$$

$$29258 := ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1))))$$

$$29259 := (-9 \times -((8 - 7) + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2) + 1))$$

$$29260 := (((((-9 + 8) - 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))$$

$$29261 := (((((-9 + 8) - 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1)$$

$$29262 := (((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))$$

$$29263 := ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) - 1)$$

$$29264 := (((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))$$

$$29265 := ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29266 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3 \times (-4 + 5!) \times 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29267 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4))/5) \times -(6 - (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 29268 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) + (5^{6+7-8}))) \times 9) \\ 29269 &:= (-12 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 29270 &:= (-1 + (2 + 3) \times (-4 + 5! + 6!)) \times 7 + (8 + 9) \\ 29271 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 29272 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 + 5 - 6 - 7)/8 - 9 \\ 29273 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 + (4 \times (5 \times 6))) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))))) \\ 29274 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3^{4-5+6})) \times -(7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 29275 &:= ((-123 \times -((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 29276 &:= (-1 + (((2^{3+4}) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) \\ 29277 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9 \\ 29278 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3 + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 29279 &:= ((-12 \times -(3^4 \times (5 \times 6))) + (7 \times (8 + 9))) \\ 29280 &:= (-(-12) \times (((345 + 6) \times 7) - (8 + 9))) \\ 29281 &:= -(((1 + (-2 \times ((3 - 4) + 5) \times 6))) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 29282 &:= (1 - ((2 + ((3 + 4) - 56)) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 29283 &:= ((-1 - (2^{3+4})) \times -((5 \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9))) \\ 29284 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3 + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 29285 &:= (-1 + (((((23 \times (4 \times 5)) + 6) \times 7) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 29286 &:= ((-1 - ((2^{3+4}) + (5^{6+7-8}))) \times -9) \\ 29287 &:= ((-12 \times -(34 \times (5 + 67))) - 89) \\ 29288 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 - 5 + 6^7)/8 - 9) \\ 29289 &:= ((-12 \times ((3 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 29290 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} - 6 - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 29291 &:= (((12^3) - 4) + (((5 - 6)^7)) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29292 &:= (-12 \times (3 + ((4 - 56) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 29293 &:= (12 + ((3 + (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 29294 &:= (-1 + (((((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 \times 7))/8) \times 9)) \\ 29295 &:= (((1 + (23 \times 4)) \times 5) \times ((-6 + 78) - 9)) \\ 29296 &:= (((((12^3)/4) + 5) \times 67) + (8 + 9)) \\ 29297 &:= (((-1 - (((23 \times 4) - 5) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 29298 &:= (1 - 2) \times (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29299 &:= (1 - 23)^4/(-5 + 6 + 7) + 8 + 9 \\ 29300 &:= ((1 - 23)^4 + 5 + 67)/8 + 9 \\ 29301 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 + 4))) \times -((5^6) + 7)/8) - 9) \\ 29302 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 29303 &:= (-1 - (((-2 \times (34 \times 5)) - 67) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 29304 &:= (((1 + (-2 \times (3 \times ((-4 + 5) + 67)))) \times 8) \times -9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29266 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29267 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 29268 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29269 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29270 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) - ((6 + 5)^4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29271 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29272 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29273 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29274 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - (6 - 5)) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29275 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 29276 &:= (((-9 + (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29277 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + (4^3)))))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29278 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29279 &:= ((9 + 8) - ((7 - (((-6 - 5)^4) - 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29280 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (((5 \times (4 + 3))^2) + 1))) \\ 29281 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -((6 - ((5^4) \times 3))/(2 + 1))) \\ 29282 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29283 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29284 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 29285 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29286 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) + (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29287 &:= ((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 29288 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29289 &:= (((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29290 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29291 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 - 6) \times 5) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29292 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29293 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29294 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29295 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + (7 + 6)) \times 5)) \times -(4 + (3^{2+1}))) \\ 29296 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29297 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29298 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29299 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29300 &:= ((((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29301 &:= -(((98) \times (7 + ((6 \times 54) - 32))) + (1)) \\ 29302 &:= ((((-9 + 8) \times 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29303 &:= (-((-98) \times (7 + ((6 \times 54) - 32)))) + (1) \\ 29304 &:= ((9 \times 8) \times ((76 \times 5) + ((-4 + 32) - 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29305 &:= (1 + (((2^3) + 456) \times 7) + 8) \times 9) \\ 29306 &:= (-1 + 2 + 3 \times (4 - 5 + 6)^7) / 8 + 9 \\ 29307 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3^{4+5} - 6 - 7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29308 &:= (((12^3) - 4) \times -((5 + 67) - 89)) \\ 29309 &:= ((1 - (2^3)) \times (-4 - ((5 - (6 \times -7)) \times 89))) \\ 29310 &:= (((-12 \times (3^4) - 5) \times -(6 + (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 29311 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 29312 &:= (-1 - (((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times (6 - 78) - 9)) \\ 29313 &:= (((-1 - ((2^3)^4)) + (56 \times (7 + 8))) \times -9) \\ 29314 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) - 456) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29315 &:= (-1 \times -(((2 + 3) - 456) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29316 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6) + 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 29317 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4^5)) + 6789) \\ 29318 &:= (-1 - (((2 - 345) + 6) \times (78 + 9))) \\ 29319 &:= (((1 \times (2 - 345)) + 6) \times -((78 + 9))) \\ 29320 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 29321 &:= ((1 - 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 29322 &:= (((-1 + 2) \times 3) \times (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9)) \\ 29323 &:= ((-123 \times 4) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29324 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 29325 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) + 5)) \times -((6 \times (7 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 29326 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((-4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\ 29327 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) + (8 - 9)) \\ 29328 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times (4 - (5 \times 6))) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 29329 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\ 29330 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 3! - 4^5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29331 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9) \\ 29332 &:= (((-123 \times 4) - 5) \times -(67 - 8) + 9) \\ 29333 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times 7))) - 89) \\ 29334 &:= (12 + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8))) \times 9))) \\ 29335 &:= (((-12 - ((3 \times (4^5)) / 6)) \times -(7 \times 8) - 9) \\ 29336 &:= (-123 + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times -89)) \\ 29337 &:= ((((-1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8)) + 9) \\ 29338 &:= (1 + (((2 + (34 \times (5 + 6))) \times 78) + 9)) \\ 29339 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 29340 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times -(5 \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) - 9)))) \\ 29341 &:= (1 + ((2 + 34) \times (5 + (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 29342 &:= (((12^3) + (4 - (5 - (6 - 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29343 &:= -1 + 2^{3!} + 4 \times (5! - 6! \times (7 - 8 - 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29305 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29306 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - 7) \times (6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29307 &:= (((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - (6 \times (5 + (4^3)))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29308 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 + 5)) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29309 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29310 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29311 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29312 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2) \times -1) \\ 29313 &:= (9 - ((87 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3^2) - 1))) \\ 29314 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + (((7 \times -6) - 5) + (4^3))^2)) + 1) \\ 29315 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) + ((6 + 5)^4)) - 3) \times 2) \times -1) \\ 29316 &:= (((-98/7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29317 &:= ((((-98/7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29318 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29319 &:= (((-9 - 8) - ((7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) \times -1) \\ 29320 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 29321 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29322 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29323 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 29324 &:= ((-9 \times ((-8 + 7) \times (6 \times 543))) - ((2 \times -1))) \\ 29325 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) - (5 - 4))^3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29326 &:= ((((-9 + 87) \times 6) + 5) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 29327 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6 - ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 29328 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6 - ((5^4) + ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 29329 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -6 - ((5^4) + (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 29330 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) - ((6 + 5)^4)) \times -(3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29331 &:= ((-9 \times -((-8) - ((7 + (6 \times 543)) + 2))) \times 1) \\ 29332 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 - 7) + (6 \times 543))) + (2 - 1)) \\ 29333 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (((7 - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29334 &:= ((-9 \times ((-8 + 7) - (6 \times 543))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29335 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 29336 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29337 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29338 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 29339 &:= ((((-9 \times ((8 + 7) \times 6) - 5) \times 4) \times -(3^2)) - 1) \\ 29340 &:= ((-((987 \times -6) - 54) \times (((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 29341 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29342 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29343 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29344 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 \times 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29345 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 29346 &:= (((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 29347 &:= (-1 + (23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)))) \\ 29348 &:= (-1 \times -(23 \times (4 \times ((5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8))) + 9)))) \\ 29349 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3 \times ((4^5) + (6 + (7 \times 8)))) \times -9) \\ 29350 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times 7))) - (8 \times 9)) \\ 29351 &:= (((((12^3)/4) + 5) \times 67) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 29352 &:= (((1234 - 5) - 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 29353 &:= (((-12 - ((3 \times (4^5))/6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 29354 &:= (1 - 23)^4 / (-5 + 6 + 7) + 8 \times 9 \\ 29355 &:= (-1 + ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 - 89))) \\ 29356 &:= (-1 \times -((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times (7 - 89))) \\ 29357 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 + (6 \times 7)))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 29358 &:= ((-1 + (-2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) + 67))) + 8)) \times 9) \\ 29359 &:= (1234 - ((5^{6+7-8})) \times 9) \\ 29360 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3^4)) \times -(((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 29361 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -(4 + (((5^6) + 7)/8))) - 9) \\ 29362 &:= -1 - 2 + (3 + 4) \times 5 \times (6! + 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29363 &:= ((-123 \times -((4 + (5 \times 6)) \times 7)) + 89) \\ 29364 &:= (12 \times (3 - ((4 - 56) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)))) \\ 29365 &:= -1 + (23^4 - 5^6 + 78)/9 \\ 29366 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((3 \times ((4^5) + 67)) - 8)) \times 9)) \\ 29367 &:= ((-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times 8)) \times 9) \\ 29368 &:= (1 + ((23 - (45 \times (6 - 78))) \times 9)) \\ 29369 &:= (-1 - ((2 - ((345 - 6) - 7)) \times 89)) \\ 29370 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (((-3 \times (45 - 6)) + 7) \times -89)) \\ 29371 &:= (1 - ((2 - (345 - (6 + 7))) \times 89)) \\ 29372 &:= (1 - 2 + 3!!) \times 4! - 5 + (6! - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29373 &:= (-12 + (((-3 \times ((4^5) + 67)) + 8) \times -9)) \\ 29374 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9)))))) \\ 29375 &:= (-1 - (((2 - (3^4)) \times 5) - (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\ 29376 &:= (12 \times (((3 - (4 \times 5)) \times -6) \times ((7 + 8) + 9))) \\ 29377 &:= ((-12 \times -(34 \times (5 + 67))) - (8 - 9)) \\ 29378 &:= 1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4 \times (5! + 6)) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29379 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times -(4 + (((5^6) + 7)/8))) + 9) \\ 29380 &:= (((1 - 2) + (-3 + 456)) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 29381 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times 4)) \times -((5 \times (67 \times 8)) - 9)) \\ 29382 &:= (((-1 + 2) - (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29344 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times (7 \times 6)) + 5) \times 43)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29345 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - (((7 - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29346 &:= ((-9 \times -8) - ((7 - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29347 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29348 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 + (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)))) - 1) \\ 29349 &:= (-9 \times -(87 + (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2 \times 1)))) \\ 29350 &:= ((-9 \times -(87 + (6 \times (((5 \times 4) + 3)^2)))) + 1) \\ 29351 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times ((5 \times (4 + (3 \times 2))) - 1)) \\ 29352 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29353 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29354 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29355 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29356 &:= (((-98) \times 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times ((43 - 2) \times -1)) \\ 29357 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29358 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29359 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - ((5 + (4 + 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29360 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (7 - (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2)))) + 1) \\ 29361 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29362 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29363 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + (((7 + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29364 &:= (-9 \times (8 + 7) - 6 - 5 + (4 + 3)!) \times (2 + 1)! \\ 29365 &:= (((-9 + 87) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29366 &:= ((((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29367 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 29368 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29369 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29370 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29371 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29372 &:= ((-98 + ((7 - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2)) \times -1) \\ 29373 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) - (5 - 4))^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29374 &:= ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29375 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) + (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29376 &:= ((987 - (65 + 4)) \times (32 \times 1)) \\ 29377 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2))) + 1) \\ 29378 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29379 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) - (5 - 4))^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29380 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + ((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\ 29381 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29382 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29383 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times (4^5) + 67)) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 29384 &:= ((1 - 2) + (((3 \times (4^5) + 67)) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 29385 &:= (((((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}))/6) - (7 + 8)) \times 9) \\
 29386 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times (4^5) + 67)) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 29387 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\
 29388 &:= (((1 \times 2) + (-34 \times (5 + 6))) \times (-7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 29389 &:= (1 - ((2 - (34 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29390 &:= (1 + (2 + 3)! \times (4! + 5 + 6)) \times 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 29391 &:= (-((((1 - 23) \times (-4 \times -5)) \times 67)) - 89) \\
 29392 &:= (-1 + (((-(23 + (4 \times 56))) \times 7) \times (-8 - 9))) \\
 29393 &:= (((-(12 \times 34)) \times (-5 - 67)) + (8 + 9)) \\
 29394 &:= (((((-1 - 2) - (3^{4+5}))/6) + (7 + 8)) \times -9) \\
 29395 &:= ((-12 \times -((345 + 6) \times 7)) - 89) \\
 29396 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (((3 \times 4 - 5)^6 + 7)/8 - 9) \\
 29397 &:= (-123 \times -((4^{5+6-7}) - (8 + 9))) \\
 29398 &:= 1 \times ((2 \times (3 + 4)^5 - 6) \times 7/8 - 9) \\
 29399 &:= -1 + ((2 + 3)^4 - 5! + 6!) \times (7 + 8 + 9) \\
 29400 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) + (8 \times 9)) \\
 29401 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times ((3 + 4)^5))) - (6 \times (78 \times 9))) \\
 29402 &:= (-1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4^5) + 67))) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 29403 &:= ((-1 - ((2^3) \times 4)) \times ((5 - ((6 + 7) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\
 29404 &:= (1 + (((2 + (3 \times (4^5) + 67))) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 29405 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 29406 &:= ((123 \times (((4 \times 56) + 7) + 8)) + 9) \\
 29407 &:= ((12 \times -34) - ((5 \times 67) \times -89)) \\
 29408 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times (5 \times 67))) - (8 \times 9)) \\
 29409 &:= (((-1 + (2 + 34)) \times (56 \times (7 + 8))) + 9) \\
 29410 &:= ((-1 + (-(23 + (4 \times 56))) \times 7) \times (-8 - 9)) \\
 29411 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (34 + 5)) \times (6 \times -7)) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 29412 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\
 29413 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (34 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) - 8) \times 9)) \\
 29414 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (34 + 5)) \times (6 + 789))) \\
 29415 &:= (((((1 \times 2)^3) - 45) \times -((6 + 789))) \\
 29416 &:= (1 - (((2^3) - 45) \times (6 + 789))) \\
 29417 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4)) \times (5 + (6 \times 7))) + 89) \\
 29418 &:= (-1 + ((2 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29419 &:= (((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 29420 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9))) \\
 29421 &:= (((-1 \times -(2 \times 3)^4) + ((5^{6+7-8}) \times 9)) \\
 29422 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times (8 - 9))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29383 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
 29384 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times (5 - (4^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 29385 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times (5 - (4^3))) + (2 + 1)) \\
 29386 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - (7 + 654)) \times (3 + 2))) + 1) \\
 29387 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + 2))) - 1) \\
 29388 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times (5 - ((4^3) + (2 + 1)))) \\
 29389 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(6 \times ((5 \times (4 \times 3)) + 2))) + 1) \\
 29390 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 29391 &:= (-9 + ((-8 - 7) \times (-(654 \times 3)) + (2 \times 1)))) \\
 29392 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) + 1) \\
 29393 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - 6) - (54 \times -(32)))) \times -(1)) \\
 29394 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 29395 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 29396 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 29397 &:= (((-9 - 87) \times (6 \times -((54 - 3)))) + (21)) \\
 29398 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (76 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) - 1) \\
 29399 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\
 29400 &:= ((-98 \times (7 - (6 - 5))) \times -(((4 + 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 29401 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 + 5)^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 29402 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 654)) \times 3) - (2 - 1)) \\
 29403 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) + (6 \times (5 \times 4)))) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 29404 &:= (((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times 654)) \times 3) + (2 - 1)) \\
 29405 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\
 29406 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 29407 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 29408 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 29409 &:= (((((9 \times -8) \times 7) - (-6^5)) \times 4) - (-321)) \\
 29410 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 29411 &:= ((9 \times (((87 + 65) \times 43)/2)) - 1) \\
 29412 &:= ((9 \times (((87 + 65) \times 43)/2)) \times 1) \\
 29413 &:= ((9 \times (((87 + 65) \times 43)/2)) + 1) \\
 29414 &:= ((-9 \times -((87 - (6 + 5)) \times 43)) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 29415 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 76) + 5) \times (((4 + 3)^2) - 1))) \\
 29416 &:= ((9 + (8 \times (76 + ((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2)))) - 1) \\
 29417 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 29418 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times -(654)) \times -3)) - (2 + (1))) \\
 29419 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\
 29420 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 - 7) - (654 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 29421 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\
 29422 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29423 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4)) \times -(5 + (6 \times 7))) - (8 - 9)) \\ 29424 &:= (-12 \times (3 - ((4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9))) \\ 29425 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\ 29426 &:= -1 + ((2 \times 3)! + 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29427 &:= (((12^3) + (45 - (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29428 &:= -1 + 2 + (3!! + 4^5 - 6 - 7) \times (8 + 9) \\ 29429 &:= (-1 + (((((23 \times (4 \times 5)) + 6) \times 7) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 29430 &:= ((-(((1 \times 2) \times 3)) + (4 \times 56)) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\ 29431 &:= (1 + (2 \times (3 \times ((4 + 5) \times ((67 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 29432 &:= (((-1 - 2)^3) + ((4 + (5 \times -67)) \times -89)) \\ 29433 &:= ((-12 \times -(((3^{4+5}) - 67)/8)) + 9) \\ 29434 &:= -1 + (2 + 3) \times (4! + 5! + 6! + 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29435 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (45 \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\ 29436 &:= (((1 + 23) - (4 \times -5)) \times (678 - 9)) \\ 29437 &:= ((1 - 23) - ((4 - (-5 \times -67)) \times 89)) \\ 29438 &:= ((1 - ((2 \times 3) \times (4 + 56))) \times (7 - 89)) \\ 29439 &:= (((123 - 4) - (5 \times 678)) \times -9) \\ 29440 &:= (-1 \times -(23 \times (4 \times ((56 \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29441 &:= (1 + (23 \times (4 \times ((56 \times 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29442 &:= (-1 + (-2 - ((3 - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29443 &:= (-1 \times (2 - ((3 - 456) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29444 &:= ((-12 - 3) - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\ 29445 &:= ((1 - 2) \times ((3 - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29446 &:= (-1 - (-2 + ((3 - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29447 &:= (-1 \times (-2 + ((3 - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29448 &:= (1 - (-2 + ((3 - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29449 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29450 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29451 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29452 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times 3) + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\ 29453 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\ 29454 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\ 29455 &:= ((-12/3) - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\ 29456 &:= (((1 - 2) \times 3) + ((-4 + (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\ 29457 &:= ((-1 + (((2^3) \times (4 - 56)) + 7) \times 8)) \times -9) \\ 29458 &:= -((-1234) - (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29459 &:= (((1 - 2) + (((345 - 6) - 7))) \times 89) \\ 29460 &:= (-12 \times (((3 \times 4) - 56) \times (7 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 29461 &:= ((1 - (2 - 3)) - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29423 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 29424 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((((6 + 5)^4) + 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29425 &:= (9 + (8 \times (76 + (((5 \times (4 \times 3))^2) + 1)))) \\ 29426 &:= (9 + 8) \times ((7 + 65) \times 4! + 3) - 2 + 1 \\ 29427 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) - (5 - 4))^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 29428 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (7 - 6))^5)/4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29429 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) + 2)) - 1) \\ 29430 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) - (5^4)))) \times -((3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29431 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) + 2)) + 1) \\ 29432 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6^5) - ((4^{3 \times 2}) + 1))) \\ 29433 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 29434 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29435 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29436 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times ((654 \times 3) + (2 - 1)))) \\ 29437 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times 4) + 3)))) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29438 &:= (((-9 + 87) + ((6 + 5)^4)) \times (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29439 &:= (-9 \times -(8 - ((7 + 6) \times (5 - (4^{3+2-1})))) \\ 29440 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6^5) - (4^{3+2+1}))) \\ 29441 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6^5) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1) \\ 29442 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times -((6 - ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29443 &:= ((((-9 + 87) + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29444 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times ((7 - (6 + 5)) - ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29445 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) - 1) \\ 29446 &:= ((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29447 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29448 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times (((((7 + 6) - (5^4))/3) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 29449 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times ((4^3) - 2)) - 1) \\ 29450 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times ((4^3) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 29451 &:= ((((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times 5) \times ((4^3) - 2)) + 1) \\ 29452 &:= ((-9 + ((87 + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29453 &:= (-9 + ((87 + (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29454 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29455 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - ((3^2) + 1))))) \\ 29456 &:= ((987 + 65) \times ((4 + 3) + ((21)))) \\ 29457 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5 + (4^3)) - 2)))) + 1)) \\ 29458 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) \times 1) \\ 29459 &:= ((((-98 + 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29460 &:= (((-9 - ((8 + 7) \times 654)) \times -3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29461 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 - 6) \times 5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29462 &:= ((-1+2) \times (3 - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\ 29463 &:= -(((1 - ((2+3))) + ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\ 29464 &:= -(((1 \times -2)) + (3 - ((4 + (-5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\ 29465 &:= -(((1 \times -2) \times 3) + ((4 + (-5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\ 29466 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + ((4^5) + 67))) + 8) \times -9 \\ 29467 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times 6)) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 29468 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times -3) - ((4 - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\ 29469 &:= ((-1 - (((2+3)^4) - (5-6))) \times -((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 29470 &:= ((1+2) \times (3!! + 4!) - 5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29471 &:= (((((1 - (2^3)) - 4) \times (5 \times -67)) \times 8) - 9) \\ 29472 &:= (-12 \times (34 + (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29473 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times (4^5 + 6^7 / (8 \times 9)) \\ 29474 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 34) - 5) \times (6 \times 78))) - 9) \\ 29475 &:= ((((-1 - ((2 + (3^4)) - 5) \times 6)) \times 7) + 8) \times -9 \\ 29476 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (34 \times (((5 + 6) \times 78) + 9)))) \\ 29477 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -((4 - 5) + (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29478 &:= ((1 - 2) \times (34 \times (((-5 - 6) \times 78) - 9))) \\ 29479 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times (5 \times 67))) + (8 - 9)) \\ 29480 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -((4 - (56 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\ 29481 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29482 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29483 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 \times ((4 - (5 + 6)) \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29484 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times ((6 \times -78) \times -9))) \\ 29485 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29486 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + (((3 \times 4) - 5) \times (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29487 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3 + 45) - 6) \times (78 \times 9))) \\ 29488 &:= (-1 - 2 + (3 + 4)!) \times 5 - 6! + 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29489 &:= (((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) \times -(67 \times 8)) + 9) \\ 29490 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((-345) + 6) \times -((78 + 9))) \\ 29491 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times ((4 - 5) - (6 \times (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29492 &:= (((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 29493 &:= (((12 - 345) - 6) \times -((78 + 9))) \\ 29494 &:= ((-1 + 2) + ((-345) + 6) \times -((78 + 9))) \\ 29495 &:= ((-1 \times -((2 + 345))) \times ((6 + 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\ 29496 &:= (((12^3) - (4^5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - ((8 \times 9)) \\ 29497 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times (5 \times 67))) + (8 + 9)) \\ 29498 &:= 1 \times 2 + ((3 + 4)! - 5!) \times 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\ 29499 &:= -1 - 2 - (3 + 4) \times 5! + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29500 &:= -1 - 2 + 3!! \times (-4! + 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9 \\ 29501 &:= (-1 + ((-(-2) - (((3 + 45) - 6) \times -78)) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29462 &:= -9 + (-8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5 + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 29463 &:= -(((9876 - 54) \times -3) + ((2 + 1))) \\ 29464 &:= ((-98/7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29465 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times (((65 \times 4) + 3) \times 2)))) \times -1) \\ 29466 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times (6 \times 5))) - 43) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29467 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times 5) + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29468 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29469 &:= (((9876 - 54) \times 3) + ((2 + 1))) \\ 29470 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29471 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29472 &:= (-9 + ((87 + 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)))) \\ 29473 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 \times ((65 \times 4) + 3)))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 29474 &:= (((-9 - 87) - ((6 + 5)^4)) \times -((3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29475 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3))) / 2) - 1)) \\ 29476 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2)) - 1) \\ 29477 &:= (-98 + (7 \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2 \times 1))) \\ 29478 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 - (6 - 5)) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29479 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times ((4 \times 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 29480 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 29481 &:= ((((-9 - 87) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29482 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) - ((4^3) \times (2 \times 1))) \\ 29483 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 \times 4)) - 3))) / 2)) - 1) \\ 29484 &:= (-(-9) \times ((87 + (6 \times 5)) \times (4 + ((3 + 21)))) \\ 29485 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times -7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29486 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6^5)) - (4^3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 29487 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6^5)) - (4^3 + 2^1)))) \\ 29488 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 + (6^5)) - (4^3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\ 29489 &:= (((((98 - 7) \times (6 \times 54)) + 3) - (-2 \times 1)) \\ 29490 &:= ((-9 + (87 \times ((6 \times 5) + 4))) \times ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 29491 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -(6 \times 54)) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29492 &:= ((-98 / -7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29493 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times -(5 + (4^3 + 2^1))) \\ 29494 &:= (-9 - (((8 - (7 \times 65)) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1)) \\ 29495 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + ((6 \times -(5 - (4 + 3)))^{2+1}))) \\ 29496 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2) - 1)) \\ 29497 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2)))) - 1) \\ 29498 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 + 7) - 6)) - 5) \times -((4 + 3)^{2+1})) \\ 29499 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times (6 + ((5 \times (4 + 3)) + 2)))) + 1) \\ 29500 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times ((6 - 5) \times 43))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29501 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 + ((76 - (5^4)) \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$29502 := (((-1 - 2) + ((3 \times ((4^5) + 67)) + 8)) \times 9)$$

$$29503 := (-(-1) + ((-(-2) - (((3 + 45) - 6) \times -78)) \times 9))$$

$$29504 := -1 + 2 - 3!! \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) - 8 - 9$$

$$29505 := (12 + ((345 - 6) \times (78 + 9)))$$

$$29506 := ((-1 + 2 + 3!) - 4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$29507 := (-12 + ((3 + 4) \times (5 + (6 \times (78 \times 9))))$$

$$29508 := (12 \times ((3 - 4) - (5 \times (6 \times (7 - 89))))$$

$$29509 := (-1 + ((2 - (((3^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))))$$

$$29510 := ((1 + ((-2 + 3) - 456)) \times -(((7 \times 8) + 9)))$$

$$29511 := (((((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}))/6) + (7 - 8)) \times 9)$$

$$29512 := ((-1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5) + 6)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))$$

$$29513 := (1 - ((2^3) \times (((-4 \times 56) + 7) \times (8 + 9))))$$

$$29514 := (-1 + ((23 \times (4^5)) + (67 \times 89)))$$

$$29515 := (((-1 \times 23) \times -(4^5)) + (67 \times 89))$$

$$29516 := ((1 - (23 \times (-4^5))) - (-67 \times 89))$$

$$29517 := (-1 \times (2 - ((3 + 4) \times (5 + (6 \times (78 \times 9))))))$$

$$29518 := (-1 \times (2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - 89))))))$$

$$29519 := (-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9))))$$

$$29520 := (((((12 + 3) + 45) \times 6) \times -((7 - 89)))$$

$$29521 := (((-1 + ((2 + ((3^4) + 5)) \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)$$

$$29522 := (-1 \times -(-2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 \times (7 - 89))))))$$

$$29523 := ((-12 \times (3 - (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)$$

$$29524 := (1 - (2 + 3 + 4)^5) / (6 - 7 + 8 - 9)$$

$$29525 := (1 + (2 + 3 + 4)^5) / (-6 + 7 - 8 + 9)$$

$$29526 := (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) / 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9)))$$

$$29527 := ((-1 \times 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 67)) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$29528 := ((1 - 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 67)) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$29529 := ((((-1 + 2) \times (3 \times ((4^5) + 67))) + 8) \times 9)$$

$$29530 := ((-1 + 2) + (((3 \times ((4^5) + 67)) + 8) \times 9))$$

$$29531 := (12 - ((3 + 4) \times (-5 + (-6 \times (78 \times 9))))$$

$$29532 := (-12 \times ((3 - 4) + (5 \times (6 \times (7 - 89))))$$

$$29533 := -1 + 2 + 3 + (4^5 + 6! - 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$29534 := (-12 + (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))))$$

$$29535 := ((-12 \times -(((3^{4+5}) + (6 + 7)) / 8)) - 9)$$

$$29536 := -((12 - (((345 - 6) - 7) \times 89)))$$

$$29537 := (1 - 2) \times 3!! \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9$$

$$29538 := ((1 - ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + 67))) + 8)) \times -9)$$

$$29539 := (-1 + 2 \times 3!! \times 4) \times 5 + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9$$

$$29540 := (-1 - ((234 - 5) \times (6 - ((7 + 8) \times 9))))$$

$$29541 := (-((1 - (2 - (3 - 45)))) \times (678 + 9))$$

$$29502 := ((((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2))) - 1)$$

$$29503 := (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1))))))$$

$$29504 := ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2)) + 1))$$

$$29505 := ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + (6^5)) - (4^{3 \times 2})))) \times -1)$$

$$29506 := (9 + ((8 \times ((7 + (6^5)) - (4^{3 \times 2}))) + 1))$$

$$29507 := (9 + ((87 - (6 - 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$29508 := (((-98 + 7) \times -(6 \times 54)) + (3 + 21))$$

$$29509 := (((987 \times 6) + (5 \times -4)) \times (3 + 2)) - 1$$

$$29510 := ((-9 \times 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2 + 1)))$$

$$29511 := (-9 \times -((((8 + ((7 - 6)^5))^4) - 3) / (2 \times 1)))$$

$$29512 := ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 + 6) - 5) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$29513 := (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - 3)) - (2 + 1))$$

$$29514 := ((-9 + (8 + 7)) \times (6 + ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1})))$$

$$29515 := (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) - 3)) \times -2) + 1)$$

$$29516 := ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times -(6 - ((5^4) + (3 \times (2 + 1))))$$

$$29517 := (((-((98 - 7) \times 6)) \times -(54)) + (32)) + (1))$$

$$29518 := (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 \times 1))$$

$$29519 := (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 + 1))$$

$$29520 := ((-9 \times 8) \times (7 - ((6 \times (5 + (4^3))) + (2 + 1))))$$

$$29521 := (((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times ((4 \times 3)^2)) + 1)$$

$$29522 := (9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - (3^2)))) - 1))$$

$$29523 := (((987 \times 6) \times 5) - ((43 \times 2) + (1)))$$

$$29524 := (((987 \times 6) \times 5) - ((43 \times -2) \times -1))$$

$$29525 := (((987 \times 6) \times 5) - ((43 \times 2) - (1)))$$

$$29526 := ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1))$$

$$29527 := (((((-9 - 8) \times 7) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -2) + 1)$$

$$29528 := ((((-9 \times 87) + 6) \times (5 - 43)) + (2 \times 1))$$

$$29529 := (-9 \times -((((8 + ((7 - 6)^5))^4) + 3) / 2) - 1))$$

$$29530 := (9 - 8 + 7!) \times 6! / 5! + 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)!$$

$$29531 := ((-9 + 8) - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 \times 321)))$$

$$29532 := (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 + 5)) - 4) \times -321)$$

$$29533 := ((9 - 8) - ((7 - (6 \times 5)) \times (4 \times 321)))$$

$$29534 := (-9 + (((87 \times (6 + 5)) - 4) \times (32 - 1)))$$

$$29535 := (((-9 \times ((8 \times (7 + 6)) - 5)) - 4) \times -(32 + 1))$$

$$29536 := (9 - 8 + 7) \times (6! \times 5 - 4 + 3!) + (2 + 1)!!$$

$$29537 := ((-9 \times -((((8 + ((7 - 6)^5))^4) + 3) / 2)) - 1)$$

$$29538 := (-9 \times -((((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5)) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) - 1))$$

$$29539 := ((-9 \times -((((8 + ((7 - 6)^5))^4) + 3) / 2)) + 1)$$

$$29540 := ((((-98 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -43) - (2 - 1))$$

$$29541 := (((-98 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -(43 \times (2 - 1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29542 &:= (1 + ((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times (678 + 9))) \\ 29543 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (34 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29544 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\ 29545 &:= (-1 - (2 - (((345 - 6) - 7) \times 89))) \\ 29546 &:= (-1 \times (2 - (((345 - 6) - 7) \times 89))) \\ 29547 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 \times 7) + 8)) \times 9) \\ 29548 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times (((345 - 6) - 7) \times 89)) \\ 29549 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (((345 - 6) - 7) \times 89)) \\ 29550 &:= (-1 \times (-2 + (((345 - 6) - 7) \times -89))) \\ 29551 &:= (((12^3) + (-4^5)) \times (6 \times 7)) - (8 + 9) \\ 29552 &:= (((-1 + 23) \times (4 \times (5 \times 67))) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 29553 &:= ((-12 \times -((3^{4+5}) + (6 + 7)/8)) + 9) \\ 29554 &:= ((-1 + 2 + 3!) + 4 - 5!) \times 6 - 7 + 8 + 9 \\ 29555 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times (34 + 5)) \times (6 \times -7)) - 8) \times 9) \\ 29556 &:= -(((-12 \times ((345 + 6) \times 7)) - (8 \times 9))) \\ 29557 &:= (1 + (((2 \times ((34 + 5) \times (6 \times 7))) + 8) \times 9)) \\ 29558 &:= (-(-12) + ((34 \times (-5 - 6)) \times (-7 - (-8 \times -9)))) \\ 29559 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4) + 5) \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) - 9) \\ 29560 &:= (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times (((456 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 29561 &:= (1 + (2^3) \times (((456 + 7) \times 8) - 9)) \\ 29562 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29563 &:= ((-1 + (-2 - 34)) \times ((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times (-8 - 9))) \\ 29564 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3) \times 45) - 6) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)) \\ 29565 &:= ((12 - 3) \times (45 \times ((-6 + 7) - (8 \times -9)))) \\ 29566 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29567 &:= ((-1 \times -2) - ((3^4) \times (5 \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29568 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (3^4)) \times -((5 \times 67) + (8 + 9))) \\ 29569 &:= (-(((1 - 23) \times (-4 \times -5)) \times 67)) + 89 \\ 29570 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (3!! + 4!) + 5 + 6!) \times (-7 + 8 + 9) \\ 29571 &:= ((-12 \times (-((345 + 6) \times 7)) - 8) - 9) \\ 29572 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3^4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29573 &:= (((-12 \times -((345 + 6))) \times 7) + 89) \\ 29574 &:= ((12 + (3^4)) \times ((5 \times 67) - (8 + 9))) \\ 29575 &:= (1 \times -(((-2 + 3) - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29576 &:= (1 - (((-2 + 3) - 456) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29577 &:= ((((-1 \times 2) - (3^4) + 5) \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 29578 &:= ((-12 - 34) \times (5 + ((6 - 78) \times 9))) \\ 29579 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29580 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - (3 \times (4 \times 5))) \times (6 + (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29581 &:= (-1 \times (234 - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29542 &:= ((((-98 \times 7) - (6 - 5)) \times -43) + (2 - 1)) \\ 29543 &:= (((-9 \times -8) - 7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29544 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(6 + ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2 \times 1))) \\ 29545 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(6 + ((5 \times (4 + 3))^2))) + 1) \\ 29546 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5))) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 29547 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5))) \times ((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 29548 &:= (((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) + (6 + 5))) \times -((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\ 29549 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) - ((4^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 29550 &:= -9 + (8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5 - 4 - (3 + 2 + 1)! \\ 29551 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2) - 1)) \\ 29552 &:= (9 + (((-87) \times (6 + 5)) + 4) \times ((-32) + 1))) \\ 29553 &:= ((-987 - (6 \times ((5 + (4^3))^2))) \times -1) \\ 29554 &:= ((((-98 + 7) \times 65) + 4) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 29555 &:= ((((-98 + 7) \times 65) + 4) \times -(3 + 2) \times 1) \\ 29556 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6^5)/4) + (3^{2+1})))) \\ 29557 &:= (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29558 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + 7)) - (((6 + 5)^4) + 3)) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29559 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5))) \times (((4 + 3)^2) - 1))) \\ 29560 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - (3^2))) - 1)) \\ 29561 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 \times ((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\ 29562 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) - (((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 29563 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times ((-7 \times 65) - (4 \times 321)))) \\ 29564 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) - ((43 + 2) + (1))) \\ 29565 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -((6^{(5+4)/3}) + (2 + 1))) \\ 29566 &:= (-9 + (((87 + 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\ 29567 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - ((5^4) - 3)) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29568 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 29569 &:= (((-987) \times -((6 \times 5))) - (43 + (2 \times -1))) \\ 29570 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) - (4 \times ((3^2) + 1))) \\ 29571 &:= (-9 + (87 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 29572 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(65 \times (4 + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29573 &:= (((987 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4) - (-(-((32 + 1)))))) \\ 29574 &:= (((-987) \times -((6 \times 5))) - 4) - ((32 \times 1)) \\ 29575 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 + 3))^2 \times 1) \\ 29576 &:= (((9 - 8) - ((7 \times -(65)) \times ((4^3) + (2 - 1)))))) \\ 29577 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) \times 5) + (-4 \times 3)) - 21) \\ 29578 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -(65 \times (4 + 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29579 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) - 6) \times -((5 \times (4 \times 3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 29580 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 + 6)) \times -(5 + ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29581 &:= ((-9 + 8) + (7 \times (((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29582 &:= ((1 - 234) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89)) & 29582 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 - 5) + (4^3))^2) + 1)) \\ 29583 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) - 6) + (-78)) \times -9)) & 29583 &:= ((((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3)))^2) - 1) \\ 29584 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3^4)) + (5^{6+7-8})) \times 9)) & 29584 &:= (((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + ((6 \times 5) + (4 + 3)))^2 \times 1) \\ 29585 &:= (((12^3) + (-4^5)) \times (6 \times 7)) + (8 + 9) & 29585 &:= (((-987) \times -6) - 5) \times ((4 + 3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 29586 &:= (1 - 2 + 3 + 4) \times (-5! - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) & 29586 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) - (4 \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 29587 &:= -1 + 2 + 3! \times (-4! \times 5 - 6 + 7! + 8 + 9) & 29587 &:= (((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) + 4) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 29588 &:= (1 - 2^{3+4}) \times 5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 & 29588 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) - (4 - (3 - 2))) \\ 29589 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 3) \times -((45 + (-67 \times 89)))) & 29589 &:= ((-9 \times (87 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29590 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times -3)) \times (-45 + (67 \times 89))) & 29590 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times ((7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 29591 &:= (-1 + (((23 - 4) + (56 \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) & 29591 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) \times (2 \times 1)))) \\ 29592 &:= ((-1 - 2) \times -(((3^4) \times 5) + 6) \times (7 + (8 + 9))) & 29592 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (((6^5) \times 4)/3)) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 29593 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 - 78)) \times 9))) & 29593 &:= ((-9 - (((8 + 7) \times (6 + 5)) + (4 + 3))^2) \times -1) \\ 29594 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) - (6 - 78)) \times 9))) & 29594 &:= ((-9 \times (87 - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29595 &:= ((-12 \times -(3 + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9) & 29595 &:= ((-98 \times -(7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4)) - (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29596 &:= -1 + (2 \times 3! \times (4! + 5!) + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) & 29596 &:= (-(((987 \times 6) \times 5) - 4) - 3) + (-21)) \\ 29597 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3) + (4 \times 5)) \times 67)) \times (8 + 9)) & 29597 &:= (9 + 8) \times (7 + 6 + 54 \times 32 \times 1) \\ 29598 &:= -1 + 2^{3+4+5} \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 & 29598 &:= (((9876 - 5) - 4) \times -(-3)) + ((-2 - 1)) \\ 29599 &:= 1 \times 2^{3+4+5} \times 6 + 7! - 8 - 9 & 29599 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - ((3 \times 2) + 1)))))) \\ 29600 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 34)) \times -(5 + (6 + 789))) & 29600 &:= ((((-987) \times -6) \times 5) - (4 + 3)) - ((2 + 1)) \\ 29601 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8))) \times 9) & 29601 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) - (-4 \times 3)) - (21)) \\ 29602 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times 6)))) \times -(7 - 89)) & 29602 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) - (4 + 3)) + (-2 - (-1)) \\ 29603 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((34 - (5^6)) + 789))) & 29603 &:= ((((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times 65) - 4) \times -((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29604 &:= (-12 - ((3 + 45) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) & 29604 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) + (5 - 4)) \times -(3 + 2)) - 1) \\ 29605 &:= (1 - (2 \times ((34 - (5^6)) + 789))) & 29605 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) + (4 - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 29606 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times 45)) \times -((6 \times 7) + 89)) & 29606 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) - ((4 + 3) - (2 + 1))) \\ 29607 &:= ((-12 - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times -((6 - 7) + (8 \times 9))) & 29607 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2) - 1))) \\ 29608 &:= (1 - (2 + 3)! - 4) \times 5 + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 & 29608 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) + (4 - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 29609 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3 + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8)) \times 9)) & 29609 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 29610 &:= ((1 + 234) \times ((5 \times 6) + (7 + 89))) & 29610 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 \times (5 \times ((4 + 3) \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29611 &:= (1 - ((2 + 3) \times (((4 \times 5) - 678) \times 9)) & 29611 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times ((6 + (5^4)) - (3 - 2))) + 1) \\ 29612 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! - 4 - 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) & 29612 &:= (((9876 - 5) \times (4 - (3 - 2))) - 1) \\ 29613 &:= (-(((1 + 2)^3) + (456 \times (-7 - (-8 \times 9)))) & 29613 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29614 &:= (((-1 - 2) - (-34 + 5)) \times (67 \times (8 + 9))) & 29614 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2))) - 1) \\ 29615 &:= (((-1 - ((2 + ((3^4) + 5)) \times 6)) \times -(7 \times 8)) - 9) & 29615 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times (2 + 1))))))) \\ 29616 &:= ((12 - ((3 \times 4) \times 5)) \times (6 - (7 \times 89))) & 29616 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) \times (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2)) + 1)) \\ 29617 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 + 45) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) & 29617 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)))) \times -2) - 1) \\ 29618 &:= (-1 \times -(2 - ((3 + 45) \times (6 - (7 \times 89)))) & 29618 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) - (-4 - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 29619 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3 + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8))) \times -9) & 29619 &:= ((((-987 \times 6) \times -5) - ((-4 \times 3) + 2)) - 1) \\ 29620 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3!! + (4 + 5 - 6)! \times (7! + 8 + 9) & 29620 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29621 &:= -1 - (2 \times 3)! + (4 + 5 - 6)! \times (7! + 8 + 9) & 29621 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3))) - (2 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29622 &:= ((-1 - (((-2^3) \times (456 + 7)) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 29623 &:= (-1 - (23 \times (4 \times (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))))) \\ 29624 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times - (5 - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 29625 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (34 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 29626 &:= (1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times (5 \times ((6 + 78) - 9)))) \\ 29627 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((34 + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\ 29628 &:= ((-(-12) \times -3) \times ((-4 - (5 \times 6)) - 789)) \\ 29629 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((34 + 5) \times (6 \times 7)) + 8) \times 9))) \\ 29630 &:= (-1 + (((2 - (3 - 4))^5 + 6) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 29631 &:= ((-1 + (-2^3)) - ((456 \times -((7 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 29632 &:= (1 \times ((-2^3) - (456 \times -((7 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 29633 &:= (-((1 + (2 \times 3))) - (- (456) \times (-7 + ((8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29634 &:= ((-1 - (2 + 3)) - (456 \times (-((7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 29635 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + 3) + (456 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29636 &:= (-1 - ((2 + (3 + 4)) \times ((5 - (6 \times 7)) \times 89))) \\ 29637 &:= ((-1 - 2) - (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29638 &:= (-((1 + (-2 + 3))) + (456 \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29639 &:= (-1 \times -((2 - 3) - (456 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29640 &:= (((((-1 + 2) \times 3^4) - 5) \times - (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29641 &:= ((-1 + 2) - (((3^4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29642 &:= ((1 + (-2 + 3)) + (456 \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\ 29643 &:= ((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (67 + 8)) - 9))) \\ 29644 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + ((3^4) \times ((5 \times (67 + 8)) - 9))) \\ 29645 &:= 1 - 2 + 3^4 \times (5 \times (67 + 8) - 9) \\ 29646 &:= (-((1 + 23) \times 4) + (5 \times 678) \times 9) \\ 29647 &:= (((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\ 29648 &:= (((1 \times 2)^3) + (- (456) \times (7 + (8 \times -9)))) \\ 29649 &:= (1 - ((-2^3) + (456 \times -((7 \times 8) + 9)))) \\ 29650 &:= -1 + (2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 29651 &:= (1 \times 2 + (3 + 4)! - 5!) \times 6 + 7 \times (8 + 9) \\ 29652 &:= (-12 \times -(((3^{4+5}) + (6 + 7))/8) + 9) \\ 29653 &:= -1 \times 2 \times 3^4 + 5 \times (67 \times 89) \\ 29654 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (3 \times ((4^5) + (67 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\ 29655 &:= (((((-1 - 2) + (3^{4+5}))/6) + (7 + 8)) \times 9) \\ 29656 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times (4 + (56 \times (7 + (8 + 9)))))) \\ 29657 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 + ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29658 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (-3 - ((4 - (5^6)) + 789))) \\ 29659 &:= (1 - (2 \times ((3 + 4) - ((5^6) - 789)))) \\ 29660 &:= (-1 - 2 - 3!!) \times (4! - 5 \times (6 + 7)) + 8 + 9 \\ 29661 &:= (-1 + (-2 + ((345 + 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29622 &:= ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 29623 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 \times (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2) + 1))) \\ 29624 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) - (6 \times (5^4))) \times -((3^2) - 1)) \\ 29625 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times -(((6 - (5 - 4))^3) \times (2 + 1))) \\ 29626 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1))) \\ 29627 &:= ((-9876 \times -((5 + 4)/3)) - (2 - 1)) \\ 29628 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (76 \times 5)) + (4 \times (3 \times 21)))) \\ 29629 &:= (((((-9 + 87) \times 6) - 5) \times (4^3)) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29630 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 29631 &:= (((-987) \times -6) \times 5) - ((4 + 3) \times -((2 + 1)))) \\ 29632 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) - (-4 + (3 - (21)))) \\ 29633 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2))) \times -1) \\ 29634 &:= ((9876 - (5 - (4 + 3))) \times ((2 + 1))) \\ 29635 &:= (((((-9 + 87) \times 6) - 5) \times (4^3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29636 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - (5 \times 4)) \times - (32 - 1)) \\ 29637 &:= ((987 \times (6 \times 5)) - (((4 - 32) + 1))) \\ 29638 &:= ((-987 \times - (6 \times 5)) + (4 \times ((3 \times 2) + 1))) \\ 29639 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) - 1)))) \\ 29640 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (((5^4) - 3)/2) + 1) \\ 29641 &:= ((-9 - ((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3))) \times - (2 - 1)) \\ 29642 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - 32)) + 1)) \\ 29643 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) - (-4 \times 3) + (21)) \\ 29644 &:= (-9 + (((8 + (7 \times 65)) \times (4^3)) + 21)) \\ 29645 &:= ((-98 - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29646 &:= (-9 \times (((8 - (7 \times 6)) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)) + 1) \\ 29647 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1))))))) \\ 29648 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) - (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 29649 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 29650 &:= -(((-((987 \times 6)) \times 5) - (43 + (-((2 + 1)))))) \\ 29651 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29652 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 29653 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 29654 &:= ((-9 \times (((8 - (7 \times 6)) - (5^4)) \times (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 29655 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 \times 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29656 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) + ((43 + 2) + (1))) \\ 29657 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^{4+3-2-1}))) \\ 29658 &:= ((((-987) \times -6) \times 5) + (((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\ 29659 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29660 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) + (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 29661 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29662 &:= ((-1 + 23) - (456 \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29663 &:= (-1 - (((2^3) - ((4 + 56) \times 7)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\
 29664 &:= (-(((-(1 + 23)) + (4 - (56 \times 7))) \times 8) \times 9) \\
 29665 &:= (-1 + (2 + ((345 + 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29666 &:= (-1 \times -(2 + ((345 + 67) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29667 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - (-345) + 6) \times -(78 + 9))) \\
 29668 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) + 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9))) \\
 29669 &:= (1 - (2 + (((3^4) + 5) \times ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)))) \\
 29670 &:= (1 \times (2 \times ((3 - (4 - (5^6))) - 789))) \\
 29671 &:= (1 + (2 \times ((3 - (4 - (5^6))) - 789))) \\
 29672 &:= (((1 + (2 + 3)) - 4) \times ((5^6) - 789)) \\
 29673 &:= (((-1 - (2^3))) \times (456 + (7 + 8))) \times 9) \\
 29674 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times (-((3 - 4) + ((5^6) - 789))) \\
 29675 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (67 + 8)) \times 9))) \\
 29676 &:= (-12 \times -(((3 + 4)^{5+6-7}) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 29677 &:= 1 \times (2 + 3) \times (4 - 5!) + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 29678 &:= -1 - 2 - 3!! + 4! + 5! + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 29679 &:= (-1 - ((2^3) \times ((4^5) - (6 \times 789)))) \\
 29680 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -((4 + (5^6)) - 789)) \\
 29681 &:= (-1 + (((23 \times 4) + 5) \times (((6 \times 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\
 29682 &:= ((-1 - (((2 \times (3^4)) - 5) \times (6 + (7 + 8)))) \times -9) \\
 29683 &:= (-1 - (2 \times ((3^4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\
 29684 &:= (-((-12 + (34 \times (5 + 6)))) \times (7 - 89)) \\
 29685 &:= ((-12 - 3) \times (-(((45 \times 6) \times 7)) - 89)) \\
 29686 &:= (-1 - ((2^{3+4}) - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\
 29687 &:= ((((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times 8) - 9) \\
 29688 &:= ((-123 - 4) - (5 \times -((67 \times 89)))) \\
 29689 &:= -1 \times 2 + 3!!/4 \times (5 + 6) \times (7 + 8) - 9 \\
 29690 &:= (-1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + (67 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 29691 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)))) \times 9) \\
 29692 &:= (1 + ((2 + (3 \times ((4^5) + (67 + 8)))) \times 9)) \\
 29693 &:= (-1 - 2^{3!} - 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29694 &:= ((-1 + ((((((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times 8)) - 9) \\
 29695 &:= (-1 + (-2 \times ((-3 \times 4) - ((5^6) - (789)))) \\
 29696 &:= ((-123 + 4) - (5 \times -((67 \times 89)))) \\
 29697 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 \times 4) + (5^6)) - 789))) \\
 29698 &:= -1 + (2 + 3!! + 4^5 - 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29699 &:= (-1 + (((2 - 3) + 45) \times (-67 - 8)) \times -9) \\
 29700 &:= -(((1^{23}) - 45) \times ((67 + 8) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29662 &:= (9 - (((-(8 - (-7 \times 65))) \times (4^3)) - 21))) \\
 29663 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\
 29664 &:= ((-9 \times 8) \times -(7 + ((6 + (5 + 4)) \times (3^{2+1})))) \\
 29665 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2)))))) \times -1) \\
 29666 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\
 29667 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\
 29668 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -(6 + (5 \times (4^3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 29669 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4))) - 3) \times -2) - 1) \\
 29670 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times ((7 \times (6 \times 5)) - 4))) - 3) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\
 29671 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times 7) \times (((6 \times 5) - (4 + 3))^2 + 1))) \\
 29672 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 29673 &:= (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) - (5^4)) \times -(3^{2+1})) \\
 29674 &:= ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) + (4^3 \times (2 - 1))) \\
 29675 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) - (3 - 21)) \\
 29676 &:= (-9 + ((8 + 7) \times (((6 \times 5) \times ((4^3) + 2)) - 1))) \\
 29677 &:= (((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + (6 - 5)) \times (4 - (3 \times 21))) \\
 29678 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) - 32))) + 1)) \\
 29679 &:= (((9876 - (5 \times -4)) - 3) \times ((2 + 1))) \\
 29680 &:= ((-98 + (7 \times 6)) \times -(((5 \times 4) + 3)^2 + 1)) \\
 29681 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)) - 2)) - 1) \\
 29682 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 + (6 + 5)) + ((4 \times 3)^{2+1}))) \\
 29683 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((76 \times ((5 \times 4) + 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\
 29684 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + (5^4))) + (3^{2+1})) \\
 29685 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times (7 - 65)) \times (4^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 29686 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2}) + 1)) \\
 29687 &:= (-9 + (-8 \times ((7 - 65) \times (43 - (-21)))))) \\
 29688 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2}) - 1)) \\
 29689 &:= (-9 - (((8 \times (7 - 65)) \times (4^3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 29690 &:= ((-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + 2))) - 1) \\
 29691 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
 29692 &:= (-9 + (((8 + 7) \times (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^3) + 2) + 1)) \\
 29693 &:= (-98 + ((7 + (6 \times (5 - (4 - 3))))^{2+1})) \\
 29694 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 29695 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) + ((43 \times 2) - (1))) \\
 29696 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))) - 1)) \\
 29697 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) + ((43 \times 2) + (1))) \\
 29698 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3) + 2) - 1) \\
 29699 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\
 29700 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) \times -((5 + (4^3)) - (2 + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29701 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 - 45)) \times ((67 + 8) \times 9))) \\
 29702 &:= -1 \times 2^{3+4} \times 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\
 29703 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
 29704 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + (34 \times (5 + 6))) \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29705 &:= (1 \times (((-2 + 3) + 456) \times ((7 \times 8) + 9))) \\
 29706 &:= (1 + ((2 - (3 + 456)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29707 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times -4) + (5 \times (67 \times 89)) \\
 29708 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3 \times (4! + 5!) + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29709 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) \times (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times (7 + 8)))))) \times -9) \\
 29710 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29711 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) \times 5)) \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9))) \\
 29712 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 29713 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times 34) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89)) \\
 29714 &:= (-1 - ((2 + 3) \times ((4 \times 5) - (67 \times 89)))) \\
 29715 &:= (((1 - 2) - 34) \times ((56 \times -((7 + 8))) - 9)) \\
 29716 &:= (-1 \times (23 \times (4 - ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29717 &:= (-1 + (2 \times ((3 - ((4 - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times 8) \times 9))) \\
 29718 &:= (1 \times (-2 \times ((-3^{4+5}) + ((67 \times 8) \times 9))) \\
 29719 &:= (((-1 \times -((2 \times 3)^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7)) - 89) \\
 29720 &:= ((1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) - 89) \\
 29721 &:= (((-1 - (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
 29722 &:= (-1 + ((23 \times -4) - ((-5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\
 29723 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (((3 - 4) + (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\
 29724 &:= ((1 - (23 \times 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\
 29725 &:= ((1 + (-2)) - (((-3 + 4) - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\
 29726 &:= ((1 + (-2)) \times (((-3 + 4) - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\
 29727 &:= (-(((1 - 23) \times -4)) - (-(-5) \times (-67 \times 89))) \\
 29728 &:= ((1 \times -(-2)) - (((-3 + 4) - (5 \times 67)) \times 89)) \\
 29729 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 29730 &:= ((1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times (((5 + (6 \times 7)) \times 8) - 9))) \\
 29731 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\
 29732 &:= ((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\
 29733 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3^4)) + (-((5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\
 29734 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
 29735 &:= ((1^2) - ((3^4) + (-((5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\
 29736 &:= ((1 \times (2 - (3^4))) - (5 \times -((67 \times 89)))) \\
 29737 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - 45) \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
 29738 &:= (-1 \times -((2 - ((3 - 45) \times (6 + (78 \times 9)))) \\
 29739 &:= ((-1 + ((2^3) \times ((4 + 5) \times 6))) \times (78 - 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29701 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))))) + 1) \\
 29702 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (((7 - 65) \times (4^3)) - 2)) + 1)) \\
 29703 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) + 1)))) \\
 29704 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + (3/(2 + 1)))) \\
 29705 &:= ((-9 + (((8 - 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times (4^{3+2}))) \times -1) \\
 29706 &:= ((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3) \times (2 \times 1)) \\
 29707 &:= (((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (5^4))) - 3) \times 2) + 1) \\
 29708 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43)) - 2))) - 1) \\
 29709 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times ((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 29710 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - ((7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43)) - 2))) + 1) \\
 29711 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - ((5^4) - 3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 29712 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\
 29713 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))))) \times -1) \\
 29714 &:= (((-98 - 7) \times (6 - ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2))) - 1) \\
 29715 &:= ((-98 - 7) \times (6 - ((5 + (4 \times 3))^2 \times 1))) \\
 29716 &:= (-9 - (((8 - 7) - (6 \times 5)) \times ((4^{3+2}) + 1))) \\
 29717 &:= (((((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times (6 - (5^4))) + 3) \times 2) - 1) \\
 29718 &:= (-(((9 - 87) \times (6 + (54 + 321)))) \\
 29719 &:= ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + (6 \times (5 - (4 - 3))))^{2+1})) \\
 29720 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 \times 2))) + 1)) \\
 29721 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 65) \times (4^3)) - 2))) \times -1) \\
 29722 &:= (9 - ((8 \times (((7 - 65) \times (4^3)) - 2)) - 1)) \\
 29723 &:= (9 + 8 + 7!) \times 6 - 5^4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 29724 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 \times 6) - (5^4))) - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\
 29725 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times 5) \times (((4 \times 3)^2) + 1)) \\
 29726 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 29727 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times ((7 + 6) \times 5)) + 4) \times -((3^{2+1})) \\
 29728 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43)))) + (2 - 1)) \\
 29729 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 43)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 29730 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 29731 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\
 29732 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) - (2 - 1)) \\
 29733 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 \times (2 - 1)))) \\
 29734 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 - 1)) \\
 29735 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + (3 + 2)))))) - 1) \\
 29736 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times (((7 \times 6) - (5^4)) \times 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\
 29737 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) + (4 \times 32)) - 1) \\
 29738 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) + (4 \times 32)) \times 1) \\
 29739 &:= (((987 \times 6) \times 5) + (4 \times 32)) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29740 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times -((34 + (5^6)) - 789)) \\
 29741 &:= (((-123 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times 8)))) - 9) \\
 29742 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times -((5 \times 6) - 7)) - 89) \\
 29743 &:= (((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4) - 5)) \times 6) + 7) \times -8) - 9) \\
 29744 &:= (((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4)))^5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\
 29745 &:= (((((12 + 3) + 456) \times 7) - (-8)) \times -(-9)) \\
 29746 &:= ((12 - (3^4)) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89)) \\
 29747 &:= (-1 \times ((2 \times 34) - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\
 29748 &:= (12 - ((3 - 45) \times (6 + ((78 \times 9)))) \\
 29749 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times (7 \times (8 + 9)))) \\
 29750 &:= (((12^3) - (45 - 67)) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 29751 &:= (((((12 + 3) \times 4) \times ((5 - 67) \times -8)) - 9) \\
 29752 &:= ((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) \times (7 - (8 - 9))) \\
 29753 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 - 4 \times 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 29754 &:= (((((12/3)^4) + 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + (8 \times 9))) \\
 29755 &:= (((-12 - 3) \times 4) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\
 29756 &:= (1 + 2 \times (3!! + 4!)) \times 5! / 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 \\
 29757 &:= ((((-1 - 23) \times 4) + 5) \times -((6 \times (7 \times 8)) - 9)) \\
 29758 &:= -1 \times 2 - 3! \times ((4 + 5 - 6!) \times 7 + 8 + 9) \\
 29759 &:= (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 - (8 - 9)))) \\
 29760 &:= -(((-1 \times (((-2 \times 3)^4) - 56)) \times (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\
 29761 &:= (((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4) - 5)) \times 6) + 7) \times -8) + 9) \\
 29762 &:= (-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) - (5 \times 678)) \times 9)) \\
 29763 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - ((3^4) - (5 \times 678))) \times 9) \\
 29764 &:= (1 - (((2 + (3^4)) - (5 \times 678)) \times 9)) \\
 29765 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3 + 4 \times 5 \times (6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\
 29766 &:= ((12 + (345 + 6)) \times (-7 + 89)) \\
 29767 &:= ((-1 + ((2 + ((3 - 45) \times 6)) \times 7)) \times -(8 + 9)) \\
 29768 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7)) - (8 + 9)) \\
 29769 &:= (((((12 + 3) \times 4) \times ((5 - 67) \times -8)) + 9) \\
 29770 &:= (((-1 \times 2) - (((3^4) - 5) \times 6)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9))) \\
 29771 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times (4 - ((5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\
 29772 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (-4 + 56 \times (7 + 8) - 9) \\
 29773 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3! + (4^5 + 6! + 7) \times (8 + 9) \\
 29774 &:= (-1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 + 5! + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\
 29775 &:= (-((12 \times 3) - (4 - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\
 29776 &:= (1 - (2 + 3)!) \times 4 - 5 + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\
 29777 &:= (((((-1 + ((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) + 7) \times 8) + 9) \\
 29778 &:= (((-1 - 2) - 34) + (((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\
 29779 &:= (-((1 \times 2) - (34 - ((5 \times 67) \times 89)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29740 &:= ((((-98 \times 76) + 5) \times -4) - (32 \times 1)) \\
 29741 &:= ((((-98 \times 76) + 5) \times -4) - (32 - 1)) \\
 29742 &:= (-9 - (((87 \times 6) \times (-54 - 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 29743 &:= (-9 - (((87 \times 6) \times (-54 - 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 29744 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 \times (6 + 5)))) \times ((4 + 3)^2)) + 1) \\
 29745 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (7 \times ((6 \times (5 + 4)) + (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\
 29746 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (((6 \times (5 + 4)) + 3)^2))) + 1) \\
 29747 &:= (-9 + ((87 \times (6 \times (54 + 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\
 29748 &:= ((-9 + (((87 + 6) \times 5) \times (4^3))) - (2 + 1)) \\
 29749 &:= ((((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -(((6 - (5 - 4))^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\
 29750 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times 7) \times -((6 + (5 \times ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1)) \\
 29751 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\
 29752 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) - 1)) \\
 29753 &:= (((-9 \times 87) \times ((6 + 5) - ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\
 29754 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times 6)) \times -5 + (4^{3+2-1})) \\
 29755 &:= (((-9 \times 87) \times ((6 + 5) - ((4 + 3)^2))) + 1) \\
 29756 &:= (((-98 \times 7) - 6) \times (5 - (((4 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 29757 &:= ((-98 + 7) \times -6 + ((5 \times (4^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 29758 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) + (5 \times (4 \times 3)))^2))) - 1) \\
 29759 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + (2 + 1))))))) \\
 29760 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\
 29761 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) \times (-54 - 3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\
 29762 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) \times (-54 - 3)) + (2 - 1))) \\
 29763 &:= (-9 \times ((87 \times ((6 + 5) - ((4 + 3)^2))) - 1) \\
 29764 &:= ((((-98 \times 76) + 5) \times -4) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\
 29765 &:= (9 - (((87 \times 6) \times (-54 - 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\
 29766 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) - (2 + 1))) \\
 29767 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\
 29768 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2))) + 1)) \\
 29769 &:= ((-9 - (((87 + 6) \times 5) \times (4^3))) \times -2 - 1) \\
 29770 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times 7)) \times -((65 \times (4 + 3)) + (2 + 1))) \\
 29771 &:= ((-9 - (((87 + 6) \times 5) \times (4^3)) + 2)) \times -1) \\
 29772 &:= (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - ((65 - (4 + 3))^2 \times 1))) \\
 29773 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times 2) - 1) \\
 29774 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + (6 \times (5 - (4 - 3))))^{2+1})) \\
 29775 &:= (-9 - (8 + (7 \times (65 - (4321)))) \\
 29776 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4) - 3)) - 2))) - 1) \\
 29777 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (((7 - 6) + (5 \times (4 \times 3)))^2))) \times -1) \\
 29778 &:= (-(((((-98) \times 76) + 5) \times 4) - 3)) - ((-2 - 1)) \\
 29779 &:= ((-((-((-98 \times 76) + 5) \times 4)) - 32) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29780 &:= (((1-2)-34) + ((5 \times (-67 \times -89)))) \\ 29781 &:= (((((-1-2) \times -3)^4) \times 5) - (6 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29782 &:= ((1^2) - (((-3^4) - (-5 \times -(678))) \times 9)) \\ 29783 &:= (-((12 \times 3)) + (4 + (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29784 &:= (-(((1+2)^3)) - (4 + (-((5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\ 29785 &:= ((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times (5 - (6 - (7 + (8 + 9)))) \\ 29786 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 29787 &:= (((-1 - 23) - 4) - (-5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29788 &:= (-1 \times ((23 + 4) - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29789 &:= (1 - ((23 + 4) + (-5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29790 &:= ((-1 + (((2 \times 3)^4) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7))) - (8 + 9)) \\ 29791 &:= (((-1 - 2) + 34)^{-1} - ((-5 - ((6 - 7) + 8)) + 9)) \\ 29792 &:= ((1 + (2 \times -((3 \times 4)))) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29793 &:= ((12 - 34) - (5 \times (-67 \times 89))) \\ 29794 &:= (((-1 - 2) \times (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29795 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + 3) \times 4) - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29796 &:= -(((1 \times 23) - 4) + ((5 \times 67) \times -89)) \\ 29797 &:= ((1 - (23 - 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29798 &:= (((((-1 \times -2)^{3+4}) \times 5) - 6) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9)) \\ 29799 &:= -(((1 - (2 - 3))^4) - ((5 \times -67) \times -89)) \\ 29800 &:= (-1 + 2^3 \times 4)^{5 \times (6-7)+8} + 9 \\ 29801 &:= (-1 \times ((2 - (3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 29802 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7)) + (8 + 9)) \\ 29803 &:= ((-1 + 2) \times -((3 \times 4) - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29804 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 \times 4) - (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29805 &:= (-1 - (((2 + 3) + 4) - ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29806 &:= (-1 \times (((2 + 3) + 4) - ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29807 &:= (1 - (((2 + 3) + 4) - ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29808 &:= (((-((-1 + (2 \times 34))) - 5) \times 6) \times (-78 + 9)) \\ 29809 &:= ((-1 + (2 - 3)) + (-4 - (-((5 \times 67)) \times 89))) \\ 29810 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times ((4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 8)))) - 9)) \\ 29811 &:= (((-1^{23}) \times 4) - (5 \times (-67 \times 89))) \\ 29812 &:= (((1^{23}) - 4) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29813 &:= ((-1 - ((2 + 3) - 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29814 &:= ((-((-1 \times -2) - 3) - (-4 - ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29815 &:= (((1^{234}) \times 5) \times (67 \times 89)) \\ 29816 &:= (-1 - (-2 - (-((3 - 4) \times 5)) \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29817 &:= (-1 \times (-2 - (-((3 - 4) \times 5)) \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29818 &:= ((-1 + ((23 + 4) \times (5 \times (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29819 &:= ((-1 - (2 - (3 + 4))) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29780 &:= ((-((-((-98 \times 76) + 5)) \times 4)) - (32 \times 1)) \\ 29781 &:= ((-9 - (8 - 7)) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 29782 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times 7) + 6) / - (5 - (4 + 3)))^{2+1}) \\ 29783 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 29784 &:= (((-9 + 8) \times 7) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 29785 &:= (-9 + (((((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5) - 4)^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 29786 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (((6 + 5)^4) \times (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29787 &:= (((-9876 - 54) \times -3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29788 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (7 + (6 + 5))) \times 4))^3) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29789 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (7 + (6 + 5))) \times 4))^3) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 29790 &:= (-9 + ((876 + 543) \times (21))) \\ 29791 &:= (((-9 - (8 - (7 + 6))) + (5 \times (4 + 3)))^{2+1}) \\ 29792 &:= (((98 \times -(76)) \times (5 - (4 + 3))) \times ((2 \times 1))) \\ 29793 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (7 + (6 + 5))) \times 4))^3) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29794 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (7 + (6 + 5))) \times 4))^3) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29795 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + 3))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29796 &:= -(((9 - 87) \times ((65 - 4) + 321))) \\ 29797 &:= ((-9 + (8 + 7)) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 29798 &:= -(((98 + ((7 - 6) - 5)) \times (4 - 321))) \\ 29799 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))) - 1))) \\ 29800 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 - 7)) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 29801 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + 3))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29802 &:= ((-9 - (((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5) - 4)^3 + 2) \times -1) \\ 29803 &:= (-9 + (((8 - (7 - 6)) \times 5) - 4)^3 + 21) \\ 29804 &:= ((((-98 \times 76) - 5) \times -4) - ((3^2) - 1)) \\ 29805 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4))/3)))) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 29806 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))))) - 1) \\ 29807 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)))))) \\ 29808 &:= -((-9 - ((876 + 543) \times (21)))) \\ 29809 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\ 29810 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times -(2 \times 1)) \\ 29811 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29812 &:= (((-9 - ((8 - (7 + (6 + 5))) \times 4))^3) + 21) \\ 29813 &:= ((((-987 - 6) \times 5) - 4) \times -(3 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29814 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) \times 2))) - 1) \\ 29815 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 \times 6))) + 5) \times -((4^3) + (2 + 1))) \\ 29816 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times ((7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) \times 2)) + 1)) \\ 29817 &:= (-9 \times -((8 \times (((7 + 6) \times 5) + 4) \times (3 \times 2))) + 1) \\ 29818 &:= ((-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))) - 2) + 1) \\ 29819 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + 3))) + 21) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29820 &:= ((-1 \times (2 - 3)) - (-4 + (-((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29821 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3)) + 4) - (-((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29822 &:= ((-(((1 - 2) \times 3)) + 4) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89)) \\ 29823 &:= -((1 - (((2 + 3) + 4) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29824 &:= (1 \times (((2 + 3) + 4) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29825 &:= (1 + (((2 + 3) + 4) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29826 &:= (((1 - 2) + (3 \times 4)) - (5 \times -((67 \times 89)))) \\ 29827 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times 3)) \times -(4 + ((5 + (6 \times 78)) \times 9))) \\ 29828 &:= (-1 + ((2 \times (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29829 &:= (-1 \times -((2 \times (3 + 4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29830 &:= -(((1 - (2 + (3 \times 4))) + (-((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29831 &:= (((1 - (2 - 3))^4) + ((5 \times -67) \times -89)) \\ 29832 &:= (((-1 - ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times -((5 \times 6) - 7)) - (8 - 9)) \\ 29833 &:= (-1 + ((23 - 4) - (5 \times -((67 \times 89)))) \\ 29834 &:= (((1 \times 23) - 4) - ((5 \times 67) \times -89)) \\ 29835 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times ((4^5) - (((6 - 7) - 8) \times 9))) \\ 29836 &:= ((-1 + 2) + (3 \times (45 \times ((6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)))) \\ 29837 &:= ((1 \times 2) - ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times ((7 + 8) \times 9))) \\ 29838 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times (4 - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29839 &:= -((-12 - ((3 \times 4) + ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29840 &:= (((1^{23}) + 4) \times (5 + (67 \times 89))) \\ 29841 &:= ((-1 + (23 + 4)) - ((-5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29842 &:= ((1 \times (23 + 4)) - (-5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29843 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (((3 - 4) + (5^6)) - (78 \times 9))) \\ 29844 &:= (1 \times (-2 \times ((-3 + 4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29845 &:= (1 + (-2 \times ((-3 + 4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29846 &:= ((-1 - 2) + (34 + ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29847 &:= (-((1 \times 2)) + (34 + ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29848 &:= (1 + (-2 + (34 - (5 \times (-67 \times 89)))) \\ 29849 &:= ((1^2) \times (34 - (5 \times (-67 \times 89)))) \\ 29850 &:= ((1^2) + (34 - (5 \times (-67 \times 89)))) \\ 29851 &:= ((1 \times 2) + (34 + ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29852 &:= -(((1 - 2) - 34) - (((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29853 &:= (-1 \times -((2 - ((3 - (4 \times 56)) \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 29854 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times -((4 + (5^6)) - (78 \times 9))) \\ 29855 &:= -((-((12 \times 3)) - (4 + (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29856 &:= ((1 - ((2^3) \times (45 - 6))) \times (-7 - 89)) \\ 29857 &:= (((-1 + ((2 \times 3)^4)) \times ((5 \times 6) - 7)) + (8 \times 9)) \\ 29858 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 + (4 \times (5 - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))))) \\ 29859 &:= -((1 + (2 \times ((-3 - 4) - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29820 &:= ((-98 - 7) \times (6 - (((5 + (4 \times 3))^2) + 1))) \\ 29821 &:= ((((-98 \times 76) - 5) \times -4) + (3 \times (2 + 1))) \\ 29822 &:= ((((-98 \times 76) - 5) \times -4) + ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 29823 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - ((6 \times (5^4))/3)) \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 29824 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 7) + (6 \times 543))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 29825 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - (3 + 2)))))) \times -1) \\ 29826 &:= (-9 \times -(((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 29827 &:= (((-9 \times 8) - (7 \times (6 - (5^4)))) \times ((3 \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29828 &:= (((-98 \times 76) - (5 + 4)) \times -((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 29829 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (((5^4) + 3)/2)) - 1) \\ 29830 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + 6))) \times (((5^4) + 3)/(2 \times 1))) \\ 29831 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) - (3^{2+1})))) \\ 29832 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 + 1))) \\ 29833 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)) \times 2))) \times -1) \\ 29834 &:= (-9 + ((87 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3)) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 29835 &:= (-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (((6 + 5) \times (4 \times (3 + 2))) + 1))) \\ 29836 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))) + (2 - 1)) \\ 29837 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 + 7) \times (6 + (5 \times 43)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29838 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 29839 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - 2)) - 1) \\ 29840 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - (2 \times 1))) \\ 29841 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) - 2)) + 1) \\ 29842 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)))) \times -2) \\ 29843 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 - (5^4)) \times 3)))) \times -2) + 1) \\ 29844 &:= (-9 - (((8 + (76)) + (5 - (-4))) \times -((321)))) \\ 29845 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + ((3 + 2) - 1)))) \\ 29846 &:= (-98 - ((7 - (6 \times (5^4))) \times ((3^2) - 1))) \\ 29847 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + ((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2)) - 1))) \\ 29848 &:= (((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) - (2 - 1))) \\ 29849 &:= (((-98 + 7) \times -6) + ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2)) + 1) \\ 29850 &:= ((-9 - (87 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3))) \times -2) \\ 29851 &:= (9 + ((87 \times (((6 + 5) - 4)^3)) + (2 - 1))) \\ 29852 &:= -(((9 \times (8 - (76 + ((54 + 3)^2)))) + 1)) \\ 29853 &:= (((9 \times -8) - 7) + (6 - (5 \times 4))) \times -((321))) \\ 29854 &:= ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) - 2))) + 1) \\ 29855 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - ((3 + 2) - 1)))))) \\ 29856 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3))/(2 + 1))) \\ 29857 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times ((6 - ((5^4) + 3)) \times 2)) + 1) \\ 29858 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5^4) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29859 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$29860 := ((1 \times (2 + 3)) \times (4 + (5 - (67 \times -89))))$$

$$29861 := (-1 + (((2 \times 34) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))$$

$$29862 := ((12 \times ((3^4) \times (5 \times 6))) + (78 \times 9))$$

$$29863 := (1 + (((2 \times 34) - 5) \times (6 \times (7 + (8 \times 9)))))$$

$$29864 := ((-1 + (2 + (3 + 4))) \times -(5 - (6 \times (7 \times 89))))$$

$$29865 := ((-12 \times -((3 + (4 \times ((5 + 6) \times 7))) \times 8)) + 9)$$

$$29866 := 1 \times 2 \times (-3!! + 4 + 5^6 + 7 + 8 + 9)$$

$$29867 := -1 \times 2 + (3!! + 4^5 + 6 + 7) \times (8 + 9)$$

$$29868 := (-12 + 3^4 \times 5) \times (-6 - 7 + 89)$$

$$29869 := (-1 \times -((2 + (3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7)))) \times (8 + 9)))$$

$$29870 := (-1 - ((2 - ((3^4) \times (56 - (7 + 8)))) \times 9))$$

$$29871 := (-1 \times 2 + 3^4 \times (56 - 7 - 8)) \times 9$$

$$29872 := (1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 - 78))) + 9))$$

$$29873 := ((((-1 - ((2 + 3)^4) - 5) \times 6) - 7) \times -8) + 9)$$

$$29874 := (((-1 - 2) + (3^4)) \times ((56 - 7) \times 8) - 9)$$

$$29875 := (((12 + 3) \times 4) + (-5 \times (-67 \times 89)))$$

$$29876 := (((-1 \times 2) \times -((3 + 4)^5)) - (6 \times (7 \times 89)))$$

$$29877 := ((-1 - 2) - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))))$$

$$29878 := (-1 \times (2 + (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))))$$

$$29879 := (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) - (5 \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 \times 9))$$

$$29880 := ((-1 + ((2^{(3-4) \times -5}) \times (6 + 7))) \times (8 \times 9))$$

$$29881 := ((-1 + 2) - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))))$$

$$29882 := (-1 \times -((2 - (3 \times (4 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))))$$

$$29883 := (-1 \times -((2 \times 34) + (5 \times (67 \times 89)))$$

$$29884 := -(((12 - (3^4)) - ((5 \times 67) \times 89)))$$

$$29885 := (-1 - (2 \times (((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))$$

$$29886 := (((-1 - 2) - (3 \times (45 \times (6 + 7)))) \times -(8 + 9))$$

$$29887 := (((-1 - (2 \times ((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times 7))) \times 8) - 9)$$

$$29888 := (-1 - (((2 + (3^4)) \times (5 \times (6 - 78))) - 9))$$

$$29889 := ((-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8))) \times 9)$$

$$29890 := ((-1 + 2) + ((3^4) \times ((56 - (7 + 8)) \times 9))$$

$$29891 := (-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) + (5 + 6)) \times ((7 \times 8) - 9))$$

$$29892 := (-12 \times ((3 - 4) - (5 \times (-6 - ((7 \times 8) \times 9))))$$

$$29893 := ((-1 - 2) + ((3^4) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))))$$

$$29894 := (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) + 9))$$

$$29895 := ((1 - (2 - (3^4))) - (5 \times -((67 \times 89))))$$

$$29896 := (((-1 \times -2)^3) \times ((4 - 5) + (6 \times (7 \times 89))))$$

$$29897 := ((-1 + 2) - (-((3^4)) + -((5 \times 67) \times 89)))$$

$$29898 := ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8)) \times 9)$$

$$29899 := ((1 + (2 + (3^4))) - (-((5 \times 67) \times 89))$$

$$29860 := -9 \times 8 - 7 \times ((6 + 5) \times 4 - 3! \times (2 + 1)!!)$$

$$29861 := (((((-9 \times 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -(54 + (3^2))) - 1)$$

$$29862 := (9 - (((8 + (76)) + (5 - (-4))) \times -((321))))$$

$$29863 := ((-9 \times -8) + ((7 + (6 \times (5 - (4 - 3))))^{2+1}))$$

$$29864 := (9 - 8 + 7) \times (6 \times (5^4 - 3) + 2 - 1)$$

$$29865 := ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) + (6 \times ((5^4) \times ((3^2) - 1))))$$

$$29866 := ((-987 \times -(6 \times 5)) + (4^{3+2-1}))$$

$$29867 := ((-9 \times 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5 + 43)^2) - 1)))$$

$$29868 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) - (2 + 1))$$

$$29869 := ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times 6) + (5 \times ((4 + 3)^{2+1}))))$$

$$29870 := (((-9 \times -8) + 7) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1}))$$

$$29871 := (-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (((6 - (5 - 4)) \times 3)^{2+1})))$$

$$29872 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + (2 - 1))$$

$$29873 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + (2 \times 1))$$

$$29874 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - ((6 + (5 + 4))^3))) + (2 + 1))$$

$$29875 := (((-98 \times 76) - 5) \times -4) + (3 \times 21)$$

$$29876 := ((-9876 - ((5^4) \times 32)) \times -1)$$

$$29877 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 \times 3))) - (2 + 1))$$

$$29878 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 \times 3))) - (2 \times 1))$$

$$29879 := (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - 3))) - (2 + 1))))$$

$$29880 := (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times ((5^4) - 3)) + (2 + 1)))$$

$$29881 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 - 1))$$

$$29882 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 \times 1))$$

$$29883 := ((((-9 \times (8 \times 7)) + 6) \times -(5 \times (4 \times 3))) + (2 + 1))$$

$$29884 := ((-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times 5)) \times (4 \times (32 - 1)))$$

$$29885 := -9 + 8 + (7 \times (6! - 5) - 4!) \times (3 + 2 + 1)$$

$$29886 := ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) - (2 + 1))$$

$$29887 := (-9 - (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))))$$

$$29888 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) - 1)$$

$$29889 := (-9 \times (((-(-87) + 6)) + (54 \times -((3 \times 21))))))$$

$$29890 := ((-9 \times ((8 \times 7) - (((6 + (5 + 4))^3) + 2))) + 1)$$

$$29891 := (-9 + ((8 + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5^4) - (3^{2+1}))))$$

$$29892 := ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times ((5 + 4)^3)) + (2 + 1))$$

$$29893 := ((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + (3 + 2)))) + 1)$$

$$29894 := (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 + 2)))) + 1))$$

$$29895 := (-9 - ((8 \times 7) \times (6 - ((5 \times 4) \times (3^{2+1}))))$$

$$29896 := (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 + 2)))) - 1))$$

$$29897 := (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1)$$

$$29898 := ((((-((98/7) \times 65)) + 4) \times -((32 + 1))))$$

$$29899 := (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - (5^4)))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29900 &:= (-1 \times -(23 \times (4 + ((5 + (6 + 7)) \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29901 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - (45 + 6)) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 29902 &:= -(((1 \times 2) - ((-3 \times (45 + 67)) \times -89))) \\ 29903 &:= (-(-(((1 - 23) \times -4))) - (-(-5) \times (-67 \times 89))) \\ 29904 &:= (((12 - 3) + (4 - 5)) \times ((6 \times 7) \times -(-89))) \\ 29905 &:= (1 + (2 \times (((3 - 4) + 5) \times 6) \times (7 \times 89))) \\ 29906 &:= ((1 \times 2) + ((-3 \times (45 + 67)) \times -89)) \\ 29907 &:= ((1 \times (23 \times 4)) + (-5 \times -((67 \times 89)))) \\ 29908 &:= (1 + ((23 \times 4) + (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29909 &:= (-1 + 2) \times 3 \times (4 - 5!) + 6 \times 7! + 8 + 9 \\ 29910 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) - (4^5)) \times -(6 + (7 + (8 + 9))) \\ 29911 &:= (((-1 - 23) \times -4) - (-5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29912 &:= (-1 - ((2 \times ((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8))) - 9)) \\ 29913 &:= ((((-1 - 2) - ((3^4) + 5)) \times -(6 \times (7 \times 8))) + 9) \\ 29914 &:= (-1 \times -((-2 \times (-34 - ((5^6) - (78 \times 9)))))) \\ 29915 &:= (-1 + ((2 + 34) \times ((56 \times (7 + 8)) - 9))) \\ 29916 &:= (-12 \times -(3 \times (((4 + (5 + 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 29917 &:= (((1 + 2) \times 34) - (-5 \times (67 \times 89))) \\ 29918 &:= ((-1 \times -2) + (3 \times (((4^5) + (6 + 78)) \times 9))) \\ 29919 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (34 \times (5 \times (6 - (7 - 89)))))) \\ 29920 &:= ((-1 + 23) \times -(4 \times (5 - ((6 \times (7 \times 8)) + 9)))) \\ 29921 &:= (1 - (-((2 \times 34) \times (5 \times (6 - (7 - 89)))))) \\ 29922 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (((3 - (45 \times 6)) \times (7 \times 8)) - 9))) \\ 29923 &:= (((1 + 2)^3) \times 4) + (5 \times (67 \times 89)) \\ 29924 &:= -1 + 2 - 3!!/4 - 5! + 6 \times 7! - 8 - 9 \\ 29925 &:= ((-1 + (2 + 34)) \times ((5 + (6 \times (7 + 8))) \times 9)) \\ 29926 &:= (-1 - 2 + 3456) \times 78/9 \\ 29927 &:= (-1 - ((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29928 &:= (-12 \times (-34 - (5 \times -((6 \times (7 - 89)))))) \\ 29929 &:= (1 - ((23 + (4 \times 5)) \times (6 - (78 \times 9)))) \\ 29930 &:= (((-1 + 2) + (3^4)) \times -(5 \times ((6 - 7) - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29931 &:= (((-1 \times (2 + 3)) \times -((4^5) \times 6)) - 789) \\ 29932 &:= ((1 + ((2 + 3) \times ((4^5) \times 6))) - 789) \\ 29933 &:= (-1 - ((2 - (((3^4) + (5 \times 67)) \times 8)) \times 9)) \\ 29934 &:= -(((123 + 4) + (5 \times -((67 \times 89)))))) \\ 29935 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (34 - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))))) \\ 29936 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (34 - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 29937 &:= (((-1 - 2) - ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29938 &:= (-1 \times (2 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 + (6 \times (7 \times 89))))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29900 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - 3)))))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29901 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - 3)))))) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 29902 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - 3)))))) - (2 - 1)) \\ 29903 &:= ((-(-9) + 8) \times (((7 - 6) + (54)) \times 32) - 1)) \\ 29904 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -((5^4) - (3 - (2 - 1)))))) \\ 29905 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times ((7 + 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 \times 2)))))) \times -1) \\ 29906 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - 3)))))) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29907 &:= ((-9 \times 87) + ((6 \times 5) \times ((4^{3+2}) - 1))) \\ 29908 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) + (3^{2+1})) \\ 29909 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)))) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29910 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -7) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 29911 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 \times (2 - 1)))))) \\ 29912 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times (((6 - ((5^4) \times 3)) \times 2) - 1)) \\ 29913 &:= ((-9 - 8) + (((7 + ((6 + 54) \times -3))^2) - (-1))) \\ 29914 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)))) - (2 + 1)) \\ 29915 &:= ((-9 \times -((8 \times 76) - 54) \times (3 \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29916 &:= (((((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times 6) - 5) \times 4) \times (3^{2+1})) \\ 29917 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) - (3 - 21)) \\ 29918 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 + ((6 \times (5^4) - 3)) + 2)))) - 1) \\ 29919 &:= ((-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))) - 3)^2)) - 1) \\ 29920 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))) - 3)^2 \times 1)) \\ 29921 &:= (-9 + (((8 \times (7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))) - 3)^2 + 1)) \\ 29922 &:= ((-9 - 8) + ((7 + 6) \times (((5 + 43)^2) - 1))) \\ 29923 &:= ((-9 - ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - 3)))))) + 2) \times -1) \\ 29924 &:= (-9 + ((8 \times (7 + (6 \times ((5^4) - 3)))) + 21)) \\ 29925 &:= (((9 + 8) + (7 \times -6)) \times (-((54 + 3)) \times (21))) \\ 29926 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 + 7)) + (((6 \times 5) + (4 - 3))^{2+1})) \\ 29927 &:= (((987 \times -6) \times -5) - 4) + (321)) \\ 29928 &:= (((9 + (87 + (65 + (4 \times 3))))^2) - 1)) \\ 29929 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) + (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29930 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) + ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 29931 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) + ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 29932 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) + (3 \times (2 - 1))) \\ 29933 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) + (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29934 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) + (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 29935 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^{4+3-2-1})))))) \\ 29936 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) - (3/(2 + 1))) \\ 29937 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))))) - (3 - (2 - 1))) \\ 29938 &:= ((-9 - (((8 \times (7 + (6 + (5 + 4)))) - 3)^2)) \times -1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29939 &:= ((-1 - ((2+3)^4) + (5+6)) \times -(7 \times 8) - 9) \\ 29940 &:= (-12 \times -(((3^4) \times (5 \times 6)) - (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29941 &:= ((-1 - ((2 \times 34) - 5) \times 6) \times -(7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 29942 &:= -((-123 - (4 - (5 \times -((67 \times 89)))))) \\ 29943 &:= ((-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times (5 + (6 + (7 + 8)))))) \times 9 \\ 29944 &:= ((-1 - ((2 - (3^4)) \times 5)) \times -((6 + 7) - 89)) \\ 29945 &:= (-1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8) \times 9))) \\ 29946 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8) \times 9))) \\ 29947 &:= (1 - (2 \times (3 - (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8) \times 9))) \\ 29948 &:= ((12^3) - (4 - (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29949 &:= (-((-12 \times (3^4))) \times (5 \times 6)) + 789 \\ 29950 &:= ((-1 \times 2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 29951 &:= (-1 + ((2^{3+4}) \times ((5 + (6 + (7 + 8))) \times 9))) \\ 29952 &:= (-((1 + 2) - 3) \times ((4 - 56) \times (7 + 89))) \\ 29953 &:= (-1 - ((2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 29954 &:= (-1 \times ((2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7))) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 29955 &:= ((1 + 2) + (((3^4) + (5 \times 67)) \times (8 \times 9))) \\ 29956 &:= ((12^3) + (4 + (56 \times (7 \times (8 \times 9)))))) \\ 29957 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (3 + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8) \times 9))) \\ 29958 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times - (3 + (((4^5) \times (6 + 7))/8) \times 9)) \\ 29959 &:= -(((12 \times (3 \times 4)) - ((5 \times 67) \times 89))) \\ 29960 &:= -1 + 2^{-3+4+5} \times 6 \times 78 + 9 \\ 29961 &:= -((((12 - 345) \times 6) \times (7 + 8)) + 9) \\ 29962 &:= 1 + 2^{-3+4+5} \times 6 \times 78 + 9 \\ 29963 &:= -1 + 2 \times (3! + 4! \times (-5! + 6! + 7 + 8 + 9)) \\ 29964 &:= (-12 \times (3 - (4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times (8 + 9))))))) \\ 29965 &:= (((1 \times 2) + ((3 + 456))) \times (-7 + (-8 \times -9))) \\ 29966 &:= (1 - ((2 + (3 + 456)) \times (7 - (8 \times 9)))) \\ 29967 &:= (1 + 2) \times 3 \times (-4! + 5) + 6 \times (7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29968 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 + 5!) + (6 \times 7! - 8 - 9) \\ 29969 &:= (-1 + ((2 + ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 29970 &:= (-1 \times -((2 + ((3 + 4) \times 5)) \times (6 \times ((7 + 8) \times 9)))) \\ 29971 &:= (1 - ((-2 + (34 + 5)) \times ((6 \times (-7 - 8)) \times 9))) \\ 29972 &:= -(1 \times 2 + 3 \times 4!) \times 5 + 6 \times (7! + 8 + 9) \\ 29973 &:= -1 - 2 \times (3 + 4 - (5! + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29974 &:= 1 \times 2 \times (-3 - 4 + (5! + 6) \times 7 \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29975 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3 \times (4 + 5)))) \times -((67 \times 8) + 9)) \\ 29976 &:= ((-1 - 23) \times -((4 \times (5 \times (6 + (7 \times 8)))) + 9)) \\ 29977 &:= (((-1 \times 2) \times - (3^4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 89))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29939 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29940 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 29941 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) - (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 29942 &:= ((-9 \times (8 - (((7 \times 6) + (5^4)) \times (3 + 2)))) - 1) \\ 29943 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (((7 - 6) - (5^4)) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29944 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))) \\ 29945 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 - 2)))))) \times -1 \\ 29946 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5^4))) \times (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29947 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5^4))) \times (3 \times 2)) + 1) \\ 29948 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) + (3 + 2))) \times -1) \\ 29949 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times 76)) \times (5 \times (4 + (3 \times 2)))) - 1) \\ 29950 &:= ((-9 + ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) + 3)) \times -(2 - 1)) \\ 29951 &:= (((-9 \times (8 + (7 + (6 + 5)))) \times -((4^3) \times 2)) - 1) \\ 29952 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times (6 - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29953 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) \times - (3 / (2 + 1))) \\ 29954 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) - (3 - 2)) \times -1) \\ 29955 &:= ((-9 - ((87 + 6) \times ((5 \times (4^3)) + 2))) \times -1) \\ 29956 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3))) + (2 + 1))) \\ 29957 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3))) + (2 \times 1))) \\ 29958 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) - (3 + 2)) \times -1) \\ 29959 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 + 2))) - 1) \\ 29960 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1))) \\ 29961 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 + 2))) + 1) \\ 29962 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - (6 \times (5^4)))) - (3^{2+1}))) \\ 29963 &:= ((-98 \times -7) + (((((6 + 5)^4) - 3) \times 2) + 1)) \\ 29964 &:= (((-9 + (((8 + (7 \times 6))/5^4)) - 3) \times (2 + 1)) \\ 29965 &:= (((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times 2) - 1) \\ 29966 &:= ((-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - ((5^4) \times 3)))) \times (2 \times 1)) \\ 29967 &:= (-9 - (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) + ((3 + 2) - 1)))))) \\ 29968 &:= (((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1))) \\ 29969 &:= ((-(-9) + ((8 \times 7) \times ((-6 + 543) - (2 \times 1)))))) \\ 29970 &:= ((-9 \times (8 + 7)) \times -(6 + (((5 + 4) - 3)^{2+1}))) \\ 29971 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -(((7 \times -(6 - (5 + (4 + 3))))^2) - 1)) \\ 29972 &:= ((((-9 + 8) + (7 \times 6)) \times (((5 + 4)^3) + 2)) + 1) \\ 29973 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times - (5^4)) - (3^{2+1})) \\ 29974 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 + 2)))) + 1)) \\ 29975 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 + (6 \times (5^4))) - (3 \times (2 + 1)))))) \\ 29976 &:= ((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -(((6 \times (5^4)) - 3) / (2 + 1))) \\ 29977 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29978 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3^4)) + (5 \times (67 \times 89)))) \\ 29979 &:= (-(((12 - 345) \times 6) \times (7 + 8))) + 9 \\ 29980 &:= ((-1 \times 2) \times ((3 \times 4) - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 29981 &:= (-1 - (((2 \times 3) - (4 \times (5 + 6))) \times 789)) \\ 29982 &:= (-123 + (45 \times (678 - 9))) \\ 29983 &:= (((-1 + (((2 + 3)^4) \times (5 - (6 - 7)))) \times 8) - 9) \\ 29984 &:= 12 \times (3^{4+5} - 6) / 7 \times 8 / 9 \\ 29985 &:= ((-1 - 2) - ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\ 29986 &:= (-1 \times (2 + ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\ 29987 &:= (-1 + (2 \times (34 \times ((5 \times (6 \times (7 + 8))) - 9)))) \\ 29988 &:= ((((-1 + (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 + 6)) - 7) \times (8 + 9)) \\ 29989 &:= ((-1 + 2) - ((3 - 45) \times (6 \times (7 \times (8 + 9))))) \\ 29990 &:= ((1 \times 2) - (((3 - 45) \times (6 \times 7)) \times (8 + 9))) \\ 29991 &:= ((((-1 \times -(2 + 3))^4) \times ((5 - (6 - 7)) \times 8)) - 9) \\ 29992 &:= ((-1 - (2 \times (3^4))) \times (5 - ((6 + (7 + 8)) \times 9))) \\ 29993 &:= (((12 \times -3) \times (4 + 5)) - (6 + 7)) \times -89 \\ 29994 &:= (1 + (((2 \times (3 \times 45)) + 67) \times 89)) \\ 29995 &:= 1 \times 2 - 3! \times (4 \times (5 + 6) - 7!) + 8 + 9 \\ 29996 &:= (((-1 + 2) - 3) \times (4 - ((5^6) - (7 \times 89)))) \\ 29997 &:= (((-12 - 345) \times -((6 + 78))) + 9) \\ 29998 &:= (-1 + ((234 - 5) \times ((6 \times 7) + 89))) \\ 29999 &:= -(((1 \times (-234 - (-5))) \times -(((6 \times 7) + 89)))) \\ 30000 &:= (-(-12) - ((-3 + 45) \times -(((6 \times 7) \times (8 + 9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29978 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 \times 1)) \\ 29979 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - 3)) + (2 + 1)) \\ 29980 &:= (-9 - ((8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) + 3))) - 21)) \\ 29981 &:= (((-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4) \times 3))) \times 2) - 1 \\ 29982 &:= ((-9 \times -(8 \times 7)) + (6 \times ((5 + (4 \times 3))^{2+1}))) \\ 29983 &:= (-9 - (8 \times ((7 - 6) - ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\ 29984 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 - (2 - 1)))) \\ 29985 &:= ((((-9 \times (8 \times (7 + 6))) - (5 - 4)) \times -32) + 1) \\ 29986 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times 7)) \times (6 + ((5^4) + ((3 \times 2) + 1)))) \\ 29987 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 - (5 + (4 + 3))))^2)) - 1) \\ 29988 &:= ((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times 6)^{(5+4-3)/(2+1)})) \\ 29989 &:= (((-9 - 8) \times -((7 \times -(6 - (5 + (4 + 3))))^2)) + 1) \\ 29990 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -(5^4)) - ((3^2) + 1)) \\ 29991 &:= (-9 + (8 \times (((7 - 6) \times 5)^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \\ 29992 &:= ((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) - (3 / (2 + 1)))) \\ 29993 &:= ((-9 + (8 \times (7 - ((6 \times (5^4)) + (3 + 2)))) \times -1) \\ 29994 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -(5^4)) - (3 + (2 + 1))) \\ 29995 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -(5^4)) - ((3 + 2) \times 1)) \\ 29996 &:= (((((-9 + 8) - 7) \times 6) \times -(5^4)) - ((3 + 2) - 1)) \\ 29997 &:= (9 - (((-8 - 76) \times ((5 + (4 \times 3)) \times 21)))) \\ 29998 &:= (((-9 - (8 + 7)) \times -((6 \times (5^4)) / 3)) - (2 \times 1)) \\ 29999 &:= (-9 + (8 \times ((7 - 6) + ((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1))))) \\ 30000 &:= ((-9 + ((8 - 7)^6)) \times -((5^4) \times (3 + (2 + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

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